

**Conference of Academies for Applied Studies in Serbia
(CAASS)**

**University Business Academy in Novi Sad, Faculty of
Contemporary Arts, Belgrade**

BOOK OF PROCEEDINGS

Editor: Dr Branko Savić, professor

International Multidisciplinary Conference

"Challenges of Contemporary Higher Education" - CCHE 2024

Kopaonik January 29th - February 3rd 2024

Vol_3

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**Challenges of
Contemporary
Higher Education**

Belgrade, 2024

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PREFACE

To the esteemed global academic community,

It is with immense pride and anticipation that I present to you the Book of Proceedings for the International Multidisciplinary Conference "Challenges of Contemporary Higher Education" (CCHE) 2024. As the President of the Organizing Committee, I have had the privilege of witnessing the dedication, passion, and collaborative spirit of countless individuals who have come together to make this conference a reality.

Higher education, as we know, is a dynamic and ever-evolving field. The challenges it faces are multifaceted, ranging from technological advancements and pedagogical shifts to socio-political changes and global crises. It is imperative, now more than ever, for scholars, researchers, and educators from diverse disciplines to come together, share insights, and collaboratively chart a path forward. This conference, held in the picturesque setting of Kopaonik, Serbia, serves as a beacon for such collaborative endeavors.

The proceedings contained within these pages are a testament to the depth and breadth of research currently being undertaken in higher education across various disciplines. From Medical Sciences to Arts, from Biotechnology to Language for Specific Purpose, the range of topics covered is both vast and pertinent. Each paper not only addresses the challenges of contemporary higher education but also offers innovative solutions, fresh perspectives, and a vision for the future.

I would like to extend my heartfelt gratitude to the numerous higher educational institutions from Serbia, members of the Conference of Academies for Applied Studies in Serbia (CAASS), and our invited institutions. Their unwavering support and commitment have been instrumental in bringing this conference to fruition. Additionally, the Scientific Committee, comprising esteemed researchers and professors from around the world, has played a pivotal role in ensuring the quality and relevance of the research presented.

To all the contributors, participants, and attendees, I thank you for your invaluable contributions and for being a part of this monumental endeavor. Your dedication to the advancement of higher education is truly commendable.

As you delve into these proceedings, I hope you find inspiration, knowledge, and a renewed sense of purpose. May the discussions, insights, and collaborations sparked by this conference continue to drive the evolution of higher education for years to come.

Warm regards,

Dr Branko Savić, professor

Бранко Савић

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SECTION 1: MECHANICAL ENGINEERING AND INDUSTRIAL SOFTWARE

SIGNIFICANCE OF SCHEDULE QUALITY IN PRODUCTION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the emerging significance of measuring schedule quality and conformance to 'good practice' and the automated tools that are now available to assist in this process. There is a strong correlation between a well-constructed schedule and a desirable production outcome, applying these concepts will enhance the probability of on time completion. The purpose of this paper is to introduce the Quality Scheduling Index, which can assist in producing and delivering goods to clients in accordance with their specifications for quality and delivery time. The index takes into account both the minimum standard of product quality and the "Just-In-Time" production schedule that the business must adhere to in order to supply the market with the necessary products, taking into account customers and their degree of satisfaction at the beginning of the production process.

Key words: quality schedule, production, production management, quality control, just-in-time, zero defect

1. INTRODUCTION

During these challenging economic times, when the global community is still dealing with the fallout from the recent financial crisis, producers ought to boost sales and brand recognition by refining and modernising their business strategies. Due to the fact that their needs are changing more quickly than they were before the crisis, it is harder to draw in and keep customers. Additionally, the pricing and quality level of the things that are purchased are receiving more attention.

As a result, businesses should look for innovative and more efficient ways to raise employee quality, shorten production times so that goods are delivered to clients in line with the "Just-In-Time" concept, and, lastly, cut associated production costs. Also, as a result of e-commerce and the increase in the use of the Internet by potential customers, products should be at the qualitative level imposed by the market in order to satisfy its demands.

One of the foundations for successful project management is to start with the right schedule. For many years scheduling was seen as a 'black art' with only subjective opinions as to what constituted a 'good schedule', any debate over schedule quality tended to be confused with arguments over personal preferences in tools and/or networking techniques. Unfortunately despite options to standardize scheduling practice evolving since the turn of the 21st century, these attitudes are still far too common [1].

In other words, producers ought to follow the PULL market concept rather than the PUSH principle, which calls for forcing goods onto the market, and they ought to fulfil client demands prior to the completed product leaving the manufacturing facility. And queries such as: How high of a quality should our products be produced? and When should goods be shipped to clients and production be finished? are, in our opinion, vital and essential to any company's success.

We think that the management of the company should be the ones to address these problems by actively participating in the production process, that is, by consistently enhancing the calibre of their output and the productivity of their operations. By meeting client criteria for quality and delivery time, managers are able to maintain and grow customer satisfaction, while also increasing work productivity [2].

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2. SCHEDULE QUALITY

2.1. Literature overview

Various approaches to enhancing product quality, such as Total Quality Management, Lean Management, Six Sigma, and task scheduling on various production lines and/or work tables, are documented in scientific literature. Nevertheless, managers are unable to use a single tool to link these two issues and regulate or enhance the manufacturing process.

According to Feibenbaum (1951), quality control is a component of every stage of manufacturing, starting with sales and client specifications and continuing through engineering, installation, and transportation [3]. Also Teruo Mori (2012) focuses on statistical methods that were developed by Taguchi, the so called Quality Engineering and the mapping of quality from the customer's perspective and designed quality (engineered quality) that minimizes the cost and is designed into the product to improve product performance efficiency [4].

Rebai (2012) presented a function for overall costs; however, the work quality is not addressed [5]. We will further examine the assumption made by Swink (2006) and other authors that the time-cost trade-offs for project activities are linear [2]. A comparison is drawn between parallel machine scheduling and the working bees of a hive, who must leave the colony to look for fresh blooms.

2.2. Quality Scheduling Index - QSI

Gruia (2013) developed the QSI in response to market need for a solution that might manage a company's time consumption as well as quality [7]. The study began with an online survey that was distributed to manufacturing companies across Europe. Based on the responses, managers from a selection of the companies were scheduled for structured interviews in order to obtain more precise data and increase the questionnaire's return rate. The index was then partially implemented in different small and middle size manufacturing companies.

Applications of QSI is viable for both single- and multi-operation jobs. We are going to focus on the issue of scheduling a series of jobs with multiple operations per job. This can be conceptualised as a sequence of operations that are added to the subsequent job upon completion, and so on, until all jobs from the first to the last line of the parallel machine arrangement are completed and subsequently assembled to form the final product.

When these steps are finished, the manufacturing task should meet all of its deadline, quality, and cost requirements. Costs and a required degree of quality are directly correlated, while quality and time are indirectly correlated.

If we consider that there is a relationship of interdependency between the operations of one task, as established by Gruia and Kavan (2013) [6], we will further consider the quality as our major function which has to be optimised. Gruia (2013) described the concept as a set of equations where we should minimise a ratio's minimising criteria while also increasing work quality, cutting costs, and shortening the colony's overall makespan. It's been denoted as Quality Scheduling Index – QSI [7]:

$$QSI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^h \sum_{k=1}^f ew_{ki}E_{ki}y_{ki} + tw_{ki}T_{ki}z_{ki} + w_{ki}C_i}{\sum_{i=1}^h \sum_{k=1}^f \frac{q_i}{tc_i * (E_{ki} + T_{ki} + C_i)}} = min$$

Where symbols are as follows:

- tc_i – total costs
- C_i – completion time
- ew_{ki} – early weight
- tw_{ki} – tardy weight

w_{ki} – weight within optimistic and pessimistic due date

E_{ki} – earliness of the job

T_{ki} – tardiness of the job

t_p – prepare time for new job

f_i – flying time

q_i – quality of the work of the worker

And two binary variables y_i and z_i

$$y_{ik} = \{1, \text{for } E_k > 0, \text{ otherwise}\}$$

$$z_{ik} = \{1, T_k > 0, \text{ otherwise}\}$$

The approach for implementing the QSI consists of three primary components, and it may be used to both single- and multi-operation jobs:

- Dividing the workload among the organisation based on a greedy perspective;
- Increasing the capacity of resource utilisation; and
- Using the QSI to determine the best values and enhance the process.

We will continue considering of the methodology's first step and use it for tasks requiring several operations. We should first divide the jobs with one operation from the jobs with more operations on the current parallel manufacturing lines and develop a methodology for solving these two cases in order to be able to schedule multiple operations within a complex job from the perspectives of quality, time, and costs.

A few examples of sequencing rules are as follows: a) Shortest Processing Time: work is scheduled based on the product's shortest processing time, which is the first operation; b) Due Date: work with the shortest due date should be completed first; c) First Come, First Served: work is completed in the order in which it arrives at the working area; d) Critical Ratio: work is scheduled based on the increasing ratio between the Due Date and Shortest Processing Time; e) Johnson's rule: it reduces the amount of time needed to complete various operations on two working areas[7].

However, from a greedy standpoint, we are equally interested in minimising time while retaining the required quality level. Thus, using the above logic, the rule MaxQminT has been created, which is applicable for operations that call for different tools or settings after each prior operation is finished [6]:

1. Assemble workers into two teams of two qualified members, assigning each team two consecutive activities, with one worker handling the first and the other handling the second.
2. Prepare all tools and equipment required for the operations that must be completed in order to finish the project. When one of them works, the other employee will be in charge of his colleague's work quality. (In this way, the likelihood of producing a product with defects is significantly decreased and the quality assurance process is effectively integrated into every manufacturing step).
3. Next, assign the team that is to perform the longest and shortest operation. The manufacturing process's second operation should be the one that takes the longest. The first team should always be assigned the input operation, which is in charge of gathering the materials, tools, and other resources needed for the entire project, as one of the two operations. The last team should always be assigned, as part of the two operations, the output operation, which comes from the production line for even-numbered operations and to the first team for odd-numbered operations.
4. Assign the second and third longest operations to the next team.
5. Repeat step 4 until only two operations remain and assign them to the last team. If only one operation remains at the end, assign it to the first team.
6. Assign the second-longest operation to the team that is waiting if the required working space is not available. Then, repeat steps 3 through 5 until all operations are completed.

Prior to putting this rule into practise, we should be aware of the following:

- All processing times for all operations (including material input and finished product output from the production line);
- All required tools and equipment;
- Job sequence can, but should not, be a determining factor in the application of this rule.

In conjunction with the MaxQminT, the NoBtl rule should be applied in order to address one of the other issues that businesses encounter with their operations [6]. We should be aware of the timing and resource availability for the input and output processes before implementing this rule.

The guideline instructs to organise and order the parallel lines' processes in the following manner, taking into account the input/output constraints:

- a) The operations will be scheduled in a sequential fashion, with the output operation being scheduled first and the shortest available operation scheduled second, starting with the output operations and their assembly/shipment constraints from each of the parallel lines;
- b) Keep sequencing the operations until the last one is the input operation. Schedule the longest operation ahead of the input operation if the input operation isn't the longest;
- c) Check and correlate the schedule with MaxQminT rule;
- d) Repeat the first three steps until only one schedule remains which satisfy NoBtl and MaxQminT rules together.

Above mentioned rule has been implemented into a middle size manufacturing company. The product that company produces, required three separate parallel machines to be operated on. In order to complete the manufacturing operations, the workers had the chance to move along the production lines and switch between parallel production lines.

Following implementation methodology of the first step of QSI has been developed:

1. Divide the jobs in two categories to be scheduled on the available parallel machines:
 - a) Jobs with one operation;
 - b) Complex jobs with more than one operation, where each operation can be considered as a separate job on different machine from the production lines;
2. Schedule the manufacturing operations according to the rule MaxQminT, which is valid for arranging the jobs in a greedy manner so that the first operation to be responsible with the most amount of work, with the requested quality level in the shortest processing time;
3. Sequence the final operations of each job from the parallel manufacturing line according to rule NoBtl so that the assemble process to proceed in a smooth and lean manner without the formation of bottlenecks.

Due to technological limitations, the parts from the first and second lines should be completed simultaneously, but the third line's portion should be completed first because it needs to be further prepared to be incorporated into the finished product. The business is open for business eight hours a day. The machine setup and manipulation times are included in the processing times (working area).

After applying the MaxQminT and NoBtl sequencing rules, following results has been obtained:

Table 1 – Computed coefficients on the available lines before and after implementing the new rules

Line	Before	After
Line 1		
Average working time	11,75	16,125
Average number of working minutes	3,9	5,4
Line 2		
Average working time	9,75	14
Average number of working minutes	3,5	5,1
Line 3		
Average working time	11	14,375
Average number of working minutes	4,2	5,5

When analyzing the two considered coefficients we see an increase in the time spent with each product of about 27 % in average. However the total processing time on each line was not increased! For instance the amount of products produced by the three lines together during a working day of 8 hours, decreases from 55 (from which 4 are defective) to a number of 54 (from which none is defective). After the implementation of the rule, the company registers an increase in the time consumption from a total average of 10,83 minutes worked per operation to an average of 14,83 minutes worked per operation (however, without the increase of the total available time on each line), i.e. an increase in average of 27% in time consumption of the available time, and an increase in the production of qualitative products too, from 51 to 54, i.e. approximate 6% increase in the quality of the products with zero defects. In the same manner the costs of quality were considerably diminished, with up to 17%.

3. CONCLUSION

The future of production management is predicted to be one that focuses on ‘soft skills’ including; communications, motivation and leadership. Uncertainty will be recognized as normal and skills for managing uncertainty will become essential for successful production managers. In this scenario, scheduling should be seen as a modelling process that helps communicate and coordinate ideas about what might happen in the future. This is achieved by providing timely and useful information, not masses of irrelevant data. This is the essence of effective time management and the basis for building project success, which in turn provides the framework for defining a quality scheduling, that is fit-for-purpose.

The Quality Scheduling Index's partial implementation and the outcomes of its initial phase—the task distribution from a greedy standpoint—are discussed in this paper. We believe that this index can address the real issues managers are having with time management and quality control, protecting consumers from the entry of subpar goods into the market.

The procedure is enhanced with the goal of raising quality and lowering production costs in the future (through rework, upkeep, and a marketing campaign to restore the company's damaged reputation as a result of defects that would have arisen had the rule not been followed, etc.).

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EXPERIMENTAL TESTING OF THE ROUGHNESS OF PARTS OBTAINED BY SLA 3D PRINTING TECHNOLOGY

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Summary: SLA technology of 3D printing enables the part production with quite high surface quality, i.e. low surface roughness. This characteristic of SLA printing provides it a wide range of application in the production of functionally applicable parts along with parts for visualization. This paper deals with the roughness of the outer horizontal surface experimentally examined by using the "MarSurf PS1" roughness measuring device. In order to obtain the most realistic values of roughness parameters, experimental tests were carried out in three directions.

Key words: 3D printing, SLA, surface roughness

1. INTRODUCTION

3D printing is a new technology that has the potential to change the environment in which we live. The technology itself is within reach today, and in a few years it has gone from being experimental stage to a technology that is now indispensable in industry and production. With the constant development and improvement of technology, it can be applied in various branches of industry, medicine, art, and the like. It is used for printing metal, ceramic, polymer, etc. parts [1]. Depending on the work procedure and the application itself, the types of work materials as well as the quality of the obtained surface, the price of the device can vary from several hundred euros to several million euros. What is absolutely certain is that printers that form a 3D model by fused filament deposition (FDM) have the greatest application. This type of printer has certainly the largest commercial and industrial application solely due to the low price of the printer and consumables (various types of polymers; PLA, ABS, TPU, PETG...). The downside of this technology is a lower quality of the surface of the manufactured parts. Management of technological parameters in the process of preparing models for printing is done with the help of specialized software packages, within which technological parameters such as layer thickness, printing strategy, printing density, temperature of the extruder head, type of printing material, etc. are adapted [2]. In addition to the aforementioned printing technology, the SLA (stereolithography) printing technology, which is based on the hardening of liquid photopolymer under the influence of UV light, is extremely widely applied in the industry. This printing technology offers the highest precision and the best surface quality of parts obtained by 3D printing. What is characteristic of these types of printers is that certain models can have micron roughness and accuracy, which enables them to be widely used.

2. STEREO LITHOGRAPHY-SLA

All procedures for hardening liquid materials are based on the principle of photopolymerisation. If such liquids are illuminated with an ultraviolet lamp or laser light, their hardening occurs. The laser beam is directed at the polymer, and the path of the beam is controlled by a computer in accordance with the created geometric data for each layer individually. Sole hardening of the polymer in depth under the influence of the laser beam is realized in the form of a half-cylinder (so-called voxel). The solidification of the working fluid (liquid polymer) is the basis on which this printing technology is based, and the procedure takes place as follows: when the fluid is exposed to UV light or laser light, it immediately hardens due to low absorption energy. Hardening is done in the form of a voxel (a small

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volume of hardened fluid in the form of a semi-cylinder). The voxel size depends on diameter of the laser beam. To create a 3D model, it is necessary to ensure the overlap of voxels in the horizontal plane as well as the overlap in the direction of the vertical axis [3]. In stereolithography, models are produced through passing a beam of UV (ultra violet) light over a pool of photosensitive liquid. In the course of production, the model is put down into the tub layer by layer, until the final product is obtained. Another advantage of this type of 3D printing technology is the high level of detail and surface finish. One of the main advantages of this printing method is its speed. In this technology, the same models are produced up to 5 times faster than in all other techniques. Seeing the final product is very interesting. After the printing of the part is finished, it is gently lifted from the tub with the photopolymer solution from which it was made. This is much simpler than breaking the remains of constructive elements, which is indispensable in other types of printing.

3. HALOT-SKY 3D PRINTER

Creality has developed an innovative SLA printer "HALOT-SKY" by using monochrome LCD technology, which is equipped with numerous features such as useful Wi-Fi connection, 5-inch screen and ARM Cortex A53 CPU. On the working surface of 192x120x200 mm, objects such as jewelry, decorative objects, models from architecture, medicine or education, dentistry and other fields can be produced. The layout of the 3D printer "HALOT-SKY" is shown in Figure 1 [3].

Figure 1 Layout of the 3D printer "HALOT-SKY"

Basic features of the printer:

- Manufacturer: Creality,
- 3D printing technology: mSLA (UV LCD),
- Working surface: 192x120x200 mm,
- Print speed: 1-4 s/layer,
- LCD resolution : 3840*2400 (4k),
- Closed chamber: YES,
- Resolution (layer):0.01 - 0.05 mm
- Thickness (layer):0.01 - 0.2 mm

Printing preparation is done with the help of the specialized program package "Halot box". The software package has the ability to read files, previously created and saved in one of the software systems for 3D modeling (for example, Autodesk Inventor, SolidWORKS, AutoCad, etc.), with the "stl" extension. After loading the model into the program, its scale is adjusted and the model is positioned in the printer's workspace.

Defining the position of the object depends a lot on the geometry and dimensions of the model. The layout of the 3D model in the Halot Box software package is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Layout of the graphical environment in the program package "Halot Box"

4. EXPERIMENTAL TEST RESULTS

The layout of the 3D model on which the roughness was experimentally measured is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Layout of the 3D model on which the roughness was experimentally measured

Measurements of the quality of the machined surface at the microgeometric level (roughness) was performed by using the MarSurf PS1 device manufactured by Mahr GmbH, Göttingen. The results of roughness on the surface of the tested 3D model are shown in Figure 4. Experimental tests were conducted in several directions, but the results are presented in the paper only in three directions. The model is printed with liquid photopolymer made of ABS material. Out of the technological parameters, the thickness of the print layer has the greatest influence on the size of roughness, and with its reduction, less roughness is obtained (model printed with a thickness of the print layer of 50 μm). Specifically, for the 3D model shown above, roughness is defined by three parameters: the highest height of bumps R_{max} , the mean arithmetic deviation R_a and the mean height of bumps R_z .

50 μm layer

	R_{max}	R_a	R_z
Roughness value	3,87 μm	0,211 μm	1,87 μm

THE FIRST DIRECTION

	R_{max}	R_a	R_z
Roughness value	1,70 μm	0,200 μm	1,45 μm

THE SECOND DIRECTION

	R_{max}	R_a	R_z
Roughness value	2,61 μm	0,201 μm	2,00 μm

THE THIRD DIRECTION

Figure 4 Roughness diagram of the SLA printing method

6. CONCLUSION

The results of the roughness of the parts printed in three directions showed that the SLA printing technology, where the model is obtained by solidifying the liquid photo polymer under the influence of laser or UV light, gives a very low roughness. Based on some previous research, it is known that the parts obtained by this method can be used for visualization as well as engineering applications. The observation that the parts are made with a very low roughness gives an even greater possibility for the engineering application of these parts, as well as for the visualization itself.

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RESIDUAL FATIGUE LIFE ESTIMATION OF CRACKED STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS USING LOW CYCLIC FATIGUE PROPERTIES

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Abstract: The attention in the work is focused on the establishment and selection of rational and precise numerical methods/procedures for calculating the lifetime of structural elements that are exposed to cyclic loads of constant amplitude and spectrum during exploitation. This primarily refers to aircraft structures where reliability and service life are of primary importance. For this purpose, when designing the aircraft structure, regulations are used that assume initial damage in the form of splinters of various shapes, all in accordance with MIL norms. The Finite Element Method (FEM) was used in the paper to analyze stress states and stress intensity factors (SIF) on the one hand and strain energy density (SED) method to estimate the residual fatigue life on the other. The main advantage of this approach is that the SED method uses the low-cycle characteristics of materials, i.e. the same ones that are used in the estimation of the life until the appearance of initial damage. The validation of this approach is illustrated on numerical examples of representative structural elements.

Key words: Fatigue, residual fatigue life, cracked structural elements, low-cycle fatigue properties, FEM

1. INTRODUCTION

When designing aircraft as well as other structural systems that are under the influence of cyclic loads during exploitation, it is necessary to ensure a long exploitation life [1]-[3]. For this purpose, it is important to use efficient and reliable calculation methods for estimating the life of structural elements. This primarily refers to the assessment of the life in the presence of initial damage. It is well known that structural elements with assumed initial damage should provide a certain remaining service life in the exploitation itself before effective breakage. This basically means designing the aircraft structure in the presence of initial damage and in accordance with appropriate recommendations such as MIL norms. Fatigue analysis of mechanical structural elements, in many cases, leads to underestimated lives and thus greater costs, so a different philosophy was developed, Damage Tolerance Design [4]-[9]. Using this theory, the designer no longer assumes a perfect component but rather the existence of an initial damage that is allowed to propagate. However, that damage is detected and repaired within the safety limits placed.

Primary attention in this research has been to develop an efficient and reliable computational method for residual fatigue life estimation of damaged structural components under cyclic loading. To determine residual fatigue life of damaged structural components two crack growth methods are used: conventional Forman's crack growth method and crack growth model based on the strain energy density method (SED).

By combining the SED method and FEM for precise analysis of stress states, especially in critical zones, an efficient and reliable computation method is obtained for estimating the remaining life and certainly the total life.

2. INITIAL FATIGUE LIFE ESTIMATION OF STRUCTURAL ELEMENTS

For the sake of systematicity, the basic relations for estimating the life until the appearance of initial damage will be briefly stated here. For this purpose, the SWT relation is considered here. To estimate the age until the appearance of initial damage of structural elements subjected to

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cyclic loads and where material plasticization occurs in critical zones, it is necessary to use the material's cyclic behavior curves. For this purpose, the SWT relation was used. The Smith-Watson-Topper (SWT) relation [3] for describing the low-cycle fatigue curve has the form:

$$P_{SWT} = \sqrt{\sigma_{max} \frac{\Delta \varepsilon}{2} E} = \sqrt{(\sigma_f')^2 (N_f)^{2b} + E \sigma_f' \varepsilon_f' (N_f)^{b+c}} \quad (1)$$

where the influence of mean stresses is included via the dependence

$$\sigma_{max} = \sigma_m + \frac{\Delta \sigma}{2} \quad (2)$$

The notation P_{SWT} in Equations (1) refers to the Smith-Watson-Topper parameter. The relation SWT (1) defines that there is no fatigue damage in situations where the value of the maximum stress, σ_{max} , is zero or has a negative value, which is not entirely true.

3. RESIDUAL FATIGUE LIFE ESTIMATION BASED ON STRAIN ENERGY DENSITY METHOD

As mentioned above, the SED method [3],[4] uses low-cycle characteristics of the material, so this section will present this method. In this work fatigue crack growth method based on energy concept is considered and then it is necessary to determine the energy absorbed till failure. This energy can be calculated by using cyclic stress-strain curve. Function between stress and strain, as recommended by Ramberg-Osgood provides good description of elastic-plastic behavior of material, and may be expressed as:

$$\Delta \varepsilon = \frac{\Delta \sigma}{E} + 2 \left(\frac{\Delta \sigma}{2k'} \right)^{\frac{1}{n'}} \quad (3)$$

where E is the modulus of elasticity, $\Delta \varepsilon/2$ is strain amplitude and $\Delta \sigma/2$ is stress amplitude. Equation (3) enables the calculation of the stress-strain distribution by knowing low cyclic fatigue properties. As a result the energy absorbed till failure become:

$$W_c = \frac{4}{1+n'} \sigma_f' \varepsilon_f' \quad (4)$$

where σ_f' is cyclic yield strength and ε_f' - fatigue ductility coefficient. Given the fact that strain energy density method is considered, the energy absorbed till failure must be determined after the energy concept is based on the following fact: The energy absorbed per unit growth of crack is equal to the plastic energy dissipated within the process zone per cycle. This energy concept is expressed by:

$$W_c \delta a = \omega_p, \quad (5)$$

where W_c is energy absorbed till failure, ω_p - the plastic energy and a - the crack length. In Equation (5) it is necessary just to determine the plastic energy dissipated in the process zone ω_p . By integration of equation for the cyclic plastic strain energy density in the units of Joule per cycle per unit volume [6]-[8] from zero to the length of the process zone ahead of crack tip d^* it is possible to determine the plastic

energy dissipated in the process zone ω_p . After integration relation of the plastic energy dissipated in the process zone becomes:

$$\omega_p = \left(\frac{1-n'}{1+n'} \right) \frac{\Delta K_I^2 \psi}{E I_{n'}} \quad (6)$$

where ΔK_I is the range of stress intensity factor, ψ - constant depending on the strain hardening exponent n' , $I_{n'}$ - the non-dimensional parameter depending on n' .

Fatigue crack growth rate can be obtained by substituting Eq. (4) and Eq. (6) in Eq. (5):

$$\frac{da}{dN} = \frac{(1-n')\psi}{4E I_{n'} \sigma_f' \varepsilon_f'} (\Delta K_I - \Delta K_{th})^2 \quad (7)$$

where ΔK_{th} is the range of threshold stress intensity factor and is function of stress ratio i.e.

$$\Delta K_{th} = \Delta K_{th0}(1-R)^\gamma, \quad (8)$$

ΔK_{th0} is the range of threshold stress intensity factor for the stress ratio $R = 0$ and γ is coefficient (usually, $\gamma = 0.71$). Finally number of cycles till failure can be determined by integration of relation for fatigue crack growth rate:

$$N = B \int_{a_0}^{a_c} \frac{da}{(\Delta K_I - \Delta K_{th})^2} \quad (9)$$

$$B = \frac{4E I_{n'} \sigma_f' \varepsilon_f'}{(1-n')\psi} \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta K_I = YS\sqrt{\pi a} \quad (11)$$

Equations (9) and (10) enables us to determine crack growth life of different structural component. Very important fact is that equations (9) and (10) is easy for application since low cyclic material properties ($n', \sigma_f', \varepsilon_f'$) available in literature are used as parameters. The only important point is stress intensity factor which, depending on the geometry complexity and the type of loading, could be determined by using analytical and/or numerical approaches.

From fatigue crack growth relations (7) and (8) can be seen that they require only mechanical and low-cyclic fatigue properties $E, \sigma_f', \varepsilon_f'$ and n' , which presents great advantage by application of this method.

The main advantage of the SED method is that it uses the low-cycle fatigue characteristics of the material to estimate the residual fatigue life, exactly as they are used to estimate the life to initial damage.

This significantly reduces the very expensive experimental tests for determining the dynamic characteristics of the material.

4. NUMERICAL VALIDATION

The validity of the considered computation total fatigue life estimation method can only be assessed through a comparison with experimental data which is the focus of this section. In addition, stress intensity factors were obtained by using analytical and numerical approaches. In the case where numerical simulation was used for stress intensity factor for crack growth life estimation the evaluated polynomial expressions were used for corrective function which include geometry of structural element. The analysis of the stress state was performed using FEM [9].

4.1 Residual Fatigue Life Estimation of Cracked Lugs

Here are considered cracked aircraft attachment lugs, Figure 1. Once a finite element solution has been obtained, Figure 2, the values of the stress intensity factor can be extracted from it. To determine Stress Intensity Factors of cracked aircraft attachment lugs here method based on extrapolation of displacements around tip of crack is used.

Figure 1 Geometry of cracked lug

Figure 2 Finite Element Model of cracked lug with stress distribution

Subject of this analyses are cracked aircraft lugs under cyclic load of constant amplitude end spectra. For that purpose conventional Forman crack growth model and crack growth model based on strain energy density method are used. Material of lugs is Aluminum alloy 7075 T7351 with the next material properties: $\sigma_m=432 \text{ N/mm}^2$ $\Leftrightarrow$ Tensile strength of material, $\sigma_2=334 \text{ N/mm}^2$, $K_{IC}=2225 \text{ [N/mm}^{3/2}]$, Dynamic material properties (Forman's constants): $C=3E10^{-7}$, $n=2.39$, Cyclic material properties: $\sigma_f=613 \text{ MPa}$, $\sigma'_f=0.35$, $n'=0.121$. The stress intensity factors (SIF's) of cracked lugs are determined for nominal stress levels: $\sigma_g = \sigma_{max}=98.1 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and $\sigma_{min}=9.81 \text{ N/mm}^2$. These stresses are determined in net cross-section of lug. The corresponding forces of lugs are defined as, $F_{max} = \sigma_g (w-2R) t = 63716 \text{ N}$ and $F_{min} = 6371.16 \text{ N}$, that are loaded of lugs. For stress analyses contact pin/lug finite element model is used. For cracked lug Figure 1, with initial crack a_0 , SIF is determined using finite elements, Figure 2.

For cracked lug, Figure 1, with crack through the thickness the crack growth behavior under load spectra is considered. Crack growth numerical simulation of cracked lug carried out using SED method and conventional Forman's method, Figure 3.

Figure 3 Comparisons crack growth behavior using SED and Forman's methods

In Figure 3 are shown results of crack growth results for cracked lug using two methods: (1) conventional Forman's method [2] and (2) strain energy density method [3]-[5] (SED).

5. CONCLUSION

This paper deals with research in the domain of estimating the residual service life of aircraft structural elements under the influence of cyclic loads and spectra. The goal is certainly to provide an efficient computation method. This investigation is focused on developing efficient and reliable computation methods for residual fatigue life estimation of damaged structural components. A special attention has been focused on determination of fracture mechanics parameters of structural components such as stress intensity factors of aircraft cracked lugs. Predictions and experimental investigations for fatigue life estimation of an attachment lug and skin under load spectrum were performed. From this investigation followings are concluded: A model for the fatigue crack growth is included which incorporates the low cycle fatigue properties of the material. Comparisons of the predicted crack growth rate using strain energy density method with experimental data and conventional Forman's model points out the fact that this model could be effectively used for residual life estimations.

The main advantage of the SED method is that it uses the low-cycle fatigue characteristics of the material to estimate the residual fatigue life, exactly as they are used to estimate the life to initial damage.

This significantly reduces the very expensive experimental tests for determining the dynamic characteristics of the material.

Since the finite element method (FEM) is used in the work for the analysis of the stress state, it enables complex structures such as aircraft structures, which makes this approach not only efficient but also general. In order to differ from the conventional approach where low-cycle material properties are used to estimate the residual fatigue life until the occurrence of initial damage and dynamic properties to estimate the residual life, here low-cycle fatigue material properties of the material are used in both cases.

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MONITORING AND VIBRATION TESTING OF MACHINES

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Abstract: Monitoring and vibration testing, based on a sufficiently developed scientific basis on mathematical and physical methods that enable optimal results, represents a new branch of technical cybernetics that is rapidly developing. Vibration analysis occupies a central place in the diagnostic investigation of machine conditions. Every disturbance in the operation of the machine causes a specific vibration, recognisable by the cause of the problem.

This term should include all activities carried out to evaluate the current technical state of the system (with and without disassembling the system) to undertake planned maintenance activities or provide a forecast of the technical condition of the system in the future.

This paper presents the basics of vibration analysis of machines, the correctness of which was confirmed by a certain number of diagnostic analyses performed on real devices during their operation.

Keywords: monitoring, vibration testing, rotating machines, diagnosis

1. INTRODUCTION

To have the necessary data for the diagnostic evaluation and analysis of the technical system available, there must be a system for collecting all relevant data. The system must allow the display of data in a suitable form (format) in which decisions about the machine's state are made and appropriate actions are maintained. The existence of a system for collecting and analysing relevant data must be a system of management and organisational machinery that clearly defines who gets access to what information and who, based on them, makes the appropriate decisions.

The progress of computer and measurement techniques and the development of permanent price reduction of computer hardware provides a significant step forward today in the oversight and protection of rotating machines, with a very financially acceptable investment. To achieve this goal, it will be equipped with more than years of all the significant systems of rotation so that they can be timely: to detect errors in the drive, set up according to the operating modes, identify the causes of malfunction of the system, and store don events essential information about the state of the machine [1] - [10].

2. VIBRATION TESTING OF ROTATING MACHINES

Monitoring parameters of rotating machines are indirect individuals associated with structural parameters (vibration, temperature, clearance in the bearing, oil pressure, etc..) Moreover, carriers have accurate information about the technical state of the system. Control parameters can be divided into several groups:

- The parameters of the dynamic movement of the machine: absolute and relative vibration
- The parameters of the position: the position of the rotor in the bearing sleeve, the relative movement of the shaft (axial displacement), relative elongation of the shaft, and absolute elongation housing.
- Other diagnostic parameters are rotation speed, temperature, shaft eccentricity, and electrical, acoustic, and technological parameters.

The general acceptance of the fact that approximately 90% of the damage to the rotary manifested in changes in the vibration response.

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Occurrence of certain faults machine produces a fixed excitation power that produces a specific oscillatory movement. The analysis of the vibration response system with sensors can determine the character of the excitation force and determine the cause of machine malfunction, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 Dependence of vibration excitation force

Vibration methods commonly used are the overall level of vibration analysis, spectral analysis, phase analysis, real-time vector analysis, orbit, DC analysis, trending parameters, the impact impulse method (SPM method), energy analysis, Zoom FFT analysis, CPB analysis, cepstral analysis, SED detection, detection of HFD, LFD detection, SEE technology, modal analysis. It is possible to extract vibrodijagnostičke methods used for early detection of causes and dynamic problems.

In addition to monitoring and vibration analysis, correctly identifying the cause of the issues in the work of rotating machines using other methods: Monitoring and analysis of air gap monitoring and analysis of magnetic flux, monitoring and analysis of partial discharge monitoring of wear and combustion products (oil and lubricant analysis of, analysis gases), corrosion monitoring (visual methods, gravimetric and electrochemical methods). By using expert systems and artificial intelligence systems, the entire diagnostic process can be partially automated [11] - [14].

Dynamic problems are typical for a particular group of machines, depending on their power, rotation, construction, base, etc. Using standard ISO 10816, all machines are classified into four classes, and each class of machines has its recommended and allowed level of vibration, measuring points for vibration, the way of measurement and the selection of parameters for measurement, as shown in Fig. 2.

Machine	Machine		Class I	Class II	Class II	Class III
	In/s	mm/s	Small Machines	Medium Machines	Large Rigid Foundation	Large Soft Foundation
Vibration Velocity Vrms	0.01	0.28				
	0.02	0.45				
	0.03	0.71			GOOD	
	0.04	1.12				
	0.07	1.80				
	0.11	2.80			SATISFACTORY	
	0.18	4.50				
	0.28	7.10			UNSATISFACTORY	
	0.44	11.20				
	0.70	18.00				
1.10	28.00			UNACCEPTABLE		
1.77	45.90					

Figure 2 - Vibration Severity Per ISO 10816-1

3. EXAMPLES FROM PRACTICE

3.1. Diagnosis of electrical feed pump

Location: Thermal Power Plant Gacko, Plant: Pump

Technical data of the system: The electric three-phase induction motor has a nominal power $P = 630$ kW with a production number of revolutions $n = 750$ rev/min. The pump has an impeller with discs. Roller bearings are as follows: L1-6326, N326-L2, L3 and L4-6318.

Figure 3 - Show plant pump

Operating mode machines: Pressure circulator water pump inlet 1.7 [bar], circulator water pressure at the pump outlet 6.2 [bar]. 62 Pump motor current [A]: the current 142 MW power blocks.

Testing methodology: This machine is one of the first machines Group 1. Vibro diagnostic formats were chosen for this testing, using the optimal model vibro diagnostic:

1) measurement of the total vibration level of all bearing signals in three directions, 2) spectral analysis of individual points, 3), if necessary, measure the levels of of HF bearing damage—measurements of working with selected optimal parameters of individual vibro diagnostic format.

The results

Overall of vibrations

Table 1. - Overall vibrations in pump bearings

bearings	Horizontal	Vertical	Axial
	$\sum v_{RMS}$ (mm/s)	$\sum v_{RMS}$ (mm/s)	$\sum v_{RMS}$ (mm/s)
1	1,6	1,2	1,8
2	1,2	1,1	1,3
3	1,9	2,1	1,5
4	3,2	3,1	1,2

EVOLUTION MACHINES

Evolution from in ISO 10816 standard: permissible.

- Spectral analysis

Let us show spectral plot horizontal vibration in 4-th bearings. In order to identify the causes of dynamic problems, it is necessary to know the characteristic frequency at which the defects can occur. The basic tone of rotation is $1X = 12.5$ Hz. Damage characteristic frequency for SKF6318: BPFO = 38,6 Hz, BPFI = 61,2 Hz; BSF = 26,1 Hz; FTF = 4,75 Hz, frequencies hydraulic damage BPF = 75 Hz, for RPM = 1500 ob/min.

Figure 4 - Spectrum plot horizontal vibration for four bearings

This is a spectrum plot which shows the detection of damage in rolling-element 4-th bearings, Fig. 4.

3.2. Diagnostics of turbine

Location: Thermal Power Plant Gacko, Plant: turbine

Operating mode:

Active power $P = 262$ MW, reactive power $P_{\text{reah}} = 40$ MVar. Steam parameters at the entrance to the turbine: $t = 520^\circ\text{C}$, $p = 235$ bar, the primary steam flow $Q = 750$ t/h. Secondary steam parameters: $t = 525^\circ\text{C}$, $p = 0.86$ bar. Oil temperature at the exit of the turbine bearings: $t_1 = 68^\circ\text{C}$, $t_2 = 60^\circ\text{C}$, $t_3 = 60^\circ\text{C}$, $t_4 = 56^\circ\text{C}$, $t_5 = 56^\circ\text{C}$, $t_6 = 64^\circ\text{C}$, $t_7 = 71^\circ\text{C}$, $t_8 = 58^\circ\text{C}$, the oil pressure at the exit of bearings $p = 1.55$ bar.

Figure 5 - Show plant turbine

Other diagnostic parameters:

R_p mturbine $n = 3000$ rev/min, axial displacement 0.30 [mm], the relative expansion of CVP 1.96 [mm], the absolute spread CVP 30.7 [mm], the absolute spread of CSP 20 [mm], the relative expansion of CSP 1.65 [mm], the relative expansion of CNP 3.2 [mm]. Temperature turbine white metal bearings: $t_1 = 54$ and 55°C (two measurement points), $t_2 = 53$ and 53°C , $t_3 = 68^\circ\text{C}$, $t_4 = 61^\circ\text{C}$, $t_5 = 62^\circ\text{C}$, $t_6 = 67^\circ\text{C}$, $t_7 = 68^\circ\text{C}$.

Testing methodology:

Record overall vibration levels on all turbine bearings. Make a spectral analysis of the measurement sites with increasing levels of vibration. If necessary, save the polar trend display 1X and 2X harmonic vibration, and analyse the orbit, depending on the mode.

The results

Overall of vibrations

Table 2 - Overall of vibrations in pump bearings

bearings	Horizontal	Vertical	Axial
	$\sum v_{RMS}$ (mm/s)	$\sum v_{RMS}$ (mm/s)	$\sum v_{RMS}$ (mm/s)
1	3,4	1,8	1,8
2	2,1	1,8	2,1
3	1,4	3,6	2,2
4	2,0	1,9	2,3
5	3,2	2,7	2,1
6	3,3	4,6	6,5
7	3,8	5,8	9,3
8	6,4	5,2	4,1

Evolution from in ISO 10816 standard: permissible.

Figure 6. - Analysis of the orbit to the turbine bearings

Polartrenddisplay

- Polartrenddisplay 1X and 2X vibration components is made to bearings 6 and 7 and the vertical bearings 5, 6, 7 and 8 in the axial direction.
- We analyzed the polartrend 1X harmonic vertical vibrations on bearings 6 and 7 in the following modes:
 - Working on the machine revs, no power at the generator excitation
 - Machines with rated load
 - Workplace rpm machine after power cut at the generator excitation.

Let us show Polarplot 1X harmonic vibration in the 6-th and 7-th of bearings, various parameters process, Fig. 8.

Figure 7. - Polar trend plots of 6 and 7 bearings

With polar display clearly shows that there is a change of amplitude and phase of the harmonic vibrations 1 X with increasing load. This suggests that in addition to them, asymmetry of the rotor changes the rotor geometry, which may be due to thermal deformation or the impact of an asymmetric magnetic field. The analysis of polar trend 1 X harmonic vibration in the stages, you can see the effects of these defects:

- Vector of A1-1X harmonic in cold conditions, operating speed,
- Vector of A2-1X harmonic on full load,
- Vector A3-1X harmonics after power cuts.

It is observed that the B1-vector thermal imbalance, little influence on the dynamic state (overall vibration level lightly changed) and C1-asymmetric magnetic field vector, which significantly affects the dynamic state of the machine it is in phase with the residual mass asymmetry of the rotor in response to the event beds.

4. CONCLUSION

Development of microprocessor technology and anti-based digital signal processing, construction monitoring system, in which shakes and other signals are processed practically in real-time. The application of modern methods of technical diagnostics can be found:

- When and where the damage occurred (technical diagnostics)
- To assess how the damage continues to evolve, and estimate the time until the final failure (technical prognostics)
- To determine the cause of failure (technical genetics)

Correct measurement, monitoring and analysis of diagnostic parameter relevant to the operation of the machine, especially those that describe the dynamic state and behavior is obtained at any time insight into the mechanical and procedural status of the machine, which is the goal of condition-based maintenance.

In this way, machines manage the entire process, resulting in increased availability and improved utilisation, reduced maintenance costs, and increased profitability for market operations.

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SPECIAL PURPOSE CONTAINER TERMINALS FOR EXPLOATATION AT LOW TEMPERATURES

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Abstract: The results of the investigation of the stress and deformation state for structural elements of the container terminal are presented in this paper. The container terminal is used for the accommodation of electric energy equipment, which is intended for operation at low temperatures. The analysis of the stress and deformation state of the structural elements was done during the loading of the container, because one container with electrical equipment weighs 18 tons. The containers are made of steel for low temperatures up to -50°C.

Key words: low temperatures, container terminal, equivalent stress, finite element

1. INTRODUCTION

The container terminals discussed in this paper are used for housing electrical and energy equipment. Most often, frequency regulators and batteries are installed. Batteries are used for power supply due to power outages. The construction of the container must meet all fire safety and occupational safety regulations. There may also be a requirement for a special fire-resistant paint, which expands in the event of a fire and thus protects the equipment for a certain period of time. The research presented in this paper refers to the analysis of stresses and deformations of the structure during container loading. Containers are lifted by a mobile crane with equipment. The mass of the container with the equipment is approximately 18 tons. First, the technical documentation was prepared, then the strength of the structure under load was calculated, and finally the results of the research were presented.

In this paper, the observed construction is considered as a problem belonging to the theory of thin-walled structures. The theory of thin-walled structures has developed in recent decades. This problem was investigated by Kollbruner C.F., N. Haydin and Tymoshenko S. [1], [2]. In recent years, problems of the strength of thin-walled structures have been investigated by Abramovicz V. and N. Andjelic [3], [4]. The application of the finite element method greatly facilitates the numerical calculation of the strength of the structure, which the group of authors investigated in their scientific works [5], [6].

2. CONSIDERED OBJECT

A container terminal is a unit consisting of two containers. A model of one half of the container terminal is shown in Figure 1. The first container is:

- width 3400mm,
- height 3500mm and
- length 10800mm.

The second container is:

- width 2900mm,
- height 3500mm and
- length 10800mm.

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Figure 1 - One half of the container terminal

After connecting the two containers, a place of joint is covered with the special plate that is fastened with bolts. At the area of joining roofs of containers is a plate of special material resistant to all weather conditions. Containers are equipped with doors that have anti-panic lock whose purpose is to provide a safe leaving the interior of the container when the door is locked.

Production Technology is such that the container is mostly made of bended metal sheets (plates), so as to form a thin-walled structure. For example, pillars and belts are made of sheet 8mm thick. A common feature of thin-walled elements is that they provide high stiffness and strength at a relatively low weight compared to other structural elements.

A thin-walled beam is a special calculation model that was created due to the specificity of the calculation of the mentioned constructions or their elements. In order for a structural element to be called a beam, it must meet a certain ratio of characteristic transverse dimensions and length (Fig. 2):

$$\frac{a}{l}, \frac{b}{l} \leq \left(\frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{10} \right), \quad (1)$$

and in order for a beam defined in this way to be called thin-walled, it is necessary that the ratio of its thickness to the characteristic dimension of the cross-section (Figure 2) should be [7]:

$$\frac{t}{a}, \frac{t}{b} \leq \frac{1}{10}. \quad (2)$$

Where:

t is the wall thicknes, and

a, b are cross-sectional dimensions.

Based on the shape of the cross-section, thin-walled beams are divided into open, closed and open-closed cross-section beams (Figure 3).

Figure 2 - Thin-walled beam

Figure 3 – Open, closed and open-closed cross-section of thin-walled beams

3. LOADS OF CONTAINER, MATERIALS AND METHOD

It is envisaged that the loads are like concentrated forces. These forces act on the floor of the container. Therefore, the stress analysis for the whole structure during loading has been performed. The effect of normal stresses is bigger compared to other stress components, so stress calculation is reduced to check the normal stresses.

Stress analysis have included the standard calculations of material resistance (calculations of floor elements, welded joints shear, eccentric tensioning of pillars, buckling belts).

Calculations have been made using finite element method [5]. The material properties used for the simulations are shown in the Table 1 and Table 2 [8].

Table 1 – Mechanical properties of steel P355 NL2

Thickness [mm]	Yuong's modulus of elasticity [MPa]	Poisson's ratio	Yield Strength [MPa]	Tensile Strength [MPa]
≤ 16	$2.1 \cdot 10^5$	0.3	355	490 – 630

Table 2 – Chemical composition of steel P355 NL2

The element	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Al	N
%	0,16	0,4	0,8-1,5	0,02	0,01	0,02	0,012

Table 2 - Continued

The element	Cr	Cu	Mo	Nb	Ni	Ti	V
%	0,3	0,3	0,08	0,05	0,5	0,03	0,05

Numerical simulations have been performed using ABAQUS software. Used units are [m], [N] and [kg]. In the Figure 4 load and boundary conditions are shown. Beam elements have been used (beam model) [9]. The load includes the weight of the container.

Figure 4 - Load and boundary conditions

4. RESULTS OF NUMERICAL CALCULATION

Figure 5 shows the distribution of the equivalent stress to hypothesis Hencky-Mises in [Pa]. The distribution of normal stresses in [Pa] is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5 - Equivalent stress according to hypothesis Von Mises in [Pa]

The distribution of shear stresses in [Pa] is shown in Figure 7. Displacement in [m] is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 6 - Normal stresses σ_{11} in [Pa]

Figure 7 - Shear stresses τ_{12} in [Pa]

Figure 8 - Displacement in [m]

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper the authors present the results of the stress analysis of structural elements of container terminal. Moreover, normal and shear stresses in upper belt of the floor have a maximum value, and are within the allowed limits for a given material, Figure 6 and Figure 7. Containers transport can be done only by a qualified person with the appropriate equipment and devices for transport. During loading and unloading of containers the cables must be placed at an angle of 60° relative to the horizontal surface, and no one should stand in the zone of the container within a radius of 15m. All equipment for manipulation (crane, chains, cables, hooks, etc.) should have the appropriate capacity and possess a valid document proving that it has been tested.

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QUALITY ASSURANCE AND QUALITY CONTROL IN WELDING

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Abstract: Quality Assurance (QA) involves a set of well-defined processes for systematic monitoring and assessment to ensure product quality, while Quality Control (QC) is the practice of confirming that the product aligns with the specified standards. This encompasses inspections and tests conducted throughout manufacturing, culminating in the examination of the final products. The results of these assessments are compared against predefined acceptance criteria. Implementing QC during manufacturing allows for the early detection of defects, enabling timely corrections and potential adjustments to the manufacturing process to prevent further flawed output. In welding, QA/QC plays a pivotal role in producing sound and reliable welds, ultimately reducing the need for rework. Supply contracts for fabrications may specify compliance with particular welding standards, which, in turn, may necessitate adherence to established QA and QC procedures.

Key words: Quality Assurance, Quality Control, Welding, Reliable Product, Safety

1. INTRODUCTION

Quality assurance (QA) in the production process of railway vehicles and components represents a set of all operational and organizational measures that guarantee that the products possess the quality characteristics required by technical and technological documentation. The quality assurance program in a company may involve several stages, such as: Planning, Technical documentation development, Production process, Measurement and control in production, Product testing, Packaging and delivery, Market analysis, Product servicing ect.

Under the concept of "quality assurance" in welding, a procedure is also defined that the manufacturer must follow to ensure a reliable product. Requirements and guidelines are provided in a series of standards, that are specific for application in different area, which are actually based on the standard EN ISO 3834-2 [1], defining general quality requirements related to fusion welding of metallic materials.

2. QUALITY ASSURANCE IN WELDING

2.1. The requirements

Welding must be regarded as a specialized process, which implies that the results of joints produced by welding cannot be fully examined on the welded elements themselves or the structures. This is because the application of certain methods that require specific mechanical testing could compromise the integrity of the structure. Therefore, to confirm the quality of the desired welded joint, approaches are taken to prove the welding technology itself through the examination of reference samples, competence checks of personnel involved in the welding process, and additional activities that may be defined by applicable standards, national regulations, or client requirements.

The requirements that must be met by the manufacturer are defined in the standard EN ISO 3834-2 [1]. This standard stipulates that the manufacturer must undertake the following activities:

- Review of the contract, i.e., a review of the technical requirements related to the product and an assessment of whether the manufacturer can adequately meet them.
- Review of the need and competence of subcontracted activities and services.

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- Competence of personnel involved in production planning, manufacturing, evaluation, and product control.
- Adequacy of equipment used both in production and in the control of essential product characteristics.
- Materials used in the product.
- Welding thermal cycle and potential post-weld heat treatment if applicable.
- Evaluation of the product and its characteristics, including testing and inspection.
- Managing non-conformities in case they are identified during the product realization and corrective measures.
- Calibration and validation of equipment used for product evaluation.
- Identification and traceability of processes and incorporated materials in the finished product.
- Quality records.

2.2. Verification of Manufacturer's Activities During Certification

Upon the manufacturer's request, the certification body conducts verification of compliance with the requirements of this standard, specifically focusing on:

- Welding personnel (welding coordinators, welders, and operators).
- Welding coordinators must undergo interviews and demonstrate a sufficient level of technical knowledge related to welding in accordance with SRPS EN ISO 14731 [3] and the EN 15085 series of standards.
- Welding technology specifications based on WPQR.
- Qualifications (certificates) of welders according to SRPS EN ISO 9606-1 [4].
- Mock-up tests performed according to SRPS EN 15085-4 [5].
- Fulfillment of technical requirements and welding execution in production workshops or maintenance and repair workshops.
- Compliance with welding quality requirements in line with the relevant sections of the SRPS EN ISO 3834 series (for the production of braking triangles, SRPS EN ISO 3834-2 [1] is relevant).
- Meeting all relevant items defined in the SRPS EN 15085 series of standards and verifying the fulfillment of these requirements.

3. QUALITY CONTROL IN WELDING

ISO 9001 offers general guidance for quality management, yet it lacks specific directives for welding operations. Hence, the utilization of the EN ISO 3834 series (Fig. 1) is recommended. This standard, crafted by welding experts, centers on various aspects:

- Overseeing welding production procedures.
- Outlining requirements pertaining solely to welded product quality.
- Advocating an engaged approach to managing and quality-checking welded products, either in workshops or on construction sites, focusing on the product or process.
- Serving as a system for factory oversight of product manufacturing actions.

While not a comprehensive quality management system, the EN ISO 3834 series furnishes a definitive checklist of specific components and organizational controls necessary in welding environments. Its development aimed to identify all factors impacting welded product quality and mandating control at every phase pre, during, and post welding.

ISO 3834-1 ensures different grades of welders, their competence, and the essential controls to adhere to client specifications for quality welding. Rooted in the ISO 9001:2015 Quality Management System, these standards concentrate on verifying, validating, monitoring, and measuring Quality Control in Welding to align with National Welding Standards, ensuring service quality.

Figure 1 □ Quality management in welding [2]

Quality control systems in welding must be provide with documentation, like procedures, records, instructions and certificates (Fig. 2).

Figure 2 □ Types of welding documents [6]

Review and internal audits play a pivotal role in ensuring active management engagement within a welding control system. They serve as mechanisms for monitoring performance and initiating corrective actions to address any shortcomings. These measures are essential for maintaining the effectiveness of the welding control system. Critical measures embedded within this system facilitate management reviews, enabling a comprehensive assessment of its performance (Fig. 3).

Product standards mandating adherence to ISO 3834 highlight two crucial considerations in determining the appropriate level of welding quality requirements:

- The criticality of product safety.
- The impact of dynamic loading in the product's operational environment.

The determination of the level of quality requirements hinges upon various factors such as safety considerations, exposure to high static and dynamic loads, material properties, design intricacies, and production processes. This assessment results in establishing quality requirements that can range from standard to comprehensive, aligning with the safety factors and load conditions inherent in the product's operational context.

The process of selecting welding quality requirements involves both mandatory and optional activities, facilitated through the implementation of ISO 3834 standards series and ISO 9001 (Fig. 4). These standards provide a structured framework for defining and implementing quality measures, ensuring that the welding processes and outcomes meet the necessary safety and performance criteria.

Figure 3 □ Welding controle measures [6]

Figure 4 □ Welding quality requirements

3.1. Welding procedure specification (WPS)

Welding Procedure Specifications (WPS) constitute the fundamental guidelines and variables necessary for welders to consistently produce high-quality welds. In the professional realm, these specifications come under various titles like Preliminary WPS, prequalified WPS, Standard WPS, or simply WPS. However, at their core, they all serve the same purpose—providing a structured framework for welding processes.

A Preliminary-WPS serves as an initial blueprint crafted by the contracted entity prior to welding a Procedure Qualification Record (PQR) test coupon. This precursor document outlines crucial factors such as metal types, joint configurations, essential variables, and any supplementary requirements. It

acts as a foundational reference for welders when conducting PQR test coupons, facilitating the establishment of sound welding parameters.

The Prequalified-WPS draws from historical welding data without necessitating further testing if the specified variables align within code parameters. For instance, the D.1.1 Structural Steel Code stipulates guidelines for preparing a prequalified WPS, enabling welds to meet mechanical and metallurgical standards without requiring a PQR.

The Standard-WPS (SWPS) provided by the American Welding Society (AWS) originates from industrial and government agency-submitted PQRs. These standardized documents offer cost-effective, tested parameters suitable for various welding processes, serving as an alternative when a prequalified WPS isn't viable.

1.2. Welding Quality Management System (WQMS)

The steelwork contractor must establish a documented Welding Quality Management System (WQMS) and appoint a Responsible Welding Coordinator (RWC) to oversee all welding-related operations (Fig. 5).

Figure 5 □ Elements of Welding Quality Management System (WQMS) [7]

The level of stringency and specific requirements for the Welding Quality Management System depends on the Execution Class (EXC) designated by the steelwork contractor for its fabricated steelwork. The relevant sections of EN ISO 3834 that apply include:

- For EXC1: Part 4 involves "Elementary quality requirements."
- For EXC2: Part 3 entails "Standard quality requirements."
- For EXC3 & EXC4: Part 2 consists of "Comprehensive quality requirements."

The project must clearly specify the required quality of fabrication or Execution Class.

The Responsible Welding Coordinator (RWC) refers to a competent individual responsible for overseeing and supervising welding activities within a steelwork contractor's operations. EN 1090-2 [8] delineates the technical knowledge prerequisites for the RWC based on the steelwork contractor's declared Execution Class and materials utilized. It refers to the Welding Coordination standard (EN ISO 14731), which categorizes three levels of technical knowledge:

- Basic (B) - International Welding Specialist
- Specific (S) - International Welding Technologist
- Comprehensive (C) - International Welding Engineer.

On completion of welding, the satisfactory performance of the welded structure can be determined by the testing procedures. The proof tested procedures to test under conditions similar to more severe than those that happened by the welded structures in the field. Quality weld tests can detect the weak and defective material that can be amended before it is released for use in the field. These weld tests help to design welding and types of equipment, forestall injury, and difficulties to the welders. Nondestructive testing or NDT is an approach to testing that involves evaluation without causing any damage to welded material like visual weld inspection, x-rays, ultrasonic testing, and liquid penetration tests.

4. CONCLUSION

In certain industries, regulatory requirements mandate adherence to specific welding standards, making the use of prescribed QA/QC processes obligatory. These sectors include the production of pressure vessels, structural steelwork, and lifting equipment. QA/QC also serves as a means of demonstrating due diligence throughout the fabrication process, providing a record of the product's condition during and at the end of its production. This documentation can be valuable in addressing potential claims of product defects. Neglecting adequate QA/QC during fabrication can result in welds of varying quality. When weld defects arise, rectification becomes necessary and may lead to delivery delays and damage to the fabricator's reputation. If the customer's contractual agreement mandates compliance with standards and the relevant QA/QC requirements are not met, it can give rise to contractual disputes and legal repercussions. This is particularly likely if quality issues are discovered after fabrication is completed, causing delays and, in more severe cases, product failure during use.

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OPTIMIZING COPPER ION BIOSORPTION WITH VINE SHOOT-ACTIVATED CARBON: A SUSTAINABLE APPROACH WITH LCA

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Abstract: This work addresses the pressing issue of heavy metal removal from water-based solutions by means of biosorption techniques, especially copper ion removal. Specifically, it studies the use of activated carbon that is derived from vine shoots, as an eco-friendly and effective biosorbent for Cu (II) ion removal. This research employed a Box-Behnken experimental design, along with Response Surface Methodology (RSM). It discovered that the initial Cu (II) concentration, stirring speed, stirring time, and activated carbon dose are crucial factors in determining the output variable of the removal process (i.e., the Cu (II) concentration in treated water). Copper removal efficiency of up to 98.40% was achieved. The removal is most effective at initial concentrations of 50 ppm. The optimal temperature was 20°C and the ideal activated carbon dose was 0.8-0.9 g. A life cycle assessment showed that vine shoot-activated carbon is an environmentally friendly option for the biosorption process.

Keywords: Adsorption; wastewater treatment; vine shoot-activated carbon; heavy metal removal; response surface methodology; Box–Behnken design; life cycle assessment.

1. INTRODUCTION

The removal of heavy metals from water-based solutions by biosorption techniques has attracted much attention in recent years. One of the major concerns to receive international attention has been the extent of water contamination. Due to its possible effects on humans, industrial wastewater has been the subject of environmental study. As trace metals are not biodegradable, they are extremely resistant in the environment and biological systems. Consequently, they constitute a problem. Copper is a metal that is used extensively in various sectors, including plating, mining, smelting, brass manufacturing, electroplating, oil refining, and producing Cu-based agrochemicals [1]. These industrial activities produce significant volumes of wastewater and sludge that contain varying concentrations of Cu(II) ions. The latter adversely affect aquatic ecosystems. Although copper is essential for maintaining human health and proper physiological functions, excessive exposure to it can lead to profound health consequences. These include the onset of liver and kidney disorders, disturbances in the nervous system, neurological impairments, and potentially fatal outcomes [2], [3]. Consequently, before being released into streams, effluent that contains copper must be treated. Adsorption employing both natural and modified adsorbents, ion exchange, membrane processes, chemical precipitation, coagulation-flocculation, reverse osmosis, and filtration are some of the treatments that are frequently used to remove Cu (II) ions from wastewaters [4]–[7]. Adsorption is regarded as one of these processes because it is easy, successful, economical, and efficient. Cu(II) removal from wastewater streams has been explored using a wide variety of adsorbents that may be roughly categorized as natural and synthetic. Bio-adsorbents from various natural sources, such as cellulose, are found in agricultural waste. Cellulose is of particular interest due to its environmental friendliness and lack of toxicity in contrast to those of manufactured adsorbents [8]. Vine shoots, with a yield of about 3 t/ha, are the primary waste from a vineyard's yearly vegetative cycle [9], [10]. According to the most recent statistics available, the 2021–2022 harvest campaign in La Rioja (Spain) produced about 250 kt of vine shoots. This indicates how much garbage is produced yearly in this industry. The goal of this research is to determine whether using activated carbon that is produced from vine shoots is a feasible

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economic and environmental option, given the significance of the wine industry in Spain and the amount of waste that it produces. By adopting this strategy, the circular economy will be supported and these byproducts may be recovered. In this study, the Cu (II) ions are removed by the biosorption technique and activated carbon made from vine shoots. Vine shoot-activated carbon has been examined for the removal of lead [11]. However, there have been no studies yet of its use to remove copper ions from wastewater. This biosorbent was chosen because of its effectiveness in the removal and purification of heavy metals from industrial wastewater. The Box-Behnken Design (BBD) approach was used to create the experimental plan for this copper biosorption research involving vine shoot-activated carbon. In addition, the Response Surface Methodology (RSM) was used in order to construct response plots and fit the model equation to the experimental data. The initial concentration of copper (Ini_C), stirring speed ($Speed$) and time (Tim), process temperature ($Temp$), and vine shoot-activated carbon dose (AC_Dose) have been found to be the input factors for improving the effectiveness of the process. The output is the concentration of copper ions in the treated water after the biosorption process (Fin_C). Finally, to complete this work, a life cycle assessment (LCA) was conducted to assess emissions, as well as the amount of energy and raw materials utilized, the amount of trash created during the biosorption process, and the consequences. With the use of LCA and a number of alternative treatments, the overall environmental effects of wastewater treatment techniques and infrastructure have been fully evaluated. Eliminating pollutants in order to comply with stricter requirements provides an environmental cost and benefit that may be analyzed by using LCA [12]. Its scope includes direct emissions from industrial wastewater treatment and the indirect emissions attributed to the transportation and manufacture of chemicals, as well as the energy required and treatment-related infrastructure. The best long-term option is believed to be activated carbon (AC) that is derived from biochar. It has been shown to have less negative environmental effects [13]. In addition, activated carbon is better suited to wastewater reuse because it is more effective in removing heavy metals and reduces the production of harmful byproducts during treatment [14].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

The vine shoots were harvested from a vineyard in Cárdenas, La Rioja (Spain). They were manually washed, left to dry for 24 hours, and then cut into small pieces. These were then chemically activated by soaking in a $ZnCl_2$ (98% extra-pure, CAS: 7646-85-7) solution for 24 hours. They were then dried at 115 °C for 14 hours in an oven before being carbonized in a nitrogen environment at 800 °C. The pieces were then rinsed with deionized water until the pH was neutral, filtered, and left to soak in HCl for an additional night at room temperature. High-speed grinding was the last stage in the creation of the activated carbon. Aqueous samples were produced chemically in the laboratory due to the impossibility of collecting real industrial wastewater samples. Therefore, distilled water was used with different initial concentrations of copper chloride dihydrate ($CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ 98% extra-pure, CAS: 10125-13-0).

2.2. Design of experiments for the Cu (II) biosorption process

A statistical strategy known as design of experiments (DoE) was employed to examine the connection between several input factors and an the outcome. DoE reduces the quantity of experiments or data points necessary by determining which factors most affect the outcome and their ideal values. A DoE was developed in the present study using a Box-Behnken Design (BBD) to provide trustworthy models that support the initial hypothesis with a minimal quantity of data. The design matrix that appears in Table 1 lists the previously noted inputs that were chosen for optimization, along with their ranges and levels.

Table 1. Design matrix for Cu biosorption.

Input	Notation	Magnitude	Levels		
			-1	0	1
Initial Cu (II) concentration	<i>Ini_C</i>	ppm	2	51	100
Stirring speed	<i>Speed</i>	rpm	100	250	400
Stirring time	<i>Tim</i>	min	30	135	240
Process temperature	<i>Temp</i>	°C	30	135	240
Vine shoot-activated carbon dose	<i>AC_Dose</i>	g	0.1	0.55	1

Using R Statistical Software v.1.6 [15], the design matrix was produced based on the parameters of the biosorption process. In order to guarantee that all potential Cu (II) biosorption process input characteristics were considered, a total of 35 experiments were conducted. This permitted the creation of a regression model that would identify the most important inputs for the ion Cu (II) biosorption process.

2.3. Life cycle assessment for the Cu (II) biosorption process

The ISO 14040/14044 [16] standards established the framework for the life cycle assessment (LCA) that examines how activities impact the environment. In this research, Simapro® version 9.2.0.2 software was used to process the data. The foundation of the LCA was the CML-IA baseline V3.06/EU25 method, which concentrates on the initial stages of the cause-and-effect chain to reduce uncertainty. To create the environmental inventory for this research, scaled-up inventory data from the Ecoinvent 3 database were used. They provided details of input parameters for the biosorption process and economic activities related to human activity. This involved the removal of initial copper content from 1,000 ml of deionized water using vine shoot-activated carbon. Even after the biosorption process, there were residual Cu ions present in the treated water that the process had not eliminated.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Experimental outcomes

After the input variables for the adsorption procedure from the DoE had been established, the final Cu (II) concentration (*Fin_C*) was determined experimentally. The experimental results for this output parameter (*Fin_C*) are shown in Table 3. They indicate the wastewater's ultimate Cu (II) ion content. In addition, the percentage of copper that was removed (*%Rem*) during the process has been calculated.

Table 3. Experimental outcomes.

Sample	Input variables					Output variables	
	<i>Ini_C</i>	<i>Speed</i>	<i>Tim</i>	<i>Temp</i>	<i>AC_Dose</i>	<i>Fin_C</i>	<i>%Rem</i>
	ppm	rpm	min	°C	g	ppm	%
1	51	250	240	30	1.00	0.3456	99.3223
2	51	100	240	30	0.55	0.4300	99.1569
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
34	100	400	135	30	0.55	29.2679	70.7321
35	100	250	135	30	0.10	31.4644	68.5356

Table 4 provides the laboratory-computed output process variables. The environmental impact of the process was evaluated using Simapro® v.9.2.0.2 software, which adhered to the CML-IA baseline V3.06/EU25. Representative environmental effects were abiotic depletion (fossil fuels) (*A*), global warming (*B*), human toxicity (*C*), freshwater ecotoxicity (*D*), and marine aquatic ecotoxicity (*E*).

Table 4. Environmental impact category results.

Sample	A	B	C	D	E
	MJ	kg CO2 eq.	kg 1.4 DB eq.	kg 1.4 DB eq.	kg 1.4 DB eq.
1	0.0355	0.0031	0.0008	0.0007	3.4000
2	0.0189	0.0017	0.0003	0.0003	1.6596
...	...	...	...	...	...
34	0.0183	0.0016	0.0004	0.0004	1.5045
35	0.0181	0.0015	0.0003	0.0003	1.5200

3.2. Regression model and analysis of variance

To generate the regressor models, the free software “R” statistical was used, so that the output variable Fin_C was obtained as a combination of the different input variables. In this way, regressor models were generated as second-order polynomials, as seen in Equation (1).

$$Fin_C = 7.0846073 - 0.3624463 \cdot Ini_C + 0.0035803 \cdot Ini_C^2 + 0.0491764 \cdot Speed + 0.0009521 \cdot Ini_C \cdot Speed - 0.0001801 \cdot Speed^2 + 0.0001026 \cdot Tim^2 - 12.3432317 \cdot AC_Dose - 0.0550796 \cdot Tim \cdot AC_Dose + 8.9088857 \cdot AC_Dose^2 \quad (1)$$

Subsequently, and with the goal of identifying which input variables exert the greatest influence on the output variables, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted. One of the most significant parameters obtained in statistical analyses is the p-value. It indicates the influence of each input variable on the respective output. For a variable to be considered to be significant, its p-value must be less than 0.05. To complete the analysis of the method in this biosorption process, the correlation, the mean absolute errors (MAE), and root mean square errors (RMSE) were calculated for the Fin_C output. The results appear in Table 5. It can be seen that the p-value is very low. Thus, the input variables (Ini_C , $Speed$, Tim , and AC_Dose) have a great influence on the output variable (Fin_C). Also, the correlation is very high, with a value very close to unity. This indicates that the approximation of the theoretical model to the actual one is very good. The MAE and RMSE values suggest that the regression model's errors in prediction are minimal.

Table 5. p-value, correlation and errors results for Fin_C .

p-value	Correlation	MAE	RMSE
$3.5126 \cdot 10^{-13}$	0.9347	0.0816	0.1051

3.3. Multiresponse optimization

The optimal values of the input and output variables that were studied were obtained by use of the multiple response surface method and combining input and output variables by employing desirability functions. As shown in Tables 6, 7 and 8, optimization is carried out for three initial copper concentrations, namely 2 ppm, 50 ppm, and 100 ppm. The intention is to minimize the energy consumed during the adsorption process while minimizing the final concentration of Cu (II) ions. This will result in energy savings and a lower energy cost of the biosorption process. Table 6 indicates that the concentration of copper ions in water after the biosorption process (Fin_C) is the lowest (1.171 ppm) for a low initial value of copper concentration ($Ini_C = 2$ ppm). For this optimization, stirring speed ($Speed$) and stirring time (Tim) reached higher values than in the two other optimizations ($Ini_C = 50$ ppm and $Ini_C = 100$ ppm). Nevertheless, the maximum value of copper that was removed ($\%Rem$) corresponds to that in Table 7, where the initial copper concentration is 50 ppm ($\%Rem = 98.40\%$). This table also shows the highest overall desirability (0.991), thereby validating the research's findings from the multi-response optimization study. In contrast, process temperature ($Temp$) and vine shoot-activated carbon dosage (AC_Dose) for the three optimizations are similar.

This suggests that the optimal temperature for this biosorption process is 20°C, and the optimal dose of vine shoot-activated carbon is approximately 0.8 or 0.9 g.

Table 6. Optimization for 2 ppm initial Cu(II) concentration.

	Goal	Min	Max	Optimum	Desirability
<i>Ini_C</i>	equal -> 2	2.0	100.0	2.0	1.0
<i>Speed</i>	min	100.0	400.0	259.3	0.469
<i>Tim</i>	min	30.0	240.0	90.8	0.710
<i>Temp</i>	min	20.0	40.0	20.0	0.998
<i>AC_Dose</i>	inRange	0.1	1.0	0.8	1.0
<i>Fin_C</i>	min	0.094	2.0	0.171	0.960
Overall desirability					0.751

Table 7. Optimization for 50 ppm initial Cu(II) concentration.

	Goal	Min	Max	Optimum	Desirability
<i>Ini_C</i>	equal -> 50	2.0	100.0	50.0	1.0
<i>Speed</i>	min	100.0	400.0	105.3	0.982
<i>Tim</i>	min	30.0	240.0	30.2	0.999
<i>Temp</i>	min	20.0	40.0	20.0	0.998
<i>AC_Dose</i>	inRange	0.1	1.0	0.9	1.0
<i>Fin_C</i>	min	0.0	50.0	0.802	0.984
Overall desirability					0.991

Table 8. Optimization for 100 ppm initial Cu(II) concentration.

	Goal	Min	Max	Optimum	Desirability
<i>Ini_C</i>	equal -> 100	2.0	100.0	100.0	1.0
<i>Speed</i>	min	100.0	400.0	105.0	0.983
<i>Tim</i>	min	30.0	240.0	30.2	0.999
<i>Temp</i>	min	20.0	40.0	20.0	0.998
<i>AC_Dose</i>	inRange	0.1	1.0	0.9	1.0
<i>Fin_C</i>	min	0.0	100.0	14.513	0.855
Overall desirability					0.957

4. CONCLUSION

Deciding the amount of sorbent needed to remove Cu ions from industrial wastewater is challenging. This research provides a method to optimize the biosorption process to efficiently remove copper from wastewater using vine shoot-activated carbon as a low-cost adsorbent. The optimal values of the input and output variables were obtained by use of the multiple response surface method, in which input and output variables were combined using desirability functions. The goal is to minimize the energy consumed during the biosorption process while minimizing the final concentration of Cu (II) ions. This will result in energy savings and a lower energy cost of the biosorption process. The results showed that the highest value of removed copper (%Rem = 98.40%) corresponds to an initial amount (*Ini_C*) of 50 ppm of Cu (II). However, for an initial copper concentration of 2 ppm, the concentration after the biosorption process is the lowest (*Fin_C* = 1.171 ppm). The process temperature (*Temp*) and the dosage of activated carbon from the vine shoots (*AC_Dose*) are otherwise similar for the three optimizations. According to this research, the ideal temperature for this biosorption process is 20°C and the ideal amount of vine shoot-activated carbon is 0.8–0.9 g.

Furthermore, the results indicate that vine shoot-activated carbon is a good biosorbent for the elimination of copper ions. In Spain these wastes generated by the wine industry are abundant. As a result, they serve as an easily available, effective and affordable biosorbent for the removal of Cu (II) ions from water. For future work, it would be interesting to study the initial pH value and how it affects this biosorption process, and also to as apply this method to real industrial wastewater.

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3-D PRINTING AND RECYCLING INTEGRATION IN FOOTWEAR SUSTAINABILITY

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Abstract: Sustainability in the footwear industry has been a complex task. It was addressed in this investigation by recycling shoe wastes by 3-D printing. The focus is on reducing environmental impact by repurposing critical footwear components such as insoles and safety shoe parts within the production process. Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) is employed for insoles [1], whereas Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) is used for safety shoe components. The research progresses through phases that include experimentation, material characterization, standardized testing and prototype manufacturing. Optimization involves exploring material compositions and printing parameters, during which the efficacy of Ethylene-vinyl acetate (EVA) for FDM insoles is highlighted [2]. Challenges persist in effectively utilizing the waste residues of different materials. This research underscores the potential for incorporating sustainability in footwear manufacturing by 3-D printing and waste repurposing. It emphasizes the ongoing need for refinement, material exploration, and rigorous testing for widespread industry acceptance.

Key words: 3D printing; Characterization; Footwear; Optimization; Recycling.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of contemporary manufacturing, the need to address environmental concerns is imperative. The commitment to do so is especially evident in the comprehensive overhaul of traditional practices of footwear production, where the integration of sustainability principles is becoming a central pursuit. This transformation seeks to mitigate substantial waste generation and its historical environmental impact that is associated with the footwear industry. The challenges in traditional footwear manufacturing are considerable. They are characterized by the creation of a significant volume of waste materials and considerable carbon footprints. In response, advanced methodologies are being explored systematically. They focus on the integration of 3-D printing technology and the innovative waste recycling. These approaches aim to alleviate environmental burdens and lead the way to a more sustainable industry model. The use of 3-D printing techniques, such as FDM and SLS, offers transformative possibilities, particularly in the production of such essential footwear components like insoles and safety shoe parts. These progressive methodologies reintegrate recycled materials into production, thus reducing the environmental impact of the manufacturing process [3]. This transformative approach outlines a comprehensive pathway to sustainability of footwear manufacturing. It addresses phases from experimentation to prototyping. The heart of this approach is the optimization of material compositions, printing parameters and the effective utilization of waste materials in footwear manufacturing. All of this with the aim of achieving the widespread industry acceptance and integration. Persistent challenges, particularly in effectively incorporating waste residues from diverse materials, require ongoing refinement and rigorous testing processes in order to achieve comprehensive sustainability goals. Nonetheless, these pioneering advancements signify substantial progress toward revolutionizing footwear manufacturing. It serves as an advocate for ecological responsibility without compromising quality or functionality. The integration of 3-D printing technology and strategic waste recycling strategies stands as a testament to the industry's commitment to ecological balance and sustainable production.

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2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The exploration of integrating residues from footwear materials has focused on 3-D printing techniques. This paper conducts an in-depth examination of printing methodologies utilizing FDM and SLS technologies in an effort to optimize sustainable manufacturing practices in the footwear industry. Initial investigations focused on utilizing diverse residue-infused materials that were sourced directly from discarded footwear components. The latter included ABS, rubber, EVA foam, and polyurethane [4]. Precision trials that were conducted with the FDM NXPRO Pellet printer provided an understanding of the feasibility and challenges of integrating residues into the 3D printing process. The particular materials were subjected to trials and tests with the loads and displacement outcomes considered. The purpose was to acquire values for subsequent processing and analysis. The experimental phase expanded to include the Formlabs 3-L printer. It was selected for its accessible resin tank, which facilitated seamless integration of chosen residue loads. Trials employed the Formlabs Tough 1500 resin with micronized polyurethane residue. These observations provided the basis for a comprehensive understanding of the complex dynamics governing residue integration within 3D printing methodologies. This provided a foundation for future attempts to optimize sustainable material use within additive manufacturing frameworks.

2.1. FDM for insoles

The exploration of printing dynamics involving a 5% residue mixture with TPU pellets encompassed a comprehensive array of four different materials that were sourced directly from discarded footwear components. These materials were selected to represent essential footwear constituents. They were ABS for heel structures, rubber for sole construction, EVA foam for supplementary sole components and polyurethane tailored specifically for safety footwear applications. The experimental trials were conducted meticulously using the FDM NXPRO Pellet printer. Its unique capability to use granular materials, enabled seamless utilization of the residue pellets mixture and preserved the inherent properties of the recycled compounds [5]. The outcomes of these instrumental trials contributed to our understanding of the feasibility and efficacy of integrating residue into 3D printing materials. ABS, well-known for its rigidity and commonly used in standard 3D printing applications, exhibited a notable increase in Shore hardness as the residue content surged. This caused it to be unsuitable for insoles or prospective soles due to excessive rigidity. In contrast, the integration of rubber residue presented unforeseen challenges. In particular, it failing to retain structural integrity beyond a 15% inclusion rate, thereby preventing successful printing processes. Polyurethane, despite partial residue fusion, yielded unpredicted softness due to the material's expansion when subjected to thermal conditions. This made it unsuitable for the intended safety footwear application. However, a notable success emerged with EVA foam. Regardless of residue content, the material consistently demonstrated commendable performance attributes. Although the residue wasn't fully integrated, the resultant blend with the base TPU and the corresponding hardness properties exhibited optimal properties. This caused EVA to be the first choice for insole development. A comprehensive examination of the printing parameters used in these tests provided an important understanding of the intricacies of the printing process. In the case of polyurethane, a series of parameter adjustments were necessary due to on varying levels of residue content. Conversely, ABS, a common material in 3D printing, required no parameter adjustments. This provided a hint of the potential for future testing with a 100% ABS printing configurations [6].

Figure 1 ABS, EVA, Rubber and Polyurethane testing probes

In the case of EVA and rubber, the tests demonstrated consistency in parameters, requiring only minor variations in flow rates. The progressive inclusion of residue remained optimal temperature ranges, thereby facilitating an ideal flow of the composite mixtures. Remarkably, the tests highlighted limitations in the inclusion of rubber residue. The inclusion rate exceeded 15%. This was unacceptable, as it resulted in failed prints lacking adherence to the base substrate. The subsequent characterization stage, which was conducted with a standardized 15% residue inclusion for all materials, used advanced genetic algorithm methodologies [7]. The outcomes of this analysis were foundational in shaping subsequent approaches to optimizing residue integration in 3-D printing processes.

Table 1 EVA data for the 3-D pellet printer

5	325	250	160
10	350	250	160
15	375	255	155
20	400	260	150
25	425	265	150

2.2. SLS for safety shoe parts

The design of experiments considered the printing parameters of the Formlabs 3L printer. The latter was chosen for its convenient access to the resin tank, which made it easier to add the selected residue load. The Formlabs Tough 1500 resin was selected due to its high resistance, in combination with the addition of micronized polyurethane residue. The technology used to cure resin by a beam of light ensured thorough amalgamation of the residue and the base resin. The experimental phase involved the printing of a series of compression and Charpy test specimens for comprehensive analysis. Surprisingly, amidst the varied residue loads that were incorporated, the results remained consistent, displaying uniform outcomes across all tests, regardless of the residue content. However, a discernible attribute emerged in the resin's composition, particularly its elevated viscosity. This occasionally posed a problem in the printer's mixing mechanism that resulted in defective prints. This phenomenon arose especially when using lower residue loads. A striking revelation was that viscosity decreased as residue content increased, significantly enhancing the material's printability.

Table 2 Charpy test results

Load (kgf)	0%	2,5%	5%	7,5%	10%	12,5%	15%	17,5%	20%	22,5%	25%
P1	2	6	4	4	8	4	2	2	4	6	4
P2	4	2	4	2	4	4	6	4	4	4	2
P3	2	4	4	4	6	2	4	2	2	4	4
Mean	2,7	4	4	3,3	6	3,3	4	2,7	3,3	4,7	3,3

Data from these experiments indicated a consistent pattern. Although material resistance remained uniform across varied residue loads, the resin's viscosity showed a significant inverse correlation with the residue content. As the residue inclusion rose, the viscosity's decrease produced a marked improvement in the material's printability. The foregoing accentuates the intricate interplay between residue content and resin characteristics. It indicates a critical threshold above which increased residue incorporation not only preserves material integrity, but also significantly enhances the feasibility of printing processes. This finding aids our understanding for future efforts to manage the interplay between residue-infused materials and printing methodologies.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research study involved the use of 3-D printing methodologies like FDM and the SLS. The initial trials used residue-infused materials from discarded footwear components such as ABS, rubber, EVA foam and polyurethane. The NXPRO Pellet printer contributed to an understanding of the integration of residues into the 3D printing process. This indicates that EVA is an optimal choice for insole development. With regard to the Formlabs 3-L printer, trials revealed intriguing results with varying residue loads. ABS showed increased hardness, which makes it unsuitable for soles. Rubber failed beyond a 15% inclusion rate, and polyurethane exhibited unexpected softness. However, EVA consistently performed well, marking it an optimal choice for insoles, despite partial residue integration. Parameter adjustments for polyurethane were necessary, unlike ABS. This suggest that 100% ABS printing has potential. EVA and rubber trials exhibited minor parameter alterations, maintaining optimal temperatures for composite flow. However, rubber residue inclusion above 15% resulted in impractical prints.

Figure 2 Results of the EVA compression test

Characterization with standardized 15% residue inclusion used genetic algorithm methodologies. The later are essential in optimizing residue integration. The SLS tests showed consistent material resistance. However, they exhibited resin viscosity challenges, particularly with lower residue loads. Increased residue content reduced viscosity, which enhanced printability. This inverse correlation between residue content and resin viscosity illustrates the subtle interplay, aiding future efforts in residue-material integration and printing methodologies. These findings underscore the intricate dynamics in residue integration within printing processes. They signal potential advancements in sustainable material utilization in additive manufacturing frameworks.

Figure 3 a) Insoles printed with a 15% of EVA rubber residue. b) Insoles printed with different ABS materials. c) Safety toes printed with Tough resin and different % of polyurethane.

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STUDY BY THE FINITE VOLUME METHOD OF THE TEMPERATURE DISTRIBUTION IN THE FINS OF AN INTERNAL COMBUSTION ENGINE

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Abstract: This work addresses the calculation of temperature distribution in the cooling fins of an internal combustion engine cylinder using the finite volume method. Specifically, the phenomena of conduction and convection are developed by means of the Fourier and Newton equations. This is followed by the study of integral conservation equations for each control volume and approximations using the first two Taylor series. The implicit finite volume method is then applied to the cylinder to solve the transient state. The initial conditions of the engine are known. Thus, the problem will be solved by analyzing temperatures after initial 10 seconds have elapsed. The highest calculated temperature is 93.06°C in the control volume closest to the combustion chamber. The lowest calculated temperature is 48.25°C in the control at the fin end. This study highlights the significant temperature changes to which metals (mainly cast iron or aluminum) in the cylinders of internal combustion engines may be exposed. Consequently, it underscores the importance of understanding temperature variations in the cooling fins of an engine. This is necessary to determine the engine's cooling capacity and the thermomechanical loads that it must bear.

Key words: Finite Volume Method; Temperature Distribution; Conduction; Convection; Combustion Engine

1. INTRODUCTION

In the field of combustion engine engineering, the ability to predict and understand the temperature field distribution at any time proves to be critical. This distribution not only impacts the efficiency of the cooling systems, but also affects the engine's thermo-mechanical loads [1]. Despite advances in sustainable technologies, combustion engines will have a pivotal role in our society for several future decades to come. This is attributed mainly to the current infrastructure, particularly in sectors such as transportation, that are deeply rooted in the use of these engines. Various industries, including aviation, shipping, logistics and transportation, heavily rely on combustion engines. In this context, finding sustainable solutions within these sectors can be a prolonged process. This is due to the complex technical challenges that are involved. Therefore, it is imperative to continuously develop technologies that optimize combustion engines, but minimize their environmental impact [2]. This paper proposes the application of the Finite Volume Method to study the temperature distribution in the fins of combustion engines that are similar to those used for motorcycles or air compressors. Understanding this thermal distribution is fundamental for optimizing engine performance, the combustion process, improving durability and subsequently reducing fuel consumption and pollutant emissions. However, this challenge requires advanced numerical methods that aid in understanding of transient thermal phenomena and facilitate simulation. In this context, the Finite Volume Method (FVM) emerges as a powerful tool [3]. It not only facilitates the determination of the temperature field at different time points, but also efficiently and accurately addresses transient problems in systems with intricate geometries. Numerous studies support the effectiveness of the FVM in solving transient thermal problems, in particular the work of [4]. The latter successfully employed this method to solve the thermal fields within a cylinder of an alternative engine. Due to its ability to deliver a robust and accurate solution, the finite

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volume method stands out as an indispensable tool for continued advances in the optimization and understanding of combustion engines. This work proposes the use of the FVM to determine the temperature field during the heating process of an explosion engine's fins. The implicit method was used to study engine's warm-up process for 10 seconds. The subsequent sections explore how this numerical approach offers an insight into transient thermal behaviors within engines, thereby fostering the evolution of more efficient and sustainable technologies.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Geometric model

The chosen combustion engine is a generic model. It is similar to that found in a motorcycle or a finned dissipative generator. It is manufactured from cast iron and has a piston diameter of 38 mm, 16 fins, and an outer diameter of 78 mm.

This type of engine is selected because it is usually designed to operate without active cooling systems. Instead, it relies solely on the geometry of its fins and conduction and convection phenomena. A model of the engine is created using AutoCAD [5]. This is essential for establishing initial conditions and boundaries for numerical simulations. The domain is discretized by dividing the control volume into triangles, with an element size ranging from 4 to 8 mm (See Figure 1). This size is considered sufficient to describe the geometry and apply the first-order approximation of Taylor series [6].

Figure 1. Mesh for the engine model

Due to the symmetric condition of its design, only the temperature distribution of one fin will be studied. Because of the symmetry, it is assumed that the remaining fins will have the same temperature distribution. For the same reason, the walls of the fin that have been cut relative to the rest of the block will be considered to be thermally insulated, as there is no heat exchange in the direction normal to the plane of symmetry. In Figure 2 the fin model illustrates nodes that are represented by the letter "a" (a1, a2, a3, etc.). These are discrete points in the model. Meanwhile, the letter "c" (c1, c2, c3, etc.) denotes the centroid of each control volume. Both of the foregoing are essential for the evaluation and recording of temperature distribution using the finite volume method.

Figure 2. Fin model

The values for the areas (in mm²) of each finite volume, distance between centroids (in mm), and lengths of edge (in mm) that are calculated using AutoCAD are summarized in Table 1:

Table 1. Geometric properties of the fin

Areas [mm ²]		Lengths of edge [mm]		Distances between centroids [mm]	
A1=A3=A5=A7	12.12	a1a4	6.31	c1c2=c2c3	3.39
A2	14.25	a1a3=a2a4=a3a6=a5a9	5.09	c2c6	6.82
A4=A8	10.00	a3a4=a4a5	4.85	c4c5=c7c8	1.12
A6	9.25	a3a7=a4a7=a4a8	5.33	c5c6=c6c7	2.95
A9=A13	9.80	a6a7= a8a9	4.00	c9c10=c12c13	1.66
A10=A12=A14=A16	11.93	a7a8	3.70	c10c11=c11c12	2.60
A11	9.06	a6a10=a9a12=a10a13=a12a14	5.00	c1c5	4.42
A15	19.11	a7a10=a8a12	5.76	c10c14=c12c16	2.94
		a7a11=a8a11	5.24	c11c15	6.80
		a10a11	4.87	c14c15=c15c16	3.11
		a11a12	4.87	c4c9=c8c13	4.35
		a11a13=a11a14	6.26	c6c11	4.25
		a13a14	7.80		

2.2. Material Properties and Boundary Conditions

Cast iron was the material that was used to manufacture the fins of the combustion engine. It is assumed to have a thermal conductivity of 45 W/mK and a volumetric heat capacity of 358800 J/mm³°C [7]. The external fluid is air at a temperature of 25°C and a heat transfer coefficient of $h_{ext}=15$ W/m²°C. The temperature of the internal fluid within the combustion chamber is considered to be 300°C, with a heat transfer coefficient $h_{int}=1500$ W/m²°C [8]. The combustion engine is considered to start at a time of 0 seconds. Therefore, it begins from rest at the ambient temperature of 25°C. As described in the previous section, the walls of centroids 9, 14, 13, and 16 are thermally insulated due to the symmetrical condition. The heat transfer phenomena that are involved in the problem include conduction (modeled by Fourier's law) and convection (modeled by Newton's law) [9].

2.3. Method

The finite volume method is a numerical technique that is used to discretize and solve equations for heat transfer, fluid flow, and other physical phenomena in systems that have complex geometries. In the context of heat transfer, this method is employed to separate the problem domain into a series of finite volumes or discrete cells. Each cell represents a portion of the physical domain, assuming that the temperature is approximately constant within each control volume. Conservation laws of energy are then applied to calculate the heat transfer between adjacent cells. This results in a discretized differential equation that describes the temperature distribution in the domain. The finite volume method relies on the numerical integration of differential equations. It employs a grid of cells where spatial and temporal discretization is applied. The equations are solved within each cell and updated iteratively based on boundary conditions and heat sources present in the problem. The equations that are used to solve the transient state of the proposed problem will be solved using the implicit method [10] iterating the calculation for the 10 seconds of the study with 10 iterations (using $\Delta t=1s$). For example, the solved equation for centroids 1, 5, 9, and 15 is presented and represents all possible sets of centroids.

$$\text{Node 1: } \frac{\Omega_1 * (\theta_{C1}^1 - \theta_{C1}^0) * cp}{\Delta t} - \left[h_{ext} * \overline{a_1 a_3} * (\theta_{\infty ext}^1 - \theta_{C1}^1) + k * \frac{\overline{a_1 a_4}}{c_1 c_2} * (\theta_{C2}^1 - \theta_{C1}^1) + k * \frac{\overline{a_3 a_4}}{c_1 c_5} * (\theta_{C5}^1 - \theta_{C1}^1) \right] = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Node 5: } \frac{\Omega_5 * (\theta_{C5}^1 - \theta_{C5}^0) * cp}{\Delta t} - \left[k * \frac{\overline{a_3 a_4}}{c_5 c_1} * (\theta_{C1}^1 - \theta_{C5}^1) + k * \frac{\overline{a_4 a_7}}{c_5 c_6} * (\theta_{C6}^1 - \theta_{C5}^1) + k * \frac{\overline{a_3 a_7}}{c_5 c_4} * (\theta_{C4}^1 - \theta_{C5}^1) \right] = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Node 9: } \frac{\Omega_9 * (\theta_{C9}^1 - \theta_{C9}^0) * cp}{\Delta t} - \left[k * \frac{\overline{a_6 a_7}}{c_9 c_4} * (\theta_{C4}^1 - \theta_{C9}^1) + k * \frac{\overline{a_7 a_{10}}}{c_9 c_{10}} * (\theta_{C10}^1 - \theta_{C9}^1) \right] = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Node 15: } \frac{\Omega_{15} * (\theta_{C15}^1 - \theta_{C15}^0) * cp}{\Delta t} - \left[h_{int} * \overline{a_{13} a_{14}} * (\theta_{\infty ext}^1 - \theta_{C15}^1) + k * \frac{\overline{a_{11} a_{13}}}{c_{15} c_{14}} * (\theta_{C14}^1 - \theta_{C15}^1) + k * \frac{\overline{a_{11} a_{14}}}{c_{15} c_{16}} * (\theta_{C16}^1 - \theta_{C15}^1) \right] = 0 \quad (4)$$

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

After formulating the system of 16 equations and 16 unknowns, the former can be evaluated as a matrix equation: $Y=A \cdot X$, where A is the coefficient matrix (constants). A depends solely on the properties of the fin material, thermal conductivity, and dimensions. It is similar to the stiffness matrix in finite element analysis. X is the solution matrix, and Y is the matrix of independent temperature terms, which varies with each of the 10 iterations. The following are the temperature results (in degrees Celsius) for each centroid that is summarized in Table 2:

Table 2. Temperature distribution of the fin.

Centroids	T0	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7	T8	T9	T10
c1=c3	25.00	25.34	26.26	27.79	29.87	32.38	35.22	38.29	41.52	44.85	48.25
c2	25.00	25.24	25.96	27.26	29.11	31.42	34.11	37.06	40.21	43.49	46.85
c4	25.00	26.00	28.02	30.74	33.89	37.27	40.76	44.31	47.88	51.43	54.96
c5=c7	25.00	25.82	27.58	30.06	33.01	36.23	39.62	43.10	46.61	50.14	53.65
c6	25.00	26.06	28.16	30.96	34.17	37.59	41.12	44.69	48.26	51.82	55.36
c8	25.00	26.00	28.02	30.74	33.89	37.27	40.76	44.31	47.88	51.43	54.96
c9=c13	25.00	27.82	32.05	36.65	41.19	45.55	49.72	53.70	57.54	61.24	64.84
c10=c12	25.00	28.94	34.07	39.25	44.15	48.73	53.03	57.09	60.96	64.68	68.27
c11	25.00	27.99	32.37	37.08	41.70	46.10	50.29	54.30	58.14	61.85	65.45
c14=c16	25.00	34.70	43.31	50.30	56.15	61.22	65.75	69.91	73.79	77.46	80.96
c15	25.00	44.03	54.99	62.71	68.78	73.89	78.37	82.43	86.18	89.70	93.06

The temperature distribution plot for T=0 seconds, T=5 seconds, and T=10 seconds is shown in Figure 3. It illustrates the inherent symmetry of the proposed problem.

Figure 3. Temperature distribution at 0, 5 and 10 seconds

It can be seen that the finite volumes that reach the highest temperatures are those that are closest to the combustion chamber, reaching a temperature of 93.06 °C for node 15. In contrast, those that are farther away remain close to 50 °C in the first 10 seconds following ignition. This highlights the importance of conducting a thorough study of temperature distribution and variation in engines to detect hot zones and anomalous operating points. This will help to improve performance and safety of use. Overall, their lifespan of the engine will be extended and fuel consumption and emissions of pollutants reduced.

4. CONCLUSION

This work demonstrates the use of the Finite Volume Method to determine the temperature field of an engine from rest to 10 seconds following ignition. The nature of the finite volume method makes it possible to treat the problem with matrix formulation (solving for the matrix Y of independent terms). This resolves the transient state iteratively. This process is easily programmable to simplify the calculations. It can be implemented using programmable calculators or coding languages such as C, C++, Python, or others. In contrast to other methods, such as finite element analysis (which uses a weak formulation), the finite volume method works with a strong formulation. This results in a more precise solution. Verifying the capability of the finite volume method to solve transient temperature distribution problems is reliable and secure. It is as a straightforward tool that enables the analysis and comprehension of the thermal performance of combustion engines. It also has proven to be useful for subsequent adjustment and tuning. Building upon the knowledge that was acquired in this study, there are several promising directions for future research. One avenue could be to investigate the influence of different operating conditions and fuel types on transient temperature distributions. This would enable the application and study of this method in an attempt to minimize fuel consumption and emissions by an internal combustion engine.

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EXCAVATION MINES AS PLACES OF CHALLENGES FOR A SAFE WORKING AND LIVING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: The mining industry is a comprehensive and complex branch of technology, one of the main elements of the creation and survival of civilization. However, the exploitation of ore can have a harmful effect on the soil, land surface, flora and fauna. In most cases, the extraction of ores disrupts the original ecosystem, and leaves the land destroyed after mining. The process of natural restoration of the excavated area is slow and sometimes impossible. In addition to this problem, mining is a high-risk profession, which requires permanent supervision, control and improvement of protection measures. The paper deals with a joint overview of the key adverse impacts on the environment and risks for workers employed in mines. At the end, the paper presents several examples of the problems of mining practice in Serbia.

Key words: mines, environmental protection, working environment protection, risk, contamination

1. INTRODUCTION

The exploitation of mineral raw materials is one of the primary human activities that contributes to the overall development in the progress of mankind. At the same time, it is one of the main activities that contributed to the expansion of human civilization from prehistoric times to the present day. Ores are a national treasure and a non-renewable resource, and mining is a comprehensive and specific technology. The life cycle of mining consists of research, mining development, mining operations, decommissioning and land reclamation [1]. The traditional division of mining is into metallurgy and coal mining, as well as surface and underground mining. It is known that the exploitation of ores can have a harmful effect on the soil, land surface (relief), water and air, and therefore on the original eco-systems. Due to the severity of the destruction, the natural restoration of the excavated area is very slow. Harmful impacts can result from erosion, loss of biodiversity, or contamination of soil, groundwater, and surface water by chemicals released from the mining process. All this ultimately affects people's health. For example, very easily high concentrations of chemicals, such as arsenic, sulfuric acid, mercury and other heavy metals in a significant area, contaminate surface or underground water, and large amounts of combustion products, primarily nitrogen and sulfur oxides, contaminate the air. In addition to the abovementioned, work in mines represents a safety hazard for workers even in contemporary conditions, so the protection of work in mines and the protection of the environment caused by their work are an important problem that requires a solution, supervision and improvement.

2. DANGERS AND HAZARDS WHILE WORKING IN MINES

According to official statistical data, from 2005 to 2019, 1,888 miners were killed worldwide [2]. In Serbia, 57 miners died in the Soko mine alone from 1974 to the present day. Analysis of safety in mines is a complex process based on the assessment of a large number of mutually independent parameters which are classified into several basic criteria that serve as the basis for estimating the state of working conditions.

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The criteria are related to the following conditions: the presence of gases (harmful, poisonous, explosive), dust (total, respirable), noise and vibrations, insufficient visibility or lighting, unfavorable microclimatic conditions. Mine injuries can be classified as: physical, chemical, biological, physiological and ergonomic.

Physical injuries can be fatal due to: falling rocks, fire, explosion, equipment malfunction, falling from a height, entrapment, and electric shock. Less common but recognized causes of fatal injuries include flooding in pits, release of silt from collapsed partitions, and air impacts caused by falling blocks. The systematic application of risk management techniques has contributed to a significant decrease in the frequency of such injuries in developed countries. The systematic application of risk management techniques has contributed to a significant decrease in the frequency of such injuries in developed countries.

Noise close to ubiquitous in mining. It is generated by drilling, blasting, cutting, material handling, ventilation, crushing, transportation and ore processing. Noise control measures are very complicated in mining, so noise-induced hearing damage is still common among miners. Microclimatic damage in terms of heat and humidity is a problem in tropical locations where the temperature of rocks and air increases with depth, due to the principle of the geothermal gradient. Inhalation of radon is a serious problem in underground mines which is controlled by adequate ventilation. Other physical agents include exposure to infrared and electromagnetic radiation, as well as barometric pressure present in extremely deep mines.

Of the chemical hazards in mines, silicosis should be singled out first, which was very widespread until more modern mining techniques were introduced with the wetting of materials, the use of ventilation and personal protective equipment, which is fully ensured in developed countries. Mining of individual minerals with a toxic effect has been determined represents a special health problem. For example, arsenic is associated with lung cancer, asbestos causes asbestosis and two forms of cancer, nickel, lead, cadmium, magnesium and platinum are also hazardous to the body. Coal dust is a problem with two aspects, firstly because of the pneumonia known as black lung, and secondly because of its very explosive properties. In addition, the danger of explosion in mines is also caused by other gases, the most dangerous of which is methane, but also carbon dioxide and hydrogen sulfide. Given the frequency of the consequences and fatality, these gases must be continuously measured, and the risk must be controlled and prevented [3].

Among the biological hazards associated with mines are specific bacterial diseases such as leptospirosis, an acute bacterial disease that belongs to the group of zoonoses. A person becomes infected through skin injuries or through the mucous membranes of the mouth, nose and eyes. The source of infection can also be contaminated soil or mud. In developed countries, correct sanitary measures have eradicated these and similar infections among miners.

The most common problem for miners are various ergonomic traumatic injuries that often have a permanent character, such as, for example. shoulder injuries, but also injuries to the ankles and joints due to the deterioration of the substrate. Due to the nature of the work in the mine, it is necessary to work in shifts lasting 12 hours continuously. This, combined with the heat in some mines, causes fatigue, but also a decline in motor and cognitive abilities. There is another risk that is quite frequently overlooked, which is drug or alcohol addiction among workers, as well as the social problem of separation from families if mines are located in remote and inaccessible areas.

3. HARMFUL IMPACT OF MINES ON THE ENVIRONMENT

Intensive exploitation of mineral raw materials has caused global problems related to the environment such as: climate change, damage to the ozone layer, destruction of forests, negative impact on flora and fauna. However, the most current are the local problems that make the wider area of the mine seriously endangered both during exploitation and years after.

The destruction or drastic modification of the site and the release of anthropogenic substances can have a great impact on the biological diversity in the excavation area, but also in the wider environment. Habitat destruction is a major component of biodiversity loss, but direct poisoning from mining and indirect poisoning from contaminated food and water can also affect animals, vegetation and microorganisms. Air pollution is manifested by the appearance of toxins such as: mercury, lead, sulfur dioxide, nitrogen oxides and other heavy metals. This causes health problems that include breathing difficulties and affects people and animals in the surrounding areas that need clean air. Mining can have harmful effects on the surrounding surface and groundwater. As already mentioned, mining waters polluted with heavy metals, sulfates or arsenic threaten water resources, soil, people and objects located in the threatened area. In the process of exploitation and flotation of solid raw minerals, the following elements, harmful and dangerous for the environment, are most often emitted: As, Be, Cd, Cu, Ag, Mn, Pb, Se, U, Zn. Awareness of the possible acidity and toxicity of these waters exists, but practice and literature show that the neutralization of these waters is mainly implemented in terms of the safety of mine workers or the use of this water for further use. It is estimated that there are 10,000 active, closed and abandoned mines in Europe, from which 5 to 10 billion m³ of polluted mine water flows into waterways. This causes very serious problems for livestock grazing and land cultivation in the vicinity of tailings.

When it comes to environmental protection in the field of mining in Serbia, it is regulated in the first place by the Law on Mining and Geological Research ("Official Gazette of RS" No. 101/2015 and 95/2018 - second law 40/2021). This law has tried to draw attention to the necessity of environmental protection in this area by introducing binding provisions for business entities operating in this industry. However, this law does not regulate the field of environmental protection in a detailed way, but mostly refers to the application of the Law on Environmental Protection. Namely, a business entity that wants to obtain the mentioned approvals is obliged to submit appropriate documentation concerning environmental protection (e.g. a study on the assessment of the impact of exploitation on the environment, for which it is necessary to obtain the consent of the body responsible for environmental protection and fulfill certain conditions (no restrictions for carrying out research in relation to the protection of areas of exceptional natural features, sources of underground water for public supply, endemic plant and animal species, etc.)). In the mentioned documentation, the business entity should determine the plan of environmental protection measures and the way of their implementation. For example, the study of the feasibility of exploitation of mineral deposits must contain an analysis of the impact on the environment with environmental protection and rehabilitation measures, recultivation measures, the impact of mining activities on the social community, etc. [4].

It is not necessary to fulfill the mentioned measures only before i.e. at the time of obtaining the approval, but must continue to comply with them afterwards. The person in charge of the supervision is obliged, among other things, to control whether the holder of the approval respects environmental protection measures during exploitation. In the case of permanent suspension of works, the holder of exploitation is obliged to take all measures to protect the mining facility and the land on which the works were performed, as well as measures to protect and rehabilitate the environment in order to ensure the life and health of people and property, i.e. everything according to the main mining project of permanent suspension of works .

4. EXAMPLES OF MINING PRACTICE ON THE TERRITORY OF SERBIA

4.1. Mining in Bor mines

Mining and smelting basin Bor is the only producer of copper and precious metals (gold and silver) in Serbia. Copper production began in 1903 in the localities of Bor and Majdanpek. Nowadays, the city of Bor is one of the most polluted cities in Southeast Europe. The copper smelter located in the city center is the main polluter, mainly due to old technology, which leads to environmental pollution caused by higher concentrations of SO₂ and PM₁₀ (particles smaller than 10 μm). The emission of CO₂ and SO₂ gases leads to soil acidity, and dust with a high content of heavy metals and arsenic destroys vegetation and thus causes soil erosion [5].

Around the mine in Bor there are seven sources of waste water as a result of mining and metallurgical activities and existing tailings. Almost 1285 tons of iron, 502 tons of copper, 1.5 tons of nickel, 0.5 tons of arsenic, 52 tons of zinc, 2 tons of lead, 300 kg of cadmium, and 61 tons of manganese are released into the rivers annually. Mine waters from the Cerovo locality, from the Veliki Krivelj mine and part of the Bor Pit flow into the Kriveljska Reka, while part of the mine waters from the Bor Pit, after partial purification, are drained into the Bor River.

These rivers, both polluted by metal ions, suspended particles and sulfuric acid, join near the town of Zagrađe and form the White River, picture 1, which flows into the Timok near the village of Vražnognac north of Zaječar. From the confluence of the Bor river, Timok is polluted with heavy metals, even significantly above the permitted value.

The area of damaged and degraded agricultural land in the municipality of Bor is estimated at around 60.6% of the total agricultural land. The main causes of land degradation are mining and metallurgy, pits, tailings dumps and flotation tailings. Many years of exploitation and processing of copper ore in the area of Bor led to the degradation of large areas of land by depositing huge amounts of mining waste and the appearance of mine waters in them.

Figure 1 –Confluence of the Borska and Kriveljska rivers [6]

4.2. Coal mines in Serbia

Surface mining of coal is carried out by PUBLIC DEPARTMENT OF ENERGY in the Kolubara and Kostolac lignite coal basins, mainly for the supply of thermal power plants that produce 61.8% of electricity in Serbia.

Underground coal exploitation is carried out within the framework of PD PEU, which currently includes eight active mines and one mine that was closed in the 1990s, but provides services for the construction of underground premises for other mines. Nowadays, there are nine thermal power plants in operation in Serbia: in Obrenovac (TE "Nikola Tesla" A and B), Lazarevac (TE "Kolubara" A and B), Kostolac (TE "Kostolac" A and B), Svilajnac (TE "Morava") and in Obilić (TE "Kosovo" A and B). These thermal power plants emit harmful substances above the limit values provided by the European Union. Of all the fossil fuels used in the world today for primary energy production, coal has the most destructive impact on the environment. Its extraction from deposits, processing and burning in thermal power plants cause incalculable pollution of the atmosphere, surface and underground waters, as well as soil degradation. In Serbia, electricity production from coal is primary. Of the total energy production in power plants of 34,546 GWh, coal-fired thermal power plants produced 70.3%. This production is accompanied by problems related to environmental pollution, starting from the mines where coal is extracted from the deposits, as well as later through processing and finally during the burning of coal in thermal power plants.

Until the coal deposit is opened for exploitation, it does not pose a danger to the environment in its natural balance. Given that these deposits are most often found in hilly and mountainous areas, i.e. in preserved ecosystems, problems begin to appear from the first preparatory works on cutting access

roads, clearing forests, and building infrastructural mining facilities. These activities often result in the emigration of the local population, and under the influence of the excessive noise of working machines and exhaust gases, part of the animal world begins to leave its habitat, and some plant species gradually disappear under the influence of increasingly pronounced terrain degradation. With the exploitation of the deposit, the morphology of the surrounding terrain begins to change. Increasing elevations are formed in one part due to the deposition of ore tailings, and depressions occur in the other due to the collapse of roof deposits after coal mining. This leads to local degradation of catchment areas and a change in the water regime of surface waters, which also affects the groundwater state. Mine waters which are pumped out of coal mine pits by dewatering systems are usually allowed to flow freely into surface streams without prior treatment and purification [7].

During the burning of coal in thermal power plants, a large amount of pollutants, soot, ash, including sulfur dioxide, carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxides and mercury are emitted. Sulfur dioxide and nitrogen oxides participate in the formation of acid rain, which lead to an increase in the acidity of the soil, surface and underground waters and leave consequences for the flora and fauna.

As Serbia is a potential candidate for EU membership, it will have to accept the implementation of all regulations for environmental protection and the goal of reducing net carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions to zero by 2050 at the latest. Since coal-fired power plants are the largest source of this greenhouse gas in the Western Balkans, it is unlikely that these plants can survive (Council of the European Union, Council conclusions on Climate and Energy Diplomacy - Delivering on the external dimension of the European Green Deal, Brussels, 25 January 2021). There are also signals from the European Commission that the oil and petrochemical sectors have no future, and that fossil gas will only play the role of a transitional fuel. The EU is also planning to introduce a CO₂ tax on foreign goods and services soon, which would likely automatically shut down many of our country's export-oriented pollutants. It is expected that the mechanisms will be further tightened and that the criteria will be raised to mitigate global warming and its consequences [8]. Figure 2 shows the share of CO₂ in the atmosphere for the period of the last 400,000 years.

Figure 2 - Share of CO₂ in the atmosphere over the last 400,000 years. [9]

5. CONCLUSION

Mining operations usually create an adverse impact on the environment, both during mining activities and after mine closure. The negative impact of mining includes soil erosion, sinkhole formation, soil contamination, habitat and biodiversity loss, groundwater and surface water pollution as well as air

pollution. Damages from mining works, environmental pollution, shorter life expectancy of miners used to be, as a rule, limited to the immediate surroundings of the mine, the miners and their families.

Miners' safety is of particular concern. Namely, according to data published in the seventies of the 20th century, the average time of using the pension of pit miners in Serbia was only two months after retirement, and it should be taken into account that the length of service was beneficial. Today, due to old technologies, low quality lignite and exceeding the permitted values of emissions from the mine, the damage caused by mining to the environment and the safety of workers are still extremely worrying.

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STRATEGIC SYMBIOSIS OF LEAN PRODUCTION AND INDUSTRY 4.0 FOR ENHANCED MANUFACTURING PERFORMANCE

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Abstract: *Lean production has enjoyed widespread acknowledgment and adoption in the industrial sector for many years. Its principles and tools are now commonly employed, either individually or holistically, in most production systems. This approach involves the seamless integration of people into production processes, continual improvement, and a concentrated effort on value-adding activities, thereby minimizing waste. However, a recent paradigm known as Industry 4.0, has emerged within the manufacturing sector over the past decade. Industry 4.0 facilitates the establishment of an intelligent network encompassing machines, products, components, properties, and individuals, and the implementation of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) systems and technologies throughout the entire value chain via smart factories. This paper outlines the characteristics of Lean production and Industry 4.0 environments, providing examples of how these two approaches can be effectively combined to mutually support each other.*

Keywords: *Lean production, Industry 4.0, Information and Communication Technology, Lean tools,*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the face of a rapidly evolving business environment, businesses, whether in production or services, confront various challenges and complexities. The ability to systematically and continuously adapt to these changes is crucial for enhancing product value and ensuring survival. The concept of Lean production emerged as a response to this dynamic and competitive business landscape, aiming to optimize resource utilization through waste minimization.

The Lean production concept, rooted in the pursuit of perfection, becomes paramount for sustaining any enterprise in today's environment [1]. Over the years, companies have employed principles and tools, particularly the Lean approach, to streamline operations, foster a culture of continuous improvement, and empower employees. The current market, characterized by heightened competition and a surge in demand for highly customized products, poses new challenges for Lean production. Integration challenges arise from the increasing complexity of customer needs, managing rapid schedule changes, and reliance on human experience for reducing setup times [2].

The past decade has witnessed the emergence of Industry 4.0, a suite of advanced digital technologies offering innovative approaches to managing complexity and improving productivity. Industry 4.0 empowers enterprises to leverage automation technology extensively within the organization. By enhancing transparency, and predictability, and enabling self-controlled systems, Industry 4.0 promotes faster, more flexible, and more efficient processes [3]. Businesses can harness these advantages to achieve broader goals such as producing higher-quality products and reducing costs.

By strategically combining the principles of Lean production with Industry 4.0 technologies, businesses can enhance speed, efficiency, and coordination, simplifying the management of operations and facilities. Both approaches share the common goal of achieving operational excellence for the company. In recent years, researchers have begun to explore how the implementation of both approaches within companies can raise levels of operational and financial performance. Some authors investigated which Industry 4.0 tools are used by companies with a Lean production concept [4]. Research of eight case studies was also conducted to establish the connection between Lean production tools and Industry 4.0 technologies, and a proposal was made for 6 areas in which connections between Lean and Industry 4.0 can be realized [2]. Other authors investigate the potential correlation between Industry 4.0 technologies

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and effective Lean production tools in enhancing business performance. They present an innovative framework known as Smart Systems Management for Synergy and a suite of tools named Dynamic Lean 4.0 tools. These tools are the result of collaborative relationships, intending to optimize production processes by seamlessly incorporating Industry 4.0 technologies and adhering to Lean production principles. [5]. In other research, an Industry 4.0 impact matrix on Lean production systems is introduced, outlining the intersection between Lean elements and Industry 4.0 technologies while providing an initial assessment of their impact. This matrix serves as a conceptual framework to evaluate the influence and compatibility of Industry 4.0 technologies on established Lean production systems [6]. Research conducted in 108 European companies shows that higher levels of Industry 4.0 can be more easily achieved when the Lean production concept is largely adopted in the company [7].

This paper is structured into three parts: the first part introduces the fundamental principles of Lean production and the techniques for maximizing resource utilization and minimizing waste. The second part explores the characteristics and technologies associated with Industry 4.0. Finally, the last part provides examples illustrating how these two approaches can be effectively applied together to mutually support each other.

2. LEAN PRODUCTION

Lean is a production philosophy encompassing a suite of principles, tools, and techniques applied in business processes to optimize time, human resources, assets, and productivity, concurrently enhancing the quality of products and services. It stands as a pivotal concept that empowers companies to gain a competitive edge in the market. The essence of Lean production lies in viewing any utilization of resources for tasks other than directly adding value to the end customer as wasteful. The fundamental principles guiding the implementation of Lean production are well-established [8]: Defining Customer Value: Recognizing that only a small fraction of total time and operations in any business truly contributes value to the end customer. Value Stream Analysis: Analyzing the production process (creating the value stream) to ensure that each step adds value. A value stream encompasses processes and activities across all business segments involved in jointly delivering a product or service. Creating Value Streams by Eliminating Waste: Reorganizing processes to facilitate the smooth movement of products through value creation processes. The elimination of waste ensures uninterrupted, efficient product or service delivery to the customer. Waste, in this context, is defined by what the customer is willing to pay for. Processes that do not contribute value according to the customer's definition are eliminated. Introduction of the "Pull" Principle: Implementing demand chain management to prevent the production of goods in stock. The "pull" principle ensures that finished products are produced based on customer demand, facilitating a continuous flow through the system. Striving for Perfection: Pursuing continuous improvement to satisfy customer needs and enhance processes without incurring losses (waste). Lean identifies various types of waste, including overproduction, overprocessing, delays, transportation, inventory, scrap, and unnecessary motion.

The implementation of the Lean concept and its principles involves a series of activities and processes, starting from planning the change, defining success factors, and extending to the implementation and measurement of progress.

The implementation of Lean production in business systems involves the application of a set of techniques to optimize processes. Some key techniques include:

1. **Just in Time (JIT):** Ensuring that materials and components arrive precisely when needed for production.
2. **Kanban Planning:** Utilizing a visual system to manage and control the flow of materials and information in the production process.
3. **Kaizen – Continuous Improvement:** Fostering a culture of continuous improvement, where employees at all levels actively contribute to enhancing processes.
4. **Jidoka – Quality at the Source:** Empowering workers to identify and address quality issues at the point of origin.
5. **SMED – Single-Minute Exchange of Dies:** Minimizing downtime by streamlining and expediting equipment changeovers.

6. **TPO – Total Productive Maintenance:** Ensuring that equipment is consistently maintained to prevent breakdowns and inefficiencies.
7. **5S - Arrangement of the Working Area:** Organizing the workspace for efficiency and effectiveness through the principles of Sort, Set in order, Shine, Standardize, and Sustain.
8. **Poka Yoke – Error Prevention:** Implementing mechanisms to prevent errors and defects during the production process.
9. **Visual Management:** Using visual aids and cues to communicate information about processes and performance.
10. **Work Standardization:** Establishing standardized procedures to streamline and improve processes.

Companies that successfully implement Lean production often exhibit the following characteristics [4]: Teamwork: Employees engage in flexible, multi-qualified teamwork, taking high responsibility for their work; Active Problem-Solving: The company maintains active problem-solving structures, focusing on continuous improvement (kaizen) activities; Lean Practices: Implementation of Lean production practices, emphasizing low inventory, quality management, prevention over detection and correction, a small number of direct workers, small-scale production, and Just in Time principles; Human Resources Commitment: A strong commitment to human resources policies that emphasize a shared destiny within the organization; Supplier Relationships: Closer relationships with suppliers to enhance collaboration and efficiency; Cross-Functional Teams: Utilization of cross-functional development teams to facilitate comprehensive problem-solving; and Customer-Centric Approaches: Retail and distribution channels prioritize close relationships with customers, fostering responsiveness and customer satisfaction.

3. INDUSTRY 4.0 ENVIRONMENT

The development of society over time is accompanied by the development of knowledge, which results in various scientific and technological discoveries and achievements. In the current state of societal development and scientific-technological advancement, the application of knowledge to diverse realms of human activity has precipitated revolutionary changes. So, the industry's evolution has progressed through distinct stages [9]: The First Industrial Revolution (Industry 1.0): Initiated with the invention of the steam engine in 1764, marking a shift from manual to machine production. It introduced mechanization and the automation of production systems. Second Industrial Revolution (Industry 2.0): Triggered by the discovery of oil in 1859, the invention of the electric light bulb in 1879, and the AC motor in 1887. This era embraced industrialization with assembly lines, mass production, and the use of new fuels (oil and electricity). Third Industrial Revolution (Industry 3.0): Commenced with the installation of the first electronic computer ENIAC in 1946 and the advent of numerical control in machine tools. This phase involved the fusion of computer and electronic automation into production processes, leveraging computers and new technologies. Fourth Industrial Revolution (Industry 4.0): Originated with the conceptualization of Industry 4.0 in 2011. It is characterized by the integration of advanced technologies, including artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, and big data analytics into the production process to create smart factories. The objective of Industry 4.0 is to establish highly efficient, productive, and autonomous factories capable of meeting the demands of the modern market. In Industry 4.0, intangible software and management technologies play a dominant role compared to tangible ones.

While a universally accepted definition of Industry 4.0 is still lacking, it can be succinctly described as the virtualization or full computerization of industrial production. Four fundamental principles underlie Industry 4.0 [10]: Interconnection: Devices, sensors, and machines use wireless communication technologies to interact through the Internet of Things; Information Transparency: By linking people and objects, greater availability of information is achieved, creating a virtual representation of the physical world; Decentralized Decisions: Enabled by the implementation of interconnection and information transparency, decisions can be made locally using relevant information, with delegation to higher levels only in specific cases; and Technical Assistance: Acknowledging the complexity of production, technical assistance is crucial.

This includes decision support systems aiding human decision-making through information collection and visualization, and physical assistance where advancements in robotic technology enable new forms of assistance within the factory.

Figure 1 The technologies in Industry 4.0

The technologies integral to Industry 4.0, as depicted in Figure 1, include:

1. **Autonomous Robots:** Robots designed to work alongside humans, enhancing productivity through collaborative efforts.
2. **Cybersecurity:** Ensuring the protection of networks and devices from potential cyber-attacks that may disrupt operations, compromise valuable data, or inflict physical damage.
3. **Augmented Reality (AR):** Involves overlaying digital information onto the physical world using technology.
4. **Internet of Things (IoT):** Facilitates the effective connection between the digital and physical worlds, linking sensors and actuators from the real world to the Internet, enabling data transmission.
5. **System Integration:** The interconnection of all hardware components into a unified unit, with resources utilized by implemented software components, creating a functional information system.
6. **Simulation:** Enable rapid testing and optimization of new designs and processes.
7. **Big Data:** Manufacturers analyze vast amounts of data generated by IoT devices and other sources, gaining insights into operations and identifying improvement opportunities.
8. **Additive Manufacturing (3D Printing):** Enables the creation of intricate shapes and structures challenging to produce with traditional methods.
9. **Cloud Computing:** A platform treating applications and data as services delivered over the Internet, rather than as products.

4. APPLICATION OF LEAN PRODUCTION IN THE INDUSTRY 4.0 ENVIRONMENT

Companies aiming to optimize their operations must comprehend the interplay between traditional Lean production and Industry 4.0. Recent studies on operational excellence programs have consistently highlighted the creation of valuable synergies when Lean production and Industry 4.0 are implemented systematically, rather than independently or sequentially. In many instances, the integrated application of Lean production and Industry 4.0, often referred to as Lean Industry 4.0, emerges as the most effective

approach to attain the next level of operational excellence. Companies that successfully implement Lean Industry 4.0 can achieve substantial reductions in conversion costs, up to 40%, over five to ten years. These reductions surpass the achievements of the best independent implementations of Lean or Industry 4.0. Realizing these benefits necessitates companies to tailor the implementation of Lean Industry 4.0 to address specific challenges across the supply chain and at the factory level. Examples illustrating the convergence of Lean production and Industry 4.0 technologies are presented below.

4.1 CUSTOMER CENTRICITY

Lean production has always prioritized a customer-centric approach, and now, digital technologies are enhancing businesses' understanding of their customers' needs. For instance, advanced data analytics and artificial intelligence can analyze customer data to gain deeper insights into their preferences. A straightforward example is analyzing application usage behavior or understanding when, where, and how many people access information about a product's origin through its label. The integration of automated and semi-automated robots into production lines facilitates mass customization, allowing customers to extensively personalize their orders due to the increased handling capacity for a greater variety of products.

4.2 CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT

The continuous improvement techniques applied on a production line traditionally involve selectively changing a variable, testing it in real time, and assessing the results. With the advent of new technologies, such as robust simulation tools and the digital twin concept, businesses now have the capability to test their assumptions in the virtual world before implementing or testing them in the physical realm. This integration of Industry 4.0 technologies enhances the continuous improvement philosophy of Lean production, providing a more advanced and efficient approach to refining and optimizing processes.

4.3 INTEGRATED VALUE CHAIN

Lean principles aspire to eliminate waste throughout the value chain, from customer order to delivery. Industry 4.0 tools, including horizontal and vertical system integration and data analytics, play a crucial role in this endeavor. The integration and connectivity of business, IT, operating systems, machines, and devices generate a comprehensive systems view of the entire value chain. This holistic perspective enables managers to identify patterns or weaknesses in the process, providing the insights needed to prioritize areas for improvement. The synergy between Lean and Industry 4.0 enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of value chain optimization.

4.4 JUST IN TIME

The imperative of digitalization further empowers a fundamental Lean tool, Just in Time (JiT). Through digitalization, JiT systems can leverage advanced capabilities such as forecasting, simulation, advanced analytics, and vertical and horizontal integration. This integration of digital tools enhances the precision and efficiency of JiT systems, allowing for more accurate demand forecasting, streamlined production processes, and optimized supply chain coordination [11].

4.5 SMART PRODUCTS

Smart products leverage sensor technologies to collect and analyze information about repetitive actions. These products possess distinctive features, including being context-aware, adaptive, self-organized, and proactive, enabling support throughout their entire life cycle and facilitating a continuous process of improvement. The data gathered by smart products allows for the visualization of the production process and information flow for a specific group of products. This data can be utilized to create a map of the current state, identifying waste in certain processes and informing future strategic planning activities, aligning with the goal of value stream mapping. Additionally, smart products can incorporate Kanban information, contributing to the control of production processes [4].

4.6 SMART MACHINES

Smart machines equipped with intelligent panels offer real-time detection of marked Kanban cards, achieving a high read rate, typically 100%. This solution ensures continuous improvement through the collection of production line data from machines, utilizing technologies such as actuators, sensors, and wireless video. The collected data is then analyzed and processed in the cloud to enhance operational intelligence and, more importantly, to prevent errors, aligning with the core principle of Poka Yoke. Additionally, the implementation of Plug'n'Produce facilitates the integration of the Single Minute Exchange of Die (SMED) method across entire production lines. This not only streamlines the changeover process but also contributes to overall operational efficiency [4].

5. CONCLUSION

Lean production has proven effective in output-oriented systems that prioritize high-quality products to achieve customer satisfaction, operating under the principle that anything not adding value is considered waste. Its successful application has contributed to the remarkable flexibility of production systems and the realization of complex products and supply chains. To enhance efficiency, there is a growing inclination to incorporate Information Technology (IT) to integrate production and planning and foster collaboration between customers and suppliers through cyber-physical systems, commonly known as Industry 4.0.

The examples highlighted in this paper, such as user-centeredness, continuous improvement, integrated value chains, Just in Time, smart products, and smart machines, illustrate the potential synergy between Lean production and Industry 4.0. These approaches can complement and mutually support each other when implemented in companies, thereby enhancing competitiveness in the market.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF MULTI-RISK ANALYSIS FOR FIRE INSURANCE

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Abstract: A fire breaking out can be a disaster wherever they occur, which means it can certainly be a disaster for a business. Whether the business premises is full of computers or furniture, paperwork or that is a factory, a fire can cause havoc and cost a number of ways, and not just financially. From direct costs associated with rebuilding and repairing damaged property to indirect costs like lost revenue and increased insurance premiums, the financial impact of a fire can be devastating for a business of any size. Today's development of protection of human and human environment from various forms of endangerment, imposes the need to undertake extensive preventive measures and introduction of multifunctional protection systems. Therefore, it is necessary to do a multi-risk assessment. The most important prerequisite for adequate planning, organization and management is the availability of the necessary information that can only be reached by developing a well-organized system for managing fire and catastrophic events.

Key words: multi risk, hazard, insurance, risk assessment

1. INTRODUCTION

As with the terms 'natural disaster', and 'hazard', there is no universally accepted definition of risk, and a range of definitions of risk from natural disaster exist as in [1]. These expressions reflect risk of natural disaster more comprehensively and most risk assessment approaches use these definitions or variants of them. However, the differences that occur mean that risk associated with natural hazards is commonly characterized in one of two distinct categories of risk assessment.

The first type defines risk as the probability of loss caused by the interactions between the vulnerability of exposure and the hazard. Risk is most commonly expressed as in equation:

$$\text{Risk}=(\text{Hazard} \times \text{Vulnerability} \times \text{Exposure})$$

The second type describes risk as a product of the probability of occurrence of a hazardous event and the consequences of such an event for exposures (the magnitude of impact resulting from realization of the hazard). Risk is expressed as:

$$\text{Risk}=\text{Probability} \times \text{Consequence}$$

The first expression the risk assessment process towards a greater consideration of the disaster formation mechanism (interaction of hazard and exposure), as in [1]. The second type emphasizes the possible consequences by assessing risk from the perspective of possibility of loss.

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2. THE COST OF FIRE

There can be no doubt that one of the most catastrophic events that any business can suffer is a fire. From direct costs associated with rebuilding and repairing damaged property to indirect costs like lost revenue and increased insurance premiums, the financial impact of a fire can be devastating for a business of any size. Despite this, many businesses are still unprepared for the potential dangers of fire, failing to implement adequate fire safety measures that can help reduce the risk of a fire. In this article, we'll explore the cost of fire, including the direct and indirect costs associated with fires, and examine the fire safety measures that can help minimise these costs. By understanding the full cost of a fire to a business, you can take the necessary steps to protect your business and employees from the financial impact of a fire. Suffering a fire is expensive When a business suffers a fire it can result in a range of costs to the company. These can be broken down into direct costs and indirect costs:

Direct costs

Repairing damaged property – the cost of repairing or rebuilding damaged property, including materials, labour, and construction costs, can be significant. Insurance claims – your insurance can help cover the cost of repairs, but the process of filing a claim and negotiating a settlement can be time-consuming and complicated.

Equipment and inventory loss – fires can destroy equipment, products, and inventory, resulting in a significant financial loss for your business.

Indirect costs

Lost revenue – suffering a fire will disrupt business operations. This will almost certainly result in lost revenue and reduced productivity. Depending on the severity of the fire, it can take weeks or even months for a business to fully recover.

Increased insurance premiums – after a fire, insurance premiums can increase, adding an additional financial burden to a business.

Reputational damage – suffering a fire can also damage your company's reputation, making it more difficult for a business to attract customers and generate revenue in the future.

3. THE MULTI-HAZARD RISK ASSESSMENT

Generally, Multi-hazard risk assessment is based on single-hazard risk assessment. The main advance of Multi-hazard risk assessment is that it puts different types of hazards into a single system for joint evaluation as in [1]. The understanding of disaster formation mechanism determines the strategy of risk assessment. Hence, perspective on the disaster formation mechanism forms the basic theory for risk assessment. The existing perspectives on the disaster formation mechanism basically can be divided into four types: natural hazard perspective, hazard-forming environment perspective, exposure perspective and regional disaster system perspective.

A conceptual model is a model made up of a composition of concepts, which are used to help understand relationships among factors in the model. A conceptual model of risk shows the relationship among factors that give rise to that risk. Two distinct categories of conceptual model of risk and were summarized. Multi-hazard risk assessment assesses the risk from multiple hazards, and building on the

models of risk from a single hazard presented above, can be expressed in two fundamental conceptual models as in [1]:

$$Risk = \sum_{i=1}^n (Hazard \times Vulnerability \times Exposure)$$

$$Risk = \prod_{i=1}^n Probability \times Consequence$$

Where, $i = (1, 2, \dots, n)$ represents i types of hazards.

These two expressions cannot express the whole regional disaster system perspective. The first expression is biased towards interaction of hazard and exposure, whilst the second emphasizes the possible consequences by assessing risk from the perspective of possibility of loss. The substantively different conceptual approaches to Multi-hazard risk assessment have both been developed in practice by many authors.

Figure 1. Conceptual model for multi-hazard risk assessment

Based on the regional disaster system perspective, the conceptual model for Multi-hazard risk assessment can be developed as shown in Figure 1.

Multi-hazard risk assessment is a relatively new field, with little Multi-hazard risk assessment research conducted before 2000. Multi-hazard risk assessment has become a major concern in the risk study area, but existing approaches do not adequately meet the needs of risk mitigation planning. The main research gap in the existing approaches was identified that they cannot consider all hazard interactions when calculating possible losses.

One of the difficult issues in natural hazards risk assessment is how to analyze the risk for more than one hazard in the same area, and the way they interact. Many authors, as in the, Figure 1 shows an illustration of how different sets- of triggering factors can cause a number of different hazards. There are many factors that contribute to the occurrence of hazardous phenomena, which are either related to the environmental setting (topography, geomorphology, geology, soils etc.) or to anthropogenic activities (e.g. deforestation, road construction, tourism). Although these factors contribute to the occurrence of the hazardous phenomena and therefore should be taken into account in the hazard and risk assessment, they are not directly triggering the events. A generally accepted definition of multi-hazard still does not exist. In practice, this term is often used to indicate all relevant hazards that are present in a specific area, while in the scientific context it frequently refers to “more than one hazard”. The terminology that is used to indicate the relations between hazards is unclear.

The importance of multi risk assessment are:

- The simplest approach is to consider that the hazards are independent and caused by different triggers. If that is the case the risk can be calculated by adding the average annual losses for the different types of hazard. This would be the case for example for earthquake hazard and flood hazard. They have different triggering mechanisms which do not directly interact. Therefore earthquake hazard is independent of flood hazard and may be analyzed separately. Also the risk may be analyzed separately and the resulting losses could be added.
- The second multi-hazard relationship is therefore between different hazard types that are triggered by the same triggering event. These are what we would call coupled events (Marzocchi et al., 2009). The temporal probability of occurrence of such coupled events is the same as it is linked to the probability of occurrence of the triggering mechanism. For analyzing the spatial extent of the hazard, one should take into account that when such coupled events occur in the same area and the hazard footprints overlap, the processes will interact, and therefore the hazard

modeling for these events should be done simultaneously, which is still very complicated. In order to assess the risk for these multi-hazards, the consequence modeling should therefore be done using the combined hazard footprint areas, but differentiating between the intensities of the various types of hazards and using different vulnerability-intensity relationships. When the hazard analyses are carried out separately, the consequences of the modeled scenarios cannot be simply added up, as the intensity of combined hazards may be higher than the sum of both or the same areas might be affected by both hazard types, leading to overrepresentation of the losses, and double counting.

- A third type of interrelations is the influence one hazard exerts on the disposition of a second hazard, though without triggering it (Kappes et al. 2010). An example is the “fire-flood cycle” (Cannon & De Graff, 2009): forest fires alter the susceptibility to debris flows and flash floods due to their effect on the vegetation and soil properties. This problem highlights the fact that the conditions that make certain areas more susceptible to hazards may change constantly. For instance land cover and land use have a large effect on hydro-meteorological hazards such as flooding and landslides. When these change as a result of other hazards (like forest fires), also the susceptibility to landslides, debrisflows or floods increases. Many of the hazard relations are of this type. It is very difficult to take this type of relationship into account before one particular hazard has changed the conditions that make the terrain more susceptible to the second hazard. The practice is to update a multi-hazard risk assessment each time after the occurrence of a major hazard event (like a volcanic eruption, major earthquake or hurricane).
- The third type of hazard relationships consists of those that occur in chains: one hazard causes the next. These are also called domino effects, concatenated, or cascading hazards. These are the most problematic types to analyze in a multi-hazard risk assessment. Hazard may occur in sequence, where one hazard may trigger the next. These hazard chains or domino effects are extremely difficult to quantify over certain areas, although good results have been obtained at a local level (e.g Peila and Guardini, 2008), as in [1].

The best approach for analyzing such hazard chains is to use so-called event-trees. An event tree is a system which is applied to analyze all the combinations (and the associated probability of occurrence) of the parameters that affect the system under analysis. All the analyzed events are linked to each other by means of nodes all possible states of the system are considered at each node and each state (branch of the event tree) is characterized by a defined value of probability of occurrence.

4. CONCLUSION

There are a number of fire safety measures that the business can take to minimise the cost of a fire. These measures can include: Carrying out regular fire risk assessments: The process should include a thorough examination of the building, equipment, and processes to identify potential fire risks. Providing fire safety training – regular fire safety training for employees can help ensure that everyone knows how to respond in case of a fire and minimise the risk of fire-related accidents. Installing fire alarms – fire alarms can provide an early warning of a fire, allowing employees to evacuate the building and emergency services to respond quickly. Installing fire sprinkler systems – fire sprinkler systems can help control and contain a fire, reducing the extent of damage to the building and contents. Implementing emergency evacuation procedures – in the event of a fire, it is important for employees to know what to do and where to go. Implementing emergency evacuation procedures, including fire drills, can help ensure a safe and fast evacuation.

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Analysis of the impact of employee efficiency on production quality in the automotive industry

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***Abstract:** Within the scope of the research presented in this paper, one of the pivotal aspects of the manufacturing process in the automotive industry has been scrutinized – employee efficiency and its impact on production quality. Through an in-depth analysis of data collected from workstations on the production line, the research is centered around comprehending the relationship between the level of employee efficiency and the quantity of defective components in comparison to the produced defect-free parts. Using the statistical regression method, key factors have been identified that can predict enhancements in production quality while optimizing workforce utilization. The outcomes of this research provide practical guidelines for enhancing efficiency and quality within the automotive manufacturing environment.*

***Key words:** Manufacturing process, automotive industry, employee efficiency, statistical regression*

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's business world, the volume of data is growing at a rapid rate, and analytical techniques are becoming essential for extracting value from information. This trend is particularly pronounced in industries such as automotive, where data generated during production can provide insight into the performance and efficiency of production processes. The automotive industry represents a key sector of the global economy, with high requirements for efficient production and maintaining a high level of product quality. It could be said that the efficiency of employees is one of the key factors in achieving these goals. Quality and quality control are essential in the automotive industry because they directly affect safety, performance, and customer satisfaction. High quality standards ensure competitive advantage, consumer appeal and maintaining brand reputation. Employee efficiency analysis becomes key in identifying challenges, providing insights for continuous improvement of manufacturing processes, thus ensuring long-term sustainability and success in the industry. For the purposes of this research, the data was collected from a multinational company, which belongs to the automotive industry and is engaged in the production of car interiors of the world's most famous brands, such as Mercedes, Porsche, BMW, Audi, and many others. In this paper, the focus is on a production line that produces parts for the Mercedes brand and that consists of multiple workstations, each with its own specific tasks and characteristics. Through the application of statistical regression, the efficiency of employees at each workstation in a certain period will be analyzed, as well as the quality of production, for the same period. Also, the effect of efficiency on product quality. NCSS software is used to analyze the data, providing visualization and detailed exploration. The goal of the research is to analyze how the efficiency of employees at different workstations can affect the quality of products on the production line, as well as to enable a better understanding of the human factor and the improvement of production quality in this company.

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2. BACKGROUND RESEARCH

According to Yuan Badrianto and his associate Muhammad Ekhsan, improving employee performance is one of the most important factors for companies to achieve their goals. In addition to contributing to the achievement of goals, employee performance also serves as a measure of the quality of human resources in the company. Some of the key factors that can influence the success of employee performance include the work environment and job satisfaction. The goal of their research is to determine whether there is an impact of variables of the work environment and job satisfaction on employee performance. Also, the purpose of the research is to examine the effect of the work environment and job satisfaction on the performance of employees at PT Nesinak Industries. The company is engaged in the production of automotive and electronic spare parts made of rubber. The sample in this research includes 88 respondents who work in the production department. This study uses quantitative research methods. The data for the research was collected by filling out questionnaires from pre-selected respondents. The method of data analysis that was used was the method of multiple regression analysis. Based on the results of the t-test (partial) and F-test (simultaneous) in this research, it was shown that the variables of work environment and job satisfaction have a positive and significant impact on the performance of employees both individually and simultaneously, [1].

Taibo Chen and his colleagues investigated the impact of organizational support on employee performance. The aim of this research was to study the influence of leadership styles, motivation, and discipline on the performance of employees in the company "PT. Kiyokuni Indonesia". This research used data collected through surveys on employee motivation, discipline, leadership style and performance. From a total of 451 members of the population, 82 subjects were selected who met the criteria for the sample, using Slovin's formula. The analytical method used in the research was the multiple linear regression method with the use of SPSS version 22. Research findings indicate a positive and significant influence of leadership styles, motivation, and discipline both individually and simultaneously on employee performance. It is especially emphasized that discipline is the most important factor that affects the performance of employees and therefore requires special attention, [2].

Preeti Dwivedi, Vijit Chaturvedi, Jugal Kishore Vashist had the goal of investigating the impact of transformational leadership on employee effectiveness. They also investigated the role of knowledge sharing as a mediator between transformational leadership and employee effectiveness. The research is based on a survey conducted among 200 employees in logistics companies. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) approaches were used for the evaluation. The study found that transformational leadership has a positive and significant impact on employee effectiveness. Research also shows that after the introduction of knowledge sharing, it fully mediates the impact of transformational leadership on employee effectiveness. The study shows that if leaders share their knowledge and expertise with the team, employees tend to be highly effective and productive compared to a situation where there is no knowledge sharing. The findings of this research will help the top management of organizations to formulate strategies to improve the relationship between management and subordinates through knowledge sharing. The study also suggests that regular knowledge sharing among the team improves the effectiveness of team members and thus the performance of the organization, [3].

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology itself is primarily based on the construction of a business intelligence system (BI), which includes:

- Data collection
- Data preparation
- Data analysis
- Data visualization
- Discussion of the obtained results

3.1. Data collection and goal definition

For the purposes of this research, data was collected in a multinational company belonging to the automotive industry, from the internal web application Production Reporting.

In addition to numerous reports included in the application, in this research we will highlight Production per station report, Manufactured parts report, Employee efficiency report, Scrap report. Therefore, the data on the produced parts per each workstation on the production line, the report on scrapped parts, as well as the report on the efficiency of employees at all workstations in each period, as well as the total produced parts, i.e., the parts that were checked at the Quality Gate station, were downloaded.

The goal of this research is to analyze the impact of employee efficiency on the quality of manufactured parts during a three-year period, from September 2020 to September 2023. To achieve this goal, the following steps must be taken:

1. Analysis of production quality - the first step includes the analysis of production quality on the production line. In this step, we identified the rate of good parts, the rate of undefined parts, and the rate of scrapped parts for each workstation during the mentioned period. In this step, the goal is to understand trends and variations in product quality.
2. Analysis of employee efficiency - the second step is the analysis of a set of data on the efficiency of employees at workstations. The efficiency rates of each operator per each workstation in each period are identified.
3. Statistical relationship between efficiency and quality - Application of statistical regression methods to understand the impact of employee efficiency on production quality.

3.2. Data preparation

Before the actual data analysis, it is necessary to clean and transform the data. Data purification represents one of the most important tasks of DataMining and includes the preparation and transformation of data into a suitable template, which is suitable for research methods [4]. It was necessary to delete unnecessary data and columns, as well as duplicates. Specifically, in our set, certain rows were transformed into columns, so that the data would be suitable for statistical analysis. Columns whose values were equal to zero were also deleted.

3.3. Data analysis

This chapter presents the role of data mining in the industry, as well as the basic concepts of statistical analysis. The concept of statistical regression as one of the methods of statistical data analysis is also explained. The software tool that was used for the purposes of the research is also described.

3.3.1. Data mining and statistical analysis

At a broader level, data mining is the process of extracting accurate and previously unknown information from large amounts of data. That information needs to be in a form that can be understood, acted upon, and used to improve the decision-making process. It is obvious that by this definition, data mining encompasses a broad set of technologies, including data warehousing, database management, data analysis algorithms, and visualization. The core of the appeal of this new technology lies in data analysis algorithms, as they provide automated mechanisms for sifting through data and extracting useful information. The ability to analyze these algorithms, along with today's data warehousing and database management technology, enables corporate and industrial data mining. The data representation model for such algorithms is quite simple. Data is considered a collection of records, where each record represents a collection of fields. Using this tabular data model, data mining algorithms are designed to work with the content, under different assumptions, and to provide results in different formats. Data analysis algorithms or data mining algorithms can be divided into three main categories based on the nature of their information extraction: predictive modeling (also called classification or supervised learning), clustering (also called segmentation or unsupervised learning), and frequent pattern extraction, [5].

The practice of statistics provides companies with several methods for testing theories and exploring innovative ideas through data analysis. When used correctly, statistical analysis aims to guide decisions by identifying and responding to trends and patterns and can impact every part of the business. Statistical analysis relies on quantitative data, or numerical data, to remove bias in the interpretation of results. For business purposes, the use of statistical analysis can be useful in many scenarios, including:

- Research - regularly conducting statistical analysis helps companies improve their research strategies.
- Modeling - data modeling, which visually represents the data through graphs or diagrams, provides relevance to the topic, making the reasons for conducting the analysis clear.
- Regression and classification are common modeling methodologies.
- Designing surveys - to create a thorough and accurate statistical analysis, it is important to collect the appropriate data. Companies achieve this by designing surveys that measure customer satisfaction and feedback for improvement, [6].

3.3.2. Statistical regression

Regression is a data mining technique used to predict a range of numerical values (also called continuous values) given a particular set of data. For example, regression can be used to predict the cost of products or services given other variables. Regression is used in multiple industries for business and marketing planning, financial forecasting, environmental modeling, and trend analysis. Regression is one of the methods within the methods that make up "statistical learning" - a large set of statistical methods, techniques and tools for modeling and understanding complex data sets.

Regression is one way to construct a model for predicting and evaluating one or more dependent variables based on one or more independent variables. In regression, there is an output, unlike other statistical techniques that deal with problems in which there is no dependent variable, [7].

3.3.2.1 Linear regression

Linear regression is the simplest and oldest form of regression used to estimate the relationship between two variables. This technique uses the mathematical formula of a straight line ($y = mx + b$). (1.1)

In layman's terms, this simply means that, given a graph of Y and X -axis, the relationship between X and Y is a straight line with little deviation. For example, we can assume that, given population growth, food production will increase at the same rate - this requires a strong, linear relationship between the two quantities. To visualize this, consider a graph where the Y-axis tracks population and the X-axis tracks food production. As the value of Y increases, the value of X will increase at the same rate making the relationship between the two linear, [7].

3.3.2.1.1. A simple linear regression

A statistical method based on the mutual relationship between two quantitative variables, where the value of the dependent variable can be predicted based on one independent variable, is called simple linear regression. This method has been widely applied in the business world, social and behavioral sciences, biology, and other scientific disciplines.

Simple linear regression is the simplest form of linear regression that can be represented by the formula (1.2), [7]:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x + \varepsilon \tag{1.2}$$

Whereby:

y – the value to be predicted (dependent variable) in the i iteration,

x – value by which to predict (independent variables) in the i iteration,

β_0, β_1 – regression coefficients (regression parameters),

ε – accidental mistake, [7].

Unlike mathematical (function), statistically, it is not perfect. In this sense, observations in the case of statistical dependence do not have an ideal linear relationship. Consequently, the random error ε in the statistical relationship explains the variability of the dependent variable that cannot be explained by the linear relationship between x and y, [8].

In theory, if the regression parameters β_0 and β_1 are known, it is possible to determine the dependent variable u for each value of the independent variable x. In practice, the values of the regression parameters are usually not known, so they are estimated based on sample data. The estimation of the value of the regression parameters is performed using the regression equation of the form, [8]:

$$\hat{y} = b_0 + b_1 x \tag{1.3}$$

Based on this equation, it is possible to determine the regression line, where $\hat{y}$ is the estimated value of the dependent variable (y) for the value of x , and b_0 is the ordinate of the intersection of the regression line, and b_1 is the estimated value of the regression coefficient for the observed case, [8].

The method of least squares is used to determine the values of b_0 and b_1 from the sample data such that the sum of the squared deviations of the actual values of the dependent variable (y_i) and the predicted value of the dependent variable is minimized:

The least squares criterion has the form:

$$\min \sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (1.4)$$

Whereby:

y_i – the actual value of the dependent variable for the i case,

$\hat{y}_i$ – the estimated value of the dependent variable for the i case.

Expressions are used to calculate the values of b_0 and b_1 :

$$b_1 = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (1.5)$$

$$b_0 = \bar{y} - b_1\bar{x} \quad (1.6)$$

Although regression analysis expresses the intensity of the relationship between two variables, it does not necessarily mean that there is a cause-and-effect relationship between the two variables. Making conclusions about the cause-and-effect relationship of the variables requires additional explanations, which must be completed with the analysis of the method, [8].

3.3.2.1.2. Multiple linear regression

Multiple linear regression is a method based on the mutual relationship of several quantitative variables, whereby the value of the output variable can be predicted based on several inputs. This form of regression is particularly suitable for establishing predictive models in scientific disciplines and experiments in which researchers can control the values of independent variables. A multiple linear regression model has the form, [8]:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_px_p + \varepsilon \quad (1.7)$$

Whereby:

y – the value to be predicted (dependent variable) in the i iteration,

x_i – the value by which to predict (the independent variable) in the i iteration,

β_0, β_i – regression coefficients (regression parameters),

ε – random error (residuals), p – total number of variables.

In matrix form, these equations are represented by the expression:

$$Y = X \beta + \varepsilon \tag{1.8}$$

$n \times 1$ $n \times p$ $n \times p$ $n \times 1$

Whereby:

$$y = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ \dots \\ y_n \end{bmatrix} \quad X = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1,p} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2,p} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ x_{n1} & x_{n2} & \dots & x_{n,p} \end{bmatrix} \quad \beta = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_0 \\ \beta_1 \\ \dots \\ \beta_p \end{bmatrix} \quad \varepsilon = \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \dots \\ \varepsilon_n \end{bmatrix}$$

(1.9)
(1.10)
(1.11)
(1.12)

For certain variables to be considered independent of x in the process of multiple linear regression, certain conditions need to be met. First, there must be a logical justification, that is, a realistic assumption that the independent variable has an influence on the dependent variable. Second, the measure of linear dependence that exists between the independent variables and the dependent variable should be determined. And thirdly, for the purposes of forming the model, it is necessary to choose a group of independent variables so that there is no linear dependence among them or so that it is relatively small, [9].

The relationship or correlation between two variables can have values ranging from -1 to 1. A zero-correlation coefficient value indicates no linear relationship, while an absolute value equal to unity represents a perfect correlation. The sign of the value represents the orientation of the correlation, with negative values indicating inverse and positive values indicating direct correlation. The strength of the correlation increases with the increase in the absolute value of the correlation coefficient [10]. For the purposes of quantifying linear dependence among data with a normal distribution, Pearson's [11] is used, and among data that do not have a normal distribution, Spearman's [12] and Kendall's [13] correlation coefficient is used. Depending on the value of the coefficients, the correlation can be characterized as weak or negligible, moderate, strong, very strong and perfect [10]. Depending on the author and the scientific field, the value limits of the correlation categories may vary to a certain extent. However, regardless of the approach, absolute values of the coefficient less than 0.2 represent a negligible and those greater than 0.2 a non-negligible linear relationship.

Independent variables that have a relatively strong correlation with the dependent variable largely determine its value. In addition, multiple linear regression predictive models often include variables that have a relatively small linear relationship with the dependent variable. At the same time, each of the independent variables "introduces" part of the influence on the dependent variable into the model. The presence of multiple input variables with linear dependence can negatively affect the simplicity and accuracy of the model. On the one hand, a larger number of variables can complete the model, on the other hand, variables exhibiting multicollinearity negatively affect the quantification of regression coefficients β . In this way, multicollinearity negatively affects the ability to determine the influence of individual variables on the prediction result and reduces the overall predictive power of the model. To prevent or reduce the negative impact of multicollinearity, it is necessary to select a suitable group of input (independent) parameters before forming the model. The procedure of selecting input parameters

can be carried out by determining the correlation coefficient among all potential variables (Pearson's or Spearman's correlation coefficient, depending on the type of data distribution), and selecting those that are not in mutual (medium or strong) correlation. Also, the procedure of selecting independent variables can be carried out by determining the VIF value, i.e., values of the variance inflation factor [14]. The acceptable value of the variance inflation factor that defines the limit of multicollinearity of the parameters varies depending on the literature and ranges from 4 [15] to 10 [16]. Regardless of the literature, smaller VIF values mean less influence or complete absence of multicollinearity.

Therefore, after adequate preparation, the selected data can be included in the multiple linear regression model. Unlike simple linear regression, whose model function is a line, the multiple linear regression model function is a plane (in the case of a function with two independent variables) or a hyperplane [17] (in the case of more than two independent variables), where each point of the plane corresponds to values of y for given values of the independent variables x . Assuming that the value of the random error ε in the model is equal to zero, analogous to simple linear regression, the function of the multiple linear regression model would have the form [9]:

$$\hat{y} = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + \dots + b_px_p \tag{1.13}$$

Whereby:

$\hat{y}$ – the estimated value of the dependent variable (y),

$b_0, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_p$ – estimated values of regression coefficients $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_p$

For the case when the values of β are known in the regression model, it is possible to determine the mean value of y for all values of independent variables x . Since in practice the values of the regression coefficients are unknown, to create a suitable model that describes the phenomenon, it is necessary to estimate them based on the observed data sample. Estimated values of regression coefficients b are determined by the method of least squares according to (equation 1.4).

The difference between the actual and predicted values of the dependent variable represents the error (e).

$$y_i - \hat{y}_i = e_i \tag{1.15}$$

In other words, in vector form:

$$e = Y - X_b \tag{1.16}$$

Whereby:

$$e = \begin{bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \\ \dots \\ e_n \end{bmatrix} \tag{1.17}$$

Both for simple linear regression models and for multiple linear regression models, it is necessary to additionally explain the cause-and-effect relationship that exists between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

Advanced techniques, such as multiple regression, predict the relationship between multiple variables – for example, is there a relationship between income, education and where one wants to live? Adding more variables greatly increases the complexity of the forecast. There are several types of multiple regression techniques, including standard, hierarchical, complex, and stepwise, each with its own application.

At this point it is important to understand what we are trying to predict (the dependent or predicted variable) and the data we are using to make the prediction (the independent or predictor variable). In our example, we want to predict the place where one wants to live (predictor variable) given income and education (both predictor variables).

Standard multiple regression considers all predictor variables at the same time.

E.g.:

- 1) what is the relationship between income and education (predictors) and neighborhood choice (predictors)?
- 2) to what extent do each of the individual predictors contribute to that relationship?

Stepwise multiple regression answers a very different question. A stepwise regression algorithm will analyze which predictors are most used to predict neighborhood choice – meaning that the stepwise model estimates the order of importance of the predictor variables and then selects the relevant subset. This type of regression problem uses "steps" to develop the regression equation. Given this type of regression, not all predictors may even appear in the final regression equation.

Hierarchical regression, as in steps, is a sequential process, but the predictor variables are entered into the model in a predefined order, that is, the algorithm does not contain a built-in set of equations to determine the order of predictor entry. This is most often used when the individual creating the regression equation has expert knowledge in this area, [8].

3.3.3. NCSS Statistical Software

A data set that has gone through the cleaning and transformation process can be imported into NCSS 2023 software for analysis.

NCSS is an interactive data analysis tool that enables users to effectively explore, analyze and visualize their data. Developed with a focus on facilitating the data analysis process, it provides a variety of options for cleaning, transforming, and interpreting data. This software offers an interactive environment that allows users to easily extract key information from their data and create visually appealing reports. NCSS excels in its ability to integrate disparate data sources and turn them into coherent analyses, thereby facilitating informed business decisions,[18].

3.4. Data visualization and sharing

After transformation and purification, the data looks like the image below, after that it needs to be processed.

Photo1. Transformed data.

StationName	OK_parts	Undefined	NOK_parts	Year
Prefixing	34783	0	0	2020
Rework station	0	0	1182	2020
Quality Gate	32692	14	13	2020
Packaging	31821	0	0	2020
Prefixing	163017	0	0	2021
Edge Wrapping	107542	0	0	2021
Rework station	0	0	3824	2021
Quality Gate	158115	10	12	2021
Packaging	157374	0	0	2021
Edge Wrapping	165058	0	0	2022
Rework station	0	0	3295	2022
Packaging	162081	0	0	2022
Prefixing	166305	1	0	2022
Quality Gate	162425	0	4	2022
Packaging	116079	0	0	2023
Edge Wrapping	121050	0	0	2023
Rework station	0	0	5377	2023
Quality Gate	116605	8	10	2023
Prefixing	122563	2	0	2023

Data visualization in NCSS software provides powerful tools for presenting information in a way that is easy to understand and interpret. This aspect of NCSS allows users to build rich visual representations of their data and facilitate the sharing of that information with others. NCSS offers a wide range of graphical displays such as graphs, scatter plots, histograms, and many others. These graphical displays allow users to quickly identify patterns, trends, and anomalies in the data. It also enables the creation of interactive visualizations that allow users to explore the data more deeply. For example, interactive controls such as filters and buttons can be added to allow users to customize the visualization according to their needs.

NCSS allows users to easily share their visualizations with their colleagues or the public. Reports and visualizations can be exported in different formats such as PDF, Excel, or shared directly via web platforms, [18].

Using the mentioned functionalities of the NCSS software, one can improve the data analysis process, facilitate the communication of the results, and contribute to a better understanding of the research data.

4. DISCUSSION OF THE ANALYSIS RESULT

When creating the results, it is necessary to import the data into the NCSS software. After that, the data should be matched with its types. The advantage of this software is that it recognizes the data type. After importing the data, it is necessary to filter it, because the data is for three different years and five different workstations.

4.1. Analysis of production quality

In this subchapter, the data on the manufactured parts at each workstation of the G463MF production line is analyzed. It was necessary to create new variables and calculate them based on the data. The following variables are created:

- "OK_Rate" is created for the ok rate.
- "Undefined_Rate" is created for the undefined rate.
- "Scrap_Rate" variable is created for the scrap rate.

4.2. Analysis of employee efficiency

Employee efficiency analysis plays a key role in evaluating the productivity and performance of an organization. In this subsection, it is shown how NCSS (NCSA Statistical Software) was used to conduct an analysis of the efficiency of employees at the workstations of the G463MF line. This process involves creating a new variable called "EmployeeEfficiencyRate" and exploring it further.

One of the key steps in analyzing employee efficiency was the creation of a new variable named "EmployeeEfficiencyRate". This variable represents a measure of the efficiency of each employee at the workstation and allows us to quantify their performance based on the available data.

To create the "EmployeeEfficiencyRate," we used NCSS to apply an appropriate formula that considers various factors relevant to efficiency, including the good parts rate, the undefined parts rate, and the scrapped parts rate. This formula provided a clear and objective measure of efficiency for each employee.

$$\text{EmployeeEfficiencyRate} = (\text{OK_Rate} / (\text{OK_Rate} + \text{Undefined_Rate} + \text{Scrap_Rate})) * 100 \quad (1.18)$$

4.3. Analysis of the relationship between employee efficiency and production quality

An analysis of the relationship between employee efficiency and production quality was conducted using multiple statistical regression. Our dependent variable will be "ScrapRate" which measures the quality of production. We will use "EmployeeEfficiencyRate" and "Year" as independent variables.

Through this analysis, it was investigated how employee efficiency and age can affect the rate of scrap parts in the production process. Analyzing these factors together, it was necessary to understand how changes in the efficiency of employees and time can contribute to the improvement or deterioration of production quality. The results of this analysis provided useful insights into the factors that are key to managing and improving production quality in the organization.

The first step is to set the correct hypotheses:

- Null hypothesis (H0): Employee efficiency and age do not have a statistically significant effect on the rate of scrap parts (Scrap Rate).
- Alternative hypotheses (H1):
 - Employee efficiency has a statistically significant impact on the scrap rate ("Scrap Rate"). Specifically, greater employee efficiency will result in a lower rate of scrap parts.
 - The year has a statistically significant influence on the rate of scrap parts ("Scrap Rate"). It can be assumed that the quality of production may improve or deteriorate over the years due to changes in processes or technology.

The results of the multiple linear regression analysis indicate significant relationships between the independent variables (Employee Efficiency and Year) and the dependent variable (Scrap Parts Rate) in our research. We can see that in the next picture:

Regression Coefficient T-Tests

Independent Variable	Regression Coefficient b(i)	Standard Error Sb(i)	Standardized Coefficient	T-Test of H0: $\beta(i) = 0$		
				T-Statistic	P-Value	Reject H0 at $\alpha = 0.05?$
Intercept	-1929.101	111.4787	0.0000	-17.305	0.0000	Yes
EmployeeEfficiencyRate	-0.06094073	0.01164205	-0.2086	-5.235	0.0000	Yes
Year	0.958375	0.05492767	0.6952	17.448	0.0000	Yes

Photo 2. T-tests of regression coefficients

First, the regression coefficient for Employee Efficiency ("EmployeeEfficiencyRate") is statistically significant with a value of -0.06094073. This negative coefficient indicates that there is an inverse relationship between employee efficiency and scrap rate. In other words, as employee efficiency increases, the scrap rate is expected to decrease. This relationship is statistically significant given the low p-value of 0.000. Therefore, the hypothesis H1 is confirmed, that the efficiency of employees has a statistically significant influence on the rate of scrap parts.

Second, Year also shows a statistically significant effect on scrap rate, with a regression coefficient of 0.958375. The positive sign of this coefficient indicates that the rate of scrap parts increases over the years, which suggests the existence of weather or seasonal factors that affect the quality of production. Therefore, the hypothesis H1 that year has a statistically significant effect on the rate of scrap parts is confirmed.

It is important to note that all three tests rejected the null hypothesis ($H_0: \beta(i) = 0$) at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, indicating that all regression coefficients are statistically significant.

Therefore, our results support the conclusion that employee efficiency and time (years) have a significant impact on production quality, i.e., the rate of scrap parts. This has practical implications for improving manufacturing processes and reducing scrap rates in the future, particularly focusing on improving worker efficiency and addressing seasonal variations.

The picture below shows the efficiency of the employees at the "Prefixing" station in the last three production months, we got the data from the company's Reporting application. The first part shows the efficiency of employees per operator. The number of parts well done, the number of parts poorly done, as well as the efficiency rate. The second part shows the report sorted by employee and part number, the amount of good and poorly produced parts is shown.

Photo 3. Employee efficiency report

The following figure shows the efficiency of the employees at the "Edge wrapping" station in the last three production months, the data is grouped as in the previous station. Therefore, there is data on the efficiency of employees by the number of good and bad parts, as well as their efficiency rate. In the second part, there is the number of parts per operator and the part number in relation to the product code.

Photo 4. Edge Wrapping employee efficiency report

To improve the production process, as well as the efficiency of the employees, based on these results, we decided to propose concrete measures to the company. Therefore, it implies the introduction of new stations for quality control after the Prefixing station, as well as the addition of the option to specify the

specific reason for rework on Quality Gate when the Rework option is selected, and that the part can be reworked several times, if necessary. To adequately monitor the efficiency of employees and improve it, it is necessary to add reports to the Reporting application that show the number of times which operator returned a part to the Rework station and the reason for rework. Based on that, the company can assess what are the most common reasons for reworking, it can also work on operator training, so that they do not make the same mistakes in the future but produce good parts and have a lower percentage of reworking, and therefore improve the quality of production.

The company adopted the proposed measures and implemented the part related to the Rework station, already on three production lines. He intends to implement the measure to introduce a new quality control station after the Prefixing station in the future.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis and the application of statistical regression to a data set that includes a multi-year period of production in the company, we can safely conclude that the efficiency of employees has a significant impact on the quality of production in the automotive industry.

Our analysis clearly shows that there is a negative relationship between employee efficiency and attrition rate. This means that when employees are more efficient, the rate of scrapping decreases. This was statistically confirmed with low p-values and significant regression coefficients. We also identified that age plays a role in changes in production quality over time. There is a tendency for the rate of scrapping to increase over several years, indicating the need to monitor and respond to seasonal or weather factors that may affect quality. Based on the obtained results, the company adopted the proposed measures and implemented the part related to the Rework station, already on three lines in production, as already stated in the paper, also the measure for the introduction of a new quality control station after the Prefixing station intends to implement in the future.

Based on these results, companies in the automotive industry can make practical decisions. Focusing on training and improving employee efficiency can directly contribute to reducing scrap rates and increasing product quality. Also, monitoring changes over the years and taking corrective measures can help maintain a stable level of production quality.

Although we obtained significant results, this research can be the basis for further research. A deeper understanding of the causes of changes in production quality over time can enable the development of specific strategies for process improvement.

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THE QUANTIFICATION OF CARBIDES IN HEAT-RESISTANT CAST STEEL HP40 NB ALLOY

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Abstract: This paper describes the application of the software for the quantification of carbides in heat-resistant cast steel HP40 Nb alloy, produced in the form of a centrifugally cast tube, which failed after 11.4 years in service was performed. The microstructure of alloy was examined using a scanning electron microscope SEM, while the phases observed were analysed using an energy dispersive x-ray analyser system (EDS). Carbide quantification was carried out in the JMicroVision program. In the work, it was found that the HP40 Nb alloy after 11.4 years in service consists of an average of 81.28% primary carbides M_7C_3 and 18.72% Nb carbides.

Key words: centrifugal cast alloy HP40 Nb, quantification of carbides, microstructure, JMicroVision

1. INTRODUCTION

In ethylene pyrolysis furnaces, the production process is based on the movement of a mixture of gases and steam under pressure through pipe snakes heated by burners. Pipe snakes are exposed to harsh working conditions that include pressure, high temperatures (up to 1150°C), sudden start and stop of the production process, etc. Due to the mentioned operating conditions in furnaces, it is necessary to use tubes that have a high resistance to creep. Recently, tubes of centrifugally cast heat resistant steel alloy HP40 Nb have been used. During exploitation, despite the good resistance of this alloy, there is a significant drop in the mechanical properties of the tubes. Reduction of mechanical properties is a consequence of phase transformations of the alloy due to exposure to high temperatures and numerous damage mechanisms (thermal fatigue, overheating, oxidation, carburization, dechromization, etc.) [1]. It is known that the largest number of alloying elements in steel react chemically with carbon forming interstitial phases or complex structures that we call carbides. In the as cast condition, the microstructure of the HP40 Nb alloy consists of an austenitic matrix and a skeletal-shaped primary eutectic carbides network. There are two types of morphologies for interdendritic eutectic-like primary carbides of the MC type, and of the $M_{23}C_6$ or/and M_7C_3 types [2-6]. The formation of special carbides of the MC type (such as NbC, VC, etc.) are formed in the solidification process and play a very important role in the HP40 Nb alloy for catalytic tubes, because their presence reduces the grain and improves the mechanical properties of the material [7]. In HP40 Nb at an elevated temperature, the transformation of M_7C_3 type carbides into $M_{23}C_6$ type carbides begins or continues along the dendrite boundaries. Secondary carbides of the $M_{23}C_6$ type are deposited and grow at temperatures of 590-650°C. Furthermore, deposited carbides have a favorable effect on the mechanical properties of alloy, representing a barrier to the movement of dislocations. By increasing the heating temperature of the alloy from 650 to 970°C, carbides start to coarsen [4, 8-14].

Depending on the temperature and duration of exposure of cast steel alloys to high temperatures, the transformation of NbC carbide into the known G-phase may occur. The transformation takes place at temperatures of 700-990°C, where it is most pronounced in the temperature range of 900-990°C [15], [16]. The G-phase is a brittle phase and has an adverse effect on the mechanical properties of the alloy. The boundary between this phase and the austenite base is believed to be where creep crack nucleation occurs [16]. MC carbides containing Ti resist the transformation of MC carbide into the G-phase [2, 17].

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The morphology and amount of carbides found in the microstructure of the alloy affect the mechanical properties of the alloy. Considering that due to the exposure of HP40 Nb alloy tubes to elevated temperatures, phase transformations occur. It is of great importance to observe which transformations occur. For carbide quantification, the most commonly used program is the JMicroVision software. JMicroVision has been designed to describe, measure, quantify and classify components of all kinds of images. This software contains tools with different degrees of automation to manage complex and varied images. Like a microscope, it allows dynamic observation of a specimen with the possibility of combining various focus or modes of lighting. This software has been specially developed for the analysis of high definition images of thin rock sections, but it can easily be used in other fields, like for counting carbides or counting precipitates in the images. In the Elvira O'Norbe's work [18] the characteristics, precipitates, and dislocations of steel alloy T91 in the received state and after thermomechanical treating are compared. Size distribution and number density of the different families of precipitates found in the alloy were measured using SEM and TEM images employing JMicroVision software. In a dissertation by Zhy [19] the volume fraction of ferrite in alloys Fe-1.5Mn-1Si0.3C and Fe-3Mn-1Si-0.3C was analyzed using image analysis software JMicroVision. Zhu used this software to determine the quantity of martensite and ferrite on an image taken on an SEM microscope. Krajšnik et al. [20] used JMicroVision software in order to quantify the microcracks in lamellar pearlite colonies in medium carbon steel C45E. In Nativ-Roth's work [21] is described a method for measuring the average pore size and the determination of the porosity of porous silicon (PSi) layers. The dimensions of the pores, as appear in the SEM images, were determined by using the JMicroVision program version 1.2.7. The JMicroVision software was also used in the work where was investigated the influence of two different shielding gases for welding on duplex stainless steel microstructure [22]. For that purpose, the ferrite content measurement of the BM and WM was done by using JMicroVision 1.2.7 software. In addition to the above, JMicroVision software has also been used in petrography and in dentistry [23]. In De Luca's work [24] they used JmicroVision software to count percentage of aggregate, binder and macroporosity in samples of mortars and plasters. Jensen et al. [25], Fontana et al. [26], Brigaud et al. [27] have used this software to determine the textural characteristics of different samples of rocks.

Considering the facts given about the carbides, phase transformation and their influence on the mechanical properties of the alloy [28] and based on the wide application of the JMicroVision program for content quantification, in this work the percentage of carbides in the alloy HP40 Nb after 11.4 years in service using JmicroVision program was examined.

1.1. Material

The materials used in this study were a centrifugal cast austenitic HP40 Nb grade alloy. The sections of the tube were taken out of the service after 100 000 h (the failed tube). All samples were cut from HP40 Nb radiant tube in an ethylene cracking unit after service. The exact locations where the sections were cut on the reformer columns in the respective plants were unknown precisely. The tube segments with 350 mm in length, were cut from the furnace regions which have been in exploitation for 11.4 years. Operating condition of the tubes was 1143 K (870°C) under the maximum internal pressure of 2.5 bars (250 kPa).

The chemical composition of the service reformer tube was analysed through standard analytical spectrometry method, using the Optical Energy Spectrometer (OES) type I Spark 8860, Thermo Scientific™, USA.

Metallographic specimens were prepared in accordance with standard metallographic preparation technique: grinding (with SiC papers, from 180 to 2400), polishing (diamond suspensions with 6, 3, 1 and 1/4 µm particle size) and etched with a solution of 15 ml HCl, 10 ml Glycerol and 5 ml HNO₃.

The microstructure was examined using scanning electron microscope JOEL JSM 6460 LV. The phases observed were analysed using an energy dispersive x-ray analyser system (EDS) INCA Oxford Instruments in conjunction with a SEM. Fractography was performed on the fracture surface of failed specimens.

Carbide quantification was performed using JmicroVision version 1.3.4 software.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1. Chemical composition

The chemical composition of the investigated alloy was consisted of: 0.45%C; 0.97%Mn; 1.36%Si; 0.045%P; 32.21%Ni; 26.22%Cr, 1.5%Nb and Fe balance (mass %).

2.2. Microstructural analysis

The microstructures of the ex-service material were shown in Fig.1a-c. The precipitation of carbides can be identified to be of two types as revealed in the SEM micrographs (Figure 1a). Light grey ones are more continuous and blockier, while dark grey ones are present mostly in the intra-dendritic locations as confirmed by SEM-EDX studies (Table 1). The microstructure consists of an austenitic matrix (Spec 7) and a continuous network of primary eutectic carbides of two types: one rich in Nb (bright particles in Figure 1b, Spec 3, 4, 5) and one rich in Cr (dark particles in Figure 1b, Spec 2, 6). These carbides are NbC and complex M_7C_3 (M= Cr, Ni, Fe) type, respectively.

Figure 1 – SEM and EDS analysis: a) SEM micrograph from cross section of the failed tube (11.4 years service) close to the inner surface, b) positions of EDS analysis (dark and light phases), c) corresponding EDS spectrum 5 [28]

Table 1 - Chemical composition (mass. %) of participate phases in HP40 Nb alloy, corresponding to Figure 1b [28]

	C	Si	Cr	Mn	Fe	Ni	Nb
Spectrum 2	31.87		41.24		15.20	11.68	
Spectrum 3	25.27	12.11	22.37		3.90	23.14	13.21
Spectrum 4	21.64	14.65	7.13		10.08	33.49	13.00
Spectrum 5	22.31	12.96	12.77		12.86	29.06	10.04
Spectrum 6	19.79	1.93	28.83	1.03	27.35	21.07	
Spectrum 7	14.82	2.06	19.13	1.17	34.63	28.19	

2.3. Quantification of carbides

The carbide quantification was done in JMicroVision program. After starting the program, it is necessary to insert the micrograph of the sample on which we want to perform quantification. Images of the microstructure obtained using SEM microscopy were used for carbide quantification in this program. Figure 2 shows an example of the application of the JMicroVision on a sample treated at 1050°C for 480 minutes. After inserting the micrograph, in the drop-down menu on the left side of the middle of the window the Point counting tool is chosen. In the small window that appears at the bottom left of the window, there is Class Editor button where we make different classes of phases and chose the color that will mark them (red dot - primary Cr_{23}C_6 carbide, yellow dot - NbC carbide, dark blue dot – Cr_7C_3 carbide, green dot - secondary Cr_{23}C_6 carbide). After defining the phases, it is necessary to start the Start button which randomly moves the pointer to 250 different points on the micrograph, and we determine which phase the cursor stopped at, and the program marks it with different colors dots. After the "pointing" is completed, the Data Viewer tool is launched, in which the table value of all phases and Pie Chart phases are obtained. The process is repeated five times on different fields of view on the same sample to obtain the average value of the proportion of carbide in the sample. Table 1 shows the percentage compositions of the carbides from all the repeated counting, and the average values.

Figure 2 – Application of the JMicroVision program for the first counting of carbides

Table 2 – The percentage of carbides in the microstructure of the alloy

	Primary carbide NbC (%)	Primary carbide M ₇ C ₃ (%)
initial state, 1. counting	17.2	82.8
initial state, 2. counting	20.0	80.0
initial state, 3. counting	18.8	81.2
initial state, 4. counting	20.8	79.2
initial state, 5. counting	16.8	83.2
initial state, average value	18.72	81.28
initial state, standard deviation value	1.73	1.73

It can be seen from the results obtained applying JmicroVision program (Table 2) that the values for the content of primary carbides M₇C₃ is in range from 83.2% to 79.2%, for NbC carbides values is in range from 20.8% to 16.8%. Furthermore, during sample examination it was determined that there are no secondary and other carbide types.

3. CONCLUSION

In this study, the microalloyed HP40 Nb heat-resistant stainless steel tube, which failed after 11.4 years in service was investigated. The percentage of carbide in alloy was determined using the JMicroVision program. Based on the results, it can be concluded that the percentage of carbides in the tested alloy was successfully obtained by applying the JMicroVision program and that the carbides are present in accordance with the results obtained through EDS analysis.

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INDUSTRIAL ROBOT CONTROL IN EDUCATION USING ONLINE AND OFFLINE METHOD

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Abstract: This paper describes two methods of industrial robot control in education. In high school institute "Polytechnic" - school for new technologies an exercise was held about machine tending and control of flexible cell. During the class present students had a chance to control the robot SCORBOT ER-4 with the control device with presence of the teacher. Carried movements were transferred to the control software for the used model called SCORBASE. After finishing the exercise robot and flexible cell are activated. In academy of applied technical studies an exercise was held where students make work space for robot that imitates material cutting and following the contour of the given work piece. Program allows students to control the robot via virtual work space and make simulation for robot movement. If no errors are present in the simulation students generate the program code for robot movement.

Key words: Robot, Programming, Online, Offline, Education,

1. INTRODUCTION

Robots are effectively used in industry to improve and increase production. At the same time, interest in using robots in education has increased over the past few years. The biggest application of robots in education is in high schools and colleges for subjects such as engineering (mechanical, electrical), programming and mathematics, also robots are also slowly being introduced in kindergartens and elementary schools. Engineering schools and universities require their students to have knowledge of integrated systems. Automation and mechatronics combine different sciences such as mechanical engineering, electrical engineering and computer science. A way to encourage students to acquire knowledge in different sciences is to present interesting projects made by students from different schools and universities.

The online method for robot control is based on guiding the robot to the desired locations and positions using devices connected to the controller and saving the positions, while offline method represents creating a virtual environment using CAD softwares for desired robot model or using other programming languages [1].

2. ONLINE CONTROL METHOD USING TEACH PENDANT AND SCORBASE

SCORBASE is a program written to control robots, peripherals and equipment to communicate with external input/output devices in real-time with a support of on-screen status display of eight digital inputs, eight digital outputs, four analogue inputs and four analogue outputs.

Defining the positions of the robot is done through two modes, JOINT mode, through the movement of the joints and the Cartesian mode using coordinate system XYZ through the movement of the center of the gripper.

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Defining the position over the joints is done using five angular values that represent the angle of rotation for each joint. These joints are: base, shoulder, elbow, gripper tilt, gripper rotation. Defining the position through the Cartesian coordinate system is done through two parameters. The first parameter is the distance between the center point of the tool and the coordinate system of the robot located in the base of the robot itself. The second parameter is the angular value of the tilt and rotation of the gripper [2].

Figure 1 – Joints and XYZ movement keys

Table 1 – Key description

Key	Joints	XYZ
1/Q	Base	Tool Center Point movement via X axis
2/W	Shoulder	Tool Center Point movement via Y axis
3/E	Elbow	Tool Center Point movement via Z axis
4/R	Gripper tilt	Axis movement for gripper tilt
5/T	Gripper rotation	Gripper rotation
6/Y	Open/close gripper	-
7/U	Mobile axis movement	-
8/I	Mobile axis movement	-
	Fully closed gripper	
	Fully opened gripper	

A SCORBASE program holds a series of instructions written by the user to control the robot, peripheral equipment, and communicate with input/output devices. Instructions used to control the robot are: Axis control and Program Flow [3].

Axis control is a set of commands that operate on robot axis and gripper. The commands that represent axis control are:

- OpenGripper (OG) - Full opening of the gripper
- CloseGripper (CG) - Complete gripper closure
- GoLinearToPosition#_Speed (GL) - Move the center point of the tool to the given position by the path of a straight line
- GoCircularToPosition#_Speed (GC) - Movement of the tool center point to the given position along the path of a circular arc.

Program flow is a set of commands that refer to the sequential order which program executes instructions. The commands that represent Program flow are:

- Wait (WT) – Delays the operation of the program for a time expressed in tens of seconds.
- Set Variable to Computation (SV) – The value of the variable is set. A name and a numerical value are added to the variable. An example of using this command is to check how many parts have been processed on machines. A counter is set that increases by 1 after each removal of the processed part from the machine.
- If Jump to (IF) – A conditional command that can change the flow of a program depending on the value of a variable. If the condition is positive (true), the flow of the program goes to the execution of the commands specified for the condition and which are in the program. If the condition is negative (false), the command continues the program flow to the first next line.
- Set Subroutine (SS), Return from Subroutine (RT) and Call Subroutine (CS)
- Print to Screen & Log (PS) – A command that displays messages and variable values on the screen. In order to display the value of the variable, it is necessary to put in the name: VARX = 'X', where 'X' is the value of the variable.

Teach Pendant is a device for operation and control of the robot that is connected to the control unit, otherwise this device is called a guidance device and is used when controlling the robot via online mode. Memory space in the robot controller is reserved for defining positions, which means realizing the position record that is defined by points. Number of points can range from 1-100.

Figure 2 – Teach Pendant

The position is recorded depending on the selected group (A or B). Everything recorded in group G will be transferred to group A via manual programmer. Group A represents joint movement, group B represents mobile axis movement and group G represents gripper. The RECORD POSITION key is used to save current robot position.

Position recording principle:

- Coordinate system selection via the JOINTS/XYZ/TOOL key
- Guiding the robot to the desired position
- Using RECORD key for position saving
- Entering a number from 1 to 100 and which represents the point.

Figure 3 – Position recording

To record a new position it is required to move the robot to a new position and selecting the RECORD POSITION key.

Moving the robot to the recorded position is done using the MOVE/MOVE L key and it's used to move the axes to the desired position. MOVE L applies only to axes robot (group A) and is not used when the mobile axis is on (group B).

3. OFFLINE CONTROL METHOD USING ROBOTSTUDIO

Robotstudio is a program for offline programming and simulation of ABB robots. Robotstudio allows users to build and test a complete robot installation for a specific task designed in a virtual 3D environment without visiting or disturbing the robotic production line. Robotstudio also uses an embedded virtual controller that is a copy of the real program used in robotic manufacturing. The experiment goal is to generate a path for robot tool tip to follow the given contour so the robot can mimic material cutting operations. The robot is placed in the station along with the tool, controller layout, work table and work piece [4], [5].

Figure 4 – Robot station

The coordinate system of the work piece is added to the lower left edge by selecting points shown on figure 5. The first point indicates the location of the X axis, second point shows the direction of the X axis and third point indicates Y axis location and its direction.

Figure 5 – Setting work piece coordinate system

To generate a path it is required to place the targets on the work piece. Targets are points that make up the path which is later translated into the program code. Target placement is shown on figure 6.

Figure 6 – Target placement

Each target becomes like new coordinate system and based on the direction of that coordinate system the tool position is set. The Z axis on the targets is facing upwards, while tool tip Z axis is facing downwards (figure 4), which means the position of the tool tip on each target will be upwards, which makes physically impossible for robot to reach those positions. The solution is to rotate all tool positions that will make the robot movement possible. That position is when tool Z axis is facing downwards and the attachment of the tool is facing the robot.

Figure 7 – Tool position

After rotating the tool positions point 1 will be copied and offset by 30 mm above the work piece so the tool can approach and exit the work piece without causing the collision. To generate the program code it is necessary to synchronize the overall workstation with the targets and the tool path.

4. CONCLUSION

The advantage of online robot control is that students can control the robot in real time through the training device and peripherals. Real-time control of the robot through the training device can improve precision and make logical decisions for the best possible control of the robot and the cell. The online method is more recommended because students can directly see the position of the robot up close to prevent collision with machines and peripherals. During the exercise, the students were supervised by the teacher.

At the end of the exercise of taking and putting away materials in the higher education institution, the students were introduced to the Robot Studio software package. Students were able, after the exercise, to create a robot workspace for material cutting and use gained knowledge and experience to create the robot workspace for material manipulation with the help of the teacher. The advantage of doing the exercise is that the students get to know the software directly, which enables the design of certain objects within the program itself.

The disadvantage of the performed exercises is that in the high school institution there is no display of the simulation of the movement of the robot and the control of the peripherals, while in the higher education institution, there is no direct contact with the robot when creating the simulation for material cutting. The most ideal solution is for high school students to get a software for robot simulation, and for the Robotstudio to get its own flexible cell through which students can program the robot using both methods (online and offline) [6], [7].

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EDUCATION FOR INDUSTRY 5.0

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Abstract: Industry 5.0 builds on Industry 4.0 by integrating human cooperation with advanced technologies. It emphasizes the importance of human-machine interaction and collaboration in industrial manufacturing and processes. Industry 5.0 makes an optimal balance between automation and human labor, using technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, robots, the Internet of Things, Big Data Analytics and digitalization; to improve productivity and efficiency, while ensuring the well-being of the working professionals and society in general. Many modifications caused by industrial revolutions have transformed job profiles over time, causing changes in the procedures of obtaining qualifications and professions within the workforce. For the subsequent Industry 5.0, educational institutions should offer innovative study programs and courses that include various methods of teaching for learners who want to be qualified and up-skilled. It is necessary to cooperate with relevant partners from the engineering domain and build the appropriate competencies of students and learners as well as teachers.

Key words: education, Industry 5.0, teaching, training, digitalization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Contemporary education is striving to answer challenges and demands in accordance to Industry 4.0. It should help students to enhance their competence and improve their employability for the present as well as for future jobs, in fast changing and evolving work environment. Learning the latest tools and technologies is expected to fill in the gap between industry requirements and the teaching offered by academic institutions. The education system should respond quickly and adapt to the upcoming complex and extensive demands of the economy and society. Although one might say that the only real challenge is funding, smart education system, smart study programs with specific properties and specializations are imperative now and will be in the future.

In [1] a proposal was given to describe the concept of Industry 5.0 as a new industrial strategy that puts a person in center of it; a strategy is supported by digital technologies to make more efficient and effective decisions in a way that corresponds to the protection of the environment and society; it enables companies to achieve the higher level of resilience and to react better in situations of negative influences from the environment. Industry 5.0 is complementing the Industry 4.0 while contributing to three out of top six priorities of the European Commission (EC) plan for 2019-2024 [2, 3]: "An economy that works for people", "European Green Deal" and "Europe fit for the digital age". European industry is a key driver in the economic and societal transitions that Europeans are currently experiencing. In order to bring prosperity, industry must adopt the digital and green transitions [2].

The making of Industry 5.0 requires the response and collaboration of several stakeholders: state authorities and all connected organizations and subjects, including education institutions. All should take part in development of technologies, as well as of training for their application. The main goals of education would be achieved through a multidisciplinary approach and cooperation between government, companies, educational and scientific institutions. When designing a new course curricula or proposal of the study program for accreditation (e.g. in vocational or professional studies), educational institutions must consider numerous factors of influence, some of which are: students' interests, relevance to the current or future job positions, requirements of potential employing companies, or related to method of teaching. One important educational goal should be for students to develop critical thinking and to focus on learning from practice and experiments.

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Innovated and to some extent reduced curricula should provide flexibility for students at basic academic and professional studies. Although it offers predominantly formal studies, higher education provides flexibility through options like: choice of elective courses, part time or full time studies, classical or work based learning or dual model of study, on-campus or distance learning, study programmes or short term training courses, and that students can change their study course according to the wishes and circumstances. It is also important to think about the future application of certain course contents from the study programme. Students can easily recognize their interests and suitable form of education, and this will increase their efficiency, which will positively affect professional competence and chances of employment. In research [4] was found out that education 4.0 is an enabler because it allows students to learn important technologies which will act as a Launch pad for industry 5.0

2. THE CONCEPT OF EDUCATION 5.0

Education 5.0 represents the latest evolution in the way learning is perceived, providing to create an immersive and holistic experience with the learner at its center [5]. Unlike traditional approach to teaching, Education 5.0 uses the power of technology, in order to personalize the learning experience and enable student's higher engagement. Artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms are used to assess students learning styles and adapt materials accordingly. Augmented and virtual reality can virtually transport students to different places, giving them an experiential and interactive tasks to solve [5]. Educational testbeds (ETs) are used as a virtual environment, where is possible to integrate digital tools for the development of teaching, however it is necessary to understand characteristics of ET [6].

A better acceptance of the large potential of Education 5.0 is still facing obstacles to overcome [7]. That education phase enables learning anywhere, anytime and makes a real-world experience a priority. By using accessible and new technologies in creating the so-called user experience, students can adopt better understanding and comprehensive knowledge of their courses. Education this way becomes more engaging, allowing learners to explore relevant topics more deeply through hands-on and guided activities (Figure 1). Education 5.0 is the future of learning and promises to provide a dynamic and intuitive educational experience that challenges both the students and their teachers. With the right tools, equipment and learning environments, it has the potential to change the teaching methods, offering exciting new ways to interact with and understand sustainable environment. [7]

Figure 1 – Education 5.0 (University Teknologi Mara, 2019) [7]

Source: <https://html.scirp.org/file/3-6307115x3.png?20230519174925928>

Because academic institutions and technologies work in parallel to transform education, the development of modern tools and techniques is also driving the better quality in education standards. Learning becomes student-connected or learner-related, focused on the learner, demonstrated by the

learner and driven by the learner [7]. The student is considered as a complete person whose values, beliefs, thoughts, knowledge and skills are seen as converged fundamentals to be nurtured and trained. The details of nurturing learners, as active agents in learning are listed in the Figure 1 [7].

Education 5.0 has following key areas for implementation to obtain maximum benefits [7]: Focused learning to become a professional, Improved and blended concept of personalized learning, Applying creative thinking for solving the problems, and Developing value based learning culture. The key pillars of Education 5.0 and their outcome are [7]: Coherent and relevant curriculum, Innovative delivery and assessment, Meaningful learning experience, and Transformative learning.

3. THE VIEW ON THE INDUSTRY 5.0

Industry 4.0 (I4.0) and Industry 5.0 (I5.0) rely on knowledge acquired in education, organized in the form of scientific research and materialized in new technologies and innovations, developed products and services [8]. There are various aspects and relationships between education and I4.0, I5.0, society and economy. Education drives the development of technological solutions, the building of new knowledge and educational profiles. I4.0 and I5.0 technologies have significant direct impact on education. It extends to [8]: changes in the organizational structure of schools and teaching programs, introduction of new technologies and knowledge in teaching, modifications in learning methodology, up to the established obligatory continuous professional education of teachers.

Industry 5.0 is a new model in manufacturing that focuses on the cooperation between man and specific automated/ autonomous machine system. The previous industry phase, i.e. Industry 4.0, benefited from technologies, such as Internet of Things - IoT, Big Data or Artificial Intelligence - AI, to create a more automated, autonomous, smart factories [9]. Industry 5.0 goes one step further and unites the creative potential of a unique human being, with the precision and capabilities of smart robots in order to achieve more sustainable economy, environmentally friendly or neutral as well as more ethical manufacturing. Industry 4.0 has tried to minimize human labor and intervention and give priority to process automation [9]. However the human being has been moved to other aspects of the production process that machines cannot perform well. This way the robots have been given more space and importance during the repetitive production processes, or in extreme working environment.

The main properties of Industry 5.0 are as follows [9]:

- Customized manufacturing: the new Industry 5.0 will promote making of products with a higher degree of customization, currently it is focused to produce huge number of various products and I 5.0 is about adapting these products to the individual needs of customers;
- Cobot Deployment: from robots to cobots (collaborative robots) for the innovative Industry 5.0, with human ingenuity and creativity in collaboration with robots as co-workers;
- Empowering people: instead of relegating man to a secondary position, in Industry 5.0 humans will leave all repetitive, monotonous, mechanical, dangerous or laborious tasks to robots;
- Speed and quality: new production lines will be faster because of new technologies, also the products will be of higher quality;
- Environmental Concern: with the use of renewable energy sources and the chain of manufacturing adapted to require less consumption of resources, reduce waste emission and produce more sustainable technologies and products.

Advantages of Industry 5.0 add new features to the manufacturing and processes including [9]:

- Cost optimization,
- Green, environmentally safe solutions,
- Personalization and creativity.

Industry 5.0 is a new development paradigm introduced by EC [10] that is possible in contemporary economic environment. It advocates fostering industrial activity that goes beyond technical and

economic goals such as productivity and efficiency. Industry 5.0 seeks to promote other purposes that are essential for the future of the society, i.e. human well-being, sustainability and resilience. [10]

Industry 4.0 is focused to minimize human intervention in manufacturing and to prioritize the automation of all processes. It relies on process digitization and the use of AI to boost productivity and efficiency [10]. In a way, the humans are made to compete with the machines, and to fall behind, being replaced in a multitude of scenarios. In Industry 5.0, this trend is reversed, namely it is about creating a balance, where machine-human interaction can provide maximum benefit and the roles of humans and machines are combine to complement and enhance each other's strengths [10]. According to this premise, technology should be at the service of humans - not the other way around - with the aim of moving towards a scenario of full machine-human collaboration. [10]

Industry 5.0 takes further and complements previous improvements that generated more efficient processes and making increasingly accurate and less uncertain decisions within Industry 4.0. The search for business models that use the least consumption and resources to achieve the greatest benefits sees Factory 5.0 as its biggest advancement to date, as man and machine work together in order to make the best business decisions for the company. None of the previous industrial transformations made environmental protection as a priority. With Industry 5.0, new technologies and corporate sensitivity are changing this trend. The sustainable policies are created, in which minimal waste production and waste management become essential processes that run through the entire organization and make it more efficient. The changes are in line with what international organizations, government legislation and consumers are increasingly demanding.

In Industry 5.0 from employees is expected to have a higher degree of emotional intelligence and master the soft skills. The workplace is adapted to the employees, so that operation tasks and unsafe tasks are performed by robots, and humans control robots making decisions. Collaborative robots should enable mass product personalization, robots would perform operations that are established and common to each product, while people perform operations that add value to the product. [1]

According to the EC, there are six fundamental technological categories, to boost Industry 5.0 [10]:

- Individualized human-machine interaction,
- Bio-inspired technologies and smart materials,
- Digital twins and simulation,
- Data transmission, storage and analysis technologies,
- Artificial Intelligence (AI),
- Technologies for energy efficiency, renewable energy sources, storage and autonomy.

This technological framework is a strategic ally for advancing towards the goals of Industry 5.0 [10]. Predictive analytics offers appropriate tool to strengthen the resilience of the company, in order to anticipate possible contingencies e.g. extreme weather or demand fluctuations. Meanwhile, cobots (collaborative robots) are sophisticated machines designed to work with operators and free them from performing more demanding, dangerous and repetitive operations and tasks. Cobots are increasingly being employed in manufacturing centers and storage facilities. The rise of cobots confirms the viability of a technology model in which machines and humans share responsibilities and work in harmony. [10]

4. DIGITALIZATION IN CONTEMPORARY INDUSTRY AND EDUCATION

Industry 5.0 and corresponding Education 5.0 are closely interconnected and mutually influenced in shaping the future of workplace, learning, teaching, and vocation. Both concepts recognize the need for a harmonious collaboration between humans and advanced technologies to drive innovation, productivity, and societal progress, with a sustainable, human-centric, environmentally focused and resilient approach. Education 5.0 has a crucial role in preparing individuals for the huge demands of Industry 5.0. It is based on equipping learners with the necessary skills, knowledge, and mindset to

thrive in a technology-driven and rapidly evolving industrial equipment and environments. Education 5.0 emphasizes personalized and learner-centered approaches, fostering critical thinking, creativity, collaboration and problem-solving skills among students. It also promotes lifelong learning and continuous skills development to adapt operators to the changing industry needs.

Transition from Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0 in the age of omnipresent digitalization, with their main properties, is presented in the Figure 2. Also the transformation of Education 4.0 into Education 5.0 is given in Figure 2. [6]

Figure 2 – By Digitalization to the Industry 5.0 and Education 5.0 [6]

Source: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-23236-7_46

Industry 5.0 influences the design and implementation of Education 5.0. It provides clear insights into the student competence level and skills that will be in high demand in the future workplace. Industry 5.0 highlights the importance of unique human skills, such as creativity, emotional intelligence and complex decision-making, which are more nurtured through Education 5.0. It informs educators about the emerging technologies and industry trends that should be integrated into the course curricula, to ensure relevance and alignment with the needs of the dynamic job market. [6]

Furthermore, Industry 5.0 and Education 5.0 hold a common focus on the important issues, like: sustainability, environmental concerns, social responsibility and ethical practices. Both mentioned concepts recognize the necessity of addressing societal challenges and promoting environmentally friendly practices in industrial processes and throughout educational systems. In general, Industry 5.0 and Education 5.0 are in full synergy, as they mutually transform and shape each other. Education 5.0 should prepare individuals for the future professional challenges and environments, driven by Industry 5.0, while Industry 5.0 provides insights and affects the design of Education 5.0, to meet the evolving needs of both various industries and society.

5. CONCLUSION

Education 5.0 refers to the next phase of education process that incorporates advanced technologies and innovative approaches to enhance learning experience. It emphasizes personalized, learner-centered education, implementing artificial intelligence, virtual reality, augmented reality and other emerging technologies, to create virtual interactive and immersive learning environments and conditions. Education 5.0 aims to foster critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and problem-solving skills among students, preparing them for the demands of the 21st century economy. The listed also promotes lifelong learning and continuous developments of skills, with a person acquiring

competence to adapt to the rapidly changing and unpredictable workforce circumstances. Moreover it recognizes the importance of interdisciplinary knowledge and encourages students to explore diverse subjects. Education 5.0 tends to transform education by utilizing technology, personalization, and a unique learner-centric approach to prepare students for the challenges and opportunities of the future.

Industry 5.0 emphasizes sustainability and social responsibility, aiming to make a more inclusive and environmentally friendly industrial ecosystems. Unlike previous industrial revolution (Industry 4.0) that is focused on automation and machine-driven processes, Industry 5.0 recognizes the human capabilities, such as creative activities, flexibility and adaptability. It aims to create adaptive work environments, where humans and machines work together, with humans taking on tasks that require complex decision-making, and emotional intelligence, while machines handle repetitive, laborious and mundane tasks. That innovative industry seeks to address societal challenges, promote ethical practices and prioritize the well-being of both workers and the environment. Industry 5.0 is a vision of future where humans' skills are important, advanced technologies and humans coexist, leading to more efficient, sustainable and socially responsible industrial processes.

Today the Industry 5.0 has important tasks in the improvement and optimization of developed Industry 4.0, using technologies currently available on the diverse market. Nevertheless, the Industry 5.0 has unique mission to make transition towards an industry that is more resilient, sustainable and human-centered. Industry 5.0 is expected to give immeasurable benefits for workers, companies, economy and sustainable development.

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IMPROVEMENT OF HYDROPOWER PLANT OPERATION BASED ON COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF QUANTITIES IN TRANSIENT REGIMES

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Abstract: Numerical simulations and mathematical models of technical systems can provide valuable insights into various characteristics and modes of operation of these. When actual object of interest is of high value or disrupting its operation is too costly, this is the case in particular. Using viable models in simulations can provide values of parameters of influence that might lead to better tuning of the mode of operation, higher efficacy of the facility or alleviate potentially harmful phenomena to occur. Paper reviews various models of Kaplan turbine operating regimes and characteristics in order to achieve better tuning of relevant parameters and provide longer availability and uninterrupted operation of the facility. Transient regimes in pipelines (e.g. in water supply systems or HPPs, etc.) are mostly harmful and very dangerous. HPPs can exhibit either normal or emergency transient regimes, and one example is waterhammer. On site measurements are combined with numerical simulations to suggest values of parameters to be tuned in order to prevent appearance of waterhammer.

Key words: Kaplan Turbine, Mathematical Models of Hydropower Plants (HPPs), Mechatronic Instrumentation and Measurements, Numerical Simulations, Transient Regimes

1. INTRODUCTION

A hydropower plant (HPP), known as a hydroelectric power plant, is a facility that generates electricity by harnessing the energy of flowing or falling water. When the water is released from the reservoir, it flows through turbines, which spin generators to produce electricity. HPPs are still in use worldwide and remain among the cleanest available renewable power sources. HPPs are the source of considerable amount of power produced worldwide although building one often requires high initial investment. HPPs with Kaplan type of turbines are numerous. Kaplan turbines are suitable for low head HPPs, where the water flow is relatively slow but has a high volume. They have adjustable blades that allow for efficient operation under varying water flow conditions. Although invented more than hundred years ago, Kaplan turbines are still in use in many of the HPPs worldwide. This is the reason why research is still focused on these [1-11].

Kaplan type of turbines are sometimes installed in systems with long open channels [3]. The hydraulic transients of Kaplan type HPP with open channel is complex [3]. Transient flow analysis in Kaplan HPPs is one of the most important issues for the prevention of undesirable pressure fluctuations in waterways [3]. To keep efficient operation of a Kaplan turbine, the wicket gates and the runner blades position should be regulated as water head changed [3]. Reverse waterhammer and rigid waterhammer are examples of the undesirable and potentially damaging transient regimes in HPPs and pipelines. In order to prevent both of these to occur (either reverse or rigid waterhammer) and to alleviate their consequences, three turbine models having the same runner diameter ($D = 9.5$ m) were tested in the laboratory conditions [1], [7], [9]. Field measurements were exploited and combined with numerical simulations.

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2. MATHEMATICAL MODELLING

Models for Kaplan turbines usually assume the runner blades always follow the optimum efficiency relationship, which is not true during transient responses [4]. This can lead to incorrect assessment of system stability. Here a dedicated software was used to determine variables of importance and parameters of the models numerically. The first model, A, is of the existing turbine with specific rotational speed $n_Q = 137$. The other two models B and C, were derived for the two revitalized turbines having $n_Q = 133$ and $n_Q = 135$ respectively [1], [6]. Field data were collected and models were simulated. Models are presented in normalized values so that they can be reused to represent other turbines.

It may be of interest also to represent the influence of the blades over flow rate or efficiency rather than only over power. In [4] these characteristics were incorporated in the turbine model for analyzing the effect of the blades dynamically and static characteristics for flow rate and efficiency were identified too. The work [4] contributes to the modelling of such turbines for dynamic analysis, since a complete representation is not provided in most modelling/ software tools. This is discussed based on the speed control response under isolated operation, showing that the model proposed in [4] can provide improved accuracy in the representation of such turbines. [4]

Based on the transient flow theory, both implicit difference method and method of characteristic are introduced in [3] to establish the mathematic model of hydraulic transient regimes calculation for Kaplan type HPP with open channel which are exhibiting unique hydraulic characteristic. In [3] the fluid transients due to load rejection is simulated to investigate the hydraulic behaviors. [3]

3. BEHAVIOUR OF KAPLAN TURBINES WHICH ARE AFFECTED BY RIGID WATERHAMMER

All three turbines have exactly the same: runner diameter D , rotational speed n , number of runner blades, Z_{RB} , guide vane blades, Z_{GV} and range of relative angle of runner blade, β . This actually means that discharge hydraulic system is basically the same for all three, however the turbines differ in values of maximal efficiency. This difference is based on modification of shape and contour of output runner blades edges. Namely, runner blades are thinner on the turbine B and C and therefore both of these reach higher installed discharge for the same runner dimensions. This is valid not just in work area but even in the so called optimum point – the point where efficiency has its maximum. Guide vanes closing law can be changed depending on the kind of transient regime that should be tested at each of the turbines. This law is the same for all three turbines tested in this paper because the purpose is to compare the turbines behavior during same closing law.

Turbine characteristics are given by the model tests propeller curves [1]:

$$\psi = \psi(\varphi, a_0, \beta), \quad H = \psi \frac{u_e^2}{2g}, \quad (1)$$

$$\mu = \mu(\varphi, a_0, \beta), \quad M_h = \rho D_e A_e u_e^2 / 4 \quad (2)$$

Table 1 – Values of the nominal point of the turbine A and its influence on β and a_0 changes in turbines B and C exploitation characteristics [1]

Characteristics	Turbine A	Turbine B	Turbine C
Q_{nom}	800 m ³ /s	800 m ³ /s	800 m ³ /s
H_{nom}	26.50 m	26.50 m	26.50 m
$a_{0, nom}$	620 mm	660 mm	680 mm
β_{nom}	14.9°	15°	15.4°

Table 1 [1] presents values at nominal point of the turbine A and changes of angle β and opening a_0 when this point was placed in exploitation characteristics` of turbine B and C.

Propeller curves` analysis is based on comparison with respect to the nominal point of the turbine A. The goal is to determine influence of the parameters at nominal point of turbine A on behavior of the two other turbines and changes of basic parameters which are important for guide vanes` and runners` closing laws necessary for testing transient regimes: relative angle of runner blade, β , and guide vane opening, a_0 . Propeller curves are supplied in part 6 of this paper.

4. BEHAVIOUR OF KAPLAN TURBINES WHICH ARE AFFECTED BY REVERSE WATERHAMMER

It is recommended to analyze the most non satisfactory regime contented in turbine quick closure and stoppage from 100% of maximal input at $H_n = 29.0$ m for the adequate analysis of axial hydraulic force. Total axial force value must be less than the critical value which is defined by using several criterions. If it isn't the case, the risk of raising up the turbine rotor is increased and this could be very harmful. Results shown in the Table 2 [1] refer to the most inconvenient transient regime on all three turbines from the aspect of negative axial hydraulic force, F_a , and the most critical and minimal net head cover pressure, p_{pok} .

Table 2 – Extreme values review of turbine quick closure and stoppage from 100% of maximal input at $H_n = 29.0$ m [1]

Turbine Type	H_{max} (m)	n_{max} (min ⁻¹)	$p_{sp\ max}$ (m)	$p_{pok\ min}$ (bar)	$F_{a,\ min}$ (kN)
Turbine A	33.5	108.4	29.7	-1.2	-13600.6
Turbine B	33.5	107.2	29.7	-1.3	-14202.9
Turbine C	33.6	105.3	29.7	-1.8	-14926.6

Additional analysis was obtained in order to present changes in rigid and reverse waterhammer when specific rotational speed (n_Q) takes place on abscissa and relative change of rotational speed (Δn) is located on ordinate. Specific rotational speed is defined by equation [1]:

$$n_Q = \frac{n \cdot \sqrt{Q}}{H^{3/4}} \quad (3)$$

Relative values (Δn) are calculated in turbines maximum using following equation [1]:

$$\Delta n = \frac{n_{max} - n_0}{n_{max}} \cdot 100\% \quad (4)$$

where n_{max} is obtained in certain period of time t when maximum turbine rotational speed is reached and n_0 is the optimal rotational speed value. Corresponding curves are given in part 6 of the paper.

5. VERIFICATION OF MATHEMATICAL MODELS

The verification of mathematical models is mandatory before the first test starts. To verify estimated procedure, mathematical model, numerical computation with appropriate software / programme and numerous input data, are included and verified. The most reliable and frequently used method of verification is based on comparison between the results obtained by numerical computation using software simulation with those obtained by measurements on turbine prototype of the normal transient regimes (references [3], [4] cited in [1]). Estimation of reverse waterhammer appearance and a risk associated with it is based on axial hydraulic force method because there were not available quite reliable

data of net head cover pressure distribution. Despite this, significant agreement of computed and measured results was observed [1].

6. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS AND HPP'S OPERATING REGIMES TESTED

Both static characteristics and dynamical characteristics are to be determined in order to obtain more accurate models [4]. Propeller curves are shown in normalized values as follows [1]: in Figure 1 are a non-dimensional relative shape $\psi_r-\varphi_r$ and a $\mu_r-\varphi_r$ relations are in Figure 2, respectively. Curves of turbines B and C in Figure 1 [1] have the steeper inclination, than the curve of turbine A (which exhibits the mildest slope), because for all three the shape of runner blades is different. The intersecting point of all three curves in Figure 1 corresponds to the nominal point of turbine A. It can be noticed that on turbines B and C this operating point is obtained with higher angle of runner blade, β , and higher guide vane opening, a_0 , when compared to these on the turbine A. This can be interpreted as follows [1]: the optimal operating points of the turbines B and C have been moved to the right along their operating characteristics in comparison to optimal exploitation characteristic of the turbine A. [1]

Figure 1 – Propeller curves ($\psi_r-\varphi_r$) on tested turbines due to nominal point of turbine A [1]

Figure 2 – Propeller curves ($\mu_r-\varphi_r$) on tested turbines due to nominal point of turbine A [1]

Figure 2 [1] presents normalized dependence of momentum (M) from discharge (Q). Both M and Q are given in non-dimensional form. Momentum values are lower than net head values given in Figure 1 in ψ form. Because of this the μ curves have milder slope than the ψ curves although in both cases comparison between the turbines was obtained in a same way, with respect to the nominal point of turbine A. Intersection point of the μ curves is moved a bit to the right and the lowest values are achieved on the turbine B (causing it to be even -1.5 and making a higher difference in minimal value than on turbine A and C).

In Figure 3. [1] a diagram of axial force (F_a) and rotational speed (n) are compared for all three turbines. It can be noticed that the minimal axial hydraulic force is above critical value which is approximately $F_{a,CR} = 16\ 500$ kN. This makes the risk that the turbine rotor is going to raise up very low (reference [6] cited in [1]) and occurrence of this problem very unlikely. Maximal rotational speed is reached at time $t = 7.5$ s, while minimal is not reached because the test included the first 30 s of transient regime (Figure 3). Change in rotational speed is not significant since it is less than 2% when maximum values on all turbines are compared. This is shown in Figure 4. [1] - it is visible that maximal rotational speeds on all turbines are approximately equalized.

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Figure 3 – Diagram of compared axial force (F_a) and rotational speed (n) for all three models [1]

Figure 4 – Rotational speed (n) dependence regarding to specific rotational speed n_0 [1]

7. CONCLUSION

Hydro turbines has a crucial role in converting the kinetic energy of water into mechanical energy, which is then transformed into electrical energy through generators in hydropower plants. During transient regimes, the operating conditions of the Kaplan turbine vary deviate from the steady-state conditions. This can cause the variations/ perturbations in the turbines performance, i.e. changes in power output, and efficiency. The response of the turbine to these transient events depends on its design, control system, and the specific characteristics of the transient event.

To ensure the quality operation of Kaplan turbines during transient regimes, proper control and monitoring systems must be implemented. Moreover, advanced modeling and simulation are used to analyze and predict the behavior of Kaplan turbines, allowing for better design and optimization of their performance.

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EXPERIENCES IN TEACHING AND MASTERING MATERIALS FROM THE TWO COURSES IN IT IN VOCATIONAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: The paper outlines educators' experiences in instructing specific Information Technologies (IT) courses and examines the outcomes achieved by students upon completing these selected exams. A representative sample of 20 students from the Computer-Mechanical Engineering Section at the Academy of Applied Technical Studies in Belgrade was selected, encompassing individuals with varying initial competencies in IT from different secondary schools. Their success in IT and Computer Science (CS) subjects was monitored afterwards. The study investigates and compares their work and competencies achieved during the second level of studies. Focusing on two courses from the fourth and fifth years - Electronic Commerce and Methods of Artificial Intelligence - their curricula are detailed, and the students' success in these exams is presented. The paper provides a brief analysis of the accomplishments of the selected students, outlines the mastered curricula, and performs an analysis of the obtained results.

Key words: Teaching and Learning Experience, Computer Science, Information Technologies, Electronic Commerce, Methods of Artificial Intelligence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Higher education (HE) refers to the current state and practices of teaching following the secondary education, and is typically offered at colleges, faculties, academies of applied studies and other HE institutions (HEIs). It encompasses a wide range of academic and professional disciplines and study programs, including undergraduate and graduate degrees. Modern higher vocational education aims to provide to students outcomes such as practical skills, industry-specific knowledge, and orientation to successful careers. It is dedicated to prepare students for immediate entry into the workforce, following graduation or to enhance their existing skills and competence for further advance in career. There is a strong emphasis on industry relevance and collaboration. Study programs are developed in close partnership with companies, employers and industry experts to ensure that the curriculum aligns with the needs and demands of the job market.

Education at all levels should adapt to the demands of work and life in the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Discrepancies between competence of the graduates and demands of the work environment has been reported for decades, e. g. in Computer Science (CS) and Information Technologies (IT). For the last 50 years Association for Computing Machinery - ACM is (and now with other institutions are) engaged in creating curricular guidelines that study programs should follow in order to provide better education in various areas of CS and IT [1]. To adequately prepare students for current and future job requirements, higher education institutions, including colleges and faculties, need to offer relevant body

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of knowledge [1-6]. The evolution in the way work is conducted, driven by increased automation and the adoption of new technologies, predates the Covid-19 pandemic, emphasizing the urgent necessity for widespread workforce training and reskilling globally. The pandemic has further underscored this need. There are labor shortages in specific areas demanding for reskilling or up-skilling of professionals. The World Economic Forum (WEF) has launched its Reskilling Revolution initiative and reported in January 2023 that over 350 million individuals benefited from improved skills, jobs, and education obtained through it [2-4].

Despite observed increase in use of advanced technologies in teaching, students' progress does not always exhibit the anticipated growth trend [7]. Students, coming from diverse secondary education backgrounds, including high schools (gymnasiums), technical or technological-focused high schools, and secondary education in Economy or Social Sciences, demonstrate varied levels of *a priori* knowledge, e.g. in IT and CS. Selected representatives from the student groups enrolled in the Academy of Applied Technical Studies Belgrade (Computer-Mechanical Section) were closely monitored throughout their undergraduate, specialist, and master's studies. Results regarding success of these students in subject WEB Applications, taken during the third year of bachelor studies, was examined in detail and presented in [5]. Parts of practical exercises performed by this group of students were illustrated as well in [5]. A selected group of students was followed-up from the start of their studies until their graduation from bachelor vocational studies, professional specialist or master professional level of studies. To illustrate their success during studies one course was selected from the fourth year of study – Electronic Commerce/ Business, and examined in detail in the part 2 of this paper. Another subject was selected from the fifth year of study – Methods of Artificial Intelligence (AI). The progress of these students is analyzed, irrespective of their prior knowledge and here results are given in part 3 and 4. The study also evaluates success of this group in adapting and mastering skills during the final year of undergraduate or graduate studies.

Figure 1 - Bloom's Taxonomy (revised) - A Taxonomy for Teaching, Learning, and Assessment [8]
Source: https://bloomstaxonomy.net/htaccess_files/Blooms-Taxonomy-650x366.jpg

Figure 1 illustrates educational objectives as part of revised Bloom's Taxonomy where the two highest level objectives are ability to evaluate and ability to create [8].

2. E-COMMERCE COURSE

In the fourth year, i.e. during specialist studies in professional higher education, students attend a course in Electronic Commerce (or E-commerce). In addition to being presented theoretical aspects, [9], students also complete a lot of practical exercises where they apply gained knowledge, strengthen competence and learn to create dynamic websites, [10]. One of the practical tasks is to create the online store selling auto parts. When creating an e-shop, students need to focus attention to multiple factors, [11]. The student-designer must keep in mind the software, hardware requirements and security issues as well as the way the content of the store is going to be displayed, the navigation through the present-

ation and the maintenance or administration of the e-shop.

The e-shop creation process requires the designer to respond to the following questions:

- How many applications are needed for the e-shop to work?
- How many databases are needed for an e-shop?
- What software is needed for the e-shop to work?
- Software required for development, improvement and maintenance of electronic stores;
- Software required for using the e-shop
- What hardware is needed for the e-shop to work?
- What kind of network infrastructure is needed for the operation of the e-shop?
- Which business processes of e-shop need automation?
- Necessary security measures for safe operation of the e shop.

The e-shop automates and emulates real business and sales processes in shops, by transferring already existing processes and operations from the physical world to the virtual level with Internet access. E-commerce security depends on payment systems and consumer systems baskets. According to the conditions and legal regulations of the country and the environment of the e-shop, the payment system is based on cash on delivery or online credit card payments. An extremely important part of creating an e-shop is designing its database and filling it with data. In this case, the term database means an organized set of data that relates to products, user data (customers, employees, suppliers and distributors), and events which are related to the operation of the e-shop and software modules that enable access to that data.

The tables and records in database created by the students refer to:

- Consumer basket - table Cart,
- Orders - table Orders,
- Products - Products table,
- Users - Users table.

Through the administrative presentation, of the so-called "Back Office", administrators perform the management of the entire offer and presentation of the e-shop, users, and database maintenance. During the presentation, the code layout is chosen, in this case UTF-8, which enables the display of the Cyrillic alphabet in search engines. Guided account of resolution and effects can be achieved with the help of CSS, Java script and flash animation. Care should be taken that the content does not burden the potential customer, not to be too colorful nor intrusive, not to have too much extra content. It is intended to draw customers' attention and not to deter them from the purchases.

The entire content of the page must be well fitted and in accordance one to others and thus will result in a visually appealing and whole form. This should achieve what was initially chosen as the basic concept of the web page layout. The one concept selected should be adhered to during the preparation of the entire presentation. That doesn't mean that some ideas may not be changed during the development of the site, but all alterations should be clearly identified and defined. Students must adhere to the basic ideas and they should not make too many changes.

The first step to shopping in an e-shop is to register the user. Besides from realization of shopping opportunities, registration also provides some benefits while shopping. By entering the required data in the form for registering new user, the user is assigned unique username and all of the data entered are used for its identification and accurate delivery of purchased goods. After creating / activating the account, the user is able to change the access password, enter new or change already entered information about himself / herself. This enables e-shops to have the right information about their customers at all times and provide them with adequate service. Web site of the e-shop offers information of the products. In addition to the picture of the product, there is also a short description, price, colors or sizes in which the product is available as well as a product order button. When the customer selects the product, its model and color, and is ready to order products, at the touch of a button "Order" data is sent to the server and entered into the database in the appropriate tables. By reviewing the administrative presentation, the

entered data is read and the order is completed and realized. More complex problem would be to design IT in supply chains [12].

3. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE COURSE

In the last year of study, i.e. the second year of the master's vocational studies, students take the subject Methods of AI with the application of the Python programming on machine learning, [13]. After getting acquainted with the basic characteristics of Artificial Intelligence, [14], students get a specific problem in technology, and the task of using machine learning methods to improve production, [15].

In the following text of this paper, one such example related to the application of machine learning to the testing of aluminum profiles will be presented. Production of profiles by extrusion processes is one of the modern and most used production processes in the world. This process produces massive amounts of profiles for different uses. Aluminum is one of the most used materials in this process. Its alloys 6000 series represent great balance between elasticity and hardness and also have great extrusion characteristics. Quality control regularly increases standards of quality of production by using modern solutions that enhance production. Aside from using the newest standards, students include modern technology to help improving quality of products. One of those technologies is Artificial Intelligence (AI). Artificial intelligence and its sub branches like machine learning (ML), deep learning (DL), neural networks (NN) and others, can aid to increase quality of production. Quality control has big database that AI can manipulate with different tools. By training different models of AI students can acquire many conclusions that will increase production quality.

Anaconda software environment as well as Integrated Development Environment - IDE Spyder is used for data processing in this practical work of students. Anaconda makes it easy to use all libraries within the Python programming language, as they come bundled with the environment. Spyder is a standard choice in this environment when it comes to writing machine learning programs, as it comes with all the necessary tools to successfully create a program.

Using the linear regression algorithm, the relationships between the parameters can be detected. For the example of linear regression, the parameters of the length of the profile in aging furnaces as well as the parameters of the profile hardness were used. The line of the linear regression algorithm shows the real influence of aging on the strength of aluminum profiles in the general sense, because all 4 alloys from the database are included in this analogy. The line does not start from scratch, because aging is an integral part of the production that each profile goes through, and depending on customer requirements, the length of the aging treatment is determined in order to achieve the desired mechanical properties. Logistic regression is a very interesting algorithm which, although it has regression in its name, is very often used for classification problems, and students use it in this case as well. In the form of regression, students most often use the sigmoid function. A great way to review the model is a confusion matrix. All test data can be seen on it, as well as where they are well and where they are wrongly distributed. The confusion matrix can also be used in classification algorithms where there are several parameters by which it is classified. Thus, all 25 profile data that were part of the test phase of the algorithm can be seen on the confusion matrix. Following the hair of the confusion matrix, students can see all the alloys that are well assigned based on the parameters. Numbers that are outside the hair indicate the number of errors in assigning the alloy name. The research part of the project that students are working on is combining knowledge about extrusion processes, aluminum alloys and artificial intelligence. First, a database is created with real data obtained from production on the basis of which research can be done, stimulated by machine learning algorithms. When examining the data, a linear regression algorithm was used, as well as several classification algorithms. At the end of the research, a web application was made that classifies aluminum alloys based on mechanical properties.

4. RESULTS

The percentage results in IT subjects during the first two years of study are shown in Table 1. [5]

Table 1 - Percentage results from IT subjects during the first two years [5]

Previous educational experience	Grades					Passed exam in the first term	Passed exam in the second term
	6	7	8	9	10		
High school	12	15	33	28	12	76	82
Secondary technical schools	64	17	10	9	/	64	68
Secondary Social Sciences schools	92	8	/	/	/	48	53

The success [%] of students in the subject of Electronic commerce/ business is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 - The percentage success of students in the subject of electronic commerce

Previous educational experience	Grades					Passed exam in the first term	Passed exam in the second term
	6	7	8	9	10		
High school	10	17	32	23	19	91	93
Secondary technical schools	25	14	27	20	14	83	86
Secondary Social Sciences schools	52	26	15	7	/	68	73

The success [%] of students in the subject of Methods of Artificial Intelligence is given in Table 3.

Table 3 - The percentage success of students in the subject of artificial intelligence

Previous educational experience	Grades					Passed exam in the first term	Passed exam in the second term
	6	7	8	9	10		
High school	/	12	36	23	29	96	97
Secondary technical schools	5	11	39	20	25	93	95
Secondary Social Sciences schools	37	33	18	12	/	81	84

4. CONCLUSION

Contemporary higher vocational education has a strong emphasis on narrow specializations, lifelong learning and adaptability. This involve offering continuing education programs, up-skilling opportunities, and professional development courses to ensure that graduates can quickly adapt to changing industry demands. In higher vocational education specializing in IT or CS, the curriculum is typically tailored to meet the requirements of the IT industry. Students are exposed to real-world scenarios, conditions and challenges, allowing them to develop practical skills that can later be directly applied in the workplace. Higher vocational IT or CS education tends to develop soft skills, such as teamwork, communication, problem-solving and critical thinking. Contemporary IT higher vocational education aims to provide to students learning of practical skills, industry-specific knowledge, and can give a strong foundation for successful careers. The paper presents the selected students' success in two representative subjects, e.g. Electronic Commerce (E-Commerce in short) and Methods of Artificial Intelligence, and shows practical project tasks that students have mastered to some extent. The highlights from curriculum for the mentioned subjects are presented, with the example project demands that the students performed during the attendance period of those courses. The percentage success of these group of students and outcomes for these subjects are given in this paper.

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ANALYSIS OF STRESS AND DEFORMATION ON THE 6600L TANK CONSTRUCTION

Andrijana Đurđević¹ Đorđe Đurđević² Milan Marković³ Bojan Ivljanin⁴ Katarina Antić⁵

Abstract: In this paper, an analytical and numerical calculation of the stress and deformation of the tank construction in which the fluid, specifically water, is placed was performed. Constant loads are adopted according to the standard. The numerical calculation was done using the finite element method in the SolidWorks software. The obtained stress and strain values are within the permitted limits. Also, the contribution of this work is a new constructional solution of the tank. Such a construction was made, which has internal and external ribs made of plates and bent profiles.

Key words: stress, strain, tank construction, finite element method

1. INTRODUCTION

Tanks are parts that are used to store liquid fluid or gas. They can be under internal pressure or loads only at atmospheric pressure. In this work, the tank has a cover on the upper side, but it is not loaded with elevated pressure, but only atmospheric pressure. [3], [4]

The construction of the tank is also done in this work. The walls are made of 4mm thick stainless steel. The bottom of the tank is made of 5 mm thick sheet metal, also made of stainless steel. The cover is made of sheet metal of the same material, 4mm thick. The shell of the tank is reinforced with bent U-profiles of dimensions 42x65x4mm. Strengthening of the tank walls was done according to the SRPS EN 1993-4-2 standard [3], which is shown in Figure 1.

In the first part of the work, a calculation was made, so that the fluid loads the internal surfaces of the tank. Also included here is the load caused by the tank's own weight. Tank cover is not loaded.

Since the tank is closed, due to the emptying of the fluid by the pump, an underpressure occurs in the tank. When the tank is completely empty, there is an underpressure that loads the walls, cover and bottom of the tank. Breathing valves are always installed in tanks of this type, in addition to the mandatory safety valve. It is in the second part of the work that the calculation for underpressure (vacuum) was made. Therefore, on tanks of this type, there must always be two safety valves, one for overpressure and the other for underpressure.

2. BASIC CALCULATION

The calculation was made according to the requirements of SRPS EN 1993-4-2; 2017 Eurocode 3 - Design of steel structures - Part 4 - 2 Tanks [3].

The analysis and calculation of the structure was performed. The analysis of deformations and stresses was done for the following load cases of the tank construction:

1. by own weight, and
2. given external fluid load.

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2.1. Introduction to calculation

The introduction to the calculation is described below. Stainless steel 316L, i.e. 1.4404, was chosen for the construction material of the tank. It is an austenitic chromium-nickel stainless steel containing molybdenum. This additive increases resistance against corrosion. Type 316L is a low carbon version of Type 316 stainless steel that reduces harmful carbide deposits from welding.

The chemical composition of stainless steel 316L, used for the calculation is shown in the Table 1[4].

Table 1 – Chemical composition of stainless steel 316L

Element	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	N	Ni	Mo
% Percent	0,03	1,0	2,0	0,045	0,015 1	16,5-18.5	0,1	10,0-13,0	2-2,5

The basic mechanical properties of this material are as follows:

- modulus of elasticity $E = 200000\text{N/mm}^2$
- breaking stress $f_u = 52\text{kN/cm}^2$
- yield stress $f_y = 21\text{kN/cm}^2$
- Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0,3$
- density at 20°C $\rho = 8\text{kg/m}^3$

The deformation value is obtained from the following expression:

$$\varepsilon = \left[\frac{235}{f_u} \cdot \frac{E}{210000} \right]^{0,5} = 1,03 \quad (1)$$

Spatial models of the steel construction of the tank were created for the purposes of the analysis.

2.2. Permanent load of the construction

A permanent load on construction of the tank is a load that changes very little or not at all during a short period of time period. It implies the own weight of the construction of the tank and the action of the fluid on the construction.

The specific value of water density (according to the EN 1911-1-1 standard [5]) is: $\gamma = 10\text{kN/m}^3$.

A load sketch is given in Figure 1. Load caused by the action of the fluid on the bottom of the tank is:

$$p = \rho \cdot g \cdot h = 997 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \cdot 10 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}^2} \cdot 1,62\text{m} = 16151,4\text{Pa} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1 - Load sketch

The tank construction model was created in SolidWorks software and is shown in Figure 2. The entire construction of the tank is made of stainless steel 316L. The walls are made of sheet metal with a thickness of 4 mm. The bottom of the tank is made of 5 mm thick sheet metal. The cover is made of 4mm thick sheet metal. The shell of the tank is reinforced with bent U-profiles of dimensions 42x65x4mm. These are cold formed profiles.

Figure 2 - Calculation model of the tank 6600L

The following figures show a global analysis of the deformations and stresses of the tank structure, with all the specified loads. Numerical calculation was done in solidworks software, and according to the experience gained in works [6], [7]. Tank cover is not loaded. Figure 3 shows that all obtained stress values are within the permitted limits. The value of the allowed stress is:

$$\sigma_d = 210\text{MPa}. \tag{3}$$

Looking at the scale given in Figure 4, the maximum value of the equivalent stress is observed:

$$\sigma_{e\max} = 121,4\text{MPa}. \tag{4}$$

Considering the condition for the correct functioning of the part:

$$\sigma_{e\max} \leq \sigma_d \tag{5}$$

it is concluded that there will be no plastic deformations or fractures of the tank.

The deformation of the tank construction, i.e. the displacement values are also within the permissible limits, as shown in Figure 4. Since the tank cover is not loaded, displacements on the cover were not considered.

Figure 3 - Distribution of the equivalent stress according to the Von Mises hypothesis

Figure 4 – Total displacement, mm

2.3. Load underpressure

Underpressure is caused by emptying liquid from a closed tank by means of a pump. In the most risky case, when the tank is completely empty, there is an underpressure that stresses the walls, cover and bottom of the tank. In addition to the mandatory safety valve, breathing valve is also installed in this type of tank. In this chapter of the work, a calculation was made when there is underpressure (vacuum) in the tank.

It is assumed that there is an underpressure acting in the tank:

$$p_v = 3,5\text{mbar} = 350\text{Pa}. \tag{5}$$

Figure 5 shows the distribution of the equivalent stress according to the Von Mises hypothesis, when the tank is loaded with a given overpressure value. Also, the corresponding scale of equivalent stress is given in the Figure 5. The value of the allowed stress is 210MPa, and maximum equivalent stress is 121,4MPa. The value of the maximum equivalent stress obtained by numerical analysis is lower than the allowed stress, so that the tank can withstand the given overpressure without the appearance of plastic deformation and fracture.

Figure 5 - Distribution of the equivalent stress according to the Von Mises hypothesis

3. CONCLUSION

The construction of the tank is made as a welded machine assembly from: sheet metal, cold-formed sheet metal profiles made by bending and from standard rolled steel profiles. The quality of the welded joints is defined by the welding technology. Control of welded joints was performed visually and by measuring the geometry of the cross-section of the welded joint. By numerical calculation, all values of equivalent stresses and deformations are within the permissible limits. The calculated tank is in operation in the process industry.

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ON SOME NECESSARY CHANGES IN THE FUNDAMENTAL PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF ENGINEERS IN ACCORDANCE WITH THE DYNAMICS OF REQUIREMENTS ON THE LABOR MARKET

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Abstract: From the perspective of the profile of the engineer currently in demand on the labor market, a reset of the education and training system in higher education institutions is necessary. In a cooperation between the academic environment, the business environment and the Territorial Labor Inspectorate, studies and analyzes are frequently carried out for a better correlation between school training and the requirements of the labor market. Following recent joint research, carried out mainly in Timiș county (Romania), some urgent improvement measures were taken, considering the general process of digitization and expansion of the telework system. The way of imposing and methodical of the fundamental subjects in the study programs was particularly monitored. The approach was achieved by attributing to the basic training of the engineer and the responsibility of knowing and understanding the progress perspective of the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in as many fields of activity and social life as possible.

Keywords: engineering, education, fundamental disciplines, artificial intelligence, telework

1. INTRODUCTION

In general, companies find themselves in an extensive maturation process following a model adopted based on specific factors, selected according to the best course of action to advance to a higher level of maturity [1]. The maturity indicators of an enterprise are influenced by the level of maturity of the digital transformation and the degree of IT achieved [2]. Several digital maturity assessment models have been created. The Digital Transformation Capability Maturity Framework (DX-CMF) model is a suitable framework that encompasses four aspects: internal policy and governance (IP), information and technology (IT), digital process transformation (DP) and human resource management (HR). Using established standards that have been approved by professionals, maturity can be assessed. The result of the maturity assessment can be used to determine digital readiness levels. The digital preparation of the organization implies the creation and appropriation of appropriate audit procedures, including digital ones [3]. Thus, a change in engineering thinking is observed over time. Engineering systems thinking is a major higher-order thinking skill that enables individuals to successfully perform systems engineering tasks.

To successfully perform systems engineering roles, systems engineers need systems view or strong engineering systems thinking ability. (Capacity for Engineering Systems Thinking, CEST). This ability has been found to be a consistent personality trait and can be used to distinguish between individual engineers. Today's successful engineer must prove 31 competencies: 10 cognitive characteristics, 11 skills, 10 individual traits, of which 3 are based on multidisciplinary knowledge and experience. This structure of engineering training evolves in relation to the complexity of new projects in which engineers have a decisive role [4].

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In the last two decades, in the engineering career, entrepreneurship has new valences, as a consistent evolution of the understanding of what it constitutes is necessary, the scope of entrepreneurship education as an academic field has expanded, from an approach focused on economics/business, to an approach that focuses more on the individual growth of engineers' skills [5]. Recently, several studies have been carried out on the population's perception of how the opportunities to use artificial intelligence (AI) in project management (PM) arise, to increase project performance, to discover new solutions for the transformation digital towards Industry 5.0 [6]. The problem of advancing the educational system correlated with these changes in industry and management, both at the entrepreneurial and societal level, remains open. It will be more and more difficult to solve these ever-deepening problems of human systems that affect thinking, not just methodology, but actual practice in individual engineering careers, but especially systems engineering. Two aspects of this will be explored: the dualistic (subjective/objective) nature of systems and systems engineering those results from including the human in the picture; and the possibility that formal knowledge of how we do systems engineering would allow us to significantly improve our practice. No attempt is made to be thorough or to support every claim, the aim is simply to provoke thought and possibly stimulate greater interest in the full depth study of human systems in engineering and management [7].

There are recent decisions at the level of the European Union (EU) after reaching a revolutionary consensus on AI regulations, setting a precedent as the first substantive legal framework for artificial intelligence (AI) in the Western world. An Agreement was signed on how to manage generative AI models such as ChatGPT and biometric identification tools. There needs to be legislative control given the known concerns of job displacement, discriminatory language, and breach of confidentiality [8]. Basically, there is a discrepancy between the level of knowledge and use of AI to the detriment of the many who do not have the necessary knowledge to counter some negative determinations.

It is considered necessary for the educational systems to train engineers, regardless of specialization, to correlate their fundamental theoretical content in relation to the dynamics of the labor market requirements. One of the aspects that have become current are related to the expansion of remote work activities, with dual effects, related to increasing the profit of companies, but also to the achievement of some well-being requirements expressed by teleworkers. Current technologies have an ambivalent character. They are liberating, empowering and revelatory, yet at the same time constraining, oppressive and opaque. Ambivalence is not inherent in these technologies.

A way out of this situation is to reverse the prevailing trend and develop and promote the liberating and empowering aspects of technology [9]. This path also includes an extensive process of developing the knowledge horizon of individuals, but especially of professional training of engineers, with a decisive role in generating and mastering the functioning mechanisms of the entire support macrosystem, under technical, technological, functional and logistics.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

1.1. The classic version of the engineer profile

In the present research, we started from some particularities of the engineering profession, starting from the classical vision. About the purpose and the role of the engineer in society, the 31st President of the USA, Herbert Hoover, left several considerations in the literature, himself having an engineering training, before becoming a politician: *„Engineering training deals with the exact sciences. That sort of exactness makes for truth and conscience. It might be good for the world if more men had that sort of mental start in life even if they did not pursue the profession. But he who would enter these precincts as a life work must have a test taken of his imaginative faculties, for engineering without imagination sinks to a trade. And those who would enter here must for years abandon their white collars except for Sunday”. ... „Every time he discovers a new application of science, thereby creating a new industry, providing new jobs, adding to the standards of living, he also disturbs everything that is. New laws and regulations must be made, and new sorts of wickedness curbed. He is also the person who really corrects monopolies and redistributes national wealth”* [10].

The professional training of an engineer is based on some fundamental disciplines, for the formation of general engineering thinking, as well as disciplines that bring him closer to the field of activity, respectively those that give him a direction of specialization.

Figure 1 shows a synthetic picture of the typology of an engineer's professional fields [11].

Figur1. - Schematic representation of job diversity for an engineer. [11].

Engineers generally use scientific principles to make machines and other structures, such as factory equipment, bridges, and tunnels. An engineer can also be involved in creating pharmaceuticals, airplanes, vehicles, roads, dams, and robots. Engineers are great problem solvers. They use math and science to find solutions. They also determine how machines, devices, and other equipment work. Engineers are usually given the task of finding practical applications for new scientific discoveries, i.e. bringing them to market.

1.2. The updated view on the engineering profession

In the last 3-5 years, certain mutations have happened in the labor market, with the imposition of automation, robotization and currently the rush to implement AI in all fields, one form being given by a variety of PM. Training AI engineers is still considered a narrow specialization of IT/Computer Science engineers. This involves building skills that enable him to identify the right approach to using AI to solve a specific business problem. In enterprises, there are AI engineers who work closely with machine learning engineers to develop and implement learning algorithms that can use historical and real-time data to predict future events. In smaller companies, the same person (AI/ML engineer) may be responsible for both AI strategy and implementation [12]. Some curricula have subject requirements that ensure a strong background in mathematics and statistics. Familiarity with Python and R programming languages, as well as their other commonly used libraries and packages, is sought. Responsibilities of AI engineers have already emerged, such as:

- Establishing business objectives for AI implementation.
- Conduct brainstorming sessions with other IT team members to explore how machine learning concepts can be used to solve specific business problems.
- Development of proofs of concepts (POCs).

- Identifying obstacles that could endanger a project based on artificial intelligence and research solutions.
- Creating metrics to measure the return on investment (ROI) of an AI project.
- Promoting best practices for data wrangling, data processing and documentation required for the project [12].

Due to some alarmist discussions in the public space regarding the risk of specialists' incompetence to govern/manage the expansion of AI, this research was carried out, based on both a documentation of the curricula of technical universities and using online debate with groups of trained employable graduates by the Politehnica University (state) and the private IOAN SLAVICI University in Timisoara.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH

The experimental research was carried out between October and December 2023, in a cooperation between the Polytechnic University (State Institution), the Ioan Slavici University (Private Institution), the business environment and the Territorial Labor Inspectorate from Timiș County (Romania). This kind of studies have become traditional, being carried out frequently, for a better correlation between school training and the demands of the labor market. It started from the analysis of the specific standards regarding the external evaluation of the academic quality of study programs imposed by the Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education" ARACIS, the specialized commissions related to training in the broad field of engineering sciences. Thus, the fundamental subjects common to all undergraduate programs in the fundamental field of Engineering Sciences include: Mathematical Analysis, Linear Algebra, Analytical and Differential Geometry, Special Mathematics and/or Differential Equations, Probability Theory and Mathematical Statistics, Equations of Mathematical Physics, Methods numerical, Descriptive geometry, Computer-aided graphics, Technical drawing and infographics, Computer programming and programming languages and/or Applied informatics, Physics and Chemistry [13].

In the II stage of the research, a set of 4 questions were addressed to the graduates-employees:

1. To what extent have the fundamental subjects studied developed your engineering thinking at the level of the requirements of your current job. Express on a scale of 1 (minimum) to 10 (maximum)
2. Briefly present what difficulties you encountered in learning, evaluating the knowledge gained and passing the exams in the fundamental subjects?
3. What changes do you think are necessary regarding the fundamental subjects in the education plans? Specify any reductions or additions of disciplines.
4. Express on a scale from 1 (minimum) to 5 (maximum), to what extent do you think that learning to practice engineering can be done online? Remarks.

Several 268 valid answer options were retained for analysis. Table 1 summarizes the results of the experimental study.

Table 1 – The centralized situation of the data resulting from the application of the questionnaire.

Question	Answers										Observations
1. To what extent have the fundamental subjects studied developed your engineering thinking at the level of the requirements of your current job. Express on a scale of 1 (minimum) to 10 (maximum)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
	8	13	26	28	28	40	46	32	24	23	

<p>2. Briefly present what difficulties you encountered in learning, evaluating the knowledge gained and passing the exams in the fundamental subjects?</p>	<p>- the obligation to memorize many misunderstood aspects - too abstract approach to notions through the lens of the mathematician, physicist, chemist, not the engineer - difficult collaboration with teaching staff</p>					<p>- Too rigid relationship between teacher and student. -Assessment as objective as possible, with a reduction in the degree of stress.</p>
<p>3. What changes do you think are necessary regarding the fundamental subjects in the education plans? Specify any reductions or additions of disciplines.</p>	<p>- - the content of the courses should have introductory, general notions, without delving into unnecessary details - the need to introduce the disciplines of understanding and using ICT, AI, PM etc., for all engineering specializations - learning oriented to understanding not memorization, practical way of using/approaching</p>					<p>Development of documentation and communication skills in the specialty</p>
<p>4. Express on a scale from 1 (minimum) to 5 (maximum), to what extent do you think that learning to practice engineering can be done online? Remarks.</p>	<p>1 24</p>	<p>2 36</p>	<p>3 68</p>	<p>4 68</p>	<p>5 72</p>	<p>- Courses taught mostly online, with practical applications in the laboratory. - Initiation into telework</p>

In table 1, extracts from the most frequent texts were specified, in the order of importance appreciated by the interviewees.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The recorded data show an increased interest in finding solutions to increase the effectiveness of the technical higher education system.

Regarding the extent to which the fundamental disciplines studied are appreciated as welcome in the development of an engineering thinking, the weighted average of the points awarded is 6.93 out of 10, which represents a rather low level, perhaps even alarming. The result can be appreciated as a rather subjective result, especially with those shown above, about the evolution of engineering thinking. But, making a correlation with the answers given to the 2nd question, regarding the difficulties encountered in learning, the evaluation of the accumulated knowledge, respectively and the passing of the exams in the fundamental disciplines, the opinions. negative is associated with some aspects of insufficient pedagogical competence. Engineering thinking is based on the understanding of phenomena and the ability to issue relevant technical solutions. In this case it is obvious that it cannot be formed by the obligation to memorize the aspects not understood. The appreciation of the teaching methodology is also interesting, with a more engineering approach to the theoretical notions of mathematics, physics, or chemistry. Difficult collaboration with teaching staff can also be due to the existing communication path and the consideration of partnership in the teacher-student relationship, like that of mentor-disciple. The report cannot be accepted by the measure of the teacher's "power" given by the right to award a mark that marks the recognition of the level of accumulated knowledge. The efficiency of the evaluation system is also given by the closeness of the grade to the one realized by the student through self-evaluation.

Regarding the changes considered necessary, in the package of fundamental subjects in the education plans, the first proposal aims at the quantitative reduction of the content of the courses, and the learning should be oriented to the understanding of the phenomena and not to the mechanical memorization of the notions. Significant is the proposal of the need to introduce several IT and communication disciplines, which will contribute to the development of the ability to understand and use ICT, AI, PM etc., at the level of all engineering specializations.

The expressions made on the conduct of the online education process, the weighted average of the assessments is 3.48 out of 5, which shows a preference for a hybrid system: the courses are mostly online, and the practical activities carried out in the laboratory.

Many interviewees considered the development of online teaching activities, a development of an inter-human communication culture, in correlation with the expansion of gainful telework activities. It is also worth noting the recognition of disturbing emotional factors in the teacher-student relationship. Of course, this aspect is of a subjective nature, (from case to case), but it must be considered, especially due to their influence on the quality and performances resulting from the training process of future engineers.

5. CONCLUSION

In the context in which contemporary society is facing a state of unease regarding the danger of implementing artificial intelligence, the most adequate training of engineers is necessary, who can make this approach, the fruit of advanced scientific research, better understood. The present study is part of a larger program to monitor the evolution of the degree of professional training of graduates, in accordance with the reality of the ecosystem of which we are a part.

The results of the research, even if they highlight certain shortcomings in the educational process, can be within the reach of decision-makers, respectively in the attention of civil society organizations, trade unions, as well as elected officials. The current progress of society determines a series of changes in thinking, but also new requirements regarding the theoretical and practical training of engineering graduates. As it has proven so many times, human society could resettle and defend itself in the face of dangers caused by various imbalances. Education has always been a determining factor in the beneficial solution of the great problems that have arisen. Thus, adequate engineering training, raising the degree of civilization and culture of the populations is the sure way to understanding and favorable determination.

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VIRTUAL MAINTENANCE

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Abstract: In production systems, the maintenance subsystem plays a very important role, since maintenance costs can represent an unavoidable and significant source of costs. In order to reduce costs, improve, train and prepare employees for audits, searching for and eliminating malfunctions, technical diagnostics and reconstruction in a safe environment, modern companies in the world increasingly apply the concept of virtual maintenance. Although there are many definitions and technologies, there is no general and universally accepted definition to unambiguously describe virtual maintenance. The perspective of virtual maintenance is related to virtual reality and extended multi-personal collaboration, remote condition checking and artificial intelligence. Virtual reality is a rapidly developing computer interface that seeks to completely "immerse" the user in an experimental simulation, thus providing a connection between man and computer, using specialized equipment with spatial sensors.

Key words: maintenance strategies, virtual reality, virtual maintenance, training, assembly

1. INTRODUCTION

Ever since Morton Heilig first introduced Sensorama simulator in 1962, followed by Ivan Sutherland's in essay "The Ultimate Display", Virtual Reality (VR) technology has been promoted in various areas of activities. Throughout the past (in 1970s and 1980s), NASA uses VR HMD (Virtual Reality Head Mounted Display) in space operation research (for telepresence control and telerobotic control for space station operations) and for fight simulations.[1] A VR HMDs is a display device which fits anatomically on the viewer's head, covering the eyes and ears, and separates the user's consciousness from the space in which he is at the time of using the virtual environment. (Figure 1)

Figure 1 – Head Mounted Display (HMD)[2]

The definition of VR has modified throuht the time, depending on state of technology of that time and the context of use. Based on current state, *Virtual Reality (VR) technology can be defined as an advanced computer technology – generated three – dimensional graphical representation of the real or imaginary environment in which users are immersed through a dedicated headset or an array on display walls.* [1] VR integrates multimedia, sensor, display, human-machine interaction, ergonomics, simulation, computer graphics, and artificial intelligence technologies to expand human perception.[3] By using VR, the person can experience vacationing on exotic destination even withough leaving home. Today provide users not only immersive sight beyond reality but also touch, hearing, and even

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ability to interact with virtual objects during the training and education in different fields – medicine [4], chemistry [5], architecture [6], archeology [7], sport, entertainment, design machine parts, product operations and maintenance etc. VR technology can be used to train nurses and doctor to diagnose some diseases or for certain surgical interventions on computers instead on live subject, animals or cadavers. In archeology VR to can be used to discover artifacts through physical interaction in a game based condition. In the largest area of VR application – entertainment – it is possible to leave reality and try some things that the average person could only dream about: stepping into an airplane avionics bay or cabin flying space shuttle, to experience a walk on another planet, to practice their own dream house, etc.

2. EVOLUTION OF MAINTENANCE STRATEGIES SECTION

Maintainability is a feature of a product given during the design and manufacturing phase and is the relative ease and economy of time and resources when a product needs to be maintained or restored. [8] Over the life of a product, maintenance costs can represent a significant percentage of life cycle costs. According to some researches [9], maintenance costs can make up to 10-25% of the direct operating costs in aircraft. During the last five decades, maintenance plays an important role in industry, considering that effective maintenance strategies include preventing production downtime, costs reduction and may increase the reliability and useful lifetime of technical systems. As a result of these reasons, maintenance approaches has radically changed from corrective maintenance (as a most primitive strategy) to contemporary prescriptive maintenance. (Figure 2)

Figure 2 – Evolution of maintenance strategies over time

Corrective maintenance, often called “run – to – failure” or “breakdown maintenance” indicates replacing or repairing of parts (an equipment component or equipment item) only when failure occurs or the equipment is unable to work without intervention. Apart from cleaning and lubrication, there are no elements of planned – preventive interventions. Corrective maintenance is not used often today, generally for less important parts, ie. auxiliary equipment, where the unplanned downtime does not directly affects on product development or business process. Due to the high costs of having unexpected failures and production stops, **preventive maintenance** involves periodical audits and replacement of parts (in equally spaced periods of time, or after a certain number of working cycles), performed before the failure has occurred. This conception, except that it involves large resources (material, additional parts and experts maintenance), also assumes stopping the equipment, which is in a situation, e.g. continuous unfavorable production.

With the technological advances in the field of Industry 4.0 and the development of the Internet of Things (IoT) **condition – based maintenance** approach emerged ie. Maintenance 4.0.[10] IoT integrates complex machines and devices networked with electronics, software and sensors to collect and exchange data. IoT integrates complex machines and devices networked with software and sensors. Maintenance interventions are carried out based on the condition determined by the sensors and by monitoring the physical parameters of mentioned networked industrial equipment (such as temperature, conductivity, vibrations, pressure, etc.). This is the form of self – learning and smart system that predicts failure makes diagnosis and next maintenance actions.[10] Digital technologies which support Industry 4.0 and therefore Maintenance 4.0 are Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality. This paper will be based mainly on Virtual Maintenance. **Predictive maintenance** also referred as “**condition monitoring**” focuses to estimate probability that a machine operates without a failure in the future, according current condition and past operation. It is characterized by mathematical models for predicting the occurrence of failure. This maintenance strategy includes computer diagnostics. It aligns the paradigms of IoT and Cyber Physical Systems with knowledge in the fields of automation, engineering, information technology and data analytics [11],[12] to predict impending machine failure and the remaining useful life of industrial assets, and to identify the optimal actions.

3. DEFINITION AND ELEMENTS OF THE VIRTUAL MAINTENANCE

As already stated, VR has been adopted in a variety of industries serving many needs, but there is no clear and generally accepted definition of Virtual Maintenance. Most of them are based on defining certain significant relationship between man and computer. Modern industrial products require the integration of electronic, hydro-pneumatic, mechanical and computer systems, so that the assembly and disassembly process is increasingly complex. The first definition of virtual maintenance can be written as: „The main content of maintenance is disassembly, and virtual maintenance is defined as the evaluation of maintainability by virtual assembly environment. This circumscription that defines virtual maintenance as virtual assembly elegantly showing the main activity that maintenance is involved, while defining maintenance as disassembly narrows the range of the maintenance”.[13], [14]

Figure 3 – Virtual assembly

Another definition given in the literature is: “Virtual maintenance is based on the computer technology and virtual reality, the virtual scene including product digital prototyping and maintenance engineer 3D computer generated and the integrated application technology of the entire maintenance process simulation is completed by driving the model of human body”. [14] In engineering digital human body are constructed for research in the field of ergonomics and focus on working postures and comfort.[3]

A third definition of virtual maintenance that can be found in the literature states: “Maintenance is a computer simulation technology that trainees can operate machine in the virtual environment”. [14], [15]

And, at the end forth definition: “Virtual maintenance is based on computer technology and VR technology. The virtual scene including product digital prototyping and 3D human model of maintenance engineer is computer generated, driving the model of human body and using human –

machine interaction technology to complete maintenance process, achieving the purpose of verifying maintenance, simulating maintenance process, maintenance training and maintenance design".[14]

Figure 4 – Virtual assembly 3D models and an engineer visualizes a mechanical hologram technology [16]

In the future, a large number of manual stations in manufacturing industries will be transformed into human-robot collaboration stations. [3] Based on the previous definitions, it is concluded that virtual maintenance consists of four key elements: virtual maintenance object, virtual maintenance engineer, virtual maintenance tool /instrument and virtual maintenance implementation process. (Figure 5) Although the virtual object does not exist in the real world, for a more reality training effect, it is important to make the size and color of the model as far as possible as same as the real object. Virtual model instrument (tool) is a model of real tools which differs from other technical systems in terms of construction, technological solution and lifetime. This model should simulate real instrument model used in real maintenance.

Figure 5 – Virtual Maintenance Technological System[14]

As can be seen in Figure 5, the virtual maintenance staff is divided into: Virtual Human Model and Real People. Virtual body represents human figures by modeling and animating in virtual environment. (Figure 6) In the Skoda factory, e.g. during the conceptual phase development of the new tram model Tramva Skoda 15 analyzed a variant interior of a tram with wooden seats. The seat assembled from 3D elements and the model used to simulate all possible future crash scenarios. By using VR technology, it can also be checked whether people of shorter stature can easily operate the train controls, whether there is enough space for tall people and whether the field of vision is restricted in any way. It is also possible to simulate the replacement of one row of seats and on that occasion,

determine whether a certain row of seats can easily pass handrails or other obstacles and thus be taken out of the tram.

Figure 6 – Simulations of crew collision in Tramva Skoda 15 [17]

4. VIRTUAL MAINTENANCE APPLICATION STATUS

In recent years, it is noticeable that in many research papers, virtual maintenance has enabled more comprehensive applications, such as training of maintenance processes, assembly and disassembly processes, operational safety (by illustrating the safety conditions required before starting the maintenance procedures), product design, simulation and process analysis.

- Large aviation giants (Air France, Boeing, Air Bus) use VR maintenance systems for the purpose of training employees and operators of maintenance facilities in the "factories of the future", i.e. Smart Factories. Given that assets in smart factories are usually extremely expensive and sensitive, and that the hiring of experienced workers and experts requires additional material resources for training new workers, Virtual maintenance allows an individual to be trained for a specific task through interaction with a simulated environment. These training are accessible on-demand basis 24/7 and for multinationals, their staff can train themselves from any of their facilities anywhere around the globe. These tasks may include training, repair and maintenance service for specific equipment.
- VR improves maintenance safety of personnel in maintenance process in two aspects. First, VR can vividly simulate the maintenance of a product as it is already shown in part 3 of this paper. VR has been successfully used to help evaluate accessibility, radiation dose and fatigue. In the power industry, maintenance of high - voltage overhead power lines is high - risk and every accident can be fatal. Because of that maintenance workers must be well trained and skilled. Compared to traditional training methods that are based mainly on the use of 2D materials (pictures, manuals), virtual maintenance can significantly improve safety, efficiency and accessibility. Second, VR make easier the process of of the on-site maintenance task (real-time maintenance guidance[18], safety-related alerts and remote operations. [19] – [21])
- The integration of VR and maintainability is still sporadic. [21]

5. CONCLUSION

In the modern world, when we are going through another economic crisis, it is difficult to carry out maintenance training tasks not only because of high costs and long maintenance times, but often also because of the limitations of the working environment. As a result, and in order to carry out the employee educations and training in the maintenance of complex mechanical and electronic products, a virtual maintenance system based on the VR technique is applied. VR maintenance provides an abstract and immersive human-computer interface, which can be a very effective tool for employee education, spotting and predicting machine malfunctions, and plays a significant role in increasing safety, reducing costs, saving time, and preventing industrial process downtime.

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DIAGNOSTIC CONTROL OF THE TECHNICAL STATE OF AUTOMOTIVE AIR CONDITIONING SYSTEM

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Abstract: The paper primarily deals with the terms technical system, maintenance, failure and technical diagnostics. After that, the principle of operation of air conditioners in motor vehicles was given. At the end of the paper, the diagnostic control of the technical condition of the air conditioning system in the Opel Astra H car is presented.

Key words: technical system, maintenance, failure, technical diagnostics, automotive air conditioning system.

1. INTRODUCTION

A **technical system** means a machine or a plant, that is, an integrated set of elements interconnected so in order to form a whole with a unique operational function. Maintenance of technical systems is a set of technical and administrative procedures that are undertaken on the technical system during its lifetime with the aim of preventing the failure, as well as returning the system to operating condition after a failure, in a short time and with the lowest possible costs, on the existing environmental and organizational conditions [1]-[4]. **Failure** means the loss of the technical system's ability to perform the function for which it is intended, [3]. Failures of the technical system can be manifested in several ways, such as: the technical system (machine) does not work, the technical system works poorly, abnormal noise, high vibration level, high temperature and the like, [3].

Technical diagnostics represents a set of activities and procedures, which are carried out with the aim of evaluating (determining) the state of the technical system, with a certain accuracy at a certain moment of exploitation, for the purpose of making decisions about further maintenance activities or providing a forecast of the behavior of the state of the technical system in the future, [3]. The main goal of technical diagnostics is to detect or postpone a potential failure. This is achieved by measuring characteristic (diagnostic) parameters, and based on certain criteria, a conclusion is made as to whether they are within the permitted limits or not [5].

2. OPERATING PRINCIPLE OF AUTOMOTIVE AIR CONDITIONING SYSTEMS

An **automotive air conditioning system** is schematically shown in Figure 1 and is a set of components (condenser, drier, expansion valve, evaporator, fan and compressor) that work together to emit cool and dry air into the interior of the car to provide the driver and passengers with a comfortable and pleasant environment.

Refrigerant (freon) is a chemical that transfers heat as it circulates through the air conditioning system, absorbing heat when it turns into a gaseous state, and giving off heat when it turns into a liquid. In older cars, freon R-134a (HydroFluoroCarbon - HFC) is most often used as a coolant, and in newer cars, ecological freon R1234yf (HydroFluoroOlefin - HFO) is used.

Automotive air conditioning systems are used to produce and distribute cold or hot air inside the car and has two heat exchangers: a condenser and an evaporator, [6]. The high-pressure line of the automotive air conditioning system carries the warm, high-pressure gas from the compressor to the condenser, while

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the low-pressure line carries the cooler, low-pressure liquid from the expansion valve to the evaporator. **The compressor**, driven by a belt connected to the engine, is the most important component of the air conditioning system. The main function of the compressor is to compress, that is, to increase the pressure and temperature of the gas that goes on to the condenser.

Compressors are much like little engines. Most of them have pistons, piston rings, a crank shaft and bearings, just like a car engine. They need to have oil circulated through them to lubricate all the moving parts. This oil is mixed into, and carried with, the refrigerant. That is why running the air conditioner without any refrigerant is like running your car's engine without any oil, [7].

The purpose of **the condenser** as a heat exchanger is to reduce the temperature of the refrigerant and make it change from gaseous state to liquid, while remaining under high pressure.

Figure 1. Automotive air conditioning system

(left - <https://www.coolcaraircon.co.uk/maintain-your-car-aircon-system/>,
right - <https://autoelektroservis.wordpress.com/auto-klime/>)

A drier is a filter that removes moisture and impurities from the refrigerant before it reaches the evaporator. This is important because it prevents potential damage to all components in the system, which can be caused by moisture and water when they turn into ice crystals due to cooling. The moisture dryer is the last element in the high pressure system and is located between the condenser and the expansion valve. **The expansion valve** is the first element in the low pressure section. As the pressure decreases, expansion occurs, in which the liquid under high pressure turns into a mixture of gas and liquid that resembles a fog. Due to the lower pressure, the temperature decreased and the cooling fluid, i.e. the fog, goes further into the evaporator. The second heat exchanger in the automotive air conditioning system is the **evaporator**, which receives heat from the cabin air but does not release it. The warm air from the cabin passes over the evaporator which fills the cooled fluid, cools down and thus returns to the cabin as cold. When it absorbs heat, the refrigerant is returned to the compressor in a gaseous state and under low pressure, and the cycle begins again.

3. CHECKING THE ACCURACY AND CHARGING OF AIR CONDITIONING IN MOTOR VEHICLES

Regular maintenance of the car air conditioner includes vacuuming the entire system (extracting 90% of the old freon) and filling with new gas - freon (R134a or R1234yf), oil and UV dye. Regular maintenance enables the correct operation of the car air conditioner. Higher Education Technical School of Professional Studies in Novi Sad for technical diagnostics of air conditioning systems in cars

possesses a fully automatic A/C service station ECOTECHNICS ECK 1890, an electronic refrigerant gas (freon) leak detector and a UV lamp for detecting refrigerant gas (freon) leaks.

The most common causes of air conditioning failure in a car are coolant leaks (in any part of the system from the compressor to the evaporator), compressor failure, insufficient oil in the compressor, clogging of the system (mainly the condenser) and insufficient coolant.

When there is not enough gas in the car air conditioner, it is necessary to fill the air conditioner and inspect the entire system in order to establish other possible malfunctions, as well as the reason for the gas release. The consequence of the lack of gas is that the air conditioner cools inefficiently or does not cool at all.

The procedure for checking the accuracy and filling of the air conditioner on the vehicle consists of the following steps:

- **Technical documentation verification**

Before checking the amount of gas (freon), one should first find basic data about the air conditioning system in the technical documentation for each vehicle, such as: number and location of gas connections, type and amount of gas, type and amount of oil. Information on the type (freon R134a) and amount (450g) of gas for filling the car air conditioner for the Opel Astra H (2009 year, diesel engine 1.7 CDTi, power 74kW / 101 HP) can be found on the sticker under the hood of the vehicle's engine compartment (hood), Figure 2, or on the website – the data on the amount of gas for filling the car air conditioner (by model) <http://www.autoklimebebe.com/podaci-za-punjenje.php>.

Figure 2. Data on the type and amount of cooling freon on the Opel Astra H vehicle (own source)

- **Checking the state of the car air conditioner**

Before checking the condition of the car air conditioner, one should start the vehicle engine and turn on the air conditioner for a few minutes, then turn off the air conditioner and the vehicle alike. To check the pressure and fill the air conditioner, a service air conditioning station is used and it must contain the same type of gas as the air conditioner on the vehicle. Different types of gas must not be mixed. After locating the gas connections on the vehicle, the plugs are removed and the connection to the station is made using a high pressure hose (marked HP - High Pressure, red color) and a low pressure hose (marked LP - Low Pressure, blue color), Figure 3.

After connecting, the gas from the air conditioner on the vehicle goes to the service air conditioning station and the gas pressure is read on the pressure gauge in the idle state. Based on the results of the reading, further steps of work on the climate are determined. If the gas pressures and exhaust temperature are within the set values, the air conditioner on the vehicle is working properly. The rest pressure of the gas should be equal on both sides of the system (low pressure and high pressure) and the correct value ranges from 5 to 6 bar. If the pressure is lower, it means that the amount of gas is insufficient and

therefore the operation of the air conditioner is blocked. A slightly lower gas pressure was found in the Opel Astra H, so the air conditioning system needed to be filled.

Figure 3. Connected connections of the station to the air conditioning gas installation (own source)

- **Removing gas from the car air conditioner**

Prepare the service air conditioning station and the air conditioner on the vehicle for safe gas removal. Before extracting the gas, program the station for the entire process of vacuuming and charging the air conditioner.

When we are sure that the valves on the gas connections are properly closed, we select the make, the model and the year of manufacture of the vehicle at the air conditioning service station, and we automatically see the prescribed amount of refrigerant freon of 450g for the Opel Astra H vehicle on the display. In addition, the vacuuming time is set to last 25 minutes and that the system is automatically replenished with the required amount of oil, Figure 4.

Figure 4. Station programming for the entire process of vacuuming and filling the air conditioner (own source)

After that, the valves open and the process of emptying or removing the gas is activated, Figure 5. The gas from the air conditioner is transferred to the station where it is filtered, dried and stored in the bottle where the gas is under pressure.

Figure 5. Procedure for extracting gas from the air conditioner on the vehicle (own source)

- **Vacuumping the car air conditioner**

After removing the gas, we set the vacuuming of the system to last 25 minutes. Afterwards, the station automatically checks the firmness of the system by monitoring the vacuum condition for 2 minutes, Figure 6. When the system maintains a vacuum, the process of filling the air conditioner continues. If the system loses vacuum, stop the charging process and take action to find and repair the system leak. After the repair, the vacuuming procedure is repeated.

Figure 6. Procedure for vacuuming the air conditioner on the vehicle (own source)

- **Filling the car air conditioner**

The process of filling the air conditioning system in a motor vehicle is greatly simplified with this device because the process is fully automated. After vacuuming, the air conditioning system in the car is ready for charging. The air conditioning service station injects the specified amount of gas, and after the filling is complete, the filling automatically stops. At the very end of the filling process of the automotive air conditioning system, the service air conditioning station issues a report in printed form with accurate information that 315 g of refrigerant freon is missing, Figure 7. At the end of this procedure, the hoses for high and low pressure should be emptied so that we can turn off the service air conditioning station.

Figure 7. Procedure for filling the air conditioner on the vehicle (own source)

- **Checking the accuracy of the car air conditioner during operation**

After charging the air conditioner, by closing the valve at the station, the gas systems of the station and the air conditioner are separated. What is left is to check the correctness of the climate during operation. The engine starts and the air conditioner is turned on with maximum blow-out and the engine number is increased to start the compressor at full power. Checking the cooling temperature is done with a thermometer on the exhaust part of the vehicle itself, while the temperature should range from 5 to 7 degrees.

4. CONCLUSION

Diagnostics of the technical condition of motor vehicles is based on the application of various diagnostic controls in order to check the accuracy, working capacity and proper functioning, as well as finding the cause of malfunction (failure).

Depending on the method of diagnosis of a technical system (motor vehicle), diagnostic methods are divided into: subjective (sensory perception of the diagnostician) and objective (application of measuring devices and diagnostic equipment).

Along the side of the development of technical systems, the maintenance of those systems have also developed. Nowadays, technical diagnostics is the most important in monitoring and detecting possible failures and maintenance of technical systems in this case of motor vehicles.

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ANALYSIS AND PARAMETER SELECTION AS A FUNCTION OF VEHICLE OPERATION AND MAINTENANCE

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Abstract: Determining the output operational characteristics of the maintenance periodicity model is done by choosing the parameters of the state of diagnostics of the observed motor vehicles components, as well as choosing an adequate model and providing model input data. The permissible values of the condition parameter and the level of reliability, the structural incompatibility of motor vehicles to the concept of preventive maintenance, which must be solved at the stage of vehicle development, are done in the same way. In this way, the reliability of the developed diagnostic model of the condition of the observed motor vehicle components is confirmed in the precisely predicted intervals during their exploitation, whereby failure of the diagnostic components do not occur. With the observed analysis of component research, it is possible to predict the occurrence of breakdowns on vehicles in a timely manner and act preventively to eliminate potential breakdowns.

Key words: vehicles, components, diagnostics, bearings, measuring places, breakdowns.

1. INTRODUCTION

The best results are obtained by analyzing the assemblies of vehicle components or the process of parameter selection itself, and then the given parameters of the state of reliability diagnostics are considered favorable from the aspect of their applicability to specific cases. The analysis of the highest achieved values is considered the best. A certain parameter expresses an optimal value, when in conjunction with other components it offers a solution that gives the maximum value when it comes to the reliability analysis. Basically, The mere application of inadequate parameters does not provide the best solutions. The very values of given deviations from the optimal solution are possible and realistic due to incorrect assessment and inadequate selection of the main influential parameters.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS OF THE RESEARCH WORK

Diagnostic analysis requires the application of the following methods in determining the reliability parameters of components of motor vehicle assemblies i.e. specifically the method which defines the empirical functions of distribution density, failure intensity and component reliability as well as the method of selected statistical distribution of reliability parameters in which the reliability function and the failure intensity function simultaneously represent appropriate functions for collecting data on component failure parameters. By using methods of studying the process or components of the condition diagnostics system, supported by the information system, the conception of the selection of the most favorable parameters and models of the condition diagnostics is enabled.

The solution of various problems should be enabled by the method of analysis through the application of new technological procedures and the adoption of new technologies, equipment, devices, innovations, various production components, etc. [3].

This analysis provides a very important dimension and characteristic crucial for the successful functioning of the components of the Volvo - D7C 275 vehicle assemblies.

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The statistical method of distributing data about component failures from exploitation by measuring the temperature and wear of bearings, which is particularly interesting for this consideration, should include, along with the already highlighted features, parameters which describe continuous or other forms of change in the state of components of motor vehicle assemblies [2]. By applying the exploitation value, which expresses the approximate reliability values of the components of the analyzed motor vehicle assemblies with maximum safety, for their more precise determination, the given correction values were used.

This was aimed at obtaining the most accurate reliability values for the determination of the overall reliability transfer function of the components of the analyzed vehicle assemblies [8].

3. THE CHOICE OF CONDITION DIAGNOSTIC PARAMETERS

The most common condition diagnostics parameters can indicate the true condition of vehicle components. The selected parameters do not affect equally the condition of components of motor vehicle assemblies, so there is a need for a greater control over them. Owing to that, the case the condition of motor vehicles can be correctly predicted. The best way to choose the diagnostic parameters of the working process of motor vehicles lies in the analysis of all the information obtained about the operation of the constituent components of motor vehicle assemblies. The very analysis of the reliability of the observed components of vehicle assemblies with the help of statistical methods will enable their mutual correlation in order to determine the safety of their operation.

The conducted experimental analysis of component failure reliability values from operationally obtained data for Volvo vehicles - D7C 275, JGSP - Novi Sad, will be used in determining the service life of the observed components of the vehicle.

By using the analysis of the parameters of the reliability correction value $K_a(t)$, the results of the quotient of the density function of the distribution of $S_a(t)$ values were obtained and the function of the failure intensity $\lambda_a(t)$ for the time interval of the operational operation of the components of the assemblies (during the operation of the components of the assemblies of motor vehicles for the duration of $500000 \leq t_1 \leq 1000000$ km, (table 1), [9], and is determined by the formula [7] [4]:

$$K_a(t) = \frac{S_a(t)}{\lambda_a(t)} \quad (1)$$

The given analysis of the reliability of the components of the observed assemblies of motor vehicles with the application of preventive maintenance technology procedures, shows that [14]:

- obtained the highest reliability in the operation of the components M_1 , M_2 and M_3 whose maximum reliability is $K_{0-1}(t) = K_{1-2}(t) = K_{2-3}(t) \approx 1,0$ and lasts in the time interval over $\Delta t_1 \geq 1000000$ km.
- based on the shape of the curve $f(M_{1-3}(t), s)$, (figure 1), i.e. according to their slope, the sequence of reliability values is determined, which is shown [8]. The analysis itself included confidence intervals after the first smaller value than the maximum.

The order of measuring points for measuring the wear of crankshaft and camshaft bearings of the vehicle is (table 1) [1] [8]:

Measuring point 1 – crankshaft (stable bearing) – M_1

Measuring point 2 – camshaft (flying bearing) – M_2

Measuring point 3 – camshaft (slide bearing) – M_3

Table 1 The results of the shown values of reliability $K_i(t)$ and the spin path s (km) of composing components of Volvo Volvo – D7C 275, JGSP – Novi Sad on which the control of the state parameters of the components is applied

Time interval of components until breakdown	Spun path in composing components operation	Names and marks of composing components of motor vehicles	Values of reliability intervals $\Delta K_{0-1} < \Delta K_{1-2} < \Delta K_{2-3}$	Obtained values of reliability $K_{M_1} < K_{M_2} < K_{M_3}$
31.07.2020 ÷ 31.07.2022	500 000 – 1 200 000	Crankshaft (stable bearing) – M ₁	0,88 – 1,00	0,891
31.07.2020 ÷ 31.07.2022	500 000 – 1 200 000	Camshaft (flying bearings) – M ₂	0,91 – 1,00	0,914
31.07.2020 ÷ 31.07.2022	500 000 – 1 200 000	Camshaft – M ₃	0,95 – 1,00	0,957

By observing the shape of the curves of the reliability correction values of the composing components of the analyzed assemblies Posmatranjem $K_i(t)$, tj. according to the slope of the curves, reliability intervals can be analytically predicted, which later is to be used as a basis for determining the authoritative reliability of figure 1 [7] (values from table 1 - reliability obtained from statistical distribution).

Figure 1 Graph of reliability correction values $K_i(t)$ of components of vehicle assemblies based on the operational data of the distance s (km) on which the control of parameters of Volvo state diagnostics was applied - D7C 275, JGSP - Novi Sad

4 RESEARCH RESULTS OF BEARING PERFORMANCE

By analyzing the observed moment of the deviation of the basic characteristics of the components of motor vehicles from the permitted values, it is very important that the selected state parameters fully define the condition of the components of motor vehicles. As a basis for the selection of parameters, it is important that their number should be as small as possible. The calculated reliability correction values will be presented in tables (table 2), and the result is the application of the selected lognormal statistical reliability distribution shown in Figure 2 [6], [3].

Table 2 - The results of the parameters $g(t)$, z , μ , σ , K_a in the case of a lognormal distribution reliability of components of motor vehicles (M_1 , M_2 and M_3) – Volvo – D7C 275, JGSP – Novi Sad [8]

Time interval of components until breakdown	Spun path of the composing components	The name of the composing components of motor vehicles	$g_{N_1}(t)$	z	φ	σ	$K_{a_i}(t) = \varphi(z)$	$R_a(t)$
31.07.2020 ÷ 31.07.2022	500 000 – 1200 000	Crankshaft (stable bearings) M_1	$1,291 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0,13	1,391	4,021	0,889	0,731
31.07.2020 ÷ 31.07.2022	500 000 – 1200 000	Crankshaft (flying bearings) M_2	$1,103 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0,12	1,172	3,362	0,913	0,783
31.07.2020 ÷ 31.07.2022	500 000 – 1200 000	camshaft M_3	$1,047 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0,09	1,095	2,404	0,957	0,816

Figure 2 - Graph of shown reliability values $K_a(t)$, distance (spun path) s (km) of the components in the area of exploitation operation at the measuring point M_1 of motor vehicles – Volvo – D7C 275, JGSP – Novi Sad

By comparing the maximum or minimum of some reliability function of the components, the application of the optimal value obtained by the selection of parameters can be shown. The obtained values of working variables, which are adjusted and changed at the same time, can ensure the optimal value of certain parameters, i.e. will be taken as optimal conditions.

By determining the optimal criteria, the obtained results can be linear or approximately linear, constantly increasing or decreasing, without a pronounced maximum or minimum of the function. Also, some optimum of the expressed value increases or decreases with the increase or decrease of the influential quantity. The research of this increase or decrease goes to the limits of what is possible for certain parameters of vehicle components.

The analysis of the state diagnostics and its impact on vehicle reliability is a way of choosing the best parameter among several possible alternatives. It means that it refers to each component of the vehicle assembly separately, i.e. that organizing the optimal process of application of the parameters of the state of the components includes several components of the assemblies. It is about showing the state of the vehicle through the state of the composing components of the assemblies, and for that it is necessary to have as much information as possible, both about the motor vehicle as a whole, and for the constituent components of the assemblies [5].

According to the observed research, we establish that the components of the Volvo D7C 275 vehicle (picture 3) are: crankshaft (stable bearings) M₁, crankshaft (flying bearings) M₂, camshaft M₃ and they all have a minimum number of failures, and for that reason they are not recorded in tabular review [2].

An overview has been made (in table 3) covering all failures that occurred due to elevated temperature and wear of bearings at the measuring points of the analyzed assemblies (Figure 2) of the Volvo D7C 275 vehicle, JGSP - NIŠ and JGSP - NOVI SAD, i.e. of their composing components [4] [6]. Table 1 presents the recorded failures where parameters of the condition of vehicle components were not applied.

Table 3 - The results of the distance covered (km) and the number of component failures of motor vehicle assemblies - Volvo D7C 275 - JGSP - Novi Sad

Spun path in composing components operation	Names and marks of composing components of motor vehicles	The number of failures on which the states of parameter components are not applied	The number of failures on which the states of parameter components are applied
$\Delta s_i < \Delta t < \Delta s_n$	Motor vehicle garage number	882 – 906	882 – 906
500 000 – 1 200 000	Crankshaft (fixed bearings) – M ₁	47	18
500 000 – 1 200 000	Crankshaft (floating bearings) – M ₂	44	13
500 000 – 1 200 000	Camshaft – M ₃	29	8

Table 3 shows the performance results of the components of the Volvo D7C 275 vehicle, obtained by observing the distance traveled and monitoring the number of failures in the period from July, 31st 2020 until July, 31st .2022. After applying the model, almost every component had a failure (their reliability was maximum).

Table 4 shows the performance results of the components of the vehicle, obtained by monitoring the distance traveled at the measuring points M₁, M₂ and M₃ (Figure 2), as well as by measuring the number of failures on 128 observed components of Volvo D7C 275 motor vehicles. The results were achieved with or without applying the control parameters of the diagnostics of the state of the components.

Determining the problem of optimal periodicity of implementation of maintenance procedures, the simulation method was used, i.e. experimenting with the model in which the processes take place at a certain time interval, in order to determine the optimal output operational characteristics of the maintenance model.

The output operational characteristics of the condition diagnostics model are the optimal intervals of preventive maintenance by time, the allowed values of the condition parameters and the upper limits of the regulation of the level of reliability of motor vehicle components. The outputs provided by the model are the result of the performance of the components being simulated, i.e. process of changing the condition and maintenance of motor vehicles.

By performing a certain number of failures caused by increased changes in temperature and wear of bearings on the components of the observed vehicle assemblies M₁, M₂ and M₃ (shown in Figure 2.) in a given period of exploitation, has shown that the first failures appeared around the 500,000 km of its operation and that on components on which the parameters of the component condition were not applied and close to 1200000 km of work on the ones these procedures were carried out [9].

The very characteristics of the failure values of the components of the observed vehicle assemblies, the components were classified according to the number of failures in the obtained risk groups. This indicates that in the analysis of the safety of functioning, more frequent measurements should be made at the measuring points that include the operation of the mentioned components on the Volvo D7C 275 and D9B vehicles. 340 (table 4).

The analysis of the failures caused by the increase in temperature changes and the wear of the bearings at the measurement points of the observed assemblies of motor vehicles where the control of the parameters of the state of the components was not applied, as well as the failures where the parameters of the state of the components were applied, are shown in table 4. (the model on the components of the assemblies vehicles was used).

Tabela 4 Prikazani rezultati pređenog puta s (km) sa mernim mestima M_1 , M_2 and M_3 and broj otkaza komponenata sklopova motornih vozila – Volvo D7C 275, JGSP – Novi Sad

The spun path by the components of motor vehicles (km)		Number of failures according to measurement points of JGSP (public transport vehicles) – Novi Sad		
		M_1 – fixed bearings	M_2 – floating bearings	M_3 – sliding bearings
Garage number		881 – 905	881 – 905	881 – 905
500 000	Without	2	3	2
550 000	applying	4	5	3
600 000	condition	5	5	4
650 000	diagnostics	6	5	4
700 000	parameters	8	6	4
750 000		9	8	4
800 000		10	8	4
850 000		2	2	1
900 000		2	2	1
950 000	With	3	2	1
1 000 000	applying	3	3	2
1 050 000	condition	4	3	2
1 100 000	diagnostics	4	4	2
1 200 000	parameters	4	4	2

Figure 3 Arrangement and numbering of the marked measuring points on the assembly of the elbow and camshaft and connecting rod with marked measuring points M_1 , M_2 and M_3 – Volvo D7C 275, JGSP (Public Transport Vehicles) – Novi Sad [4] [8]

The analyses of preventive maintenance procedures can be carried out during the period of operation of crankshaft bearings, and failures occur without exception, at the time of engine operation, and there are a large number of factors that affect reliability and performance in further operation. For this reason, when a failure occurs relatively soon after engine repair, failure testing must also be considered in the repair procedure: cleaning, assembly, selection and origin of parts, oil, engine starting method, and operating conditions during the engine's operating period.

5. RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND RESULT FINDINGS

Some empirical research studies have made it possible to easily determine the optimal value of diagnostics of the state of components of motor vehicles, for which it is necessary to know the law of distribution of working time until failure. The results obtained by computer simulations show that all correlations in operating conditions depend on the choice of parameters, as well as on the performance of the observed components. This affirms the reliability of the developed model as well as the reliability of the developed model algorithm. By performing diagnostics of the condition of the observed components of motor vehicles at precisely predicted intervals during their exploitation, we have noticed no failure of the diagnostic components. Also we have noticed that by reducing the number of cancellations, maintenance costs are also reduced. We have concluded that in order to obtain reliable values, it is necessary to apply the appropriate parameters of the state of operation of the components. In the case of carrying out the vehicle condition diagnostics procedure, all important and necessary influencing parameters of the condition diagnostics that satisfy all important criteria have been taken into account. The selected parameters, manifested through the improvement of the surface quality and the change in the size of the gap, $z_{M_1, M_2 \min} = 0,012(mm)$, $z_{M_1, M_2 \max} = 0,021(mm)$, $z_{M_3 \min} = 0,011(mm)$, $z_{M_3 \max} = 0,013(mm)$ record a 14.2% reduction in the percentage of medium size, which justifies their introduction. By applying the same, i.e. by reducing the oil recycling interval and constant filtering, the operating temperature interval is maintained $94^\circ C \div 96^\circ C$, while without applying the parameters it is $95^\circ C \div 99.5^\circ C$, the temperature range decreased by 4.05%, which justifies the introduction of these parameters.

Non-compatibility of the quality of the surface and clearance, that is, by applying the parameters of diagnostics of the state of motor vehicles, the wear of the bearings is reduced, i.e. their extreme values by 15.35%. By including parameters in the diagnostic procedure (oil and filter replacement), the operating temperature range of $94.4^\circ C \div 96^\circ C$, is maintained, and without the application of parameters it is $95^\circ C \div 95.5^\circ C$, i.e. by 7.3%, which also justifies the introduction of this parameter [6] [11]. By introducing the model with the application of the parameters of the state diagnostic procedures in the period from July, 31st, 2020 to July, 31st. 2022., along with the distance covered (km), there is a reduction in the occurrence of failures caused by bearing wear by 3.9%, i.e. based on the given model, the values of relevant clearances can be reduced [11] [14].

Applying diagnostics of the state of bearings and engine oil in operation, it is of great importance for the assessment of the condition of the oil and for the assessment of the state of the bearings, that is, the components of the vehicle. This is the way to confirm the correctness of the developed diagnostic model of the condition of the observed components of motor vehicles in the precisely predicted intervals during their exploitation, in which no failure of the diagnostic components occurred. Based on the analysis of engine oil research, it is possible to predict the occurrence of breakdowns on vehicles in a timely manner and act preventively to eliminate potential breakdowns.

6. CONCLUSION

We have done an analysis of the determination of the degree of safety and parameters, which represents one of the most promising and economical methods of managing the processes of changing the condition and maintaining motor vehicles. The use of the developed state diagnostics model based on this concept, significant effects are achieved in terms of ensuring the required level of reliability and availability of motor vehicles, while reducing maintenance costs. The choice of the level of safety and parameters could not be a general

solution for organizing the optimal process of state diagnostics of motor vehicles as very complex systems, and having wished to form a state diagnostics model that would include all the characteristics of a real system, this inevitably led to the inclusion in the state diagnostics model of time. The very use of the state diagnostics model allows to solve two main types of problems of the preventive maintenance methodology according to reliability: the first one based on the observation of the stochastic process of state parameter change (on the basis of recorded failures in the case of application of state diagnostics parameter control), and the second one based on information about the function distribution operation time until failure (in the case when the failure intensity function in the time base has a decreasing character).

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ADR TRANSPORT OF FLAMMABLE LIQUIDS IN LIMITED QUANTITIES AND EXCEPTED QUANTITIES

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Abstract: In this paper, the applicability of the provisions and transport conditions of selected examples of Class 3 dangerous goods in limited and/or exempted quantities, was analyzed. It was assumed that the applicability of the provisions of ADR transport in excepted and limited quantities depends on the dangerous properties of the substance and the degree of danger it may cause during transport. Based on the results obtained in the series of Class 3 dangerous goods (motor gasoline, kerosene, methanol, ethanol, carbon disulfide, diethyl ether), it can be considered that the properties of dangerous goods, primarily volatility (flammability, flash point/flash evaporation) as and the corresponding degree of danger that these substances cause in transport; significantly affect the applicability of the provisions for transporting those substances in limited and/or excepted quantities; and also on the conditions under which it is allowed. The ADR class and the classification code of dangerous goods predetermine the conditions of transport of selected examples of dangerous goods of Class 3: Flammable liquids in limited and/or excepted quantities. Compliance with the prescribed conditions during the transport of the considered examples of Class 3: Flammable liquids can be considered to increase the safety of vehicles and all traffic and, at the same time, reduce the risk of transport accidents.

Keywords: dangerous goods, ADR, flammable liquids, excepted and limited quantities, volatility, degree of physical danger, safe transport conditions

1. INTRODUCTION

Regardless of the dangers they cause, hazardous substances are increasingly used both in the economy and in everyday life [1]. Annually, significant quantities of dangerous goods are produced and transported, which causes the creation of high risks for human life and health, the environment, and material goods [1], especially in the case of their transportation contrary to the rules and provisions of the Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road (hereinafter: ADR) [2]. It is impossible to imagine modern society without the transportation of dangerous goods, where the safe transportation of hazardous substances is of particular importance.

Dangerous goods are substances and objects whose transport is prohibited, i.e. permitted if it is carried out under the conditions according to ADR [2]. Dangerous cargo is dangerous goods that are properly packed, marked with certain markings and markings, with correctly filled out transport documents, and loaded into a means of transport [2]. Dangerous goods mean, in the broadest practical sense, all those substances and objects, which in the production process or during transport and handling can cause damage to human health and/or the environment. So, these are all those products, semi-products, raw materials, and waste materials that can pose a threat life and health of people. These substances can also cause environmental risk/contamination [1-4].

Selected dangerous goods packed in small quantities (limited quantity) or very small volumes (excepted quantity) pose a lesser risk in transport than do the same goods packed in larger volumes [2,5,6].

Thus they qualify for some relief from robust packaging requirements provided that they are packed and marked properly [2,5]. This could save considerable packaging costs [2,5,6].

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The carriage of Class 3: Flammable liquids (as dangerous goods in road transport) is a very common way of transporting dangerous substances that are widely used as motor fuels, chemicals, and raw materials for the chemical and oil-petrochemical industry. Very widely used representatives of Class 3: Flammable liquids in terms of motor fuels, originating from the oil industry, are motor gasoline, diesel fuel, and kerosene [3]. Very widely used representatives of Class 3: Flammable liquids in terms of industrial chemicals and raw materials/products of the oil and petrochemical industry, are diethyl ether, acetone, methanol, carbon disulfide, ethanol, paints, varnishes, glues, coatings, etc. [3].

In this paper, the applicability of the provisions and transport conditions of selected examples of Class 3 dangerous goods in limited and/or exempted quantities, was analyzed. It was assumed that the applicability of the ADR transport provisions of dangerous goods in excepted and limited quantities depends on the dangerous properties of that substance (class and subclass of dangerous goods) and the degree of danger (classification code) that it can cause during transport [2].

2. FLAMMABLE LIQUIDS

The heading of Class 3: Flammable liquids covers substances and articles containing substances of this Class which [2]:

- Are liquids according to subparagraph (a) of the definition for "liquid" in 1.2.1 of ADR ("Liquid" means a substance which at 50°C has a vapor pressure of not more than 300 kPa (3 bar), which is not completely gaseous at 20°C and 101.3 kPa, and which [2]:

(a) Has a melting point or initial melting point of 20 °C or less at a pressure of 101.3 kPa; or

(b) Is liquid according to the ASTM D 4359-90 test method; or

(c) Is not pasty according to the criteria applicable to the test for determining fluidity - penetrometer test, described in 2.3.4 of ADR)).

- Have at 50°C a vapor pressure of not more than 300 kPa (3 bar) and are not completely gaseous at 20°C and at a standard pressure of 101.3 kPa; and
- Have a flash-point of not more than 60°C.

The heading of Class 3 also covers liquid substances and molten solid substances with a flash-point of more than 60°C which are carried or handed over for carriage whilst heated at temperatures equal to or higher than their flash-point [2].

The substances and articles of Class 3 are subdivided as follows [2]:

- F - Flammable liquids, without subsidiary hazard and articles containing such substances:
- F1 - Flammable liquids having a flash-point of or below 60°C;
- F2 - Flammable liquids having a flash-point above 60°C which are carried or handed over for carriage at or above their flash-point (elevated temperature substances);
- F3 - Articles containing flammable liquids;
- FT - Flammable liquids, toxic:
- FT1 - Flammable liquids, toxic;
- FT2 - Pesticides;
- FC - Flammable liquids, corrosive;
- FTC - Flammable liquids, toxic, corrosive;
- D - Liquid desensitized explosives.

Substances and articles classified in Class 3 are listed in Table A: Dangerous Goods List in Chapter 3.2. of ADR [2].

Flammable liquids shall be assigned to one of the following packing groups according to the degree of danger they present for carriage [2].

3. ADR'S DEFINITION OF LIMITED QUANTITY AND EXCEPTED QUANTITY

The limited quantity is the maximum quantity per inner packaging or article for transporting dangerous goods in limited quantities [2,5,6]. It can be found in the column 7a of Table A: Dangerous Goods List [2].

The excepted quantity is the maximum quantity per inner and outer packaging for transporting dangerous goods as excepted quantities [2,5,6]. The quantity limit can be found in the column 7b of Table A: Dangerous Goods List [2]. Column 7b does not directly list the maximum quantity per inner and outer packaging. Instead, 7b gives various E codes (E0~E5) (Table 1 [2,5]).

Table 1 – Excepted quantities provisions (E codes)

Code	Maximum net quantity per inner packaging (in grams for solids and ml for liquids and gases)	Maximum net quantity per outer packaging (in grams for solids and ml for liquids and gases, or the sum of grams and ml in the case of mixed packing)
E0	Not permitted as Excepted Quantity	
E1	30	1000
E2	30	500
E3	30	300
E4	1	500
E5	1	300

3.1. Limitations and labeling requirements for dangerous goods transported in limited quantities or excepted quantities

Even for dangerous goods transported in limited quantities or excepted quantities, there is some packaging and labeling (Table 2 [5]).

Table 2 – Provisions for the transport of dangerous goods in limited quantities or excepted quantities

No.	Provisions for limited quantities	Provisions for excepted quantities
1.	Goods must be carried in small containers (e.g., bottles), which are then packed in boxes or on shrink-wrapped trays	UN-approved packages are not required
2.	Packages must pass certain performance test requirements (less stringent than UN-approved packages);	Dangerous goods hazard symbols are not required;
3.	The maximum gross weight is 30 kgs for boxes or 20kgs for shrink-wrapped trays;	Packages must pass drop tests and stacking tests;
4.	Outer packages must bear a limited quantities mark (see Picture 1 [2]) and hazard symbols;	The total number of packages carried on any one cargo transport unit shall not exceed 1000;
5.	Dangerous goods transported in limited quantities must be communicated in a shipping document.	Outer package must bear excepted quantities mark;
6.	/	A statement "Dangerous Goods in Excepted Quantities" and several packages shall be included in a shipping document.

3.2. Limited quantities and excepted quantities marking

Limited quantities and excepted quantities marking for ADR dangerous goods are shown in Figure 1 [2].

Figure 1 Limited quantities and excepted quantities marking

4. CONSIDERATION OF THE IMPACT OF CLASS AND CLASSIFICATION CODE ON THE APPLICABILITY OF TRANSPORTATION OF SELECTED EXAMPLES OF FLAMMABLE LIQUIDS IN LIMITED AND EXCEPTED QUANTITIES

The influence of class and classification code on the applicability of transport of selected examples of flammable liquids, in excepted and limited quantities, is shown in Table 3. To determine the mutual influence of the observed terms, Table A: Dangerous Goods List, chapter 3.2 of ADR was used, but also individual parts of ADR [2] as a whole.

Table 3 – Applicability of transport provisions in limited and excepted quantities for a series of flammable liquids

No.	UN number	Name of dangerous good	Class (description, degree of flammability) of dangerous good	Classification Code	Transportation in limited quantities (l)	E Code for carriage in excepted aggregates
1.	1203	Gasoline or petrol	Class 3 Flammable liquids with an ignition temperature below 23°C and a boiling point above 35°C.	F1 Flammable liquids have a flash-point of or below 60 °C.	1	E2
2.	1223	Kerosene	Class 3 Liquids with a flash point above 23°C but not above 61°C and a boiling point above 35°C.	F1 Flammable liquids have a flash-point of or below 60 °C.	5	E1
3.	1155	Diethyl ether	Class 3 Highly flammable liquids with a boiling point below 35°C.	F1 Flammable liquids have a flash-point of or below 60 °C.	0	E3
4.	1090	Acetone	Class 3 Flammable liquids with an ignition temperature below 23°C and a boiling point above 35°C.	F1 Flammable liquids have a flash-point of or below 60 °C.	1	E2
5.	1230	Methanol	Class 3 Flammable liquids with an ignition temperature below 23°C and a boiling point above 35°C.	FT1 Flammable liquids, toxic.	1	E2
6.	1131	Carbon disulfide	Class 3 Highly flammable liquids with a boiling point below 35°C.	FT1 Flammable liquids, toxic.	0	E0
7.	1170	Ethanol	Class 3 Liquids with a flash point above 23°C but not above 61°C and a boiling point above 35°C.	FT1 Flammable liquids, toxic.	1	E2

Based on the results obtained in the considered series of dangerous goods of Class 3 (motor gasoline, kerosene, methanol, ethanol, carbon disulfide, diethyl ether) it can be considered that the volatility (and associated flammability, flash point) and the associated degree of danger, which these substances cause in transport; significantly affect the applicability of the transporting provisions for those substances in limited and/or excepted quantities; and also on the conditions under which it is allowed.

Considered substances with a higher degree of flammability can be transported in smaller, limited quantities (Table 3), except for carbon disulfide, the transport of which in limited quantities is prohibited.

The transport of all considered dangerous substances (Table 3) is permitted in excepted quantities, whereby the quantities of substances per inner and outer packaging differ significantly depending on their transport properties and classification code.

Therefore, the ADR class and the dangerous goods classification code predetermine the permitted conditions of transport of selected examples of dangerous goods of Class 3: Flammable liquids in limited quantities and/or excepted quantities.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained in the considered series of flammable liquids, it can be considered that the applicability of the terms and conditions of ADR transport of dangerous goods in excepted and/or limited quantities depends on the dangerous properties of that substance (class and subclass of dangerous goods) and the degree of danger (classification code) that the same, can cause during transport.

From the aspect of preventing transport accidents, it is very advantageous if the transport of certain dangerous goods, belonging to Class 3: Flammable liquids, is allowed in limited and/or excepted quantities.

Selected dangerous goods packed in small quantities (limited quantity) or very small volumes (excepted quantity) pose a lesser risk in transport than do the same goods packed in larger volumes.

The further course of work could include a more detailed study of the requirements for transport packaging used for the transport of flammable liquids, depending on the prescribed packaging group, finding the connection between transport in limited and/or excepted quantities and the type of transport packaging, etc.

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ADR CLASSIFICATION CODE AND PACKAGING GROUP OF FLAMMABLE LIQUIDS AS DANGEROUS GOODS

Matilda Lazić¹ Miodrag Kovačević²

Abstract: In this paper, the influence of the class on the determination of the classification code and packaging group of dangerous goods in road transport is presented. In the selected series of dangerous substances, which belong to Class 3: Flammable liquids, the impact of the dangerous properties of the substance on the classification code and packaging group will be shown. It was assumed that the class of dangerous goods predetermines the classification code and group of packaging because dangerous substances and objects are classified in the ADR class of dangerous goods according to their properties (flammability, ignition temperature, ignition temperature) and the degree of physical danger; they could represent during road carriage. For the observed series of dangerous substances that belong to Flammable liquids, it can be considered that the classification code and packaging group differ depending on the degree of their volatility, i.e., flammability (boiling temperature/flash evaporation or ignition) and consequently, the degree of danger (primarily physical, but also dangers to human life and health and the environment) that these substances can cause during transport. Knowing the physical properties and degree of danger, as well as indicators that indirectly depend on them (classification code) and further classification into the appropriate packaging group significantly contributes to determining the safe and only permitted conditions for the transport of flammable liquids as a very common class of dangerous goods in road.

Keywords: dangerous goods, ADR, flammable liquids, volatility, degree of physical danger, classification code, packing group, safe transport conditions

1. INTRODUCTION

Regardless of the dangers they cause, hazardous substances are increasingly used both in the economy and in everyday life [1]. Annually, significant quantities of dangerous goods are produced and transported, which causes the creation of high risks for human life and health, the environment, and material goods [1], especially in the case of their transportation contrary to the rules and provisions of the Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road (hereinafter: ADR) [2]. It is impossible to imagine modern society without the transportation of dangerous goods, where the safe transportation of hazardous substances is of particular importance.

Transportation of dangerous goods should be approached with special caution, knowing in detail all properties of hazardous materials, i.e. dangerous goods, and choosing appropriate means of carriage. By determining the general conditions for the safe transport of dangerous goods and educating persons who are in direct contact with dangerous substances and/or participate in transport activities, the risks of transport accidents are reduced and, consequently, the safety of road traffic is increased.

Dangerous goods are substances and objects whose transport is prohibited, i.e. permitted if it is carried out under the conditions according to ADR [2]. Dangerous cargo is dangerous goods that are properly packed, marked with certain markings, with correctly filled out transport documents, and loaded into a means of transport [2]. Dangerous goods mean, in the broadest practical sense, all those substances and objects, which in the production process or during transport and handling can cause damage to human health and/or the environment. So, these are all those products, semi-products, raw materials, and waste materials that can pose a threat life and health of people. These substances can also cause environmental contamination [1-4].

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The carriage of flammable liquids as dangerous goods in road transport is a very common way of transporting dangerous substances, which are widely used as motor fuels, chemicals, and raw materials for the chemical and oil-petrochemical industry. Very widely used representatives of the class of dangerous goods called flammable liquids in terms of motor fuels, originating from the oil industry, are motor gasoline, diesel fuel, and kerosene [3]. Very widely used representatives of the class of dangerous goods called flammable liquids in terms of industrial chemicals and raw materials/products of the oil and petrochemical industry, are diethyl ether, acetone, methanol, carbon disulfide, ethanol, paints, varnishes, glues, coatings, etc. [3].

In this paper, the influence of the class on the determination of the classification code and packaging group of dangerous goods in road transport is presented. In the selected series of dangerous substances, belonging to Class 3: flammable liquids, the influence of the dangerous properties of the substance on the classification code and packaging group will be shown. It was assumed that the class of dangerous goods predetermines the classification code and packaging group because dangerous substances and objects are classified in the ADR class of dangerous goods according to their properties (flammability, ignition temperatures, ignition temperatures); and the degree of physical danger they could represent during road carriage [2].

2. FLAMMABLE LIQUIDS

The heading of Class 3: Flammable liquids covers substances and articles containing substances of this Class which [2]:

- Are liquids according to subparagraph (a) of the definition for "liquid" in 1.2.1 of ADR ("Liquid" means a substance which at 50°C has a vapor pressure of not more than 300 kPa (3 bar), which is not completely gaseous at 20°C and 101.3 kPa, and which [2]:

(a) Has a melting point or initial melting point of 20 °C or less at a pressure of 101.3 kPa; or

(b) Is liquid according to the ASTM D 4359-90 test method; or

(c) Is not pasty according to the criteria applicable to the test for determining fluidity - penetrometer test, described in 2.3.4 of ADR)).

- Have at 50°C a vapor pressure of not more than 300 kPa (3 bar) and are not completely gaseous at 20°C and at a standard pressure of 101.3 kPa; and
- Have a flash-point of not more than 60°C.

The heading of Class 3 also covers liquid substances and molten solid substances with a flash-point of more than 60°C which are carried or handed over for carriage whilst heated at temperatures equal to or higher than their flash-point [2].

The substances and articles of Class 3 are subdivided as follows [2]:

- F - Flammable liquids, without subsidiary hazard and articles containing such substances:
- F1 - Flammable liquids having a flash-point of or below 60°C;
- F2 - Flammable liquids having a flash-point above 60°C which are carried or handed over for carriage at or above their flash-point (elevated temperature substances);
- F3 - Articles containing flammable liquids;
- FT - Flammable liquids, toxic:
- FT1 - Flammable liquids, toxic;
- FT2 - Pesticides;
- FC - Flammable liquids, corrosive;
- FTC - Flammable liquids, toxic, corrosive;
- D - Liquid desensitized explosives.

Substances and articles classified in Class 3 are listed in Table A: Dangerous Goods List in Chapter 3.2. of ADR [2]. Substances not mentioned by name in Table A: Dangerous Goods List shall be assigned to the relevant entry of 2.2.3.3 of ADR and the relevant packing group by the provisions of this section [2].

Flammable liquids shall be assigned to one of the following packing groups according to the degree of danger they present for carriage (Table 1) [2].

Table 1 – Packaging groups for Flammable liquids according to the degree of danger they represent in ADR carriage

Packing group	Flashpoint (closed cup)	Initial boiling point
I	/	≤ 35°C
II	< 23°C	> 35°C
III	≥23°C ≤ 60°C	> 35°C

2.1.ADR class of dangerous goods, classification code, and packing group by Table A: Dangerous Goods List

Explanatory notes for Column (3a) "Class"; Column (3b) "Classification code"; Column (4) "Packing group" (Table A: Dangerous Goods List in chapter 3.2 of ADR [2]) that is, the term of interest for this paper.

Column (3a) "Class". Contains the number of the class, whose heading covers the dangerous substance or article. This class number is assigned by the procedures and criteria of Part 2., ADR [2].

Column (3b) "Classification code". Contains the classification code of the dangerous substance or article. For dangerous substances or articles of Classes 3 the codes are explained in 2.2.x.1.21, ADR [2].

Column (4) "Packing group". Contains the packing group number(s) (I, II, or III) assigned to the dangerous substance. These packing group numbers are assigned based on the procedures and criteria of Part 2. (section 2.1.1.3, ADR [2]). Packing group - the group into which, for packaging, certain substances are classified based on their degree of danger during carriage [2].

Packing groups have the following meaning [2]:

- Packing group I: Substances of high danger;
- Packing group II: Substances of medium danger;
- Packing group III: Substances of low danger.

In the next chapter of this paper, the influence of hazard class, classification code, and packaging group will be considered on selected examples (series) of dangerous substances, which belong to Class 3: Flammable liquids.

3. CONSIDERATION OF THE INFLUENCE OF THE HAZARD CLASS ON THE CHOICE OF CLASSIFICATION CODE AND PACKING GROUP ON A SERIES OF SUBSTANCES BELONGING TO FLAMMABLE LIQUIDS

The influence of the ADR dangerous class on the choice of classification code and packaging group on the selected series of dangerous substances, which belong to Class 3: Flammable liquids, is shown in Table 2. To determine the mutual influence of the observed terms, Table A: Dangerous Goods List, chapter 3.2 of ADR was used, but also individual parts of ADR [2] as a whole.

Table 2 – Relationship between class, classification code, and packing group for selected examples (considered series) of flammable liquids

No.	UN number	Name of dangerous good	Class (description, degree of flammability) of dangerous good	Classification Code	Packing group
1.	1203	Gasoline or Oto motor fuel	Class 3 Flammable liquids with an ignition temperature below 23°C and a boiling point above 35°C.	F1 Flammable liquids have a flash-point of or below 60 °C.	II Substances of medium danger
2.	1223	Kerosene	Class 3 Liquids with a flash point above 23°C but not above 61°C and a boiling point above 35°C.	F1 Flammable liquids have a flash-point of or below 60 °C.	III Substances of low-danger
3.	1155	Diethyl ether	Class 3 Highly flammable liquids with a boiling point below 35°C.	F1 Flammable liquids have a flash-point of or below 60 °C.	I Substances of high danger
4.	1090	Acetone	Class 3 Flammable liquids with an ignition temperature below 23°C and a boiling point above 35°C.	F1 Flammable liquids have a flash-point of or below 60 °C.	II Substances of medium danger
5.	1230	Methanol	Class 3 Flammable liquids with an ignition temperature below 23°C and a boiling point above 35°C.	FT1 Flammable liquids, toxic.	II Substances of medium danger
6.	1131	Carbon disulfide	Class 3 Highly flammable liquids with a boiling point below 35°C.	FT1 Flammable liquids, toxic.	I Substances of high danger
7.	1170	Ethanol	Class 3 Liquids with a flash point above 23°C but not above 61°C and a boiling point above 35°C.	FT1 Flammable liquids, toxic.	III Substances of low-danger

For the observed series of flammable liquids, the classification code and packaging group differ depending on the degree of their volatility, that is, their flammability and, consequently, the degree of danger that the substance can cause during transport. The classification code results from the further division of Class 3: Flammable liquids according to flammability and ignition temperature.

Flammability and flash point are physical properties of hazardous substances that directly depend on the volatility of that liquid substance. In this way, the degree of volatility affects the classification of certain dangerous goods into the appropriate class and subclass of danger with the corresponding classification code and group of packaging for transport by vehicles in road transport. Easier washable substances Class 3: Flammable liquids have a classification code that indicates a very low flash-point and, consequently, a higher degree of danger, which they can cause in transport. Certain substances from the observed series are also toxic, in addition to being easily flammable, which may affect the classification in the packaging group, but it does not have to be considered as a rule.

The label for examples of Class 3: Flammable liquids (given in Table 2) is shown in Table 3 [2].

Table 3 – The label for examples of Class 3: Flammable liquids (given in Table 2)

No.	UN number	Name of dangerous good	Label (appearance and description)
1.	1203	Gasoline or Oto motor fuel	<p>Number 3</p> <p>Symbol (flame): black or white. Base: red. Number 3 in the bottom corner.</p>
2.	1223	Kerosene	
3.	1155	Diethyl ether	
4.	1090	Acetone	
5.	1230	Methanol	
6.	1131	Carbon disulfide	
7.	1170	Ethanol	

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained for the observed series of dangerous substances, that belong to flammable liquids, it can be considered that the classification code and packaging group differ depending on the degree of their volatility, i.e., flammability (boiling temperature/flash evaporation or ignition) and consequently, the degree of danger (primarily physical, but also dangers to the life and health of people and the environment) that these substances can cause during transport. Knowing the physical properties and degree of danger, as well as indicators that indirectly depend on them (classification code) and further classification into the appropriate group of packaging significantly contributes to determining the safe and only permitted conditions for transporting flammable liquids as a very common class of dangerous goods in road transport.

The further course of work could include a more detailed study of the requirements for transport packaging used for the transport of flammable liquids, depending on the prescribed packaging group, etc.

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MODERN METHODS IN PROCESSING AND WELDING OF MATERIALS

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Abstract: Modern methods in processing and welding of materials includes new techniques on obtaining a product by using different types of processing methods that will allow to simplify the manufacturing productivity process. This creates a paradigm shift from economies of scale based on the operational lever to agile manufacturing. The aim of the paper is to introduce modern methods in processing and welding of materials to obtain a better performance of the product. This will involve a CAD procedure and after that a manufacturing process that will involve all the types of techniques that are required to obtain a product. The CAD procedure is required to obtain a 3D model and a 2D draft that will help to create the final product, after that there will be involved procedures in manufacturing the product from hard ways of manufacturing to the easy ways of finishing technologies.

Key words: Modern Methods, Processing of Material, Industrial Parks, Manufacturing, Technological Park, CAD, Innovation

1. INTRODUCTION

Methods of manufacturing and the manufacturing software that enable them have changed shifting from the rigid, push-oriented production principles of the early 20th century to more flexible, pull principles. Put simply, assembly line manufactures historically pushed mass production ahead based on estimates of future demand, which often resulted in wasted effort and resources when customers failed to produce the estimated demand. Modern companies can't afford this kind of waste, so they wait for actual demand to pull production forward, manufacturing products when they've been requested by customers or when the previous batch of products has sold out.

Unfortunately, understanding the many complex strategies behind these new manufacturing methods can be as difficult as predicting the weather, as they have brought along with them a series of three-letter acronyms that dominate jargon-filled conversations about current manufacturing trends, like JIT, TPM, QRM, and JIS.

Basically, modern manufacturing methods boil down to three key concepts:

- Reduce waste – reduce the number of materials, capacity, and manpower waste in the process by producing just enough product to meet current demand.
- Maintain quality – devise more effective manufacturing methods to continue making quality products despite strict reductions of waste.
- Accelerate production – decrease the amount of time needed to manufacture product, making up for the lack of surplus.

The modernization of the manufacturing process is certainly conditioned by the increase in the performance of the technological equipment for processing, assembling and control. Achieving this goal is possible if new solutions are also promoted in the field of technological devices, but also thorough the development of special or modular components for the modernization of machine-tools [2].

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Modern industry constitutes a driving force in the development of local and global economies. The absence of such expansion can doom countries to market marginalization. Industry has used information technology for many years, mainly to optimize manufacturing and logistics processes. The operational specificity of industrial processes includes large volumes, high costs of downtime and breakdowns, high costs and long depreciation periods for manufacturing facilities [2].

Current solutions enable users to perform better work, bringing benefits to both the company and its customers, while also creating added value for the national economy. The development of this technology, and technological development in general, is not an end. We should consider which applications of AI/CI technology can serve responsible development and the implementation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Another question concerns what threats to sustainable development might be caused by the development of AI technology and what would be an appropriate response to these challenges.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research by Murtzis showed that simulation in the design and operation of manufacturing systems includes the following areas:

- Simulation in the operation of manufacturing systems: 10.28%.
- Product and production lifecycle simulation tools: CAD, CAM, CAPP, digital mock-up, material flow simulation, process simulation, layout planning simulation, ergonomic simulation, manufacturing execution systems, supervisory control and data execution systems, supervisory control and data acquisition, supply chain simulation, and the design and planning of the manufacturing network.
- Intertwined lifecycles of product and production

The most popular domains of research were computer assisted exercise (CAx), manufacturing systems, network planning and control, virtual factories, as far as material and information flow. There relatively novel domains of study have developed dynamically recently in machine modelling and simulation history (some in the past few years). Such a situation emphasizes the significance of the computational tool in our work [1].

Figure 1 – Table of Simulation system

At the end of the 1990s, special attention was being paid to the advantages of implementing such CAx tools as: creation of barrier-free production, reduction of the expenses incurred during the technological phase of production preparation, reduction of production costs and product prices, while maintaining high quality. This was complemented by other achievements in the area of IT, thanks to which computer networks were able to control the state of the production process, auxiliary processes and financing, as these activities require efficient data exchange between different information systems, known as information islands [2].

At the stage additional advantages were discussed, such as doubling production, reducing unit costs by 15-25%, launching a new product 6 months before the competition, and increasing profitability by 25-30%. The implementation of CAx technology made it possible to include systems that play an essential role in data processing in many areas of the company. The main functions are planning, preparation and control of production processes, material supply, workstation and socket loads and the active control of work in progress. The percentage relations between these areas are shown in Figure 2 [2].

Figure 2 – CAx technologies- data exchange (CAQ – computer aided quality, CAM – computer aided manufacturing, PPC – production planning and control, CAP – computer aided planning)

The capacity to forecast future production trends through cloud technology is set to play a significant role, offering businesses economical, adaptable, and scalable options. This approach involves leveraging shared production resources as services. Utilizing the cloud for such predictions enables companies to plan and adjust their production strategies efficiently, aligning them with market demands and resource availability. This method not only optimizes resource utilization but also reduces operational costs, enhancing overall productivity and competitiveness in the market. The integration of cloud computing in production planning allows for real-time data analysis and decision-making, leading to more accurate and timely responses to changing market trends. This system is particularly beneficial for small to medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), providing them with access to advanced production capabilities without the need for substantial capital investment.

By using cloud-based solutions, companies can quickly scale their operations up or down based on demand, ensuring they remain agile and responsive to the dynamic nature of the market. In summary, the ability to generate production trends using cloud technology presents a transformative opportunity for businesses to optimize their operations, reduce costs, and stay competitive in an ever-evolving economic landscape [3].

1.1. Industrial applications of the Internet of Things

The advancement in production processes is increasingly influenced by new technologies, leading to the emergence of novel product categories that fully leverage these technologies' capabilities. In Poland, sectors such as consumer markets, logistics, transportation, and general industry show substantial potential for development through the Internet of Things (IoT). The scope of IoT applications is broad, encompassing areas like safety and certification, finance, insurance, smart cities, intelligent buildings, healthcare, smart metering, agriculture, environment, telecommunications, and transport [4].

Technology companies specializing in Industrial IoT (IIoT) and other cutting-edge technologies are evolving rapidly. They are prepared to adapt and apply their top innovations across various industries, wherever they may be beneficial or in demand. Notables are the developments of companies offering bespoke design and production services in electronics, as well as emerging enterprises that develop intelligent intra-logistics systems using their self-guided vehicles. Numerous research and development centers, along with universities, are engaged in extensive research in areas like IIoT, artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), machine learning, Big Data, and User Experience. These research activities are poised to significantly bolster the growth and implementation of IoT technologies.

Figure 3 - Proportional contribution of artificial intelligence in different sectors and production procedures

The deployment of the Internet of Things (IoT) systems in various settings enables the collection of tool data, both in real-time (online) and through non-real-time methods (offline). While these functionalities often intersect, accessing data offline can pose challenges, particularly in industrial environments. This difficulty arises from the inherent risks associated with gathering industrial data and the necessity of investing in adequate computational resources and specialized software capable of analyzing extensive data sets.

The fundamental objective of Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) systems lies in the optimization of industrial operations. This includes enhancing work efficiency and minimizing the consumption of raw materials. Essentially, the goal is to streamline processes in a manner that effectively reduces both operational risks and costs. By doing so, IIoT systems contribute to creating more efficient, cost-effective, and safer industrial environments. The effective use of these technologies not only aids in process optimization but also plays a crucial role in driving innovation and sustainability in industrial practices [5].

1.1.1. Barriers

Enterprise operations are significantly influenced by logistics capabilities, including the availability of essential infrastructure like roads, railways, ports, and both cargo and passenger airports. Such logistical elements necessitate national involvement in planning and developing the necessary infrastructure, which is crucial for industrial activities that often demand specialized solutions, like high throughput and large tonnage capacities.

Infrastructure investment should consider the need for stable energy supply, ensuring adequate connection capacity and a reliable transmission network. Additionally, the presence of robust ICT (information and communication technologies) networks, encompassing both high-capacity radio and cable connections, particularly fiber-optic, is vital. However, the industry also encounters growing challenges due to environmental regulations. These regulations can be categorized into internal ones, pertaining to production plant procedures, and external ones, linked to the development of the IoT market [6].

A key challenge for Industry 4.0 is the integration and cooperation of various incorporated technologies. This integration aims to reduce the time required to launch new products in the market and ensure that the cost of unit production remains competitive, particularly in comparison to the economies of BRIC countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China). This approach is essential for maintaining market competitiveness and adapting to evolving industrial and technological landscapes.

Automation necessitates extensive preparation, which includes several key steps:

- Establishing a clear business objective.
- Conducting thorough technical and business analyses before making any investment.
- Allotting sufficient time for testing automation systems.
- Ensuring the scalability of the automation equipment.
- Providing adequate service and maintenance for the equipment.

Evaluating the return on investment (ROI) against the risks associated with research and development (R&D) projects.

An additional issue is the underappreciation of the importance of data in the industrial and economic sectors. This limitation affects the readiness to make data sets machine-readable and the absence of API interfaces on some state or industrial websites. There's a pressing need to establish widely accepted standards and develop data governance practices in Poland. This includes the management of shared data and incorporating the right to disconnect from the network.

Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) in Poland are tasked with initiating pilot solutions in these areas. Despite rapid global industrial growth, a persistent challenge is the lack of effective communication and collaboration among software developers. This issue continues to be a significant barrier to industry advancement (table 1) [7].

Table 1 - Significant recognized challenges

Area (in alphabetical order)	Identified problems
Augmented reality (AR)	Low tracking accuracy, end-to-end latency
Computer –aided design (CAD)	Lack of the human-computer interface, complexity of menu
Computer-aided manufacturing (CAM)	Lack of efficient data exchange, of efficient communication and of collaboration
Computer-aided processing planning (CAPP)	Lack of adaptability and of dynamic operation adjustment
Digital MockUp	Extension need for service functions
Discrete Event Data Processing Notation	Lack of collaboration, low accuracy in data exchange

(DPMN)	
Ergonomy	Complexity, lack of models of interaction and of human quality measuring techniques
Enterprise resource planning (ERP)	Lack of mobility and of communication, need for Business Intelligence
Knowledge managemet (KM)	Lack of agent learning, lack of knowledge reuse
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	Need for modularisation, standardisation
Lean Production System (LPS)	Need for extensibility, lack of interoperability
Manufacturing execution System	Lack of communication and of ahead planning

Although significant progress has been made, the areas under discussion are still in their nascent stages. With technology advancing rapidly and workforce skills becoming outdated at an increasing pace, the costs associated with retraining employees are escalating. As a result, some organizations are reevaluating the risks of employing full-time staff and are considering automation as a cost-effective alternative to address these issues. Selecting the appropriate technology for automation and enhancing productivity is crucial, especially in aligning this technology with a comprehensive future strategy.

Machine modeling and simulation play a vital role in enhancing these processes and can even evaluate a company's preparedness for change. These tools are essential for practical application, and the most effective approaches depend on the coordinated development of various interconnected technologies, including organizational processes. The rapid evolution of these areas means their final form and influence should be monitored closely. Advancements in machine modeling and simulation may necessitate collaboration among experts from diverse fields. While this interdisciplinary integration can be challenging, it also holds the potential for groundbreaking innovations.

A novel methodology in the realm of machine modeling and simulation has been introduced to address the deficiencies of existing simulation methods, particularly those pertinent to the demands of the Industry 4.0 framework. This includes the incorporation of digital twins, enhanced hybrid simulation, and expanded utilization of virtual and augmented reality. The primary benefits of this innovative approach encompass:

- Access to more intricate models.
- Enhanced visual realism in representations.
- Improved monitoring throughout the product lifecycle.
- Integration of real-time data.
- Remote maintenance capabilities for products.
- Enhanced decision-making processes.

Despite these advantages, there are notable challenges and current limitations that need addressing:

- The absence of standardized terminology and applications.
- A lack of comprehensive integration within the industry.
- The necessity to modify existing digitization practices to suit new requirements.
- The challenge of integrating cutting-edge technologies, such as AI/CI.
- The digital conversion of implicit, non-codified knowledge.

3. CONCLUSION

Manufacturing methods and the software enabling them to have significantly evolved, transitioning from early 20th-century rigid, push-oriented production to more adaptable, pull principles. This shift means that instead of mass-producing based on estimated demand, leading to potential waste, modern companies produce based on actual demand or when existing stocks are depleted. Navigating these complex strategies, encapsulated in acronyms like JIT, TPM, QRM, and JIS, is crucial. These modern methods focus on reducing waste, maintaining quality, and accelerating production.

The modernization of manufacturing is closely tied to the enhanced performance of technological equipment in processing, assembly, and control. The integration of digital twins, hybrid simulation, virtual and augmented reality are advancing machine modeling and simulation, addressing Industry 4.0 challenges. Despite the benefits like complex models, improved lifecycle monitoring, and enhanced decision-making, challenges remain, such as lack of unified terminology and the need for industrial integration.

The growing influence of new technologies, particularly IoT, is reshaping production processes, creating novel product categories. Sectors like logistics, transportation, and general industry, especially in Poland, show significant development potential through IoT. The deployment of IoT systems facilitates real-time data collection but also poses challenges like data access and the need for substantial computational resources.

Automation requires careful planning, including clear business objectives, thorough analyses, and evaluation of ROI against R&D risks. The importance of data in industry and the necessity for data governance practices, including the right to disconnect from networks, are critical considerations.

Despite rapid advancements, challenges like effective communication and collaboration among software developers persist, impacting industry progression. These dynamics emphasize the importance of monitoring the evolution of these areas and the potential for interdisciplinary collaboration leading to innovative breakthroughs.

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TECHNOLOGIES AND 4.0 INDUSTRY IN THE MANUFACTURING OF BIOMASS CUTTING EQUIPMENT

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Abstract: Industry 4.0 represents a significant leap in manufacturing, offering substantial advantages over previous industrial eras. The development of intelligent products necessitates cutting-edge technologies throughout the design and production phases, heralding a shift from traditional scale-based operations to agile manufacturing methodologies. This study aims to enhance manufacturing processes and their crucial performance metrics. The paper introduces novel systems poised to revolutionize mold pellet production, commencing from a 3D mold model crafted in a CAD program. Leveraging cloud manufacturing, the system seamlessly integrates CAD modelling with CAM procedures, streamlining mold creation. Reverse engineering enhances mold design, while analytics-driven cloud manufacturing expedites problem-solving by swiftly processing mold data. Centralizing information, cloud manufacturing ensures scalability and efficiency, focusing on Industry 4.0 tenets such as productivity, data processing, connectivity, predictive engineering, and sustainability. This initiative strides towards comprehensive digitalization, optimizing pellet and briquette mold manufacturing using cloud, cyber, reverse engineering, and Industry 4.0 technologies. The study's contributions encompass time reduction via cloud manufacturing, error minimization through cyber manufacturing, efficient replication of old components sans 3D models, and proactive issue detection and resolution.

Key words: Production optimization, Cloud manufacturing, Cyber manufacturing, Reverse engineering, Industry 4.0, Cutting equipment.

1. INTRODUCTION

The primary aim of this research is to enhance the efficiency of manufacturing and product design concerning biomass cutting equipment. This involves leveraging cutting-edge technologies such as cyber manufacturing [1], cloud systems, reverse engineering, and Industry 4.0 principles. The objective of this study is to introduce innovative systems that will revolutionize the production processes for cutting equipment [2]. It begins with the development of a 3D model using CAD software for the equipment. Through the implementation of a cloud-based manufacturing system, data from the CAD model facilitates the CAM procedure, streamlining the creation of the cutting equipment. Furthermore, within the cloud manufacturing setup, data obtained from the manufacturing process is analysed to anticipate and address potential issues.

Introducing cloud manufacturing [3] into this process centralizes information, fostering scalability and facilitating long-term strategic analysis across machinery and facilities.

Reverse engineering [4] enables the enhancement of older machine components, making them more efficient and easier to produce.

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Cyber manufacturing acts as a transformative system, translating interconnected data into predictive and prescriptive operations, ensuring resilient performance. Embracing the impact of Industry 4.0 embodies advancements in productivity, data processing, industrial connectivity, predictive engineering, and sustainability. [5] It signifies a leap forward in the digitalization of resources necessary for implementing a cutting-edge production system.

Industry 4.0 represents the technological evolution of production, prompting companies to transform their production units into "smart factories" to meet the evolving market standards.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The examined biomass cutting equipment is owned and operated by a small-scale manufacturing enterprise based in Cenei. [6] This company specializes in the production of heating pellets and briquettes, utilizing the shredder as an essential component in their manufacturing process. The shredder's role within the company's activities is crucial, as it aids in the preparation and processing of materials necessary for the creation of high-quality heating pellets and briquettes.

The currently implemented constructive solution for the cutting assembly is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Cutting assembly

The studied model is TB160T, a round bale chopper designed for chopping straw, hay, and alfalfa bales, accommodating a maximum bale diameter of 1200 mm. Its operation relies on a 22 kW primary motor and a 1.1 kW gearmotor, allowing for a production capacity of 1300 kg/h. [2] The resulting mince size ranges between 2-5 cm.

For its physical specifications, its road measures include a diameter of 1600mm and a length of 1250 mm, with a road plate thickness of 3 mm. The drum rotates at a speed of 7 rotations per minute and is supported by a chassis constructed from a straight profile of 60x40x4. The drum's movement is facilitated by two trapezoidal belts measuring 5182mm x 17mm.t

The engine specifications entail a primary engine of 22 kW and a gear motor of 1.1 kW, with the gear motor operating at a speed of 60 rotations. The primary motor is controlled by a star-delta type switch, while the secondary motor is operated using a single-position switch. Both motors are powered by three-phase current and are connected through a three-phase power cable measuring 6 mm x 4000 mm.

The methodology employed in this research involves a comprehensive exploration of cyber manufacturing, cloud manufacturing, reverse engineering, and Industry 4.0 within the context of optimizing bale chopper manufacturing and product design.

The research process began with an extensive review and analysis of existing literature, aiming to comprehend the foundational principles and applications of cyber manufacturing, cloud manufacturing, reverse engineering, and Industry 4.0 in the manufacturing sector.

Subsequently, a systematic approach was taken to identify the potential areas for enhancement within the bale chopper manufacturing processes [7]. This involved conducting in-depth assessments and evaluations of current manufacturing practices and their inefficiencies in addressing the challenges posed by global competitiveness and fluctuating demands.

The next phase involved the application of the identified methodologies - reverse engineering, cloud manufacturing, cyber manufacturing, and Industry 4.0 - to modernize and optimize the technological line at Cenei. Implementation strategies were devised and executed to integrate these advanced techniques into the existing manufacturing processes of bale choppers.

3. EMPIRICAL DATA ANALYSIS

The empirical data analysis phase involved a detailed examination of the practical application and outcomes resulting from the implementation of cyber manufacturing, cloud manufacturing, reverse engineering, and Industry 4.0 methodologies within the bale chopper manufacturing setting.

3.1. CYBER MANUFACTURING

The Cyber manufacturing stands as a revolutionary concept involving the interpretation of data from interconnected systems [1], transforming it into predictive and prescriptive operations aimed at achieving resilient performance. By amalgamating industrial big data with smart analytics, it identifies and comprehends latent issues crucial for informed decision-making. This research paper introduces a foundational framework and architecture pivotal for cyber manufacturing systems. Figure 2 illustrates the operational mechanism of cyber manufacturing.

Derived from e-manufacturing, cyber manufacturing represents a systematic methodology facilitating the seamless integration of manufacturing operations with the enterprise's functional objectives. This integration is made possible through the utilization of tether-free technologies such as the Internet, wireless communication, web interfaces, etc., coupled with predictive technologies.

Figure 2 - Cyber Manufacturing System

3.2. CLOUD MANUFACTURING

In our context, cloud manufacturing refers to the utilization of cloud-based technologies and resources to enhance various aspects of our manufacturing processes. This approach involves leveraging cloud computing services, which offer scalable and flexible resources such as storage, processing power, and software applications over the internet.

Implementing cloud manufacturing in our situation can significantly enhance our manufacturing processes by optimizing resources, promoting collaboration, enabling efficient data analysis, offering flexibility, facilitating remote access, and ensuring robust security measures.

3.3. REVERSE ENGINEERING

We applied reverse engineering specifically to the cutting assembly, Figure 2, a crucial component in manufacturing. This practice involves dismantling and scrutinizing the cutting assembly to reveal its constituent materials and operational functionalities. This process offered invaluable insights essential for refining production processes, enhancing the efficiency of the product, and ensuring patent protection.

Ultimately, this methodology resulted in the development of a functional model aligned precisely with the tailored specifications meeting our customers' needs.

Figure 3 - Reverse engineering the cutting assembly

The reverse engineering process is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Reverse engineering process

3.4. INDUSTRY 4.0

In our specific situation, embracing and aligning with the principles and advancements brought forth by Industrie 4.0 can usher in transformative changes, aligning our operations with cutting-edge technological strategies and standards set forth by this pivotal movement.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, this paper highlights the utilization of an integrated cyber-physical system within cloud manufacturing, showcasing four distinct applications. These applications encompass functionalities such as remote monitoring and control, distributed process planning, model-guided remote assembly, and active collision avoidance for human-robot collaboration, all packaged as cloud services. Future endeavours will focus on refining these functions, conducting testing, and integrating the four strategies into assembly plans to ensure seamless human-robot collaborative assembly by aligning the robot's behaviour with the task's nature.

The amalgamation of cyber manufacturing, cloud manufacturing, reverse engineering, and Industry 4.0 techniques has a substantial impact on enhancing overall plant production and optimizing the manufacturing processes and design of bale choppers for pellets and briquettes.

A key contribution of this paper lies in introducing these four novel technologies, showcasing their potential to significantly influence scalable manufacturing, reduce manufacturing schedule durations, and lower the costs associated with producing bale choppers for pellets and briquettes. These technologies pave the way for substantial improvements in manufacturing efficiency and cost-effectiveness within the bale chopper production domain.

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BEHAVIORAL STUDY OF THE MATERIALS USED IN THE 3D PRINTING PROCESS UNDER THE ACTION OF ULTRASONIC COMPACTION

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Abstract: Fused Deposition Modelling (FDM) stands out as a widely employed commercial method in materials extrusion-based additive manufacturing (AM). It is extensively utilized for creating 3D-printed components, primarily using thermoplastic polymers like PETG.

Environmentally friendly ultrasonic welding is a preferred method by leading manufacturers in line with European circular economy regulations.

This study examines the effects of ultrasonic compaction on the mechanical properties of FDM printed thermoplastics.

The results, obtained by non-destructive and destructive tests (visual analysis, microscopic and macroscopic investigations, tensile tests, hardness tests and bending tests), were interpreted and compared with the base material printed but not compacted using ultrasonic energy.

Key words: thermoplastic material, PETG, 3D printing, FDM, ultrasonic compaction

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. FDM-based Rapid Prototyping process for 3D printing

Additive manufacturing methods represent a cutting-edge production technique, constructing components layer by layer directly from a computer-supported data file known as „CAD (Computer-Aided Design)”. Making a part by 3D printing of thermoplastics is a modern technology used in leading technical fields. FDM (thermoplastic extrusion moulding) rapid prototyping technology is the deposition of molten material to obtain a three-dimensional object, based on the model of the part made in 3D software. To obtain a part, the part is first designed in 3D using computer-aided design software (CAD, SolidWorks, Catia), resulting in a CAD file with the final shape of the honeycomb structure. This file with the help of a dedicated software application (usually Simplicity software) is sectioned into cross-sections (layers) and then used to produce the matrix that is optimised for 3D printing.

Figure 1 –Schematic illustration of the FDM process showing the rheological impact of molten filament on the manufacturing steps, [6]

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The printing technology consists of passing a plastic filament coil through a nozzle that heats it to the melting point, then applying it evenly (by extrusion) layer upon layer horizontally, with high accuracy to physically print the 3D model according to the SolidWorks file, using a 3D printer [1-5].

FDM offers key benefits, including the swift and economical manufacturing of personalized components, enhanced sustainability in contrast to traditional processing methods, and the versatility of utilizing common materials for diverse applications. This encompasses fields such as biomedical devices, dental pieces, architectural structures, as well as automotive and aerospace components, among others [7-9].

1.2. Ultrasound welding for thermoplastics materials

Ultrasonic welding is emerging as a non-toxic, green solid-state joining process using high-frequency mechanical vibration to create durable bonds between thermoplastic materials.

The ultrasonic generator serves to supply high-frequency currents to the transducer, which transforms received electrical signals into mechanical vibrations through the piezoelectric effect. These vibrations undergo amplification by the booster positioned between the transducer and the sonotrode. Focused ultrasonic waves are directed toward the active tool (sonotrode), utilizing these oscillations and applying contact pressure to facilitate the welding of parts, as illustrated in Figure 2

Figure 2 –Diagram of the ultrasonic welding equipment, [11]

Uses mechanical vibration at ultrasonic frequencies (15 kHz - 35 kHz) to generate frictional heat at the joint interface. Sequential steps include contact (application of pressure), vibration (rapid vertical oscillation of the ultrasonic sonotrode) and melting (localised melting of the thermoplastic).

Weld forming involves continuous ultrasonic vibrations, which expel the molten material, exposing the fresh material to frictional heat. When the vibrations stop, the molten material solidifies, establishing a strong bond.

Advantages for usage of ultrasound joint, [10]:

- Fast processing, suitable for high volume production.
- Ensures consistent and repeatable welds.
- Energy efficient due to localised heat generation at the joint interface.

The present article aims to analyse the behaviour of a layered structure made by 3D-FDM printing of thermoplastic material - PETG - in order to obtain a mechanically improved structure. These will be compacted with ultrasonic energy to be joined, obtaining a unique structure in which the distance between the layers of material is compressed and end with the final layer. This composite can be used in the fields of nanotechnology, advanced materials such as aeronautics and renewable energy.

In the INCD ISIM Timisoara materials testing laboratory, the specimen will be prepared for destructive testing: tensile, hardness, as well as NDT: visual analysis, macroscopic investigations, where the results are interpreted and compared with the unarmored base material as well as with the control sample.

2. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1. Material used for samples

Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol (PETG) belongs to the thermoplastics category and stands as a prominent material in 3D printing technology. It is widely utilized owing to its favourable characteristics, including facilitating the effective printing of desired objects, ease of processing, and ensuring strong adhesion between layers. Thanks to its elevated strength, components produced from PETG can operate effectively under high-temperature conditions, showcase impressive impact performance, and demonstrate notable chemical resistance, as illustrated in Tables 1 and 2. [12, 13].

Table 1 –Chemical composition of PETG, [14]

Element	Compound	Molecular Formula	Molecular Weight [g/mol]
PETG	Terephthalic acid (TPA)	C ₈ H ₆ O ₄	166.13
	Ethylene glycol (EG)	CH ₂ OH ₂	62.07
	Cyclohexanedimethanol (CHDM)	C ₈ H ₁₆ O ₂	144.21

Table 2 –Physical and mechanical properties of PETG, [15, 16, 17]

Tensile Strength [PSI]	Yield strength [MPa]	Elongation [%]	Density [g/cm ³]	Hardness (Vickers) [HV]	Printing temperature [°C]	Glass transition temperature [°C]	Printing speed [mm/s]	Water absorption [%]
7.700	6.95-7.67	5.83	14.4-15.9	14.4-15.9	230-250	81-91	40-60	0.2

2.2. Technical equipment

The open ENDR3 V2 printer, featured in Figure 3, from the INCD ISIM Timisoara technical laboratory, is employed for the printing of PETG composite specimens. These specimens are crafted using black Azabache filament with a diameter of 1.75 mm.

Technical specifications of the 3D printer:

- Print size: 300 x 220 x300mm
- Nozzle Diameter: Standard 0.4mm – can use 0.6mm
- Software: Cura, Slicer3d, Repetier-host
- File format: stl,obj, gcode

- Print speed: Normal 60mm/s, Max 100mm/s
- Filament diameter: 1.75mm
- Filament type: PLA, ABS, PTEG, TPU, WOOD, Nylon, Carbon fiber, Copper, etc
- Power requirements: 120VAC, 250W
- Extruder type: direct Bowden;
- 3D printing technology: FDM, FFF.

Figure 3 –Printer 3D Creality Ender 3 Pro, [18]

The Hermann Ultrasonics HiQDialog ultrasonic welding equipment used for joining PETG structures and Kevlar textile material in the CEEX-US ultrasonic laboratory at INCD ISIM Timisoara shown in figure 4 has the following characteristics:

- the equipment is equipped with the HMC pneumatic drive system;
- supply voltage: 220-240 V/50-60 Hz;
- working frequency: 35 kHz;
- maximum power: 1200 W;
- welding force min./max. [N] at 8 bar-10 / 650;
- stroke [mm]- 100 stroke/stroke;
- cylindrical stepped sonotrode;
- generator power -1200 [W];

Figure 4 –Ultrasonic welding equipment used for tests with cylindrical step sonotrode, [19]

SolidWorks software is employed to generate both 2D and 3D graphics representing the PETG specimens designed to conform to STAS dimensions. Detailed technical drawings are depicted in the accompanying figure 5 a) and b).

Figure 5 –2D graphical representation of PETG specimens: a) top view; b) cross-sectional view

Figure 6 –Representation of the arrangement of stress concentrators on the specimen surface

The specimens are printed in pairs, where the stress concentrators are printed tilted at an angle of 70 degrees on the surface of the mirror specimen body, and at the ends of the specimen the concentrators are printed in such a way that they overlap, as shown in figure 6. Their role is to increase the quality of the bond between the two composites, improving the strength of the composite in its final form.

2.3. Experimental program

FDM technology is employed for composite printing. The 3D printer utilizes a printing nozzle with a melting temperature of 250°C and a diameter of 0.6 mm to heat and extrude the filament. The liquefied filament is then deposited onto a heated platform, reaching temperatures up to 80°C, in a user-defined pattern to attain the desired planar shape, as illustrated in Figure 7. Key parameters governing the printing process are detailed in Table 3.

Figure 7 –Layering PETG material

Table 3 –Technical printing parameters 3D

Parameters	Values
Layer thickness [mm]	4
Filament diameter [mm]	1.75
Nozzle temperature [°C]	250
Bed temperature [°C]	80

Printing speed [mm/s]	50
Infill [-]	Gyroid
Infill density	50%

Layer by layer, the PETG material is deposited to form test specimens measuring 150 x 20 x 4 mm³, dimensions in accordance with standard 1B. The deposition involves two straight surfaces angled at 45 degrees in one direction and a second set at 45 degrees in the opposite direction. Filling between these two sets of surfaces and the subsequent two is executed in a "gyroid" style. Notably, the initial and concluding layers boast a refined and smoother surface compared to the intermediate layers. Figure 8 below illustrates the ultimate shapes of the specimens.

Figure 8 –Test specimens from PETG deposition thru FDM process

The Hermann HiQ Dialog ultrasonic equipment's workbench secures both PETG specimens. These specimens will undergo ultrasonic waves at a working frequency of 35 kHz, as depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 9 –PETG specimens welded with US

For the experimental part, two sets of specimens are prepared, between which the values will be used for comparison:

- PETG reference specimens;
- US-welded specimens from PETG.

Multiple joints are created on reference specimens, as well as on specimens welded using ultrasound, until optimal parameters are identified for our specific application. The welding technology parameters are outlined in Table 4.

Table 4 –Welding parameters

No.	Welding time [s]	Amplitude [μm]	Power [W]	Welding force [N]	Welding frequency [kHz]	Depth RPN [mm]	Trigger point [mm]	Energy [J]
1	1,5	6,0	1200	100	35	0,07	57,30	92

The technical welding parameters influencing the composite joint are illustrated in Figure 10. Various joints are created at different parameters, and their shapes are depicted in the graph below. Each colour corresponds to a specific technical welding parameter, with its graphical shape being influenced by the interplay of other parameters during the welding process.

Figure 10 –Graph generated by Hermann HiQ Dialog ultrasonic equipment software

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Upon visual inspection of the reference samples, it is evident that the surface of the latest printed layer appears glossy and refined compared to the consecutive layers deposited on the specimen. Following the application of ultrasonic welding parameters, the joined areas in the specimens exhibit conforming configurations, showcasing the positive influence of stress concentrators on achieving a high-quality joint.

To ascertain the mechanical characteristics of the composite materials resulting from PETG filament deposition, tensile tests were conducted on both reference specimens and those welded with ultrasonic parameters, as specified above. The tests were performed using a Zwick/Roell Germany universal testing machine with a maximum load capacity of 10 kN. A pretension of 5 N was applied, and the loading speed was set at 5 mm/min, maintaining an ambient temperature of 23±5°C and a humidity level of 50%.

After the implementation of the welding technological parameters, the composite material resulting from the joining of the materials is shown in figure 11.

Figure 11 –Front view of the two types of specimens

The mechanical properties of 3D printed specimens, both reference and those combined with ultrasonic welding, were assessed using the test procedure outlined in DIN EN ISO 527. Specifically, ISO 527-2 defines the specifications for the types of specimens used in tensile tests, with Type 1B (A2) being employed.

The initial specimens subjected to testing were the reference specimens, illustrated in Figure 12. Notably, almost all of these specimens exhibited failure in approximately the same region of the specimen.

Figure 12 –Reference specimen tensile test

The test results for the reference samples are shown in table 5 below.

Table 5 –Table with reference specimen tensile test

No.	Specimen designation	E_t [MPa]	σ_m [MPa]	ϵ_m [%]	ϵ_b [%]	b [mm]	h [mm]	A_0 [mm ²]
1	Ref 1	2590	30.8	1.5	1.5	10.3	4.0	41.2
2	Ref 2	2660	31.8	1.5	1.5	10.41	3.96	41.2
3	Ref 3	2600	31.2	1.5	1.5	10.43	3.98	41.5
4	Ref 4	2620	31.2	1.5	1.5	10.37	3.95	41.0
5	Ref 5	2590	31.0	1.4	1.4	10.38	3.94	40.9

Graphical representation of the values resulting from the tensile test, where it can be seen that at a tensile force of 30 MPa the material fails, as shown in the graph below.

Figure 13 –Graph of tensile test results of reference specimens

In the second tensile test, the 3D printed non-drilled but ultrasonically welded specimens, compared to the reference specimens, failed at different places on the specimen as can be seen in figure 14.

Figure 14 –Welded US specimens

Test results for specimens welded with ultrasonic energy are shown in table 6.

Table 6 –Table of results for specimens welded with US

No.	Specimen designation	E_t [MPa]	σ_m [MPa]	ϵ_m [%]	ϵ_b [%]	b [mm]	h [mm]	A_0 [mm ²]
1	Nr 1	3620	37.2	0.98	0.98	10.25	4.08	41.8
2	Nr 2	3580	41.5	1.2	1.2	10.16	4.09	41.6
3	Nr 3	3320	38.4	1.2	1.2	10.38	4.2	43.6
4	Nr 4	3560	36.5	0.98	0.98	10.25	4.15	42.5

The graphical representation of specimens welded with ultrasonic energy shows an increased tensile strength compared to the 10-unit reference specimens, as shown in figure 15.

Figure 15 –Graph of tensile test results of specimens welded with US

Microhardness tests on PETG printed specimens performed on the Zwick 3212 machine, and the results 9.57 and 13.5 HV1, are inconclusive as can be seen in figure 16, as no standards are known for plastics.

Figure 16 –Graph of tensile test results of reference specimens

4. CONCLUSION

From the results obtained in the tests, the following observations can be made:

- Welding concentrators impact the quality of material joints when utilizing ultrasonics energy;
- Ultrasonic treatment improves the mechanical properties of completed parts without affecting the 3D printed material;
- The surface of the parts undergoes enhancement, yielding a uniform and smooth finish;
- Non-destructive and destructive tests led to the conclusion that welding enhances the properties of the samples;
- Outcomes from the experimental ultrasonic welding program suggest the applicability of this technology in aerospace applications.

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METHOD FOR EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF HEAT TRANSFER COEFFICIENT - HOT BOX APPARATUS

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Abstract:

The heat losses of building structures depend on the thermophysical characteristics of building elements and the construction from which the objects are built. The largest heat losses, as well as heat gains, occur through windows and doors, or transparent structural elements of the building envelope. In this regard, it is crucial to know the heat transfer coefficients to obtain more precise results in engineering calculations of thermal and cooling loads. The method for experimental calculation is based on the "hot box" method. The method relies on the existence of a chamber at a higher temperature and a chamber at a lower temperature, where the air temperature is artificially maintained. The tested sample is placed between the chambers, and due to the temperature difference between the chambers, heat passes through the sample. Using the obtained data, the value of the heat transfer coefficient is determined.

Key words: thermodynamics, software, heat transfer, building physics, energy efficiency

1. INTRODUCTION

Energy consumption in the construction sector has significantly increased over time to meet user needs. In developed countries, energy consumption in the construction sector accounts for 20 to 40% of the total consumption. When considering the percentage share of consumption, in the European Union and the United States, energy consumption in buildings is greater than that in industry and transportation [1]. For this reason, directives have been introduced, such as the European Union Directive 2010/31 [2], on energy efficiency in buildings, aiming to achieve minimum energy standards for both individual building components and the entire structure. The development of construction quality and the selection of the right components are of crucial importance in implementing energy efficiency measures. To ensure more accurate calculations, it is necessary to precisely determine the thermal characteristics of materials (thermal conductivity). For homogeneous materials, determining their characteristics through calculations is relatively straightforward. However, when structures cannot be treated as homogeneous, such as windows, a different approach is needed. Numerical methods can provide good results, but the best method is an experimental approach to the problem.

Heat transfer is a process in which heat moves from a fluid at a higher temperature to a wall, then conducts through the wall, and finally transfers to a fluid at a lower temperature. An example of heat transfer is the way heating in technology occurs by transferring heat from hot water circulating through heating elements to the air in a space or cooling a heated space due to the passage of heat from the air in the space to the surrounding air. The aim of this study is to present a methodology for determining a more accurate heat transfer coefficient to minimize heat losses. It is important to emphasize that under stationary conditions, in a unit of time, the amount of heat transferring from a fluid at a higher temperature to the wall is equal to the amount of heat conducted through the wall, simultaneously with the amount of heat transferring from the wall to a fluid at a lower temperature.

There are various ways to experimentally determine the heat transfer coefficient. The most well-known methods for one-dimensional heat transfer through homogeneous materials include the guarded hot plate and the fluxmeter. These approaches have certain limitations, as they can only be applied to small, homogeneous materials. When dealing with large, non-homogeneous assemblies, the hot-box method has an advantage.

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The hot-box method is an experimental technique for determining the heat transfer coefficient. In this method, the test specimen is positioned between a higher and a lower temperature chamber, with temperature sensors, i.e., thermocouples, attached to it. When a steady-state is reached, data is collected, processed, and then the heat transfer coefficient is calculated. This method allows for the examination of various building envelope components, such as walls, roofs, and windows, providing an assessment of their actual thermal performance.

The use of the hot-box method offers the advantage of being a highly reliable testing apparatus for evaluating the real thermal performance of building envelope components. In comparison with mathematical models predicting building thermal performances, the hot-box method enables more precise and realistic results.

When it comes to countries in the European Union, the determination of the heat transfer coefficient through windows and doors is carried out according to the applicable EN ISO 12567-1 standard [3]. In Serbia, in accordance with the domestic Regulation on the Energy Efficiency of Buildings [4], the standard SRPS EN ISO 12567-1:2012, Thermal Performance of Windows and Doors: Determination of Heat Transfer Coefficient by the Hot Box Method, Part 1: Complete Windows and Doors [5], is used (previous standard: SRPS U.J5.060:1984). The basis for determining the heat transfer coefficient in both standards lies in an experimental procedure based on the hot box method.

By balancing the energy flows for both chambers, the portion of the thermal flux passing through the tested sample is determined. After obtaining the data and performing simple calculations, the values of the heat transfer coefficient through the sample are determined. The measurement procedure and obtaining valid experimental results depend on the material and dimensions of the sample, as well as the steadiness of the process.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 History of Development

The first concept of the hot-box apparatus was introduced over a century ago in the United States [6]. Initially presented as an analog test method for determining the thermal characteristics of homogeneous building materials [7], the construction of the testing device has evolved and adapted to testing needs. The hot box is capable of testing larger surface materials as well as those with non-homogeneous compositions, representing components of building structures. It consists of two chambers—a measurement chamber and a chamber for achieving external climatic conditions—to simulate the internal and external temperatures of an object. During testing, the sample is placed in the center, and efforts are made to achieve steady-state conditions. There are two designs of the apparatus: the calibrated hot box and the guarded hot box. The main difference between these two design solutions is the presence of a protective chamber in the guarded hot box. The protective chamber surrounds the measurement chamber and helps maintain the temperature difference between the measurement chamber and the protective chamber, minimizing heat transfer between the chambers. In the case of the calibrated hot box, the surrounding air serves as the protective chamber, and the amount of heat that passes from the hot box to the surrounding air or vice versa must be measured. The calibrated hot box is used when the size of the tested sample is smaller than the opening of the panel that separates the higher and lower temperature chambers, while the guarded hot box is used when testing samples of larger dimensions. There is a significantly larger number of tests documented in the literature that have been conducted using the calibrated hot box [8].

2.2 Methodology

The hot-box method for calculating the heat transfer coefficient is described in the standards EN ISO 8990: Thermal Insulation, Determination of steady-state thermal transmission properties, Calibrated Hot-Box Method [9], and EN ISO 12567-1. Thermal performance of windows and doors determination of thermal transmittance by the hot-box method, which is used for measuring the heat

conduction resistance for windows and doors [3]. According to the EN ISO 8990 standard, the heat transfer coefficient is described as the value of heat flow per square meter of the structure, divided by the temperature difference of the air. The external walls of the chamber are well-insulated to minimize heat transfer. The auxiliary panel holding the sample is also well-insulated. The entire apparatus is placed in an environment with a known temperature.

The specific heat flow ($\dot{q}_{sp}$) through the tested sample is calculated as follows:

$$\dot{q}_{sp} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{in} - \dot{Q}_{sur} - \dot{Q}_{edge}}{A_{sp}} [W/m^2] \quad (1)$$

where:

$\dot{Q}_{in}[W]$ - heat flow transferred to the higher temperature chamber, representing the total energy transferred to the higher temperature chamber ($\dot{Q}_{in} = \dot{Q}_{in}^* \pm \dot{Q}_{out}$), where $\dot{Q}_{out}$ depends on the laboratory temperature, whether it is higher or lower than 20 °C;

$\dot{Q}_{sur}[W]$ - heat flow transferred through the partition separating the higher and lower temperature chambers, further passing through the walls of the lower temperature chamber;

$\dot{Q}_{edge}[W]$ - heat flow passing through the boundary zone between the auxiliary panel and the tested sample;

$A_{sp} [m^2]$ - surface area of the tested sample.

Due to the temperature difference (ΔT) between the higher chamber (T_i -internal) and the lower temperature chamber (T_e -external), i.e., the measurement chamber and the chamber for achieving climatic conditions, there is heat transfer through the tested material (Figure 1).

The heat transfer coefficient (U-value) is calculated according to EN ISO 8990 as:

$$U_{value} = \frac{\dot{q}_{sp}}{\Delta T} [W/m^2K] \quad (2)$$

Figure 1 – Hot Box Apparatus

According to the EN ISO 12567-1 standard procedure, calibration must be performed with a minimum of six specific heat flows covering all required ranges when testing samples. It is recommended to

conduct the test at three different average air temperatures. The average air temperature is calculated as the arithmetic mean of the temperatures in the "warm" and "cold" chambers while maintaining the same fan speed to simulate natural convection.

For calibration, two calibration panels are used, each with a known heat transfer coefficient. The first panel has a thickness of 68mm and is composed of polyurethane (60 mm), with the front and back sides covered with 4 mm glass. The second panel has a thickness of 28mm and is composed of polyurethane (20 mm), with the front and back sides covered with 4 mm glass. By comparing the obtained values with known data, we perform the calibration of the device. The temperature of the "warmer" chamber remains constant during calibration, while the average temperature difference ΔT_s changes by 5 degrees for each test. Three tests are conducted with two different calibration panels, thus satisfying the procedure outlined in the standard, i.e., six tests in total. The average air temperature (ΔT_s) is the arithmetic mean of the temperatures in the higher and lower temperature chambers. The term "inner side" refers to the chamber with a higher temperature, simulating the interior of the space, while "outer side" refers to the chamber with a lower temperature, simulating the external, surrounding air around the object. For this reason, chamber temperatures are denoted as T_i , the temperature of the chamber with a higher temperature, and T_e , the temperature of the chamber with a lower.

Table 1 – U coefficient values for calibration panels

No.	Panel	$U [W/m^2K]$
1.	68 mm	0,52
2.	28 mm	1,31

3. CONCLUSION

One-dimensional thermal analyses are often computationally efficient, providing precise results. However, when components cannot be considered homogeneous structures, as in the case of materials with varied compositions or in multidimensional heat propagation, it is essential to validate numerical analyses experimentally. The hot-box method has proven effective in experimentally confirming numerically obtained heat transfer coefficients for both homogeneous and non-homogeneous materials.

Achieving prescribed heat transfer coefficients in accordance with standards leads to enhanced thermal protection, mitigates thermal bridging issues, reduces overall building energy consumption, and improves energy efficiency classifications. As a consequence of effective energy management, a decrease in CO₂ emissions occurs, contributing to climate change mitigation. For precise data, it is crucial to establish accurate initial conditions when testing materials. From all the provided data obtained during calibration, it is evident that accurate calibration is a prerequisite for the reliability of data when examining the thermal properties of materials.

Transparent elements of building envelopes, such as windows, external doors, and glazed surfaces, play a crucial role in ventilation and transmitting heat losses. Therefore, meticulous attention must be given to their design. The hot-box method finds its greatest application in the calculation of these thermally sensitive components due to their non-homogeneous composition, which represents a crucial element in the design and construction of new structures.

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RESEARCH ON THE WELDING TECHNOLOGY OPTIMIZATION OF VALVE FROM THE STRUCTURE OF SOME DIESEL ENGINES

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Abstract: The purpose of the work is the design and experimental optimization of the pressure welding technology for the semi-finished products used in the valves of Diesel engines. The main issues to be addressed in this work are three parts: Processing bibliographic materials related to pressure welding of metallic materials; Designing the butt-to-butt pressure welding technology of semi-finished products for Diesel engine valves, involving the following stages (description of the procedure; constructive analysis of the weld joints using this procedure; verification of the base material; determination of welding regime parameters; selection of welding equipment; mechanical processing of the welded joints; Experimental optimization of the designed welding technology, including the following stages (presentation of the optimization methodology, presentation of the experimental optimization program, and development of specifications for pressure welding procedures).

Key words: welding technology, valve, optimization, diesel engine,

1. INTRODUCTION

The technology of pressure welding has been known since the end of the 18th century. In 1891, in the United Kingdom, the use of the friction effect in joining flexible wire cables was patented. In the late 1930s, pressure welding was used in Germany for welding thermoplastic resins, [1]. Patents for the use of friction in joining parts were issued in Germany (1926) and in the United Kingdom (1941). However, these mentioned works did not go beyond the stage of laboratory research. In practice, pressure welding was first introduced by the innovative turner A.I. Cindikov in 1956. These works had an impact as an incentive for starting research in the field of pressure welding in the USA, Japan, the United Kingdom, West Germany, etc. Recognizing the priority of Russian scientists, foreign scientists referred to pressure welding as „Russian welding”, [2].

2. THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE WELDING PROCESS

2.1. Theoretical considerations

In pressure welding, the energy required for the welding process is obtained through the transformation of mechanical pressure energy into heat.

In all cases, the two contacting surfaces must have relative motion, with a pressing force F transmitted between them to generate the pressure necessary for heat production, [3].

The relative motion between components can be achieved in the following ways (figure 1):

- by rotating one and axially fixing the second, (figure 1a);
- with rotation and axial pressing force applied to the components, (figure 1b);
- by rotating both components in opposite directions and applying axial force to both components, (figure 1c);

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- by rotating an intermediate piece placed between components and applying axial force to both components, (figure 1d);
- by rotating one component and applying force F to the other component, which vibrates, (figure 1e);
- by vibrating one component and applying force F to the other, (figure 1f).

Figure 1 – Possible schematic principles of friction welding, [4]

2.2. Stages of the welding process

The stages of the welding process are (figure 2), [5]:

- imparting rotation to one of the components (figure 2a);
- ensuring contact between the two components in relative motion by applying a force (figure 2b);
- heating the ends of the components under the action of the pressure moment, and the components are kept in relative motion under the action of axial force until a temperature necessary for plastic deformation is reached (figure 2c);
- upsetting of the components is performed after stopping the relative rotational motion, and it is achieved by maintaining the value of the heating force or a greater one (figure 2d).

Figure 2 – The phases of the friction welding process, [5]

The initial components are at a certain distance, one rotates while the other remains stationary. After this process, the two components become close. A certain amount of metal in a plastic state is extruded through the pressure surface, (figure 2d).

3. DESIGNING THE PRESSURE WELDING TECHNOLOGY OF SEMI-FINISHED COMPONENTS FOR DIESEL ENGINE VALVES

3.1. Sketch of the Diesel engine valve

The pressure welding process of cutting tools involves the following stages and operations, [6]:

- clamping one component in the sled's jaws and the other component in the chuck;
- advancing the sled until the two components make contact;
- pressure stage;
- upsetting stage;
- retracting the sled with the welded piece and opening the jaws.

Figure 3 – Intake-Exhaust Valve

Except for clamping the components in the jaws and extracting the welded piece from the jaws, the other operations are performed automatically. The following welding regime parameters are adjusted, [7]:

- clamping force of the components;
- pressure force;
- upsetting force;
- duration of maintaining the pressure force;
- delay time of the main shaft braking;
- duration of maintaining the upsetting force.

3.2. Selection of base materials for components

For the valve head (disc), subjected to intense thermal and chemical stresses, a steel of type 53CrMnNi219 is used with the following characteristics:

- chemical composition [%]:
C = 0.47-0.57; Mn = 1-1.5; P = max 0.03; S = max. 0.03; Si = 0.75-1.25; Cr = 20-22; Ni = 21-23.
- physical properties:
 - specific weight: $\gamma = 7.9$ [kg/dm³];
 - specific heat at 293 K : $c = 0,44$ [J/g·K];
 - thermal conductivity at 293 K: $\lambda = 0,36$ [J/cm·sec·K];
 - average coefficient of thermal expansion at 293 K: $\alpha = 12.17$ [1/K];
 - electrical resistivity at 293 K: $\rho = 12.9$ [$\mu\Omega \cdot \text{cm}$];
- mechanical characteristics:
 - yield strength: $R_{p02} = \text{min. } 633$ [N/mm²] la 20°C, resp. 225 [N/mm²] la 760°C;
 - tensile strength: $R_m = 914$ [N/mm²] la 20°C, resp. 281 [N/mm²] la 760°C;
 - elongation at break: $A_5 = 12$ [%] la 20°C, resp. 25 [%] la 760°C;
 - necking at break: $Z = 30$ [%] la 20°C, resp. 40 [%] la 760°C;
 - coefficient of thermal expansion;
 - melting temperature: $T_{\text{top}} = 1723$ [K];
 - longitudinal elastic modulus: $E = 2.06 \cdot 10^6$ [daN/cm²].

For the valve stem, a steel of type 40MoCrNi15X has been used with the following characteristics:

- chemical composition [%]:
C = 0.38-0.43 ; Mn = 0.50-0.80; P = max 0.035; S = max 0.035; Cr = 1.80-2.50; Mo = 1.70-2.20; Ni = 1.45-1.6.
- physical properties:
 - specific weight: $\gamma = 7.8$ [kg/dm³];
 - specific heat at 293 K: $c = 0.44$ [J/g·K];
 - thermal conductivity at 293 K: $\lambda = 0.36$ [J/cm·sec·K];
 - average coefficient of thermal expansion at 293 K: $\alpha = 12.17$ [1/K];
 - electrical resistivity at 293 K: $\rho = 12.9$ [$\mu\Omega \cdot \text{cm}$];
- mechanical characteristics:
 - yield strength: $R_{p02} = \text{min. } 500$ [N/mm²];
 - tensile strength: $R_m = 700-850$ [N/mm²] – after quenching and tempering;
 - elongation at break: $A_5 = \text{min. } 14$ [%];
 - necking at break: $Z = \text{min. } 30$ [%];
 - hardness: max.235 HB – normalize;
- Treatment state: - normalized or quenched and tempered.
 - normalizing: T = 840-870 K and air cooling.
 - quenching: T = 820-850 K and water cooling;
T= 830-860 K and oil cooling;
 - tempering: T= 540-680 K and air cooling.
- longitudinal elastic modulus: $E = 2.06 \cdot 10^6$ [daN/cm²];
- delivery state: hot-rolled;
- hardness in quenched and tempered state = min. 35 HRC;
- melting temperature: $T_{\text{top}} = 1723$ [K].

3.3. Preparation of components for welding

The components to be pressure welded were machined on a lathe. The front surface of the harder component was bevelled at an angle of 3-5° relative to the plane normal to the axis of the components, to ensure uniform heating across the section of the components. The front surfaces of the components were machined to a smooth metallic finish before welding.

The front surfaces of the components and equivalent areas within a width equal to the diameter of the components were machined to a smooth metallic finish before welding.

3.4. Welding parameters

During the practical work, the ZTa-10 pressure welding machine was used, and the welding parameters for pressure welding are as follows:

- Diameter of the components: $d = 20$ [mm];
- Rotation speed of the component in the welding machine chuck: $n = 1450$ [rot/min];
- Maximum cross-section of the welded pieces: $A = \frac{\pi \cdot d_s^2}{4} = 314$ [mm²];
- Pressure force: $F_f = 6 \cdot 314 = 1884$ [daN];
- Upsetting force: $F_r = 12 \cdot 314 = 3768$ [daN].

3.5. Experimental optimization of pressure welding regimes

For optimization, an indirect method called the gradient method will be used. This experimental method starts from an approximate welding regime and approaches the optimal regime through successive improvements in the direction of the gradient. The optimization process includes the following stages:

- the opening phase, which sets the initial level of experimentation, the starting point;
- the exploitation phase, consisting of experiments with various regimes to determine the direction of the gradient;
- the final phase, where the optimal solution is determined.

APPROVAL SHEET OF THE WELDING PROCEDURE ACCORDING TO CR 21-99		WPS No. 1	
WELD CHECK DETAILS		Pp. 1	
UNIT:	Welder:	No. piercer:	
WELDING PROCEDURE SPECIFICATION: WPS		JOINT TYPE: End to end	
WELDING PROCEDURE: FRICTION WELDING			
BASE MATERIAL			
BM 1	Name: 40MoCrNi15X	BM 2	Name: 53CrMnNi219
	Norm: STAS 800-88		Norm: STAS 7382-88
	Type: bar		Type: bar
Length: 150 mm	Diameter: 20 mm	Length: 150 mm	Diameter: 20 mm
Welding equipment: Friction welding machine ZTa-10			
Method of preparation and cleaning: mechanical processing			
WELDING REGIME PARAMETERS			
Part speed, $n = 1450$ rpm; Friction pressure: $p_f = 0.3$ Ma; Friction time: $t_f = 17$ sec.; Discharge pressure, $p_r = 0.45$ MPa; Discharge time, $t_r = 7$ sec.; Axial shortening, $s_a = 15$ mm			

Figure 4 – Specification of the pressure welding procedure for the analysed welded joints, [7]

3.6. Metallographic examination of samples welded under optimal conditions

The samples welded under optimal conditions underwent metallographic examination, adhering to the following rules:

- Ensure that humidity and ambient temperature do not influence the operator's activity and should be within standard atmospheric limits, between 45% and 75% humidity and between 16°C and 28°C temperature.

Sample preparation:

- obtain flat surfaces through grinding, milling, or polishing;
- surface grinding is performed using abrasive materials, manually or mechanically;
- highlighting the structure: the polished, washed, and dried sample is generally introduced/immersed in the reagent that highlights the structure.

Analysis and interpretation of highlighted metallographic structures were conducted using an optical microscope at a magnification of 100x. Microstructures of the welded joints under optimal conditions are presented in Figures 5, 6, and 7.

Figure 4 – Microstructure of the valve stem, 100x: a) base material, b) Heat-Affected Zone (HAZ)

Figure 5 – Microstructure of the valve head (disc), 100x: a) base material, b) Heat-Affected Zone (HAZ)

Figure 6 – Microstructure of the welded zone, 100x

4. CONCLUSIONS

After welding, it was necessary to perform a heat treatment of the welded joint by heating in an oven at 740-760 [°C], for approximately 6 hours, followed by slow cooling along with the oven. After mechanical processing, the valves underwent a quenching and tempering treatment to restore mechanical properties. Following the destructive testing, it was found that all welded joints failed during mechanical tests in the welded seam area.

The mechanical strength of the joint was within the mechanical strength limits of the valve stem material. The purpose of the work was to optimize the butt-to-butt pressure welding parameters of Diesel engine valves, obtaining experimentally the welding procedure approval record.

Figure 7 – Intake-exhaust valves after pressure welding

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DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION SMALL GROUPS

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Abstract: The World Class Manufacturing but also LEAN, TPM, TQM methodologies implies a lot of activities that can only be done as a team. Little attention is paid to the organization of the teams, so the teams are dysfunctional, and they very often spend a lot of effort and do not get the expected results. Therefore, this paper represents a contribution to the methodological approach in the formation of small teams, which should ensure, along with all other prerequisites, the successful implementation of methodologies such as World Class Manufacturing, LEAN, TPM, TQM, etc.

Key words: WCM, Small groups, Optimization, Communication, Decision accuracy

1. INTRODUCTION

The World Class Manufacturing (WCM) is a systematic way to improve continuously manufacturing competence by specially focusing on the followings [1]:

- Substantial quality improvement to satisfy customers
- Cost competitiveness based on elaborate cost deployment
- Short lead time to serve customers better than competitors

Follow WCM way from a firefighting approach to a systematic step by step improvement approach:

1. Identify what problems need to be addressed
2. Detect where they are
3. Prioritize them
4. Analyze them and choose right methods
5. Estimate how much they cost to be solved
6. Implement solutions with rigor
7. Evaluate the achieved results against the original objective

Teamwork is necessary for using many WCM tools, such as those used to define problems using the 5W2H method, identify the root causes through the 4M and 5Whys approaches, and also for defining temporary and definitive corrective measures [2].

The true value of the 5W2H tool is reflected in teamwork. In this way, the team gets a real picture of the problem and data collection is facilitated.

With the 4M tool, each team member tries to establish a relationship between the problem and its potential causes classified into 4 basic groups (machine, material, method, human). The 4M analysis helps teams to identify and analyze the potential sources of problems or inefficiencies within a system. By examining these four key factors, organizations can develop targeted solutions to improve processes and outcomes.

In WCM Culture, depending on the complexity of the problem, we are using different types of kaizens to solve problems and optimize processes. Only in the case of sporadic phenomena, we use quick kaizen where only one employee participates in its making. But even with the basic technical sporadic phenomena, a small team participates in the making of quick kaizen. With complex sporadic

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phenomena (standard kaizen), complex chronic phenomena (major kaizen), as well as with very complex chronic phenomena (advance kaizen), the formation of teams is necessary (Figure 1).

Figure 1. – Size of team depend of probelm complexity

2. SMALL GROUPS

2.1 Characteristics of small groups

Different groups have different characteristics, serve different purposes, and can lead to positive, neutral, or negative experiences. While our interpersonal relationships primarily focus on relationship building, small groups usually focus on some sort of task completion or goal accomplishment. A college learning community focused on math and science, a campaign team for a state senator, and a group of local organic farmers are examples of small groups that would all have a different size, structure, identity, and interaction pattern.

2.2 Size of Small Groups

There is no set number of members for the ideal small group. A small group requires a minimum of three people (because two people would be a pair or dyad), but the upper range of group size is contingent on the purpose of the group. When groups grow beyond fifteen to twenty members, it becomes difficult to consider them a small group based on the previous definition. An analysis of the number of unique connections between members of small groups shows that they are deceptively complex. For example, within a six-person group, there are fifteen separate potential dyadic connections, and a twelve-person group would have sixty-six potential dyadic connections [3]. As you can see, when we double the number of group members, we more than double the number of connections, which shows that network connection points in small groups grow exponentially as membership increases. So, while there is no set upper limit on the number of group members, it makes sense that the number of group members should be limited to those necessary to accomplish the goal or serve the purpose of the group.

Small groups that add too many members increase the potential for group members to feel overwhelmed or disconnected.

Internal and external influences affect a group's structure. In terms of internal influences, member characteristics play a role in initial group formation. For instance, a person who is well informed about the group's task and/or highly motivated as a group member may emerge as a leader and set into motion internal decision-making processes, such as recruiting new members or assigning group roles, that affect the structure of a group [4]. Different members will also gravitate toward different roles within the group and will advocate for certain procedures and courses of action over others. External factors such as group size, task, and resources also affect group structure. Some groups will have more control over these external factors through decision making than others [5].

3. RULES FOR OPTIMIZING SMALL GROUPS

For optimizing WCM small groups it is necessary to establish next rules:

1. Group members must have the basic knowledge and ability to identify and evaluate alternatives. Not everyone needs to be an expert but everyone must be able to ask intelligent questions.
2. Each member must be granted equal status or standing within the group. A single member may be the only one to have the correct solution. Equal status improves the chances that this solution will be expressed.
3. Each member must be allowed to fully explain and argue for his or her proposed solutions. This is the only way a single individual with the correct solution can convince the group.
4. Criticisms of options should be made only after all options have been listed. This helps insure that all options are identified.
5. For major decisions, discussion should proceed until there is unanimous agreement that a workable solution has been reached. Requiring a unanimous agreement forces a greater amount of discussion and gives a single individual with the correct solution the opportunity to convince others. Unanimous agreement can involve compromise. It means that all the members have agreed to a workable solution although it may not be their personal favorite.
6. For minor decisions, the majority rules. This speeds up group activities without a major loss of effectiveness.
7. Groups should have an odd number of members. This prevents ties and improves the odds of making a correct decision when using majority rules.
8. The optimum group size is about 5 members. Groups should be expanded beyond this size only when there is good reason. For instance, effective implementation may require buy-in by more than 5 major stakeholders.

Such groups have two key problems.

The first is management of communication.

The second is decision making accuracy.

Generally having more people in a group increases the likelihood that someone will propose the correct decision. However, more people means more opinions and ideas that have to be communicated and discussed. This makes management of the communication process more difficult and can end up reducing group effectiveness. The best ideas may never even be heard.

4. MANAGEMENT OF COMMUNICATION

The total number of possible social interactions for any sized group is simply the sum of all possible combinations taken two at a time or higher (Figure 2). These are calculated for 2-person interactions using the following Formula:

$$\sum_{x=2}^n \frac{n!}{x!(n-x)!} \tag{1}$$

Where:

n – the number of people in the group

Figure 2 – Group dynamics vs Group size

5. AVERAGE PROBABILITY OF PICKING A GOOD ALTERNATIVE

Divorce statistics for first marriages provide information on the average probability of picking a good alternative in an important decision using partial information. Failure to pick a good alternative can be defined as divorce. Overall, after 20 years 50% of all first marriages have ended in divorce.

Based on the divorce statistic, it looks like 50% would be a good number for the average decision making accuracy of typical individuals. However, closer examination indicates that 50% is a low

estimate. Women who marry when they are less than 18 years old have a 67% chance of ending their first marriage within 20 years. On average, members of this group have not fully developed their ability to identify and evaluate alternatives. Their higher divorce rate skews the average results for all marriages to the low side (Figure 3).

Women between 20 to 24 years of age, on the other hand have a 41% chance of divorce within 20 years. This rate appears to remain approximately stable for women who marry at 25 years of age or older (see Figure 1A). Based on this information 60% accuracy looks like a better rule of thumb for adult decision makers who are using partial information.

Adoption of the 60% average accuracy rule of thumb is not based on a mathematical proof but is reasonable. In many cases a 50% average accuracy could be achieved by coin tossing. It's unlikely for human decision making to be worse on average than 50% accuracy unless fraud or deception is involved. 60% accuracy seems more reasonable without being overly optimistic about humankind's abilities.

Figure 3 – Divorce rates vs age of wife at marriage

6. DECISION MAKING ACCURACY

Assuming an average decision making accuracy of 60% allows us to calculate the probability that no one in a group will identify a good alternative. Obviously if this were true then the group could not possibly make a good decision. The probability of no one in the group identifying a good alternative is found as follows:

$$P_0 = 0.4^n \tag{2}$$

Where:

n – the number of people in the group

The best possible decision making accuracy of the group would be $P_g = 1 - P_0$ (Figure 4).

Figure 4 – Decision making performance vs Group size for various individual accuracies

7. DECISION MAKING ACCURACY – ASSUMPTIONS

1. There is a partial information available on all possible alternatives. Obviously, if there's no information available then decision accuracy is random. If complete information is available then the decision accuracy should depend only on having enough time and expertise to evaluate the information.
2. All alternatives can be clearly categorized as good or bad. Those categorized as good are clearly superior to those categorized as bad. Selecting a good alternative is a good decision by definition. There can be no ties. A decision is either good or bad.

3. The probability of successfully identifying a superior alternative is not influenced by the number of alternatives. If bad alternatives greatly outnumber good ones then it does not make the good ones harder to identify. In real life many bad alternatives can be quickly eliminated.
4. Each group member has the same probability of successfully identifying a good alternative. A decision making group should contain qualified people who have the ability to discuss and analyze the alternatives. When only partial information is available there typically are no experts with the special ability to consistently guess the right answer. If such an expert existed then there would be no accuracy advantage in using a group.

8. CONCLUSION

The Figure shows that a group size of five is optimum. Five takes advantage of the desirability of odd numbers for majority rules decisions. For the unanimous decision making style a group of five will have a 99% accuracy assuming 60% individual accuracies and that a single person with the right answer can convince the others.

Figure 5. Optimum group size

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SMART MINING

Nenad Vušović¹ and Milica Vlahović²

Abstract: The technological innovation and digital transformation implementation is becoming an increasingly important issue for the successful operation of many mining companies today. A new term "Smart mining" is present in modern mining industry. It represents a set of processes of connected geospatial and innovative technologies, which can increase productivity, safety of mining operations and reduce operational costs. In Smart mining, raw data is automatically collected in large quantities via IoT sensors and devices. IoT provides mining companies to connect work and auxiliary machinery, machines and devices, people and sensors into integrated platforms. A huge network of linked physical devices (sensors) enables the data flow management in cycles in real time. The Smart mining technology impact indicates that its adoption is the key to the overall mining sector growth.

Key words: smart mining, geospatial technology, IoT, 5G network technology, digital transformation

1. INTRODUCTION

In its basic activities, mining is traditionally focused on the technical aspects of exploitation and processing of useful mineral resources, in an efficient and sustainable manner. The mineral raw materials exploitation and processing at today's world development level occur with the use of modern scientific achievements, advanced computer technology, geoinformatics, automation and robotization [1]. The technical premises for such a symbiosis are brought by the modern fourth industrial revolution or Manufacturing 4.0, which, compared to previous ones, is taking place at an unprecedented rate. In this 4th industrial revolution, machines are not just automated, but they are ubiquitously connected to cyber systems that monitor, learn and respond to operating conditions changes. The Internet of Things has a central role to play here [2]. However, regardless of the importance of these activities, which cannot be ignored, focusing only on the technical aspects of mining is no longer a sufficient guarantee of mining production success, even in rich ore deposits. Economic skills are an important counterpart to technical achievements, skills and knowledge, in all mineral raw materials exploitation phases. Finally, the exploitation economy is important from the perspective of the necessity of successful business and ensuring adequate profit from mining production. The desired drivers for achieving these goals is the search for new technologies and the tendency to increase the production volume. Many world mining companies allocate significant financial resources to implementing new technologies and the complete automation of the production management process [2]-[4].

The strategy of the mining industry for solving economic business, i.e. increasing productivity, safety of work operations and reducing working costs, is today focused on the concept of Smart Mining. Geospatial technologies (GPS, LiDAR, UAV, GPRS, GIS) combined with digital devices such as cameras, sensors and drones, which connect mutually and to their environment via the Internet of 5G network communication, ensure full automation of work operations and connection of different mining processes into one unit, controlled through modern Dispatch systems. The requirements of mining engineers are aimed at the availability of clearly interpreted heterogeneous data in different digital formats, obtained from various sensors, with the possibility of linking them with other data sources (geological, hydrogeological, production, economic, etc.). All this provides a basis for a comprehensive and balanced discussion on new concepts of mining production management [1-2]. In this study, the idea is to estimate if the moment has come for a powerful turn and a new strategy in mineral raw materials exploitation and processing using the Smart Mining concept.

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2. SMART MINING BASED ON INTERNET OF THINGS AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

The new technological revolution, which is primarily reflected through the application of geospatial technologies, industrial Internet (IoT), 5G network, object-oriented programming, computer vision, artificial intelligence and expert systems, has influenced the development and functionality of many scientific disciplines, including mining. The technological innovation and digital transformation implementation is becoming an increasingly important issue for the successful operation of many mining companies.

Smart mining represents a set of all processes of connected geospatial technologies and takes advantage of innovative technologies, including IoT devices, artificial intelligence, machine learning, virtual and augmented reality, portable sensors on equipment, big data paradigms and centralized databases for their processing. When digital technologies are used together, they generate combinatorial effects, which increase the capabilities of these technologies exponentially – and far more than if each were used individually (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – The trends in digital information technologies in basic industry [5].

Traditional mining operations rely on collecting data on-site and then taking that data back to the main office for processing. This can be a slow process, especially if the work site is in a rural area. This manual process can take a considerable amount of time, especially when dealing with large file sizes typical of geographical surveys and 3D renderings. Smart mining operations use high-speed 5G connectivity to support large data sets and automatically transfer data through secure high-capacity connections at low latency. Operators leverage smart mining technology to gain new insights into their operations, monitor health and safety metrics, and reduce their operational costs as they scale. By bridging the gap between work site devices, corporate network resources and edge computing, enterprises can increase productivity, and reduce their operational expenses.

Mining has always been dangerous work, but smart mining tools set out to make it safer than ever before. Both open pit and underground mining pose unique safety and logistical challenges. In mineshafts, operators can use IoT sensors to monitor seismic activity, structural integrity, and air quality. This data can be collected from underground and relayed to site offices above ground through a network of cellular access points. This 5G wireless connectivity can improve communication underground in areas where traditional radios struggle to reach the surface due to lack of strong coverage / range properties. While open-pit mines don't struggle with underground conditions, landslides, flooding, and

ground collapse all still put miners at risk. Smart mining IoT sensors can monitor ground stability and alert to sudden weather changes in real time.

2.1. Industrial IoT for Mining Industry

The main technology supporting Smart mining is IoT (Internet of Things), which implies using a network of sensors and devices connected via the Internet and eliminating the need for direct human participation in data collection and transmission processes. In Smart mining, raw data is automatically collected in large quantities via IoT sensors and devices.

When used in industries like mining, IoT is called IIoT (Industrial Internet of Things). The Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) is part of the Industry 4.0 concept, which emphasizes the idea of consistent digitization and the connectivity of all productive units, combining the strengths of the traditional industry with internet technologies. IIoT provides mining companies to connect work and auxiliary machinery, machines and devices, people and sensors into integrated platforms. A huge network of connected physical devices (sensors) enables the management of data flow in cycles. Data is transferred from sensors to data warehouses, then to analytical platforms (databases), where they are processed by authorized users, and finally returned to the work process or embedded sensor. Combined with databases and software for data analysis and visualization, these platforms create enhanced views and are a significant factor in decision-making, as conceptually shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Mining Internet of Things [6]

Analyzing enormous amounts of data, either historical or collected during mining operations, gives mining engineers great opportunities to optimize efficiency and profitability. During the mining period in the 20th century, these data were collected manually, thus certainly making it complicated to store big data sets and use them to their full potential. Not only is it now possible to collect large amounts of data, but it is also possible to use Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) to calculate and analyze the results automatically. Artificial intelligence and machine learning are currently the two main strongpoints of automation in the modern age. In addition, artificial intelligence uses data to predict operational needs and generate actionable items for improving processes.

The total number of installed IoT devices in the mining sector was slightly below 0.6 million items worldwide in 2018 [source: Berg Insight] and reached 1.2 million in 2023. It is obvious that the mining industry is finding an interest in implementing IoT networks. Also, IoT networks of devices help in automating processes, streamlining operations, gathering information and connecting different parts of the mining process. IoT allows people, machines and vehicles to stay connected, thus automatically transferring data between devices. All this is included in the work process in the so-called "cloud mining

works", which provides a new type of organizing production and monitoring operational costs at the mine. This increases visibility in the mine to improve maintenance and machine operation.

5G network technology offers numerous advantages such as lower latency, operating speed up to ten times higher than today's Internet networks, reliability, and a high ability to connect up to a million devices per square kilometer.

For Smart mining implementation, the 5G network technology concept offers high reliability and data transfer rate, which is of utmost importance for implementing large automation projects. Joint sensors supported by 5G network technology ensure complete automation of work operations and connecting various mining processes into one unit, controlled through modern Dispatch systems. 5G for Smart mining opens up the autonomous operation of vehicles and equipment (Figure 3). This can save companies thousands of hours in labor and downtime by relying on the deterministic latency and bandwidth offered by cellular wireless technology across mining sites. IoT sensors are inexpensive and require little power to operate, allowing businesses to deploy hundreds across their work environments. Even older analog equipment that lacks internet connectivity can use IoT sensors powered by a mobile network.

Figure 3 – The principle of mine network communication [7]

2.2. Digital transformation in the mining industry

Modern technology is growing very fast, and companies need to adapt themselves to the new changes. Digital transformation plays a critical role in helping entities for this industrial revolution. Improving digital technology such as automation, sensors, advanced analytics, intelligent systems, etc. has forced the companies to think about more productivity and efficiency by using new technologies. The mining industry, as one of the leading industries in many countries, is facing a significant challenge to use the digital transformation when the maturity of people, technology, data, and management systems is not good enough to open the doors of the digital world in front of this industry. The main goal of digital transformation programs in mining has come to define how companies adapt to digital changes. Digital transformation is a transversal process of change in the entire mining industry value chain, from exploration to the production of final products, their commercialization and even the closure of operational mine sites. Figure 4 shows the basic elements of digital transformation [8].

Autonomous mining operations and the possibility of complete control over the entire exploitation technological process in real time represent the ultimate goal of digital transformation. In 2020 Gao et

al. introduced the parallel concept of autonomous mining, a so-called "end-to-end system", based on an IoT-oriented approach and inspired by Artificial Intelligence for modeling, computer applications of data collection, analysis, processing, and distribution as well as for parallel execution in control ACP (Advance Care Planning) concept [7].

Figure 4 – Digital transformation components [8]

The ACP concept consists of fully interconnected sub-systems, modeled and controlled through a parallel virtual mine operation. Through many IoT devices, the virtual mine operation is updated in real time through data fusion, processing, and visualization. Data transmission volume is relatively low as video files are not transferred under normal conditions. The Parallel Management & Control Center (M&C) is responsible for comprehensive real-time monitoring and supervision of autonomous equipment. The parallel mining system consists of autonomous transport platforms, semi-autonomous mining platforms, and remote retrieval platforms. From M&C, the prediction and control strategy is explored in the virtual world through computer experiments and parallel execution can be applied to a real mining system, allowing to deal with unknown work scenarios and tasks (Figure 5). In parallel systems, various intelligent algorithms and optimization algorithms are used to predict and optimize the operation of the real system; they send results to the real system to realize its optimal control [7].

Figure 5 - Solution for IoT-based parallel mines [7]

3. BENEFITS OF IMPLEMENTING SMART MINING

The apparent impact of Smart mining technology clearly shows that its adoption is the key to the overall growth of the mining sector.

The main benefits of Smart mining implementation are:

Reduced Operational Costs. While the upfront costs of implementing smart mining technologies are high, they help reduce mining operational costs in the long run. Tasks that are usually done by people are automated for ultimate productivity, leading to increased profits. Additionally, with automated machines performing various tasks, fewer people need to be on the field at a time, making a reduced task force possible. Automation also makes certain costs unnecessary, like the cost of labour for manual data collection and cable maintenance. A mine's three main cost areas are equipment, energy, and safety. Investing in equipment leads to fewer costs in energy and safety. Collecting data through smart sensors helps mines use energy more efficiently and prevents expensive safety incidents, leading to a safer working environment.

Optimized Workflow and Decision-Making. Big data automation makes it easier to optimize every stage of the mining process, including mine discovery, excavation, stockpile management and sales. Large-scale data gathering leads to less downtime because errors or inconsistencies are immediately identified and addressed sooner than they would have been otherwise. It also simplifies tracking materials across the value chain, so that less time is wasted on figuring out logistics. Regularly going over data allows organizations to continuously adapt and find room for improvement, producing a lean and effective organization. Smart technologies can automatically provide valuable insights, leading to better decision-making and leaving more time for implementing beneficial changes. Additionally, interconnected device networks make it possible to increase collaboration across all levels of a mine, leading to better decision-making.

Figure 6 – Solution for Smart mines [9]

Increased Accuracy in Drill and Blast Mining. In mining, the number of natural resources excavated determines profits. Therefore, making sure machinery is used as efficiently as possible is crucial to meeting performance goals. Using AI and data analytics decreases manually searching for ores and minimizes the possibility of human error. The same mining site becomes more productive and yields more profits when smart technologies are leveraged. The use of high-tech equipment in the mining industry makes it easier to understand a mine's geography and weak points. For example, drone mapping and image recognition technology allow workers to gain a better understanding of a mine's terrain. Automated drones and image recognition technology will be discussed later in this article. More detailed

mapping increases the accuracy of explosive deployment, optimizing various resources like the required number of explosives and hours of labour.

Predictive Equipment Maintenance. IoT sensors generate a constant stream of data on equipment “wear and tear”, allowing for the predictive maintenance of equipment. Predictive maintenance allows a mining operation to know when and where there will be equipment issues based on all variables, like temperature, pressure, and usage. This means maintenance checks and replacements can take place when it is truly needed, saving money and resources compared to constant routine maintenance upkeep.

Improved Recruiting and Employee Retention. Maintaining a skilled workforce is a continuous challenge in the mining industry. Increasing demand for resources, a retiring workforce, and a lack of emphasis on skilled trades in younger generations have created a mining labour shortage. Almost half of the current workforce is over 45 years of age, and 60,000 people will retire in the next decade. One source estimates that 100,000 new workers will be needed in the next ten years to meet sector labour supply requirements (Source: Mines Canada). While mining has been and continues to be a respectable profession for hardworking individuals, fewer and fewer people are interested in pursuing careers in the sector. This lack of interest is caused by a combination of factors, including the physical and mental toll, possible dangers, and the remoteness of many mining communities. Smart mining makes the mining sector more attractive to new workers by making it possible to work from a safe, remote location while using cutting-edge technology. With this new technology, smart mining is introducing more jobs to people from a broader set of educational backgrounds. The new mining workforce includes engineers, computer scientists, programmers and data analysts.

Better Worker Safety with Smart Mining. Perhaps the most apparent advantage of Smart Mining is its benefits for worker safety. Mining is a notoriously dangerous job, with workers facing physical dangers like cave-ins, explosives, and extreme temperatures. Mineworkers are exposed to many medical risks, from physical injuries due to heavy lifting to respiratory diseases like lung cancer and “black lung disease.” There’s also the risk of hearing loss due to loud, repetitive noises. Equipping a mine and workers with connective technologies and providing the appropriate training assists mines in all these areas. AI helps generate detailed, actionable reports, facilitating safety accountability, planning, training, monitoring, and improvements.

Figure 7 – Smart Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) [10]

With AI and machine learning constantly analyzing data, negative behavioural trends can be quickly spotted and recommended corrective training can then be automatically recommended. Smart mining and automated equipment allow many workers to do their jobs remotely, away from the dangers of unstable areas within the mine. Thus, in many cases, new technologies have removed a lot of the labour-intensive work and improved overall safety. For example, autonomous vehicles keep people out of dangerous areas while transporting materials to where they need to go. Additionally, technology helps

workers who can't do their jobs remotely stay safe. In cases where miners must work under potentially dangerous conditions, Smart PPE and wearable sensors can alert workers about abnormalities in their environment or their individual biometrics, prompting them to follow emergency procedures when needed [10].

Prevention of Environmental Incidents. In the mining industry, any errors can lead to injuries and fatalities, as well as have dire consequences on the local environment. The best solution is to take advantage of the latest technology to automate equipment, monitor processes, and use data to proactively predict outcomes and make efficient decisions. Jiskani et al. established a framework based on six leading indicators that evaluate mines for cleaner production: environmental protection, pollution control, waste management, energy and resource consumption, technology enablement and implementation, and strategic and managerial efficiency [10]. IIoT can help mines improve their performance for every one of these factors. The best solution for operations to avoid unexpected consequences on the environment is the large-scale collection of real-time data. Using historical data, AI technology can use algorithms to predict environmental risks and generate actionable insights. AI can also be used to predict energy peaks, allowing operations to control their energy usage, reduce overall energy demand, save costs, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

4. CONCLUSION

Mining today is changing direction and focus, and the application of innovative sensor-based solutions is helping to propel the entire mining industry forward, preparing it to face and overcome the ever-increasing challenges of the modern age. The development of geospatial technologies, along with the sudden affirmation of autonomous decision-making technology, based on artificial intelligence and machine learning, creates the basis for the complete automation of management and decision-making processes within all work processes in mining. The autonomy of work operations, machines, and devices improves the intellectual deficiencies of man, thus reducing errors to a minimum. In cooperation, sensors and applications build Smart mining systems that drastically change conventional mining today. As Industrial Revolution 4.0 accelerates, sensors will play a central role in many technological operations shortly. Digital transformation, geospatial technologies, and 5G mobile networks enable mining companies today to become more economically efficient by increasing production and reducing costs. The apparent impact of Smart mining technology clearly shows that its adoption is the key to the overall growth of the mining sector.

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STUDY ON SOME EFFECTS OF THE COLOURING PIGMENTS OF V4 RESIN USED IN 3D PRINTING

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Abstract: The aim of this research is to examine the properties of tensile strength and evaluate the suitability of V4 resin specimens in various colours for ultrasonic welding. These specimens are made using low force stereolithography (LFS) technology, which lowers printing forces to produce the finest possible finish. The „Form 3+” 3D printer is used to create these components with great precision. Important material properties may be retrieved, examined, and condensed to offer recommendations on the best resin choice for different application scenarios.

Key words: Low Force Stereolithography, V4 resin, 3D printing, tensile tests, ultrasonic welding

1. INTRODUCTION

Using the concepts of stereolithography, LFS (Low Force Stereolithography) is a 3D printing technique that builds things layer by layer from a liquid resin. It is distinguished by using the least amount of force possible during the printing process, which produces printed items with finer details and better print quality. LFS technique is well-known for its capacity to lessen the mechanical strains placed on printed components during the printing process, improving dimensional accuracy and surface smoothness, [1]. This technique is frequently employed in fields like the creation of complex prototypes and components, where extreme accuracy and attention to detail are crucial.

LFS stands out for a few important reasons, [2]:

- High accuracy: LFS technology prints with remarkable accuracy, which makes it appropriate for applications requiring precise details and close tolerances;
- Reduced Print Forces: Unlike traditional Stereolithography (SLA) 3D printing, LFS uses lower forces during the printing process, which can lead to reduced internal stresses and warping in the printed parts;
- Smooth Surface Finish: LFS minimises mechanical forces during the printing process, resulting in smooth surface finishes and reduced visible layer lines on printed parts;
- Laser-Based Curing: To ensure precise and regulated material deposition, LFS uses a strong laser to selectively cure or harden liquid resin layer by layer;
- Spatial Filtering: By optimising the form and intensity distribution of the laser beam, LFS printers frequently use spatial filtering to further improve print quality;
- High-Resolution Details: LFS technology is appropriate for applications like dental equipment, jewellery manufacture, and prototyping because it can accurately replicate complicated and delicate shapes;
- Resin Compatibility: Depending on the material qualities, colours, and applications, LFS printers are usually made to operate with a particular resin that has been optimised for the technology;
- Less Supports: Less post-processing work and material waste might result from LFS printers' potential need for fewer or no supports for overhanging parts;

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- Ideal for Prototyping: LFS is frequently used in rapid prototyping, where precise and thorough models are required for design validation and testing;
- Enhanced Quality Control: The technology is useful for applications where accuracy and quality control are crucial due to its accuracy and consistency.

Benefits of LFS (Low-Force Stereolithography), [3]:

- Large-format 3D printing is a specialty of LFS 3D printing. Furthermore, the customisable printing speed makes it possible to strike the ideal balance between speed and detail;
- The parabolic mirror and laser used in LFS 3D printing provide increased platform uniformity and precision and accuracy, respectively.

The following are other distinctions between the LFS and SLA procedure, [4]:

- It is quicker than SLA;
- Parts printed using LFS technology are finer and more exact than SLA;
- The LFS process employs a smaller laser spot;
- LFS uses an LPU (Light Processing Unit) that contains a lens and mirror system.

Ultrasonic welding is achieved by applying high-frequency vibrations to two pieces or layers of material using a device called a „sonotrode”. Hysteresis and friction at the interface between the two components create heat when these vibrations get there, melting the material and strengthening the bond between them. Moreover, ultrasonic methods may be used to insert, anchor, swaddle, degate, and spot-weld components. Using ultrasonic welding requires that the parts that need to be welded be made of thermoplastic materials. Numerous factors, including chemical composition, density, polymer structure, stiffness (elasticity modulus), viscosity, and melt temperature, influence how weldable thermoplastic materials are, [5].

Photopolymer resins are cured by exposure to UV light. Unlike thermoplastics, they cannot be remelted, shaped, or joined utilising the heat and pressure produced by friction in ultrasonic welding.

Photopolymer-based 3D printing technologies might still be utilised to create weldable prototype components since they have been used to create injection moulds that benefit from the high resolution and superior surface finishes of 3D printed materials.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials used in SLA, DLP, and other resin-based 3D printing methods fall within the category of 3D printed resins. These resins are designed specifically to solidify in the presence of certain light wavelengths, usually visible or ultraviolet (UV) light.

White Resin V4 is ready to use right out of the printer. It has a matte look, a matte surface finish, and fine detailing. Additionally, its understated neutrality makes it a great basis for items that will be painted or go through other finishing procedures, [6].

The preferred tool for general purpose prototyping is Grey Resin V4. This resin has an exceptionally high tensile strength, comparable to that of cured ABS plastic, and is specifically designed for fine detail [7].

Black Resin V4: Comprising the strongest functional components, these resins are sturdy, long-lasting, and able to bear dynamic demands, [8].

Table 1 gives fundamental physical and chemical features.

Table 1 – V4 resins fundamental chemical and physical properties, [9]

<i>Appearance</i>	White, Grey and Black Liquid
<i>Odor</i>	Characteristic Acrylate
<i>Initial boiling point/range</i>	>100°C
<i>Flash point (closed cup)</i>	>93.5°C

Flammability (solid, gas)	Not flammable
Density	1.08 g/cm ³ - 1.09 g/cm ³
Dynamic viscosity	930 cps @ 25°C - 980 cps @ 25°C

The research was conducted using the 3D printer „Form3+” (figure 1) for printing the samples, the „Zwick/Roell Z005” equipment (figure 2) for tensile tests, and the ultrasonic welding tests of the V4 resin were performed using the „Herrmann Ultrasonics Dialogue 1200” ultrasonic welding equipment (figure 3), which is part of the research equipment at ISIM Timisoara.

Figure 1 - „Form 3+” 3D printer Figure 2 - „Zwick / Roell Z005” equipment for tensile tests Figure 3 - Welding equipment of the „Herrmann Ultrasonics HiQ Dialog 1200”

Compared to earlier models, the „Form 3+” 3D printer achieves an efficiency gain of 20% - 40%. These increases in acceleration are the result of innovations in both hardware and software, elevating the most widely used SLA technique to a higher level, [10]. „Form 3+” provides excellent resolution, fast printing, and maximum accuracy.

Precise Accuracy: Accurate and reproducible printing is ensured by a laser processing unit (LPU) built with accuracy in mind. It does this by maintaining a constant laser point with variable density. Clear and accurate components are produced by passing a high-power density laser (250 mW) through a spatial filter to guarantee a clean laser point. The XY resolution of the laser is 25 microns.

Quick Printing Times: Using a strong laser with a high intensity and exact settings for every material, printing may be done quickly. By assigning layer heights based on an intelligent analysis of the components' shape, Adaptive Layer Thickness maximises printing rates without sacrificing fine detail preservation.

Tensile, compression, bending, and multi-axial tests may all be performed with the „Zwick/Roell Z005” universal testing equipment. Testing of bundles, tiny composites, or fibre filaments at high temperatures is made possible by its temperature range of -150°C to 1700°C, [11]. With pneumatic fat grips, the maximum torsional force is 20 Nm and the maximum tensile force is 5 kN.

The „HiQ DIALOGUE 1200” ultrasonic welding equipment, which is utilised in the experimental programmes, possesses the accompanying technological attributes, [12, 13]:

- Power: min. 1200W, 240V/50-60 Hz;
- Industrial front panel for programming and display of technological parameters, colour, 15 inches;
- Software for programming welding parameters;
- Display of welding parameter graphics;
- Display of accomplished parameters;
- Data process memory.

Test specimens were made using the same kind of material, V4 (white, grey and Black), to conduct the research. The file made in the CAD programme „Simplify 3D” was transferred into the printer's

„PreForm” software (figure 4), which controls the printing supports, appearance, and orientation, to make the specimens printable, [14].

Figure 4 - The test specimen design

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Five specimens with the identical measurements (150 x 20/10 x 4 mm) and filling density (100%) were 3D printed for each colour (white, grey, and black) of V4 resin (figure 4). Figure 5 illustrates how the properties of each hue of V4 resin caused variations in the printing time for each specimen.

Figure 5 - The arrangement and print time for test specimens using the Form 3+ 3D printer

Figure 6 illustrates the look of the test specimens that were produced prior to the ultrasonic welding testing.

Figure 6 - The 3D printed specimens' appearance prior to the tensile test

Following several attempts, table 2 provides specifics on the values acquired for the 3D printed V4 specimens.

Five specimens with the identical measurements (150 x 20/10 x 4 mm) and filling density (100%) were 3D printed for each colour (white, grey, and black) of V4 resin (figure 4). Figure 5 illustrates how the properties of each hue of V4 resin caused variations in the printing time for each specimen.

Table 2 demonstrates that following tensile failure, each sample (white, grey and black) displayed a brittle fracture, and the changes in the appearance of the fracture section varied between the three hues. Towards the core of the specimen, the brittle fracture has a larger surface area, and the flow circles this region, [15]. Only in some areas is the flow apparent, and the samples with black colouring show the greatest region of brittle rupture.

Table 2 - V4 resin test specimen test results

Nr.	Specimens' designation	F_{max} [N]	ϵ_b [%]	E_t [MPa]	R_m [MPa]	Fracture appearance	
1	White specimen 1	2370	2,8	1990	52		
2	White specimen 2	1850	2,0	2190	46		
3	White specimen 3	2430	2,8	2270	56		
4	White specimen 4	2000	2,4	2350	50		
5	White specimen 5	2190	2,4	2110	48		
6	Grey specimen 1	2070	3,1	2330	56		
7	Grey specimen 2	2270	3,2	2090	57		
8	Grey specimen 3	2210	3,6	2300	61		
9	Grey specimen 4	2300	3,4	2930	59		
10	Grey specimen 5	1900	2,7	2360	54		
11	Black specimen 1	2170	4,8	2360	58		
12	Black specimen 2	2490	5,1	2190	64		
13	Black specimen 3	2360	5,4	1840	65		
14	Black specimen 4	2430	5,7	2200	63		
15	Black specimen 5	2380	5,3	1740	61		

The tensile strength (R_m) values for the black, grey, and white samples are displayed in figure 7, and the elongation at fracture (ϵ_b) is displayed in figure 8.

Figure 7 - Tensile strength (Rm) values [MPa] on a graph

Figure 8 - The elongation at fracture (εb) values [%] graph

Following ultrasonic welding, the „Herrmann Ultrasonics HiQ Dialogue 1200” equipment produces a report containing measured values, limitations, and a printout of the weld graph, as seen in figure 9.

Figure 9 - Weld graph printout with measured values and restrictions

The values obtained for each specimen after repeated ultrasonic welding experiments are listed in table 3, and figure 10 includes information and a section devoted to the specimens' post-weld inspection.

Table 3 - Data from ultrasonic welding test results

Nr.	Specimens' designation	Triger point (TP) [mm]	Weld time (t) [s]	Depth RPN (RPN) [mm]	Distance ABS (ABS) [mm]	Frequency (f) [Hz]	Dept RPN after hold time RPN + [mm]
1	White specimen 1	7.21	12.00	0.02	7.35	35055	0.07
2	White specimen 2	7.22			7.33	35052	0.07
3	White specimen 3	7.35			7.35	35056	0.06
4	White specimen 4	7.31			7.39	35062	0.04
5	White specimen 5	7.39			7.39	35061	0.05
6	Grey specimen 1	7.59			7.50	35048	0.04
7	Grey specimen 2	7.68			7.49	35042	0.07
8	Grey specimen 3	7.63			7.51	35036	0.06
9	Grey specimen 4	7.65			7.46	35040	0.06
10	Grey specimen 5	7.58			7.47	35039	0.06
11	Black specimen 1	7.91			7.70	35011	0.06
12	Black specimen 2	7.75			7.68	35016	0.05
13	Black specimen 3	7.81			7.65	35012	0.07
14	Black specimen 4	7.72			7.65	35014	0.07
15	Black specimen 5	7.84			7.68	35002	0.06

Figure 10 – Specimens after welding, with an area devoted to their inspection

Following the welding process (see figure 10), it was noted that:

- White resin specimens are extremely fragile; ultrasonic welding was applied to them, but the material broke apart instead of welding. With values ranging from 35036 - 35048 Hz, the welding frequency is the highest (table 3).
- Grey resin specimens have characteristics that are comparable to those of the white specimens; the only distinction is that the welding was done in isolated places and the specimens were not able to endure tensile forces. The frequency range for welding is 35036 - 35048 Hz (table 3).
- Black resin specimens offer the finest welding characteristics. Despite showing minor cracks after being subjected to ultrasonic treatment, they did not fracture, and all specimens were successfully welded. The frequency range for welding is 35002 - 35014 Hz (table 3). were 3D printed for each colour (white, grey, and black) of V4 resin (figure 4). Figure 5 illustrates how the properties of each shade of V4 resin caused variations in the printing time for each specimen.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The experiment findings from 3D printed samples of V4 resin (white, grey, and black) that were created with the same settings, at the same temperature, and at the same dimensions - all with extremely high printing precision - are presented in this publication.

The „Simplify 3D” application was used to develop the samples, and the „PreForm” programme was used to send the design to the printer. The „Form 3+” 3D printer (figure 1), which is specifically designed for resin 3D printing, was utilised to create them.

The numerical values of tensile strength (figure 7) fall within the typical values of the material (V4 resin), ranging between 38 and 65 MPa, according to the results of tensile tests (table 1) performed on the „Zwick/Roell Z005” universal testing machine (figure 2). The specimens' tensile strength values ranged from 46 to 65 MPa.

After tensile tests at a speed of 1 mm/min, the samples' characteristics (table 2) show that the fracture is brittle.

It can be seen from the ultrasonic welding results (figure 9) using the „HiQ DIALOGUE 1200” ultrasonic welding equipment that the resin is brittle in every instance and that welding is not advised (figure 10). Out of the three hues, the black resin, however, demonstrated the greatest welding performance. It may be noticed that the numerical values of frequency are relatively low, with a variation of around 50 Hz, which is inconsequential.

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ENGINEERING INNOVATION: EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF INCUBATORS ON MECHANICAL ENGINEERING ADVANCEMENTS

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Abstract: This paper analyses the role of incubators in the field of mechanical engineering. It highlights the significance of innovation in this field, important for sectors like automotive, aerospace, and robotics, and its broader societal and economic impacts. The study focuses on how incubators support early-stage mechanical engineering startups by providing essential resources, mentorship, and industry connections, crucial for navigating the unique challenges of this field. It also examines the growing trend of entrepreneurship in STEM education and the role of universities in fostering innovation among students. The findings offer valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and incubator managers, emphasizing the critical role of incubators in driving mechanical engineering innovations and contributing to technological progress and economic growth.

Key words: innovation, engineering incubators, prototype development, innovation ecosystem, industry-academia collaboration,

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of innovation in mechanical engineering should be highlighted, as it lies at the core of the technological advancement and industrial development [1]. Mechanical engineering, a discipline that fundamentally involves the design, analysis, and manufacturing of mechanical systems, shape the engineers in various sectors including automotive, aerospace, energy, and robotics. Innovation in this field drives progress not only in these industries but also has an enormous effect on the broader economy and society [2]. One of the key aspects of innovation in mechanical engineering is its role in addressing contemporary challenges such as climate change, sustainability, and energy efficiency. Innovations in renewable energy technologies, for instance, heavily rely on advances in mechanical engineering [3,4]. The development of more efficient wind turbines, solar panels, and biofuel systems are prime examples of how innovative mechanical engineering contributes to sustainable solutions. Moreover, innovation in mechanical engineering is important in improving the competitiveness of industries. In the automotive sector, for example, advancements in material science and engineering have led to the development of lighter, stronger, and more fuel-efficient vehicles [5]. Similarly, in the field of robotics, innovative mechanical designs have enabled the creation of more sophisticated and versatile robotic systems, which are transforming manufacturing processes [6]. The evolution of manufacturing techniques, largely driven by innovations in mechanical engineering, has also been transformative. The advent of technologies such as 3D printing and computer-aided manufacturing (CAM) has revolutionized product design and production, allowing for more complex geometries, reduced waste, and increased customization [7]. Furthermore, mechanical engineering innovations play an important role in improving safety and reliability in various domains. From the design of safer automobile structures to the development of more reliable medical devices, the contributions of mechanical engineering to safety and reliability are significant and far-reaching. In essence, innovation in mechanical engineering is not just about advancing technology; it's about solving some of the most pressing problems facing humanity, improving industrial competitiveness, revolutionizing manufacturing processes, and ensuring safety and reliability in numerous applications.

The rise of incubators in recent years has become a significant catalyst in shaping engineering advancements [8]. Incubators, originally conceptualized to support early-stage startups by providing

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them with essential resources and guidance, have evolved into important pillars in the innovation ecosystem, especially in the field of engineering [9,10]. One of the central roles of incubators in engineering is to lower the barriers to entry for startups. Engineering projects, particularly in fields like mechanical, electrical, and chemical engineering, often require substantial capital, sophisticated equipment, and specialized expertise. Incubators provide startups with access to these resources at a reduced cost, which is crucial for early-stage companies with limited funds [11]. This access not only accelerates the development process but also allows for a greater focus on innovation and experimentation [12]. Moreover, incubators facilitate a unique environment where collaboration and knowledge sharing are encouraged. This aspect is particularly important in engineering where interdisciplinary collaboration can lead to breakthrough innovations. In incubators, engineers often find themselves in a community of like-minded individuals, including mentors, investors, and other entrepreneurs, who can provide valuable insights, feedback, and support [13,14]. Another critical aspect of incubators is their role in bridging the gap between academia and industry. Many engineering innovations originate from university research. Incubators, especially those affiliated with academic institutions, have focus on translating academic research into commercial products. They provide the necessary business environment and industry connections that most researchers lack, which is essential for successful market entry [15]. Furthermore, incubators are increasingly focusing on specific engineering sectors, offering customized support and resources. For instance, some incubators specialize in biotechnology, renewable energy, or robotics. This specialization ensures that startups receive the most relevant and effective support, enhancing their chances of success [16]. The potential role of incubators in engineering also extends to fostering a culture of innovation and entrepreneurship. They serve as hubs where new ideas are constantly generated, tested, and refined.

The aim of the paper is to comprehensively present how incubators, as key elements in the innovation ecosystem, contribute to the advancements in mechanical engineering and represent the needed path in higher education especially for engineers. This involves examining the resources, support systems, and environments provided by incubators and assessing their effectiveness in mechanical engineering projects from conception to commercialization. Another significant aspect of the paper is to evaluate the impact of incubators on the commercial success and scalability of mechanical engineering projects. Additionally, the presented findings hold importance for policy makers, educators, and incubator managers, as it will provide valuable insights into what makes an incubator successful in supporting mechanical engineering innovations. This can guide future strategies and policies for developing more effective incubation programs for engineering entrepreneurship.

2. INNOVATIVE INCUBATORS TRANSFORMING HIGHER EDUCATION PROCESS

In recent years, entrepreneurship has become an increasingly popular career choice, not only for skilled and experienced individuals but also among university students and graduates. There's a noticeable rise in new ventures created by students, especially in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics - STEM fields, and a growing demand for entrepreneurship education and support structures in universities worldwide [17]. Studies have examined these entrepreneurship education programs, finding that such education and an entrepreneurial culture are positively linked to active student entrepreneurship [18-21]. As a result, national and university policies are increasingly promoting student entrepreneurship [22].

Large companies like Dell, Yahoo!, Google, Facebook, and Dropbox were all started by university students [23]. Many corporations are now interested in hiring employees with entrepreneurial skills and in supporting startups to develop innovations [24]. This trend has led universities to include entrepreneurship knowledge in more curricula, particularly in technology and engineering schools [25]. These activities help universities offer practical experiences to students, enhancing their employability and fostering industry collaborations. However, research has often focused on "academic entrepreneurship," involving senior researchers or academics, and has tended to overlook the role of student entrepreneurship in technology transfer [26,27]. Student entrepreneurship is an essential aspect of rethinking academic entrepreneurship, where economic revenue from research commercialization

integrates with technology transfer activities like patents and academic spinoffs. The goal is to shift from a purely research-based university model to one more focused on entrepreneurship and technology transfer. Universities are important in this process as they provide an ideal context for generating business ideas and testing entrepreneurial capabilities. They also create and share knowledge that helps identify new entrepreneurial opportunities, leading to new ventures. University entrepreneurship education, especially at higher education levels, is positively related to nascent student entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial activities in universities involve a wide range of stakeholders who influence the outcomes of entrepreneurship programs and offer unique opportunities for testing and experimenting with ideas. These stakeholders are increasingly involved in developing student entrepreneurship programs, given their interest in employees with entrepreneurial competencies. Researchers [28] point out that two significant activities promoted by universities to support student entrepreneurship are preincubators and incubators. Studies have shown that preincubators positively impact the local entrepreneurial ecosystem in the U.K., both economically and socially [29,30]. The trend of preincubator activities is growing globally, with notable examples like LiU Innovation in Sweden, the Student Startup Summer Pre-Incubator Programme in the U.K., Ubee Lab in France, and eLab, Helix, and Startup Garage in the U.S [30]. These programs, often conducted in virtual or hybrid settings, help students develop and test their entrepreneurial ideas within the supportive university environment. The OECD/EU notes the importance of preincubation in selecting entrepreneurs for more intensive incubation support [31]. Preincubation services include practical entrepreneurship teaching, mentorship, coworking spaces, and venture labs [17]. Research [32] emphasizes the critical role of mentorship in fostering entrepreneurial creation, especially for those with limited entrepreneurship experience. Mentors often come from various university departments or local stakeholders, adding to the complexity but enriching the students' learning and networking opportunities. Study [33] highlight that interactions with other entrepreneurs are beneficial for student entrepreneurship activities. It's common for young entrepreneurs to start businesses in teams, and the members of preincubators often have an informal background. Researchers [34] stress the importance of informal collaborative networks, such as students working with firms, in encouraging student entrepreneurs to start new businesses.

The impact of incubators on mechanical engineering advancements is considered to be important, as seen through various real-world examples and supported by academic and industry studies. Incubators have been inevitable path in transforming mechanical engineering concepts into viable products and technologies, significantly influencing the field. One prominent example is the development of advanced robotics technologies. Companies like Boston Dynamics, which began in an environment similar to an incubator, have made groundbreaking advancements in robotics, a field deeply rooted in mechanical engineering. The supportive environment provided by the incubator, with access to necessary tools, mentorship, and funding opportunities, played a crucial role in their early development and success [35]. In the automotive sector, incubators have also left a significant mark. For instance, the rise of electric vehicles has been partly attributed to the support startups in this sector received from incubators. Companies like Tesla, in their early stages, benefited from the incubator-like environments that provided not only financial backing but also access to industry networks and technical expertise. This support was crucial in overcoming the initial challenges of developing new, sustainable automotive technologies [36]. The aerospace industry presents another example. Startups like SpaceX, although not traditional incubator products, created an internal culture that mirrored the incubator model, focusing on rapid innovation and development. This approach led to significant advancements in reusable rocket technology, changing the economics of space travel [36]. Moreover, the development of sustainable energy solutions, such as wind turbines and solar panels, has been accelerated by the support of incubators. Startups in these fields often face high research and development costs, and incubators provide the necessary resources and connections to industry and academia to bring these innovations to market. In Europe, several successful mechanical engineering projects have been developed in incubators, showcasing the continent's strong innovation culture. Koenigsegg Automotive AB in Sweden develops high-performance sports car manufacturer is known for its innovative automotive engineering. While not a traditional incubator product, the company's growth in the Swedish automotive ecosystem, supported by various forms of government and industry backing, mirrors an incubator's

environment. Koenigsegg has been at the forefront of automotive engineering, with innovations in engine design and aerodynamics [37]. DeepMind Technologies from UK, which started in a London-based incubator, has significantly contributed to engineering fields, including mechanical engineering, through its AI-driven solutions. For instance, their AI algorithms have applications in predictive maintenance of mechanical systems, a crucial aspect of mechanical engineering [38]. Originating in a British incubator, Graphcore develops semiconductors and systems that accelerate AI and machine learning computations. Their technology has significant implications for mechanical engineering, particularly in designing intelligent systems and robotics [39]. Acquired by Qualcomm, Scyfer was a spin-off from the University of Amsterdam and developed in an incubator environment. They specialize in machine learning technologies that have applications in various engineering fields, including mechanical systems analysis and predictive maintenance. AeroMobil from Slovakia, which has been part of the Slovak startup ecosystem and supported by various European incubators and investors, is known for developing a flying car – a hybrid vehicle that combines automotive and aeronautics engineering [40]. These examples from across Europe demonstrate the continent's prowess in fostering mechanical engineering innovations through incubators and startup ecosystems. Incubators have played an important role in advancing mechanical engineering practice as well shaping the future curriculum, as evidenced by their impact in robotics, automotive, aerospace, and renewable energy sectors. Their contribution lies not just in providing financial support, but also in offering access to technology, mentorship, and networks crucial for innovation.

3. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the paper underscores the importance of innovation in mechanical engineering. Innovations in mechanical engineering are important in addressing global challenges like climate change, sustainability, and energy efficiency, as well as in enhancing the competitiveness of industries through advancements in materials science, manufacturing techniques, and the development of sophisticated and safer systems. The emergence of incubators has been a significant development, having an important role in shaping engineering education as well. These incubators provide support to early-stage startups, particularly in engineering fields that require substantial resources. They offer a unique environment that fosters collaboration, knowledge sharing, and bridges the gap between academia and industry, thereby accelerating the journey from innovative ideas to commercial success. Furthermore, the rise in entrepreneurship, especially among university students and graduates in STEM fields, has led to an increased focus on entrepreneurship education and support structures. This shift towards entrepreneurship in universities, supported by incubators, is reshaping the academic landscape, improving students' employability, and fostering closer industry collaborations. Student entrepreneurship, supported by university programs and incubators, is becoming an integral part of the technology transfer process and is driving a shift towards a more entrepreneurial university model.

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ELECTRONICALLY GENERATED VIBRATIONS AS A CAUSE OF DISTRIBUTION OF MATTER

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Abstract: The importance of the beginning of the use of fire in human society cannot be disputed. It can even be said that it was one of the most important, perhaps the most important prerequisites for the beginning of the development of human civilization. The use of fire brought countless advantages but also some dangers. One of those dangers is the uncontrolled spread of fire or fires. This phenomenon is undesirable and from the very beginning there was a need to prevent the fire or, failing that, to put it out as quickly and efficiently as possible. The very first means of extinguishing were water and sand because they were the only elements available at the beginning of the development of human society. Further development of technology brought new technological materials and assemblies which contained special types of combustible materials. Such dangers require special, new chemical types of fire extinguishing agents began to be used. There are also various extinguishing gases, etc. With the latest development of technology, we have come to know that fire can be influenced by sound. A new fire extinguishing method has appeared, which extinguishes the fire with sound instead of certain substances. When "treated" with low-frequency sound of high enough intensity, it was perceived that the fire goes out. The first variants of fire extinguishers based on this principle have already appeared. This paper deals with the basics of fire extinguishing with sound, notably the way the sound itself distributes the fuel in the flame itself, which explains the phenomenon of extinguishing fire with sound.

"If you want to discover the secrets of the universe, think of energy, frequency and vibration" – Nikola Tesla

Key words: new technologies, fire extinguishing with sound, cymatics, matter distribution

1. INTRODUCTION

It is inconceivable for the modern society to exist without the use of fire. It is absurd to imagine our world without it. However, fire, as useful as it is, is dangerous at the same time. A proverb says: "Fire and water are good servants, but bad masters", which clearly indicates that people have known of this problem since the beginning of the world. Fire damage can be huge and can also take human lives, which is unacceptable. The causes of fires can vary just as the materials that can cause them. Most often, the equipment used to extinguish a fire contains water, foam, powder, carbon dioxide and halogen elements [1].

The problem of the nature of the fire itself has always determined the method of extinguishing it. So, over time, the system, materials and techniques for extinguishing fires enhanced. For example, a lot was done to make fire extinguishing powder more effective or extinguishing gases to have a wider range of extinguishing capabilities. This approach has been accepted for some time since it seemed that everything important had already been said and that there would be no new extinguishing methods.

Recently, a revolutionary method of fire extinguishing has come into existence, namely fire extinguishing with sound [2]. It was perceived that fire goes out when "treated" with a low frequency sound of sufficiently high intensity [3]. This new knowledge was used to construct a fire extinguisher with the use of sound. This paper deals with the basics of fire extinguishing with sound, notably the way the sound itself distributes the fuel in the flame itself, which explains the phenomenon of extinguishing fire with sound.

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2. A FIRE AS A PHENOMENON

The first step to solving a problem is to analyze and understand that problem. In our case, it is the understanding of the so-called triangle of fire. Fire is a chain reaction of the elements that make up fire. These are fuel, oxygen and heat. The reaction (burning) continues as long as all the elements required for fire are present. So, to stop combustion, one of the elements of the fire triangle must be removed. Figure 1 shows the fire triangle. These are fuel, oxygen and heat. The reaction (burning) continues as long as all the elements required for fire are present. So, to stop combustion, one of the elements of the fire triangle has to be removed. Figure 1 shows the fire triangle.

Figure 1. The fire triangle [4]

This principle applies to all types of fires and is universally applicable.

3. THE EXISTING FIRE EXTINGUISHING SYSTEMS, MATERIALS AND TECHNIQUES

It can be said that in the modern firefighting arsenal there is a really wide range of firefighting solutions. Each of these methods or techniques has a specific type or types of fire for which it is intended. Fires caused by different fuels are classified as different types of fire. The choice of fire extinguishers in some e.g. business premises depends on the fire hazard of different classes. Some types of fire extinguishers cannot be used for certain types of fires. The choice of fire extinguishers in some e.g. business premises depends on the fire hazard of different classes. Some types of fire extinguishers cannot be used for certain types of fires. This is because each type of fire contains a different type of fuel that burns, and this determines the method of extinguishing it. Figure 2 shows a fire extinguisher based on carbon dioxide. This type of extinguishing is based on breaking the fire triangle in the arm containing oxygen. Basically, at the scene of the fire, it squeezes oxygen out of the flame and replaces it with carbon dioxide, which prevents further combustion of the fuel. This reduces the flame and finally extinguishes it.

In order to comply with fire protection regulations, it is necessary to ensure the appropriate size and weight of the appliance in a space. Of course, every fire extinguisher uses a substance to put out the fire. After extinguishing, the substance either remains at the scene of the fire (dust) or goes into the atmosphere (gas). In any case, the appliance must be serviced before the next use.

Figure 2. Carbon dioxide fire extinguisher as an example of the current technical state

It should be noted that the fire extinguisher requires special care. It must be serviced on a regular basis, and it must be recharged and serviced after each use. This causes additional financial expenses to the user and requires regular monitoring of the servicing period.

The question arises whether it is possible to make a fire extinguisher that would not have to be serviced and maintained and that would not have to have any special maintenance after use? Also, in some situations it is impossible to service the device, so such a new approach would actually be the only possible solution [6].

4. SOUND FIRE EXTINGUISHER

It is an attempt to answer the above requests affirmatively. Efforts to find such a solution have intensified in recent years. The appearance of one such solution is shown in Figure 3, and it suggests fire extinguishing with sound.

Figure 3. Sound-based fire extinguisher [5]

A basic block diagram of a sound-based fire extinguisher is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of a sound-based fire extinguisher

Figure 4 shows the recognizable parts of the device from the block diagram:

- Tone generator
- Audio amplifier
- Source of electricity (battery)
- Acoustic output (speaker)

Based on the image, it can be concluded that the image shows an audio circuit, which is essentially similar to a home audio system. The difference is that attention would be paid to the power of the audio output at low frequencies to make it a mobile application of such an approach.

5. SOUND EXTINGUISHING MECHANISM

In the flame mechanism, the following ideal gas equation applies:

$$PV = nRT$$

P = Gass pressure

V = volume

n = number of gas moles

R = universal gas constant

T = absolute temperature

It can be observed that during the increase in the volume of the fire, the pressure decreases, which leads to a decrease in the temperature of the fire, and the fire is extinguished [5], [7].

Experimental results were also obtained on the dependence of extinguishing efficiency, frequency and intensity of fire. During the research, it was concluded that high-pitched sounds, with frequencies from 30Hz to 60Hz, repel oxygen from the surface of the burning material and extinguish the fire in this way [8].

Figure 5 shows the interdependence of amplitude and frequency, which are required for successfully extinguishing a test fire [9].

We already know that fire is a monolithic structure of three elements. If we remove an element, the fire goes out. During the testing of this idea, it was found that the low frequency sound of 30Hz to 50Hz creates space around the fire and the surface of the flame expands. During the research, it was concluded that high-pitched sounds, with frequencies from 30Hz to 60Hz, repel oxygen from the surface of the burning material and thus extinguish the fire [6]. The aforementioned principle has described been confirmed during testing by the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA).

Figure 5. Dependence of frequency and sound amplitude [8]

6. DISTRIBUTION OF MATTER IN CYMATICS AS A POSSIBLE EXPLANATION OF FIRE EXTINGUISHING MECHANISM

Cymatics is derived from the Greek κύμα which means "wave" [8]. It is usually an experiment in which sand or some similar material is spilled on a steel plate. In this case, a certain electronically generated sound frequency is applied to that plate. Depending on that, different distributions of patterns appear on the board, i.e. Matter is distributed in a certain way. That experiment has been known since the time of Galileo Galilei [10]. One of the possible forms is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Several possible forms of schematics depending on frequency

Such experiments clearly show that the frequency really determines and distributes the matter on the metal plate. Sound is a 3D phenomenon. It spreads spatially from the sound source in all directions. It is fair to assume that this 2D distribution on the plate is also repeated in the 3D space around the sound. The composition of a pattern or distribution of particles follows the form seen in Figure 6.

It is clear that as a result the fuel is not evenly distributed in the flame. This then causes the matter to expand in the flame, which then gives a space without fuel. This is where the flame cools down and eventually causes it to go out.

From this form of distribution of sand particles on the plate, it can be concluded that a redistribution of matter particles (fuel) in space due to the influence of sound. It is logical to assume that, since sound is 3D, it will create a distribution of matter/fuel in space. This, we assume, causes the fire to go out in the part that is without fuel. This is because we know that fire requires a "triangle" from Figure 1.

Figure 5 shows that the fire is extinguished best in lower frequencies. It can also be seen that Simatic has the fewest patterns/the patterns are furthest away at lower frequencies. This all leads us to the conclusion that "empty" spaces/spaces without fuel are highest at low frequencies, ie. then the fuel is grouped into shapes. It tells us that extinguishing is most effective in that range, as experiments show. The influence of sound on the behavior of matter, water in this case, can best be seen in Figure 7 [11].

Figure 7. The influence of sound on the behavior of matter [11]

The distribution and movement/suspension of matter particles in the air is a consequence of acoustic standing waves, which are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Sound levitation

7. CONCLUSION

The history of the human race is elementally a history of constant technological progress. This progress is evident in all areas of human activity. One of the areas that is particularly important for the safety and health of people is the area of fire protection. Fire is an indispensable part of the existence of human society. Although it is extremely useful, it sometimes gets out of control and causes significant problems. Long ago, the problem of putting out fires arose. The first techniques were extinguishing with water. The appearance of synthetic materials caused the appearance of newer types of firefighting techniques. As the last, in a long series of previous improvements, the method of extinguishing fires with low-frequency sound appeared.

All previous firefighting techniques required regular maintenance and servicing of the equipment. Also, after use, the extinguishing agent itself had to be serviced. The latest idea of extinguishing fires with sound eliminates the need for such costs. It also gives a new level of possibilities and significantly facilitates the shutdown itself. In this paper, the principle of extinguishing the flame with sound, the extinguishing mechanisms, and an attempt to explain the physical part of the separation of fuel from oxygen through schematics are presented. We see that the low-frequency sound separates the fuel, shapes it in space, and thus prevents the actual burning of the fuel in the flame. It looks as if, due to the increase in volume, the temperature of the flame decreases, and it goes out.

We witness the beginning of the implementation of this principle in practice, and time will tell how suitable this method is in different situations in real practice.

For the time being, preliminary tests and results have given a bright future for this completely new approach to firefighting.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ITERATIVE PROCESS AND THEORETICAL KNOWLEDGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLES

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Abstract: As the global utilization of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) continues to expand, there is a growing market demand for the development of versatile unmanned systems. These systems play an essential and irreplaceable role in various industries. The development process is intricate, requiring meticulous consideration of structural, static, and dynamic calculations, alongside comprehensive testing. This article focuses on a UAV with a hybrid power system, featuring vertical take-off and landing (VTOL), a composite structure, and an innovative hybrid propulsion system with a starter-generator mechanism. The VTOL capability provides operational advantages, eliminating the need for specific ground conditions or extensive space for take-off and landing. The integration of a starter-generator system optimizes performance by reducing fixed masses, such as batteries. Simultaneously, the composite structure ensures a reduced overall mass while maintaining essential characteristics like strength, corrosion resistance, and fatigue durability. This paper presents a review of the development process, offering insights into the latest technological advancements concerning system and subsystem operations. It emphasizes the financial feasibility and high-quality construction of UAVs. Highlighting the iterative nature of the development process, the article underscores the significance of theoretical knowledge in steering UAV innovation towards constructions that are both economically viable and of high quality. By navigating the intricate landscape of system development, this paper contributes to the ongoing evolution of unmanned aerial vehicles, ensuring they remain at the forefront of technological innovation to meet the diverse needs of contemporary industries.

Key words: VTOL UAV development, composite materials

1. INTRODUCTION

Iterativeness has been crucial in the design phases of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), influencing every stage of development. From initial concept, an iterative approach allows continuous refinement of design and functionality. Prototyping and testing iterations facilitate flaw identification and performance optimization.[1] In aerodynamic design, iterations enable precise adjustments of airfoils for efficient flight characteristics. Integrating diverse systems benefits from iterative processes, fostering synergy and compatibility resolution. This iterative journey ensures that the final product meets high standards in UAV performance, safety, and operational efficiency [2]. The development prerequisites for this unmanned aerial vehicle primarily encompass establishment of the most optimal methodology. The aircraft must possess both vertical take-off and landing (VTOL) capabilities and conventional take-off and landing capabilities. The structure should be composite, ensuring an optimal balance between mass and structural strength. The transition to a piston engine should facilitate a flight autonomy of up to 5 hours, with a payload capacity of 25 kg. The UAV's mission encompasses offensive actions or target positioning and irradiation.

This paper provides an overview of a conceptual prototype solution for a hybrid unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) configured with Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) capabilities. The UAV utilizes four electric motors in a quadcopter configuration to achieve vertical take-off and landing, enabling operation on various terrains. Upon reaching a specific altitude, the propulsion transitions to a fifth engine, a piston engine, for sustained cruising. Simultaneously, a specially developed generator harnesses the piston engine's power to charge the onboard batteries, contributing to the advancement of autonomy in

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unmanned systems. The integration of hybrid propulsion represents a contemporary technological approach that significantly enhances the operational autonomy of such unmanned systems [3].

2. DEVELOPMENT REQUIREMENTS

The development prerequisites for this unmanned aerial vehicle focused primarily on propulsion and operational methods. The aircraft was required to possess the capability for both vertical take-off and landing (VTOL) and conventional take-off and landing. The structure is composite, ensuring an optimal balance between mass and structural strength. Additionally, transitioning to a piston engine was mandated to achieve a flight autonomy of up to 5 hours, with a payload capacity of 25 kg. The UAV's mission encompasses offensive actions, target positioning, and irradiation.

Table 1 – General characteristics of UAV.

Payload	25 kg
Gross Weight	87 kg
Fifth Engine	Piston Engine Twin Spark
Engine Power	14.5 kW
Minimal speed	70 km/h
Cruise speed	150 km/h
Maximum speed	200 km/h
Lift to drag ratio	13
Maximal vertical speed	7 m/s
Wing area	2.2 m ²
Wingspan	4.6 m
Aspect Ratio	9.62

Table 1 outlines the overarching characteristics fulfilled during the development of the unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). The mission profile of the UAV encompasses key stages, including vertical take-off and climb, transition between vertical and horizontal flight, cruise and loitering, hovering, and vertical landing[4],[5]. These stages are carefully orchestrated, with specific attention given to factors such as velocity, engine transitions, and charging mechanisms for optimal performance. The development process prioritized these mission requirements to determine the most effective methods for the UAV's successful realization [6].

3. METHODOLOGY IN DEVELOPMENT

The methodology of development an unmanned aerial vehicle begins with conceptual design, defining goals and requirements. After that, an analytical analysis of aerodynamics, structure and systems is carried out in order to provide the initial structure. The next phase involves the creation of a 3D model that accurately depicts the planned design, which allows further calculations using software tools and verification of the analytical calculation. This model goes through iterative processes, taking into account aerodynamic characteristics, materials and technical specifications. In Figure 1, 3d model of adopted concept is shown. After achieving a satisfactory 3D model, there is a phase where the concept is transferred into physical form. Then comes the production and manufacture of molds for the production of composite structures. After the parts are made, the aircraft is assembled. This prototype

then goes through static and dynamic testing to identify potential flaws. Adjustments are made with the help of theoretical, software calculations and experimental results. This methodology enables the gradual and systematic development of UAV from the initial idea to the actual prototype, ensuring a high level of efficiency and functionality in the final product, applying both theoretical knowledge and experience. The prototype of the aircraft is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. 3D model of UAV

Figure 2. UAV prototype

4. CONCLUSION

This study illustrates a multidisciplinary approach in the design of an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV), encompassing numerous iterations towards the desired solution. This approach extends beyond aerodynamics to include the structure, systems, and other components. Additionally, the methodology employed in designing such a system is meticulously outlined, detailing the progression from concept to prototype and the subsequent development of the final product. The incorporation of various processes, modifying or iterating specific calculations and approaches, facilitates the identification of errors and the correction and enhancement of these issues. Throughout the development of the initial prototype, it underwent all phases and modifications, supported by

calculation verifications and experimental research. The very process of transforming an idea from a white paper into a finished product necessitates a series of optimization processes. The multidisciplinary approach is crucial as it allows the integration of different expertise, including aerodynamics engineers, structural engineers, systems experts, and others. This is particularly significant as UAVs require the integration of diverse aspects to achieve optimal performance. The methodology employed in designing the system emphasizes progression through developmental stages. It commences with conceptualization, where goals and requirements are defined. Subsequently, the prototyping phase ensues, involving the creation of a physical model of the system. Following this is the development of the final product, where additional optimizations are conducted based on the prototype results. This approach facilitates the identification of potential issues in the early stages of development, contributing to process efficiency. These corrections often stem from a combination of theoretical calculations, experimental results, and expert experience. This ensures that UAVs are developed to high standards of quality and system performance. Throughout all these developmental stages, from concept to the final product, continuous optimization is crucial. This process ensures that the UAV meets all specified requirements, whether in terms of aerodynamic characteristics, structure, or system performance. Thus, this research contributes to the understanding and application of a multidisciplinary approach in UAV design, providing a foundation for further development and enhancement of UAVs in the future.

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MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF AN ECO-COLUMN FABRICATED FROM NON-RECYCLABLE PLASTIC-BASED MATERIAL

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Abstract: This paper introduces an innovative technology for recycling materials that are not recyclable through conventional methods, such as composite plastics. The result is an eco-friendly material with good mechanical properties that can replace wood, metal, as well as other plastic materials. The production and application of this eco-material align completely with environmental principles. The mechanical and other properties obtained from laboratory testing of the new materials themselves, as well as the characteristics of a product, eco-column, made from these materials, are presented. The key aspects emphasized in this paper unquestionably affirm that this groundbreaking technology, aptly labeled as 'green technology', emerges as a viable solution for repurposing diverse mixtures of waste plastics, composites, and glass.

Key words: Eco-product, recycling, innovative technology, non-recyclable materials, mechanical properties, eco-column.

1. INTRODUCTION

In everyday use, there is a vast number of products and packaging based on plastic materials. Despite discussions about their recyclability, a significant portion remains as waste, contributing to environmental pollution. Composite plastic variants containing glass, metal, and other materials don't even fall into the category of recyclable, and there is currently no solution for them. Up to today plastic production has been steadily increasing. The worldwide production of plastics reached a staggering 390.7 million tons in 2021 [1]. The packaging industry undoubtedly takes the lead. Plastic bottles for bottled water and soft drinks, a whole range of other types of packaging in the food and other industries, as well as the automotive, electrical, and construction materials industries, are practically inconceivable without the use of plastic. Only 9% of the mentioned quantity of plastic produced after use is recycled, so it is clear that plastic waste represents a global problem [2].

The projected scenario foresees the accumulation of plastic waste surpassing one billion tons by 2050 [2], demanding a rigorous commitment to recycling, alongside advancements in innovation in this field and the development of new types of materials.

2. PREVIOUS EXPERIENCES IN PLASTIC RECYCLING

Current plastic recycling methods necessitate meticulous and thorough categorization of waste materials based on their types, a process that is far from straightforward and demands prior knowledge to effectively segregate and organize them post-collection. In fact, existing recycling technologies can only process homogeneous plastic materials. Sorting plastic materials, especially when dealing with large quantities, is challenging because plastic materials often appear almost identical at first glance, and the markings for plastic type are sometimes hard to spot.

In practical terms, inadequate sorting during the initial selection phase and the subsequent mechanical shredding of plastic waste in the primary recycling phase often result in the mixing of different types of plastics.

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From contacts with larger plastic recycling centers in the country and the region, we have information that during one business year, between 5-10% of the amount of plastic waste processed through primary recycling cannot be further processed with known technology. It is also common for plastic pieces to be sent for recycling that consist of multiple parts made of different types of plastic. The costs of separating such parts far exceed the upper limit of profitability, and they need to be manually separated using various tools. Unfortunately, even such an approach is not a guarantee of achieving complete separation [3, 4]. In such cases, all parts are shredded together and pose a problem for further recycling. At present, there is no established technology for recycling, processing, and repurposing composite and mixed plastics containing glass. Consequently, these waste materials are predominantly either incinerated or disposed of in landfills

This paper presents one of the recycling ideas for composite and mixed plastics. The result is a new, innovative technology that successfully recycles 80% of previously non-recyclable, non-hazardous composite and plastic-glass mix, with only 20% consisting of selected plastic materials. The produced eco-friendly material possesses very good properties, as demonstrated in the following. First we will present the fundamentals of the innovative technology for recycling composite, mixed plastics, and glass.

3. INNOVATIVE RECYCLING TECHNOLOGY

The innovative recycling technology involves processing and reusing different types of composite and mixed plastics, often considered non-recyclable. This is achieved through a specialized process for preparing the initial plastic waste. The essence of innovation lies in a particular type of homogenization of the initial material, coupled with changes in the sequence of operations in the recycling process. The formulation and recipe design that combine waste materials are also a form of innovation, requiring a significant number of hours for experimentation and trials.

In comparison to the conventional recycling process, this one offers the following new solutions (Figure 1):

Figure 1 – The Diagram of Innovative Recycling Technology

- A specific process and formulation for blending waste plastic to achieve homogeneity in a straightforward manner.
- Minimizing or potentially eliminating the need for sorting by type (polypropylene, polyethylene, polyvinyl chloride, etc.) due to our formulation incorporating only 20% selected plastic, as previously mentioned. This results in significant time, labor, and storage container savings.
- Removing the necessity for separate processing of sorted plastic through different lines (washing, drying, granulation) or waiting for one type to complete processing before moving to the next.
- Reducing the mechanical processing steps of waste plastic before the final product is produced.
- Engaging in the processing, recycling, and reusing of diverse waste mixtures, plastic composites, and glass.
- Introducing a novel process and formulation for blending waste plastic to create a versatile material suitable for various end products.

The aforementioned lead to the conclusion that this innovative technology presents a solution for the reutilization of a significant quantity of mixed waste plastics, composites, and glass. It demonstrates energy efficiency and yields a product with a broad spectrum of applications.

After reviewing the literature in this field, it seems that there are similar concepts related to recycling composite and mixed plastic waste. However, these concepts are usually limited to specific combinations of plastic and composite mixtures. Our solution stands out due to its significantly simpler and more extensive mechanical treatment of the initial material. Furthermore, these concepts lack a homogenization process, relying on high temperatures, leading to unavoidably higher energy expenses and, consequently, increased recycling costs.

The formulation of innovative technology involves the following types of waste materials:

- Soft PVC - Index number according to the waste catalog: 150201 [7]. After grinding, this mass is homogenized with glass and other non-recyclable plastics, and it is used as a filler for profiles. It is rarely recycled, even though recycling is possible, and is typically subjected to incineration.
- Rigid PVC - Waste index number: 1501002 [7]. It is used as a filler in a certain percentage or for manufacturing profiles.
- Multi-layer HDPE plastic bags with an addition of 10-15% PA or PET are used as a component for filling material. Waste index number: 150102 [7].
- Ground packaging glass, waste index number 150107 [7]. The potential for recycling is significant, but it has almost become inactive in our region. [8].
- Manufacturing products from non-hazardous waste plastics that have not been suitable for recycling until now, occurs in several stages..
- The extrusion process for creating elongated hollow profiles from recycled plastic,
- Filling hollow profiles with a composite filler made from non-recyclable plastic-based materials, with the addition of ground glass or fabric.

4. APPLICATION OF MATERIALS OBTAINED THROUGH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY

From materials obtained in this way, various products can be made, and the paper examines filled or hollow plastic profiles - eco column, which can serve as a replacement for traditional columns made of wood, concrete, metal, etc. For this patent, an intellectual property protection certificate number 57664 was obtained in Serbia. In future research, it is necessary to conduct a life cycle assessment of the eco-product using the appropriate methodology [5], as this would further position this eco-material.

It is important to note that this innovative technology falls within the recycling sector, which is certainly one of the priority areas for development and investment worldwide, in accordance with the principles of Agenda 2030 [6]. Considering that, until now, there hasn't been a cost-effective and beneficial solution for waste materials such as composite plastics, various plastic mixtures combined with waste glass, etc., the market for this innovative technology, eco-material, and its related products is substantial.

5. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE ECO-MATERIAL AND THE FINAL PRODUCT

There are numerous potential applications for these materials. One of them that we have conducted is a square cross-section column with infill. First, the mechanical properties of the material used for constructing the eco-column and the material used for filling are determined. The tests were conducted in laboratory at the Faculty of Civil Engineering in Subotica.

5.1. The Laboratory Testing of Plastic Material for Column Profiles

The mechanical properties testing of the plastic profile material was conducted on 9 samples [9]. The test specimens were rotationally symmetrical in the cylinder shape with a length of 50 cm, and a diameter of 30 mm (Figure 2), with mass per volume $m=1,414 \text{ g/cm}^3$. The obtained average values of the results are:

- tensile strength: $\sigma = 33.24 \text{ MPa}$,
- recovery of strain after tensile failure: $\delta_E = 98.6 \%$.

Figure 2 – The Characteristic Shape of the Samples for the Tension Testing, Sample During Testing, and Cross Section of the Sample After the Testing

5.2. The Laboratory Testing of Composite Filler Material

The mechanical characteristics testing of the composite filler material based on hydraulic binder was conducted on 9 samples in the form of a prism with dimensions of 4x4x16 cm. The reported results represent the mean values and pertain to a water-saturated state, with mass per volume $m=1.471 \text{ g/cm}^3$. The obtained average values of the results are:

- bending tensile strength: $\sigma = 2.68 \text{ MPa}$,
- compressive strength: $\sigma = 6.22 \text{ MPa}$.

5.3. The Laboratory Compression Testing of Short Columns Until Failure

In order to obtain certain mechanical properties of the eco-columns, tests were conducted on hollow and filled plastic profiles. These tests were conducted on samples that were cut out of the columns (hollow and filled) and prepared in a way to avoid slenderness effects during compression testing. The tests were performed on three samples of hollow and three samples of filled columns. The columns had square cross-section dimensions of 75x75mm, an average wall thickness of 7.2 mm, and a composite recycled mixture as the filler, while the height of the samples was 260 mm. Samples during testing are shown on Figure 3 and obtained diagrams on Figure 4.

Figure 3 – The Samples During Testing: Hollow, Full and Column After Testing

Figure 4 – The Compression Testing Until Failure Data of Hollow and Full Profiles

The maximum achieved compressive force at the point of failure for the filled column is $F=51.87$ kN, and for the hollow column $F=44.89$ kN. The maximum deformations (shortening) for the filled column is $\Delta L=17.21$ mm, and for the hollow column is $\Delta L =25.42$ mm.

5.4. The Laboratory Bending Testing Until Failure

The eco-columns had square cross-section dimensions of 75x75mm, an average wall thickness of 7.2 mm, and a composite recycled mixture as the filler, while the height of the samples was 1998.0 mm. For hollow profiles average profile mass was $m=2.4$ kg. For the filled profiles average profile mass was $m=10.81$ kg. The diagrams obtained are presented on Figure 5.

The bending moment at failure for hollow profiles (measured on the fixed end of the console with a span of $L_c=1.0$ m, loaded with concentrated force at the free end of the console), the average value, was $M =573.9$ Nm, and individual smallest $M =556.5$ Nm.

The bending moment at failure for filled profiles (measured on the fixed end of the console with a span of 1,0 m, loaded with concentrated force at the free end of the console) was, average $M=614.9$ Nm, and individual smallest $M =598.4$ Nm. The deflection at failure (measured on the free end of the console with a span of 1.0 m, loaded with concentrated force at the free end of the console) for hollow profiles (average value) was, $u =33.9$ cm ($L_c/2.95$), and for filled, $u =29.5$ cm ($L_c/3.4$).

Figure 5 – The Bending Testing Untill Failure Data of Hollow and Full profiles

6. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the potential of an environmentally conscious material which exhibits functional attributes and is accompanied by a multitude of advantages, notably: environmental protection, savings and conservation of natural resources - waste materials that were previously incinerated or deposited in landfills are used instead of primary raw materials, it can replace traditional materials (metal, concrete, wood, etc.) in the production of widely applicable products in construction, agriculture, transportation, etc., the products can be recycled again using the same technology, it doesn't require additional protection in terms of impregnation or painting, and green manufacturing technology.

The key aspects emphasized in this paper unquestionably affirm that this groundbreaking technology, aptly labeled as 'green technology', emerges as a viable solution for repurposing diverse mixtures of waste plastics, composites, and glass. It can serve as an example of sustainable development and the circular economy that is pursued on a global scale.

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SECTION 2: TRAFFIC, URBAN PLANNING AND CONSTRUCTION

STRUCTURAL SHAPE DESIGN FOR SPORTS FACILITIES

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Abstract: Structural shape design solutions for sports facilities require the special attention of designers because their design needs to bridge over such a large-scale area. With such a constant demand for this kind of structures, it has been researched in many ways, with numerous solutions emerging. In regard, the designer will attempt to modify the constant functions, constructions, façade, views and urban planning, but endeavor at the same time to give the whole project a sense of originality. In this paper, several characteristic examples of the shape of sports facilities are shown, reflecting the colorfulness of architecture.

Key words: structural shape, design, sports facilities

1. INTRODUCTION

Sports objects, these large buildings, not only become landmarks within a city but also gave new approaches to structure and technology exploration. In modern sports facilities design, engineering and architecture go hand-in-hand. Structural solutions for sports facilities require the special attention of designers because their design needs to bridge over such a large-scale area. From a field and seating to the roof overhead, the designs demand attention to views, light and circulation. Today, architects are exploring how to take these impressive structures to new heights. From cantilevered forms to fully enclosed structures, they represent long-span solutions and innovative roof design. The following examples of sports facilities architecture were analyzed within the scope of the construction time and the features of the location, the size and the architectural form.

Every major sporting event offers the opportunity for the host country to demonstrate their level of structural engineering in the facilities they provide. Building sports facilities has the aim of concentrating sport and recreation, services, catering and similar within a single independent facility, which should offer complete high-quality service that will satisfy the needs of modern man [1].

2. SPORTS FACILITIES SHAPES AND DIMENSIONS

The first physical traces which indicate that people used physical activity as recreation were found near Baghdad around 2500 BC in the form of bronze statues. This most significant civilization began to mature in terms of the development of physical activities as recreation only with the birth of the Aegean civilization, and various archaeological findings have indicated the development of games and competitions in the eastern Mediterranean in different forms of games and fights. The forerunners of sports halls can certainly be found in ancient Greece in the form of buildings for gymnastic exercises called Palestres and Gymnasiums. By definition, Pelestras are spaces for martial arts – boxing and wrestling, while gymnasiums are spaces for general physical education.

Although the history of amphitheatres and stadiums dates back centuries ago, the modern arenas began to take shape in USA, especially in New York and Chicago. The early college gymnasiums at the beginning of the 20th century, first of all in the USA, and later in Western Europe, were often multi-purpose buildings, which were primarily intended for all sports and activities such as gymnastics and general physical education.

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In the period following World War II, the main forms of gatherings were mostly either sporting or cultural, for which large polyfunctional buildings were necessary. For holding such large numbers of spectators and audiences, there was a come-back of the form of the ancient theatre (amphitheater). The challenge faced by those building such large constructions was finding an answer to the question of how to cover the enormous area of the stadium with a roof without internal support. The invention of reinforced concrete created the conditions for solving these problems. The period from the late 50s to the early 60s of the 20th century witnessed the expansion of the use of concrete in the construction of grandiose sports facilities, particularly indoor arenas. The next construction material that made it possible to bridge large spans was steel. Using this material created two new structural systems which signified a revolution in the design of sports arenas. The first system used a spatial steel lattice supported by pillars as the main structural element, while the other used taut steel cables, or the so-called suspended construction.

The dimensions of the facilities, regardless of its shape, were increased by the discovery of new structural systems. Observed throughout history, sports halls have defined their base plan form rather than their final dimensions. There are four most common forms of sports halls, namely: square, circular, elliptical and oval. The challenge faced by the engineers was how to cover the huge space of the hall with a roof without internal supports.

A wide range of facilities, from the earliest humble gymnasiums of yesteryear to the gigantic and extravagant domes and arenas of today, have also undergone dramatic changes in terms of dimensions and shape, as well as structural assemblies and materialization. From the original sports halls that served only for sports purposes, one have come to real multifunctional sports halls with a wide range of uses, which in addition to sports events include music, film, exhibition, that is, halls with many accompanying contents, starting from club rooms, restaurants, amphitheaters, parking space, shopping centers and many others. Often the upgrades in facilities have been an attempt to keep up with the increased interest in sport, while at other times new facilities have themselves laid the groundwork and spurred the popularity of a particular game.

3. THE STRUCTURAL DESIGN – EXAMPLES ANALYSIS

Modern technological development has enabled remarkable progress in the field of architecture. Thanks to the new structural assemblies and contemporary materials, sports complexes and arenas have become extremely representative building structures. Through several characteristic examples, the authors will try to approximate the structural shapes development.

3.1. Palazzetto dello Sport

Palazzetto dello Sport in Rome, Italy, is a work of Annibale Vitellozzi designed in 1956 in collaboration with Pier Luigi Nervi, which was built between 1956 and 1957 for the 1960 Olympics. The project consisted of a circular system of 60 meters in diameter. The cover is made of reinforced concrete prefabricated modules and wedge-shaped. The architect Bruno Zevi compared the Mansion of the Pantheon, suggesting analogies and parallels with the building of Hadrian: based on the same premise Zevi noted that, where the Pantheon has a spherical shape, structure Nervi and Vitellozzi comprises a hemisphere in which light enters laterally and expands the ideal space, mitigating the monumental effect [2].

The Palazzetto is a modest sports stage with an innovative reinforced concrete dome, 58.8 m in diameter and 21 m high, on reinforced concrete ribs, as it is shown in Figure 1. The dome consists of 1620 prefabricated diamond-shaped AB plates, but only 19 different types of them (12 rhomboidal elements of varying shapes and 1 anomalous piece for the apex were repeated 108 times, while the 6 elements for the edge were repeated 36 times). The elements are 12 cm thick, connected by AB ribs visible from the inside. The dome is secured by 36 radially placed inclined pillars in the shape of the letter "Y". The foundation is a reinforced concrete ring with a width of 2.50 m and a diameter of 81.50 m.

Precast "rhomboidal elements" were employed to create the entire dome of the Palazzetto dello Sport. The 12 types of elements all have the same thickness (2.5 cm). They were prefabricated in series by using a mould created with a model. Once these elements were mounted on the scaffolding, only resting on 2 points, the reinforcement was placed in the channels and the cast was executed. The reinforcement also extends to the extrados of the dome where a 3 cm thick layer of concrete was cast.

Figure 1 Palazzetto dello Sport , section. Source: according to [3]

3.2. Madison Square Garden

This hall is also circular in shape, but with an even larger diameter of 130 m. Here too, reinforced concrete is used as the basic structural element from which the columns and stands are built. However, what is innovative about this hall is the way the roof structure is designed, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Construction work in progress on the new Madison Square Garden arena (29th November 1966). Source: according to [4]

In contrast to Nervi's shells on AB ribs, roofs with steel cables are used here for the first time, so-called suspended structures. Cables can bridge large spans, which has encouraged many architects when designing roofs for halls, stadiums, airports, etc. Suspended structures can cover large areas without internal supports. The construction of the roof of this hall is similar to the shape of the wheels on a bicycle. It consists of 48 radially placed cables on a span of 130 m. The outer ring is made of steel blocks to which the cables are connected. The central ring is also made of steel cables. In order to keep the cables taut, concrete blocks or panels that form the roof covering are placed on them. The total weight of the cables used on the roof is 163 tons.

3.3. Zagreb Arena

The unique shape of this building is strongly inspired by its significance in the city context, and has been achieved by synergy between its architecture and structure. Shaped as an oval ribbed white bowl, 86 large pre-stressed, pre-fabricated concrete curved columns form the main façade.

They are mutually connected by an illuminate semi-translucent double-skin polycarbonate envelope which enables various light effects. Suspended roof structure is hanging from those columns leaving minimum roof structure below roof level.

The building is oval in shape (Figure 3a) with a specific construction of 86 pre-stressed reinforced concrete arches at a distance of 5.33 m, which are also the supports of the suspended steel roof structure. Prefabricated AB arches of variable height (from 26.42 to 37.8 m) also form a colonnade on the façade.

The roof bearing structure (Figure 3b) consists of 23 suspended steel girders with approximately 100 m span, mutually connected with two stabilization spatial girders and a network of catwalks. From this structure the load is transferred to the pre-stressed concrete curvedly formed columns, lamellas positioned around the venue's perimeter. They have been produced on the site with support of the site installed concrete production plant and with usage of filtered gravel material from excavation of the pit, by which unnecessary transportation was avoided.

The construction of the stands is made of reinforced concrete slabs supported by AB beams on columns in a grid of 8 x 8 m. The roof structure consists of 23 suspended steel girders at a distance of 5.25 m with a length of about 100 m interconnected and stabilized by 2 spatial girders. The roof is constructed as a steel grill with a trapezoidal sheet and thermal and PVC insulation. The load from this structure is transferred to the prestressed reinforced concrete arches.

Figure 3 Arena Zagreb, a) ground floor; b) cross section. Source: according to [5], [6]

3.4. Four Sport Scenarios

The peculiar shape of the sports stage designed by Equipo Mazzanti and Plan b Arquitectos in 2009, is defined by the structure itself, which for a modular steel structure was chosen. The geometry and layout of the buildings are considered taking into account the prevailing winds, from the north and south, thus automatically generating positive and negative pressure zones. The project involves four sports halls placed next to each other. They are independent units, but the roof vaults are extended to shelter the spaces between, so that they read from above or afar as a unified structure (Figure 4). The shadow these roofs cast on a sunny day further expands the composition, balancing the mass of the stadium. The complex contains halls for basketball, volleyball, martial arts and gymnastics.

Figure 4 Four Sport Scenarios in Colombia, section. Source according to [7]

The geometrical roofing system of parallel strips, that gives the complex its distinctive profile, was conceived for ease of manufacture and assembly, as shown in Figure 5. These parallel bars act again as technical, spatial and bioclimatic patterns. Lattice steel trusses were brought to the site in 12m lengths, bolted together and craned into place. They are set at 5m intervals and are supported at either end by double columns fabricated from reinforced concrete. These stripes are a 7 parallel metallic trusses system which geometry changes and relates directly with the city mountainous or topographic context. A metallic columns system, made by three assembled columns, supports the roof system and acts as a rain gutters, conducting water to the city drainage system.

Figure 5 Four Sport Scenarios, interior structure detail. Source: according to [8]

3.5. Ingalls Hockey Rink

Architect Eero Saarinen's design for the hockey rink (1953-1958) in New Haven, Connecticut, USA, is centered on a massive curving concrete arch (Figure 6 a,b). The arch form creates a structural backbone or spine for the building and has led to many interpretations of the building's form including references to a brontosaurus and a Norse helmet, as well as its most common nickname, the Yale Whale [9], [10].

Figure 6 Ingalls Hockey Rink, a) original drawings; b) layers showing the impacts of various forces. Source: according to [11], [13]

The roof of the building is in the form of two symmetrically placed cylindroids in relation to a straight guide curve (part of a sinusoid) in the vertical plane, the other guide of both cylindroids is a part of an ellipse in the horizontal plane. The wooden roof structure is supported by tension cables and reinforced concrete arches. Sarinen was among the first to use this kind of construction with an arch as a ridge for a sports arena [12]. The roof is a suspension-cable-hung structure, similar to a suspension

bridge, with a 90 m central reinforced concrete parabolic arch. The arch forms the characteristic humpback shape of the exterior before it dives below grade to support the structure. The fins that extend and curve upwards on either end of the arch on the exterior create a concrete canopy over the glass entrances at either end of the oval-shaped rink. Aluminum cables were hung at regular intervals from the concrete arch creating a net that supports the roofing materials. Three external bracing cables were placed on both sides of the building to help resist snow loads. The interior of the roof is composed of tongue-and-groove wood planks supported by the steel cables, while the exterior is covered in a black flexible neoprene. Beneath the roof structure, reinforced concrete walls curve outwards at a 15-degree angle to provide additional structural stability. The cable net structure that rises 23 m above the ice at its highest point, provides a 88 m long and 56 m wide area free of support columns.

4. CONCLUSION

This analysis shows that through sports architecture, different approaches in design were successfully implemented, and that on that occasion, truly extraordinary solutions were obtained that stand out in their surroundings and represent recognizable landmarks. The construction of sports arenas through history has brought much that is new to architects and constructors through the challenge of bridging over large areas and introducing new materials into the construction. Every major sporting event offers the opportunity for the host country to demonstrate their level of structural engineering in the facilities they provide. Building sports arenas has the aim of concentrating sport and recreation, services, catering and similar within a single independent facility, which should offer complete high-quality service that will satisfy the needs of modern man. In this paper, several characteristic examples of the shape of sports facilities are shown, reflecting the colorfulness of architecture..

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CHALLENGES OF INTERIOR ADAPTATION IN CIRCUS FACILITIES

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Abstract: Throughout history, with the greatest expansion during the 19th and 20th centuries, stationary circus facilities were built along the entire Europe. The century we live in does not bring new buildings of this purpose, but a certain number of circuses still exist. Adapting these gigantic buildings to modern times is quite demanding, especially since circuses are no longer relevant as a form of entertainment. In some cases, the adaptation was sufficient in terms of renovation and reconstruction, and somewhere additional purposes appeared, which required the conversion of certain parts of the buildings. The examples of the Belarusian State Circus (in Minsk) and the Bouglione Winter Circus (in Paris) can best show these differences in the adaptation of the interior of circus facilities. Regardless of the fact that stationary circus facilities never appeared on the Balkan Peninsula, these examples tell us that the need to perform circus skills has not disappeared in Europe and that there is a need to preserve such facilities.

Key words: circus facilities, spectacle, adaptation, interior, reconstruction

1. INTRODUCTION

Circus should be associated with colorfulness, laughter and joy, i.e. what circus performances bring with the display of unusual and unattainable acrobatics. This term has two meanings - it represents a stage performance form, but also a building in which this type of entertainment is shown. The architecture of the circus itself is certainly less thought about.

The development of the traditional spectacle began with acrobatics on horses, and over time the training of other animals and comic clown shows appeared. Amazing human skills are still displayed today in circus performances, where the strength and flexibility of the body play an important role. The development of the spectacle continued and now the traditional circus has 8 basic circus genres. There is also a modern circus spectacle, which differs from the traditional one mainly in that it does not include animal shows. [1]

Figure 1 Territorial distribution of stationary circus facilities in the 21st century

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The architecture changed and adapted to the age in which it was built, and in the 21st century, the construction of stationary circus facilities was stopped. Regardless of that fact, there are over 50 such facilities left on the European continent. They are now being reconstructed, renovated and adapted with great difficulty. Some transformations are related to a change of purpose, because in the western part of Europe these facilities have become multifunctional: in addition to the display of circus performances, the buildings have also gained other contents. The situation in the eastern part of Europe is not largely related to the conversion of space. Reconstructions are certainly necessary in order to prevent the deterioration of buildings, while financial restrictions due to the large number of these buildings should be taken into account. [2]

2. ARCHITECTURE AND PREMISES IN CIRCUS

Circus facilities can be prefabricated - known traveling circus tents, and can also be built structures - stationary circus facilities.

Circus buildings have a main arena and auxiliary spaces. In the main arena of the facility there is a stage for showing circus performances and seats for the audience. All circuses have a circular stage space, which is located in the middle of the building, while stands for accommodating the audience are located on all sides around it in a 360° circle. This makes it even more difficult to show circus acrobatics. In stationary circuses, the stage is lowered, and the stands are raised around it. [3]

Figure 2 Belarusian State Circus - a circular stage area, elevated tribunes and glazed technical rooms above them

In the case of prefabricated facilities, auxiliary spaces are separated in the form of wagons and trailers, and in the case of built circuses they form a complex system. Some parts are located under the stands for the audience. These spaces include make-up rooms and dressing rooms, i.e. what is needed to prepare the actors before the performance. As part of the circus, there are also workshops for making costumes and props. Some also have an auxiliary stage area with the same dimensions as in the main arena, which is used for training and preparation of performances, but with the exception that there are no seats for the audience. The circus performances on stage are monitored from the technical rooms and therefore this space is elevated and placed between the stands for the audience. Lighting and music are controlled from there, and what is very important, indispensable props in circus performances are lowered or removed from there. The entire apparatus in the technical rooms is now harmonized with ventilation systems and cameras. [2], [4]

Figure 3 Belarusian State Circus - auxiliary stage area

Circuses are buildings of cultural purpose that include a small zoo in their structure, and that is what distinguishes them. Since all circuses were built in the period when shows with animals were shown, spaces with stables and cages were provided everywhere. Due to the small dimensions of the cages in which the animals are separated, mostly within the circus complex you can find larger separate parts where groups of animals are released in a certain way (for movement and socializing). If the circus no longer shows performances with animals, these spaces have changed their purpose. Instead of stables and cages for housing animals, cafeterias, restaurants, conference and similar smaller halls, suitable for the main circus purpose, can now be found here. This mostly applies to countries in the western part of Europe where laws have been introduced prohibiting the use of animals for entertainment purposes. [2]

Figure 4 The base plan of the Bouglione Winter Circus with the layout of the rooms

One such facility is the Bouglione Winter Circus in Paris (*Cirque d'Hiver Bouglione*). After the reconstruction, the main circus arena remained, but in another part of the building, instead of cages and stables, rooms for other purposes were created.

In the following discussion, reconstructions of two circus facilities in different countries, with different needs in the modern age, will be presented.

2.1. Reconstruction of Belarusian State Circus (*Беларускі дзяржаўны цырк*)

In the Soviet Union, after the October Revolution (20th century), a renaissance period for the circus spectacle followed, when facilities were built en masse for this purpose. Regardless of the fact that there was a wooden circus, a decision arrived from Moscow according to which a master plan was drawn up for the construction of circus facilities in 20 different cities of the USSR, including Minsk. Thus, in 1959, a circus made of solid material was opened.

Serious reconstruction took place between 2008 and 2010. The interior of the circus remained in the luxurious style of the fifties. There are reliefs on the walls with gold leaves and crystal chandeliers, with marble flooring. The museum of the history of the Belarusian circus was opened, where awards, old photos, exhibits and sculptures can be seen. [6]

Figure 5 Stage space after reconstruction - moving platforms

The stage area has experienced the biggest changes - a system for changing the moving platforms has been installed. A pit of about 15 meters was excavated, in which the platforms were placed in four levels. The mechanism allows changing scenes within 15-20 minutes. Depending on the circus act, a certain platform is used, which is characteristic for its surface. A platform with a rubber base is used for animal performances. The second platform has a parquet floor and is used for dance performances, and the third is electronic with light effects. There is a special platform for performances on ice and in water. [7] The main arena seats 1650 visitors.

Figure 6 Layout and plan of the Belarusian State Circus, Minsk

The basement rooms, which served as an atomic shelter, were adapted to accommodate all the animals. A solarium and cloakroom, as well as showers and a dining room, were introduced for the horses. Also, in the underground part there is a space where all animals can move freely. After the reconstruction, additional buildings were found on the same plot. Next to the building itself, a seven-story building was built, which also houses an auxiliary stage. Along the walls of the auxiliary building, there are administrative rooms and a cloakroom.

2.2. Reconstruction of Bouglione Winter Circus (*Cirque d'Hiver Bouglione*)

The development of the circus, as we know it today, began in Great Britain and in a short period of time it moved to the territories of France. During the 19th century, the largest number of stationary circus facilities were built in this country, and later in Germany. Thus, the oldest circus facility, built way back in 1852, has been preserved in Paris. [1], [8]

In history, this facility is known for being the first circus where electricity was introduced. There were several reconstructions, e.g. 1923 wooden seats were replaced with concrete structures. Later, the circus received elements that correspond to television shows and the film industry, which was a facilitating circumstance in the additional adaptation of the building to modern needs. In 2002, it celebrated its 150th anniversary. [2]

Figure 7 Bouglione Winter Circus, Paris

The circus facility became multifunctional in order to adapt it to the modern needs of society in this country. The capacity of the stands was reduced to 1600 seats due to the law on fire protection. After the abolition of performances with animals, the premises for their accommodation were adapted for new needs. Transformed spaces have become: bar and restaurant (*Bar de L'impératrice*), an elegant meeting room (*Les écuries Napoléon III*) and a small theater (*Théâtre de la Ménagerie*). The facility is adaptable for almost all types of events, and is used less for circus spectacles.

The restaurant and bar area is intended for cocktails and meetings. The specific social space *Les écuries Napoléon III* has 14 cabins, created from former stables. There are tables inside the cabins, so it is possible to create a more intimate atmosphere. The small theater can accommodate 480 guests. Cabaret can also be revived here. [9]

Installations and electrical elements were reconstructed. The renovation was focused on cinema decoration, that is, the introduction of a large screen that can be used for various occasions. Additional screens can be set up and cameras can be directed to show movies or what is happening on stage. [10]

Figure 8 Cinema screen stretched over the stands in the main arena of the Bouglione Winter Circus and the premises of Les écuries Napoléon III - created from the former stables

3. CONCLUSION

The number of circus buildings has decreased on the European continent. The show has gone into oblivion, but somewhere it still makes a unique kind of entertainment. These facilities, on an extremely large scale, are difficult to maintain. There are many problems, from outdated installations and props, through the deterioration of facades and roofs, to the abandonment of certain rooms inside the building itself. Different principles of adaptation and reconstruction are applied in order to maintain these objects and adapt them to the modern age.

The question arises, how long will these buildings be able to keep up with the times and follow new trends, and will the interior adaptations be able to respond to all the demands that modern times bring. These two examples of stationary circuses tell us about what the needs were in the previous centuries, when they were built, but they also tell us about what is current today in order to continue working in the modern age. Since the examples are from different countries, there is a difference in the adaptations: in Belarus, the circus spectacle remained current, so the reconstruction focused on improving the stage for the circus spectacle, while the example in France shows us that the actuality of the circus spectacle is weakening in these areas and in order to preserve these facilities, it is necessary to introduce additional contents that accompany other current stage performances.

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INFLUENCES ON ANGER AMONG CYCLISTS IN NOVI SAD

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Abstract: Previous research shows that anger and rage among road users often lead to inappropriate driving, increased speed, poor perception of risk and thus a higher risk of accidents. Traffic anger is understood as a personal tendency that makes people blame others for unfulfilled goals or mistakes in specific situations. Observing the categories of traffic participants and the percentage of injuries received in relation to the type of traffic accident, it is easy to determine that pedestrians and cyclists are the most vulnerable category of participants. Considering that cyclists are often a nuisance to pedestrians and drivers of motor vehicles, because they share space with them, they are subjected to situations in which they express anger. The aim of this scientific research was to determine which situations in traffic have the greatest influence on anger in cyclists and how it affects their further participation in traffic.

There is very little research on the topic of cyclists in the area of the city of Novi Sad, as well as the entire territory of the Republic of Serbia, and this research should answer the question of what degree or level of anger our fellow citizens feel when riding a bicycle and whether they express it or not. also to the question of whether anger can be managed and in what ways it could be done.

Key words: cyclists, anger, anger, traffic

1. INTRODUCTION

Young cyclists (10-15 years and adolescents 15-18 years) have a proportionally higher risk of cycling injuries than older groups, while older cyclists (65+ years) have a higher risk of injury [1]. Interactions with motor vehicles are therefore the most risky traffic situation for cyclists [2]. The majority of cyclists killed or seriously injured take part in collisions at intersections [3]. Misunderstanding and inaccurate expectations about mutual behavior are important factors in car and bicycle crashes. [4]. Cycling is different from driving a car in many ways. Handling, effort taken to move and all interactions with other road users are more direct for cyclists. They also have a higher proportional risk of being seriously injured in a traffic accident than motor vehicle drivers because they do not have a chassis to protect their body [4]. Successful interaction with others, especially with motorized road users, is extremely important for the health of cyclists. Cyclists often find themselves in mixed traffic situations. This includes situations with motorized vehicles and bicyclists on the same road as non-motorized road users and bicyclists on sidewalks. [5]. Conflicts arise when there is great uncertainty regarding the behavior of other traffic participants [5]. In addition, conflicts also occur if other traffic participants perceive cyclists as an unnecessary nuisance [6], which is a common case where motorized traffic shares the same road as cyclists. In addition, cyclists can pose a threat to pedestrians when sharing the sidewalk. Therefore, cyclists have a greater chance of encountering situations that can cause conflicts and anger than any other road user. Unlike motor vehicle drivers, the roles of emotions and personality of cyclists in traffic have only just begun to attract scientific attention. Many scientists began to qualitatively investigate the perceptions, cognitions, emotions and open behavior of cyclists and other road users towards cyclists.

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A theme that emerged was a sense of an informal hierarchy of road users, with those who exclusively travel by car behaving more aggressively towards other road users, while those who also use other means of transport (e.g. cycling or walking) show more empathy towards other road users. [7] found that the lack of infrastructure triggers emotional stress, which is responded to by anxiety, anger and fear. Therefore, this paper examines the reasons for cyclist anger in relation to other cyclists and cars.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 RESEARCH METHOD

The research was conducted in the territory of the city of Novi Sad. The research material and survey forms were distributed in the following six locations: the plateau in front of the Promenada shopping center, in front of the entrance to the Student Canteen, the main entrance to the town beach Štrand, the main entrance of the Faculty of Technical Sciences, the entrance to the Electrical Engineering School "Mihajlo Pupin" and the corner of Futoška and Jevrejska in your face. The survey forms were distributed in groups of two students in shifts, in order to cover the time when people come and go from work, college, high school, recreation and the like. The entire statistical analysis was carried out in the SPSS 22.0 statistical package, and the data were then transferred to Microsoft Excel 2010.

2.2 FILE FORMS

Through the cooperation between the Faculty of Technical Sciences in Novi Sad and the Higher education technical school of professional studies in Novi Sad, a survey form was formed consisting of 156 questions divided into 4 scales, related to the behavior of cyclists and their habits while driving, as well as 9 personal questions, i.e. questions about the survey participant himself. The time required to fill out the form was between 15 and 20 minutes. At the end of each form there is a map of addresses, i.e. places where the participants, after filling out, could put the survey in a specially marked box set up for research purposes. Also, research participants could take a photo of the completed survey form and send it to the e-mail address or Viber contact person, which was on the first page of the form. In addition, there was an option to fill out the form in electronic form, the link of which could be accessed by scanning the code that was also on the first page of the form.

2.3. PARTICIPANTS AND PROCEDURES

A total of 87 people submitted a completely or partially filled survey form about their experiences while riding a bicycle. Out of the total number of submitted survey forms, 50 of them were filled in by members of the male gender, and 36 by members of the female gender, while one form was missing that information. The participants in the research reported that in the largest percentage of cases (64.7%), the purpose of their trip was work, i.e. shopping. Then followed the answer that the bicycle was most often used for recreation (30.6%), and the lowest percentage was for professional riding (4.7%). Most of the completed forms (43%) were returned by university and college students, followed by secondary school participants (40.7%), followed by persons with a completed sixth level of education, i.e. master's studies (14%) and finally primary school students (2.3%). As many as 88.4% of respondents reported that they most often ride a bicycle in the neighborhood along the bicycle path.

Finally, the respondents answered a question about their participation in traffic accidents in the past two years. The largest percentage, as much as 87.2% of respondents, reported that they had not had a single traffic accident in the past two years, 9.3% ie. a total of 8 participants had one traffic accident in this period, and 3 participants, which is 3.5% of the total number of respondents, had two or more traffic accidents

3. RESEARCH RESULTS

Drivers of motor vehicles, pedestrians and cyclists are equally participants in traffic, what we can distinguish them individually is their reaction in a given situation, e.g. expressing anger, anger or frustration in unexpected situations in which the participants found themselves. It all depends on the general expression of feelings, behavior in general, personal characteristics, attitudes, knowledge, life habits, home upbringing, etc. According to the survey that was carried out, the analysis of the results for the anger of cyclists can be divided into the following categories:

1. Analysis of the results of the level of anger of cyclists when interacting with other cyclists,
2. Analysis of the results of the level of anger of cyclists when interacting with cars.

3.1 ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF THE LEVEL OF ANGER OF CYCLISTS WHEN INTERACTING WITH OTHER CYCLISTS

Out of a total of 57 survey questions answered by survey participants, we include 19 survey questions in this category. In these questions, the respondents had the opportunity to express their anger towards other cyclists, i.e. towards their behavior while riding. They rated their answers on a scale of 1, which meant - "I'm not angry at all", number 2 - "I'm a little angry", number 3 - "I'm quite angry", number 4 - "I'm very angry", and number 5 - "I am extremely angry."

Table 3.1 Tabular presentation of the results of the analysis of the level of anger towards other cyclists

Assumption	1	%	2	%	3	%	4	%	5	%
A cyclist on a cycle path is cycling on the wrong side	23	26,4	20	23,0	21	24,1	16	18,4	7	8,0
By his behavior, the cyclist forces you to get off your path	3	3,4	14	16,1	26	29,9	15	17,2	29	33,3
The cyclist is moving very quickly towards you and thus obstructing you	31	35,6	24	27,6	19	21,8	10	11,5	3	3,4
The cyclist who overtakes you does not give an audible signal with the bell	32	38,1	31	36,9	9	10,7	10	11,9	2	2,4

A cyclist rides a bicycle in the middle of the track	22	25,9	18	21,2	27	31,8	10	11,8	8	9,4
The cyclist behind you warns you by excessive use of the bell	23	27,1	22	25,9	18	21,2	13	15,3	9	10,6
Cyclists move on the cycle path parallel (in pairs) and talk	21	24,4	19	22,1	20	23,3	12	14,0	14	16,3
A cyclist overtakes you unsafely	13	14,9	27	31,0	26	29,9	10	11,5	11	12,6
A cyclist meets you at night and blinds you with a bright or flashing light	23	27,1	26	30,6	14	16,5	15	17,6	7	8,2
Cyclists do not pay attention to the sound signal of the bell that you give them	7	8,1	18	20,9	30	34,9	17	19,8	14	16,3
A cyclist moves in a winding direction on the cycle path	13	15,1	20	23,3	21	24,4	19	22,1	13	15,1
The cyclist does not give you the right of way	14	16,3	28	32,6	22	25,6	10	11,6	12	14,0
The cyclist in front of you is moving too slowly	32	37,6	20	23,5	14	16,5	10	11,8	9	10,6
Cyclists send you negative comments	14	16,1	13	14,9	24	27,6	18	20,7	18	20,7
A cyclist overtakes you in a narrow lane	17	20,0	23	27,1	27	31,8	11	12,9	7	8,2
A cyclist does not give a hand signal when turning or stopping	21	24,4	22	25,6	18	20,9	16	18,6	9	10,5
A cyclist is blocking the cycle path and deliberately does not want to move	5	5,7	6	6,9	15	17,2	19	21,8	42	48,3
A cyclist rides at night without using lights	17	19,8	21	24,4	18	20,9	16	18,6	14	16,3
Cyclists use mobile phones or listen to music with headphones in their ears	21	25,0	17	20,2	21	25,0	9	10,7	16	19,0
Average value	19	21,6	20	23,8	21	23,9	13	16,5	13	14,9
1 – I'm not angry at all; 2 – I'm a little angry; 3 – I am quite angry; 4 – I am very angry; 5 - I am extremely angry										

If we look at the tabular presentation, Table 3.1., we can single out two questions that received the most answers with an anger intensity score of "5, I am extremely angry", namely: "the cyclist forces you to get off your path with his behavior", which is 29 33.3% of the respondents answered that "a cyclist is blocking the bike path and deliberately does not want to move", which received the most answers from 42 respondents, i.e. 48.3% of the total survey participants. In addition, it can be seen that active cyclists rated the most appropriate with the ratings "2 I'm a little angry" and "3 I'm quite angry" which was rated most often with 23.9%.

3.2. AN ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF CYCLISTS' ANGER LEVELS WHEN INTERACTING WITH CARS

Table 3.2 Tabular representation of the results of the analysis of the level of anger of active cyclists towards drivers of motor vehicles

Assumption	1	%	2	%	3	%	4	%	5	%
Car drivers make negative comments or swear words at you when you are cycling on the road	16	18,4	15	17,2	14	16,1	15	17,2	27	31,0
Car drivers do not pay attention to cyclists when turning	3	3,4	9	10,3	16	18,4	23	26,4	36	41,4
A car crosses your path when leaving the parking lot or opening the vehicle door	5	5,7	10	11,5	19	21,8	24	27,6	29	33,3
A car overtakes you at a short lateral distance	8	9,4	13	15,3	20	23,5	30	35,3	14	16,5
Driving a car in a bicycle lane	3	3,5	7	8,2	11	12,9	15	17,6	49	57,6
Cars overtake you and then turn right or stop in front of you	3	3,4	11	12,6	13	14,9	17	19,5	43	49,4
The car forces you out of your lane	2	2,3	11	12,8	25	29,1	26	30,2	22	25,6
Cars overtake or swerve in front of you at high speeds	1	1,2	10	11,6	25	29,1	21	24,4	29	33,7
Car drivers honk at you when you drive on the road	8	9,4	13	15,3	31	36,5	17	20,0	16	18,8
Riding motorcycles/mopeds on the bike path	14	16,1	22	25,3	14	16,1	20	23,0	17	19,5
A car overtakes you in a narrow lane	10	12,0	17	20,5	22	26,5	20	24,1	14	16,9

Cars block the bicycle crossing in front of you when stopping at traffic lights or when turning and passing pedestrians	8	9,5	16	19,0	19	22,6	19	22,6	22	26,2
Parking a part or the whole vehicle on the bicycle path	4	4,8	9	10,7	14	16,7	28	33,3	29	34,5
The car does not give you the right of way	6	7,1	11	13,1	27	32,1	24	28,6	16	19,0
The car moves quickly and overtakes you at a small lateral distance	6	7,1	14	16,7	18	21,4	24	28,6	22	26,2
Average value	6	7,6	12	14,7	19	22,5	21	25,2	25	29,9
1 – I'm not angry at all; 2 – I'm a little angry; 3 – I am quite angry; 4 – I am very angry; 5 - I am extremely angry										

In this table, where active cyclists answered questions related to their relationship with motor vehicle drivers, i.e. situations that cause them to feel angry towards motor vehicle drivers, we can clearly see a linear growth of anger among cyclists. The smallest number of those who said that they are "not angry at all" (only 6 respondents out of a total of 87), and the highest number of those who said "I am extremely angry" (25 out of 87 respondents).

4. CONCLUSION

Anger and aggression, both in cycling and in traffic in general, often lead to risky situations and irresponsible driving, which can result in serious consequences, even if we consider that cyclists are a vulnerable category of participants. The level of traffic safety for cyclists is very low, because they are often difficult to see by other road users, and they often do not follow the rules themselves, which is why they are often involved in traffic accidents. Cycling is very common in Novi Sad and cyclists make up a large number of traffic participants in the city area. The network of cycling surfaces is one of the longest networks in the entire Republic of Serbia. What is important, in order to reduce the level of anger, it is necessary to work on traffic education and upbringing, but also on our own attitudes, behavior, moral values and the propagation of tolerance so that we understand that anger is not the only option, but we need to learn to follow the actions of others road users and we try to assess their intentions in order to react correctly, properly and safely in unforeseen situations or in any other kind of affect. Proper cycling is a healthy and fun activity. Cycling offers a fun, consistent and long-term sustainable form of exercise while improving cardiovascular function and general endurance. Also, riding a bicycle provides a feeling of freedom, without the use of external energy sources. On the other hand, for slightly more extreme riders, riding a bicycle is an excellent source of adrenaline and excitement. So, in addition to the great advantages that cycling brings, safety stands out as a great disadvantage and the biggest problem.

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CONNECTING LOGISTICS WITH URBAN PLANNING: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract: Planning sustainable logistics systems in urban areas significantly influences the pursuit of societal sustainable development goals. The growing recognition of logistics' pivotal role in achieving urban sustainability has resulted in a surge of articles linking urban planning with logistics. This article aims to provide a concise bibliometric analysis of the current literature in this domain. The analysis concentrates on exploring ongoing topical trends, evolving collaboration patterns, and highlighting some of the most notable and impactful research articles. To conduct this analysis, data from Web of Science (WoS) was used.

Key words: urban planning, logistics, sustainability, analysis, bibliometrics

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, the topics of sustainability and sustainable development have attracted significant attention within both expert and scientific circles [1]. It is argued that achieving sustainable development rests upon three main pillars: economic, environmental and social [2]. Rapid urbanization during the last century has put urban areas under great pressure because they did not manage to adapt to the forthcoming changes. Inadequate urban planning has led to the fact that modern cities are places with the most visible sustainability issues in society. Even though they occupy only 3% of global space, they are responsible for 75% of global energy consumption and air pollution [3]. Sustainability in urban planning is recognized by the UN as an important topic because the treatment of urban sustainability issues determines whether the world and society will move towards a sustainable future [4].

The realization of logistics activities, especially transportation, is a significant cause of negative effects on urban sustainability [5]. Traffic congestion, air pollution, inefficient realization of logistics processes, the increase in logistics costs, noise, etc., are some of the consequences caused by the neglect and inadequate approach to planning urban logistics [6]. The main problem is the lack of planning activities and encompassing, long-term city logistics policies and practices. The existence of multiple stakeholder groups with different goals, various characteristics of urban areas, and the lack of knowledge in the field of city logistics in administrative structures of the city additionally complicate the issue and make the planning of city logistics complex [7].

A recent study by [8] performed a comprehensive bibliometric analysis of urban studies and urban planning. This article focuses on a more narrow aspect of urban planning tied explicitly to logistics. The goal is to perform a brief bibliometric analysis of articles that consider solving logistics problems/issues as an integral part of urban planning. The focus is on investigating the ongoing trends in the field and the existing collaboration patterns, as well as highlighting some of the most influential works over time.

2. DATA AND METHODS

For this analysis, data from Web of Science (WoS) were used. The data were extracted according to a user-defined query whose aim is to encompass all relevant works that bring logistics and urban planning into connection. The search was based on keywords that are considered the most relevant for such a topic.

The query used for extracting the bibliometric data was:

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TS = (URBAN PLANNING AND (LOGISTICS OR TRANSPORTATION OR SUPPLY CHAIN OR INTERMODAL OR WAREHOUSE* OR VEHICLE OR NETWORK* OR GOODS OR DELIVERY)) AND DT = (ARTICLE OR REVIEW)

The logic behind the query was to connect the term „urban planning“ with some of the most common logistics-related terms („logistics“, „transportation“, „supply chain“, „intermodal“, „warehouse“, „vehicle“, „network“, „goods“, „delivery“). The focus was set on journal articles and reviews. The articles were then filtered by the meso citation topics „Transportation“ and „Supply Chain & Logistics“ defined by WoS. This filtration resulted in 5173 articles considered for the bibliometric analysis. The articles were grouped into four groups depending on the time period they were published: before 2001, between 2001 and 2010, between 2011 and 2018, and after 2018.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The initial look into the considered dataset shows that only 2.4% of all articles were published in the first period (125 articles). In the second period, 505 articles were published (9.8% of all articles), 1632 articles (31.5% of all articles) in the third period, and the remaining 2911 articles (56.3% of all articles) in the fourth period. In the following text, a more detailed look into collaboration networks and topics of the research is presented.

3.1. Geographical collaboration

When considering collaboration between countries it is worth mentioning that in the first period (between 1960 and 2001) there were no significant collaboration patterns in the field. In the second period (2001-2010), the USA was the main global collaboration partner, but the collaboration network was still sparse (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Geographical collaboration between 2001 and 2010

During the third period (2011-2018), China emerged as an equal global collaboration as the USA. Other countries were more present in the collaboration network as well (Australia, France, Sweden, Canada, Iran, England, Netherlands, etc.) (Figure 2). During the fourth period (after 2018), China emerged as the leader in global collaboration networks (Figure 3).

Figure 2 – Geographical collaboration between 2010 and 2018

Figure 3 – Geographical collaboration after 2018

3.2. Keywords and topics

The keywords that appeared in the observed article groups were diverse and evolved over time. Keywords such as „land-use“, „transportation“ and „model“ were in the top 10 most used keywords for all four periods. In the first period, the keywords were more general („GIS“, „travel“, „traffic“, „transportation“, „model“, etc.), while they became more focused in later periods. „Optimization“,

„accessibility“, and „design“ gained more prominence after the year 2000, while „mobility“ and „built environment“ became more popular after 2011. Keywords that appeared in the fourth period among the top-ranked but not in previous periods are „impact“ and „public transport“.

Figure 4 shows the co-occurrence of keywords in the period after the year 2018. Four clusters of keywords are evident. The keywords in the blue cluster are focused on urban form, built environment, travel behaviour, health, mobility, choice, etc. Keywords in the green cluster are related to the topics of growth, impact, network, accessibility, transit, etc. The red cluster consists of keywords that are more oriented towards modelling, planning and optimization. The yellow cluster consists of keywords related to passenger-related topics such as cycling, policy, behaviour, safety, mode choice, etc.

Figure 4 – Co-occurrence of keywords in the period after 2018

3.3. Most influential articles

Some of the most influential articles from the first period focused on travel behaviour and its dependence on urban form. The article [9] argues that accessibility is a fundamental concept in transportation planning and analysis. The author developed a model for measuring accessibility in urban areas. The article [10] describes the characteristics of transportation demand management as a required step for applying policies that focus on improving the efficiency of urban transportation systems. The article [11] highlights that transportation planning plays a crucial role in ensuring that the quality of life in cities is not affected by their constant growth.

The most influential articles in the second period focus on the connection between the built environment and travel/mode choice [12], the identification of sustainable urban forms and their design concepts that contribute to sustainability [13], and the developing of simulation models for supporting land use, transportation planning and growth management in growing urban areas [14].

Some of the most notable articles from the third group focused on humanitarian logistics network design [15], evacuation transportation modelling [16], and transit-oriented development of urban areas [17]. Another notable article from this group is [18] which introduces the concept of urban computing, discussing its general framework and key challenges from the perspective of computer sciences.

The most influential articles published after 2018 highlighted the role of operational research in green freight transportation [19], electric vehicle routing problems [20], the impact of urban design on the economic vitality of cities [21], the integration of e-scooters in urban transportation [22], and collaborative urban transportation [23].

3.4. Discussion

The analysis of geographical collaboration shows some already known trends in the scientific literature that apply to the selected group of articles in this study. Collaboration networks became denser over time because of the intensification of collaboration between countries globally [24], the proliferation of research publications on a yearly basis [25], and increased researchers' institutional and geographical mobility [26]. The USA had the central collaboration spot in the second period, but after 2010, China overtook the leading position.

Regarding the keywords, as expected, with time they became more diverse and specific. In the last two periods (after 2010), keywords that refer to sustainability issues such as „accessibility“, „mobility“, „impact“, „design“, etc. became more popular. We might assume that understanding the importance of operational research in planning sustainable logistics systems [19] caused the proliferation of articles that propose specific methods and approaches for modelling such systems in the function of urban development. Similarly, the most influential works in the field evolved from some general discussion on the topics of urban form, accessibility, transportation demand management, etc. to a more refined understanding of the significance of logistics in achieving urban sustainability.

4. CONCLUSION

This article presented a brief bibliometric analysis of articles that brought into connection urban planning and logistics. The goal was to promote the importance of logistics in achieving local (urban) sustainability. The results show how the research has evolved over time – from more general articles to more logistics-specific studies that propose methods, approaches, and concepts for achieving sustainable city logistics systems in urban areas. The findings regarding the collaboration patterns are aligned with the general trends in the scientific literature – the rising role of China in global collaborations. Future works should dive more deeply into the topic and compare the solutions proposed in the literature with the solutions practically applied around the world.

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IMPLEMENTATION OF PHYSIOLOGICALLY EQUIVALENT TEMPERATURE (PET) ANALYSIS IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYLLABI

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Abstract: This paper explores the implementation of Physiologically Equivalent Temperature (PET) analysis as a crucial component in higher education curricula, particularly in fields addressing urban planning, environmental science, architecture and public health. PET, a comprehensive index for assessing thermal comfort and heat stress, is increasingly relevant in the context of urban heat islands and climate change. The paper initially delves into the theoretical underpinnings of PET, emphasizing its importance in understanding urban thermal environments. It then advocates for the integration of PET analysis in academic syllabi, highlighting the current educational gap and potential benefits. Methodologies for embedding PET in educational processes, including practical workshops and case studies, are proposed, underscoring a multidisciplinary approach. Real-world applications are illustrated through various university-based case studies. The conclusion emphasizes the necessity of PET analysis in preparing future professionals for tackling urban thermal challenges, advocating for its broader adoption in educational settings to foster sustainable and climate-resilient urban development.

Key words: PET, education, thermal comfort, heat stress, syllabi

1. INTRODUCTION

The escalation of urban heat islands effect and the increasing frequency of extreme heat events have brought to the forefront the critical need to understand and mitigate urban thermal stress. In this context, the Physiologically Equivalent Temperature (PET) emerges as a pivotal tool for assessing thermal comfort and heat stress in urban environments. This tool, grounded in human biometeorology, provides a comprehensive measure that encapsulates the combined effects of air temperature, humidity, wind speed, and radiation on human physiology.

The significance of PET analysis extends beyond the realm of meteorological and environmental studies, casting a direct impact on urban planning, public health, and ecological sustainability. As urban populations continue to swell and climate change exacerbates thermal extremes, the incorporation of PET analysis into higher education curricula becomes not just relevant but imperative. This integration serves a dual purpose: firstly, to equip future professionals with the necessary tools to address and adapt to urban thermal challenges, and secondly, to foster a holistic understanding of the interplay between urban environments and human health.

Despite its growing importance, the presence of PET analysis in academic curricula, especially in disciplines such as urban planning, environmental science, and public health, is notably sparse. This gap indicates a missed opportunity in educating the next generation of professionals who will be at the forefront of designing and managing climate-resilient cities.

This paper aims to explore the necessity and potential methodologies for the incorporation of PET analysis into higher education curricula. By examining existing curricular structures, identifying gaps, and proposing integration strategies, this study endeavors to establish a framework that can be adopted

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by educational institutions to enhance their educational offerings and better prepare students for the challenges of urban thermal stress in the context of a changing climate.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF PET ANALYSIS

Physiologically Equivalent Temperature (PET), as conceived by Höppe (1999), is a robust index used to assess thermal comfort in various environmental contexts. PET is calculated using the Munich Energy-balance Model for Individuals (MEMI), which is based on the human energy balance [1]. This index simulates the temperature at which the human body, while maintaining a core temperature of 37°C and a heat resistance of clothing typical for indoor activities, would experience the same thermal sensation in an idealized indoor setting [2]

PET has been widely acknowledged as a comprehensive tool for evaluating human thermal comfort and stress in outdoor environments [3]. It integrates various meteorological parameters such as air temperature, humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation, offering a more holistic approach to understanding human thermal perception [4]. In urban planning and public health, PET plays a crucial role in identifying heat stress conditions, aiding in the development of heat mitigation strategies [5]. Categorization of human sensation and thermal stress level according to PET values is given in Figure 1.

Human feeling	PET(°C)	thermal stress level
Very cold	<4	extreme cold stress
Cold	4.1 - 8.0	strong cold stress
Cool	8.1- 13.0	moderate cold stress
slightly cool	13.1 - 18.0	mild cold stress
Comfortable	18.1 - 23.0	no thermal stress
mild temperate	23.1 - 29.0	mild heat stress
mild	29.1 - 35.0	moderate heat stress
Hot	35.1 - 41.0	Strong heat stress
Very hot	>41.0	extreme heat stress

Figure 1. Comparative view of Human feeling, PET values and Thermal stress level categories

Significant research has been conducted on the application of PET in different climatic and geographic contexts. Studies by Blazejczyk et al. [6] and Matzarakis and Mayer [7] have illustrated PET's effectiveness in evaluating microclimatic conditions in urban areas and its impact on human health. Further research by Hwang et al. [8] has demonstrated the relevance of PET in designing climate-responsive urban spaces. These studies underscore the utility of PET in guiding urban and environmental planning towards sustainable and health-focused outcomes.

3. NEED FOR CURRICULUM INTEGRATION OF PET ANALYSIS

The contemporary curricula in higher education, particularly in fields such as urban planning, environmental science, and public health, often overlook the critical aspect of urban thermal comfort and stress. According to a study by Kántor and Unger [9], urban climatology is insufficiently represented in most urban planning programs. This gap highlights the need for an educational paradigm shift to include comprehensive environmental analysis tools like PET in the academic syllabus.

Integrating PET analysis into higher education curricula can significantly enhance students' understanding of the complex interplay between urban environments and human comfort. As indicated by Emmanuel and Johansson [10], incorporating biometeorological concepts into educational frameworks prepares students to address urban climate challenges effectively. Furthermore, studies by Lin et al. have shown that knowledge of thermal comfort indices, including PET, is crucial for developing sustainable and livable urban spaces [11].

To effectively integrate PET analysis into higher education curricula, a multidisciplinary approach is required. This integration could include developing new courses focused on urban microclimate analysis, embedding PET-related modules in existing courses, and encouraging research projects that utilize PET as a primary tool [12]. Collaborative efforts with industry practitioners can also provide practical insights and enhance the real-world applicability of the curriculum [13].

4. METHODOLOGY FOR INTEGRATING PET ANALYSIS INTO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

To effectively integrate PET analysis into higher education, it is essential to adopt a comprehensive and interdisciplinary approach. This involves not only the inclusion of PET in the syllabus but also the development of interactive learning methods. As highlighted by Charalampopoulos et al, experiential learning through field studies and hands-on projects enhances the understanding and application of complex concepts like PET [14]. Incorporating simulation tools and software for PET calculation can also be an effective educational strategy.

Practical workshops and case studies are invaluable in translating theoretical knowledge into practice. According to Nikolopoulou and Lykoudis, workshops that involve real-world problem-solving, data collection, and PET analysis can significantly improve students' ability to apply these concepts in urban design and planning [15]. Additionally, integrating case studies from diverse climatic and urban settings, as discussed by Johansson et al, provides students with a broad perspective on the application of PET in various environmental contexts [16].

Assessing the effectiveness of PET integration in the curriculum is crucial for continuous improvement. Adopting a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative feedback from students and educators, can provide comprehensive insights into the effectiveness of the integration. This assessment can help in refining the educational strategies and aligning them more closely with the learning outcomes.

5. CASE STUDIES IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PET ANALYSIS

To illustrate the practical application of PET analysis in higher education, this chapter examines several case studies from universities across the globe. For instance, the curriculum at the Technical University of Munich incorporates PET in its urban planning courses, focusing on sustainable urban development [17]. Similarly, the University of Freiburg has integrated PET analysis in its environmental science programs, emphasizing climate-sensitive urban planning.

The practical application of PET analysis in real-world scenarios can be highlighted through projects undertaken by students. For example, a study conducted by Lin and Matzarakis involved students in assessing the thermal comfort of different urban settings using PET, providing valuable insights into urban microclimate management [18]. Another notable project is the adaptation strategies developed for heat-stressed urban areas in Singapore [13].

The impact of integrating PET analysis into higher education extends beyond academia. It equips future professionals with essential skills to address urban thermal comfort challenges [12]. The case studies demonstrate not only the educational benefits but also the potential societal impacts, such as improved urban planning and public health outcomes. The positive feedback from these implementations suggests a promising future for broader adoption of PET analysis in educational curricula worldwide.

6. CONCLUSION

The comprehensive examination of the Physiologically Equivalent Temperature (PET) analysis within the realm of higher education underscores its vital role in addressing contemporary urban and climatic challenges. This paper has elucidated the theoretical foundations of PET, highlighted the necessity for its integration into educational curricula, proposed methodologies for its effective incorporation, and presented case studies illustrating its practical application.

The integration of PET analysis into higher education is not merely an academic exercise but a critical step towards equipping future professionals with the necessary tools to tackle urban thermal comfort and heat stress issues. As urban areas continue to expand and the impacts of climate change become increasingly pronounced, the ability to accurately assess and respond to urban thermal environments becomes paramount.

The methodologies and case studies discussed in this paper demonstrate that PET analysis can significantly enhance students' understanding of urban microclimates and human thermal comfort. These competencies are crucial for developing sustainable and livable urban spaces, particularly in the face of escalating urban heat islands and climate change.

Adoption of PET analysis in higher education represents a forward-thinking approach to environmental and urban planning education. It fosters a deeper understanding of the complex interplay between urban environments and human health, ultimately contributing to the creation of more resilient and climate-adaptive urban spaces. Future research and educational endeavors should continue to expand upon this foundation, exploring innovative ways to integrate PET analysis into diverse educational settings and disciplines.

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RESEARCH ON THE TRANSPORT SYSTEM CHARACTERISTICS FOR THE PURPOSE OF IMPROVING SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY IN URBAN AGGLOMERATIONS

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Abstract: *The basic characteristics of transport systems in urban agglomerations include: high level of traffic congestion, significant increase in noise level, decreasing level of traffic participants' safety, as well as declining level of service quality. The presented issues have significant impact on the functioning of social processes, the economy, the life and work of residents, as well as on the city spaces, and can only be addressed in qualitative way by a systemic approach, that is, by preparing a sustainable development strategy from which sustainable mobility plans should derive. Implementation of the sustainable development strategy (integral economic, technological, social and cultural development in line with environmental protection needs) involves, among other things, harmonizing traffic movements on the network with lifestyle of residents in urban agglomeration.*

The paper presents research on the transport systems characteristics for the purpose of improving sustainable urban mobility.

Key words: *transport system, sustainable development, sustainable urban mobility, traffic congestion, traffic safety.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The city represents a complex system of diverse functions that are spatially dispersed. Within the urban space, there is a constant need for movement among residents in order to meet various needs: first of all, for going to work and returning home from work, and then also for shopping, recreation, etc. On the other hand, there is no activity or space in the city that is not in some way dependent on transportation of supplies, shipment of goods [1]. Also, every city is a part of an internally connected urban system, which, on the other hand, is a part of regional, national and international urban system. In this way, cities form a complex interconnected network. The current transport system of the European Union (EU) is faced with a growing conflict between increased demand for mobility, due to which negative environmental impacts issues are becoming more and more critical, and the undeniable contribution of transport to the overall economic development. Practically, arguments related to increased traffic congestion, poor quality of services, frequent traffic accidents, damage to the environment and isolation of certain regions, are opposed to facts that confirm economic significance of the sector: the total traffic costs within the EU amount to around 1000 billion Euros, contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is over 10%, and the employment sector employs over 10 million people [2]. Contemporary approaches to addressing the mentioned problems can be found in the sustainable transport principles, which was developed as part of the sustainable development strategy. Reducing the use of motor vehicles is achieved by undertaking "soft measures", such as: the use of different types of communication, advertising, and education in order to change attitudes and behavior in traffic [3].

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2. SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY - A CHALLENGE FOR CITIES

In the majority of European cities during the past twenty years, the traffic volume has increased, as well as the number of cars. Along with the increased use of cars, the number of negative consequences also increases, such as the number of traffic victims and property damage, traffic congestion, noise, air pollution, contribution to global warming and extension of space occupied by cars. It is clear that some of the pollution related problems can be addressed to some extent by reducing fuel consumption or through the so-called "cleaner automotive industry", but other problems cannot be solved by improvements in the motor vehicle industry. This refers to endangering individual health (traffic victims and lack of physical activity), the economy (through congestion and loss of time), the environment (land use, noise and effects on wildlife) and division and loss of living community space. Moreover, the increase in traffic volume, particularly in urban agglomerations, generates the construction of new roads. Considering the Braess' paradox, which points to one fact that every capacity addition to the network does not necessarily mean an improvement in quality [7], solving of the aforementioned problems, both in the current state and within short-term and long-term scenarios, should be approached through analysis of the entire system. In the revision of the White Paper on Transport [8] in 2006, the European Commission announced its intention to present the Green Paper on Urban Transport [9] and subsequently organized numerous public discussions. According to the Green Book findings and extensive material from discussions, forums, and conferences that preceded its publication in 2007, in the European Union over 60% of population resides in urban areas, and almost 85% of the European Union domestic product is generated in urban areas. Obviously, cities are drivers of the European economy, because they attract investments and jobs, and at the same time represent the living environment for the vast majority of the population, and it is of great importance that the quality of life in these areas is as high as possible. This is the reason why the problem of urban mobility in Europe is being considered very seriously and comprehensively. Any strategy formulated at the European level can only be successful if decisive action is undertaken at the local level, if concrete activities are implemented by local authorities. Starting from that, the new motto of this European strategy of the urban environment mobility which meets people's (citizens') expectations is the creation of a new urban mobility culture. By combining strategies aimed at reducing the use of individual cars and strategies focused on enhancing the attractiveness of alternative modes of travel (public urban transport and non-motorized traffic), an improvement in the overall functioning of the transportation system is achieved [10]. In addition, when preparing the future models, it is necessary to involve citizens within the public consultations framework, as well as when developing the action plans, studies and implementation of measures in the transport system [11].

3. OVERVIEW OF PREVIOUS RESEARCH, RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

In European practice, "hard" and "soft" strategies are used, between which there is a significant difference. "Hard" strategies refer to infrastructure (such as building roads, taxation or new services). The stated measures can play significant role in combating the increased use of cars in the network. For instance, introducing a new bus or metro route could be an important or significant measure that will enable larger number of people to use public mass transport. Accordingly, objectives of the strategies - economic measures, that is, of economic instruments, are increasingly focused on discouraging the use of private and encouraging the use of public passenger transport, as well as encouraging energy-efficient modes of transport and types of vehicles, thereby reducing pollutant emissions [12]. On the other hand, the key role of the "soft strategies", that is, of "campaigns" is often simply informing people who predominantly use cars for their travels. Even in cities with a well-organized public transport system, new services alone may not bring about significant changes [13].

The most common objectives to be achieved through the campaign are:

- **Reducing the intensity of motorized traffic:** reducing the number of trips made by private cars and avoiding unnecessary congestion is the primary objective of any transport plan, especially in urban areas.

- **Increasing the safety of all traffic participants:** increasing road safety through reduction of road accidents and number of road fatalities implies an impact on traffic participants. Following the EU example, the European Commission has set a goal of halving the number of road traffic victims in the EU by 2020, and all countries intensified the work of the traffic police, improvement of legislation, with the aim of increasing road traffic safety, primarily by implementing long-term campaigns [14].

According to research conducted in the "Tapestry" [15] international project, with a team composed of 24 groups from 12 countries, the activities necessary to be undertaken when designing the campaign in order to promote sustainable mobility have been identified. Also, significant possibilities of applying the campaigns within the framework of enhancing the traffic participants' safety [16] were identified; algorithms were established that can assist in defining the target group, in monitoring behavior changes, as well as in choosing an adequate campaign strategy. Before the campaign implementation, it is important to understand connection between an attitude toward a problem and a mode of behavior, because it is crucial for the campaign success. A common mistake because of which several campaigns failed is assuming that habits will change quickly. It is unrealistic to expect that individuals who exclusively use their own car for transportation will change that habit overnight and start using public transportation. Research in other areas, such as promoting a healthy lifestyle, has shown that awareness and opinion about certain problem must be changed first; only then it is realistic to expect changes in behavior. Based on research conducted within the "Tapestry" project, the "Seven Stages of Change" model was developed, representing quality modeling for target group identification and campaign strategy determination. Once the target group's way of thinking and attitude regarding the transport system problems are established and understood, it is easier to assess what the realistic campaign objectives are and how to achieve them. The author Lewis A. [17] states that, within the "Tapestry" campaign analysis, the most significant are: general objectives, the campaign initiator, strategic partnership and campaign financing. In accordance with previous researches [18, 19, 20, 21, 22] including the two most significant ones on the road safety improvement, with the review done in 17 countries and the analysis of 265 campaigns [23], as well as those previously mentioned in the area of sustainable mobility – "Tapestry", it can be concluded that the most common objectives to be achieved through the campaign in transport systems are: reducing the traffic volume, enhancing the safety level of all traffic participants, environmental protection, promoting healthy lifestyle, and accessibility. Researchers have found that national campaigns are most effective when they are broken down into lower-level campaigns [24], with necessary coordination between institutions at all levels, in accordance with the recommendations presented in the Green Paper published in 2007. Accordingly, it is highly important to conduct education of all structures involved in the campaign implementation and to evaluate problems in the urban agglomeration system.

By reviewing previous researches related to the analysis of transportation system characteristics, considering that "the professional public generally represents a high-quality group of respondents who, each in their specialized field, are competent to observe problems globally and systematically, precisely defining them while seeking causal relationships among their manifestations" [25], the significance of factors was evaluated within the established criteria on a scale of 1 to 5 based on evaluations of the study participants. In the mentioned Study on Traffic Improvement in Nis, the absolute significance was determined as follows: traffic congestion (4,5), time losses of passenger vehicles (3,7), time losses of the Public City Passenger Transport vehicles (3,9), number of vehicle stops during travel (3,8), endangerment of pedestrian in traffic (4,6), signaling and protective urban equipment in traffic (4,1), visibility of intersections (4,4), road and sidewalk quality (4,2), vehicle noise (4,0), among others. In line with available theoretical assumptions concerning the functioning of public urban passenger transport systems as one of the fundamental elements of sustainable mobility [26], a comprehensive study was conducted on the territory of the local self-government unit [27], analyzing the following parameters: enabling mobility for specific social groups under favorable conditions (weighted number of responses 6,3; average rank 6,3), passenger transport system development (weighted number of responses 5,4; average rank 5,5), lower operating costs of the

system (weighted number of responses 4,2; average rank 4,1), improving the service quality level for the system users (weighted number of responses 2,9; average rank 2,8), achieving high participation of the passenger transport system in the total number of trips (weighted number of responses 1,9; average rank 2,0).

The conducted research on characteristics of taxi passenger transport as a subsystem of the city transportation system, with special emphasis on the attitudes of local government bodies and existing taxi operators (obtained through expert opinion surveys), explicitly reveals the most significant objectives to be achieved in the process of reengineering the taxi system structure, so that hierarchy in implementing the process of reengineering the structure, in terms of importance ranking, in the first place requires creation of conditions for establishing sustainable mobility within the transport system (R1), coupled with increase in the quality level of transportation services (R2). Third in significance (R3) for the experts is the enhancement of taxi transportation organization and management, with improved monitoring and work control (R4), and ride reservation systems (R5) [28].

Also, in researching the transport system characteristics within the subsystem of light rail transport [29], the SWOT analysis tool was used to support decision-making and environment analyzing in systematic way. Within Strengths: service quality (reliability, transport speed, comfort), low operational costs, eco-friendly transport. Weakness: large investments, limited number and distribution of stations, longer walking distances. Opportunities: availability of the public transport market due to existing transport conditions, creating a habit among passengers to use public transport. Threats: increased use of passenger motor vehicles, economic sustainability - dependence on subsidies. Through the conducted analysis in the study, the authors came to conclusion that in the city transport model, it is necessary to primarily utilize Strengths while minimizing the negative impact of external Threats, that is, to use ecological features to reduce the use of passenger cars.

In order to prepare a high-quality model of sustainable mobility, it is necessary to conduct research where current problems in the transport system will be examined by competent persons involved in planning and infrastructure management.

In accordance with the above, a survey was conducted in the local self-government on a sample of 64 experts, in June 2023.

Figure 1 – Valuation of problems in the city transport system

Existing problems in the city transport system	Class - Rank	Significance factor	Absolute significance
Traffic congestion	1	1-10	8,8
Parking of motor vehicles	2	1-10	8,6
Safety level of traffic participants	3	1-10	8,5
Safety level of non-motorized traffic flows	4	1-10	9,0
Spatial organization of the network surfaces – Accessibility of traffic surfaces	5	1-10	7,8
Route network organization and service level in public passenger transport subsystem	6	1-10	8,0
Impact of railway infrastructure in transport system	7	1-10	8,4
Equipment and quality of traffic signals	8	1-10	7,5
Level of traffic culture	9	1-10	8,8

Based on the example of conducted research and statistical processing of the obtained data, the absolute significance of defined problems in the city transport system was determined. Thereafter, priorities can be established for defining the model of sustainable mobility. In the presented example, it can be observed that local administration needs to pay special attention to raising the safety level of non-motorized traffic flows, then to reducing traffic congestion, as well as to improving the traffic culture of traffic participants. Following the conducted research analysis in the earlier period and the presented results, in this particular case, the parameters can serve as the basis for preparatory research, and it is necessary to realistically look at the conflict between non-motorized and motorized traffic flows and, accordingly, prepare appropriate campaign goals (target groups, etc.) and prepare messages. In addition, the established research results can be an excellent basis for preparing a quality transport model, which should serve as the basis for implementing the urban planning of the city or part of the city, that is, for preparation of traffic studies, which, after that, can be independently implemented in the urban plan or may be developed simultaneously, so that individual designs are integrated into the urban plan [30].

4. CONCLUSION

Urban systems comprise, among other things, also transport systems, that in functioning of transport processes, are characterized by problems related to compromising the quality of environment, human health, and society. The negative effects of transport processes can be reduced by using "cleaner" technologies for powering motorized traffic flows. However, the problems caused by the mentioned processes development are associated with the increasing use of transportation means, and cannot be solved in that way. Contemporary models that aim at solving problems in transport systems are based on implementation of measures and actions for the purpose of reducing the use of motorized traffic flows and motivating users to use sustainable modes of transport. In addition, sustainable urban mobility can be improved by using the following measures and activities:

- determining characteristics of traffic flows (systematic counting of motorized and non-motorized flows, as well as passengers in the public passenger transport subsystem) in the network and periodic checking of parameters in order to adopt quality (sustainable) solutions;
- continuous recording of environmental pollution parameters;
- educating local government members involved in organizing campaigns related to promoting sustainable mobility;
- organizing workshops and participation of local governments members in national and international projects related to sustainable development - sustainable urban mobility;
- introducing "permanent measures" in transport systems;
- implementing iterative process in order to constantly review the achieved results in relation to the organized campaigns from previous years;
- preparing documents at national and local levels related to enhancing sustainable mobility, such as Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, Urban Mobility Action Plans, Sustainable Urban Mobility Master Plans, etc.

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UAV AT AIRPORTS: EFFECTS ON AIR TRAFFIC CONTROLLER WORKLOAD

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Abstract: With the development of technology in recent years, the aviation industry faced many innovations such as Unmanned Area Vehicles (UAV). The UAV's expansion was followed by their application for a wide range of purposes, including the tendency of their application at the airports. However, integrating unmanned aircraft into airspace with manned aircraft brings a lot of safety concerns, including the increased workload of Air Traffic Controllers (ATCo). This paper analyzes the effect of UAV presence at airports on ATCo workload. This research problem was addressed using the Ishikawa diagram, which enables the evaluation of causal factors. The paper ends by suggesting some preventive measures that will enable UAV's safe integration at airports and effective workload management.

Key words: UAV, ATC, ATCo, Aviation Safety, Airport

1. INTRODUCTION

The technology of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles is evolving at a very fast pace with increasing potential to compete successfully with more traditional alternatives in a number of sectors. Despite the fact that they are referred to as "unmanned", some of the major challenges regarding this emerging innovation are related to human factors – such as Air Traffic Controller factor. [1]

Air Traffic Controllers are responsible for air traffic management in the airspace system and their workload and ergonomics are a wide-ranging topic due to the multiple responsibilities that encompass equipment, operations, communications, and management. The ATCo workload is expected to increase due to projected increases in air traffic, including the number of UAV currently flying in the airport airspace and the continued growth of UAV activities. [2]

As ATCo has a crucial role in air traffic safety, understanding factors that influence their increased workload is vital to prevent unsafe events. This paper aims to identify and analyze factors affecting the mentioned increased workload. Besides, successful management of increased ATCo workload needs adequate system barriers and measures adopted within regulations, technology and training. This research ends with proposing some of the measures that need to be implemented to manage identified factors.

2. UAV AT AIRPORTS

The tendency to use UAVs (commonly known as drones) at airports takes great interest, primarily because of its potential to increase the efficiency and safety of different processes. [3], [4], [5] The potential areas of UAV applications at airports include:

- Aerial photography and measurements, monitoring of the airport's surroundings;

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- Construction of infrastructure;
- Aircraft surface inspection;
- Inspection of airport movement areas;
- FOD detection and removal;
- Meteorological analyses and forecasts;
- Calibration and inspection of navigation systems;
- Bird control;
- Aircraft De-icing and Anti-icing;
- Responding in emergency situations; and
- Transport services.

As the mentioned UAV applications mean their integration in the airspace with many aircraft, this tendency presents a huge challenge from a safety perspective including the concerns referring to ATCo's increased workload. This research considers increased ATCo workload due to UAVs at airports for the mentioned applications and unauthorized operations in airport surroundings.

3. ATCo WORKLOAD

Integration of UAV at airports has a great impact on the Air Traffic Control (ATC) system, air traffic controllers' job tasks and responsibilities, as well as their workload. Air traffic controller workload refers to the physical and psychological stress experienced by controllers during their work to maintain the safe, efficient, and rational operation of guaranteed air traffic. [6]

Nowadays, ATCo is faced with many UAVs in airport surroundings (mainly for recreational purposes), but also at the airport movement areas for different, above-mentioned, processes. This situation requires ATC to maintain situational awareness across an increasingly complex airspace system, such as multiple aircraft types at different altitudes, emergency situations, and manned-unmanned interoperability. [2]

For now, the precise procedures on how to handle UAV traffic or act in situations of airspace violation by UAVs do not exist. In addition, communication with the UAV operator is usually done through telephone conversations, and it is not uncommon that the line is occupied until the completion of the flight. Besides, collision avoidance depends on avoidance maneuvers performed by manned aircraft crew as Airborne Collision Avoidance System (ACAS) solutions for UAVs do not exist yet.

The main consequences that can arise from such a working environment are related to ATC and airport traffic disruptions, but also disruptions in airline flights. Within ATC, consequences can be the engagement of an additional air traffic controller, re-sectorization, reduced capacity or closing part of the airspace, etc., while regarding the airport, consequences can include: holdings, flight diversions, flight delays, suspension of traffic at the airport (i.e. "zero-rate"), all mentioned following with economic consequences for the involved actors.

Understanding factors that can contribute to the increased ATCo workload is of great importance. The mentioned factors can be both internal (connected with ATC policies, technologies, etc.) and external (environment, other technologies, etc.) as identified below by using the appropriate method.

4. METHOD

4.1. Ishikawa Diagram

The Ishikawa diagram is a tool used to systematically identify and present all possible causes of a particular problem in a graphical format.

Possible causes are presented at different levels of detail in the related branches, and the level of detail increases as the branch goes outwards, i.e. the outer branch is the cause of the inner branch to which it is attached (Figure 1). [7] The diagram construction usually has the following steps:

- Prepare the basic framework of the diagram (backbone);
- Define the problem to be solved (fish head);
- Finalize the categories of causes of the main branches;
- Conduct a brainstorming session; and
- Analyze of the Ishikawa diagram.

Figure 1 – Ishikawa Diagram

4.2. Ishikawa Diagram for ATCo increased workload due to UAV activities at Airports

Figure 2 represents the Ishikawa diagram for the safety-related problem: „ATCo increased workload due to UAV activities at airports“. The identified causes categories are: "Equipment", "Procedures", "Machine (UAV)", "Human", and "Environment". By conducting a brainstorming session, each of the causes categories was further developed with primary and/or secondary sub-causes.

Figure 2 – Ishikawa Diagram for ATCo increased Workload due to UAV Activities at Airports

5. ANALYSIS

By using the Ishikawa diagram for the identified problem, a lot of influencing factors are identified within the five categories. In terms of handling traffic that includes UAV activities at airports, within the „Equipment“ category, it is recognized that lack of adequate equipment in ATC (like inappropriate radar screens) and on manned aircraft (like Detect and Avoid – DAA solutions that recognize UAVs) can be contributing factors to ATCo increased workload. Within the „Procedures“ category, deficiency of procedures for UAV's flight plan management, communication as well as for abnormal situations are identified as causes of an increased workload. Category „Machine (UAV)“ considered technical issues, control issues and DAA capabilities. Regarding the „Human“ category, it can be concluded that besides ATCo, causes can be related to manned aircraft crew, UAV operators, and the public. The category „Environment“ is the most complex one and includes meteorological conditions, operating conditions, other traffic, as well as abnormal and emergency situations.

In aviation, unsafe events usually come as a result of failure on different levels which emphasizes the need to analyze their interactions. In mentioned terms, for example, one visual interpretation and analysis of the diagram can be: inadequate surveillance capability (presented as "UAV not visible on ATC radar" within the "Equipment" branch) combined with heavy traffic intensity at the airport (presented as "Heavy Density Traffic" within the "Environment" branch) and lack of standard protocols for handling UAV traffic (presented as "Lack of Standardized Protocols for managing UAV Traffic by ATCo" within the "Procedures" branch) can lead to ATCo increased workload.

6. MEASURES FOR SAFE UAV INTEGRATION AT AIRPORTS AND ATCo WORKLOAD MANAGEMENT

The safe integration of UAVs into airspace with manned aircraft requires system barriers to cover identified factors that can lead to unsafe events. Some barriers i.e. measures for UAV safe integration at airports and successful management of ATCo workload are proposed in the table below (Table 1). Proposed measures cover technology, training and regulation measures.

Table 1 – Proposed measures

No.	Proposed measures
1.	"Anti-drone" systems at airports (like "DroneShield")
2.	Monitoring solutions (equipment) that enable information of UAV position displayed on radar screen both in ATC center and in the cockpit of manned aircraft
3.	UAV flight plan processing systems
4.	Airborne Collision Avoidance System (ACAS) for UAV
5.	Development of Ground Control Station (GCS) at airports for UAV operators with the appropriate link to ATC
6.	Develop and adopt phraseology for UAV operations
7.	Develop pre-defined routes for UAV operations at the airport
8.	Develop emergency and contingency procedures for UAV-related safety events
9.	Develop and adopt communication protocol for handling UAV traffic
10.	Use of identification codes (not necessarily assigning a code to each UAV if there are system limitations, but the use of a general code that would indicate that it is a UAV)
11.	Promotion of legislation for the recreational use of UAV
12.	Air traffic controller simulator training for handling UAV traffic in different scenarios
13.	Introduce UAV ATCo - "uATCo" position in ATC center (ATCo focusing on UAV traffic and flight authorization based on collaboration with other ATCo)

One measure can be highlighted - Airborne Collision Avoidance System (ACAS). It is clear that the presence of an ACAS system for UAVs will accelerate their safe integration with the potential to

prevent increased ATCo workload.

However, when defining an ACAS solution for the UAV, it must be kept in mind that regulations and procedures should reflect as closely as possible those applicable to manned aircraft so that their safety is not compromised at any time. On the other hand, it is necessary to consider all differences in the concept of UAV operations, but also their various limitations. [8]

7. CONCLUSION

The increased number of UAVs at airports and in their surroundings, in addition to the increasing number of manned aircraft flights, leads to an increased ATCo workload. The paper identified factors that affect the mentioned workload within the categories: "Equipment", "Procedures", "Machines (UAV)", "Human" and "Environment". A detailed analysis of the mentioned factors enables the establishment of appropriate system measures in order to prevent and manage the increased ATCo workload. Some of such measures are proposed in this paper. Overall, controllers must be prepared for operations with unmanned aircraft (through a training simulator) in the airport environment, but also for different scenarios in terms of working conditions (complex meteorological conditions, emergency situations, etc.) with the support of the necessary procedures (such as communication protocols) and technological solutions (such as radar displays of UAV operations, ACAS, etc.) that will assist in the work and contribute to the successful management of the ATCo workload. Finally, the detailed procedures, the required training and the integration of the mentioned technological solutions must be covered by the appropriate regulation at the international and national level to ensure uniformity in the work of all involved entities.

The future directions of the research can be related to the analysis of the different UAV-manned aviation conflict scenarios with the assessment of ATCo behavior in such situations, all with the aim to define detailed system barriers.

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ROAD TRANSPORT MARKET OVERVIEW

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Abstract: The transport sector must always be ready for significant changes that can be expected in the coming period. Changes occur, on the one hand, due to the development of technology, but also due to other factors, such as the rapid evolution in the organization of work and the nature of labor relations. It is the responsibility of all transport stakeholders to prepare for that change – to manage it, minimize its costs and maximize its benefits.

Key words: technological changes, jobs in transport, transport market

1. INTRODUCTION

Transport plays a significant role in the economic and social development of every country. It also has a great impact on economic growth and employment. Countries must contend with a mix of old and new challenges when modernizing transportation systems. It is the responsibility of all transport stakeholders to prepare for that change – to manage it, minimize its costs and maximize its benefits.

2. TRENDS IN ROAD FREIGHT TRANSPORT

Technology will be key in modernizing transportation systems, improving their efficiency and effectiveness. However, the use of data requires new governance structures related to data sharing and privacy. The transport sector must build systems that will increase resilience to cyber and environmental risks. [1]-[3]

Some of the trends that can be singled out are:

- Creating sustainable transport financing mechanisms – sustainable alternatives to fuel taxes need to be developed, examined and defined, encouraging transparency of government agencies to build public trust.
- Electric vehicles - it is necessary to build solutions to the problem of charging infrastructure and to ensure the necessary number of employees in this sector
- Modernizing transportation systems in an equitable way – an equity-focused approach needs to be adopted to invest in and design transportation systems, including underserved and marginalized communities in project planning processes.
- Increasing the resistance of the transport system to possible threats - cyber threats and climate-related threats.
- Accelerated digital and technological innovations in the transport sector - it is necessary to create better systems for the wider application of digital innovations in the transport sector.

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3. VOLUME OF TRANSPORTATION

The volume of road freight transport is constantly increasing (Figure 1). In 2022, the volume of road freight transport (in tkm) remained at the same level as in 2021. [4]

Source: Eurostat

Figure 1. Volume of road freight transport in the EU, 2018-2022, in billions of tkm

Source: Eurostat

Figure 2. Growth rate of the volume of road freight transport in the EU, based on tkm, 2020-2021, 2021-2022

The transport industry accounts for about 5% of the gross domestic product (GDP). Transport services, broadly defined, make the main and essential contribution to other economic branches, and transport is also a large customer of products and services of other economic branches. [5]

The value of the road freight transport market records constant growth, except in 2020. It is estimated that the value of the market will continue to grow in the coming years (Figure 3).

Transport also has an indirect impact on other economic branches. To carry out its activities, transport purchases products and services from other economic branches (vehicles, fuel, information systems services, professional services, etc.). The personal consumption of employees in transport and the investments of transport companies in new facilities and equipment represent a special importance for the economy. [6]

Other economic branches use transport for their own production or service provision. Without reliable and high-quality transport, other economic branches would suffer significant losses in production, creation of new values, efficiency and reputation. The provision of high-quality, reliable transport services is therefore essential to ensure continued productivity, profitability and employment in all sectors of the economy.

Source: Statista

Figure 3. Value of the road freight transport market in Europe, 2010-2025, in billions of euros

4. WORK IN TRANSPORT

The largest group of employees in road transport are drivers. Driver jobs are particularly sensitive to upcoming technological changes, given the emergence of semi-automated and automated driving and navigation systems.

The average age of transport employees is high. The level of formal training and qualifications is relatively low, although working in transport is a demanding occupation. Employees acquired knowledge and skills through on-the-job training, not through formal qualifications and higher education. [7]

Development and changes in the organization of work in transport services will be a key factor in changes in work in transport. The number of transport workers employed in the functions of auxiliary

services is constant, since transporters now hire external collaborators (suppliers, subcontractors) for many functions that they previously performed internally.

The majority of employees are engaged in traditional "standard" employment: permanent, paid, full-time work with standard rights such as vacation and sick leave. A part of the employees is part-time (occasional, irregular jobs), while a significant part is self-employed (truckers). Owner-managers of trucking companies perform the same jobs as standard/traditional salaried employees, but usually with lower compensation, but without the same protections and the same rights (which include taxes and contributions).

The transport industry is an important employer. The overall demand for transport services has increased compared to other branches of the economy. And in traditional occupations (drivers), employment growth is relatively high. The unique demographic characteristics of the transport industry - with a relatively older, predominantly male and less formally educated workforce - represent both a challenge and an opportunity for the coming changes. Transport faces problems regarding the quality and stability of work, mainly related to the spread of non-standard employment (part-time jobs, casual jobs, self-employed and outsourcing).

5. CAUSES OF CHANGES

The activity of transport continues to develop and grow and is becoming more and more important for the work and development of other economic branches. It faces enormous uncertainties and problems that will have a strong and unpredictable impact on transport services and transport businesses in the future. [1]-[2]

The first driver of change is the accelerated pace of innovation in technology: drive systems, driving and navigation systems, support systems, information and data management technology. In addition to innovation, transportation is affected by environmental challenges, fiscal issues, governance, globalization and demographic aging.

Another cause of changes in transport is the change in the nature of labor relations. New forms of work engagement and remuneration for work performed (self-employment and contracts with service providers) and vertical disintegration of supply chain relationships (with multiple jobs taking place in independent subsidiary firms instead of all jobs being performed in one firm, i.e. all jobs be integrated in the company itself).

6. CONCLUSION

Transport is facing changes that bring challenges and uncertainty. Accelerating technological changes is one of the drivers of these changes. But other factors also shape and reshape the entire sector and the lives of the people who work in it - including the trend towards non-standard or insecure forms of employment, which significantly affected the stability and quality of work. Factors influencing the production and sale of transport services are environmental, demographic and fiscal in nature.

In the midst of all this change and uncertainty, there are also sources of stability and continuity that can instill confidence in stakeholders as they prepare for the coming changes. The economic and social importance of transport is not in question. The only question is how to manage this sector, in the conditions that bring changes. Transport jobs will change significantly, but they will not disappear.

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SELECTION OF HYBRID VEHICLE USING MCDM METHOD

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Abstract: In this paper, an evaluation and ranking of four models of hybrid vehicles that are available on the Serbian market (Hyundai Kona, Suzuki Vitara, Renault Conquest and Toyota Yaris Cross) was performed. Five criteria were used (price, fuel consumption, engine power, CO₂ emissions and warranty). An analytical hierarchy process was used for evaluation and ranking. Based on the obtained results, the best ranked model is the Hyundai Kona. The paper also carried out a sensitivity analysis in order to determine how the change in the weighting factors affects the change in the ranking of the alternatives. It was determined that only changes greater than twenty percent lead to changes in the ranking of alternatives, which leads to the conclusion that the obtained results are relevant.

Key words: AHP, hybrid vehicle, selection, alternative, criteria

1. INTRODUCTION

Concerns over the environmental degradation and the depletion of fossil fuel resources have driven a paradigm shift in the automotive industry towards sustainable solutions. Hybrid vehicles (HV) can be a good transitional solution until the introduction of fully electric vehicles. With the development of technology, the price of hybrid vehicles can be expected to fall further. Also, saving fuel/costs is another reason for the increasing penetration of hybrid vehicles on the market in the coming period.

There are a numerous hybrid vehicles on the Serbian market today. HV have different technical specifications. For proper selection of HV it is necessary to consider numerous criteria, otherwise the selection can be poor. The application of the multicriteria decision making (MCDM) methods for assessment and selection of HV where all relevant criteria can be considered, can lead to relevant decision. There are numerous MCDM methods applied in theory and practice such as: analytical hierarchical process (AHP), analytical network process (ANP), preference ranking organization method for enrichment of evaluations (PROMETHEE), technique for order of preference by similarity to ideal solution (TOPSIS), etc. AHP is one of the most used method for solving decision making issues in: energetics [1], environment [2], tourism [3]. Also, AHP is used to select electric/hybrid vehicle independently and/or in combination with other methods [4]-[5]. In this paper AHP method is used to assess and rank selected HV available in Serbian market.

2. APPLIED METHODOLOGY

Methodology for HV selection in this paper is conducted through four steps:

Step 1. Define decision making goal – at the beginning, it is necessary to define the goal of the decision making (for example, selection of the cheapest, highest quality, etc) which depends on the needs of the decision maker.

Step 2. Define list of HV to be assessed and list of decision making criteria – in the second step, it is necessary to define a list of HV that will be the subject of assessment and decision making. Also, in order for the decision to be made, it is necessary to define a list of criteria based on which the HV will be evaluated.

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Step 3. Assessment using AHP – after defining the list of HV and criteria, the AHP method can be applied for evaluation and ranking. The AHP was developed by Thomas Saaty (1980) [6]. The AHP methodology can be explained step by step approach as following:

1. In the first step, the problem is formulated in a hierarchical manner. In this step, the aim, main criteria, sub criteria and alternatives should be identified clearly.
2. Paired comparisons are performed and the relative importance are determined.
3. The consistency of pair wise comparison matrices is determined. If the consistency ratio (CR) is equal or smaller than 0.1 value, the comparisons are consistent.
4. In the final step, priorities of alternatives are found by combining the weights of criteria and the ratings of the alternatives.

To perform a pair wise comparison by all relevant criteria/alternatives, an $n \times n$ matrix A is formed, where a_{ij} values are obtained using a 9-point scale (Table 1).

Table 1. Saaty's 1-9 scale of pairwise comparisons

Intensity of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal Importance	Two activities contribute equally to the objective
3	Moderate Importance	Experience and judgment slightly favor one activity over another
5	Strong Importance	Experience and judgment strongly favor one activity over another
7	Very Strong	An activity is favored very strongly over another
9	Extreme Importance	The evidence favoring one activity over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation
2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate results	They are used to present a compromise between the priorities listed above

In this paper, the AHP methodology will not be explained in detail. For a detailed introduction to the AHP methodology, readers are referred to [6]-[8].

Step 4. Sensitivity analysis - The sensitivity analysis is to be performed after obtaining the decision making results to confirm how changes in the weight factors influence the ranking of alternatives.

3. CASE STUDY

As already mentioned in chapter 2, a four-step model is proposed for the selection of HV in this paper.

Step 1. Define decision making goal – in this paper goal is to select optimal hybrid vehicle in Serbian market.

Step 2. Define list of hybrid vehicles to be assessed and list of decision making criteria – there are numerous hybrid vehicles available in Serbian market today. In this paper we selected vehicles

presented in table 2. When is about decision making criteria for hybrid vehicle selection, different criteria are used in literature. In this paper we selected criteria presented in table 2.

Table 2. Decision making alternative and criteria

Criteria Vehicle	Price (€) (C1)	Fuel consumption l/100km (combined) (C2)	Engine power (kw/ks) (C3)	Emission of CO ₂ (g/km) (C4)	Guarantee (years) (C5)
Hyundai kona hybrid (A1)	29,990	3,9	77,2/105	90	5
Suzuki vitara hybrid (A2)	21,550	4,6	95/129	119	3
Renault megane conquest hybrid (A3)	29,190	5,8-6,1	103/140	130	6
Toyota yaris cross hybrid (A4)	24,990	4,4	85/116	101	3

Step 3. Assessment using AHP – after defining the list of HV and criteria, the AHP method can be applied for evaluation and ranking. In the first step, it is necessary to compare the criteria in relation to the goal. In this work, all criteria have equal importance (Table 3). The equal importance of the criteria was applied in order to make the ranking results as precise as possible and so that no alternative would have an advantage. A more detailed impact of the value of the criteria in relation to the goal will be presented in the sensitivity analysis. Then, a comparison of the alternatives in relation to the criteria was carried out and presented in Table 4.

Table 3. Comparison of criteria in relation to the goal

	C1	C2	C3	C4
C1	1	1	1	1
C2		1	1	1
C3			1	1
C4				1
Inconsistency=0				

Table 4. Comparison of alternatives in relation to criteria

Comparison of alternatives in relation to price (C1) criteria					Comparison of the alternative in relation to the fuel consumption (C2) criterion				
	A1	A2	A3	A4		A1	A2	A3	A4
A1	1	1/4	1	1/3	A1	1	4	5	2
A2		1	4	3	A2		1	3	1/2
A3			1	1/2	A3			1	3
A4				1	A4				1
Comparison of the alternative in relation to the engine power (C3) criterion					Comparison of the alternative in relation to the CO ₂ emissions (C4) criterion				
	A1	A2	A3	A4		A1	A2	A3	A4
A1	1	1/4	1/5	1/3	A1	1	3	4	3
A2		1	1/3	2	A2		1	3	1/3
A3			1	4	A3			1	1/4
A4				1	A4				1
Comparison of the alternative in relation to the guarantee (C5) criterion					Inconsistency				
	A1	A2	A3	A4					
A1	1	3	1/2	3	Inconsistency C1 = 0.02				
A2		1	1/4	1	Inconsistency C2 = 0.03				
A3			1	4	Inconsistency C3 = 0.04				
A4				1	Inconsistency C4 = 0.09				
					Inconsistency C5 = 0.01				

After evaluation of all criteria and alternatives, the obtained results were synthesized and a final ranking list was obtained, which is presented in Figure 1. Inconsistency is <0.10, then the decision making result is acceptable. Based on the obtained results, the best ranked alternative is A1 (Hyundai kona - 0.3), while the worst ranking belonged to alternative A4 (Toyota yaris cross - 0.208).

Figure 1. Final rank (inconsistency=0.02)

Step 4. Sensitivity analysis - The sensitivity analysis is performed after obtaining the decision making results to analyse how changes in the weight factors influence the ranking of alternatives. In this paper, the minimum changes in weight factors that influence the change in the ranking of alternatives are analyzed (Table 5). All changes in weight factors that lead to changes in the ranking of alternatives are greater than 20%, so it can be concluded that the obtained results are relevant.

Table 5. Sensitivity analysis

Criteria	Value used in decision making	Minimal change (+ or -)	New rank
C1	0.200	0.246	A1 (0.289) - A2 (0.251) -A3 (0.250) -A4 (0.210)
C2	0.200	0.110	A3 (0.278) - A1 (0.277) - A2 (0.242) - A4 (0.203)
C3	0.200	0.268	A3 (0.282) - A1 (0.280) - A2 (0.235) - A4 (0.023)
C4	0.200	0.145	A1 (0.300) - A2 (0.243) - A3 (0.242) - A4 (0.215)

4. CONCLUSION

Hybrid vehicles are gaining more and more significant market share and also contribute to the reduction of harmful emissions. In this paper, an evaluation and ranking of four models of hybrid vehicles that are available on the Serbian market was performed. According to the obtained results, the best-ranked alternative is the A1 (Hyundai Kona). Also, a sensitivity analysis was conducted in order to determine how changes in the values of the weighting factors affect changes in the ranking of alternatives. It was determined that only changes greater than 20% affect changes in the ranking of alternatives, so it can be concluded that the obtained results are relevant.

Five criteria were used to evaluate hybrid vehicles (price, fuel consumption, engine power, CO₂ emissions and guarantee). In future papers, a larger number of criteria should be included. Also, subjectivity in decision-making can lead to insufficiently precise results, so it is recommended that in future papers, decision-making is carried out in a fuzzy environment. Also, group decision-making in which different decision-makers (experts, owners of considered models, etc.) would be involved can help in obtaining more precise decision-making results.

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BUILDING'S STRUCTURAL PERFORMANCE AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY CORRELATION WITH REGARD TO CHOICE OF CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS

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Abstract: Nowadays energy efficiency, with the main purpose of saving energy and decreasing carbon emission, is a highly emphasized topic. For a very long period of time budget, modeling the massive buildings systems, load bearing capacity of construction elements, and choice of construction materials has been in focus. Buildings, especially residential ones are huge polluters and energy consumptions, we use a lot of different mechanisms to reduce it by choosing various of building materials. Implementation of different mechanisms for reducing electricity is a big step for decreasing greenhouse gas emission, or carbon dioxide emission. There is a need for reconstruction old, historical buildings, and new ones, using new inventive construction materials and new way of building design. The proper selection of construction systems and material applications to achieve optimal load bearing capacity and energy efficiency of the object itself.

Key words: building structures, massive buildings systems, load bearing capacity, buildings energy efficiency, construction elements

1. INTRODUCTION

The irrational energy production and energy consumption have not been sustainable, and thus, it is extremely harmful and it have bad impact on the environment. The ever-growing awareness of the negative consequences has led to the study and development to reduce energy consumption. Republic of Serbia in 2011 enter into force the Energy Efficiency Regulations For energy saving and put into practice sustainable forms of energy consumption.

As the population increases, the greater need for energy supply is evident. The development of sustainable forms of energy consumption should be prioritized, and we need to highlight the ecological consequences of the current methods of energy supply and consumption. All three steps of the circle - production, distribution, and energy consumption - affect the variety of human activities. They also have a huge impact on social and economic progress, so we need to take into consideration all social aspects in the process of deciding upon the most satisfactory approach to meet the need for energy production. The economic, social, and environmental aspects are almost equally important.

The adequate choice of construction materials plays a significant role in construction modeling and the budget calculation of building structures. The particular elements for building construction should be appropriately defined in order to be in line with the efficacy and capacity requirements. Apart from reaching the corresponding load bearing capacity, the corresponding energy efficiency of the construction element itself and the entire object should be also measured and predicted[1]. Therefore, even if the building code requirements of the period of construction are met (discrepancies are often observed), there is an effort needed to reduce the earthquake vulnerability of the building when

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compared to current building codes[2],[3]. Such awareness is increased for buildings in existing urban areas by experiencing the consequences of recent earthquakes. These calculations/predictions should also comply with the legal framework for the construction facilities pro-calculation in the Republic of Serbia. This is the reason why, in 2019, the acceptance of European technical norms from zero to nine was applied.

The upgrading of existing buildings provides a potential with regard to the planning of land use in urban areas, but it also highlights the differences in building's time period of construction and the current code demands. The long-term upgrading (or reconstruction) is not carefully regulated as it is for the new buildings. The presented case study is referring to planned activity of residential masonry building upgrading by considering the current earthquake resistant design criteria that differ from those of the time period of the construction of the building. The complete details of the study can be found in [4], [5].

As a next step, the selection of the appropriate construction elements along with the construction system of the housing facility were carried out based on the conducted comparative analysis. The main goals that construction engineers should take into consideration and prioritize (based on the requirements) are planning and rational energy consumption, analysis of the building energy efficiency, and implementation of various approaches. These approaches should define the energy efficiency of the objects. Additionally, the construction engineers should analyze the carrying capacity of the construction elements throughout a housing object depending on the applied construction element, and define the energy grade.

2. ENERGY-EFFICIENT HOMES AND BUILDINGS, AND ENERGY PERFORMANCE CERTIFICATION (EPC) OF BUILDINGS

Different regulations that evolved over the years have influenced the creation of new architectural approaches, materials, and different energy consumption mechanisms. The new approaches had to be defined and applied in order to reconstruct the existing buildings and introduce new design methods and materials. The existing building objects (mainly housing facilities) present the largest objects of energy consumption, which indicates that they are also large environmental pollutants. With the continual implementation of the above-mentioned, carbon emissions will be decreased, and rational energy consumption prioritized.

The overall construction budget is mainly invested in buildings, or more precise 40% in buildings, 32% in traffic, and only 28% in industry [6]. Out of this 40%, only 2% of construction projects are related to the construction of new buildings. In other words, more than two-thirds of the construction budget is invested in the existing buildings. In order to change the wide, general picture and address properly the global decrease in energy consumption, the focus should be directed to the reconstruction and energy repair of the existing buildings with the simultaneous development of new and improved features.

In seventies of the twentieth century, the construction industry increasingly advanced. The initial regulations that were applied were a change in regulations and regulations on the thermal protection of buildings. The highest values of construction parts heat coefficients in the object structure were defined back then. In eighties of the twentieth century, the value of the permissible heat-flow coefficients decreased by 30%. In 2012, we may record the implementation of the Rulebook on Conditions, Contents, and Methods of Issuing a Certificate on Energy Properties and the Rulebook on Energy Efficiency of Buildings. Here, we may find the specific definitions of the maximum heat coefficient value for each constructive part of the building (i.e., walls, floors, roofs, etc.).

Finally, The Energy Efficiency Regulation of Buildings [7] defined more precisely the required energy characteristics. In terms of the methodology, the budget calculation of building thermal characteristics in combination with the new requirements was more precisely defined. The Rulebook on the Terms, Contents, and Method of Issuing a Certificate on the Energy Properties of Buildings regulates

the process of building energy certification. This method provides the content of the certificate and defines the energy grades for residential and non-communal buildings, new and existing.

3. LOAD-BEARING CAPACITY OF WALLS

According to production control, masonry elements are divided into two categories. Category I wall elements are those for which the manufacturer has provided constant quality control and which, within delivery, have a defined compressive strength that does not deviate from the mean value of more than 5% (5% fractile). Category II elements are those whose average value of compressive strength is equal to the declared value, so the elements of natural stone are classified in category II. To determine the load-bearing capacity of walls, it is necessary to know the mechanical properties of masonry elements and binder material [8].

The most reliable data on the characteristic compressive strength of the wall are certainly obtained directly, experimentally, when it is necessary to use materials that are applied to a specific wall in practice. In the absence of concrete experimental results of wall compressive strength, the current legislation in the field of wall constructions, Eurocode 6, allows the characteristic wall compressive strength to be defined on the basis of the expression [9], [2]:

$$f_k = K \cdot f_b^\alpha \cdot f_m^\beta \quad (1)$$

where:

f_k – characteristic value of compressive strength of the masonry structure [N/mm²],

K – constant that depends on the characteristic of the elements used for masonry,

f_b – normalized mean value of compressive strength of masonry elements in the direction of the applied load [N/mm²],

f_m – mortar compressive strength [N/mm²],

α, β – constants.

Relationship between characteristic value of the compressive strength of the masonry structure f_k , the normalized mean value of the compressive strength of masonry elements f_b and mortar strength, can be determined depending on the type of mortar used.

In order to adequately calculate the load-bearing capacity of elements of the masonry structure exposed to vertical load, in accordance with Eurocode 6, it is necessary to first define the effective and to determine the effective wall thickness.

Calculated load-bearing capacity of the non-reinforced wall (N_{Rd}), per unit length of single-layer wall, on the effect of vertical load, is defined on the basis of the expression

$$N_{Rd} = \frac{\Phi_{i,m} \cdot t \cdot f_k}{\gamma_M} = \Phi_{i,m} \cdot t \cdot f_d \quad (2)$$

where:

$\Phi_{i,m}$ – load reduction coefficient (Φ_i and/or Φ_m) which takes into account the effect of slenderness and load eccentricity,

γ_M – partial safety factor for the material.

Based on Eurocode 6, for the ultimate limit state, partial safety coefficients are defined, depending on the material properties. The value of the partial safety factor depends on the masonry category, A, B and C. Thus, category A includes facilities that are under constant supervision and quality control during construction, carried out by the supervisory authority, category B includes periodic supervision and control, and category C includes facilities that are built without a supervisory body and the only control is carried out by the construction contractor.

When structure is under action of horizontal load it is necessary to calculate design value of the shear resistance. The calculated value is less or equal of wall's shear capacity:

$$V_{Rd} = t \cdot f_{vd} \cdot l_c \quad (3)$$

where:

t – wall thickness resisting the shear,

f_{vd} – design value of the shear strength of masonry, based on the average of the vertical stresses over the compressed part of the wall that is providing the shear resistance,

l_c – is the length of the compressed part of the wall, ignoring any part of the wall that is in tension

4. EXAMPLARY BUILDING

For the residential two-story unreinforced clay block masonry building is conducted static and dynamic analysis and energy efficiency calculus. A case study building is II category, situated in city of Niš. Building is located on soil category B, and the class of the building is II, in compliance with [3]. The clay exterior block masonry walls are 25 cm thick, interior brick walls are 20 cm thick, and the partition solid brick walls are 12 cm thick. The floor slabs were made of reinforced concrete of 20 cm thickness, made by concrete class C25/30.

Figure 1 -Building plan (measures in cm)

The following different cases i.e. building upgrade (reconstruction) possibilities with masonry blocks “Porotherm Profi” or with seismic blocks “Porotherm S” blocks sealed with mortar. Building was considered existing building without tie columns, and upgraded with tie columns, with vertical confining elements reinforcement 4Ø12 and stirrups Ø6/15, concrete C25/30.

Figure 2 -Model view in AmQuake software

The following different cases i.e. building upgrade (reconstruction) possibilities were considered:

- Model 1a: existing building without tie columns, with masonry “Porotherm Profi” blocks sealed with mortar,

- Model 1b: existing building without tie columns, with seismic blocks “Porotherm S” blocks sealed with mortar M5,
- Model 2a: existing building with tie columns, with masonry “Porotherm Profi” blocks sealed with mortar,
- Model 2b: existing building with tie columns, with seismic blocks “Porotherm S” blocks sealed with mortar M5,

Structural model of the above stated cases, for the purpose of earthquake performance evolution, were built in AmQuake computer program [10], energy performance of buildings by energy efficiency URSA software[11].

4.1. Static and dynamic building analysis

The above stated cases were analyzed under seismic and static actions. For seismic action representation, selected was the response spectrum of Type 1 (earthquake magnitude greater than $M > 5.5$), for seismic hazard with a return period of 475 years. Building is located in medium seismicity zone IMCS=VII with corresponding peak ground acceleration (PGA) of 0.1g i.e. 1 m/s^2 , with attenuation of 5%. The analysis was performed by means of nonlinear static i.e. pushover analysis. The structural and non-structural components of the building were considered in the model, however, partition walls were included only through their mass distributed on the surrounding structural elements.

By changing construction model, and changing masonry blocks there is a change of model mass, and automatically there is a change of oscillation period of building and seismic forces acting on building. Vertical forces acting on ground floor load bearing wall is also decreasing as well. Building with tie columns and with different masonry blocks also decreases mass, and vertical force in load bearing wall on ground floor is increasing.

Figure 3 - Mass change in the building model and vertical forces in load bearing wall

4.2. Building model energy efficiency analysis

Using URSA software is estimated energy efficiency of models. For construction models was performed one year analysis for heating energy in case when for thermal insulation in walls is used 12 cm hard pressed mineral wool and mounted Reahau Euro 70 windows. By conducted calculus all models are B energy class.

Figure 4–Energy building model consumption and energy need correlation by defining building model

5. CONCLUSION

All building masonry models are satisfying bearing by Eurocode 6 according to static and dynamic analysis. As all models are satisfying load bearing capacity, we can conclude the choice of structural system is not relevant as choice of building energy efficiency. The amount of heating energy is most adequate in Model 1a. Based on the conducted static and dynamic analysis as well as the conducted of the energy efficiency calculations of models, Model 1a is satisfactory in terms of bearing capacity and energy efficiency. The masonry building model, made of "Porotherm Profi" blocks sealed with mortar, meets both load-bearing and energy efficiency requirements.

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IMPLEMENTATION OF AI IN TEACHING: ANALYSIS OF THE CREATION OF 3D RENDERINGS WITH AI ON THE EXAMPLE OF INFLUENTIAL ARCHITECTS

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Abstract: In architectural design, as well as in industrial, interior, and urban design, the use of artificial intelligence programs and platforms – text-to-image generators, like Midjourney, DALL-E, Stable Diffusion, and similar, is drastically transforming creative and research processes of creating form, concept, and atmosphere of design projects. When it comes to teaching architectural/interior design, one of the numerous questions is: How can AI platforms positively influence the process of thinking, creating a concept, and making 3D models of architectural objects? The paper focuses on analyses of the use of AI platforms by several influential architects and architectural studios, aiming to anticipate guidelines for new AI implementation models in teaching architectural design.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, AI, Architectural Design, Interior Design, 3D Modelling, 3D Renders, Teaching Methods

1. INTRODUCTION

The contemporary architectural design process largely involves using artificial intelligence and working with AI platforms – text-to-image generators, mostly Midjourney, DALL-E, and Stable Diffusion. Despite many concerns about AI intervention in architects' jobs and their role in the design process, AI has many advantages in architectural design practice. Research has shown that AI has the potential to liberate architects' and designers' creativity [1]. Architectural practical skills (technical approach) and knowledge of using AI (more poetic approach) can offer new creative opportunities. At this moment, this is particularly significant in developing architectural ideas and concepts. AI can be used in the research and design thought process. It may lead architects to consider translating pragmatic and rational architecture into a more poetic one [2].

The paper analyses the selected experimental projects of famous and influential architectural studios. These projects differ in scale and theme – urban design (large permanent architectural structures or temporary public space installations), architectural design (eco-friendly, interpolating new structures in old buildings, etc.). Projects' aims, with important references to social aspects, can lead to new guidelines and methods for implementing AI platforms in teaching architectural and interior design.

2. INFLUENTIAL ARCHITECTS AND THEIR USE OF AI

2.1. Zaha Hadid Architects: Three-dimensional implied coherency of AI images

Studio principal of one of the most influential architectural studios in Europe, famous for embracing new technologies – Zaha Hadid Architects, Patrik Schumacher, revealed how the studio is using AI text-to-image generators like DALL-E 2, Midjourney, and Stable Diffusion in the process of developing design ideas for their new projects, as well as presenting them in this initial phase to clients. They use these AI platforms because of their potential to give “interesting ideas and new kinds of form and moves”, emphasizing the power and quality of “light, shadow, geometry, coherency, the sense of gravity and order” in these generated images of the project, and their “three-dimensional implied coherency” [3]. Figure 1 is a presentation of Zaha Hadid Museum DDP (Dongdaemun Design Plaza) showing prompts typed into DALL-E 2. Schumacher compared a presentation of projects to clients using AI text-

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to-image tools and conventional design meetings to come up with ideas, giving credit to the first one. When it comes to the 3D modeling phase of the project, Schumacher stated that the studio selects around "10 to 15 percent" of the output from the AI text-to-image generators. Also, Zaha Hadid Architects studio has set up an internal AI research group, firmly giving the importance of integrating AI into architectural design practice.

Figure 1 – A presentation of Zaha Hadid museum DDP showing prompts typed into DALL-E 2

2.2. Micheal Mareena: Futuristic Nostalgia as an AI architectural narrative of the dualities

Young architect Micheal Mareena uses Midjourney to explore and present dualities between new (and wealthy) and traditional (and poor) urban life in India. Creating futuristic architectural structures with AI platforms and juxtaposing them to everyday life in the streets of India, Mareena opens up cultural and historical dimensions through AI aesthetics and research and explores contrasts and complexities of social aspects in architectural and urban future development. Utopia vs. dystopia thematic in these AI renderings is emphasized with vintage filters, and they illustrate “futuristic buildings towering over slums, iconic structures coexisting with flooded roads, and architectural bridges spanning over cluttered, dirt-laden slum areas”, as presented in Figure 2 [4].

Figure 2 – Juxtaposition of progress and disparity in India generated with Midjourney

2.3. Yongwook Seong: Fusion of arctic land, living forms and mythical figures

Canadian architect and designer Yongwook Seong made an original approach to using AI in researching and creating different architectural structures. The central concept of these renderings of surreal architectural structures, generated with Midjourney, is to celebrate the roots of Inuit traditions, history, and culture. These architectural structures vary from habitable structures to public cultural spaces and pavilions. The main design motifs are land, life, and mythology. In Figure 3, the AI render depicts the Aiviq House, as a walrus that has transformed into a habitable cabin [5].

Figure 3 – Aiviq House: Aiviq walrus turns itself into a house

2.4. Hassan Ragab: ‘Novelty’ vs. ‘beauty’

Through visual experimental exploration under ‘The Cities we Build,’ digital artist and computation designer Hassan Ragab uses the AI program Stable Diffusion 2 to create renderings of monumental, vibrant, digitalized architectural forms intertwined with the traditional ones in one hybrid form. With this, he is creating a new vision of urban landscapes, as presented in Figure 4. At first glance, these surreal, dynamic, futuristic structures enliven the streets, but at second glance, the questions of favoring monumental form over function and the connection between notions of novelty, beauty, and functionality of architecture of the digital age arise [6].

Figure 4 – Interpolation of old (late 19th-century blocks) and new (surreal, colossal structures) architectural structures generated with Stable Diffusion 2

2.5. Vincent Callebaut Architectures: Urban vision of Paris – Eco ‘Haussmannian’ buildings

Biomimetic positive-energy structures called ‘Archibiotics’ and a collection of green ‘Haussmannian’ buildings in Paris were created by Vincent Callebaut Architectures, using AI platforms for text-to-image generators [7]. This project, called Haussmann 2.0 – a Resilient, Green & Breathable Paris, represents a futuristic, green, eco, urban transformation of Paris as a part of the ‘Paris Smart City 2050’ ecological transition plan. Important aspects of this project are the contemporary dialog that preserves the historical heritage of Paris and simultaneously creates islands of urban freshness by reviving nature, as illustrated in Figure 5. These ‘Archibiotics’ units are built from biobased materials (such as rammed earth, bamboo, microalgae, mycelium, etc.). They are designed to produce their energy and convert their waste into renewable resources to achieve the national goal of carbon neutrality in 2050.

Figure 5 – Interior of the 'Hausmannian' building as a futuristic, bio-inspired architecture

2.6. Ulises Design Studio: Floating Fantasies – castles crafted from recycled plastic

The experimental project Floating Fantasies presents poetic renderings generated with the AI platform Midjourney, through which design studio Ulises created their vision of new urban environments. These multi-layered installations in the form of castles, made from recycled plastic, float along the river Seine, and are eco-friendly, with a socially conscious approach to urban design [8]. The main goal of this project is to reimagine different public spaces as urban environments that are more inclusive and engaging for all citizens, as in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Floating Fantasies, castles crafted from recycled plastic

3. TOWARDS A NEW MODEL OF IMPLEMENTING AI IN TEACHING: METHODOLOGY OF USE OF AI IN ARCHITECTURAL PROJECTS

The main advantage of using AI in architectural design practice is that stunning project renderings of atmospheres are created easily and quickly. So, the design process with AI is vice-versa to the standard design process in architecture. For example, in the 3D modeling process, architects create the geometry and then produce the atmosphere, while with AI platforms, they first produce the atmosphere of the project and then think about how to translate it into 3D geometry through plans and sections drawings into the 3D form [9]. Also, working with AI text-to-image generator platforms requires knowledge of history and culture because it searches for a phrase that should be reconstructed, reworked, paraphrased, and the more references (historical and cultural) are connected to the desired context, the better images are generated.

Elaborated examples of architectural studios' use of AI platforms are summarised in Table 1 below. The emphasis is on projects' aim/s, which depend primarily on their spatiotemporal contexts. Methodology of use of AI platforms in similar contemporary and futuristic architectural experimental projects could be formulated starting from the project's main aim and, further on, formulating the criteria for satisfying render visualizations. This methodology could be translated from architectural design practice to teaching methods for using AI platforms.

Table 1 – Examples of architectural studios’ use of AI platforms summarised

Architect / architectural studio	AI platform/s	Project name	Architectural structure (form) / architectural elements	Spatio-temporal context	Project aim
Zaha Hadid Architects	DALL-E 2, Midjourney and Stable Diffusion	Zaha Hadid museum DDP [Dongdaemun Design Plaza] AI variations	complex buildings / light, shadow, geometry, coherency	Contemporary cities	- AI as a method of coming up with ideas
Micheal Mareena	Midjourney	<i>Futuristic Nostalgia: Architectural Echoes in India’s Changing Tapestry</i>	futuristic buildings / towering over slums	Future Indian cities	- to explore contrasts and complexities of social aspects in architectural and urban future development
Yongwook Seong	Midjourney	<i>Nuna</i>	habitable structures to public cultural spaces, and pavilions / contemporary vaults with organic rounded contours	Arctic and Sub-Arctic in the future	- to celebrate the roots of Inuit history, culture, and traditions
Hassan Ragab	Stable Diffusion 2	<i>The Cities we Build</i>	dynamic, futuristic, monumental structures intertwined with the traditional ones / hybrid form	Potential future of the late 19th-century blocks	- to explore functionality of architecture of the digital age - to explore notions of ‘novelty’ vs. ‘beauty’
Vincent Callebaut Architectures	DALL-E 2, Midjourney and Stable Diffusion	<i>Hausmann 2.0 – a Resilient, Green & Breathable Paris</i>	green, organic structures, contemporary eco-forms + historical ‘Hausmannian’ buildings	Paris in 2050	- contemporary dialog with the historical heritage of Paris - to create islands of urban freshness by reviving nature
Ulises Design Studio	Midjourney	<i>Floating Fantasies</i>	large, multi-layered installations crafted from recycled plastic	Contemporary River Seine	- to reimagine more inclusive and engaging public spaces

4. CONCLUSION

Analyses of different types of architectural and urban design experimental projects have shown the connections between AI platforms used, the aesthetic of renderings’ visualization and projects’ aims. This could be further developed by categorizing project typologies and paralleling their AI renderings, depending on their aims. Thus, some patterns of use of AI platforms in architectural design may be defined. Also, AI in teaching architectural design may have a method that could be divided into two main segments:

- Gaining knowledge of historical and cultural architectural references, which would be the frame for shaping textual prompts in AI programs and platforms for generating images,
- Thinking of the best way to use AI in the process of shaping the concept, idea, and atmosphere of the project while simultaneously making technical drawings and 3D models.

To conclude, significant guidelines for the implementation of AI in teaching architectural design are:

- To encourage curiosity in using AI;
- To teach students and young architects to bring a critical assessment of what AI created and to make a final decision;
- To search for a reason for choosing an idea or a concept and
- To set critical issues related to the offered solutions or iteration.

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CBTA – NOVEL APPROACH IN TRAINING OF AVIATION PROFESSIONALS

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Abstract: Aviation presents a constantly evolving industry. Innovations make industry more complex and the need emerges to provide adequate training which produces persons with the skills, but also flexibility and adaptability to cope with different changes and challenges. A good approach to answering the mentioned need presents the Competency-based Training and Assessment (CBTA) concept. This paper aims to provide a CBTA concept overview, as well as its analysis. The concept analysis was performed by using a SWOT analysis which enables the identification of both advantages and challenges that come with this novel approach in the training of future aviation professionals.

Key words: CBTA, competencies, aviation, training, flight operations

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent times, rapid technological advancements in the aviation sector have led to the adoption of novel training methods and tools. [1] The Competency-based Training and Assessment (CBTA) concept presents a novel approach that changes traditional training and assessment approaches by focusing on needed competencies for different roles. Namely, innovations usually create new interactions and complex working environments while emphasizing the need for a training method with a system of competence measurement that looks at the total performance, rather than performing single job tasks.

Within the aviation industry, it can be expected that CBTA will be firstly integrated into the training of personnel involved in flight operations i.e. complex working environment for which adequate competencies are crucial and for which only knowledge cannot be enough.

The main advantages of this novel approach refer to providing highly qualified trainees to specific roles which further for companies means facilitated entry of new employees into the real operations, as well as safety improvement. However, there are also challenges and some of them are identified in the paper within SWOT analysis as “Weaknesses” and “Threats”.

2. CBTA CONCEPT

Competency-based training and assessment (CBTA) concept presents a program that focuses on the abilities required to do the job, rather than focusing on the completion of specific tasks or the acquisition of specific knowledge. Such an approach allows individuals to handle unexpected or infrequent events using the same abilities. These abilities are referred to as competencies. Competencies define „what can be done versus what is known“, emphasizing the individual to adapt and utilize their abilities in any scenario. Moreover, competencies allow people to formulate solutions for complex and difficult situations, including first-time experiences. [2]

Within aviation, an International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) provides CBTA regulation and guidance for involved entities (primarily training organizations), including a competency framework that presents a selected group of competencies for a given aviation discipline. [3]

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Figure 1 presents an overview of CBTA workflows given by the ICAO. Workflows 1 and 2 establish the training specification, adapted competency model, assessment plan and training plan. Workflows 3 and 4 develop and conduct the training course. Workflow 5 reviews the effectiveness of the training and assessment conducted and recommends improvements, as appropriate. [2]

Figure 1 Competency-based training and assessment workflows [2]

2.1. Target audience for CBTA

For now, it is recognized that the CBTA concept is of the highest importance for aviation professionals working in an operational environment: operations control staff (flight operation officers, flight dispatchers, etc.) as well as pilots [4,5].

Namely, all personnel involved in the system of operational control must be competent and with role-specific qualifications. Besides, due to the dynamic environment, the processes, procedures and tools needed for operational control change frequently and the individuals involved must understand the relevant factors of influence on the general and specific operational risks, and should demonstrate greater flexibility in the application of their competencies in this context. [2]

The usual practices imply that employees entering the company with general industry knowledge and only after spending several months on-the-job training can face different possible scenarios for specific job roles. The tendency of introducing the CBTA concept for aviation professionals in operational control has a great potential to facilitate the entry of new employees into the company, as well as to improve quality and safety.

The mentioned tendency of introducing the CBTA concept in the training of operational staff was already supported by relevant aviation regulation authorities with several manuals and guidance for the successful design and application of the CBTA programs.

2.2. Responsibilities in CBTA

The CBTA concept implies the involvement of at least the following stakeholders (Figure 2): the local regulatory authority, the company from the industry and the approved training organization, as well as their collaboration. [2]

Within the CBTA approach, the training concept should be based on the training targets defined by the company from the industry (for training in flight operations – by the AOC (Air Operator's Certificate) holder) under supervision by the National Civil Aviation Authority (NCAA). It is recognized that the processes for the transfer of tasks, competency indicators, data and information (including Learning objectives – LO, and Observable behaviour – OB) from the AOC holder to the Approved Training Organization (ATO) are crucial for the quality of CBTA. [2]

Figure 2 Responsibilities in CBTA

3. CBTA CONCEPT – SWOT ANALYSIS

A SWOT analysis, which refers to “Strengths”, “Weaknesses”, “Opportunities” and “Threats”, is a tool and method used for strategic planning and management in organizations, as well as for evaluation of any process, project, industry, etc. [6] Table 1 presents a SWOT analysis for a novel approach in education and training of future aviation professionals – CBTA concept.

Table 1 – SWOT analysis for CBTA

S - Strengths	W - Weaknesses
Produces personnel with the flexibility and adaptability to cope with day-to-day challenges; Enables individuals to cope with predictable and unforeseen situations; Training is relevant to the job and the context in which the job will be performed; Is geared towards learning rather than passing a test; Makes full use of available training tools and methodologies; Supports continuous learning and performance improvement.	Require experienced and qualified course developers; Qualifying CAA inspectors for approving ATO’s CBTA training programs; The inspector job is more complex than traditional training (no "tick box" approach); Each ATO-adapted competency model is different there is no one-size-fits-all – and performance criteria are different for each training program.
O - Opportunities	T - Threats
Safety enhancement; Increased training effectiveness and efficiency; Facilitates the entry of new employees into the company; Adapted to the individual candidate and instructor's needs.	Transfer of tasks, competency indicator, data and information from the industry to the ATO (lack of data reflecting operational relevance); Heterogeneity in requirements and competencies due to large heterogeneities in business models of AOC holders in one country; Alignment of Safety Data and Training Data taxonomies; Training data quality; Training data protection; License recognition; Challenges for the States to integrate CBTA within their regulatory framework.

4. CONCLUSION

Nowadays, aviation needs a competency-based training program that is in alignment with the industry's needs while assuring that trainees demonstrate proficiency in competencies that are valued by aviation entities. CBTA concept presents a novel approach in the education of aviation professionals with high potential to produce personnel with the flexibility and adaptability to cope with both day-to-day challenges and thus facilitates the entry of new employees into the company. Moreover, as a CBTA concept is sustained by specific operational data used in training, it has the potential to bring additional value for global safety enhancement in the industry. However, the CBTA concept has several challenges and threats that need to be addressed including coordination between involved stakeholders, lack of data reflecting operational relevance, training data quality, training data protection, experienced and qualified course developers and CAA auditors, regulatory framework, etc. CBTA expansion within the aviation industry should continue to be supported by the proper awareness and implementation efforts by the States and industry.

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SECTION 3: ARRANGEMENT, PROTECTION AND USE OF LAND, WATER AND AIR

NOISE MEASUREMENT ON AN ASPHALT BASE

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Abstract: Noise and vibrations are forms of physical pollution of the environment that can have a harmful effect on the human body, and occur, in the case of asphalt base, during the asphalt production process, i.e. during the operation of the loader that transports fractions from the landfill to the dispenser - silo, as well as during operation conveyor belt, rotary drum. Noise on the asphalt base also occurs as a result of the movement of vehicles that deliver stone aggregate, bitumen, fuel oil and vehicles that take away the finished product - asphalt mass. This paper describes the measurement of the physical and subjective magnitude of sound and noise, in accordance with the JUS standard. N. N4 010, on an asphalt base.

Key words: asphalt base, noise, protection measures, asphalt mixture

1. INTRODUCTION

Using construction machinery for the commercial or residential buildings construction or for various types of excavation in urban areas can cause significant noise emissions. Construction machinery belongs to the group of temporary or occasional sources of noise. The limited duration of noise generated by these sources must be taken into account when assessing the impact of noise on the environment.

A significant noise level can be generated by the operation of asphalt production plants, as well as transport vehicles and machines for handling granulated stone aggregate and the final product - asphalt. [1]

As sources of noise, construction machines can be divided into two groups: mobile sources (trucks, dozers, excavators, backhoes, loaders, etc.) and stationary sources (cranes, compressors, sledgehammers, pneumatic hammers for breaking and cutting concrete and similar electrical equipment). They are very noisy, usually without any noise reduction systems and often very poorly maintained. Operations are generally carried out without taking into account the consequences they cause on the environment. [2,3]

The noise produced by construction machines can be of continuous and impulse type. Sources of continuous noise include motor-driven equipment for various types of excavation, material handling equipment and stationary equipment. Exhaust system noise is the dominant source of noise in this type of equipment, but noise from intake systems, cooling fans, and transmission systems cannot be ignored either. Sources of impulse or impact noise include equipment such as sledgehammers, hammers for drilling and breaking concrete and various types of electrical devices for e.g. nailing, impact tightening, etc. In conventional rammer hammers, the main mechanism of noise generation comes from the impact of the hammer on the post being rammed.

Driving sources of noise are negligible. In order to reduce the noise, different types of hydraulic drills or vibratory rammers can be used, if the terrain conditions allow, With pneumatic equipment, the main sources of noise are the exhaust systems and the impact of the tool on the material being processed.

Table 1 shows the maximum noise level values for some of the construction machines at a certain distance from the source.

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Table 1 Noise level of some construction machines [2]

Construction machines	Noise level		
	Distance from the noise level		
	10 m	20 m	50 m
Loaders	80	67	38
Trucks	77	69	31
Finishers	74	68	34
Roller	72	62	22
Bus	65	51	21
Belt conveyer	88	76	32
Rotary drum	85	75	35
Compressor	92	78	48

The harmful effects of noise are assessed by measuring the noise level at a specific workplace and a specific work premises, expressed in dB(A). The measured noise level at workplaces and premises must not exceed the permitted values. [3] Table 2 shows the permitted noise levels in relation to the noise duration level.

Table 2 The permitted noise levels in relation to the noise duration level [2]

Hours, h	Noise level, dB (A)
8	85
6	87
4	90
3	92
2	95
1,50	97
1	100
1,05	105
0,25	110
0,125	115

2. TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS OF ASPHALT PRODUCTION

Asphalt production takes place in several separate technological units:

- Pre - dose facilities,
- Drying and heating plants,
- Plants for dusting flue gases,

- Plants for sieving, weighing and mixing,
- Plants for dosing fillers and other additives,
- Plants for storage and loading of asphalt,
- Bitumen supply plants,
- Fuel oil supply plants and
- Command center - system for managing of asphalt production.

Figure 1 shows a schematic view of the asphalt base, where the technological units are listed, combined into a single technological process. [5]

1. Dosing with an integrated collector
2. Drying drum with Aman burner
3. Dust removal filter with centrifugal coarse collector
4. Chain elevator with HE II- Reh chain
5. Warm screen with VA 1846-6 bypass switch
6. Warm silo for minerals with 6 units and switches
7. Measuring platform and minerals and bitumen fillers and others weighing materials
8. Mixing platforms for Amix 3,0 or 4,0t two – component mixer
9. Sliding funnel, optional horizontal
10. Mixed silo 100 t directly stitched
11. Direct loading of mixtures into trucks or silo
12. Silo for filters
13. Electroheated bitumen plant
14. Command container

Figure 1 Schematic view of the asphalt technological production

Pre - dosers

The pre-dosers consist of metal silos at a level below which there is a collective conveyor belt, Figure 2. Opening and closing is automatic By measuring the weight flow by fractions dosing is carried out. The amount of individual fractions is obtained based on the recipe for that type of asphalt that is currently being produced. Aggregate fractions from all predosers fall on the collective conveyor belt and are introduced into the drum for heating and drying. The dried and heated aggregate is lifted from the drum by a hot elevator to the sieving system, where it is separated into the specified number of hot fractions that fall into bunkers under the sieve.

Figure 2 Pre - dosers
[A.Sošić]

Figure 3 Rotary dryer
[A.Sošić]

Figure 4 Silo of finished asphalt
[A.Sošić]

Figure 5 Filter dusting
[A.Sošić]

Inclined conveyor belt

The role of this conveyor belt is to transport the mixed aggregate from the dispenser conveyor belt to the drying and heating plant, i.e. rotary dryer.

Rotary dryer

The steel sheet drum, internally coated with refractory material, which during operation rotates around the longitudinal axis is tilted towards the end where the burner is located, i.e. where the heated aggregate comes out. The stone aggregate is inserted into the upper part of the drum by means of a conveyor belt and moved downwards, thanks to the gentle rotation of the drum from the longitudinal axis and the spiral ribs inside the drum. The direction of aggregate movement is opposite to the direction of the flow of hot air from the burner. The drying process is the most expensive operation in the production of asphalt mixture, Figure 3. The role of the rotary dryer is to dry the stone aggregate, dust the stone grains, so that they are clean without a layer of dust or dirt, which allows the bitumen to penetrate and envelop the clean stone grain in the mixer and heating of stone aggregate in the 180°C.

Hot material elevator

The heated aggregate comes out at the lower end of the drum, where it is received by a vertical elevator and raised by a system of continuous vessels to the screening system. The role of the elevator is to accept the heated material from the rotary dryer, lift it onto the vibrating sieve, i.e. to the mixing assembly of the asphalt base.

Vibrating - dosed mixing assembly

The task of the vibrosieve is to sift the hot material-mineral mixture according to the grain size and direct the sifted material into the bunkers above the basket of the scale. Each type of base scale has defined sieve ratios. By sieving the aggregates on vibrating sieves, new fractions are obtained which are cleaner, with little over grain and under grain and dust on the grains.

Boxes - dispenser baskets above the scale basket

Their task is to temporarily store the heated and sifted mineral mixture according to the granulometric grain size before it is shaken into the basket of the scale.

Aggregate scale basket

The task of the aggregate basket scale is to accept, temporarily store and weigh stone aggregates by fractions. The scale is mechanical-electronic, which means that the system of levers and toothed racks weighs the material, converts weight elements into electronic impulses, and sends it to the command and control central unit. After reaching the given weight, the mineral is shaken in a simple current mixer.

Screw conveyor

The purpose of the screw conveyor is to transport the filler from the silo to the mixer. The screw conveyor is activated when the mixer is empty, i.e. when the aggregate is shaken into it, and it stops when the basket of the scale is emptied. From the cistern with heated bitumen, it is transported to the apparatus for volume dosing of bitumen using a double-pole pipe and a gear pump. The pump pipes are heated using hot thermal oil heated to 180°C. In this way, the bitumen is heated, which enables the unimpeded circulation of the bitumen from the cleaner to the mixer. After finishing bitumen dosing the mass is mixed, and then it is shaken out via the basket guide into a cart for transporting ready-made asphalt to the silo for ready-made asphalt. From the mixer, the asphalt is shaken into the finished asphalt transport trolley from the mixer to the finished asphalt silo.

Silo of finished asphalt

The finished asphalt silo consists of 4 compartments of the bunker-pre-silo in which the asphalt mixture is shaken out, Figure 4. They receive (accept) or store asphalt mixture until the vehicles arrive. At the lower part the silo has shutters that are opened and closed by means of pneumatic cylinders. The lever of the shutter of the trolley moves along these stops, which leads to the opening of the shutter of the trolley, and thus the shaking out of the asphalt into the desired silo. By opening the limiter, the help of electric limit switch signals is automatically provided when and where which limiter is activated, i.e. the brake on the winch electric motor is activated.+

Dedusting system, stone particles in the rotary dryer and flue gas discharge from the rotary dryer

The task of dedusting and removal of flue gases and dust from the rotary dryer is achieved by means of a suction fan, of high power, the so-called the coarse and fine filter cyclone that ejects the purified gases into the atmosphere, Figure 5. Material heating system in rotary dryer Drying and heating of stone fines in a rotary dryer is achieved by a flame system, i.e. a burner in which heating oil burns. For the smooth operation of this system, i.e. the combustion of fuel oil, the following are necessary: fuel oil purifiers and the transport and pipeline system from the pump to the burner.

Bitumen heating system and pipelines through which bitumen is transported

Bitumen is stored in above-ground tanks, with a capacity of 3x60m³. It is heated using hot oil. Oil is heated in a boiler with a heating oil burner, and that boiler is called a thermogen.

Bitumen transport to the mixer on an asphalt base

The heated bitumen is transported to the mixer using a gear pump, through a heated pipeline. Before the production process, the bitumen circulates through the pressure line to the speedometer and then back, if the speedometer is not open the bitumen is not sent to the mixer. If mixing is carried out, the bitumen is transported through the speedometer to the nozzles in the mixer, where it is sprayed into the mass.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Description of the technological process of the plant

Stone aggregate of different granulations is fed into a drum for drying, where the material is heated and at the same time moisture is removed. The heat required for drying the aggregates is obtained from the burner, which uses light heating oil as fuel. In the mixing and weighing section, individual aggregate fractions are weighed and mixed with heated bitumen and filler according to a defined recipe with set temperatures and mixing speeds.

Waste gas and removed moisture from the drying drum are introduced into the filter plant and, after purification, are discharged into the atmosphere through the chimney.

Description of the measuring site

The requirements for measuring sections and measuring points are given in the standards MEST EN 15259 from 2016. and MEST EN 13284 - 1 from 2018. In the planning and selection of the measurement location, there are certain requirements - recommendations in order to validly realize the measurement process, which should be fulfilled:

- a) The measuring section must be selected in such a way that the sample taken is representative for the determination of all target parameters.
- b) The measuring plane must be located where the homogeneity of the flow and measured concentrations cannot be questioned.
- v) Measurement at all measurement points of the measurement line should ensure that the gas flow in the measurement plane must meet the following requirements:
 - The gas flow angle must be less than 15° in relation to the channel axis.
 - Minimum speed for flow measurement (PIT pipe differential pressure higher than 5Ra).
 - The ratio between the highest and the lowest speed should be 3:1

$$W_{\min} = 7.1 \text{ m/s}$$

$$W_{\max} = 14.6 \text{ m/s}$$

Measurements were made on a chimney with a circular cross-section $\varnothing$ 1m.

3.2 Permissible noise level

The measurement of the noise level was carried out in order to evaluate the level of noise in the environment that is generated during the operation of equipment and plants at the location of the asphalt base. Instruments as well as basic information about devices used for noise measurement are:

- Sound level meter "Bruel-Kjaer" type 2270 class 1
- Microphone "Bruel-Kjaer" type 4189 class 1
- Calibrator "Bruel-Kjaer" type 4231 class 1
- Anemometer Testo 4102-2 - Digital thermohygrometer and barometer Testo 622.

Noise measurement is performed in accordance with the following standards:

- SRPS ISO 1996 - 1 Acoustics - Description, measurement and assessment in the environment - Part 1: Basic quantities and assessment procedures.
- SRPS ISO 1996 - 2 Acoustics - Describing, measuring and evaluating noise in the environment - part 2: Determination of noise in the environment.

The source of noise consists of: asphalt base, construction machines and cargo trucks.

At the measuring site, one measuring point was selected on the asphalt base.

The measurement was in progress, and the time interval of observation was from 9:00 a.m. to 1:00 p.m. Measurement of the residual noise level performed in a time interval of 15 minutes, in the period when specific noise sources are turned off.

The distribution of sound energy depending on the frequency was determined by the frequency analysis of the noise level using tertiary filters. Third frequency analysis in the frequency range of 50 - 10,000 Hz. During the measurement of the noise level, the "SLOW" characteristic was used to determine the type of noise according to the time course.

Table 3 shows the tertiary level of noise at the measuring point.

Table 3 Tertiary level of noise at the measuring point [13]

Frequency (Hz)	50	63	80	100	125	160	200	250	315	400	500	630
Noise level (dB)	25,9	29,4	36,6	39,2	39,7	42,8	41,6	41,6	41,9	44,1	45,9	47,3
Frequency (Hz)	800	1000	1250	1600	2000	2500	4000	4000	5000	6300	8000	10000
Noise level (dB)	49,2	49,8	50,5	49,7	48,2	46,1	40,4	40,4	36,8	31,8	28,4	24,2

3.3 Official noise level

The official noise level is used as a basic indicator for the assessment of noise disturbance and comparison with limit values. The relevant noise level is determined to define the reference time interval day-evening-night. In order to determine, in addition to the equivalent noise level, knowledge of the following parameters is also required: the duration of the rated noise, the content of prominent tones, the content of pulses and the duration of the reference time interval. When the total noise is uniform, and the duration of the specific noise is equal to the reference time interval, the relevant noise level is determined based on the measured. $L_g = L_{eq} + K$ L_g – authoritative noise level (dV(A)) L_{eq} – equivalent noise level (dV(A)) K – correction. [4]

Table 4 shows the relevant noise level at the selected measuring point.

Table 4 The relevant noise level at the selected measuring point

Measuring point	The relevant noise level Lg dB(A)		Treshold value of the noise indicator dB(A)	
	Day	Night	Day	Night
MP 1.	54	-	60	56

3.4 Noise protection

1. The contractor must take into account the level of noise during the execution of the works;
2. Work affecting the emission of noise in the environment should be performed during the day, during defined working hours;
3. During works, use regularly maintained equipment and machinery that does not generate a high level of noise. Equipment and vehicles that are not in use should be turned off ;
4. Use protective equipment in order to prevent or reduce noise emission.
5. The working space should have appropriate acoustics, which in the general case must provide cushioning of sound propagation.
6. At the maximum value of the acoustic pressure, together or individually displayed 90dV(A) and 200Pa, as well as noise level exceed 85dV(A), personal protective equipment must be used (typhons, ear protectors).

4. CONCLUSION

Noise is a form of physical environmental pollution that occurs during the asphalt production process. The noise on the asphalt base occurs during the operation of the conveyor belt, the rotary drum and the loader that transports the fractions from the landfill to the silo. Noise on the asphalt base is also caused by the movement of vehicles that deliver stone aggregate, bitumen, fuel oil and vehicles that remove the asphalt mass. In order to assess the level of noise in the environment at the location of the asphalt base, noise level measurements are made at the selected measuring point. The official noise level at the asphalt base plant does not exceed the limit values of the noise indicator in the environment.

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2023. THE YEAR OF NATURAL DISASTERS

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Summary: Every year the world is faced with an increasing number of disasters with immeasurable consequences which are yet to be felt for generations to come. Natural disasters are caused by the action of natural forces, and are manifested through earthquakes, fires, floods, droughts, storms, landslides, hurricanes, volcanic eruptions, etc. Elemental disasters take a huge toll in terms of lost human lives and material damage. A common feature of natural hazards is their sudden occurrence (e.g. earthquakes, landslides and landslides, wildfires, etc.), although scientific achievements and modern technology, the occurrence of some natural hazards can predict their place and time (e.g. floods, hurricanes, low temperatures, drought, etc.). This paper deals with the year 2023, a year in which there were numerous disasters in the world with a large number of human casualties and enormous material damage, as well as an adversary impact on the environment - water and air pollution, destruction of flora and fauna.

Key words: disaster, elemental disaster, technical-technological accidents, environmental consequences

1. INTRODUCTION

The Law on Disaster Risk Reduction and Emergency Management [1] defines that "a disaster represents an elemental disaster or a technical-technological accident whose consequences threaten the safety, life and health of a large number of people, material and cultural goods or the environment on a larger scale, the occurrence or consequences of which cannot be prevented or eliminated by the regular action of authorities and public services"; natural disaster is seen as "an occurrence of hydrological, meteorological, geological or biological origin, caused by the action of natural forces such as earthquakes, floods, torrents, storms, heavy rain, atmospheric discharges, hail, drought, landslides or landslides, snow drifts and avalanches, extreme air temperatures, accumulation of ice on watercourses, pandemics, epidemics of infectious diseases, epidemics of livestock infectious diseases and the appearance of pests and other large-scale natural phenomena threatening the safety, life and health of a large number of people, material and cultural goods or the environment in general scope"; technical-technological accident as "a sudden and uncontrolled event or series of events that got out of control in the course of the management of certain means of work and during handling of dangerous substances in production, use, transport, traffic, processing, storage and disposal, such as fire, explosion, accident, traffic accidents, river, railway and air traffic, accident in mines and tunnels, human transport cable cars stoppage, collapse of dams, accidents at power, oil and gas plants, accidents when handling radioactive and nuclear materials, severe soil, water and air pollution, the consequences of war destruction and terrorism, the consequences threatening the safety, life and health of a large number of people, material and cultural goods or the environment on a larger scale".

Images of natural disasters are more and more disturbing. Climate research steadily confirms that the chances of extreme weather events have become bigger. Natural disasters have caused the death of almost 10,000 people. Disaster statistics for 2021 made a strong impression as some extreme weather events fell into the category of those likely to become more frequent or more severe due to climate change. Many scientists agree that the weather events in 2021 were exacerbated by climate change and that due to the warming of the Earth's atmosphere, the situation will be even worse in the next ten years and beyond. Hurricane Ida caused \$36 billion in damage between New Orleans and New York. Damage from the winter storm that primarily hit Texas was about \$15 billion, Germany flooding caused billions in damage. The year 2021 was among the most expensive in US hurricane and winter storm insurance history. Damage insured from natural disasters amounted to about 120 billion dollars in 2020, and it was higher only in 2017 when it was 146 billion dollars, due to hurricanes Harvey, Irma and Maria. 2011 was also difficult and marked by strong earthquakes in Japan and New Zealand, and also the year 2005, when Hurricane Katrina

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ravaged New Orleans. The year 2023 is a year of disasters, starting with earthquakes in Turkey, Afghanistan, fires and floods in Greece and Turkey, typhoons in Thailand, dams bursting in Libya, supercell storms and rains in Europe and in our country and others. The damage data have not been summarized, but they will be of considerable size.

2. THE WORST NATURAL DISASTERS IN HUMAN HISTORY

In most cases there is no defense against nature and devastating disasters, regardless of the technology we have. Increasingly frequent hurricanes, earthquakes and massive landslides, according to numerous experts, are the result of climate change. The world has been hit by disasters in the past, and this is the worst of the worst.

2.1. The deadliest flood

The floods of 1931 killed the highest number of people i.e. between one million and four million. From 1928 to 1930, China was hit by great droughts, and the winter of 1930 was one of the most severe ones. Huge amounts of snow fell, and rains and floods followed in the spring of the following year. The region was hit by nine cyclones in July. The Yangtze River flooded millions of people. The worst period was in July and August. The Yangtze and the Huai River reached Nanjing, then the capital of China, and caused catastrophic damage. Millions of people drowned, while some died of starvation, cholera and typhus. In the city of Hankou, the water level was 16 meters higher than normal. After the water had receded, the authorities toured the area and promised to repair the damage. However, they didn't have enough money, and a civil war was going on, so they only managed to build a few small dams on the Yangtze River.

2.2. The worst tropical cyclone

It was the great Bhola Cyclone in December in 1970 in Pakistan. Between 300,000 and 500,000 people lost their lives. A cyclone formed over the Bay of Bengal on November 8th and began to "travel" northwards. On November 11th, the wind was blowing with a force of 185 km/h. The cyclone also hit India and brought heavy rain. The largest number of victims died from the huge waves caused by the floods. The poor reaction of the authorities led to student protests. Those protests later turned into a civil war that led to the separation from Pakistan and the declaration of the independent state of Bangladesh in 1971.

2.3. The largest volcanic eruption in the 20th century

It happened on May 8th, in 1902, on the French island of Martinique in the Caribbean. Around 30,000 people died. In terms of the number of casualties, it was the deadliest volcanic eruption in the entire 20th century. It practically completely destroyed the city of Saint-Pierre, at that moment the largest community on the island. Earthquakes began at the beginning of May, and explosions could also be heard from the direction of the volcano. Fine volcanic ash fell over the city of Saint-Pierre. Many residents had already evacuated by then, but a significant part decided to stay, believing that it would not be a powerful eruption.

2.4. The most powerful earthquake ever recorded

It occurred in the Chilean city of Vallaparais on May 22nd, in 1960. The strength of the earthquake was 9.5 degrees on the Richter scale. An earthquake of such power caused tsunamis in Chile, Japan, the Philippines and New Zealand. However, considering the strength of the earthquake, the number of victims did not exceed 2,000 people. The second largest earthquake hit Alaska on March 28th, in 1964. The magnitude of the earthquake was 9.2, which also caused a tsunami that killed 28 people. The damage was estimated at 330 million dollars, and some places in Canada also felt the tremors.

2.5. The deadliest earthquake

The deadliest earthquake hit the city of Shaanxi in China in 1556. It was reportedly of magnitude of 8 degrees on the Richter scale, and 830,000 people lost their lives. The area within a radius of 840 kilometers was completely flattened.

2.6. The deadliest tornado

It occurred in Bangladesh on April 26th, in 1989. The exact death toll is unknown, but it is estimated that around 1,300 people lost their lives, which makes it the deadliest tornado in known history, not only in Bangladesh but the entire planet. That tornado was 1.6 kilometers wide and travelled 13 kilometers.

2.7. The biggest disasters caused by human error

By destroying the environment, humans cause ecological disasters, thereby endangering the environment, material goods and their own survival on planet Earth. They have witnessed (and caused) numerous environmental disasters on a wider scale. The below-mentioned disasters claimed a large number of human lives, caused adversary effects on human health, left permanent consequences for the environment, destroyed material goods and disrupted the socio-economic systems of countries.

Chemical disaster in Bhopal, India in 1984 [2]: 2,500 people died in an accident at a pesticide factory on the night between December 2 and 3, 1984, while over 500,000 people were exposed to the toxic effects of chemicals. Although the first signs of danger were detected in time, an accident occurred, causing a catastrophe of enormous proportions. About 40 tons of methyl isocyanate flowed from the tank and within two hours reached the air, spreading downwind. The outside temperature at that time was around 14°C, so the gas cooled and thus reached the lower layers of air. The worst consequences of this disaster were felt by the least privileged population who were located around the factory, as well as pregnant women, which resulted in a large number of stillborn children, miscarriages and deformities in live births were recorded. About 150,000 people were injured in the disaster, and according to the estimates by the International Medical Commission for Bhopal, from 1994 to the present, about 50,000 people have been partially or completely disabled as a result of the accident. The flora and fauna also suffered - about 4,000 livestock, dogs, cats and birds died as a result of this disaster.

Chernobyl nuclear disaster (USSR) in 1986 [2]: on April 26th, 1986, an explosion occurred at the fourth reactor of this power plant, which caused a large amount of radioactive material to be released into the environment. "The explosion had a devastating impact on society and the economy in Ukraine and neighboring countries." The areas in which the impact of this disaster was most pronounced are the western parts of the former USSR and Europe, i.e. the area of today's states of Belarus, Ukraine and Russia. "In order to keep the population safe, in the period from 1986 to 2000, people were evacuated from the 30 km diameter area around the nuclear power plant, which means that about 350,400 people became environmental refugees." The disaster occurred due to poorly performed tests on the cooling system which were meant to increase safety at work. Owing to the uncontrolled rise in temperature, there were two reactor explosions. The reactors release a large amount of radioactive elements into the atmosphere, which, due to the force of the explosion, fly several kilometers into the air. Radioactive materials were carried by the wind to Belarus and other parts of Europe, and increased radioactivity was detected as far as Japan and North America. It is impossible to precisely estimate the human victims of this disaster - from a few hundred (the official position of the USSR), to over 400,000, and even a million of those who have permanent consequences of exposure to excessive radiation. 400 workers and firefighters working to extinguish the burning reactor were exposed to the highest doses of radiation - 30 of them died on the same day (28 from the effects of radioactivity), and 134 of them died later from the effects of radioactivity. About 116,000 people who lived within a radius of 30 km of the accident were soon evacuated, and in the period from 1990-1995, another 210,000 were resettled. All of them were exposed to excessive doses of radiation. A huge number of people developed malignant diseases as a result of radiation - 270,000 people, according to reports from the World Health Organization. In addition, the disaster

left long-lasting consequences for the rest of the living world. 784,320 hectares of land was contaminated, as well as 694,200 hectares of forests. This also led to adversary consequences for the economic system of Ukraine, that is, the former USSR, because farming production in contaminated areas was no longer possible.

Great oil spill (Mexico) in the year 210 [2]: on April 22, 2010, due to an explosion and fire, the oil platform of the "British Petroleum" company sank in the Gulf of Mexico. As a result of technical problems on one of the platforms, there was an oil spill from the well for a full 87 days. In that period, more than 4.6 million barrels of crude oil leaked, polluting more than 7,000 kilometers of coastline. The disaster hit the federal state of Louisiana the hardest, which was declared the largest oil disaster in American history. The oil slick was 1.6 in area kilometers square and about eight kilometers long. As a consequence of this disaster, the sea surface of about 6,000 km² was polluted. The disaster had terrible consequences, starting from the pollution of water, air, coast, animal world, and all the way to major economic consequences for the local economy. The disaster led to the loss of fish, marine flora and fauna and various birds that inhabit the area affected by the accident. Fishing in three American states, stopped entirely. Birds that nested at the confluence of the Mississippi, died in a mass. Turtles, fishes, and fishes are the biggest victims of ecological disasters. The economic damage was also huge - the company spent between 760 million dollars and 4.6 billion dollars to repair the damage.

3. CATASTROPHES IN 2023 [3]

3.1. Earthquakes in Turkey and Syria on February, 6th, 2023

On February 6, 2023, an earthquake struck southern Turkey west of the city of Gaziantep at 4:17 a.m. Turkish time, causing extensive damage across Turkey and Syria. With a maximum Mercalli intensity of IX (*violent*) and a magnitude of 7.8, it is the second strongest earthquake in Turkey after the 1939 Erzincan earthquake. On February, 14th, a total of more than 41,100 deaths were pronounced; over 35,400 in Turkey and 5,700 in Syria. On March, 6th, 2023, the number is at least 50,000 dead, 214,000 collapsed buildings or structures that threaten to collapse. The Syrian Civil Defense called the situation in the northwestern part of the country "catastrophic". Many buildings collapsed and people were trapped. The collapses occurred in the cities of Aleppo and Hama. In Damascus, many people fled their homes to the streets. Many buildings in Syria have already been damaged in the 12-year civil war. As a result many people were left without homes in the earthquake, 8.8 million people were affected by the earthquake and 5900 people officially lost their lives. The actual number of victims could be significantly higher. Data from August 2023 show that the death toll is around 60,000, and twice as many injured. How is it possible that so many supposedly safe buildings were destroyed in an earthquake? State negligence is one of the reasons. In many cases, valid building regulations were not followed, which exacerbated the disaster. In Turkey, 957 people were questioned on suspicion of being responsible for inadequate construction. 236 of them were arrested, and 330 are under "judicial control". Four suspects are still in custody, there is an arrest warrant for 270 people and five of them fled the country. 82 of them were released, and 32 died. The official Turkish institution for protection against natural disasters, AFA, had been warning for years about the severe consequences of a possible earthquake. "Disaster Risk Reduction Plans" were published. A 2020 report warned of a possible earthquake of 7.5 magnitude in Kahramanmaraş province. Such warnings of scientists and proposed preventive measures were ignored by the state. Buildings in other countries were shaking for up to 40 seconds. In Beirut, residents left their homes and stayed on the streets. The earthquake was felt as far as Cyprus. The European Mediterranean Seismological Center announced that the earthquake was felt in Greece, Jordan, Israel, Iraq, Romania, Georgia and Egypt. In Iraq, many residents remained outdoors waiting for a safety announcement to go back home.

3.2. Floods in Slovenia, 2023

According to preliminary data from the Slovenian government, in the devastating floods that occurred in that country at the beginning of August, 34 buildings were completely destroyed, while almost 500 buildings were unfit for habitation, and 649 people were displaced, over 1000 were evacuated. Between 2,000 and 8,000 rescuers and volunteers, as well as members of the army, police and civil protection, participated in rescuing people and removing the last ones, and so far more than 4.5 million euros have been collected through the Red Cross and Slovenian Caritas. The worst recorded floods in Slovenia killed at least six people, swept away houses and littered villages with rubble. Heavy rains fell for days in about two-thirds of the country, destroying buildings and bridges. The damage was estimated at around 500 million euros. The European Union offered heavy machinery and engineering units. Slovenia also requested helicopters, soldiers and prefabricated bridges from the NATO military alliance. Croatia and Hungary helped with helicopters, and Germany with a civil protection team. The Republic of Serbia, with its team, participated in the rehabilitation of the consequences of floods with 22 members and helicopters "H-145" and "Mi-17. Italian-made unexploded hand grenades and cartridges from the Second World War, brought by torrential water, were also found. Due to the floods, many roads in the northern Primorje, Carinthia, Styria, Zasavje and Central Slovenia were closed. Due to the destroyed infrastructure, some parts of the country are still without electricity, so one of the main priorities of the civil services will be the delivery of aggregates. According to the authorities, there is a sufficient number of aggregates.

3.3. Floods in Lybia – bursting of the dam on September, 10th, 2023

A tsunami-sized surge broke through two outdated dams on rivers upstream of the city after heavy rains hit the area on September, 10th. Entire settlements were destroyed, and countless thousands were swept away by the torrent into the Mediterranean Sea. The bursting of two dams near the town of Derna (in mid-September) contributed to making the scale of the disaster immeasurable. The dams collapsed after the storm Daniel hit the area, and the water carried people, entire buildings and settlements into the sea. By September 2023, about 100,000 people lived in this city, and it is feared that the death toll will be up to 20,000. So far, more than 11,000 people have been reported dead, and thousands are missing, as many as 43,000 people have been displaced. Dams in Derna, one 12 kilometers from the city and the other closer, only a few kilometers away, gave way under the huge amount of rainfall brought by storm Daniel. According to Libyan meteorologists and hydro experts, the amount of rain that fell on the area around Derna in the east of the country in 24 hours equalled to the amount of precipitation for the entire month of September. The dams were made of fill stone, that is, only the central core was made of clay, just as in filled earthen dams.

These dams, which are about 50 years old, worked well, because in 1986 and 2011 they did the job and saved the city from floods. The dams had an accumulation of 1.5 and 18 million cubic meters of water. Water management experts said that it is likely that the first dam, about 12 kilometers from the city, had collapsed first, causing the water to slide down the river valley towards the second dam, which is located closer to Derna - where entire settlements were flooded. The head of the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) said on Thursday (September, 14th) that the fatalities could have been avoided if the divided country, wracked by 12 years of conflict and chaos, had had a functioning weather service that could issue warnings.

In a research paper published last year, hydrologist Abdelwanis A.R. Ashour from Libya's Omar Al-Mukhtar University stated that seasonal flooding of the river bed poses a threat to Derna. He stated that there have been five floods since 1942 and called for urgent measures to ensure regular maintenance of the dams.

3.4. Greece – floods in September, 2023

Storm "Daniel" hit central Greece, brought heavy rains that caused floods and landslides, destroyed roads and bridges. The city of Volosio, the region of Pilion, and Thessaly are among the most severely affected areas. On Tuesday, 820 people were evacuated in Greece, 750 of them in the region of Thessaly. After three days of unprecedented fire weather, Pelion, Larissa, Lamia, Trikala and Kardica were turned into mountains of mud, landslides, Volosličina, a lake that seemed to be the beginning of the end. The situation is particularly difficult in the area of Kardica, where water reached a depth of two meters and flooded the roof.

The army was involved in the rescue operation. The most vulnerable, flooded homes were evacuated, boats were used, since roads and bridges exist. "Daniel", accompanied by lightning and thunder, brought an unprecedented amount of water to Greece, while hurricane-like winds on the twelfth day prevented any kind of aviation engagement. The final number of "Daniel" casualties is not known, nor is the number of missing persons.

The floodwaters damaged property, farms and infrastructure, houses were swept away, vital infrastructure was destroyed, everything was destroyed. More than 1,800 people were rescued from flood-affected areas across Greece.

There was no running water in Volos, the electricity supply lasted only a few hours, shops were deserted, and food supply was scarce. It piled up dramatically, all the roads and buildings were destroyed or flooded and the bridges collapsed.

3.5. Earthquake in Afganistan, October 7th, 2023

The death toll from the powerful earthquakes on October 7th in the province of Herat in western Afghanistan, on the border with Iran (which was at a depth of 10 km) exceeded 2,400 people in 20 affected villages with about 10,000 were injured and 1983 buildings were destroyed.

On October 7, two earthquakes of magnitude of 6.3 struck the area 40 kilometers northwest of the city of Herat, and were followed by four large aftershocks of magnitude 5.5, 4.7, 6.3 and 5.9. Afghanistan is frequently affected by earthquakes - especially in the Hindu Kush mountain range which is located near the junction of the Eurasian and Indian tectonic plates.

Entire villages were flattened to the ground, people were trapped under collapsed houses, and the locals were waiting for help without even a shovel to dig people out.

In June 2022, Paktika province was hit by an earthquake of 5.9 degrees on Richter scale earthquake and it killed more than 1,000 people and left tens of thousands homeless.

3.6. Balkan Region

After the devastating earthquakes in early February in Turkey and Syria, a series of weaker earthquakes hit the Balkan region. The ground was shaking in Kraljevo, Belgrade and Bor in Serbia, and it also shook in Croatia, North Macedonia, and Romania. Seismological activities in the Balkans have increased, but they are not directly related to the earthquakes in Turkey and Syria.

The entire region and Europe, as well as the rest of the Northern Hemisphere, lives at greater risk, in the future we will encounter such situations more often because the process of climate change will not stop in the foreseeable future. An increase in the concentration of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere leads to planet warming and an increase in the frequency of warm extremes, a warmer planet means more extreme precipitation, but also changes in the usual patterns of movement and the formation of circulation systems.

An increase in the average temperature of a little more than one degree, i.e. the actual temperature of the planet today compared to the end of the nineteenth century, means an increase in the amount of water vapor by about 7% that can be found in the atmosphere, so we should expect more abundant and intense precipitation, which is a prerequisite for increasing the risk of floods.

4. CONCLUSION

Disasters, such as the aforementioned ones, along with many others, cause incalculable consequences for people (deteriorated health, threatened life and physical integrity, property, but also other values, even the survival of the human race), for the socio-economic system of the country (weakened economy), for the environment (whole areas have been contaminated, numerous animal and plant species were destroyed).

New technologies and techniques, the need for fast and cheaper production, the increasing use of dangerous and flammable substances, create an increasing risk of accidents, fires and explosions, and thus endangering the survival of human race.

Disasters represent a problem due to the impossibility of predicting when and the way they will occur, as well as the consequences they will cause. Disasters have a humanitarian, economic and environmental effect.

The humanitarian effect is reflected in the loss of human lives and the emergence of post-disaster effects. Economic effects include direct, indirect and macroeconomic effects. Man-made disasters have a negative impact on the overall safety. That influence is reflected in the great pollution of the environment, i.e. in its destruction, i.e. destruction.

Environmental disasters produce the following consequences: human health deterioration; food contamination; jeopardizing macroeconomic stability of a country; violation of personal and collective security of the community; total destruction of the environment (putting one specific area out of use; total destruction of flora and fauna - destruction of entire plant and animal species; soil, water and air contamination). As a result of chemical disasters, there are various adversary effects on people and the environment - soil, water and air contamination caused by chemicals (food contamination from the spreading of agricultural products on the fields with aerosols released from chemicals). Pollution of soil, water and air alters and pollutes the entire process of the food chain - if livestock graze on contaminated grass or feed on contaminated food, through the processing-production process of meat, it affects human consumption (milk, eggs, meat). In these cases, the risks to human health are very high, they can be difficult to control, leading to the illness of a large number of people.

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Simulation on Slow Steaming Influence in Nitrogen Oxides Emissions from Ship's Propulsion Engines

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Abstract: Harmful gas emissions have become a growing problem in the world. Global institutions are addressing this problem and developing solutions. Countries that are aware of the problem are implementing regulations that affect global industry and, in particular, maritime transport. Considering that the combustion process, namely diesel, remains the main energy conversion process on board ships, the question arises: what is the best solution to reduce pollutant emissions? Coastal countries have taken various measures to reduce the emission of harmful gases into the marine environment. The problem with these measures is that it is difficult to accurately predict their impact on the environment. The main concern is carbon dioxide emission but, there are other harmful gasses emitted from ships. The paper looks at one of these measures, i.e. slow steaming, to determine how it affects nitrogen oxides (NO_x) emissions from ships. Different engine room, i.e. marine power plants simulators in different operating conditions are used in this study. Several parameters, including main engine (ME) power and nitrogen oxides emission, was measured. In some cases, power reduction led to a reduction in both fuel consumption and nitrogen oxides emissions. In other cases, the result was quite different: while the power reduction led to a reduction in fuel consumption, nitrogen oxide emissions increased.

Keywords: environmental protection; main engine; operating condition, nitrogen oxides

1. Introduction

Ocean-going vessels must have a reliable power supply. Nuclear energy in becoming interesting as a propulsion means onboard merchant ships is still not fully considered. Fuel cell technology is not yet mature enough for such a power supply. The most efficient method is still the diesel engine, and most of the work in the reference list deals with low-speed diesel engines. These facts are undisputed.

Regardless of the process used in the internal combustion engine, the HC compounds are consumed, and the emission of water vapor and carbon dioxide is the side effect. The lighter fractions of crude oil or even methane and methanol instead of the typical heavy fuel oil (HFO) would lead to a reduction in carbon emissions as mentioned by Pelić et. al [1]. Radonja et. al [2,3] and Glujić et. al [4] are investigating different methods to increase the efficiency of main engines, which would lead to a reduction in pollutant emissions. Pelić et. al [5-7] have investigated ways to increase the efficiency of four-stroke diesel engines. Nevertheless, the emission of a certain amount of carbon dioxide cannot be avoided, and the problem has been addressed in many scientific papers. Carbon monoxide, methane, ash and nitrogen oxides are also emitted. Although their amount is several orders of magnitude smaller compared to carbon dioxide emission, the emission of nitrogen oxides is a challenge and there are measures to reduce it.

Various methods or measures have been introduced in many countries around the world to reduce or minimize emissions of nitrogen oxides and other pollutants in ports and coastal waters in general. Stazić et. al [8], Pastorčić et. al [9] and Radonja et. al [10] have measured pollutant emissions in Croatian ports. Unfortunately, it is believed that the reducing effect can be predicted only in 30% of cases while in 70% cases is not possible to predict the outcome. It is known from the history of mankind that technological processes were introduced, which we call revolutions. After a certain time, along with the positive effects, certain negative sides were observed. The history of mankind is full of such examples [11].

Vorkapić et. al [12-14] have attempted to identify a method for optimizing speed with the goal of reducing fuel consumption, energy losses, and pollutant emissions. One approach to reduce pollutant emissions is to optimize speed throughout the voyage [2]. Some coastal countries limit vessel speed in their waters to 12 knots up to a distance of 200 NM from shore to reduce pollutant emissions. This mode of operation is referred to as "slow steaming." It is a universal measure, meaning that any vessel, regardless of engine type or mode of operation, must comply with these regulations.

Many authors have addressed the effectiveness of slow steaming in reducing the fuel consumption of the main engine as Tezdogan et. al [15], Degiuli et. al [16], Gospić et. al [17], Zanne et. al [18] and Giocochea et. al [19]. It seems that fuel consumption of all engines or equipment on board and not only that of ME should be considered. There are papers on on-board innovations, such as the Pelić et. al [20] where on-board photovoltaic power source is considered.

What would be the effect of slow steaming, or at least reduced power, on nitrogen oxide emissions? Boersma et. al [21] investigated the issue of NO_x generation by ships using OMI observations of tropospheric NO₂ columns and GEOS-Chem simulations. Cheng et. al [22] calculated the nitrogen oxide emission factors and total NO_x emissions from two groups of post-Panamax container ships engaged in long-term slow-moving traffic on Euro-Asian routes. In the study conducted by Cheng et. al [23], an accurate method for calculating NO_x emission factors and total NO_x emissions using the actual performance probabilities of diesel engines of four types of bulk carriers is presented.

The objective of this work is to investigate how a speed reduction to 12 knots affects nitrogen oxide emissions. The analysis is performed using the Kongsberg K-Sim ERS engine room simulator on different types of main engines and during different operations modes. The use of nautical and engineering simulators in scientific research is not new and present less expensive methodology compared to conventional on-board measurements [24-34].

Marine equipment manufacturers use two different approaches to reduce nitrogen oxides:

- primary methods that acts on the combustion process in the engine cylinders,
- secondary methods that acts on the exhaust gases through chemical reactions.

The goal of this research is to investigate if mode of operation has a significant impact on pollutant emissions, what is the best mode of operation and how would slow steaming as a method affect nitrogen oxide emissions.

2. Engine Room Models and Modes of Operation

The simulation is performed on several engine room models during different operation modes. The models used in this research are based on Kongsberg K-SIM ERS simulator, with software versions ERS-MC90-V 2.7.1.021 and ERS-RTFLEX-I 2.7.0.0104. Reasons for choosing these models is based on statistical data that 95% of merchant ships still use slow speed diesel for propulsion. Mentioned two engine room models were used in this research, slow speed, cross-head, large diesel engines.

The engine room simulator is simulating the computer management system used onboard. There are two remote control panels; one located in engine control room and another on navigational bridge. The engine control room has more built in control features; precision control, displays, management and regulation. Twelve logbooks with six parameter recording channels is available. Nitrogen oxide emissions is measured only on the exhaust gases from ME and not on the exhaust gases from boilers and diesel generators.

The first row of Table 1. and Table 2. lists the abbreviations for the main engine and the power generators. The following lines indicate the percentage of the maximum power of the ME and the operating configuration of the generating set. These tables show what fuel is used on each fuel consumer and which equipment is in operation to increase efficiency.

For each ship/propulsion engine model several operation modes have been used. The difference in operational modes includes the different vessel type as well as usage the turbo-generator (TG) and shaft generator (SG) for power generation.

In accordance with the NO_x generation logs partially shown in Figures 4 through 12, fuel consumption and NO_x emissions are calculated. The calculations were performed using MS-Excel and the calculated values are presented in Table 3.

Total fuel oil consumption is calculated using the expression (1).

$$B_{ME} = b_{ME} \times P_{ME} \times \frac{T}{10^6} \quad (1)$$

where B_{total} [t] is the mass of fuel consumed by the main engine, b_{ME} [g/kWh] is the specific fuel oil consumption for main engine, P_{ME} [kW] is the power generated by the main engine and T [h] is the travel time. Travel time is calculated according to the following model (2).

$$T = \frac{S}{V} \quad (2)$$

where S [NM] is the total distance travelled at specified speed, in this case taken as 200 Nm and V [kn] is the ship speed.

For the nitrogen oxide emissions calculation, the specific NO_x generation (g/kWh) was multiplied by the power generated by the ME and travel time according to equation (3).

$$B_{NOx} = b_{NOx} \times P_{ME} \times \frac{T}{10^6} \quad (3)$$

The effects of ambient air and sea water, i.e., wind, waves, and others, were neglected during these simulations.

2.1. VLCC Ship Model and its Operational Modes

First simulation models is performed onboard very-large crude carrier (VLCC) with a slow-speed MAN B&W 5L90MC propulsion engine (ME) model simulator. This engine develops 18000 kW MCR at 74 rpm. Machinery system is equipped also with two diesel generators (DG), a turbo-generator (TG) that use steam generated in an exhaust steam generator, and a shaft generator (SG) that can be operated as an electric motor and transfers its power to the propeller shaft. The ship has a large heavy fuel oil (HFO) oil-fired steam generator. The fuel oil system of the main engine contains a fuel-water emulsifier. Its purpose is to reduce the highest combustion temperatures and thereby nitrogen oxide emissions. However, fuel-water emulsifier was not in-service during simulation as the first three operating modes were intended to simulate a classical diesel system.

The first operational modes for this particular engine room is to run the main engine at maximum continuous rating (MCR) and the SG and TG on. The diesel generators were not in operation.

The second operational mode is to run the ME at control level setpoint (CNTLVLSP), reducing by this ship's speed to 14.66 kn and applying the same power¹ generation setup as in first operational mode.

The third operational mode is to run ME at CNTLVLSP, reducing by this ship speed to 11.89 kn. Required electrical power is in this case generated by TG and one of the diesel generators.

Table 1. 5MC90 engine room and operation modes

Mode	ME	SG	TG	DG1	DG2
Mode 1.1.	100%	IN	IN	OUT	OUT
Mode 1.2.	80%	IN	IN	OUT	OUT
Mode 1.3.	60%	OUT	IN	IN	OUT

2.2. Container Ship Model and its Operational Modes

Next three different scenarios were applied to a second ship model, Panamax class container vessel propelled by Wärtsila RT-flex 82C L11 engine. This engine develops 54240 kW of MCR at 102 rpm. The electrical power plant consists of three DG, one TG, which uses steam generated in an exhaust steam generator, and one SG, that can be operated as an electric motor to transmit power to the propeller shaft. An oil-fired steam generator (HFO) is also part of machinery plant.

First three operation modes (Mode 2.1., 2.2. and 2.3.) were performed by simulating the ship propulsion driven by fixed pitch propeller (FPP). Next three operation modes (Mode 2.4., 2.5. and 2.6.) simulations were performed by simulating the ship propulsion driven by controllable pitch propeller (CPP). Therefore, first three operation mode simulations were performed with machinery plant setup as noted below.

1. Main engine operated at 100% CNTLVLSP, shaft generator in power take in (PTI) mode by transferring additional power to propeller shaft, and the TG in service. No any diesel generators were in operation.
2. Main engine running at 80% CNTLVLSP, reducing by this ship's speed to 21.17 kn. Shaft generator was in PTI mode, transferring additional power to the shaft. Electrical power was generated in this case was generated only by the TG. All diesel generators were out of service.

¹ The term "electrical power" in a marine power plant is electrical energy used for powering auxiliary equipment.

3. Main engine running at 40% CNTLVLSP, reducing by this ship's speed to 11.92 kn. Electrical power was generated by the TG and one diesel generator. Two other diesel generators and the shaft generator were out of service.
4. Other three operation modes of operation simulations were performed with machinery plant setup as follows:
5. Main engine control lever at 100% CNTLVLSP where CPP pitch setpoint of 1.115. Shaft generator running in PTI mode transmitting additional power to the shaft, and the TG in service. None of the diesel generators were in operation.
6. Main engine control lever setpoint at 80% CNTLVLSP where CPP pitch setpoint of 1.170. Vessel in this case achieve speed of 24.34 kn and shaft generator operated in PTI mode by transmitting additional power to the shaft. Electrical power was again generated only by the TG. All diesel generators were out of service.
7. Main engine control lever setpoint at 20% CNTLVLSP where CPP pitch setpoint of 0.612. Vessel in this case achieve speed of 12.0 kn and electrical power was generated by the TG and one diesel generator in service. Two other diesel generators and the shaft generator was out of service.

These six modes are listed in Table 2. The column with the main engine (ME) indicates the ME power setpoint percentage, while the other columns indicate the operation of the power machinery for electrical energy generation. The row with Mode 2.3. indicates that ME is operating at about 40% CNTLVLSP, while the Mode 2.6. row indicates ME power of about 20% CNTLVLSP.

Table 2. RT-Flex 82C L11 engine room and modes of operation

Mode	ME	SG	TG	DG1	DG2	DG3
Mode 2.1.	100%	IN (PTI)	IN	OUT	OUT	OUT
Mode 2.2.	80%	IN (PTI)	IN	OUT	OUT	OUT
Mode 2.3.	~40%	OUT	IN	OUT	IN	OUT
Mode 2.4.	100%	IN (PTI)	IN	OUT	OUT	OUT
Mode 2.5.	80%	IN (PTI)	IN	OUT	OUT	OUT
Mode 2.6.	~20%	OUT	IN	IN	OUT	OUT

2.3. Simulation modeling

Calculated NO_x emission is based on data modeled by simulator with unknown exact behavior-based models. However, relationship between ME power and specific NO_x emission during simulation is presented in Figure 1a. Model used for ship power to speed curve is presented in Figure 1b. Furthermore, model used for power to propeller speed is presented in Figure 1c. Setpoints of CPP propeller pitch in relation to operational speed is presented in Figure 1d.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. Simulator behavior-based modeling: (a) Behavior based model for specific NOx emission to ME power; (b) Behavior based model for ME power to ship speed; (c) Behavior based model for ME power to propeller speed; (d) Behavior based model for Container CPP pitch to propeller speed. ME power to ship speed.

3. Simulation Results

During simulations the operating parameters of the main engine that were observed are power and nitrogen oxide emissions. Specific fuel consumption was also measured but recorded separately.

Consistent with the tables 1 and 2, the figures 2, 3 and 4 represent the NOx emission and engine performance logs for the 5MC90 engine room model. The other six figures (Fig. 5 – 10) show the same data for the RT-Flex 82C L11 engine room model.

Each of the recorded parameters is marked with a specific color and described in the figure. The overall scale for each of the parameters is given on the right side of the figure. All parameters were recorded during the total travel time, which was calculated according to the ship speed. The total travel time for each mode was given in column T of Table 3. The curves show the parameters during a very short period (5, 10 or 15 minutes), but some of the parameters could have zero values and some could remain constant during the complete sailing time. In case certain disturbances were detected, the corresponding period was shown on presented figures.

Figure 2 shows, a constant NOx content of 15.04 g/kWh in the exhaust gasses of the main engine for mode 1.1. Neglecting the external disturbances, the power of the main engine remains constant during the whole sailing period. The exhaust gas NOx treatment (Selective Catalytic Reduction – SCR) in this case was not in operation.

Figure 2. Specific NOx emission for Mode 1.1.

Figure 3. Specific NOx emission for Mode 1.2.

In mode 1.2., a disturbance that occurred at point when the power of the main engine was reduced to 80% CNTLVLSP, which finally resulted in lower specific NOx generation. After stabilizing period, the parameters stabilized and remained constant throughout the trip.

Figure 4. Specific NOx emission for Mode 1.3.

The NO_x specific emission logs for Mode 1.3. is shown in Figure 4. In this case a large disorder in specific NOx emission values is noticed when ME power was reduced from 80% CNTLVLSP to 60% CNTLVLSP. The stabilization of specific NOx emission values took longer than during Mode 1.2. The specific NO_x emission is found to be lower than in mode 1.2.

The following figures (Fig 5.-10.) shows specific NOx emission values for container ships (Modes 2.1. – 2.3. for FPP and Modes 2.4. - 2.6. for CPP, for the same container model ship).

Figure 5. Specific NOx emission for Mode 2.1. (Container ship - FPP)

The curves for mode 2.1. specific NOx emission and ME power are shown in Figure 8. As simulated during Mode 1.1, there are no disorders in specific NOx emission. Smooth engine running at MCR and maximum speed generate consistent results.

As presented at Figure 6, the reduction in ME engine power to 26.33 MW, cause a steady decrease in specific NOx emission. The total quantity of generated NOx during the trip is in this case calculated when the specific NOx emission remains constant and is presented in Table 3. SCR unit in this case was in operation and setpoint has been set to 1.39.

Figure 6. Specific NOx emission for Mode 2.2. (Container ship - FPP)

Figure 7. Specific NOx emission for Mode 2.3. (Container ship - FPP)

From Figure 7., a large disorder in specific NOx emission values can be noticed when ME power was reduced from 80% CNTLVLSP to ~40% CNTLVLSP in order that ship can reach/hold 12 kn of speed. However, stabilization of specific NOx emission value took relatively short time (~2-3 min). SG, that had operated in PTI mode in this case switch off due to considerably decrease of generated steam quantity from exhaust gas steam generator. The specific NO_x emission in this case considerably increase.

Figure 8. Specific NOx emission for Mode 2.4. (Container ship - CPP)

Figure 8 presents same ship model as one used on Modes 2.1.- 2.3. with the exception that CPP is used instead of FPP. The results in this case is similar to one on Mode 2.1., showing constant specific NOx emission at full speed by neglecting external conditions. The specific NOx emission is 1.39 g/kWh, while generated ME power is 50 850 kW.

Figure 9. Specific NOx emission for Mode 2.5. (Container ship - CPP)

Figure 9 shows slight change of specific NOx emission when ME power was reduced from 50850 kW to 39150 kW. It also shows a slight increase in specific NOx emission to the value of 1.45 g/kWh.

Figure 10, shows a large disorder in specific NOx emission value when ME power was reduced from 39150 kW to 5970 kW. The specific NOx generation increases to 11.57 g/kWh. The reason for this is that SCR unit has ceased its operation as exhaust gas temperature has dropped below operations limits for SCR unit. However, stabilization of specific NOx emission value took longer time when compared to the case when FPP was used (Mode 2.3.). Mentioned disorder in specific NOx emission and ME power values might be attributed to lack of generated steam quantity from exhaust gas steam generator and consequently automatic switch off of SG that had operated in PTI mode.

Figure 10. Specific NOx emission for Mode 2.6. (Container ship - CPP)

Aggregated total fuel consumption values and calculated specific/total NOx emission values and during complete period of slow steaming is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Fuel oil consumption and NOx emissions calculations

Mode	b_{ME} (g/kWh)	B_{ME} (t)	b_{NOx} (g/kWh)	B_{NOx} (t)	T (h)	V (kn)	P_{ME} (kW)
Mode 1.1.	184.56	3.09	15.04	3.2781	13.01	15.37	16750
Mode 1.2.	180.23	2.56	14.39	2.7897	13.64	14.66	14210
Mode 1.3.	193.44	1.47	11.29	1.4383	16.81	11.9	7580
Mode 2.1.	179.94	9.13	1.39	0.5423	7.69	26.01	50740
Mode 2.2.	174.03	4.58	1.39	0.3458	9.45	21.17	26330
Mode 2.3.	242.11	1.08	12.71	0.9519	16.79	11.91	4460
Mode 2.4.	179.94	9.15	1.39	0.5437	7.69	26.00	50850
Mode 2.5.	177.34	6.94	1.45	0.4665	8.22	24.34	39150
Mode 2.6.	251.30	1.50	11.57	1.1512	16.67	12.00	5970

4. Results Comparison and Discussion

The aggregated calculated fuel consumption values and NOx emission values during sailing time on 200 NM trip are shown in the 3rd and 5th columns of Table 3. Mentioned vales are compared graphically on Figure 11.

First ME and ship model shows that the most efficient results were obtained by performing slow steaming at operating ME with approximately 60% MCR and with the switched off SG and TG. Fuel consumption and nitrogen oxide emissions were greatly reduced during operating in this operating mode.

Second ME and ship model shows slightly different pattern. In terms of total fuel consumption, the most efficient is to reduce the speed to 12 kn. Reduced vessel speed cause rapid decreasing of fuel consumption. However, NOx emission shows different pattern. As presented in Figure 11d., most efficient NO_x emission values are simulated for Modes 2.2. and 2.5. In these cases, engine control lever was set to 80%. Further reducing ME speed; to 12 kn; NOx emission values increase significantly. The reason for this is that SCR unit has ceased its operation as exhaust gas temperature has dropped below operations limits for SCR unit. Container vessel equipped with FPP shows lower emission values and lower fuel consumption values then one equipped with CPP. Container vessel equipped with CPP require that ME operate at higher power for the same speed, therefore generate higher NOx emission and consumes more fuel.

(a)

(b)

Figure 11. Aggregated calculated fuel consumption and NOx emission during complete slow steaming period for different operation modes: (a) VLCC aggregated fuel consumption; (b) Container vessel aggregated fuel consumption; (c) VLCC aggregated NOx emission; (d) Container vessel aggregated NOx emission.

Obtained results shows that by decreasing fuel consumption, total aggregated NOx emission decrease. This is in line with similar research as one of Boersma et. al [21] where slow steaming in North Sea during 2009 decrease NOx emission by 46% while total emission fell by 69%. Research by Cheng et. at [23] shows that operating at lower engine load specific NOx emission raise to the levels above appropriate Tier limits. This is confirmed by our study where specific NOx emission in g/kWh increase when slow steaming is implemented. This is especially valid where secondary NOx reduction technologies are not service. Super slow steaming in case of container vessel (Mode 2.6.) shows rapid increase of specific and even total NOx emission as even SCR unit onboard might not be able to impact NOx emission due to drop in engine operations limits required for SCR unit operation.

5. Conclusion

It was expected and confirmed that lower speed of both VLCC and container ships results in significant reduction of fuel oil consumption compared to consumption when sailing at maximum speed. However, the savings are very different.

When a combination of SG and TG is used, the savings are greatest. It appears that modern marine power plants with shaft generators capable of operating in PTI mode, TG, and other methods of waste heat recovery would achieve the best results at slow speed. In contrast, the classical power plant with a slow-speed main engine and several medium-speed diesel generators has the worst results. From a fuel consumption standpoint, consumption is lower when the ship is steaming slower. Slow steaming yields significant fuel savings (20% on the 5MC90 and 50% on the RT-Flex 82C L11). In super slow steaming, where the speed is set at 12 kn, the fuel savings is even greater. For a VLCC it is 50% compared to full speed, and for a container ship it is as much as 85%.

NOx reduction from slow or super slow steaming is a shows different pattern. For VLCCs, NOx emissions are lower in both modes, i.e., slow and super slow. However, SCR unit in this case was not in operation. The best result is obtained in super slow steaming at 12kn. In this mode (Mode 1.3.), NOx emissions are 50% of those at full speed. For the container ship, the best results are obtained at slow steaming. At super slow steaming the specific NOx production is very high, and although the power (ME) is low, the total amount of NOx emissions is twice that at full speed. The reason for this is that SCR unit has ceased its operation as exhaust gas temperature has dropped below operations limits for SCR unit. The best-case scenario for the container ship is modes 2.2 and 2.5, which reduce NOx emissions by 30% and 10%, respectively.

Due to the significant differences in fuel oil consumption and nitrous oxide emissions, and the fact that only a few operation modes were considered, further studies should follow. These studies should consider different ship loadings, the use of steam to heat liquid cargo, etc. In addition, emissions of other harmful gases should also be studied.

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THE CONNECTION BETWEEN THE QUALITY OF THE ENVIRONMENT AND THE QUALITY OF LIFE

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Abstract: The problem of preserving the quality of life, and thus the environment as its essential condition, is conditioned by the level of development of social relations, production methods, living conditions, work, education, treatment, etc. Considering that the quality of life is mostly contributed by, among other things, a healthy and preserved environment in our work, we started from the assumption of the influence of sociocultural context on the perception of environmental risks and immediate vulnerability. Within the descriptive research method, a survey questionnaire was used as the basic research instrument for obtaining data. The research was done on the territory of Serbia. The research sample was determined by the method of random sampling and included 600 subjects. Based on the obtained results, the set hypotheses were confirmed and the directions of raising the ecological awareness of the population in the future were formed.

Key words: environment, hazards, quality of life, environmental quality, perception of risks.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the growth of social, especially scientific interest in environmental protection, the question of environmental quality has arisen. In order to determine the quality of the environment, operationalization through indicators is needed, starting from monitoring the state of natural and created resources, through analysis of activities and processes in the environment, formation of long-term policy of environmental improvement and provision of measures and means for its realization, to the examination and analysis of the existing quality for further socio-economic development. However, it is not only possible to consider the issue of environmental protection from further degradation in a given approach to environmental quality, but it is also necessary to consider the quality of life in the new conditions of technological development. Quality of life is a relative term because it is a subjective feeling of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with one's own life and is dependent on the possibility of satisfying human needs [1]. Quality of life encompasses a system of spiritual, material, sociocultural, demographic and environmental components of life. A set of relationships that binds the individual, the society in which he lives and the natural environment, so that each of these elements has its own character and nature, represents the quality of life [2]. The most important elements of a person's social environment that determine his quality of life are: social relations, working environment and environment of living [3]. Under the concept of quality of life, contemporary authors mean various areas such as: health insurance, social insurance, education, upbringing, opportunities and conditions of leisure, housing conditions, natural and social component of the environment, personal security and law, political area, etc.

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Some theorists mean quality of life to meet human needs over a period of time, others have a subjectivist approach, while others look at quality of life in relation to the concepts of happiness on the one hand and meeting needs on the other [4]. Observing the relations of environmental protection, the role of education in the context of ensuring its quality and quality of life in general, some authors view the environment as:

- the environment as a nature that must be preserved, recognized and respected (it is a "clean" environment from which man has become alienated and with which he must learn to live if he wants to survive in modern conditions) [5];
- environment as a resource that must be managed sustainably (it is our common biophysical heritage that maintains the quality of life and that requires management according to the principles of sustainable development;
- the goal of sustainable development, according to WCED (1987), refers to this idea of the environment as a resource: it is necessary to act responsibly to ensure that we have enough resources for both present and future generations [6], [7];
- the environment as a problem that must be solved (these are problems of environmental degradation that must be solved in order to maintain and improve its quality);
- the environment as a place to live-to learn about it, to take care of it and to plan (everyday environment at school, at home, in the neighborhood, at workplace and during play; it is a complex of human, socio-cultural, technological , historical and other components; it is our environment that should be respected, valued, belong to it, be responsible for it, plan activities to protect their place to live) [8];
- the environment as a biosphere - where we all live together, for the future (This is Buckminster Fuller's "Spaceship Earth" or the "finite world" of Albert Jacquard (1991); the "Terre-Patrie" of Edgar Morin and Brigitte Kern (1993), and James Lovelock's (1986) selfregulating organism called GAIA. It is the subject of global consciousness; requires an understanding of the different dimensions of the environment and the world, their connection and conditionality with the quality of life) [9];
- the environment as a community project in which to participate (calls for solidarity, democracy and personal and joint participation in order to achieve community development) [10].

These concepts of the environment can be observed simultaneously, but they can also be observed diachronically, as they are also the result of an evolution in time. However, in recent decades, scientific and professional interest in the dimension of the environmental biosphere has grown, i.e. all those risks, dangers and threats that can endanger its quality and bring into question the quality of life and survival of all mankind.

2. METHODOLOGY

We undertook the research with the aim of assessing the dangers and risks that endanger or may endanger the environment and thus the quality of life. We were interested in how the respondents perceive the risks in the environment and the immediate threat in the immediate environment. Within descriptive research method, a survey questionnaire was used as a basic research instrument for gathering data. Research sample was determined by the method of random sampling and it involved 600 respondents. Population in our research consists of adults (people aged 18 plus) living in Kosovo and Metohija. We drew up a hypothetical framework of research which is comprised of the following assumptions:

H1: There is a statistically significant correlation between the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents and the assessment of the dangers and harms that can lead to environmental pollution.

H2: There is a statistically significant correlation between the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents and the perception of risks in the environment.

H3: There is a statistically significant correlation between the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents and the immediate vulnerability in the immediate environment.

We assigned the status of an independent variable to the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, while we treated certain aspects of the environment as a dependent variable (Table 1).

Table 1- Independent and Dependent variables

Socio-demographic characteristics Independent variables	Environment Dependent variables
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Age 2. Gender 3. Educational level 4. Employment status 5. The environment in which the respondents live 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Environmental and hazard assessment in the environment 2. Perception of risks in the environment 3. Immediate endangerment in the immediate environment

With regard to age, the most represented are respondents aged 18-27 (28%) and respondents aged 28-37 (26.17%), followed by respondents aged 38-47 (24.50%) and finally respondents aged 48 year and more (21.33%). Judging by the gender of the survey, we included a higher percentage of women (51%) than men (49%), but the difference is almost completely negligible, so we can say that the desired proportion of male and female respondents is almost completely achieved. When it comes to the level of education, respondents with secondary education are the most represented (52.33%), the percentage of respondents with college degree and university degree (35.17%), and respondents with incomplete and complete primary school are the least included. (12.50%). There is a higher number of employees (63%) in the sample than the unemployed (37%). The number of respondents living in rural areas is higher (58%) than in urban areas (42%).

Preliminary research, which was aimed at testing the validity of the instrument, was conducted at the beginning of 2022. It showed to be very useful and justified pointing to the ambiguous and vague questions, which required their amendment and correction in the final form of the instrument. In the phase of gathering data significant for the investigation of problems, as a technique we used survey, i.e. a questionnaire as a measurement research instrument. Since the examinees filled in an instrument which was subsequently partially modified, data gathered in preliminary research were not taken into account during processing of data gathered in the main research. In October and November (same years) we completely carried out the field part of research. In processing the data gathered by empirical research we applied a set of statistical procedures: percentage expression of the major quantitative and qualitative data, ranking, calculation of arithmetic means, standard deviations, Chi-square test (χ^2) and contingency coefficient.

3. RESULTS and DISCUSSION

H1: There is a statistically significant relationship between socio demographic characteristics and evaluation of risks and hazards that can lead to environmental pollution (Table 2).

Table 2 - The relationship between sociodemographic characteristics and evaluation of risks and hazards that can lead to environmental pollution

Socio-demographic characteristics	Evaluation of risks and hazards (*p<0.05 ; **p<0.01)	
	χ^2	C
Age	2.616	.066
Gender	1.518	.050
Educational level	23.413**	.194
Employment status	8.428*	.118
The environment in which the respondents live	14.482**	.154

Of all the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents, only age and gender, we can say, do not have a statistically significant stake in the assessment of environmental risks and hazards. However, we must point out that the largest percentage of respondents (as many as 80.00%) from all four age categories believe that there are great risks to the environment while the smallest percentage of those respondents (only 3.00%) who believe that there are not. This data points to the fact that the awareness of environmental risks among our respondents exists, which is undoubtedly of special importance in the creation and implementation of educational policy for environmental protection. Also, men and women almost equally believe that there are great environmental risks, which could be expected because both genders have expressed concern for the health and well-being of their families.

The level of education of the respondents is statistically significantly related (at the level of 0.01) with the assessment of risks and hazards to the environment.

Respondents with higher levels of education (college and university degree) generally assess the risks and hazards that can threaten the environment as a major. Analyzing the difference between the employees and the unemployed in respect to the evaluation of risks and hazards that may endanger environment (or they are already polluting it) we have found C = 0.118, chi square was significant at 0.05 level. Respondents who are employed believe that there are great risks and hazards that can lead (or they are already lead them) to endangering the environment in which they live. This could be expected to some extent given the specificity and diversity of conditions to which these respondents are exposed (physical working conditions - lighting, temperature, noise, gases, drafts, dust, risk, occupational safety (injuries, occupational diseases), responsibility, conflicts, interpersonal relationships, etc.). Therefore, when we talk about working (and living) conditions, we do not mean only physical conditions, but also social relations as conditions, although there are authors who reduce working (and living) conditions to physical-technical ones, which impoverishes this concept and loses its entire dialectical meaning and fuller analytical research value. Having in mind the higher presence of pollutants in companies and urban settlements, the results obtained are completely understandable and in accordance with our expectations, which indicate that respondents from urban settlements (more than respondents from rural areas) believe that there are great risks and hazards to the environment.

H2: There is a statistically significant correlation between the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents and the perception of risks in the environment (Table 3).

Table 3- Relationship between socio-demographic characteristics and environmental risk perceptions

Socio-demographic characteristics	Environmental risk perceptions (*p<0.05 ; **p<0.01)	
	χ^2	C
Age	10.694	.068
Gender	16.832	.086
Educational level	17.604	.088
Employment status	8.954	.063
The environment in which the respondents live	52.828**	.151

There is a statistically significant correlation only between the type of environment (urban, rural) and the perception of risk in the environment. Our research showed that the respondents from both urban and rural areas very carefully perceived the risks in the environment (C = 0.151, chi square significant at the level of 0.01). Respondents stated as the greatest risk to the environment: the proximity of landfills, illegally constructed facilities that are not under sanitary supervision, wastewater, polluted air, destruction of green areas and excessive deforestation, etc. Our question in the survey questionnaire regarding the perception of the state of the environment was of a combined type. However, we did not receive a single answer from the respondents beyond the ones offered, so we are of the opinion that by careful description of the terrain we managed to register the relevant facts and offer the most adequate answers for the respondents living in urban and rural areas.

H3: There is a statistically significant correlation between the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents and the directly risks in immediate environment (Table 4).

Table 4- The relationship between sociodemographic characteristics and directly risks to the environment

Socio-demographic characteristics	Directly risks (*p<0.05 ; **p<0.01)	
	χ^2	C
Age	0,234	.020
Gender	0,410	.026
Educational level	0,256	.021
Employment status	0,674	.034
The environment in which the respondents live	5,778*	.098

The statistical association of low intensity only appeared between the type of environment (urban, rural) and the immediate risks. Respondents of urban areas in relation to respondents of rural areas more often characterize as great risks and hazards that can lead (or already lead) to environmental pollution. A large percentage of respondents (69.00%) believe that they are directly endangered in the environment.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of our research show that there is an awareness of people that achieving favorable living conditions and preserving the quality of the environment is necessary to meet existential, biological and social needs.

So, those needs whose satisfaction, at the same time, determines the quality of people's lives. It is with the re-examination of the value system and goals of modern industrial societies, especially in the conditions of endangered quality of the environment, that doubts have arisen in the further perspective of the quality of life in these societies. This only confirms the thesis that human being and his life cannot be viewed outside the problems of the environment and vice versa. A clean environment, aesthetically refined, is actually a precondition of modern ecological culture. As some authors describe, if we imagined an imaginary mental image and placed the quality of life in the center of that image, spheres would be formed around that center (around the quality of life). The first area closest to the center would include: health and social care, economy, culture, people and space, environment, social security, transport and access, household, education, social cohesion and inclusion. A little further from the center, but in correlation with it, the spheres would include economic, social, state development and environmental development. In these spheres, a ring would be singled out, which implies renewability, vulnerability and risks. All circles are correlated with each other. The center and the periphery are interconnected by flows of information, capital, labor, and ideas

The quality of life, therefore, is mostly contributed by: stable social movements; economic opportunities of the individual and society as a whole; establishing a balance between people's social differences and the economic development of society; the existence of institutions and respect for the rule of law in all areas and at all levels; environmental protection; availability of knowledge; adherence to standards; developed system of responsibility, etc.

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INVESTIGATION INTO THE POSSIBILITY OF THE INTERACTION OF “SUPERHALOGEN” CLUSTERS/COMPOUNDS WITH HIGH IONIZATION ENERGIES

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Abstract: It is known that compounds that are considered environmental pollutants have high ionization energy (IE) values, which makes them less reactive. Theoretical works have shown that “superhalogen” clusters, thanks to their high electron affinity, can react with these compounds and thus contribute to their elimination. However, experimental evidence is scarce. Therefore, in this work, we investigated the possibility of obtaining “superhalogen” clusters from lithium fluoride and the interaction of these clusters with water molecules (as a prototype for compounds with high IE) using laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometry (LDI MS). Preliminary results showed that it is possible to obtain “superhalogen” clusters such as LiF_2^- , LiF_3^- and polynuclear “superhalogens” Li_2F_3^- , Li_5F_6^- in the negative mode of LDI MS. It was also shown that polynuclear “superhalogens” interact with water molecules $\text{Li}_2\text{F}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$, $\text{Li}_2\text{F}_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2^-$, $\text{Li}_5\text{F}_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ were detected).

Key words: “superhalogens”, LDI-MS, Li_2F_3 , Li_5F_6 , polynuclear “superhalogens”

1. INTRODUCTION (HEADING 2 STYLE)

“Superhalogen” clusters were discovered by Gutsev and Boldyrev [1] and refer to molecular clusters that have an unusually high electron affinity compared to conventional halogen molecules. The term “superhalogen” is derived from the expectation that these clusters exceed the electron affinity of a Cl atom, namely 3.6 eV. In these clusters, a central atom is surrounded by a shell of halogen atoms, creating a unique electronic environment that increases the overall attraction of the system for electrons. Therefore, Gutsev and Boldyrev [1], [2] proposed the general formula MX_{k+1} , where M corresponds to a metal atom with maximum formal valence k surrounded by k + 1 halogen ligands X. Research has shown that the central atom (M) does not have to be a metal and that the ligands can be different functional groups [3]-[8]. Theoretical research has shown that there are also polynuclear “superhalogens”, general formulas M_nX_{n+1} , such as $\text{Na}_x\text{F}_{x+1}$ (x=1-4) and $\text{Li}_n\text{F}_{n+1}$ (n=2-5) [9], [10].

Theoretical studies have shown that these species can be used as halogen-free electrolytes in metal ion batteries, as building blocks for hydrogen storage materials, as ionic conductors with improved ionic conductivity and as moisture-resistant hybrid perovskite solar cells [11]-[14].

Thanks to their high electron affinity, “superhalogens” are considered strong oxidizing agents that can ionize very stable molecules with high ionization energy such as H_2O (IE 12.6eV) or benzene (IE 9.24eV). This opens up the possibility of using “superhalogens” to remove carcinogenic substances such as benzene from the environment [15], [16].

In this work we have investigated the possibility of producing lithium fluoride clusters using laser desorption/ionization mass spectrometry. It is interesting to see whether the formation of “superhalogen” clusters, which is theorized, takes place. We also investigated possible interactions between LiF clusters and water molecules as a model for the interaction between the “superhalogen” cluster and compounds with high ionization energies.

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2. EXPERIMENTAL

A commercially available Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionisation Mass Spectrometer (MALDI MS), Voyager-DE PRO (Sciex, USA), was used for this work. This mass spectrometer is equipped with a nitrogen laser (with a pulse frequency of 20 Hz, a wavelength of 337 nm and a pulse duration of 3 ns), and a time-of-flight (TOF) mass analyzer is used. All mass spectra were obtained without matrix e. i. laser desorption/ionization method. The mass spectrum shown was obtained under the following conditions: acceleration voltage 20000 V, grid voltage 94%, laser intensity 1858 a.u. and number of laser beats 300, with a delayed extraction time of 100 ns. The mass spectra were recorded in negative reflectron mode.

The sample was a solution of lithium fluoride in water, 0.1 mol/dm^3 ; $1\ \mu\text{l}$ of the sample was applied directly to a stainless steel plate and dried at room temperature before being introduced into the mass spectrometer.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSION

The inhomogeneity of the dried LiF sample is typical for the LDI-MS method. Figure 1 a and b show the consequences of the inhomogeneity. The comparison of these two images shows that the inhomogeneity has no influence on the type of ions obtained, but does have an influence on the variation of the intensity of the peaks obtained. The intensity of the peaks is related to the stability of the ion species obtained, suggesting that the amount of desorbed sample influences the stability of certain clusters.

Figure 1. The LDI mass spectra (negative mode) of the lithium fluoride salt solution a) light part and b) dark part of the sample after drying on the stainless steel plate.

In Table 1, we have shown the identification of selected peaks from the LDI mass spectrum of LiF (Figure 1a and b).

Table 1 Identification of selected peaks detected in the LDI mass spectra of lithium fluoride.

Peak identity	Experimental peak position, m/z	Calculated m/z	Peak identity	Experimental peak position, m/z	Calculated m/z
Li(OH)(H ₂ O) ⁻	42.03	42.03	Li ₂ F ₃ (H ₂ O) ⁻	89.11	89.04
	41.02	41.03		88.06	88.04
LiF ₂ ⁻	45.03	45.01	Li ₂ F ₃ (H ₂ O) ₂ ⁻	107.02	107.03
	44.02	44.01		106.04	106.03
LiF ₃ ⁻	64.01	64.01	Li ₂ F ₅ ⁻	109.04	109.02
	63.05	63.01		108.04	108.02
Li(OH) ₃ ⁻	58.04	58.06	Li ₂ F ₅ (H ₂ O) ⁻	127.05	127.03
	57.04	57.06		126.04	126.03
LiF ₂ (OH) ₂ ⁻	79.03	79.02	Li ₅ F ₆ (H ₂ O) ⁻	167.22	167.08
	78.09	78.02		166.15	166.08
Li ₂ F ₃ ⁻	71.08	71.03	LiF ₈ (OH) ₂ (H ₂ O) ⁻	211.27	211.02
	70.07	70.03		210.27	210.02

The results show that the negative ions detected are the “superhalogen” clusters LiF₂⁻ and LiF₃⁻. The negative ions of the polynuclear “superhalogen” clusters Li₂F₃⁻ and Li₅F₆⁻ were also detected in this way. The peak at m/z 64 has the highest intensity in Figure 1b, indicating that the LiF₃⁻ cluster has greater stability under certain circumstances than other detected compounds. Polynuclear clusters were shown to interact with water molecules; the ions Li₂F₃(H₂O)⁻, Li₂F₃(H₂O)₂⁻, Li₅F₆(H₂O)⁻ were detected. Ions such as Li(OH)₃⁻, Li₂F₅⁻, Li₂F₅(H₂O)⁻, LiF₈(OH)₂(H₂O)⁻, LiF₂(OH)₂⁻ were also detected in the LDI mass spectrum, which could have “superhalogen” properties. In addition, a peak at m/z 42 was isolated, indicating that Li can bind a hydroxyl group and a water molecule, which could provide important information for future studies on the structure of “superhalogen” clusters and their interaction with H₂O molecules.

4. CONCLUSION

The preliminary results presented in this paper show that the LDI-MS method is suitable for obtaining “superhalogen” clusters and for studying the interaction of “superhalogens” and compounds with high ionization energy. LiF_n and polynuclear Li_nF_{n+1} (n = 2, 3, 5) “superhalogen” clusters were detected. It has been shown that polynuclear clusters can bind to water (Li₂F₃(H₂O)⁻, Li₂F₃(H₂O)₂⁻, Li₅F₆(H₂O)⁻). In addition, some ions such as Li(OH)₃⁻, Li₂F₅⁻, Li₂F₅(H₂O)⁻, LiF₈(OH)₂(H₂O)⁻, LiF₂(OH)₂⁻ have been identified whose stoichiometry could exhibit “superhalogen” cluster properties.

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RADIOACTIVITY OF THE WASTE Pb-Ag PRECIPITATE FROM THE ZORKA ŠABAC ZINC INDUSTRY

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Abstract: After the Zorka Šabac zinc factory ceased operation in 2007, a large amount of various wastes remained, among which is Pb-Ag precipitate that results from the three-stage hot-acid leaching process and is categorized as hazardous chemical waste. The aim of this work is to determine the content of natural radionuclides (²³⁸U, ²²⁶Ra, ²³²Th and ⁴⁰K) as well as the artificial radionuclide ¹³⁷Cs in Pb-Ag precipitate and to assess the radiation risk for workers who were exposed to radiation while working with this waste. Measurements of radionuclide activity concentrations were carried out using the gamma spectrometry method. The measured values of the analyzed natural radionuclides are around and below the average values for soil in the world, while the values for ¹³⁷Cs are below 1 Bq kg⁻¹. The values of annual effective doses are far below 1 mSv, and the values of excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR) are around the world average, so it can be said that the workers were not exposed to an excessive dose of radiation.

Key words: Radioactivity, Zinc, waste, Pb-Ag precipitate, Dose.

1. INTRODUCTION

The environment around us since the formation of the Earth contains small amounts of naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM). Their prevalence in the environment is generally at levels that are not potentially harmful to human health [1]. A major concern arises when levels are elevated as a result of human activities such as mining. In nature, mining and ore processing involves the production of large amounts of waste, which can contaminate the soil over a large area and thus negatively affect the environment and human health. Mining is one of the main causes of increased NORM concentrations on the earth's surface, causing health risks to humans, especially when inhaled or ingested. The most important natural radionuclides in radiation protection are those from the decay series of uranium-238 (²³⁸U) and thorium-232 (²³²Th) as well as potassium-40 (⁴⁰K). Therefore, knowing the activity concentrations of these radionuclides is important in the assessment of absorbed doses that can lead to the assessment of their radiological danger for the population, especially for workers [2]-[4].

In the world, there are many different wastes that are produced by ore processing in chemical industries in huge quantities, which, in addition to the content of heavy metals, have a toxic effect, but can also contain a certain concentration of natural radionuclides [5]-[7]. Serbia is a country with a different tradition in the mining and production of non-ferrous metals (zinc and cadmium) from the fifties of the last century until fifteen years ago when the production was stopped, leaving behind a

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large amount of waste materials. Non-ferrous metallurgy in Serbia and the former Yugoslavia has always had a huge technical, economic and social importance. Zinc was produced in the Zorka Šabac and Trepča factories in Kosovska Mitrovica with a maximum production of 36,756 and 48,500 tons of zinc per year, respectively. According to the level of zinc production from its own raw materials, Yugoslavia occupied one of the first places in Europe [8].

Zinc is one of the most important and widespread heavy non-ferrous metals. In nature, it is not found in a free state, but in the form of various zinc ores. The main zinc ores exploited in the world are sphalerite (ZnS) and marmatite [(ZnFe)S], which are always found with the lead mineral galena (PbS), and are separated by the flotation process. Zinc ores are usually low grade ores containing 2–7.5% Zn. The mineral enrichment process (i.e. flotation) leads to the separation of Pb and Cu sulfides and the concentration of zinc (ZnS). Zinc concentrates obtained by flotation usually contain 47-60% Zn, 3.5% Cu, 1.5-2.5% Pb, 3-10% Fe, 0.2% Cd and 29-33% S, $\leq 0.5\%$ As, $\leq 0.2\%$ Sb; smaller concentrations of Tl, In, Ge, Ga, Se and Te are also present. Two processes are used to extract zinc from the ore: a pyrometallurgical process and a hydrometallurgical process followed by an electrometallurgical process. The hydrometallurgical process is predominantly used to extract zinc from low-grade ores. This process produces zinc of high purity (99.99%) and also leads to a higher recycling rate of valuable by-products [9], [10]. The hydrometallurgical production process involves roasting zinc sulfide concentrate (ZnS) and converting it into oxide form (ZnO), and then leaching into diluted sulfuric acid.

Bearing in mind that after the process of neutral leaching, 15-32% of Zn remains in the precipitate (solid phase), which is mostly bound with iron in the form of zinc-ferrite containing 55-60% (Zn+Fe), and that no significant zinc losses, this precipitate is further processed in order to extract Zn. Further processing involves three-stage leaching of the precipitate in an acidic medium at elevated temperature (70-95 °C) [11].

Figure 1 – (a) Appearance of Pb-Ag precipitate deposited directly next to the production plant in a concrete box at the Zorka non-ferrous metallurgy factory in the last years of operation; (b) Appearance of Pb-Ag precipitate deposited after moving to another location in 2020 without adequate soil protection measures.

During the leaching of zinc sulfide concentrate, several precipitates and intermediate products are obtained (Pb-Ag precipitate, Jarosite precipitate, Copper sludge, Co-Ni precipitate, etc.) which, in addition to the base metal, zinc, also contain a whole series of other useful metals [5]. In addition to useful metals, these sludges also contain a number of toxic ingredients, and their disposal in landfills poses a danger to the living environment, especially to soil and surface water [8], [11].

Pb-Ag precipitate represents solid waste from the technological process of three-stage hot-acid leaching of unleached precipitate from the process of neutral leaching of zinc sulfide concentrate. Pb-Ag precipitate usually contains traces of zinc, lead, copper, cadmium, cobalt and other metals. The

content of zinc ranges from 2-6%, iron 3-8%, lead 15-25% and silver 0.05-0.1% [11]. Pb-Ag precipitate is not difficult to process in aggregates of the lead refinery according to the standard pyrometallurgical procedure [11], which was not the case in Zorka Šabac, and this waste accumulated in the landfill. One of the largest disposal sites for Pb-Ag deposits in Serbia is located within the industrial complex of the Zorka non-ferrous metallurgy factory, which was deposited before 2007, i.e. in the last years of the factory's operation, Figure 1a, and which, after the privatization of the factory in 2020, was moved to another location without adequate protection measures, thus contaminating the local soil with heavy metals contained in this waste, Figure 1b. Therefore, the location where this hazardous waste is currently located is not in the function of protecting public health. During the operation of the factory, an average of 650 tons of this waste was generated per month, the total amount of deposited waste in Figure 1b is unknown.

The starting ore as well as the zinc sulphide concentrate contain a certain concentration of natural radionuclides. The technological processes used to extract zinc from the concentrate can affect the distribution of radionuclides in different ways among raw materials, intermediate products and wastes, as well as among other materials in industry [5], [6], [12]. For this reason, it is necessary to determine the activity concentration of the mentioned radionuclides in order to further assess the radiation risk for workers in terms of annual effective doses.

The aim of this work is to determine the activity concentration of natural radionuclides: ^{238}U , ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K and the artificial radionuclide ^{137}Cs in samples of Pb-Ag precipitate produced in the Zorka Šabac zinc industry and to compare it with values for other waste materials and to assess the level of contamination of the surrounding land with radionuclides. Also, the aim is to assess the radiation risk for workers who were exposed to external gamma radiation while working with this waste.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

10 samples of Pb-Ag precipitates taken from the location where a larger amount of this waste is located, Figure 1b, within the Zorka Šabac industrial complex, were examined. Before measurement, all samples were dried for 6-8 hours at 105 °C in order to minimize the influence of moisture on the measurement. After drying, the samples were homogenized to a fine powder by manual grinding in an avan and then transferred to sample holders (cylindrical plastic containers measuring 67 mm in diameter and 62 mm in height) which were sealed with wax to prevent ^{222}Rn from escaping from the container. The mass of the samples was about 230 g. All analyzed samples were closed and left for at least 30 days to achieve a secular radioactive balance between ^{226}Ra and ^{222}Rn , and then radioactivity measurements were performed [13]. The samples were prepared in the Physics Laboratory at the Academy of Applied Studies in Šabac, Serbia.

Samples were prepared and analyzed using the standard IAEA TRS 295 method [14]. The activity concentrations of natural radionuclides: ^{238}U , ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K as well as the artificial radionuclide ^{137}Cs were determined based on the gamma lines shown in Ref. [5]. Samples were measured with standard gamma spectrometry method using low-level high purity germanium (HPGe) detector (relative efficiency of 36% and energy resolution of 1.9 keV for gamma line of ^{137}Cs at 662 keV). The shielding around the detector is made of 12 cm thick lead to minimize the influence of background radiation and 3 mm thick copper to prevent the penetration of X-radiation from the K-shell of lead in the energy range of 75–85 keV [15]. The acquisition and analysis of spectra were done using Canberra Genie 2000 software. Typical measurement time was 72000 s. The measurements were made in the Department of Physics, Faculty of Sciences, University of Novi Sad.

Data were collected and analyzed using Canberra Genie 2000 software, which calculates activity concentration values for a given radioisotope, taking into account all significant gamma lines, after subtracting the part of the spectrum originating from background radiation. The calibration of the used HPGe detector was performed using a cylindrical reference radioactive standard embedded in silicone resin, volume 250 cm³ produced by the Czech Metrological Institute [16]. The integral count rate in the range between 30 and 3000 keV was about 1.2 counts s⁻¹. Results are presented with measurement uncertainties with 95% confidence [5].

Based on the measured values of the activity concentrations of natural radionuclides: ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K , the values of the hazard index and annual effective doses were determined for the workers who manually carried this waste from the leach plant to the nearby landfill. The values of radium equivalent index (Ra_{eq}), gamma index (I_γ), absorbed gamma dose rate (D), annual effective dose (E) and excess lifetime cancer risk ($ELCR$) were determined according to the methodology described in our previous research [5]. The average value of the absorbed gamma dose rate in the world is 59 nGy y^{-1} [17]. The recommended value of the radium equivalent index is $< 370 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ [18]. The recommended value of the gamma index < 1 , which ensures the recommended annual effective dose of less than 1 mSv [19]. The average value for excess lifetime cancer risk is 0.29×10^{-3} [18].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The measured values of the activity concentrations of ^{238}U , ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs for 10 samples of Pb-Ag deposits are shown in Table 1. The comparison of the measured values of the analyzed radionuclides in this waste with other wastes in the world from mining and chemical ore processing industries is shown in Table 2.

Table 1 Measured values of ^{238}U , ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs activity concentrations for 10 samples of waste Pb-Ag precipitate.

Sample ID	Mass of sample (g)	Activity concentration (Bq kg^{-1})				
		^{238}U	^{226}Ra	^{232}Th	^{40}K	^{137}Cs
PBAG1	224.6	50±5	53.3±2.0	6.3±0.8	66±8	< 1.0
PBAG2	223.4	47±4	49.7±1.8	6.49±0.60	73±8	< 0.9
PBAG3	231.1	33±7	39.3±1.6	5.20±0.54	61±8	0.24±0.09
PBAG4	245.3	45±5	48.0±1.6	6.54±0.60	74±8	0.35±0.10
PBAG5	224.3	39±5	55.3±1.8	6.3±0.80	68±8	< 0.9
PBAG6	240.4	44±6	47.5±1.8	4.22±0.52	63±8	< 0.8
PBAG7	229.0	41±5	44.3±1.8	5.56±0.52	61±8	< 0.9
PBAG8	236.6	36±3	38.7±1.6	5.16±0.48	56±8	< 0.8
PBAG9	211.8	37±4	39.4±1.6	4.22±0.46	40±6	< 0.9
PBAG10	230.1	35±4	43.3±1.6	6.06±0.52	77±8	< 0.8
Range		33-50	38.7-55.3	4.22-6.54	40-77	< 1.0
Average±SD		40.7±5.3	45.9±5.6	5.61±0.84	64±10	-
Average in the soil¹		33	32	45	420	-

¹given in Ref. [17]. SD=standard deviation.

The measured values of ^{238}U activity concentrations are in the range of $33\text{-}50 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$. The average value for ^{238}U is $40.7\pm 5.3 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$, which is around the average value of 33 Bq kg^{-1} for soil [17]. The measured values for ^{238}U are comparable to the values in phosphogypsum from Brazil, gold mine tailings from Ghana and Fiji, Table 2. Compared to the values for waste EMCO precipitate and Pyrite ash from our previous research [5], higher values of ^{238}U were measured, Table 2. The obtained values are drastically lower than those measured in mill tailing from South Africa, tailings from zinc ore from Pennsylvania, and tailings of tin from Nigeria, Table 2.

The measured values of ^{226}Ra activity concentrations range from $38.7\text{-}55.3 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$. The average value for ^{226}Ra is $45.9\pm 5.6 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$, which is around the average value of 32 Bq kg^{-1} for soil [17]. Based on the measured values of the activity concentrations of ^{238}U and ^{226}Ra , it can be said that these two radionuclides are in balance, and that the technological processes of leaching did not disturb their radioactive balance. The measured values are drastically lower compared to those measured in phosphogypsum, Red mud, metallurgical slag, bottom ash-coal slag and fly ashes, Table 2. The obtained values are higher compared to the values measured for: waste from lead-zinc mine, tailings from zinc ore, EMCO precipitate and pyrite ash, Table 2.

The measured values of ^{232}Th activity concentrations range from 4.22-6.54 Bq kg⁻¹. The average value for ^{232}Th is 5.61±0.84 Bq kg⁻¹ and is about 8 times lower than the average for the country [17]. The obtained values for ^{232}Th are comparable to those measured in phosphogypsum from Serbia, waste from lead-zinc ore, tailings from zinc ore, EMCO precipitate and pyrite ash, Table 2. The measured values are lower compared to those measured in other wastes: phosphogypsum from Brazil, red mud, mill tailing, gold mine tailings, metallurgical slag, tailings of tin and coal, bottom ash-coal slag, fly ashes and jarosite precipitate, Table 2.

The measured values of ^{40}K activity concentrations range from 40-77 Bq kg⁻¹. The average value for ^{40}K is 64±10 Bq kg⁻¹ and is about 6.5 times lower than the average for the country [17]. The measured values for ^{40}K are comparable to those measured in phosphogypsum from Serbia, red mud, gold mine tailings from Fiji and tailings of coal, Table 2. Compared to the following wastes, drastically lower ^{40}K values were measured in Pb-Ag precipitates: mill tailing, waste from lead-zinc mine, gold mine tailings from Ghana, metallurgical slag, bottom ash-coal slag, fly ashes, EMCO precipitate, pyrite ash and jarosite precipitate, Table 2.

Table 2 Comparison of activity concentrations of ^{238}U , ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K for wastes in other industries in the world and those obtained in this research.

Waste	Country of origin	Activity concentration (Bq kg ⁻¹)				References
		^{238}U	^{226}Ra	^{232}Th	^{40}K	
Phosphogypsum	Serbia	/	488-737 (600)	2.1-4.5 (3.2)	<5-117 (47)	[6]
Phosphogypsum	Brazil	20-69 (42)	450-1251 (849)	47-346 (222)	/	[23]
Red mud	6 European countries	-	97-301 (205)	118-539 (327)	50-215 (95)	[24]
Mill tailing	South Africa	87-2668 (485)	/	20-89 (44)	226-781 (427)	[3]
Waste from lead-zinc mine	Iran	/	(26.18±2.53) ^a	(6.98±2.25) ^a	(222±6) ^a	[2]
Tailings from zinc ore	Friedensville, Pennsylvania	(4.81)	(7.4)	(1.1)	/	[25]
Gold mine tailings	Ghana	(48.3±11.0) ^a	/	(29.6±6.2) ^a	(577±122) ^a	[26]
Gold mine tailings	Fiji	7.1-47.9	/	ND-129	46-176	[27]
Metallurgical slag	13 European countries	/	15-336 (139)	1-152 (65)	20-786 (249)	[24]
Tailings of tin	Nigeria	1710-16600 (7220)	/	5290-47500 (16800)	ND	[28]
Tailings of coal	Nigeria	/	13.4-27.2 (20.2±1.0) ^a	20.9-32.3 (25.7±1.3) ^a	56-126 (91±4) ^a	[4]
Bottom ash-coal slag	8 European countries	/	68-1391 (345)	14-100 (59)	200-500 (410)	[24]
Fly ashes	16 countries	/	75-815 (191)	37-140 (91)	157-900 (561)	[24]
EMCO pecipitate	Serbia	5.7-31.2 (13.3)	11.8-20.9 (16.4)	4.7-6.1 (5.2)	100-119 (113)	[5]
Pyrite ash	Serbia	1.8-6.0 (3.5)	5.1-9.7 (6.8)	2.8-4.5 (3.5)	109-122 (114)	[5]
Jarosite precipitate	India	/	(55.4±0.9) ^a	(72±3) ^a	(295±18) ^a	[29]
Pb-Ag precipitate	Serbia	33-50 (40.7±5.3)	38.7-55.3 (45.9±5.6)	4.22-6.54 (5.61±0.84)	40-77 (64±10)	Present study

- range; (average). ^a(average ± standard deviation). ND=not detectable value.

Compared to the values for soil from India, the obtained values of ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K are significantly lower [20], while the values for ^{238}U and ^{226}Ra are comparable to the content in the soil of Vojvodina, and the values of ^{232}Th and ^{40}K are significantly lower [21]. All measured values of ^{137}Cs are < 1 Bq kg⁻¹. The measured values of ^{137}Cs in the Pb-Ag precipitate are lower than those measured for e.g. land in Hungary [22] and Vojvodina [21].

Comparing the values for ^{238}U and ^{226}Ra that were measured in zinc sulfide concentrate as the starting raw material (on average 3.4 and 9.4 Bq kg⁻¹, respectively) in our previous research [5] and this research for this waste, it can be clearly seen that the process leaching of roasted zinc sulphide concentrate led to the fact that these radionuclides are concentrated to a considerable extent in this waste. This is confirmed by the average value, which for ^{238}U and ^{226}Ra is about 12 and 9 times higher, respectively, in the Pb-Ag precipitate compared to the one measured for these radionuclides in the initial raw material [5]. The other analyzed radionuclides in the waste Pb-Ag precipitate had similar values as the starting raw material, so the leaching process had no effect on their concentration in this waste.

Table 3 Obtained values of radium equivalent index (R_{eq}), gamma index (I_γ), absorbed gamma dose rate (D), annual effective dose (E) and excess lifetime cancer risk ($ELCR$) for workers in the leaching plant for exposure Pb-Ag precipitates.

Sample ID	R_{eq} (Bq kg ⁻¹)	I_γ	D (nGy h ⁻¹)	E (μSv y ⁻¹)	$ELCR \times 10^{-3}$
PBAG1	67.4	0.23	31.2	38.2	0.13
PBAG2	64.6	0.22	29.9	36.7	0.13
PBAG3	51.4	0.18	23.8	29.2	0.10
PBAG4	63.1	0.22	29.2	35.8	0.13
PBAG5	69.6	0.24	32.2	39.5	0.14
PBAG6	58.4	0.20	27.1	33.3	0.12
PBAG7	56.9	0.20	26.4	32.3	0.11
PBAG8	50.4	0.17	23.3	28.6	0.10
PBAG9	48.5	0.17	22.4	27.5	0.10
PBAG10	57.9	0.20	26.9	33.0	0.12
Range	48.5-69.5	0.17-0.24	22.4-32.2	27.5-39.5	0.10-0.14
Average±SD	58.8±6.9	0.202±0.024	27.3±3.2	33.4±3.9	0.117±0.014
Permissible or average value	< 370 ^a	< 1 ^b	59 ^c	< 1000 ^d	0.29 ^c

SD= standard deviation. ^aRecommended value given in Ref. [18]; ^bRecommended value given in Ref. [17]; ^cWorldwide average given in Ref. [17]; ^dRecommended value given in Ref. [19].

Obtained values of radium equivalent index (R_{eq}), gamma index (I_γ), strength of absorbed dose of gamma radiation (D), annual effective dose (E) and lifetime cancer risk ($ELCR$) for workers who worked in the leach plant with the analyzed precipitate are shown in Table 3.

The values of the radium equivalent index (R_{eq}) range from 48.5-69.5 Bq kg⁻¹, that is, for all analyzed samples it is below the recommended 370 Bq kg⁻¹ [18]. The gamma index values for the analyzed samples are in the range of 0.17-0.24 and are far lower than 1 [19] for all Pb-Ag precipitate samples.

The absorbed gamma dose rate (D) values range from 22.4–32.2 nGy h⁻¹. The average value is 27.3±3.2 nGy h⁻¹ and is about 2 times lower than the world average, 59 nGy h⁻¹ [17]. The obtained values of annual effective doses (E) are far lower than the recommended 1 mSv y⁻¹ [19] for all samples and range from 27.5-39.5 μSv y⁻¹ with an average value of 33.4±3.9 μSv y⁻¹. The values of excess lifetime cancer risk ($ELCR$) when working with this waste are far lower than the average value of 0.29×10^{-3} [17] and range from $(0.10-0.14) \times 10^{-3}$ with an average value of $(0.117 \pm 0.014) \times 10^{-3}$, Table 3.

All obtained values (R_{eq} , I_γ , D , E and $ELCR$) are lower compared to those estimated for exposure to waste EMCO precipitate and pyrite ash in the same factory in our previous research [5], which can also be said for e.g. copper tailings from a Turkish mine [30]. The values of absorbed dose rate (D) and annual effective dose (E) are significantly lower than those obtained for soil near a thermal power plant in India [20] as well as for tin ore tailings and soil from Malaysia (which can also be said for $ELCR$ values for samples from this country) [31].

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the measured values of the activity concentrations of natural radionuclides (^{238}U , ^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{40}K) as well as the artificial radionuclide ^{137}Cs , it was established that waste Pb-Ag precipitate deposited without adequate protection measures does not cause additional soil contamination with these radionuclides. It was found that the activity concentrations of ^{238}U and ^{226}Ra are around the average for soil, while the activity concentrations of ^{232}Th , ^{40}K are far below the average values. The activity concentrations of ^{137}Cs are far below the values measured in soil. All activity concentration values of natural radionuclides are comparable to values for other waste materials from the mining and chemical industries. It was concluded that ^{238}U and ^{226}Ra are concentrated in this waste to a considerable extent if their activity concentrations in the starting raw material (zinc sulfide concentrate) measured in our previous research [5] are taken.

Based on the estimated values of the hazard index, it was concluded that all values are below the recommended or average values in the world. It is concluded that the annual effective doses to which the workers were exposed during the removal of this waste from the leaching facility were far below the recommended 1 mSv, and there was no significant risk of excessive exposure to gamma radiation from this waste. This is also in favor because the values of excess lifetime cancer risk are below the average value.

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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF FARMER EDUCATION IN MANAGING AGRICULTURAL WASTE IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

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Abstract: Agricultural waste arises as a result of activities in agriculture. The management of agricultural waste requires primarily raising awareness and continuous education of farmers to reduce its quantity and negative impact on the environment and human health. A significant portion of the waste from agricultural activities could be utilized, but due to insufficient knowledge among farmers and the absence of incentivizing measures, it remains unused. Education of farmers on proper handling of agricultural waste is precisely the key element to overcoming the problem. This paper provides an overview of specific examples of agricultural waste management in Serbia, a review of forms of farmer education, and measures that are systematically implemented to address issues related to waste generated in agriculture.

Key words: education, farmers, agricultural waste, Republic of Serbia, management

1. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural waste is generated daily in agricultural activities. It cannot be precisely defined, but generally includes: machinery waste, plastic (e.g. containers and cups for seedling production), plastic packaging (from pesticides, mineral fertilizers, etc.), veterinary products, construction waste, cardboard and paper, metal, wood, glass, tires, ash, animal waste, and crop residues [1].

It is estimated that agricultural waste accounts for 0.7 billion tons of the total 1.3 billion tons of waste worldwide. This waste represents a potential raw material for new products such as those in the food and pharmaceutical industries, compost, and organic fertilizers [2].

A particular challenge in agricultural waste management is the insufficient level of knowledge among farmers regarding proper handling of crop residues, manure, packaging waste, waste from agricultural machinery, dead animals, veterinary products, and similar items.

2. HANDLING AGRICULTURAL WASTE

The current handling of agricultural waste in the Republic of Serbia can be assessed as inadequate, as a significant portion of waste materials is either discarded by farmers or used in an inappropriate manner, posing risks to both people's health and the environment.

2.1. Handling of Biomass

Biomass in the agricultural sector consists of secondary or tertiary products from agriculture (such as wheat straw, soybean, barley, rye, cornstalks, sunflower stalks, etc.). Agricultural biomass has significant energy potential, determining its long-term sustainability, which also takes into account competitiveness effects in food production. It has a substantial impact on biodiversity and carbon dioxide emissions during combustion. For these reasons, the use of biomass must be considered throughout its entire life cycle, from biomass production through logistics to final use [3].

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Among agricultural producers, it is a common practice to plow the majority of biomass back into the soil. They believe that this practice helps rejuvenate the soil by replenishing mineral substances, preparing it for a new season and planting period. In livestock farming, biomass is often applied as bedding for animals. However, the prevailing practice indicates that a significant number of agricultural producers tend to burn crop residues on their fields, leading to environmental pollution. This burning of biomass is an irrational use which simultaneously violates laws that prohibit the burning of biomass on agricultural plots [4].

2.1.1. Handling of Manure

Manure represents the oldest and most commonly used organic fertilizer. It contains numerous macro and microelements, making it the most complete organic fertilizer essential for modern agriculture. In organic production, it is sometimes the only fertilizer used. Solid manure is a mixture of liquid and solid excreta from domestic animals and bedding residues. If domestic animals are kept without bedding, liquid manure is obtained.

Liquid manure is an important source of energy, as it can be used to generate heat, electricity, fuel, and more. The use of energy derived from liquid manure contributes to greater environmental protection by reducing emissions of sulfur dioxide, carbon dioxide, and nitrogen dioxide compared to the combustion of fossil fuels. However, in Serbia, the processes of collection, treatment, preparation, and more intensive use of liquid manure for energy purposes have not seen widespread adoption, mainly due to extensive production practices and significant financial investments [5].

2.2. Handling of Packaging Waste

Dominant packaging waste in agriculture includes:

- Plastic packaging waste (packaging for liquid plant protection products; cups, pots, seedling containers; foils; bags; crates; boxes, etc.),
- Paper and cardboard packaging waste (for animal feed; transport boxes – e.g. for eggs, day-old broiler chicks, and day-old laying hens; labels, instructions for use, etc.)
- Other packaging waste (textile; wooden pallets and crates, etc.).

The majority of this packaging waste ends up in mixed household waste or is incinerated.

2.3. Handling of Veterinary Waste

Veterinary waste on agricultural farms arises as a result of specific veterinary procedures. According to the Regulation on the conditions and methods of sorting, packaging, and storing secondary raw materials, it is classified in group 18 02 – waste from the diagnosis, treatment, or prevention of animal diseases [6].

It poses a risk to health and the environment as it leads to infections, injuries, poisoning, and environmental pollution, particularly of soil and groundwater. The existing practice of managing veterinary waste on agricultural farms is currently at a low level. Waste is often disposed of together with other types of household waste. It is common for it to be inadequately burned without control and supervision, or it is disposed of without prior treatment along with other waste in landfills, released into sewage systems, and septic tanks. Some farmers bury dead animals in their own yards.

2.4. Handling of Agricultural Machinery Waste

Waste from agricultural machinery includes liquid waste (used oil, antifreeze), parts (tires, batteries, metal and non-metal parts, etc.), and associated waste materials (wastewater from machinery washing, workshop waste, packaging, etc.). Most of these materials have value as secondary resources – both energy and raw materials, but some of them also fall into the category of hazardous substances [7]. Proper treatment of these materials is crucial for reducing negative impacts on the environment.

Used oils contain a certain percentage of toxic and carcinogenic substances, making them hazardous waste that adversely affects living organisms in water and soil. Improper combustion of used oil, a popular alternative fuel, produces exhaust gases with an extremely unfavorable composition. Used antifreeze, in addition to ethylene glycol, may contain traces of heavy metals and other substances, making it hazardous waste. If ingested, antifreeze is poisonous (affecting the central nervous system), and if it enters sewage, soil, or water, it can be lethal to plant and animal life. While tires do not belong to the hazardous waste group, their shape and dimensions require a lot of space for disposal. Water retention is possible in tires, providing a favorable environment for the development of unwanted insects (e.g., mosquitoes). However, accumulated tires can also pose a potential fire hazard. There is a practice of using waste tires as solid fuel, where in an uncontrolled combustion process, dense black smoke containing partially burned hydrocarbons is produced, negatively impacting air quality. During combustion, harmful and dangerous pyrolytic oils can also be formed [8].

3. FARMER EDUCATION IN AGRICULTURAL WASTE MANAGEMENT

Organized education of farmers in agricultural waste management is of great importance to reduce the amount of waste and, consequently, the harmful impacts on human health and the environment. Education must be conducted continuously through the joint participation of relevant ministries (environmental protection and agriculture), agricultural advisory services, local authorities, educational institutions, non-governmental organizations, and the media.

3.1. Training Farmers for Organized Collection of Pesticide Packaging

Regulations on the types of packaging for pesticides and fertilizers, as well as the disposal of pesticides and fertilizers, prescribe the types of packaging for pesticides and fertilizers for their packaging and placement on the market, the disposal of pesticides that have exceeded their expiration date, and the disposal of packaging in which pesticides and fertilizers were packaged [9].

Farmers should know the following:

- Collection and disposal of empty packaging must not be done by throwing it into water sources (springs, wells, rivers, lakes, ponds, and the sea), pits, canals, sewer systems, along roads, landfills, or in any other way that could lead to environmental pollution.
- The collection and disposal of empty packaging (cardboard boxes and foils) by the end user can be done by burning in a specially excavated pit on non-agricultural land.
- The collection of empty plastic and metal packaging (bottles, canisters, and barrels), as well as glass bottles, by the end user (individual farmers) is done by returning them to agricultural pharmacies. For agricultural farms, the disposal is done by submitting them to regional collection centers for destruction.
- Empty packaging must retain the existing label to determine the origin of the pesticide packaging.

- The end user, before returning the packaging, is obliged to rinse the packaging in which the pesticide was packed at least three times during pesticide application, and the rinsed liquid must be used together with the prepared solution for treatment (Figure 1).
- Empty packaging must be punctured (except for glass) in three places to make it unusable for other purposes. The packaging is returned together with the closing system (cap).
- The return of empty packaging is done twice a year (June-July and November-December).

Figure 1 Handling pesticide packaging [10]

ENVIPACK Ltd. is a specialized operator with an integrated permit for the collection and transportation of hazardous and non-hazardous waste, established by Galenika Fitofarmacija a.d. The primary goal of ENVIPACK is to establish a system for collecting and disposing of waste packaging from plant protection products in the territory of the Republic of Serbia. One of its activities is to educate owners of waste packaging, conduct inspections, control and transport collected packaging waste, organize media campaigns, and promotions related to the collection, proper treatment, and sorting of generated hazardous and non-hazardous packaging waste from plant protection products and other chemical articles.

As an example of good practice in the organized collection of this type of packaging waste, the association SECPA stands out – a voluntary and non-profit organization that has developed the SECPA ECO MODEL for its users. In the development of the packaging waste disposal system, SECPA utilized the knowledge, experience, written materials of the European association CropLife Europe (formerly ECPA), as well as a study prepared for these purposes by the City Institute of Public Health in Belgrade. SECPA provides a leaflet with clear instructions for users, as well as an online form for submitting requests for the collection of packaging [11].

Successful collection campaigns of this waste from farmers have been carried out in recent years in the territory of Vojvodina, municipalities of Šid, Sombor, and Sremska Mitrovica.

3.2. Educating Farmers on Proper Handling of Crop Residues

Burning crop residues remains a dominant and illegal method of their removal from fields. According to data from the Ministry of Environmental Protection, in 2022, there were 15,000

fires caused by open burning. In order to overcome the negative effects of such handling of crop residues on human health, safety, and the environment, a national campaign 'Don't Burn the Straw' was launched in September 2023. The campaign involved the Ministry of Environmental Protection, the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, and the Ministry of Construction, Transport, and Infrastructure, with the support of the European Union and the United Nations Development Programme – UNDP [12]. The campaign received media coverage, and since 2018, educational video materials highlighting the harmful effects of burning crop residues have been available on the Ministry of Environmental Protection's website.

4. CONCLUSION

The practice of managing agricultural waste in the Republic of Serbia is not satisfactory because a significant portion of this waste possesses raw material and energy potential that farmers do not recognize. This waste is often deposited with mixed household waste, burned in open areas, or ends up on others' fields, in forests, watercourses, or sewage. To change this unfavorable practice, it is necessary, first and foremost, to educate farmers through organized campaigns and actions at the national level. The goal of education is to help farmers understand the harmfulness and consequences of inadequate handling of agricultural waste on their health and safety, as well as the negative impact on the environment. The process itself takes time, must be continuous, and supported by the media.

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THE NEW LAW ON OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY AND HEALTH AT WORK

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Abstract: At the end of April 2023, the new Law on Occupational Safety and Health at Work was adopted ("Official Gazette of RS", No. 35/23). Significant changes were made in it in relation to the then valid Law on Occupational Safety and Health at Work ("Official Gazette of RS", No. 101/05, 91/15, 113/17 - other law). The Higher Education Technical School of Professional Studies in Novi Sad, within its study programs, has a certain number of teaching subjects that deal with various aspects of safety and health at work. The School has also helpfully completed a large number of acts on risk assessment, organizes conferences where topics from this field are discussed, and for fifteen years has been conducting preparatory classes for taking a professional exam in occupational safety and health. These are the reasons why the employees of this institution are very interested in the novelties brought by the new Law.

Key words: work at height, depth, from home, remotely; associate and adviser for safety and health at work; register of injuries at work; license register

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of the process of harmonization of the regulations of the Republic of Serbia with the legislation of the European Union, in the field of health safety at work the greatest progress has been made in relation to other areas of protection - environmental protection, fire protection, disaster risk reduction and emergency management. Regulations have been passed, their implementation on the ground, at least in a formal sense, is ubiquitous. However, it was the application of these regulations that pointed out their shortcomings through user reactions, as well as through statistics on injuries and fatalities at work. New challenges have also appeared, such as the increasingly widespread work from home and remote work (freelance [1], the pandemic caused by the SARS CoV 2 virus). The stated factors were the reason for the new Law on Occupational Safety and Health at Work [2] to replace the old one [3]. The paper will highlight the differences (news) compared to the old Law on Occupational Safety and Health at Work [3].

In the old law, it was stated only where the law does not apply, and now it is clearly stated where this law applies: to state bodies, bodies of autonomous provinces, bodies of local self-government units, companies, other legal and natural persons, in all activities. The rights, obligations and responsibilities related to safety and health at work, determined by this law, are regulated in more detail by the collective agreement, the rulebook on safety and health at work or the work rulebook (now specific general acts of the employer are listed), i.e. the employment contract. The concept of prevention is defined in more detail and more comprehensively than before, so it is the basic principle of safety and health at work, the goals of which are: development and strengthening of mechanisms to prevent the occurrence of injuries at work, occupational and work-related diseases and create conditions for continuous improvement of the field safety and health at work, which includes culture, policy, activities and measures [2].

Certain terms appear for the first time, or are concisely defined for the first time. A self-employed person is a natural person who performs an economic or other activity, such as: an entrepreneur who independently performs an economic or other activity and does not employ other persons; or the holder or member of a family agricultural holding, who performs work with members of the family agricultural

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household in accordance with the regulations on agriculture.

A workshop is an open-air space where work is carried out in accordance with the elaboration on the arrangement and execution of works, in accordance with the regulations on safety and health at work. Work in depth is work in excavations deeper than one meter or embankments higher than one meter. Work at a height is any work that an employee performs using supports at a height of two meters or more from a solid surface, where the work area is not protected from falling from a height. In the old Law [3], means and equipment for personal protection at work were defined, but now they do not appear among the defined terms, and in the further text of the Law [2], the term personal protective equipment is used. Harm is a feature or characteristic that can endanger the health of an employee. A serious, unavoidable and immediate danger is a concrete, real and existing danger which, in accordance with current scientific and technical knowledge, cannot be excluded or limited. Working from home is work that the employee performs using information and communication technologies for the employer from the place of living, i.e. staying or other place of residence, which is not under the direct control of the employer. Remote work is work that the employee performs using information and communication technologies from a space that is not the employer's space and that is not under the direct control of the employer.

An occupational safety and health advisor is a professional person who performs occupational safety and health tasks, has the appropriate level of qualifications, passed an appropriate professional exam, is licensed to perform the tasks of an occupational safety and health advisor, and is appointed by the employer to perform these tasks in a written act. Occupational health and safety associate is a professional person who performs occupational health and safety tasks in activities that are not reserved for a advisor, or independent performance by the employer, according to the Law [2], has the appropriate level of qualifications, passed the appropriate professional exam, license for the performance of the duties of an associate for safety and health at work and whom the employer appoints in writing to perform those duties. A legal entity for the performance of inspection and check of work equipment and inspection and testing of electrical and lightning protection installations (electrical and lightning protection installations were not covered by the old Law), testing of working environment conditions, i.e. chemical and physical hazards (except ionizing radiation), microclimate and lighting, examination of working environment conditions - biological hazards (now separated from chemical and physical hazards) is a legal entity to which the minister responsible for labor issues issued a license, in accordance with this law. A legal entity or entrepreneur for the performance of occupational health and safety activities is a legal entity or entrepreneur to whom the minister responsible for labor issues has issued a license, in accordance with this law. A health institution that performs occupational medicine is a health care provider, to which the employer entrusts the performance of prevention and health protection of employees, in accordance with the law. The responsible person for performing inspections and checks of work equipment and inspections and tests of electrical and lightning protection installations, tests of working environment conditions, i.e. chemical and physical hazards (except ionizing radiation), microclimate and lighting, and testing of working environment conditions - biological hazards, as well as for signing expert findings, is a person with a license to perform these tasks.

The register of work injuries is a unique, electronically managed database of work injuries, which is maintained on the basis of work injury reports. The license register is a unique, electronically managed database of issued, renewed and revoked licenses in accordance with this law. According to the new Law [2], persons who are self-employed, volunteer, perform temporary and occasional jobs through youth or student cooperatives, participate in organized public works of general importance, have the right to safety and health at work, as well as all those who also had under the old Law [3] - employed or engaged outside of employment, students on internship or dual education, persons undergoing professional training, prisoners in economic units of prisons, persons who find themselves in the working environment with the knowledge of the employer.

2. OBLIGATIONS AND RESPONSIBILITIES OF THE EMPLOYER

A legal entity with a license to carry out inspections and checks of work equipment, inspections and tests of installations and working environment conditions is obliged to issue a professional report after the inspection/check/testing, no later than 30 days from the day of the performed inspection and check, i.e. testing. If it is determined that measures for safe and healthy work have not been applied to the work equipment, the person who performed the inspection and check immediately informs the employer, i.e. the advisor or associate for safety and health at work, and places a sticker on the equipment about the malfunction. The employer, that is, the advisor or associate for safety and health at work, immediately prohibits work on the equipment until the irregularities are eliminated [2].

The employer's duty is to provide first aid, to train the appropriate number of employees to provide first aid and to provide means and equipment for first aid, taking into account all relevant parameters. First aid must be available to every employee during working hours, in all shifts and in all locations. The training of employees to provide first aid is carried out by a health institution that performs occupational medicine in accordance with the law regulating health care, as well as by the Serbian Red Cross, in accordance with a special law. The method of providing first aid, the types of means and equipment that must be provided at the workplace, the number of employees who must be trained to provide first aid, the method and deadlines for employee training are mutually prescribed by the minister responsible for labor affairs and the minister responsible for health affairs [2].

The employer is obliged to: inform employees about serious, unavoidable and immediate danger, accompanying risks and measures aimed at protection; issues instructions on stopping work and/or immediately leaving the workplace and going to a safe place; does not require employees to return to the workplace in a work environment where there is still a serious, unavoidable and imminent danger [2].

Before starting the activity, the employer is obliged to submit a request to the competent labor inspection, to determine the fulfillment of the prescribed conditions in the field of safety and health at work, and cannot start the activity without obtaining a decision on the fulfillment of the conditions for starting work. The activities for which it is necessary to determine the fulfillment of the prescribed conditions are: activities of production, traffic, distribution, processing, disposal and storage of: dangerous, harmful and waste materials; oil and oil derivatives; poisons, chemical production activities; adhesives; solvents; the colors; means for disinfection, disinsection and rodent control and raw hide; social protection services, namely: home accommodation for adults and the elderly, home accommodation for children and young people, day care, small home community, shelter and drop-in center [2].

In the event of emergency works being carried out on infrastructural facilities for the purpose of eliminating defects or a sudden and uncontrolled event on the facility, the employer is obliged to report the emergency works to the competent labor inspectorate immediately, from the moment of occurrence, orally and in writing (it can also be done electronically), as well as to when performing emergency works and rehabilitation, it applies measures in accordance with the act on risk assessment [2].

The employer is obliged, before starting work at height, in depth, in a confined space, in a space with potentially explosive atmospheres, on an energy facility, when using dangerous chemical substances, for work in zones where there is a serious, unavoidable or immediate danger or harm that may endanger the health of the employee, ensure the issuance of a work permit. Previously, the employer is obliged to determine the procedure and method for issuing a work permit [2].

According to the Law [3], the training and verification of employees' training for safe and healthy work is carried out by the employer theoretically and practically, at the workplace, in accordance with the training program for safe and healthy work brought by the employer, in a language that the employee understands and adapts to the possibilities and abilities of special groups of employees. The law [2] additionally mandates that the training program for safe and healthy work contains a general and a specific part. The general part of the training program includes familiarizing employees with the rights, obligations and responsibilities in the field of occupational safety and health from Law and by-laws, as

well as familiarization with the employer's general acts in the field of occupational safety and health. A special part of the training program includes familiarization with all potential hazards and harms in the workplace, assessed risks and measures for safe and healthy work. Both Laws stipulate that periodic training for safe and healthy work of an employee working in a workplace with increased risk is carried out within one year from the date of the previous training at the latest, and in other workplaces within at the latest three years (according to the old Law four years) from the day of the previous training. The employee representative has the right to training in order to perform the activities of the employee representative, and the training costs cannot be borne by him.

Training of employee representatives is carried out immediately upon selection or appointment, and periodic training is carried out no later than three years from the date of the previous training and is organized during working hours either within or outside the employer's premises [2]. In case of serious injury at work, fatal injury at work or collective injury at work with serious or fatal injury at work, the employer is obliged to immediately, and at the latest within eight days from the occurrence of the injury, carry out additional training of the employees in that workplace in the organizational unit where the injury occurred, with the obligation to notify all employees [2].

3. RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS OF EMPLOYEES AND SELF-EMPLOYED PERSONS

The employer is obliged to ensure that all employees are trained to take appropriate steps in accordance with their knowledge and technical means, which are available to them in the event of a serious, unavoidable and immediate danger to their safety and/or the safety of others and in the event that the immediate supervisor, who is responsible, is not present, in order to avoid the consequences of the danger. The employee is obliged to take care of his own safety and health at work, as well as the safety and health of other persons who may be affected by his work in accordance with the training for safe and healthy work and the instructions for safe and healthy work received from the employer. A self-employed person is responsible for his own safety and health and for the safety and health of other persons, who are affected by his work and failures in the application of safety and health measures at work. A self-employed person is obliged to apply the regulations in the field of safety and health at work and to cooperate with other employers and employees in the implementation of safety and health measures at work, when the performance of work is related to them [2].

4. WORK FROM HOME AND REMOTE WORK

When working from home and working remotely, the employer is obliged to ensure safety and health at work in cooperation with the employee, whereby the employer is obliged to determine the conditions for safe and healthy work, means of work issued by the employer, to define the work process in connection with the execution of tasks for which the employee is in charge and prescribes preventive measures for safe and healthy work. The employer can issue an act on risk assessment for working from home and remote work in written form with the participation of the employee. The employee is obliged to inform the employer about the fulfillment of the conditions required for safe and healthy work in accordance with the act on risk assessment, as well as to inform the employer in a timely manner about any subsequent change in conditions [2].

5. ORGANIZING SAFETY AND HEALTH AT WORK

For the performance of safety and health at work, the employer is obliged to hire one or more persons with whom he has concluded an employment contract, and who fulfills special conditions in accordance with the Law [2]. They are the adviser, that is, the associate for safety and health at work, i.e. a person who has passed an occupational health and safety examination and a license to perform the duties of an advisor, i.e. associate (in Law [3] it was a person for occupational safety and health, who had to have passed an occupational examination, but it was not issued a license). If, for occupational health and safety matters, he cannot designate one of his employees who meets the requirements for an advisor, that is, an associate, the employer, exceptionally (which means that it is not recommended, while the Law [3] did not emphasize this), can hire a legal entity or entrepreneurs who have a license to perform safety and health at work.

In activities that, according to the Law [2], provide for an adviser, the employer who employs, that is, hires from 251 to 500 employees, is obliged to conclude a full-time employment contract with at least two advisers for safety and health at work, and for more than 500 employees is required to conclude a full-time employment contract with at least three occupational health and safety advisers. In all other activities, an employer who employs more than 500 employees is obliged to conclude a full-time employment contract with at least two occupational health and safety associates. If the employer hires a legal entity or an entrepreneur who has a license to perform occupational health and safety activities, that legal entity or entrepreneur determines the number of occupational health and safety advisers in accordance with the criteria for activities for which an adviser is required.

The employer can perform occupational health and safety tasks on his own in the activities of retail trade, accommodation and food services, informing and communication, financial and insurance activities, real estate business, professional, scientific, innovation, administrative and auxiliary service activities, activities of mandatory social insurance, education, art, entertainment and recreation, other service activities, if there are up to 20 employees. In this case, he is required to take a professional exam (he was not required to do so until now) for the performance of occupational safety and health duties prescribed by the minister responsible for labor affairs, and he is not required to have a prescribed license. An alternative is to hire a advisor [2].

Employer in the activities of construction, agriculture, forestry and fishing, mining, processing industry, supply of electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning (except trade in electricity and gaseous fuels through the gas network), water supply, waste water management, control of waste removal processes, wholesale trade, transport and storage and similar activities, as well as in health and social protection activities, is obliged to appoint an adviser for occupational safety and health, i.e. a person with a higher education of at least 240 ESPB points on academic or professional studies within the educational-scientific field of technical-technological sciences and natural-mathematical sciences from the areas of: biological sciences, environmental sciences, physical sciences, physical-chemical and chemical sciences. An employer in health and social care activities can hire a person who has a higher education of at least 240 ECTS points in academic or professional studies within the educational-scientific field of medical sciences [2]. Until now, these tasks were performed by the person for occupational safety and health with at least 180 ESPB [3], from the same type and field of acquired higher education as in the Law [2].

In activities that are neither reserved for an advisor nor performed independently by the employer, according to the Law [2], the employer is obliged to appoint an associate for safety and health at work, i.e. a person with a higher education level of at least 180 ESPB points within the educational-scientific field of technical-technological sciences, natural-mathematical sciences, medical sciences or social-humanities.

The advisor, that is, the associate for safety and health at work performs tasks in accordance with the Law [2]. The employer is obliged to enable continuous improvement of knowledge in the field of safety and health at work to the employee whom he appoints to perform these tasks. Continuous improvement of the knowledge of occupational safety and health advisers, occupational safety and health associates, occupational safety and health coordinators in the project development phase, occupational safety and health coordinators in the construction phase, the person responsible for the inspection and checking work equipment and inspecting and testing electrical and lightning protection installations, the person responsible for performing the work of testing the conditions of the working environment, i.e. chemical and physical hazards (except for ionizing radiation), microclimate and lighting, and the person responsible for performing the work of testing the conditions of the working environment - biological hazards, is a requirement for license renewal. The employer is obliged to provide the listed persons with paid leave for the continuous improvement of knowledge, in order to renew the license, in accordance with the Law.

An employer who hires a legal entity or an entrepreneur with a license to carry out safety and health at work is obliged to familiarize them beforehand with the work process, the risks in the work process

and the measures that have been applied to eliminate the risks, inform them about the start of work of each separate unit, about the start execution of works on the construction site, that is, the workshop and the hiring of each new employee.

6. HEALTH PROTECTION AT WORK

Health protection at work is a new special chapter in the Law [2]. Previously, the employer was obliged to provide an employee at a workplace with an increased risk before starting work with a previous medical examination, as well as a periodic medical examination during work [3]. The new thing is that the employer is now obliged to provide the employee who works at night, in accordance with the law, with a preliminary and periodic medical examination. In the text of the Law [2], targeted medical examinations are now mentioned for the first time, which have long been introduced as a preventive measure when working with carcinogens and mutagens in workplaces that are not determined by the risk assessment act as workplaces with increased risk [4]. It was decisively stated that the costs of medical examinations are borne by the employer [2].

7. PROFESSIONAL EXAMINATION AND ISSUANCE OF LICENSES

In order to perform the duties of an adviser, that is, an associate for safety and health at work and the duties of a responsible person, a corresponding professional exam is taken [5]. In order to perform the duties of occupational safety and health coordinator in the project development phase and occupational safety and health coordinator in the construction phase, preparation is organized and a corresponding professional exam is taken [6].

The minister responsible for labor affairs for the performance of appropriate safety and health at work tasks issues or renews a license [2], [7], namely:

- 1) occupational safety and health advisor (new, as a natural person);
- 2) associate for safety and health at work (new, as a natural person);
- 3) coordinator for safety and health at work in the project development phase (new, as a natural person);
- 4) to the coordinator for safety and health at work in the construction phase (new, as a natural person);
- 5) to the person responsible for the inspection and check of work equipment and inspection and testing of electrical and lightning protection installations (it was there before, it was of a permanent nature, as a natural person);
- 6) to the person responsible for performing the work of testing the conditions of the working environment, i.e. chemical and physical hazards (except for ionizing radiation), microclimate and lighting (it was there before, it was of a permanent nature, as a natural person);
- 7) to the person responsible for performing the work of testing the conditions of the working environment - biological hazards (it was there before, it was of a permanent nature, as a natural person);
- 8) to a legal entity or entrepreneur for the performance of safety and health at work tasks (it was there before, as a legal entity);
- 9) a legal entity for the performance of inspection and check of work equipment and inspection and testing of electrical and lightning protection installations (it was there before, as a legal entity);
- 10) to a legal entity for the performance of testing the conditions of the working environment, i.e. chemical and physical hazards (except for ionizing radiation), microclimate and lighting (it was there before, as a legal entity);
- 11) to a legal entity for the performance of testing the conditions of the working environment - biological hazards (it was there before, as a legal entity).

The request for issuing and renewing the license from 1) to 4) is submitted to the Labor Inspectorate, in order to determine the fulfillment of the conditions for issuing the license. The Labor Inspectorate supervises the work of natural persons with a license and prepares proposed solutions for issuing, renewing and revoking licenses from 1) to 4), which it keeps records of. The request for issuing and renewing the license from 5) to 11) is submitted to the Occupational Safety and Health Administration. Licenses from 1) to 11) are issued by the minister responsible for labor affairs with a validity period of five years. Licenses from 1) to 7) can be issued, i.e. renewed to the applicant, if the license issued in accordance with the Law [2] has not been revoked in the previous five years and if he has not been convicted by a final court decision of criminal offenses for not taking safety measures at work, causing danger by not providing safety measures at work, illegally and irregularly performing construction works and engaging in a certain activity without authorization, i.e. not having been imposed a safety measure in accordance with the Criminal Code by a legally binding court decision, namely: prohibition of professional engagement, activities and duties due to which he cannot perform tasks in the field of safety and health at work. The person from 1) to 7) together with the request for renewal of the license, also submits proof of continuous improvement of knowledge in accordance with the Law [2] and the regulations adopted for its implementation. A person who has been convicted of a criminal offense by a final court decision or who has been given a safety measure in accordance with the Criminal Code, is required to retake the appropriate professional exam. Licenses from 8) to 11) can be issued, i.e. renewed, to the applicant, if he meets the prescribed conditions in terms of premises and technical equipment for the performance of activities and if the founder or a person related to him in terms of regulations on business companies, a license issued in accordance with the Law [2] has not been revoked in the previous five years (previously it was three years).

A legal entity, an entrepreneur and a natural person whose license was revoked by the decision of the minister in charge of labor affairs can re-submit a request for the issuance of a license after five years from the date of revocation of the license. The Ministry responsible for labor affairs publishes on its website a list of legal and natural persons to whom licenses for performing work in the field of safety and health at work have been issued, revoked or have ceased to be valid [2].

8. VALIDITY OF PASSED PROFESSIONAL EXAMINATION AND ISSUED LICENSE

The professional exam for the performance of occupational health and safety duties and the duties of a responsible person and the professional exam for the performance of the duties of an occupational safety and health coordinator in the project development phase and an occupational safety and health coordinator in the construction phase were passed before the entry into force of the Act [2] effective, remains valid. A natural person who submits an application for the issuance of a corresponding license for the first time in accordance with the Law [2] is not required to provide evidence of continuous improvement of knowledge, or other appropriate evidence.

A person who performed safety and health at work for at least three years prior to the entry into force of the Law [2], and who does not meet the requirements established for a advisor, i.e. associate, may continue to perform these tasks upon obtaining an appropriate license depending on the activity in for which he performed safety and health at work duties.

A person who performed occupational health and safety duties less than three years before the entry into force of the Law [2], and who does not meet the conditions established for an advisor, i.e. associate, may continue to perform those duties until the conditions established by the Law [2] are met, and a maximum of five years, except for a person who has a maximum of five years remaining before fulfilling the conditions for acquiring the right to an old-age pension according to the regulations on pension and disability insurance.

Licenses issued to legal entities and entrepreneurs for the performance of work in the field of safety and health at work, according to the provisions of the Law on Amendments to the Law on Safety and Health at Work, are valid until the expiration of the term for which they were issued.

Persons responsible for the inspection and check of work equipment and examination of working environment conditions to whom the license was issued five or more years ago are required to submit a

request for license renewal in accordance with the Law [2] without delay, and within 90 days at the latest from the date of entry into force of this law, and the persons responsible for the inspection and check of work equipment and examination of the conditions of the working environment, where five years have not passed since the issuance of the license, are required to submit a request for renewal of the license in accordance with this law no later than 60 days before five years have passed since the license was issued.

Employers are obliged to organize their operations in accordance with this law within two years from the date of entry into force of this law (deadline May 2025).

9. CONCLUSION

The paper deals with the reasons that led to the adoption of a completely new Law on Occupational Safety and Health. Then the terms that appear for the first time in the law are defined: self-employed person, workshop, work at depth and height, work from home and remote work, advisor and associate for occupational health and safety, register of work injuries and register of licenses. Below are the innovations and comparisons with previous solutions, if there were any, related to the employer's obligations and responsibilities, the rights and obligations of employees and self-employed persons, working from home and remotely, organizing safety and health at work, on health protection at work, professional exams and issuing licenses, as well as on the validity of previously passed professional exams and issued licenses.

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ACTIVITY CONCENTRATION OF ^{40}K AND ^{137}Cs IN FOOD IN WESTERN SERBIA AND HEALTH IMPACT

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Abstract: The soil may contain certain concentrations of the natural radionuclide ^{40}K as well as the artificial radionuclide ^{137}Cs . As a result, during the cultivation of plants, these radionuclides may accumulate in the fruits that humans use in their diet. In this research, the activity concentrations of ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs were determined using the gamma spectrometry method for 292 food samples that were analyzed in the area of Western Serbia in the period 2010-2020. years. Food is classified into 4 groups (cereals and flour, fruit, teas, and additives). The measured values of ^{137}Cs are far below the recommended values for all types of food that were placed on the market. The measured values of both radionuclides are comparable to those measured for other foods in other studies. The health risk of food consumption was assessed in terms of annual effective doses. The obtained values indicate that all individual types of analyzed food have an estimated annual effective dose below the recommended value for food ingestion of 0.1 mSv, and it can be said that there is no significant radiation hazard or health risk from consuming the analyzed food.

Key words: Radioactivity, Food, Gamma spectrometry, Dose, Health impact.

1. INTRODUCTION

Radioactivity in the environment originates from natural radionuclides, cosmic radiation, and artificial radionuclides. The general population is exposed to natural levels of radiation, which means radiation that comes from the presence of naturally occurring radionuclides from the uranium and thorium series and ^{40}K in the soil. The largest part of the content of radionuclides, which can be found in the soil, comes from the basic substrate of the surface of the Earth's crust [1], [2]. A certain percentage of all potassium in the earth's crust consists of the natural radioactive potassium isotope ^{40}K , which leads to its presence in almost all food products [3]. In surface soil, radionuclides exist with smaller or larger variations in their activity concentrations [4], [5]. Radionuclides can be found everywhere, including food, animal feed, and drinking water in varying concentrations due to different background levels of radioactivity, climate, and agricultural conditions prevailing in a particular area. Also, the sources of internal exposure to radiation in foodstuffs are mainly due to exposure to gamma radiation from the most important radionuclides of the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th series, as well as ^{40}K [3], [4], [6], [7].

In addition to being the main source of continuous exposure of the general population to radiation, the soil is an important medium for the transfer of radionuclides to plants and animals, thus representing an indicator of radiological contamination of the environment [2], [5], [6]. Plants have the ability to absorb and transport radionuclides through mineral uptake because radionuclides have chemical and physical characteristics that are similar to minerals commonly used by plants. Radionuclides found in the environment can be transferred to different plant species through the root system or through the aerial parts of plants [2], [6]. The accumulation of radionuclides from the soil into the plant through the roots is influenced by soil properties such as pH, content of clay minerals, and organic matter. In addition, procedures such as plowing, fertilization, and irrigation for soil cultivation significantly affect the profile of uptake and distribution of radionuclides through roots in plants [6], [8].

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In modern plant production, in order to achieve optimal productivity, and therefore a high yield, it is necessary to add large amounts of chemical fertilizers, which can increase the concentration of radionuclide activity in the surface layer of the earth [6], [9]. Fertilizers compensate for the lack of macro and micronutrients in the soil necessary for plant growth. The most important elements in macronutrients are nitrogen, phosphate, and potassium. Potassium (NPK) fertilizers contain ^{40}K radionuclides. These fertilizers are successively transferred to plants and fruits, thus increasing contamination with radionuclides. The uncontrolled presence of these radionuclides in vegetables and fruits represents a potential danger to human health if their concentrations exceed the recommended levels [10]. In our previous research in chemical fertilizers, the concentration value of ^{40}K activity was measured up to 11000 Bq kg^{-1} [11], which can additionally contain the soil with this radionuclide. The measured value of activity concentration ^{40}K in soil e.g. in India ranges from $400\text{-}607 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ with an average of $479\pm 58 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ [1], while e.g. in Pakistan measured ^{40}K activity concentration in the range of $605\text{-}1087 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ with an average value of $877\pm 153 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ [12] which is almost double the value compared to the average in India. The average value of the concentration of ^{40}K activity in the world in soil is 420 Bq kg^{-1} [4].

In the food chain, plants are the primary recipients of radioactive pollution. Direct and indirect pollution of vegetation with natural or artificial radionuclides is possible. Deposition of radioactive elements from the atmosphere on parts of plants above ground is called direct contamination of vegetation. Nevertheless, the absorption of radionuclides from the soil through the root system of plants is called indirect contamination [2], [5], [6].

Anthropogenic radioisotopes can be released into the environment through releases to air or water, during normal practice or, on a larger scale, during incidents. Airborne activities can contaminate plants through dry aerosol deposition or wet deposition during rain showers. Radionuclides released in water can contaminate plants when surface water is used for irrigation [3]. Many years after nuclear weapons tests in the 1950s and 1960s, spent fuel reprocessing, weapons development, production, testing, and accidental releases from the nuclear fuel chain, as well as the 1986 Chernobyl and 2011 Fukushima accidents, some concentration of artificial radionuclide remains in ecosystems. ^{137}Cs which can also be found in food in trace amounts [3], [13] - [16]. When the concentration of activity in food products exceeds the intervention level, it is considered that the product is not suitable for human consumption and should not be placed on the market [3]. Due to these incidents, the human body is exposed to radiation in the entire food chain, i.e. plants and animals in their regions [1].

In natural environmental conditions, ^{137}Cs as an important fission product primarily enter the human body through the food chain and breathing. Due to its high radiotoxicity and relatively long half-life, ^{137}Cs is recognized as an important artificial radionuclide in terms of radiological risk assessment for the public and the environment. Consequently, ^{137}Cs concentrations in environmental and food samples are often monitored in regular radioactivity monitoring programs, especially in areas around nuclear facilities [13]. The behavior of the artificial radionuclide ^{137}Cs is similar to that of ^{40}K , so it is easily transported through many environments [6]. The measured values of ^{137}Cs in the soil in Serbia range from $<0.03\text{-}21 \text{ Bq kg}^{-1}$ [2].

The radiological safety of food and water is essential for human health and the protection of the general population from internal radiation exposure [17]. The main purpose of monitoring radioactivity in plants is to determine the natural levels of radiation to which people who directly or indirectly consume them are exposed and to detect significant changes in the level of environmental radiation. It is vital to examine the radioactivity of plant foods consumed by humans in order to determine the health impact [18]. Radioactivity in food can be incorporated either within the volume of the food or on the surface [17]. Dangers to human health arise when radionuclides are present in food, especially when they enter the human body by ingestion [6], [19]. Internal exposure to radionuclides from the environment can have harmful health effects on humans.

Radionuclides are accumulated from the soil through the roots on the edible parts of the plant and when these edible parts are taken into the human body through digestion, they contribute to the total internal dose of radiation [8]. In order to examine the radiological safety and suitability of food for humans, that is, to assess the health impact, it is necessary to monitor the radioactivity in the food consumed and use individual doses of each radionuclide to estimate the total annual effective dose for

humans [8]. For this purpose, researches were conducted in different countries in order to define the dose to which people are exposed depending on the consumption of certain food [5] - [7], [8], [14], [16]. Of the total average annual effective dose (2.4 mSv y^{-1}), 0.29 mSv y^{-1} is ingested by humans through food and water, of which it is estimated that radionuclides of the ^{238}U and ^{232}Th series contribute 0.12 mSv y^{-1} , and radionuclide ^{40}K with 0.17 mSv y^{-1} [4], from which it can be clearly concluded that this radionuclide makes the biggest contribution to the ingestion dose for humans during the year.

The aim of this work is to examine the content of natural radionuclide ^{40}K and artificial radionuclide ^{137}Cs in different food samples that were used in the area of Western Serbia in the period 2010-2020, that is, including the disaster in Fukushima in 2011. Also, the goal is to assess the health risk of food consumption during the year in terms of annual effective doses and compare it with reference values as well as values reported in other research. This work represents one of the first studies of food radioactivity in Serbia.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 292 samples of different food samples (cereals, fresh and frozen fruits, teas, additives, salt, and other foodstuffs, Table 1) were produced in the area of Western Serbia or imported via border crossings with Bosnia and Herzegovina in the period 2010 - 2020 were examined. Amalized food is classified into four groups: cereals and flour, fruit, teas, and additives. All fruit samples were produced in the area of Western Serbia.

For the purposes of measurement, the samples were transferred to sample holders (cylindrical plastic containers with dimensions of 67 mm in diameter and 62 mm in height). Samples were prepared and analyzed using the standard IAEA TRS 295 method [19]. The activity concentrations of the natural radionuclide ^{40}K and the artificial radionuclide ^{137}Cs were determined based on their gamma lines at 1,460 keV and 662 keV, respectively. Samples were measured with the gamma spectrometry method using a low-level high-purity germanium (HPGe) detector (relative efficiency of 36% energy resolution of 1.9 keV for gamma line of ^{137}Cs at 662 keV). The protection around the detector is made of 12 cm thick lead in order to minimize the influence of background radiation [20]. The acquisition and analysis of spectra were done using Canberra Genie 2000 software. The typical measurement time was 70000 s.

Data were collected and analyzed using Canberra Genie 2000 software, which calculates activity concentration values for a given radioisotope, taking into account all significant gamma lines, after subtracting the part of the spectrum originating from background radiation. The calibration of the used HPGe detector was performed using a cylindrical reference radioactive standard embedded in silicone resin, volume 250 cm^3 [20]. The integral count rate in the range between 30 and 3000 keV was about 2 counts s^{-1} . Results are presented with measurement uncertainties with 95% confidence. Within the standard uncertainty, statistical and systematic errors are included (originating predominantly from the uncertainty of determining the detector efficiency and corrections to the sample geometry) [20].

Based on the measured values of the activity concentrations of natural radionuclides ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs , the values of individual annual effective doses (E_K and E_{Cs}) as well as the total annual effective dose (E_{tot}) that a person receives annually by consuming the analyzed branch was determined.

Annual effective doses due to intake of radionuclides through food can be calculated based on the relation (1) [7], [8], [14]:

$$E = A_c \cdot I_R \cdot D_F \quad (1)$$

where E is the annual effective dose (mSv y^{-1}) for each analyzed radionuclide in food; A_c is the measured activity concentration of a certain radionuclide (Bq kg^{-1}); I_R is the food consumption rate (kg per year). Bearing in mind that there are no precise data on the consumption of analyzed foods for humans during the year, the consumption of 20 kg of cereals (wheat, corn, and soy) as well as wheat flour, 5 kg of each individual fruit (raspberry, blackberry, blueberry and cranberry, strawberry and plum), 1 kg of tea dry matter and 1 kg of additives (salt, baking soda, food colors, and other additives). D_F is the conversion factor of activity into dose for ingestion (Sv Bq^{-1}) which is $6.2 \times 10^{-9} \text{ Sv Bq}^{-1}$ for ^{40}K and $1.3 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Sv}$

Bq⁻¹ for ¹³⁷Cs [21]. According to the Rulebook in Serbia, the annual effective dose for ingestion of food is limited to 0.1 mSv y⁻¹ [22].

Table 1 – Food samples analyzed in the period from 2010-2020. in the area of Western Serbia with measured values of ⁴⁰K and ¹³⁷Cs for food during individual years.

Years	Food samples	Number of samples	Sampling location	⁴⁰ K (Bg kg ⁻¹)	¹³⁷ Cs (Bg kg ⁻¹)
2010	Wheat grain, corn grain, soybean grain, wheat flour, modified corn starch, fresh raspberry, frozen raspberry, fresh blackberry, fresh strawberry, prune, teas, baking soda, nitrite salt, sea salt, industrial salt, flavorings, mannitol powder	62	Šabac, Loznica, Debrce, Mali Zvornik, Ivanjica	<1.7-840 (62±139)	<0.10-3.30 (0.91±0.82)
2011	Wheat grain, corn grain, soybean grain, wheat flour, corn starch, frozen blackberry, frozen blueberry, frozen cranberry, frozen raspberry, frozen wild blackberry, frozen strawberry, frozen cherry, baking soda, nitrite salt, industrial salt, table salt, enzymes for juice filtration, other additives	55	Šabac, Loznica, Valjevo, Čačak, Debrce, Mali Zvornik, Osečina	<2.9-5861 (174±786)	<0.2-4.40 (1.01±0.85)
2012	Wheat grain, corn grain, soybean grain, wheat flour, frozen raspberry, frozen blackberry, frozen plum, baking soda, sea salt, industrial salt, teas, additives	26	Šabac, Debrce, Skupljen, Mali Zvornik, Osečina	<1.7-780 (105±179)	<0.22-6.20 (1.05±1.26)
2013	Wheat grain, corn grain, wheat flour, corn starch, wild blackberry, fresh blackberry, frozen blackberry, cherry, raspberry, frozen plum, frozen strawberry, industrial salt, nitrite salt, baking soda, glucose syrup	39	Šabac, Čačak, Debrce, Skupljen, Mesarci, Jevremovac, Mali Zvornik, Slepčević	<3.7-397 (58±92)	<0.25-2.40 (0.90±0.60)
2014	Modified corn starch, frozen fruit (raspberry, blackberry, blueberry, strawberry, sour cherry and plum) nitrite salt, sea salt	19	Šabac, Jevremovac, Mali Zvornik, Skupljen	<2.3-70 (33±23)	<0.30-4.5 (1.27±1.04)
2015	Modified corn starch, fresh fruit (raspberry and plum), frozen fruit (blackberry and strawberry), sugar	8	Šabac, Jevremovac, Loznica	17-62 (43±17)	<0.90-2.60 (1.71±0.60)
2016	Frozen fruit (blackberry, plum, raspberry, cherry and strawberry), nitrite salt	10	Šabac, Jevremovac, Mali Zvornik,	<7.3-1214 (156±354)	<0.8-13.0 (3.0±3.6)
2017	Frozen fruit (raspberry, cherry and strawberry), food coloring	6	Šabac, Jevremovac	42.5-1100.0 (528±486)	<1-11 (4.1±3.8)
2018	Dietary supplements, frozen fruit (strawberry, raspberry, cherry and blackberry), food coloring	23	Šabac, Jevremovac, Draginac	<9.8-906 (279±311)	<0.8-19.0 (6.27±5.27)
2019	Frozen strawberry, food coloring	25	Šabac, Jevremovac	<7.9-880 (332±274)	<0.9-18 (7.9±4.4)
2020	Fresh blueberry, food coloring	17	Šabac, Svileuva	29-828 (382±279)	<1.5-21.0 (8.2±5.0)

- range; (average ± standard deviation).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, the content of ⁴⁰K and ¹³⁷Cs was monitored over the years. The measured values of activity concentrations of ⁴⁰K and ¹³⁷Cs for the food analyzed in individual years are shown in Table 1. It can be seen that the values for ⁴⁰K depended on the type of food that was analyzed, which gave a rather wide range of values because certain foods have a higher and lower content of natural non-radioactive potassium. The values of ¹³⁷Cs were low with a slight increase in the average values observed over the years of analysis, which is purely statistical in nature because the same type of food was not analyzed over the years and the number of samples was not the same. It should be noted here that different plants absorb ¹³⁷Cs differently, and some accumulate it more and some less. Bearing in mind that the analyzed period included 2011 (the year of the accident in Fukushima), it can be seen that in that year and in the

following years there was no increase in the content of ^{137}Cs in the analyzed food samples compared to the results from 2010, that is, before the accident in Fukushima.

The measured values of ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs activity concentrations for 292 food samples classified into 4 groups are shown in Table 2. The obtained values of ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs activity concentrations for food in other studies with which the obtained values were compared are shown in Table 3.

The measured values of ^{40}K activity concentrations in cereals and flour range from (<12-641) Bq kg^{-1} with an average value of (217±190) Bq kg^{-1} . The values are comparable to the reported values for wheat, barley and oats, white bread, beef, cheese, and salt from Turkey [8], wheat from Jordan [6] as well as Cassava, Yam, and Taro flour [23]. The average value is significantly higher than those obtained for hazelnuts from Turkey [14] and fruits from India [24], Table 3.

The measured values of ^{40}K activity concentration in fruit samples are in the range of (<5.8-345) Bq kg^{-1} with an average value of (67±57) Bq kg^{-1} . The range of obtained results is significantly higher, while the average value is comparable to the value for fruits from India [24], while other foods contain significantly higher concentrations of the activity of this radionuclide, Table 3.

Table 2 – Measured values of activity concentrations of ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs with values of annual effective doses for individual radionuclides (E_K and E_{Cs}) and total annual effective dose (E_{tot}) from consumption of the mentioned food groups analyzed in the period 2010-2020.

Type of food	Number of samples	^{40}K (Bq kg^{-1})	^{137}Cs (Bq kg^{-1})	E_K (nSv y^{-1})	E_{Cs} (nSv y^{-1})	E_{tot} ($\mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$)
Cereals and flour	23	<12-641 (217±190)	<0.40-3.30 (1.48±0.68)	<1490-79490 (26916±23551)	<104-858 (306±118)	<2.35-79.7 (27.2±23.5)
Fruits	69	<5.8-345 (67±57)	<0.20-5.20 (1.27±0.94)	<180-10700 (2077±1757)	<13-338 (83±61)	<0.20-10.77 (2.16±1.76)
Teas	8	16-780 (317±322)	<0.40-2.80 (1.40±0.92)	<99.2-4836 (1966±1995)	<5.2-36.4 (18.2±11.9)	<0.11-4.87 (1.99±2.00)
Additives	192	<1.7-5861 (177±492)	<0.1-21.0 (3±4)	<11-36338 (1098±3050)	<1.3-273.0 (42±57)	<0.013-36.36 (1.14±3.07)
Total	292	<1.7-5861 (156±411)	<0.1-21.0 (2.6±3.7)	<11-79490 (3415±9987)	<1.3-858 (73±103)	<0.013-79.70 (3.5±10.0)
Recommended/average value		-	<15 ^{a*} <150 ^{a**} <600 ^{a***}	170, 000 ^b	-	100 ^c

- range; (average ± standard deviation). ^arecommended value given in Ref. [22]. (*given for fruits and cereals; **given for teas; ***given for additives with a consumption of less than 2 kg per year); ^baverage value for ^{40}K for food and water intake given in Ref. [4]; ^crecommended value given in Ref. [22].

The measured values of ^{40}K activity concentrations in 8 tea samples ranged from (16-780) Bq kg^{-1} with an average value of (317±322) Bq kg^{-1} . The obtained values are comparable with the results reported for tea from China [7], Herbal plants from Malaysia [16] and endemic plants from Turkey [18], Table 3.

The obtained values of ^{40}K activity concentrations for 192 samples of different additives range from (<1.7-5861) Bq kg^{-1} with an average of (177±492) Bq kg^{-1} . The average value is comparable to the average for salt originating from Turkey [8], as well as other food samples, Table 3.

Observing all the analyzed food samples, it can be seen that the measured values of ^{40}K activity concentrations were uneven among individual samples or food groups, which was accompanied by high standard deviations in the average values. The lowest value was measured in the sample from the additive group (<1.7 Bq kg^{-1} salt sample), while the highest value was also measured in the same group (5861 Bq kg^{-1} in the food coloring sample). In about 15% of the samples, ^{40}K activity concentrations were below the minimum detectable activity (salt and baking soda samples). The average value of ^{40}K activity concentrations for all analyzed food samples is (156±411) Bq kg^{-1} . The measured values of ^{137}Cs for all analyzed samples are in the range of (<0.1-21.0) Bq kg^{-1} with an average value of (2.6±3.7) Bq kg^{-1} .

kg⁻¹. In about 90% of the samples, the concentration of ¹³⁷Cs activity was below the minimum detectable activity, i.e. far below the recommended values given in Table 3 defined in the Serbian Rulebook for different food groups [22]. The obtained values for ¹³⁷Cs activity concentrations are comparable to the values reported for most other foods shown in Table 3: wheat from Jordan, hazelnut from Turkey, herbal plant from Malaysia, milk and rice from China as well as fruits from India where negligible activity concentrations were also detected ¹³⁷Cs. The obtained values are significantly lower compared to those measured in game and poultry samples, as well as wild mushrooms, Table 3.

Table 3 – Comparison of the measured activity concentration of ⁴⁰K and ¹³⁷Cs in food in this research and other research in the world.

Type of food	Country of origin	Activity concentration (Bq kg ⁻¹)		References
		⁴⁰ K	¹³⁷ Cs	
Hazelnut	Turkey	MDC - 298 (136)	MDC-6 (2)	[14]
Beef meat	Turkey	(207±23)	/	[8]
Game and poultry	Netherlands	/	3.4-1100	[3]
Wild mushrooms	Netherlands	/	16-136	[3]
Wheat	Jordan	140-382 (220)	< MDC	[6]
Wheat	Turkey	(294±42)	/	[8]
Oats	Turkey	(202±57)	/	[8]
Barley	Turkey	(235±46)	/	[8]
Cucumber	Egypt	1094-1459 (1160±164)	/	[10]
Sweet pepper	Egypt	1176-1245 (1204±29)	/	[10]
Cheese	Turkey	(169±18)	/	[8]
White bread	Turkey	(196±33)	/	[8]
Cassava flour	Nigeria	207-693 (427)	/	[23]
Yam flour	Nigeria	207-244 (227)	/	[23]
Cocoyam flour	Nigeria	142-248 (196)	/	[23]
Tea	China	174	/	[7]
Herbal plants	Malaysia	(396±18)	(0.70±0.18)	[16]
Endemic plants	Turkey	207-812 (451±30)	/	[18]
Milk	Zhejiang, China	/	< MDC	[13]
Rice	Zhejiang, China	/	0.004-0.26	[13]
Salt	Turkey	(117±23)	/	[5]
Fruits	India	3-111 (44±56)	0.03-0.70 (0.35±0.31)	[24]
Cereals and flour	Serbia	<12-641 (217±190)	<0.40-3.30 (1.48±0.68)	This paper
Fruits	Serbia	<5.8-345 (67±57)	<0.20-5.20 (1.27±0.94)	This paper
Teas	Serbia	16-780 (317±322)	<0.40-2.80 (1.40±0.92)	This paper
Additives	Serbia	<1.7-5861 (177±492)	<0.1-21.0 (3±4)	This paper
Foods (Total)	Serbia	<1.7-5861 (156±411)	<0.1-21.0 (2.6±3.7)	This paper

- range; (average value±standard deviation). MDC = Minimum detectable activity concentration.

The obtained values of individual annual effective doses for ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs (E_K , E_{Cs}) and the total annual effective dose of gamma radiation for these two radionuclides (E_{tot}) are shown in Table 2. The dose values for ^{40}K range from ($<11-79490$) nSv y^{-1} with an average value of (3415 ± 9987) nSv y^{-1} . The lowest value was estimated for the nitrite salt sample and the highest for the corn sample. Not a single food sample exceeds the average value of 0.17 mSv, which is estimated for exposure to ^{40}K due to food ingestion [4]. In an extreme case, if a person were to consume individual samples that generate the maximum dose from all food groups during the year, he would not exceed this value. The obtained dose values for ^{40}K are significantly lower than those shown for food consumption in a study [7] from China. The values of annual effective doses (E_K) for cereals and flour as well as additives are comparable with the reported results in the research [8] for cereals and salt as well as other types of food from Turkey. The average dose value of ^{40}K (E_K) for fruit is comparable to that reported for fruit from India [24]. The values for teas are comparable to the results shown for Malaysian herbal plants [16].

Estimated annual effective doses for ^{137}Cs range from ($<1.3-858$) nSv y^{-1} with an average of (73 ± 103) nSv y^{-1} . The average value is about 47 times lower than the average annual effective dose for ^{40}K , which indicates that analyzing the total annual effective dose (E_{tot}) the main contribution is directly from ^{40}K . The total annual effective dose (E_{tot}) ranges from ($<0.013-79.70$) $\mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$ with an average of (3.5 ± 10.0) $\mu\text{Sv y}^{-1}$. All obtained values (individual and average) are below the recommended value of 0.1 mSv [22]. The average dose value (E_{Cs}) for fruits is 2.8 times higher than that reported for fruits from India [24], while for teas it is comparable to that reported for Star anise in expression [16]. From Table 2, it can be clearly seen that the annual effective dose for a given group of foods is determined by the amount that a person enters the body through ingestion (kg y^{-1}), which indicates that sufficient amounts of intake were taken for assessment so that the estimated doses do not reach.

4. CONCLUSION

In this research, the activity concentration values of ^{40}K and ^{137}Cs were determined using the gamma spectrometry method for a total of 292 samples of cereals and flour, fruits, teas, and additives that were imported or produced in Western Serbia. Based on the measured values, an assessment of the health impact was made in terms of annual effective doses. The measured values of ^{40}K are comparable to the content in similar foods analyzed in research by other authors in the world. The measured values of ^{137}Cs are far below those prescribed by law in the Republic of Serbia. The values are comparable to those for other food samples in the world.

The obtained values of annual effective doses for all foods are below 0.1 mSv y^{-1} . The values are mostly comparable with the results for casual food reported in other research. Since the values are below the recommended and comparable to other food samples, it can be concluded that there is no particular danger from consuming this type of food during the year. It can be considered that the analyzed food was radiologically safe for consumption, especially considering that in the analyzed period (2010-2020), also included the period of the nuclear accident in Fukushima in 2011, which obviously did not lead to an increased content of ^{137}Cs in the analyzed food samples.

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APPLICATION POSSIBILITIES OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN WASTE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: The paper shows and describes the possibility of applying artificial intelligence in waste management. Traditional waste sorting technologies are mostly based on manual work. Unlike traditional technologies, robotics is based on the work of artificial intelligence, and its application in waste sorting implies continuous upgrading of software support with the aim of increasing the efficiency, precision, speed, and capabilities of the existing system in the waste sorting process. Upgrading the system allows the addition of new fractions of waste and makes the sorting process adaptable for all set-up tasks. The main advantages are working in multiple shifts without stopping and interrupting the process, high accuracy rate, quality and purity of separated recyclable materials. The paper will analyze new methods for sorting waste that contribute to increasing the degree of recycling.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Waste Management, Sorting, Recycling

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern humanity is constantly faced with numerous issues of sustainable waste management, especially since these issues are of key importance for the preservation of life on our planet. The historical development of human civilization meant, among other things, a constant growth in the number of inhabitants, which directly resulted in a constant increase in the amount of generated waste. Large amounts of waste were especially generated and accumulated due to the development of industry, and man tended to dispose of waste as far as possible from the place where he lived. Waste disposal has become one of the most important goals of human society, with the tendency for waste not to pollute the environment, but to turn it into a finished product or material for new production, depending on the type of waste, through the application of recycling technology. In the process of waste management, there are several problems such as: choosing a suitable location for waste disposal, disposing of accumulated huge amounts of waste - the so-called. of historical waste, creation of illegal landfills near settlements and watercourses, disposal of hazardous waste, provision of equipment and machinery for waste disposal, development of population awareness of the need for sustainable waste management, etc.

The basic and most important tasks in the process of sustainable waste management are waste sorting and recycling. In order to reuse materials from waste after its collection, it is necessary to carry out a sorting process. Sorting or selection of waste can be primary - performed at the place of waste generation and secondary - performed in a waste treatment facility. Nowadays, the waste sorting process is a combination of automated and manual work. It is necessary to consider the automation of the waste sorting process because manual sorting is a slow process that can be harmful to human health if the foreseen and prescribed measures of safety and protection at work are not applied. Technologies have been developed for automatic waste sorting that are more efficient and economical compared to manual sorting.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

Untreated mixed waste has little, almost no market value, but individual materials found in mixed waste have a corresponding market value. Sorting the waste reduces the non-recyclable part of the waste and enables the realization of economic benefits by using the obtained increased recyclable part of the waste. The waste sorting process involves the classification of waste according to different types.

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For the effective and efficient application of recycling technology, the introduction of the so-called primary selection, i.e., sorting of waste at the place of origin, which ensures a higher degree of purity and quality of separated recyclable materials from waste. Recyclable materials obtained in this way can be directed to re-production as raw materials or to sale as a finished product, and in addition to economic profit, the amount of waste for final disposal or depositing is reduced, thus saving precious landfill space for disposing of non-recyclable waste. Waste sorting can be manual/manual and automatic. The economy and market of developed countries support and require sophisticated technologies, while in developing countries, simpler technological solutions, considering the costs of operation and maintenance. In manual sorting, recyclable materials are manually separated from other types of waste through the following processes: separation of non-recyclable materials, oversized or heavy materials or materials incompatible with recyclable materials, precise separation of recyclable materials after the sorting process in order to ensure better quality of materials and separation of recyclable materials from other waste. Workers are located on both sides of the conveyor belts and separate the different waste fractions into the appropriate tanks. This type of work can be harmful to health due to: daily exposure to dangerous substances, working in an awkward position, falls, inhalation of harmful gases, working in constant noise, at extreme temperatures, etc. In order to work safely, workers must be educated, use protective equipment, and observe prescribed protection measures. Protective equipment includes gloves, safety glasses, safety shoes, helmet, mask, and reflective vest.

A combination of manual and automated procedures is most often applied because some steps in the sorting process are best handled manually, while other steps are simpler and more practical automated procedures. The general goals of automating the sorting process are sorting of larger amounts of various waste, greater safety and hygiene conditions in sorting facilities, assurance of the quality of sorted raw materials (waste), separation of hazardous from useful waste and economic profitability of the procedure. Manual waste sorting is monotonous, physically demanding and extremely dangerous work. In order to protect the health of employees, but also to increase the economy of business, it is logical to apply automation and modern technology in waste sorting processes. In this way, the process will become safer and more profitable. The successful use of automated waste sorting depends on the quality of designing the plant for waste sorting, from the input of raw materials to the output of recyclables as well as the use of the most adequate technologies in all phases of waste sorting.

The type of waste to be sorted affects the steps and applied waste sorting technologies. Municipal waste represents a large mixture of materials that requires complex sorting technology with the aim of separating the purest possible fractions. Waste sorting technologies must have the ability to sort increasingly diverse types and quantities of materials regardless of size, moisture content or pollution level resulting in a combination of technologies being applied for successful waste sorting. Waste sorting facilities use several types of technologies. In order for the flow of waste through the sorting facility to be efficient, planograms are created to determine the flow of waste through the facility.

The waste first goes through pre-treatment operations. Transport of waste between individual devices is carried out by conveyor belts consisting of rollers and rubber bands connecting the rollers. The rubber bands move by rotating the rollers and thus transport objects from one workplace to another, i.e., from the unloading point to the waste sorting plant. Conveyor belts bring the waste to the sorting device. Depending on the type of waste, different sorting devices are used. Some of the main technologies used in these facilities are waste screening, air current separation, ballistic separator, magnetic separator, sensor technology, radio identification, robotics and artificial intelligence and recognition technology. New technologies in waste sorting include sorting sensors, artificial intelligence, the use of robots and recognition technology, which represent the so-called SMART (advanced) sorting technologies.

Optical sorting represents a modern method of sorting waste based on sensors. Such a system recognizes and separates different types of waste using sensors, manipulators, robots, and the like. By using this technology, the desired material fractions are extracted from the waste quickly and economically. A sensor is a device that converts a physical phenomenon into an electrical signal. As such, sensors represent part of the connection between a physical part and a part of an electronic device, such as a computer.

Sorting drives containing sensor-based devices consist of three subsystems:

- 1) Waste access assembly (vibrating feeders, conveyor belts) - transports waste to the sensor assembly. In order to sort the waste with the help of this technology, it is necessary to ensure a distance between the waste units so that the sensors can recognize the components;
- 2) Sensor assembly (sensors for distinguishing waste according to characteristics) - sends rays to the waste. With the help of cameras and lasers, the sensor system or sensor unit recognizes the waste by type and measures the dimensions of the waste and sends a signal to the computer where it is processed, and then the computer sends a task to the system for removing waste from the conveyor belt. The dimensions and position of the object are defined in the task.
- 3) Assembly for removal (robots or manipulators) - removes waste from the conveyor belt and places it in the appropriate warehouses depending on the type of waste.

The sensor assembly is based on "machine" vision, which is an optical and electronic assembly that can automatically capture a 2D image or analyze a 3D image of an object or part of an object, as well as process such an image. The basic device of the machine vision system is a camera that captures the desired image. object after which the received information is sent to analog-digital transformation and further processing with program support.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The optical sensors used in waste sorting processes are:

- NIR (Near infrared) - differentiation of plastic materials (PET, HDPE, PVC, PP and PS);
- VIS (visible light sensors) - material recognition based on color;
- XRF (X-ray Fluorescence) - distinguishing metals and alloys (eg, copper from iron);
- XRT (X-ray Transmission) - determines materials based on atomic density - for example, halogens and organic components.
- EMS (electromagnetic sensor) - identify metals based on their conductivity.

Optical sensors used in waste sorting plants are usually based on NIR or VIS technology. The NIR sensor detects different types of polymers, paper, stone, wood, and construction waste. Figure 1 shows a device for optical sorting of waste based on NIR sensors.

Figure 1. UNISORT device for optical sorting of waste based on NIR sensors.

The VIS sensor uses the visible light spectrum of electromagnetic radiation. It is most often used in mutual interaction with NIR sensors and cameras. The VIS sensor provides the necessary information to the NIR sensor so that it can recognize the types of waste based on their colors. The recognition process takes place so that the sensor emits wavelengths of different colors on the waste material. Based on the difference in the received wavelength compared to the sent beam, the beam that returns to the sensor provides information to the sensor about the paint, that is, the type of material it is dealing with. Figure 2 shows an optical sorting device from the CP Group company MSS, which leads the industry in the production of state-of-the-art optical sorting systems. MSS optical sorting systems have been proven in the field as the most effective devices for automatic separation of: paper, plastic, metal, glass, wood, e-waste and other types of waste.

Figure 2. Optical sorting device of the MSS company from the CP Group

The X-ray sensor uses X-rays to analyze the material on the conveyor belt. Figure 3 shows the operation of the X-ray sensor, which, after scanning the waste, uses X-rays to sort the waste into the associated waste separation chambers.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the operation of the X-ray sensor

The transfer of material on the conveyor belt takes place with the help of a vibrating conveyor. If necessary, the conveyor belt can be stopped or the speed of movement can be changed, which leads to the control of the flow of waste to the separator, after which the material is separated. At the moment when the waste is in the scanning area of the sensor, the belt stops and the X-ray source, which is placed under the conveyor belt, irradiates its narrow area. The amount of radiation absorbed by the material is measured by detectors located on the conveyor support. Each object on the tape is classified according to the criteria programmed in the computer. When the sorting decision corresponds to the set sorting criteria, the scanned object is separated from the rest of the material and separated into a waste separation chamber. Electromagnetic sensors are used in metal waste sorting and electronic waste processing. The EMS uses the interaction between the metal and the magnetic field as a criterion for distinguishing between metals. The principle is based on the change in the strength of the electromagnetic field of the magnetic field in electrically conductive materials in waste streams.

When a conductive material (e.g., a metal wire) passes through a magnetic field, eddy currents are induced, which leads to the loss of the energy field, and this phenomenon is detected by sensitive electromagnetic sensors. After detecting metals in the waste stream, a mechanical arm or conveyor belt separates a certain fraction into a disposal container. Robotics is a scientific and technical discipline whose goal is the creation and development of robots, automated devices controlled by computers using a control program and information received through sensors, i.e., electronic senses.

The fields of robotics are design, construction, operation, and use of robots, as well as computer systems for their control. Today, robots are used in dangerous environments (among other things for bomb detection and deactivation), production processes or in areas where there is a danger to health and human life. Robots find their application in numerous industries, from car manufacturing to surgical procedures in operating rooms, but they also have their application in sorting different types of waste. One example of the application of robotics in waste sorting is Apple's robot "Daisy" (shown in Figure 4), which was introduced in 2018, which disassembles defective iPhones and reuses valuable materials such as silver and tungsten. Robot Daisy disassembles nine types of iPhones in 18 seconds, sorting them into useful parts.

Figure 4. Apple robot Daisy

Robots perform tasks in environments that are dangerous for humans but also monotonous and tedious repetitive tasks. In contrast to human work, robots work without interruption and without the need for rest, thus enabling the simplification of the work process and improvement of the production cycle. The field of industrial robotics is defined as the study, design, and use of robotic assemblies in manufacturing processes. Typical applications of industrial robots include welding, assembly, pick and place, product inspection and testing with high durability, speed and precision of operation.

The application of robots in waste processing is a necessity and a reality for the future that will ensure new and significant benefits to man through an automated process that will be reflected in speed, precision, safety and durability among all other advantages. Artificial intelligence and robotization definitely represent the future of waste management. These intelligent systems will help communities manage recycling centers more efficiently. ZenRobotics Ltd, a Finnish company founded in 2007, has developed a robotic waste sorting system. ZenRobotics Recycler - ZRR (shown in Figure 5) developed an innovative concept in waste sorting that enabled the replacement of dangerous and inefficient manual work with highly efficient and fast autonomous robotic collectors. ZRR's key innovation is a unique system based on machine learning that collects gigabytes of data about its environment, from which commands emerge that move the robot's arm into an unpredictable environment and perform waste sorting.

The ZenRobotics recycler consists of a set of sensors, a control circuit, and industrial robots. Sensors and controllers control industrial robots to select targeted materials from waste on the conveyor and separate them into multiple compartments. The combination of sensors integrated with artificial intelligence (AI) solutions allows the ZRR system to recognize and select new fractions according to customer needs. When the output fractions are used as raw materials, the precision and cleanliness of the fractures is extremely important. ZRR can reach up to 98% purity of the output fractions, which makes the output product a quality raw material on the market.

ZRR systems have the ability to sort the following types of waste: metals (ferrous and non-ferrous), wood, rigid plastic (mixed rigid plastic, pipes by color), construction waste (mixed construction waste, construction waste by fractions: concrete, brick, limestone, asphalt). , old cardboard sheets and mixed municipal waste sorted into bags by color. Unlike traditional recycling machines that are based on mechanical and electrical components, the Zenrobotics Recycler (ZRR) is powered by artificial intelligence (AI). The core of ZRR is ZenRobotics Brain, a unique software that analyzes data and controls robots. It is an essential part of the ZRR waste sorting system. Like a smartphone, the ZRR gets software upgrades that make it even smarter and more efficient. Future software upgrades may add new features, such as additional fractions and new waste streams, or increase the efficiency, accuracy, speed and capability of an existing system. ZRR is easily trained to introduce a new sorting fraction, improve the sorting quality of a fraction, or divide existing fractions into new sub-fractions. Learning is simply done by showing the samples to the ZRR, and in this way the system gets information on what needs to be sorted. During the learning and practice process, typical sample items of desired fractions are placed on a sorting conveyor belt and run through the ZenRobotics Recycler. The ZRR device consists of a sensor module at the top of the conveyor belt, followed by one or more robotic manipulators that move objects of different fractions from the conveyor belt into boxes or compartments. Inputs from multiple sensors are combined to identify objects and recognize their materials using sensors and machine learning algorithms.

Figure 5. ZenRobotics Recycler (1-sensors, 2-control system, 3-robot, 4-sorted waste)

The system optimizes the sequence of waste collection considering its properties. Optimizing this process maximizes the financial benefit from reusing recycled materials. The robotic arm is programmed to perform precise and accurate material gripping operations. The most important input for selecting a robotic arm is the 3D sensor. Two important learning problems involved in data processing are distinguishing identified objects and choosing how to find irregular objects. Zenrobotics continuously improves the operation of the robotic waste sorting system in such a way that the administrator first records errors that occur in the system. In cases where the materials are not recognizable or are too rare to be recognized by the device, people are involved who sort the actual waste into the desired fractions, which are then fed through the system to obtain samples for future material recognition.

The ZenRobotics Recycler uses several sensor inputs to recognize a wide range of objects and/or materials on the waste conveyor. The unification of the data provided by the sensors enables a more precise analysis of the waste, so the system can prepare data on the composition of the waste on the belt in real time, as well as monitor the weights and values of the waste streams.

Unlike other waste sorting methods, the robotic waste sorting system can recognize and separate specific components with a high degree of separation accuracy. The system can process multiple components simultaneously, which improves the efficiency of the waste treatment system. With the help of the TwinCAT application (Figure 6), the system continuously downloads software updates and thus ZenRobotics Recycler is continuously improved and upgraded. The software can be updated for better performance or sorting of new materials, which turns the waste sorting methodology with the help of Zenrobotics into an even more profitable recycling process.

Figure 6. TwinCAT application in the Zenrobotics process

4. CONCLUSION

The development and application of modern methods for the classification and utilization of waste would give results in waste management that would achieve the standards set by the directives of the European Parliament for waste management. With quality and automated management processes, waste can be turned into a valuable economic resource. Waste sorting is the first stage in the process of extracting recyclable fractions from waste. Manual sorting of waste is economically inefficient compared to modern technologies and brings numerous dangers to the health of workers. For this reason, the automation of the waste sorting process is necessary.

With the progress of science and information technology, a new technology for sorting waste has been developed, which gives new possibilities, therefore it is necessary to apply it. The integration of robots into plants has brought technological progress, removes humans from dangerous and tiring work, and increases productivity in all areas of industry.

The use of artificial intelligence in the process of sorting and sorting waste leads to great economy in the recycling process, but such a process is extremely expensive. Even so, investing in automated waste recycling facilities is economically viable. The application of robotics in the waste sorting process increases efficiency, reduces costs and increases the quality of recyclables, which leads to a higher price of recyclables on the secondary raw materials market. The main advantage of such a waste sorting system is that it works 24/7. Robotic systems are very durable and require minimal downtime or maintenance. By introducing additional working hours, materials that were previously unprofitable for sorting can be sorted because significantly more energy is not consumed for this work. Increased profit from recycling and reduced waste costs. High purity fractions have better prices and sorted material is easier to market. Labor costs are reduced as robots work tirelessly all the time. Once installed, the robots save many man-hours every year and increase operational safety by reducing personnel injuries during manual sorting. Calculations have proven that the investment for the procurement of robotic plants is returned in a period of 2 years, and the benefits are multiple, from a safer working environment for humans, to the reuse of various materials and the utilization of waste for the purpose of producing electricity and heat.

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MERGING ECO-ART AND RECYCLING TO ADVANCE ENVIRONMENTAL PRESERVATION

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Abstract

Eco-art and recycling initiatives often involve comprehensive community engagement and participation in specific conditions. This paper explores the synergy between eco-art and recycling processes, as an optimal strategy to advance environmental preservation, alongside the integration of land art with ecological concepts. As environmental concerns escalate, the integration of ecoartistic measures and practices with recycling initiatives emerges as a potential to enhance environmental consciousness and sustainability. The study delves into the interconnectedness of these two disciplines, examining how the creative expression of eco-art can amplify the impact of recycling efforts and activities, leading to heightened environmental awareness and conservation. By detailed examination of the intersections of these creative and ecological disciplines, the research aims to contribute insights into innovative approaches that simultaneously harmonize artistic expression and environmental conservation aspect, with the final important task of protecting our planet and ensuring sustainable development.

Keywords: eco-art, recycling, environmental, land art, sustainability.

1. INTRODUCTION

The intersection of art and ecology has gained significant attention in recent years, with a growing body of literature exploring the potential of art to foster environmental awareness and sustainability. The concept of eco-art, which encompasses artistic practices that engage with ecological issues, has emerged as a powerful tool for promoting environmental consciousness and advocating for sustainable practices. Moreover, the incorporation of recycling into eco-art has further expanded its potential to contribute to environmental conservation and resource management. Recycling within the context of eco-art contributes significantly to waste reduction by repurposing materials that would otherwise end up in landfills, mitigating the environmental impact of excessive waste. The influence of land artists on ecology has been a subject of increasing interest, reflecting the relationship between environmental aesthetics and land. [1]

Land art, a movement that emerged in the 1960s and 1970s, challenged traditional art notions of objectness, commodification, and permanence, thereby redefining the interaction of ethics and aesthetics in environmental art [2]. This movement has played a key role in curating exhibitions that convey ecological knowledge rooted in places, highlighting the struggle for environmental justice. [3]

Land art projects, combined with ecological concepts, have the potential to transform public spaces, promoting biodiversity, and serving as living examples of sustainable co-existence between art and nature. This paper aims to explore the relationship between ecology and art, particularly focusing on the role of eco-art in promoting recycling and sustainable practices.

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2. INFLUENCE OF ECO-ART ON THE ENVIRONMENT

Art has the capacity to evoke emotional and compassionate responses, leading to a deeper connection with nature. This emotional connection to nature has been shown to be beneficial in fostering pro-environmental behavior and promoting a sense of meaning and beauty in the natural world. Eco-art leverages these emotional and compassionate pathways to nature connection to convey messages about environmental sustainability and the importance of recycling. [4]

Eco-art serves as a powerful platform for artists to communicate environmental messages. It transforms recycled materials into expressive works, fostering a deeper connection between art and sustainability.

The feminist theoretical debate on the relationship between culture and nature has led to the emergence of bio-art, land-art, and eco-art, where the use, reuse, and recycling of waste materials promote artistic experimentation and interdisciplinary border crossings. [5]

This approach highlights the potential of recycling as a means to repurpose waste materials into artistic expressions that convey powerful messages about environmental conservation and sustainability.

Recycling within the realm of eco-art serves a dual purpose, extending beyond the creative repurposing of materials to actively contribute to resource conservation. This dynamic process plays a crucial role in diminishing the demand for new raw materials, thus directly mitigating the environmental footprint associated with resource extraction and production. By diverting materials from the conventional waste stream and giving them new life through artistic expression, eco-artists play a vital role in fostering a sustainable and circular economy. The incorporation of recycled materials into eco-artistic endeavors not only showcases the inherent beauty and potential of discarded items, but also underscores the significance of responsible consumption. This practice aligns with the principles of environmental stewardship, as it actively reduces the strain on natural resources and minimizes the ecological impact associated with the extraction and processing of raw materials.

In recent years, the arts have been increasingly recognized for their contributions to understanding the challenges of global environmental change and sustainability. This recognition has paved the way for the integration of artistic practices into sustainability science, emphasizing the role of the arts in addressing complex social-ecological challenges. Eco-art, particularly when recycling is incorporated, serves as a platform for artists to engage with sustainability science and contribute to the discourse on environmental conservation. [6]

Furthermore, indigenous artistic practices have been instrumental in inspiring change against environmental degradation, with a focus on recycling, sovereignty, and interventions that promote sustainable environmental practices. [7]

The incorporation of indigenous art and recycling practices underscores the cultural and traditional knowledge embedded in eco-art, highlighting the importance of indigenous perspectives in promoting sustainable and recycling-oriented artistic expressions.

Government incentives for eco-innovation in recycling systems have also underscored the multifaceted implications of recycling for the environment, economic performance, and wealth generation. This recognition of the economic and environmental benefits of recycling further reinforces the significance of incorporating recycling practices into eco-art as a means to promote sustainable and economically viable artistic expressions. [8]

Eco-art, with its emphasis on sustainable practices and resource efficiency, becomes a beacon for environmentally conscious living. It embodies the principles of a circular economy, where materials are reused, repurposed, and given a second life, reducing the need for continuous extraction and production. This approach aligns with the broader goal of achieving a more sustainable and resilient planet, where the delicate balance between human activities and the natural environment is upheld.

The concept of circular economy and financial circularity of the plastic packaging value chain have also emphasized the challenges and opportunities associated with improving material and financial circularity through recycling. This perspective underscores the potential for eco-art to engage with the principles of circular economy and promote the reuse and repurposing of materials, particularly in the context of plastic waste and packaging. [9]

Arts-based research has sought to redefine and extend beyond the constraints of interdisciplinary research by incorporating the processes, forms, and approaches of artistic practices into science-policy processes, addressing the "imagination gap" when dealing with complex social-ecological challenges. This integration of artistic practices into science-policy processes highlights the potential for eco-art to contribute to transformative change towards sustainability, particularly through its engagement with recycling and sustainable material use. [10]

The performing arts sector, particularly the Opera industry, has initiated actions towards adopting and disseminating more sustainable practices, evaluating and mitigating environmental impacts, and engaging in a sectoral roadmap towards environmental goals.

This demonstrates the potential for eco-art to influence and inspire sustainability initiatives within the arts sector, particularly through the adoption of recycling and sustainable scenography practices. [11]

The integration of land art with ecological concepts has contributed to a re-evaluation of the relationship between art and the environment. Land artists have employed the earth as a canvas, creating large-scale works that are often located in natural landscapes. These works interact not only with the environment but also with the viewers to reconsider their relationship with nature. The use of natural materials and the incorporation of ecological elements in land art installations have served as a catalyst for discussions on ecological sustainability and the human impact on the environment. Land artists have also challenged traditional notions of art by creating works that are inherently transient and subject to the forces of nature. This approach has led to a reexamination of the permanence and commodification of art, highlighting the interconnectedness of art and the environment. The enduring legacy of land art has influenced the discourse on environmental aesthetics, emphasizing the importance of place-rooted ecological knowledge and the struggle for environmental justice.

The integration of arts and sciences has facilitated collaborative action on sustainability, fostering learning, connection, and action for sustainability in diverse contexts. This interdisciplinary approach underscores the potential for eco-art to bridge the gap between artistic expressions and scientific knowledge, particularly in promoting recycling and sustainable practices for environmental conservation. [12]

Emotional aspects of human behavior, particularly with respect to sustainability, have been recognized as a key factor in nurturing the link between passion, emotion, and the sustainability discourse through art. This recognition emphasizes the role of eco-art in evoking emotional responses and fostering a sense of environmental stewardship, particularly through its engagement with recycling and sustainable artistic practices. Artists and environmentalists continually innovate within the realms of eco-art and recycling, adapting to new technologies and materials to create impactful and sustainable artistic expressions. [13]

The challenges of achieving a consistent and coherent approach to integrating culture in sustainability have been acknowledged, highlighting the complexities of harmonizing cultural heritage with sustainable development goals. This recognition underscores the need for eco-art to navigate the complexities of cultural heritage and sustainability, particularly through its engagement with recycling and sustainable artistic expressions. [14]

Arts-based environmental education has been identified as a powerful tool for advancing the transition towards sustainability, acknowledging the multidimensionality of the interaction between people and nature. This perspective underscores the potential for eco-art to contribute to environmental education and advocacy, particularly through its engagement with recycling and sustainable artistic practices. [15]

Eco-artists consider sustainability, interdependence, and the totality of ecosystems, often drawing on systems thinking as an approach to environmental change. This systems-oriented approach highlights the potential for eco-art to engage with recycling as a means to address complex environmental challenges and promote sustainable resource management. [16]

3. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the synthesis of the literature highlights the significant potential of eco-art in promoting environmental awareness, sustainability, and recycling practices. Emotional and compassionate pathways to connection with nature, interdisciplinary border crossings, indigenous inspirations, circular economy principles, and collaborative sustainability actions all underscore the multifaceted role of eco-art in addressing environmental challenges. By incorporating recycling and sustainable material use, eco-art has the capacity to inspire change, foster environmental stewardship, and contribute to the discourse on sustainable practices. Recycling in eco-art not only repurposes materials but also contributes to resource conservation by reducing the demand for new raw materials, thereby lessening the environmental footprint. The environmental footprint, often measured by the amount of natural resources consumed and the resulting waste generated, is significantly lightened when recycled materials are creatively repurposed in artistic endeavors. In addition, the ripple effects of this reduction in environmental footprint extend beyond the art world. As eco-art gains recognition and popularity, it catalyzes a shift in societal attitudes toward consumption and waste. Viewers and admirers of eco-art are prompted to reconsider their own habits, fostering a collective awareness of the environmental impact of individual choices. In essence, recycling in eco-art becomes a powerful agent of change, influencing not only artistic expression but also shaping a more sustainable and responsible global community.

Furthermore, the influence of land artists on ecology has been profound, shaping the discourse on environmental aesthetics and the interaction of ethics and aesthetics in environmental art. Through their large-scale installations and reevaluation of traditional art concepts, land artists have contributed to a deeper understanding of the relationship between art and the environment, leaving a lasting impact on the discourse surrounding ecological sustainability and environmental justice.

Eco-art and recycling play significant roles in safeguarding the environment, serving as potent tools for raising awareness and educating the public about pressing environmental issues through visually appealing and creative means. Defined by art practices oriented toward the environment, eco-art actively promotes sustainability by frequently incorporating recycled materials, repurposing waste, and crafting artistic creations from these elements. Recycling, considered the process of converting waste materials into reusable resources, effectively contributes to the reduction of the overall waste volume.

These practices of eco-art and recycling are not only impactful but also distinctive approaches to enhancing environmental preservation. Their influence extends beyond simple awareness raising, as they actively advocate for sustainable practices and vividly showcase the transformative potential of turning waste into valuable resources. Through their combined efforts, eco-art and recycling emerge as powerful agents of positive change in environmental conservation.

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CHALLENGES WITH WASTE MATERIAL OBTAINED BY 3D PRINTING

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Abstract:

Today, the waste material obtained by 3D printing operations presents significant challenges due to the increasing global adoption of this technology, leading to serious environmental implications. The generation of plastic waste from unsuccessful prints and end-of-life products is a growing concern, impacting the circular economy. With a 26% annual growth rate in additive manufacturing, the amount of waste is rapidly increasing, necessitating effective waste management strategies. However, 3D printing offers advantages in waste reduction compared to traditional manufacturing methods, with only 40% waste generation compared to subtractive technologies and much of the waste being recyclable. The challenges of waste material obtained by 3D printing are numerous and require a comprehensive approach to waste management and recycling. Moreover, leveraging the abundant opportunities for reusing materials and developing sustainable composite filaments, 3D printing can contribute to environmental sustainability and the principles of circular economy.

Keywords: metals, polymers, waste material, 3D printing, environment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Contemporary 3D printers employ a diverse range of materials, including thermoplastics, light-curing resins, and metal powders. Among these, thermoplastics, such as ABS, PETG, or PLA, commonly used in 3D printing, exhibit notably high recycling potential. These materials can undergo mechanical recycling through processes such as shredding, melting, and the subsequent production of new filament.

The preservation of the quality of the material stands out as one of the main challenges in the recycling of 3D printing materials. During the mechanical recycling process, thermoplastics may undergo a decline in their mechanical and chemical properties. Consequently, ensuring stringent quality control of the secondary raw material is crucial, necessitating adjustments to 3D printing parameters based on its specific characteristics leading to a quality assurance. The practical challenge arises from the potential heterogeneity of materials in 3D prints, making recycling a complex task. Therefore, the imperative lies in the development of novel technologies and processes that allow efficient recycling of multi-material printouts [1-4]. Hence, the recycling of 3D prints is feasible, particularly for certain materials like thermoplastics, yet it entails challenges that require resolution to unlock the full recycling potential within the realm of 3D printing. Ongoing research and technological advancements are imperative to foster sustainable development and realize the environmental, economic and social advantages of 3D print recycling. The implementation of pertinent legal regulations and standards regarding 3D print recycling can enhance user awareness and advocate responsible waste management practices. Furthermore, exploring the creation of educational programs and initiatives is worthwhile, as they can promote recycling awareness and responsible utilization of 3D printing technology.

The aim of this paper is to systematically investigate the obstacles associated with the waste generated throughout the 3D printing process, with the ultimate goal of proposing sustainable solutions and fostering environmentally responsible practices within the industry. This theme seeks to enhance understanding, prompt innovation, and contribute to the development of effective strategies for managing and minimizing the environmental impact of 3D printing waste materials.

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2. REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Several studies have focused on the recycling and reprocessing of waste materials from 3D printing, including plastics and metals, to promote sustainability and reduce environmental impact. The inability to reprocess thermoset materials used in 3D printing has resulted in substantial waste, raising concerns about environmental implications. [5]

While some argue that 3D printing waste is not a significant problem and that the technology can be used to combat postproduction waste, the increasing annual growth rate of additive manufacturing, especially in 3D polymer printing, has led to a rapid increase in waste generation. [6]

Although 3D printing presents challenges in waste management, it also offers opportunities for sustainable practices, such as the reconstitution of plastics into 3D printer filament, reducing pollution and printing costs [7].

The waste of 3D printed plastic products is particularly concerning due to its impact on the circular economy, highlighting the need for sustainable waste management practices. The performance of recycled ABS waste and PET 3D printing waste was found to be similar to products printed using the fused filament fabrication (FFF) method, suggesting that recycled 3D printing waste materials can be used effectively in the production of new products, thus reducing the generation of waste and promoting a circular economy. [8]

The paper [2] highlighted the incorporation of recycled metal waste, including titanium, nickel alloys, stainless steel, copper, and rare earth metals, into 3D printing, demonstrating the potential to reuse metal waste materials in 3D printing processes, contributing to waste reduction and sustainable material utilization. In the paper [3] key elements to address sustainability in 3D printing were proposed, including the development of hardware and processes that minimize waste generation, the deployment of renewable raw materials, the reuse and recycling of printed products, and applications in sustainability, emphasizing the importance of integrating sustainable practices in 3D printing, including waste materials management.

Furthermore, some researches emphasized the unique opportunity presented by 3D printing of plastics to efficiently recycle plastic waste, indicating the potential for waste reduction and sustainable utilization of materials in 3D printing processes. In [5] a two-step polymerization strategy is proposed in order to develop 3D printing reprocessable thermosets (3DPRTs) that allow: a printed 3D structure to be reshaped into a new arbitrary form; a broken part to be repaired by 3D printing new material over the damage; and unwanted printed parts to be recycled so the material can be reused and repurposed. According to [6] filaments for 3D printing can be made from a variety of thermoplastic materials, including those obtained from recycling. A review of the available literature is given in [6] regarding production of filaments for 3D printers from recycled polymers.

Additionally, the use of solar thermal energy to recycle waste plastic for 3D printing and the implementation of recycled materials for the manufacturing of unmanned aerial vehicles underscore the various applications of sustainable practices in 3D printing [9-10]. Furthermore, the potential to tailor lightweight aggregates for concrete 3D printing applications emphasizes the role of material selection in amplifying the sustainability advantages of this technology [11]. The mechanical recycling of PLA 3D printing waste and the use of recycled disposable masks, such as 3D printing filament, further demonstrate the potential for waste reduction and resource efficiency in 3D printing. [12-13]

Overall, these studies collectively underscore the potential for waste reduction and sustainable utilization of materials in 3D printing processes through the recycling and reprocessing of waste materials. By incorporating recycled materials, including plastics and metals, 3D printing can contribute to a more sustainable and environmentally friendly manufacturing approach.

The exploration of non-planar printing strategies and the use of sustainable recycled materials in 3D printing have been proposed as approaches to minimize material consumption and control production-related environmental impacts. In the broader context of sustainability, non-planar 3D printing has been identified as a potential transformative technology that can minimize material consumption and control production-related environmental impacts. [14]

The management of waste materials from 3D printing presents several challenges, particularly in terms of recycling and reusing the materials. However, efforts have been made to explore the potential of recycling 3D printing waste, such as the development of sustainable 3D printed meat analogs and the transformation of electronic waste plastics into sustainable filaments for 3D printing. Likewise, Gaikwad et al. demonstrated the transformation of electronic waste (e-waste) plastics into sustainable filaments for 3D printing, highlighting the potential for upcycling waste materials to create new printing filaments, thereby reducing environmental impact. [15]

The challenges associated with waste management in 3D printing extend beyond environmental concerns to encompass socio-ecological impacts and barriers to waste management techniques. Production of municipal solid waste, including 3D printing waste, represents a significant challenge for waste managers worldwide. [16] Barriers have been identified in the implementation of waste management techniques in manufacturing organizations, highlighting the complexities of waste management in industrial settings. [17]

In addition, the use of recycled plastics and fibers from industrial waste and domestic recycling for 3D printing has been proposed as a potential solution to address challenges in waste management. [18] Furthermore, the environmental impact of 3D printing waste has been a topic of concern, with studies indicating the potential for waste reduction through 3D printing processes, particularly in the construction industry. [19] Then the energy consumed by electricity for 3D printing has been identified as a contributing factor to the environmental impact of the technology. [20]

The listed advances in 3D printing technology and material reuse demonstrate a concerted effort to address the environmental implications of waste material obtained by 3D printing.

3. MATERIALS FOR 3D PRINTING

The 3D printing industry uses various materials. It is estimated that less than 10% of materials used in 3D printing are currently recycled [21]. The materials that can be recycled for use in 3D printing are e.g. thermoplastics. The 3D printing industry has to be more sustainable, with projections that approximately 40 %-60 % of 3D printed items can be recycled.

A variety of plastic materials is available for 3D printing, and each of these has unique properties suited to specific use cases. There are two types of plastic, thermoset and thermoplastic. Thermoplastics can be melted and reformed and do not form chemical bonds while curing, making them remoldable and recyclable. Thermoset plastics are cured by photopolymerization (with ultraviolet light) and they cannot be melted or reshaped by heating once the 3D printed object hardens. [21]

The metals which are often used for 3D printing are: titanium, stainless, aluminum, nickel alloys. 3D printing processes available for metal 3D printing are: Metal FDM and Selective Laser Melting (SLM) and Direct Metal Laser Sintering (DMLS). Compared to plastic 3D printers, metal 3D printing is more expensive, complex, and has certain limitations [21].

Waste material obtained by 3D printing refers to excess or unused material that is generated during the additive manufacturing process. Several types of waste material can be produced in 3D printing: support material, failed prints, rafts and brims, unused material.

The cost-effectiveness of the use of recycled materials can be an attractive option for early stage of the product development. The use of recycled material in 3D printing contributes to sustainable construction solutions. The so-called recycling of materials minimize waste generation and the reduces requirements for primary plastics as a raw materials. [1]

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the challenges with waste material obtained by 3D printing are multifaceted and encompass environmental, socioecological, and industrial barriers. Efforts to address these challenges include the exploration of recycling and reusing waste materials, the development of sustainable 3D printing processes, and the consideration of energy consumption in 3D printing. However, further research and innovation are needed to develop effective waste management strategies and minimize the environmental impact of 3D printing waste. Implementing appropriate legal regulations and standards on 3D print recycling can contribute to increased awareness among users and facilitate the promotion of responsible waste management practices. Moreover, investigating the establishment of educational programs and initiatives is worth investigating, as these efforts can foster awareness of recycling and encourage the responsible use of more present 3D printing technology.

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A COMPARISON OF SEASONAL ARIMA AND HOLT-WINTERS EXPONENTIAL SMOOTHING MODELS FOR URBAN DROUGHT PREDICTION

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Abstract: Urban drought is one of the most devastating event that impacts various sectors such as public health, agriculture, industry as well as environment. In order to prevent this catastrophic event, various prediction methods can be used. Most popular forecasting methods for time series are Seasonal Arima and Holt-Winters Exponential Smoothing methods. This paper aims to present methodology of preparing and analyzing raw data, applying both methods to meteorological data sets and then comparing both model results in order to find the best model to predict parameters like temperature, precipitation and soil moisture which can indicate the possibility of urban drought. Our findings suggest that the Holt-Winters method gives more accurate predictions based on the KPI that were used.

Key words: Urban drought prediction, SARIMA, Holt-Winters Exponential Smoothing, univariate time series, R, RStudio

1. INTRODUCTION

Urban areas are one of the most affected by extreme weather events particularly droughts. Global warming contributes to higher temperatures leading to increased evaporation rates and the drying of water sources. In order to prevent urban drought consequences and reduce water demand and at the same time conserve and manage precious water resources, careful monitoring and appropriate water plans are needed [1]. Forecasting urban droughts is the approach that can be used for both municipalities and water management agencies in order to prepare them in timely manner to respond and implement adequate measures.

One of the methods used for urban drought prediction, is statistical forecasting method such as time series analysis. By analysing historical meteorological data, certain trends and patterns can be identified which can be later used for predicting urban drought parameters.

2. FORECASTING TIME SERIES

Forecasting time series involves predicting future values based on past observations and it is a crucial aspect in various fields such as finance, economics and meteorology. Time series can be seen as a set of observations or data points of a single variable collected over time. Several methods are employed for time series forecasting with two common approaches being statistical methods and machine learning techniques. Statistical methods include ARIMA and Exponential Smoothing Models like Holt-Winters which are based on models built on historical data. These data-driven models have been proved to be very accurate in meteorological forecasting applications [2].

When forecasting time series, it's crucial to analyze the characteristics of the data including trends, seasonality and any other factors which may affect the accuracy of the model. Model performance should be evaluated using certain statistical metrics like Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE) or Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE).

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2.1. ARIMA method

ARIMA method (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average) is a widely used statistical method for drought forecasting. It combines three components:

- **AutoRegressive (AR)** component,
- **Integrated (I)** component and,
- **Moving average (MA)** component.

AutoRegressive or “AR” component uses linear regression to model the dependant relationship between the current observation and its past values creating a weighted sum.

Integrated or “I” component is only used if the data are non-stationary. In order to become stationary, data needs to be differenced. The process of differentiation represents the operation of subtracting an observation from the observation in the previous time step. The order of differencing indicates how many times differencing is applied to achieve stationarity. Stationarity means that certain statistical properties of the series such as mean and variance remain constant over time.

Moving average component models the relationship between the current observation and a residual error from a moving average model applied to past values [3].

All components in the ARIMA model can be represented with three parameters, one for each component:

- ***p***: order of the autoregressive component which represents the number of ordinary or non-seasonal lagged observations
- ***d***: order of differencing which represents how many times an observation has been differentiated
- ***q***: order of the moving average

Standard notation for non-seasonal ARIMA model is **ARIMA (*p,d,q*)** and each parameter is determined through analysis of the autocorrelation function (ACF) and partial autocorrelation function (PACF) of the time series. The parameters can have integer values which indicate that the certain component is used in the model. If the value of the parameter is 0, it means that the model component is not used.

2.1.1. Seasonal ARIMA method (SARIMA)

ARIMA model which is applied to a time series which contains seasonality is called Seasonal ARIMA or SARIMA model (Seasonal AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average). It is actually an extension of the ARIMA model designed for forecasting seasonal time series. In addition to forementioned three non-seasonal components, SARIMA also includes three seasonal components P, D and Q. Its notation is SARIMA (*p,d,q*)(*P,D,Q*)*s* where *s* is the length of the seasonal cycle indicating how many observations constitutes one seasonal period [4].

2.2. Holt-Winters Exponential Smoothing method

The Holt-Winters Exponential Smoothing method is another popular time series forecasting technique which is used for data with trends and seasonality. This method extends simple exponential smoothing by incorporating three components: level (α), trend (β) and seasonality (γ). Each component has its own parameter which is used to control the influence of the component. These parameters are typically determined through optimization techniques. Level represents the smoothed value of the time

series at the current time point. Trend component represents the direction and rate of change in the time series and seasonality addresses repeating patterns in the data such as daily, weekly or monthly cycles.

Basic equations for the Holt-Winter's method with trend and additive seasonality can be expressed as following [6]:

$$\text{Level: } L_t = \alpha(Y_t - S_{t-s}) + (1 - \alpha)(L_{t-1} + b_{t-1}) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Trend: } b_t = \beta(L_t - L_{t-1}) + (1 - \beta)b_{t-1} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Seasonality: } S_t = \gamma(Y_t - L_t) + (1 - \gamma)S_{t-s} \quad (3)$$

Holt-Winters is also called triple exponential smoothing and it can be expressed as:

$$F_{t+m} = L_t + mb_t + S_{t-s+m} \quad (4)$$

where:

F_{t+m} is the forecast for m period,

s is the length of seasonality,

L_t is the level of the series,

b_t is the trend component,

S_t is the seasonal component [5].

2.3. Forecasting metrics

Forecasting metrics are used to assess the accuracy and performance of predictive models, including those used in time series forecasting. Some common metrics which are usually used include:

- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):** It represents the average of the absolute differences between predicted and actual values.
- **Mean Squared Error (MSE):** It represents the average of squared differences between predicted and actual values. This measure gives more weight to large errors compared to MAE.
- **Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE):** This measure is square root of MSE. It's in the same unit as the predicted and actual values, making it more interpretable.
- **Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE):** It represents the average percentage difference between predicted and actual values, calculated as the mean of the absolute percentage errors.

In order to evaluate the performance of the both models, three accuracy measures are used: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) and their equations are given below [6]:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (5)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (6)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{y_i} * 100\% \quad (7)$$

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Software selection

Combination of **R** programming language and **RStudio (version 2021.09.0 Build 351)**, as an IDE for the R, was chosen as a software tool for the purpose of this research. R is a very popular statistical programming language and environment widely used for statistical computing, data analysis and visualization. It contains many packages available through the R archive network called CRAN (<http://cran.r-project.org>) [7].

3.2 Data selection

Data for this research was collected from the sensor station which belongs to the type of network called "Proactive Networks" and was located in the municipality of Novi Sad Station. The data was taken in the period from January 2014 to December 2018. The sensors can be divided into six categories: sensors for measuring soil moisture (SM1, SM2, SM3, SM4, SM5, SM6), sensor for measuring humidity (AH1), sensor for measuring wind speed (WS1), sensor for measuring wind direction (WD1), sensor for measuring the air temperature (AT1), sensor for measuring precipitation (PP1) and sensor for measuring the state of battery power (BT1).

Sensors make recordings every hour so in total 288 recordings are made per day. After being recorded, data is sent to the web portal where it can be downloaded from in CSV format. There are 4 attributes in the data set which are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 - Attribute description

Attribute name	Description
Time	Time and date of the measured value
Device	Identification number of the device
ID value	Sensor identifier
Value	Measured value of a certain parameter

3.3. Data preparation

After being downloaded from web portal, data is converted and stored in a data frame. Data frame is fundamental data structure used for storing and organizing tabular data in R programming. After being stored, data is filtered and only relevant parameters such as air temperature, precipitation and soil moisture are extracted from the data set. Air temperature and Soil moisture time series are further aggregated using the „mean“ function for calculating the mean values. For Precipitation time series, the „sum“ function is used for calculating the sum values. Then, all values are sorted by months and years and converted into time series objects. In the end, obtained data set needs to be divided into two subsets where one will be used for building a model and the other one for model verification [8].

3.4. Data modeling

After being partitioned, data is used for building a predictive models. Two most popular methods were chosen, Seasonal Arima method and Holt-Winters exponential smoothing method. These methods will be used only for Temperature time series as an example. Function “*hw ()*”, which is a part of *forecast* package, is used for building a model with Holt-Winters method. Another function called “*Arima ()*” is used for building another model with seasonal Arima method.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Visual representation of the average temperatures is shown in Figure 1. Y-axis displays average temperatures in the period from January 2014 to December 2018. It can be seen that the temperature rises and falls depending on the season and that the lowest temperature was in January 2017 but oscillations in temperature are smaller on annual basis.

Figure 1 – Graphical representation of average temperatures

4.1. Results of the SARIMA method

After the function Arima is being applied, twelve models with different components are obtained. Based on the minimum values of AICc (Akaike Information Criteria corrected) and p values of the Ljung-Box test shown in Table 2, it is found that the best selected model for predicting the air temperature is ARIMA (0,0,0)(1,1,0)[12].

Table 2 – SARIMA models for time series Temperature

Model	AIC	AICc	BIC	Ljung-Box test
ARIMA (0,0,0)(1,1,0) _[12]	161.12	161.48	164.29	0.450
ARIMA (0,0,0)(0,1,1) _[12]	162.58	162.95	165.75	0.155
ARIMA (1,0,0)(0,1,0) _[12]	165.52	165.88	168.68	0.522
ARIMA (0,0,1)(0,1,0) _[12]	166.77	167.13	169.94	0.325
ARIMA (1,0,0)(1,1,0) _[12]	161.03	161.78	165.78	0.889
ARIMA (1,0,1)(1,1,1) _[12]	164.51	166.51	172.42	0.798
ARIMA (1,0,1)(0,1,1) _[12]	162.75	164.04	169.08	0.855
ARIMA (1,1,1)(1,1,1) _[12]	165.01	167.08	172.79	0.752
ARIMA (0,0,0)(1,1,1) _[12]	163.12	163.87	167.87	0.367
ARIMA (1,0,0)(1,1,1) _[12]	162.89	164.19	169.23	0.805
ARIMA (1,0,0)(0,1,1) _[12]	161.18	161.93	165.93	0.849
ARIMA (1,0,0)(1,1,0) _[12]	161.03	161.78	165.78	0.889

Forecast obtained from the best fitted SARIMA model is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Forecasts from ARIMA (0,0,0)x(1,1,0)_[12] model

4.2. Results of Holt-Winters method

Figure 2 shows predictions for time series Temperature from 2018-2019 for a period of 12 months. The original data is shown by the black line. Modeled data is shown by the purple dashed line while the predictions are shown by the blue line. The red line shows the test data which is used for verification of the selected model. According to the 95% confidence interval

which is shown by the dark gray lines and 80% confidence interval shown nby the lighter gray lines, it can be concluded that the forecasted values seem accurate and the modeled data folow the real data.

Figure 3 – Forecasts from Holt-Winters additive method

The estimated model components are:

- Level component: $l=13.1034$
- Trend component: $b=-0.0208$
- Seasonal component: $s= -10.237 -4.9735 -0.7281 5.8391 9.7491 10.726$
 $9.3542 4.951 0.1695 -4.2175 -7.8419 -12.7908$

4.3. Comparison between Holt-Winters and SARIMA models

Comparison between two models has been performed by using three measures of accuracy which are respectively MAE, RMSE and MAPE. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 – Accuracy measures for both models

Measure	ARIMA (0,0,0)x(1,1,0) _[12]	Holt-Winters
MAE	1.182155	1.26373
RMSE	1.749263	1.549957
MAPE	44.54082	36.56575

Table 3 indicates that the Holt-Winter method gives the minimum values for mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) and root mean squared error (RMSE), i.e. standard deviation. While both of the measures summarize the variability of the observations around the mean they are not in the same scale so the values cant be expected to be similar. Root mean squared error normally takes precendece over the other statistic measures and it can be a valid indicator of the quality of the model but when comparing between models, MAE or MAPE should also be concerned. Both RMSE and MAPE are lower in Holt-Winters model so we can conclude that the Holt-Winters model is the best to fit the data.

5. CONCLUSION

Arima and Holt-Winters method are two most popular methods for forecasting time series. The aim of this research was to show the methodology of selecting the best forecasting model based on certain metrics like RMSE, MAPE and MAE. The methodology was presented on meteorological data set of average temperature values. First step was to select the best Holt-Winters model and ARIMA model. During the analysis two selected models were obtained: ARIMA (0,0,0)(1,1,0)_[12] based on lowest AICc and Holt-Winters with additive seasonality and certain values of level, trend and seasonal component. The accuracy evaluation of both model was performed based on the used metrics and the conclusion is that the Holt-Winters model had lower MAPE and RMSE than Arima model and therefore it can be considered as the best model for forecasting the monthly values of the average temperatures. The future work would include improving the accuracy of the prediction model by collecting more data and tuning the model parameters.

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POSSIBILITIES FOR CURRICULA IMPROVEMENT IN THE FIELD OF LANDFILL LEACHATE MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This paper addresses the imperative of enhancing educational curricula in the field of landfill leachate management, with a special focus on integrating innovative tools like LandSim software. It begins by examining the environmental impacts of landfill leachate, highlighting the complexities and challenges in its management. The paper then explores the functionalities and educational benefits of LandSim, demonstrating how it bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. By incorporating LandSim into the curriculum, the paper argues for a more experiential and effective learning approach, better preparing students for real-world challenges in environmental management. The conclusion underscores the necessity of adopting such advanced tools in educational programs, emphasizing their role in equipping future professionals with the skills and knowledge required for effective leachate management and environmental sustainability.

Key words: Landfill Leachate, Environmental Education, Waste Management, Curricula Enhancement, LandSim Software

1. INTRODUCTION

The management of landfill leachate presents a significant environmental challenge, necessitating a comprehensive approach that spans technical expertise, policy development, and educational innovation. The increasing complexity of waste management, driven by both volume and diversity of waste, has brought landfill leachate into sharp focus [1]. This paper introduces the importance of advancing curricula in the field of landfill leachate management, underscoring the need for integrating modern tools and methodologies into educational programs.

Landfill leachate, the liquid that emanates from waste decomposition and percolates through landfill waste, carries a plethora of contaminants that can significantly impact soil, water, and air quality [2]. The first aim of this paper is to provide a thorough examination of leachate, focusing on its generation, composition, and the profound effects it can have on the environment. This study delves into the complex interactions between leachate and various environmental components, such as soil, groundwater, and surface water, exploring both the immediate and long-term implications of leachate contamination. The management and treatment of leachate are critical to minimizing these environmental impacts [3]. As such, the education and training of future professionals in this field are of paramount importance.

Current educational curricula in environmental science and engineering often lack practical, hands-on tools that can simulate real-world scenarios encountered in landfill leachate management. The integration of software tools, such as LandSim software, which models the generation and flow of leachate in landfills, offers an innovative approach to bridge this gap [4]. By incorporating such tools, educational institutions can provide students with a more realistic and applied understanding of the challenges and solutions in leachate management.

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Furthermore, this paper sets the stage for a detailed discussion on the environmental impacts of landfill leachate, the role of advanced software in education, and the need for curriculum enhancement to better prepare students for future challenges in this field..

2. CHARACTERISTICS OF LEACHATE

Leachate, a by-product of landfill operations, is a complex and variable liquid that poses significant environmental challenges. This chapter aims to dissect the multifaceted nature of leachate by examining its key characteristics, which are crucial for understanding its environmental impact and for devising effective treatment strategies.

2.1. Composition of Leachate

The composition of leachate is highly variable and depends on factors such as the age of the landfill, type of waste, climate conditions, and landfill management practices. Generally, leachate is characterized by high concentrations of organic matter, inorganic macro components, heavy metals, and xenobiotic organic compounds [5]. Organic components primarily include dissolved organic carbon (DOC), volatile fatty acids, and a wide range of other organic substances. Inorganic macro components typically found in leachate include ammonium, chloride, iron, and other heavy metals like cadmium, lead, and mercury. The presence of xenobiotic compounds, such as pharmaceuticals, pesticides, and other industrial chemicals, adds to the complexity of leachate [6].

2.2. Physicochemical Properties

The physicochemical properties of leachate, such as pH, conductivity, and turbidity, are indicative of its potential impact on the environment. Leachate typically exhibits a high biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD), reflecting its high organic content. The pH of leachate can vary widely, but it is typically alkaline due to the degradation of organic matter and the generation of ammonia [1].

2.3. Variability Over Time

The characteristics of leachate evolve over time. In the early stages of landfill development, termed the 'acid phase', leachate tends to have high organic strength and a low pH. As the landfill matures and enters the 'methanogenic phase', the concentration of organic matter decreases, and the pH tends to rise [7]. Understanding this temporal evolution is essential for the effective management and treatment of leachate.

2.4. Environmental Implications

The complex nature of leachate, with its high concentrations of potentially hazardous substances, poses a significant threat to environmental health. If not properly managed, leachate can contaminate soil, surface water, and groundwater, leading to severe ecological consequences [8]. The impact on aquatic ecosystems can be particularly detrimental, as leachate can disrupt the balance of aquatic life by introducing toxic substances and reducing oxygen levels in water bodies.

3. IMPACT OF LEACHATE ON ECOSYSTEMS

The environmental impact of leachate is both profound and multifaceted, affecting various aspects of ecosystems. This chapter aims to explore the consequences of leachate contamination on different environmental components, emphasizing the urgency for effective leachate management strategies. The influences of leachate can be divided into [8]:

- Impact on Groundwater
- Effect on Surface Water
- Soil Contamination
- Biodiversity and Ecosystem Health.

3.1. Impact on Groundwater

One of the most significant concerns associated with leachate is its potential to contaminate groundwater, a crucial resource for drinking water, agriculture, and industrial processes. The contamination of groundwater by leachate is a critical environmental issue, given the reliance of many communities and ecosystems on groundwater resources. The percolation of leachate through landfill liners and soil layers allows a cocktail of pollutants to seep into aquifers. This process can be exacerbated in areas with inadequate landfill design or poor waste management practices .

The pollutants in leachate, such as heavy metals (like arsenic, cadmium, and lead), organics (including persistent organic pollutants or POPs), and nitrates, can have far-reaching consequences on groundwater quality. These contaminants, once in the groundwater, can persist for long periods, often proving difficult to remediate due to their stability and the complexity of subsurface environments [9].

Furthermore, the interaction of leachate with the natural constituents of groundwater can lead to secondary pollution. For instance, the reduction-oxidation reactions can mobilize heavy metals, making them more bioavailable and toxic. Similarly, the breakdown of organic compounds in leachate can produce byproducts that are more harmful than the original pollutants [10].

The risk to human health from contaminated groundwater is significant. Pollutants from leachate can make their way into drinking water supplies, leading to a range of health issues, from acute poisoning to long-term chronic illnesses like cancer, kidney failure, and reproductive disorders. The risk is particularly acute in areas without adequate water treatment facilities, where the population relies directly on groundwater for drinking, cooking, and agriculture.

Additionally, the remediation of groundwater contaminated by leachate is often a complex, time-consuming, and costly endeavor. It requires a multifaceted approach, including continuous monitoring, the application of advanced water treatment technologies, and, in some cases, the complete abandonment of contaminated aquifers as a water source.

3.2. Effect on Surface Water

When leachate finds its way into surface water bodies such as rivers, lakes, and wetlands, it can lead to several detrimental effects. The high organic load in leachate can cause eutrophication, characterized by excessive growth of algae and aquatic plants. This overgrowth can deplete oxygen levels in the water, leading to the death of fish and other aquatic organisms [8].

3.3. Soil Contamination

Leachate can adversely affect soil quality and its ability to support plant life. The accumulation of heavy metals and other toxic substances in the soil can lead to decreased soil fertility, alteration in soil pH, and harm to microorganisms vital for soil health. This contamination not only impacts plant growth but can also enter the food chain, posing risks to wildlife and human health [11].

3.4. Biodiversity and Ecosystem Health

The contamination of ecosystems with leachate can lead to a loss of biodiversity. Toxic substances in leachate can harm or kill various species, leading to shifts in ecological communities and the disruption of food webs. The long-term exposure to pollutants from leachate can also result in genetic mutations and a decrease in reproductive success among wildlife.

4. EDUCATIONAL TOOL IN LANDFILL LEACHATE MANAGEMENT

The integration of specialized software tools like LandSim in educational curricula represents a significant advancement in the field of landfill leachate management. This chapter delves into the functionalities of LandSim, its role in enhancing educational outcomes, and the benefits it offers in bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application.

4.1. Overview of LandSim

LandSim is a sophisticated software tool designed for simulating the leachate generation, migration, and management in landfill sites. It employs advanced algorithms and modeling techniques to provide realistic scenarios, enabling students to visualize and understand the complex processes involved in leachate management. The tool is capable of simulating various conditions and scenarios, such as leachate leakage, varying landfill designs, and contaminant travel times, offering a comprehensive understanding of the challenges in leachate management [11]–[13]. LandSim allows for the export of certain values calculated during the simulation for further processing outside of LandSim. The LandSim output data, which can be useful in education about predicting events at a landfill, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 – Outputs from LandSim [14]

Property	Output
Hydraulics	Leachate head
	Leakage through the liner and dilution in the aquifer
	Leachate flow and any surface breakout
Travel times	Time for peak concentrations at specified receptors
Contaminant concentrations	In the leachate source
	At the base of the unsaturated zone
	At the monitoring well
	At the compliance point for the whole site

These types of output data are necessary to determine the impact of landfills on the environment, and thus assist future experts in this field to identify preventive measures that could be implemented during the design of landfills.

4.2. Educational Benefits of LandSim

The incorporation of LandSim into the landfill leachate management curriculum offers several educational benefits. It facilitates a hands-on learning experience, allowing students to engage with real-world problems and apply theoretical knowledge in a practical context. By working with LandSim, students can experiment with different management strategies, observe the outcomes, and understand the implications of their decisions. This experiential learning approach is invaluable in developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

One of the key challenges in environmental education is the gap between theoretical knowledge and its practical application. LandSim serves as a bridge, providing students with a practical tool that they can use to apply their theoretical understanding in a simulated environment. This helps in reinforcing core concepts and principles in landfill leachate management, making the learning process more engaging and effective.

By integrating software tools into the curriculum, educational institutions can better prepare students for their future roles as environmental professionals. The experience gained from using LandSim equips students with the skills and knowledge required to address real-world challenges in landfill leachate management. This prepares them not only to effectively manage leachate in their professional careers but also to innovate and develop new strategies for environmental protection.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper has explored the multifaceted aspects of landfill leachate management, emphasizing the critical need for curriculum enhancement in environmental education, particularly in the integration of advanced software tools like LandSim. The comprehensive analysis of the environmental impacts of landfill leachate, presented in the earlier chapters, underscores the complexity and significance of this issue.

Through the exploration of LandSim's capabilities, we have demonstrated how such innovative tools can revolutionize the educational landscape. By bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, LandSim provides students with a hands-on, experiential learning experience. This approach not only reinforces their understanding of key concepts in landfill leachate management but also equips them with vital skills necessary for addressing real-world environmental challenges.

The integration of LandSim into environmental protection curricula represents a significant step forward in preparing future professionals. As environmental challenges continue to evolve, it is imperative that educational institutions respond by adopting such innovative tools and methodologies. This will ensure that the next generation of environmental professionals is well-equipped to manage landfill leachate effectively and contribute to the broader goal of environmental sustainability.

In conclusion, the enhancement of landfill leachate management curricula, coupled with the integration of advanced tools like LandSim, is not just an educational imperative but a necessity for the future of environmental management. As the world moves forward, it is crucial that such innovative approaches become standard practice in environmental education, ensuring that students are adequately prepared to meet the challenges of tomorrow's world.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION ON THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN PRINTING INDUSTRY

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Abstract: Circular economy in printing industry imply establishing economic system of production and consumption based on the reuse and regeneration of raw materials and nus products, especially by means of sustainable or environmentally friendly printing processes. Education on the circular economy in the printing industry is oriented toward teaching methods and techniques for achieving savings in the production process and fulfillment of legal norms in the field of occupational health and environmental protection. The most common application of circular economy in printing industry is through the 3R principle (Reduce – Reuse – Recycle), which is strongly applicable in material balance and waste minimalization. As a part of the educational process, this paper presents several examples of good manufacturing practice in circular economy in printing industry, not just because of compliance with legal obligations, but to achieve economic benefits.

Key words: circular economy, printing industry, education, 3R principle, economic benefits

1. INTRODUCTION

Printing is a process of reproducing original (text or/and images) on the material substrate (paper, cardboard, plastic, foils, textile, metal, glass...). Printing industry presents mass production process and an essential part of the publishing industry worldwide [1]. Beside printing industry, there is also digital (electronic) publishing (digital visual media, electronic books, social networks, commercials...) as a part of the global publishing world. To stay in its status of huge importance, the printing industry must respond to some global challenges – to stay competitive, low-cost, environmentally friendly, but still actual and up to date with the modern world and new arrivals. The printing industry understands how important it is for everyone in the production process (from suppliers to dealing with wastes and effluents) to do their part in making sure they conserve the planet for future generations [2]. Sustainability means access to and use of natural resources in a way that fulfills economic and commercial needs while still preserving them for future generations [2]. That is why it is so important for students – future experts in this field to get useful competencies, such as knowledge of the production process itself (technical aspects of print production) and to have basic knowledge in economics as well. In the printing industry, several avenues for sustainability exist, including the materials (substrate and inks) or equipment used for printing, the printing process itself, and the management of waste. Main goals and principles of sustainable printing industry (and graphic industry in general) are [3]:

- fidelity of reproduction – quality and accuracy of the whole print run (performance);
- attractiveness and usage value of the printed product (design as well);
- high productivity (printing speed, serviceability of graphic machines and devices);
- high degree of process automation and usage of digital workflows;
- competitive price of the final printed product and
- respect for the principles of safety at work and environmental protection.

One of the most important tasks of the graphic industry in the implementation of environmental protection measures is the responsible and rational use of resources: energy, water and air, basic raw materials (paper and paint) and auxiliary raw materials. This principle is binding for all participants in the graphic production chain: printers, manufacturers of printing systems, subcontractors in printing houses and companies dealing with waste treatment [3].

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2. IMPLEMENTING SUSTAINABILITY AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN PRINTING INDUSTRY

Since 1993, significant improvements have been made at the level of the global graphics industry in relation to sustainability and environmental protection. Nowadays, there are several compelling business motivations for adopting sustainable practices in the printing industry (improving efficiency and productivity also often coincides with becoming more sustainable). According to Forbes, in many places around the world, companies can take advantage of tax credits and financial incentives when they become more sustainable. Besides that, the modern consumer of printed products prefers more environmentally conscious brands - more than 65 % of consumers of printed products consider sustainability when making purchasing decisions [2]. The need for more sustainable printing practices is important not just for preserving the environment, but in a business sense as well, because sustainability brings significant economic benefits in production (savings in raw materials and energy, decrease of pollutant emission, decrease of injuries at work and professional diseases). On its way towards more sustainable production, printing companies should implement efficient technologies and eco-friendly materials, as well as to make improvements in equipment, design, and logistical practices to contribute to the reduction of carbon emissions.

2.1. Implementing 3R principle

The general principles and goals in the implementation of environmental protection and the introduction of sustainability in the graphic/printing industry are based on the 3R principle (Reduce, Reuse & Recycle). Reduce means reducing the generation of waste to the smallest possible extent (e.g. waste minimization, reduce leaks and involuntary spills of liquid and gaseous fluids, improve the sealing of pipelines and tanks, re-use of already used raw materials where possible). Table 1 presents waste minimization methods for the Commercial printing industry [4].

Table 1 – Waste minimization methods for the commercial printing industry [4]

Operation	Waste minimization methods
Material Handling and Storage	Material pre-inspection, proper storage of materials, restrict traffic through area, inventory control, purchase quantities according to needs, recycle empty containers, recycle photographic film and paper
Image Processing	Electronic imaging and laser platemaking, material substitution, extend bath life (e.g. use of squeegees), employ countercurrent washing, recover silver and recycle chemicals
Plate Processing	Reduce solution loss, replace metal etching/plating operations, use non-hazardous developers and finishers
Makeready	Implement accurate counting methods, automated plate benders, scanners, automatic ink key setting system, computerized registration, ink/water ratio sensor
Printing	Install web break detectors, automatic web splicers, use automatic ink levelers, store ink properly, use less hazardous inks, standard ink sequence, recycle waste ink, use alternative fountain solutions, use alternative cleaning solvents, automatic blanket cleaners, reduce the need to clean, improve cleaning efficiency, collect and reuse solvent, recycle lube oils, alternative printing techniques
Finishing	Reduce paper use and recycle wastepaper, sort waste on site

Second letter R in 3R principle means Reuse - to re-use everything that can be returned to the process and reused (e.g., installation of ventilation systems and systems for the recovery of useful substances from waste streams). Recycle, i.e., using waste matter as a secondary raw material in some other production process (e.g., wastepaper, which represents waste for a printing house, is also a raw material to produce cardboard from recycled fibers). Recycling plays a massive role in ensuring

excessive waste products from printing companies get into the recycling stream [5]. Some items that printers can recycle include paper, cardboard, plastics, and other containers, while other recyclables include metal plates, cylinder boxes, and pallets. None of these belong in landfill, and when directed into the recycling stream, they continue to live again, helping to keep the circular economy in motion [5].

2.2. Increasing carbon emissions (greenhouse gases balance)

One of the most important aims in reaching sustainability in the printing industry is carbon balanced printing. Carbon (CO₂) emissions produced in the process of printing can be quantified and compared by printing companies themselves. Carbon balancing is achieved when the CO₂ produced during the entire paper and printer production and delivery have been offset; so, there are carbon balanced printers and carbon balanced papers in the market to make printing more sustainable [2]. Printing houses can measure their carbon footprint and take steps to reduce and offset it; WLT performs carbon balancing by conserving ecologically important forests under imminent threat of clearance [6]. They claim that using carbon balanced paper and printers is one of the most sustainable print solutions available today. While this method may seem simple - just like using recycled paper as a raw material, it goes a step further. To produce recycled paper, mills still use fresh fibers from new trees. When these fibers are obtained from sustainably managed forests, the overall carbon emissions are reduced [2].

An example of good practice in Serbia with the aim of achieving sustainable graphic production (and reducing CO₂ emissions) is represented by a company that produces printed and laminated cardboard packaging and blister cardboard for products from various industries, which expect well-designed, quality printed, reliable, on time completed and delivered package [7]. This company is committed to achieving zero GHG impact on the environment, and regularly measures its impact and transparently reports it to the public. In 2023, this company prepared and presented its first publicly available published report on the GHG inventory, and the activities it implements to reduce its emissions with the goal of achieving zero CO₂ emissions.

Figure 1 – Greenhouse gases (GHG) generation in industrial companies, including printing industry [8]

LEGEND: **Scope 1** - Direct emissions from owned or controlled sources;

Scope 2 - Indirect emissions from the generation of acquired and consumed electricity, steam, heat, or cooling;

Scope 3 - All indirect emissions (not included in Scope 2) that occur in the value chain of the reporting company, including both upstream and downstream emissions

2.3. Usage of sustainable (eco-friendly) printing inks

Printing ink has the ultimate impact on the final press sheet. Content of pigments in inks, and the content of additives are the most dominant factors influencing the quality of final printed product. Aside from making the process more efficient and using sustainably produced papers, companies can also take advantage of more eco-friendly inks for sustainable printing, based on raw materials like vegetables (soy ink is among the most popular of these eco-friendly options) [2]. Printing inks contain different kinds of organic and inorganic matter, which can be emitted to the air (so called VOC – volatile organic compounds), soil and water, sometimes causing long-lasting damage to the environment, while toxic and dangerous vapors from inks violate quality of working surrounding and present the threat for employees in printing facilities [9]. Almost four billion kilograms of ink is used annually for printing around the world, which means almost 800 million kilograms of petroleum-based pigment in conventional inks. Eco-friendly inks forgot the very limited petroleum as raw material and are made from alternative, such as innovative ink created from algae; this ink can only produce a limited range of colors, but many organizations are already using it [2].

Colors based on vegetable oils are used only in the offset printing technique. Paints based on soybean oil can replace 20-40% of alcohol-based paints. The reduction of VOC when applying paints based on soybean oil reaches as much as 80%. This percentage is lower if solvents are still used during cleaning. Paints based on soybean oil are significantly more expensive than alcohol-based paints and require a longer drying time, without increasing the drying heat [9]. Drying time can be shortened by using conventional dryers or electric sprayers. The advantages of vegetable oil-based paints are [9]:

- lower emissions of VOC into the atmosphere, compared to traditional paints (depending on the percentage of soybean oil in the paint);
- washing cylinders and containers can be done with the help of water-based chemicals or detergents, which reduces the use of highly concentrated solutions of various chemicals;
- smaller amounts of wastepaper, since the balance of color and wetting agent is easier to achieve;
- a more uniform layer of paint on the board is achieved faster;
- acceptable portability and reduced foaming on the printing plate;
- darker black shades and lighter colors, due to better color retention.

The negative sides of using soy oil-based colors are longer drying time, higher costs compared to standard colors and more demanding adjustment before printing, as well as employee training.

In the case of water-based printing inks, the solvent component is replaced by water, whereby the organic component of the solvent is eliminated, and the share of VOC emissions is reduced. The use of these colors is limited due to the impossibility of drying the color on non-absorbent printing substrates [9]. The best application of these colors is in flexo printing, intaglio and screen printing (on a textile substrate). The use of organic solvents is very low in these paints, although the use of pigments with heavy metals is still present. The main advantages of these colors are a low level of fire hazard and better printing conditions, taking into account the reduction of VOC emissions. The disadvantage of these paints is that the drying time is extended, and the resulting print is of poor durability.

3. EDUCATION ON THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN PRINTING INDUSTRY

To accelerate the circular economy in industry and all aspects of living, it is important for it to be presented everywhere, in people's everyday lives, whether in transport, reuse, repair, waste prevention, food and consumers behaviors and decision-making about supporting local businesses, circular designs and sustainability every day [10]. Working methods and tools for eco-efficiency in the graphic industry should be industry-specific, with environmental information and knowledge of the current production circumstances and products, tailored to small and medium sized enterprises (SME) and simple in the sense of being easy to use [11].

Achieving sustainability by applying circular economy in industrial processes demands a multidisciplinary approach, from good insight in technical details concerning production process itself, to economics and management. Obtaining sustainability is based on teamwork among experts in the field, thus it needs competent staff, with the demanded skills, knowledge, and competencies.

The evaluation of the competences of graduated engineers in the field of environmental protection, sustainable production and circular economy, carried out by mentors from business organizations during the students' professional practice and the preparation of final exam, established the areas in which the students do not have enough knowledge, and which should be improved [12]:

- knowledge of the theoretical principles of water, air and soil purification technology;
- knowledge of waste management procedures;
- knowledge of strategic planning, related to sustainable production;
- students lack more practice and
- students should be specially trained in the field of legal regulations in circular economy.

4. CONCLUSION

Achieving sustainability by applying circular economy in printing industry demands a multidisciplinary approach, from good insight in technical details concerning production process itself, to economics and management. On its way towards more sustainable production, printing companies should implement efficient technologies and eco-friendly materials, as well as to make improvements in equipment, design, and logistical practices to contribute to the reduction of carbon emissions. One of the most important tasks of the graphic industry, it's employees and management in the implementation of environmental protection measures is the responsible and rational use of resources: energy, water and air, basic raw materials (paper and paint) and auxiliary raw materials. Obtaining sustainability is based on teamwork among experts in the field, thus it needs competent staff, with the demanded skills, knowledge, and competencies. In the education for sustainable production in Serbia, some improvements are identified to be implemented, mainly in the field of soft skills and more practical work in the field.

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WORK OUTSIDE LOCALISED WORKPLCE/WORK ENTITY – BRIEFLY ANALYSE OF ACTUAL CONCEPTS PERCEPTIONS

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Abstract: The paper is a comparative analysis of actually perception/understanding of next concepts: „work at home” (WAH)/ “homeworking” (HW), „telework/ICT-mobile work” (T/ICTM) and „remote working” (RW). The analysis is based on studies of Romanian national law, EU and ILO regulations, and reports and different dedicated scientific papers indexed in databases. Based on results, the most important conclusion was a random approach of such concepts, determined by a lot of factors: economical, technical, social, etc. Also, the necessity to standardize the normative framework and to extend the regulatory topic area, simultaneously with the study of the new and specific elements of generated occupational risks were justified.

Key words: work outside localized work place, work at home, telework, remote working, analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

The idea of work outside localized workplace (work entity), is relatively old. In 1973, Jack M. Nilles, from University of Southern California, coined the term of telecommuting „to refer to the partial or total substitution of telecommunications, with or without the assistance of computers, for the twice-daily commute to work” [1]. Later, in 1988, Nilles précised the „telecommuting is a subset of teleworking” [2], another coined concept for including „all work-related substitutions of telecommunications and related information technologies for travel”. In 1979 year, IBM started the experimental work at home with 5 employees, estimating an increasing the number to 2000 employees till 1983.

Do the development of Information Technologies (conference calling, video telephony, internet access, cloud computing, mobile telecommunications, etc.), IT equipment (laptop, tablet computers, smartphones, etc.), and adequate specialized soft (Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Google Meet, WhatsApp, etc.), after 1990-year different work outside localized workplace forms were developed in different concepts: telework, mobile work, work at home, nomadic work, remote work, online work, e-Work, etc.[3]. At the same time, various professions use such work: managers, technicians, programmers, customer services staff, consultants, marketers, purchasing agents, market investigators, publishers, journalists, interprets, brokers, accountants, and others.

In the developing process of work outside localized workplace can be identified two „waves of accelerations”: the first oil crisis from 1973 and the COVID-19 pandemic crisis. Of course, the speed and acceleration were different; the work outside localized workplace was well known after the pandemic impact in generalized society. Even the pandemic restrictions are not valuable, remain very important the necessity for transports’ reduction, and their impact on environment protection and cost saving.

The first ‘classical’ logo appears in 1995: "work is something you do, not something you travel to" or „work is what we do, not where we are" [6]. The most favorable criteria already mentioned was the significant impact of technology on the work [4], and the fact of work done from home and other different locations [5].

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Other benefits can be determined by:

- Cost saving regarding office maintenance and facilities;
- Increasing of work productivity, [6];
- Increasing of employments' loyalty and recruitment area;
- More access to employments' relocation, without change sets in contract, etc.

Even in main European countries the work outside localized workplace- on different innovative forms- are well-known, in Romania, as well as other former East-European countries, it is expanding very slowly. Figure 1 presents the percent of employees working outside localized workplace all over the world in 2019. It can be observed high disparities between different regions and countries.

Figure 1 – Employees working outside localised workplace in 2019, (based on [7])

Based on EU statistics, in 2022 a percentage of 10,2% from EU employees worked, usual, from home [8]. But there are great disparities between countries, on the first place is Ireland (25,3%), and on the last place is Romania (1,4 %), [8]. But do the last position, Romanian efforts to reduce the gap with other EU countries, and the integrated management from a lot of organizations it is predictable that the number of employees who work from home will increase in the next period.

The paper aims to realize a synthesis of actual approaches regarding the perceptions of the concepts developed regarding work outside localized workplace: work at home (telecommuting), telework, and remote work.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

Figure 1 – The methodological steps

The methodological steps are presented in figure 2, where next abbreviations were used: EU – European Union; ILO – International Labour Organization; IDB – Indexed Databases.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on methodology, after the consulting of bibliography, the results were grouped on each concept in different tables, according to the objective of the paper.

Table 1 – Results for analysis of the concept „work at home” (WAH)/ “homeworking” (HW)

Consulted document		The given definition of the concept	Obs
Name of the document	Address of the document		
Law.53/2003 Romania	Monitorul Oficial	Employees perform their duties specific to the position at their home and the working schedule is at the discretion of the employees	
ILO- Defining and measuring remote work, telework, work at home and home-based work	https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---stat/documents/publication/wcms_747075.pdf/	Home at work refers to work carried out, whole or in part, at the worker's own residence. The work at home category is independent of the default place of work, but might overlap where the worker's home is both the place where the work is carried out and the premises of the economic unit (in the case of an independent worker who has an office at home, for example).	
Morganson V, Major D, Oborn K, et al. (2010) Comparing telework locations and traditional work arrangements: Differences in work-life balance support, job satisfaction and inclusion. Jrn. Man. Ps.25(6): 578–595	https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Debra-Major/publication/228358052_Comparing_Telework_Locations_and_Traditional_Work_Arrangements_Differences_in_Work-Life_Balance_Support_Job_Satisfaction_and_Inclusion/links/53e501b50cf25d674e953076/Comparing-Telework-Locations-and-Traditional-Work-Arrangements-Differences-in-Work-Life-Balance-Support-Job-Satisfaction-and-Inclusion.pdf	Men and women employed in organisations who perform some of their usual paid hours at home as part of flexibility or ‘teleworking’ arrangements approved by employers.	
Playing catch up? An exploration of supplementary work at home among Australian public servants	https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0022185618769340#bibr25-0022185618769340	Work at home is now most commonly performed outside of normal working hours on an informal, ad hoc basis, to prepare for or catch up on tasks workers usually perform in the workplace.	
Leaveism at work. Occupational Medicine	https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/full-record/WOS:000335896200001?SID=EUW1ED0A2FMUeLtdDEg6G8F5GYNWI	Working at home can also involve the employees preparing for or reaching assignments, before or after their regular office hours, or keeping up with work while on vacation.	
Working at Home The Impacts of COVID 19 on Health, Family-Work-Life Conflict, Gender, and Parental Responsibilities	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34325437/	Remote work can be in different forms, including work based partly at home and partly in the office. Full-time work at home, work performed mainly from home, independently for several employers, work performed at several different locations and work performed at a distance from the employer's premises.	
A.Powell, L. Craig Gender differences in working at home and time use patterns...	http://eprints.lincoln.ac.uk/id/eprint/39969/1/Powell%20%26%20Craig%20%282015%29%20Gender%20WAH.pdf	Working at home is most common in managerial and professional occupations and in knowledge-intensive industries	

Each table presents the consulted (studied) documents and the obtained results for definition of the concept. Table 1 presents the results for analysis of the concept „work at home”. Table 2 presents the selection of obtained results regarding analysis of the concept „telework”. Finally, the selection of obtained results regarding analysis of the concept „remote working” is presented in Table 3.

Based on study results can be observed important differences of the perception for the concepts considered. Perception of the concept work at home (WAH) is generally the same at EU, ILO and Romanian law. Also, many papers have the same perception, some of them try to introduce in potential definition ideas concerning characteristics, not defintory elements.

A lot of confusions can be identified between perception of telework and remote work.

Actually, only ILO specifications make a clearly differences between both concepts and give complete definitions.

Table 2 – Results for analysis of the concept „telework”/ICT-„mobile work” (T/ICTM)

Consulted document		The given definition of the concept	Obs.
Name of the document	Name of the document		
Law 81/2018 Romania	https://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocumentAfis/199418	The work by which, on a regular and voluntary basis, they fulfil the duties specific to the function, occupation or trade they hold in a place other than the place of work organized by the employer, using information and communication technology.	
Conclusions of the Council regarding telework	https://data.consilium.europa.eu/	Work that uses information and communication technology and is performed outside the employer's workplace	
ILO-Defining and measuring remote work, telework, work at home and home-based work	https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---stat/documents/publication/wcms_747075.pdf/	I. The work is fully or partly carried out at an alternative location other than the default place of work. This criterion is based on the previous definition of remote work. II. The use of personal electronic devices such as a computer, tablet or telephone (mobile or landline) to perform the work: The use of personal electronic devices needs to be an essential part of carrying out the work. (Eurofound and ILO 2017, p. 5). The different devices or tools can be used for communicating with colleagues, clients and so on, as well for carrying out specific job-related tasks without being directly in contact with other persons.	
Emerging workplaces in post-functional cities. J. Urban Technol	https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/10630732.2017.1297520	Teleworking, also called telecommuting, refers to working, partly or entirely, from home or in an alternative location, such as a nearby library or coffee bar, as opposed to a centralized workplace at a remote location	
The impact of teleworking on work motivation in a U.S. federal government agency. The Am. Rev. of Pub. Adm.	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254078354_The_Impact_of_Teleworking_on_Work_Motivation_in_a_US_Federal_Government_Agency	With telecommuting, employees have been given the opportunity to perform some or all of their tasks at home or at an alternate location	
Di Martino V, Wirth L. Telework: a new way of working and living. Int Labor Rev 1990; 129:529	https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/intlr129&div=54&id=&page=	Before the COVID 19 pandemic, telework was conceptualized as an agreed work arrangement to support flexible workload management and usually undertaken by choice and agreed between the worker and the employer.	
The differences of firm resources and the adoption of teleworking	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0166497205000726	Telecommuting uses more flexible HR practices and variable compensation, outsources more activities, and manages employees by goals	

Table 3 – Results for analysis of the concept „remote working” (RW)

Consulted document		Consulted document	Obs.
Name of the document	Name of the document		
The Janus Face of the ‘New Ways of Work’. Rise, Risks and Regulation of Nomadic Work. ETUI, Working Paper	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/268220250_The_Janus_Face_of_the_'New_Ways_of_Work'_Rise_Risks_and_Regulation_of_Nomadic_Work	Remote work has led to the emergence of the "virtual, invisible, work-everywhere employee"	
Managing Telework: Strategies for Managing the Virtual Workforce. New York: John Wiley and Sons	https://www.worldcat.org/title/managing-telework-strategies-for-managing-the-virtual-workforce/oclc/902121564	Assigning jobs to employees rather than assigning employees to jobs	
Implementation of the European Framework Agreement on Telework	http://erc-online.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/2006-01429-EN	Remote working is defined as a type of work arrangement whereby work that could be performed at the employer's premises is regularly performed elsewhere, through the use of information technology.	
ILO-Defining and measuring remote work, telework, work at home and home-based work	https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---stat/documents/publication/wcms_747075.pdf/	However, remote work can be described as situations where the work is fully or partly carried out on an alternative worksite other than the default place of work. Remote work can be performed in a variety of possible locations, all of which can be viewed as an alternative to the location where the work could typically be	

		expected to be carried out taking into account the profession and the status in employment.	
Telework: A new way of working and living	https://heinonline.org/HOL/LandingPage?handle=hein.journals/intr129&div=54&id=&page=	Remote work is defined as a flexible work arrangement that allows an employee to work from a remote location outside of corporate offices or manufacturing facilities, without personal contact with co-workers, but with the ability to communicate with them via means of information and communication technologies	
Teleworking: Benefits and Pit-falls as Perceived by Professionals and Managers. New Technology, Work and Employment,	https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Teleworking%3A-benefits-and-pitfalls-as-perceived-by-Baruch/524d87da5e90c69f6a61b26df86a3555ba927b45	Remote work is just work done from home	
K.S.Allen, D.Grelle, E.M. Lazarus, E.Popp, S.L. Gutierrez - Hybrid is here to stay: Critical behaviors for success in the new world of work	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0191886923003823?ref=cra_js_challenge&fr=RR-1	The shift to remote and hybrid working requires not only adjusting to new technologies for remote collaboration but also adjusting fundamental behaviors in day-to-day work.	

4. CONCLUSIONS

The present analysis generates a first conclusion regarding a random approach of the three concepts, determined by a lot of factors: economical (level of are development), technical (level of IT&C introduction), social (perception, culture, social system etc.), etc.

Another important conclusion suggests the need to develop some standards in the specific field to clearly regulate these concepts, so as to facilitate the exchange of information and solutions in the event of the appearance of some aspects of negative impact.

In the same time present results justify the necessity to standardize the normative framework and to extend the regulatory topic area, simultaneously with the study of the new and specific elements of generated occupational risks. Also new assessment methods are necessary.

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STRATEGY FOR REDUCING CARBON FOOTPRINT IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND THE PATH TOWARDS THE GREEN AGENDA

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Abstract: This paper delves into strategies addressing the reduction of carbon footprints within higher education institutions in alignment with the imperative objectives of the Green Agenda. Considering impending European directives mandating actions against climate change, the study explores viable plans and methodologies for curbing greenhouse gas emissions in these educational settings. Emphasizing the pivotal role of education and research, it assesses the significance of institutional engagement in fostering sustainability and outlines actionable strategies guiding these establishments toward meeting the Green Agenda's objectives. Through a systematic review encompassing timeframes, analytical methods, emission sources, and mitigation plans, this paper aims to facilitate the transition of higher education institutions towards a more sustainable future.

Key words: timeframe, analytical methods, emission sources, reduction plans, higher education institutions, sustainable future.

1. INTRODUCTION

Developing strategies to reduce carbon footprint has become crucial due to increasing environmental preservation demands, especially within higher education institutions. The European Union is directing efforts towards reducing greenhouse gas emissions, thereby imposing obligations on higher education institutions to take steps in that direction. This paper explores the necessity of adapting educational environments to new sustainability standards, providing insight into key strategies and methods that could be implemented [1]. The carbon footprint, as an environmental pollution indicator, has become a primary focus in addressing climate change. Higher education institutions, as centers for education and research, have the potential to become key drivers of change towards a more sustainable future. This paper will explore various approaches, tools, and strategies that can support the transition of higher education institutions towards a more sustainable environment, providing a comprehensive overview of current practices, analytical methods, and emission sources. This goal stands as one of the key pillars in global efforts to preserve the planet and create a more sustainable society. Additionally, in anticipation of the challenges posed by Chapter 27, this paper aims to stimulate all relevant stakeholders to contribute to reducing the carbon footprint within higher education institutions [2].

2. CURENT STATE OF CARBON FOOTPRINT IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITTIONS

The current status of carbon footprint in higher education institutions can significantly vary between institutions in Serbia and those in the European Union (EU). In Serbia, progress in monitoring and disclosing carbon footprints within the education sector may be less pronounced compared to EU countries, where stricter guidelines and sustainability requirements are often established [3]. One of the key differences may lie in the level of awareness regarding the need to monitor carbon footprint. In EU countries, regulations, government support, and awareness of climate change often encourage higher education institutions to thoroughly monitor their carbon footprint and publish results. Conversely, in Serbia, where this issue might receive less attention due to other priorities or less pressure from regulators, there might be lower transparency or less detailed documentation regarding carbon footprint. Approaches to carbon footprint analysis and measurement can also vary. Institutions in the EU often

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utilize standardized methods and tools for assessment, leading to greater consistency and comparable accuracy of data. In contrast, in Serbia, there might be more variations in methodologies and less standardization, posing challenges for comparing and analyzing data across different higher education institutions [4].

In summary, differences in the current status of carbon footprint among higher education institutions in Serbia and EU countries may stem from variations in regulations, sustainability awareness, measurement and analysis approaches, as well as the support institutions receive from relevant bodies or governments.

2.1 Connectivity of Higher Education Institutions with Initiatives for Reducing Carbon Footprint

In the European Union (EU), higher education institutions are often directly linked to initiatives aimed at reducing carbon footprint through projects, research, and programs focusing on sustainability and climate change. One example includes the EU's Erasmus+ programs, which support various education-related projects, including higher education, emphasizing sustainability and reducing environmental impact. Through these projects, higher education institutions can collaborate on innovative initiatives, exchange knowledge and best practices, and develop curricula emphasizing sustainability and ecological impact. For instance, there might be projects where multiple universities from different EU countries unite to explore specific methods to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in their operations, employing new technologies or resource management practices. These projects typically encourage experience sharing and the development of shared solutions applicable at a broader level, contributing to the EU's sustainability goals. Such programs promote institutional engagement in reducing carbon footprint and encourage them to become leaders in sustainable development [5].

As part of the KA220 project GREENES, AATPS Niš has included one activity focusing on reducing the carbon footprint of higher education institutions. Together with the University of Maribor and the University of Bitola, it is tasked with presenting this as one of the partnership project's outcomes.

2.2 Carbon Footprint Analysis

Carbon footprint analysis involves quantifying greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions produced directly or indirectly by an institution, providing insight into its overall environmental impact. Key points of analysis include the methodology used to estimate GHG emissions. Employing standardized methods such as the IPCC handbook ensures consistency and result validity. Identifying emission sources (such as energy systems, transportation, and waste management) is crucial for understanding where the bulk of emissions originate.

The subsequent section tracks sectors with the most significant impact by identifying those with the highest GHG emissions, aiding in prioritizing reduction measures. Following this is the assessment of GHG emission factors from various sources to comprehend their relative harm and influence on the overall footprint.

Developing specific strategies to reduce emissions may involve implementing energy efficiency, transitioning to renewable energy sources, or changes in transportation and resource management. Carbon footprint analysis enables institutions to identify key areas for improvement and set goals for emission reduction, representing critical steps toward a more sustainable future [6].

3. INNOVATIONS AND TRANSFORMATIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS TOWARDS A CARBON FREE SOCIETY

Innovations and transformations of higher education institutions toward a carbon-free society are becoming increasingly crucial in light of global efforts to combat climate change. These institutions are recognized as catalysts for change, wielding significant influence in shaping future generations and societal norms regarding sustainability.

The shift toward a carbon-free society demands a multidimensional approach. This entails adopting innovative technologies and practices that reduce greenhouse gas emissions in all aspects of institutional operations: from energy efficiency in buildings and infrastructure to transportation, resource utilization, and integration of renewable energy sources.

Higher education institutions also play a pivotal role in raising awareness and educating students and the broader community about climate change and sustainability. Through educational programs, research, and public campaigns, these institutions can mold new generations of leaders and experts dedicated to addressing environmental challenges.

Innovations are also reflected in partnerships with industry and local communities to develop practical solutions. This enables higher education institutions to become centers of excellence in researching and implementing sustainable technologies and practices.

The transition toward a carbon-free society requires comprehensive engagement and changes in the structure and culture of higher education institutions. This transformation is not only a strategic goal but also a moral responsibility toward current and future generations [5, 6].

3.1 Shortcomings and Differences in Carbon Footprint Collection and Disclosure

In the collection and disclosure of carbon footprints within higher education institutions, significant drawbacks and disparities exist, complicating data comparison or standardization. Some of these challenges encompass three key aspects:

- **Diverse methodologies and standards:** Higher education institutions often employ different methodologies to calculate their carbon footprints, impeding data comparison. Lack of standardization can lead to inconsistent results.
- **Variability in reporting:** Institutions may have distinct approaches to reporting their emissions. Some provide only partial information or focus on specific emission aspects, complicating a comprehensive understanding of the overall impact.
- **Disparities in coverage and scope:** Differences in considering types of emissions (direct or indirect) and which sectors or parts of institutions are analyzed can result in varying levels and types of reporting.

Regarding official statistical data, their availability can vary and is often limited due to different approaches in collecting and disclosing carbon footprint data among higher education institutions. International organizations such as the Global University Network for Innovation (GUNi) or UNESCO collect sustainability data of higher education institutions, yet this data is often aggregated and may lack detailed information on the carbon footprints of each individual institution.

To overcome these shortcomings, greater standardization, alignment of methodologies, and adoption of common standards for collecting and disclosing carbon footprint data within higher education institutions are necessary. This would enable more accurate comparisons and a comprehensive assessment of the ecological impact of these institutions.

4. THE PATH TO THE GREEN AGENDA AND INSPIRATION FOR STUDENT

The path toward the Green Agenda in higher education institutions represents the adoption of sustainable practices and values that support ecological sustainability. Inspiring students, as key players in the future, plays yet another significant role in this domain.

Through sustainability curricula, institutions can integrate courses and programs emphasizing sustainability, encouraging students to contemplate environmental issues and develop skills necessary for addressing challenges. Active student involvement is crucial through initiatives like sustainability student groups or projects that encourage students to actively engage in environmental preservation, providing opportunities for practical learning and the application of theoretical knowledge.

Modeling sustainable practices is one way higher education institutions can serve as role models for sustainable practices, prompting students to recognize the importance of ecological values and promote them in their communities and future careers. Mentorship by professors and staff can play a crucial role in inspiring students to engage in sustainability research and take actions that support the Green Agenda.

Collectively, this fosters an atmosphere that inspires and empowers students to become leaders in sustainability, motivating them to actively participate in reducing the carbon footprint.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the sustainability of higher education institutions and their transition towards a carbon-neutral society represent pivotal pillars in achieving the Green Agenda and global efforts to reduce the ecological footprint. Carbon footprint analysis reveals the complexity of challenges institutions face, from methodological shortcomings to variations in data collection and reporting. Despite these challenges, student inspiration and the integration of sustainable principles into the educational system are key factors in the path toward a more sustainable future. Developing curricula, supporting student initiatives, and modeling sustainable practices create an environment that fosters engagement and leadership in sustainability.

The path toward the Green Agenda requires a comprehensive approach, encompassing theoretical frameworks to practical solutions. Standardizing and aligning methodologies for carbon footprint analysis are crucial steps toward valid and comparable data. Higher education institutions have the opportunity to become pioneers in the global fight against climate change, fostering innovation and transformation toward a sustainable society for future generations.

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DEVELOPMENT OF A CLUSTER IN THE FIELD OF RENEWABLE ENERGIES - ACTIVITIES IN THE APPLICATION FOR FINANCING

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Abstract: Heralding the promise of a more sustainable and innovative future, the project, situated within the ambit of the Research and Innovation Consolidation Program, is unequivocally committed to fortifying research and innovation in the realm of renewable energy. At its epicenter lies the MERWT Cluster (Renewable Energy and Environment), aspiring to burgeon Research, Development, and Innovation capabilities. The overarching objective of the project is to engender the capacity of the MERWT cluster. Comprising four specific objectives, the project entails a panoply of activities germane to cluster development, novel constructions, innovation, service acquisitions, and operational facets. The narrative of the project attains granularity with the inception of a new headquarters for the MERWT cluster, entailing the addition of two levels to an extant edifice. This edifice is envisioned to accommodate communal facilities, laboratories, events, and innovation-centric activities.

Key words: *energy, energy industrial park, green energy, solar panels, energy resources*

1. INTRODUCTION

Integral to the project is the pursuit of research into unconventional renewable energy sources and the conduct of feasibility studies. As the project unfolds, it orchestrates the creation of an innovation ecosystem through symbiotic collaboration among research, education, and production entities in the realm of renewable energy. The anticipated outcomes are formidable, encompassing the augmentation capacity within the cluster through the provision of new facilities and equipment, the intensification of innovation endeavors, and a concomitant elevation in economic competitiveness. The concomitant result is the generation of employment opportunities within the interdisciplinary domain of renewable energy and information technology, thereby contributing substantively to the specific goal of augmenting capacity in smart specialization domains.[1] The project is characterized by an intricately organized structure, delineated through tables correlating objectives, activities, indicators, and human resources. The management team, possessing a wealth of experience garnered from pertinent projects, allocates the budget judiciously based on the specific objectives articulated within the project framework. Building upon insights gleaned from a previous evaluative iteration, the project has undergone refinement, specifically addressing critiques related to team capacity and financial sustainability. Cluster members exhibit sustained engagement in multifarious activities, encompassing construction initiatives, start-up projects, collaborative partnerships, and equipment procurement endeavors. Public benefits and research trajectories assume paramount importance within the project's purview. The societal dividends encompass environmental preservation and job creation, while research endeavors encompass the extraction of renewable energy from sludge, pellet and briquette production, process optimization, and the establishment of contemporary databases.[2] The project's value proposition is underscored by its comprehensive approach to renewable energy, seamlessly integrating research with commercial imperatives.[14] Know-how accrues from both external sources, including subscriptions and patents, and internal efforts orchestrated by students and researchers alike. In this manner, the project transcends mere scientific endeavor, evolving into a captivating narrative emblematic of a community's vision and concerted endeavors in forging a brighter and greener future.[3]

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2. STRATEGIC IMPERATIVES AND OUTCOMES: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF SERVICES, GOVERNANCE, AND IMPACT IN RENEWABLE ENERGY INNOVATION PROJECT

The project endeavors to introduce novel and enhanced services as a direct outcome of its implementation. These services encompass a diverse range, spanning assistance and consultancy for experimental models and prototypes, innovation services tailored for products and processes, specific technological services, innovation support services, event organization and training courses, online documentation and sales services, as well as facilitating access to international databases and journals. Additionally, the project aspires to provide services geared towards internationalization.

In alignment with the principles of smart specialization, the project strategically positions itself within the domains of intelligent health and energy. Its specific emphasis lies in addressing issues pertinent to energy, the environment, and climate change.[4]

The imperative for project intervention stems from an analysis of main needs and problems, a comprehensive examination conducted within the project's working group. Governance aspects, encompassing leadership and management processes, justify project intervention to ensure success in both research and commercial dimensions, particularly within the field of renewable energy.[6]

A key objective of the project involves bolstering international relations and augmenting international visibility for the cluster. This is envisaged through collaborative initiatives, the expansion of existing international partnerships, and the advocacy of European concepts within the purview of research and development.[9]

Focusing on competitive advantages and economic growth opportunities, the project aims to position itself favorably by concentrating on renewable energy. This strategic orientation is anticipated to contribute significantly to economic growth and enhance market positions.[7]

The delineation of the target group encompasses legal entities within the cluster, specifically orienting towards start-ups and spin-offs associated with renewable energy. It further extends to include individuals, such as students, master's students, young researchers, and enterprises operating within the renewable energy sector. Quantification of the target group is meticulously defined, encompassing both legal entities and individuals, with a steadfast focus on their relevance to renewable energy.[13]

The anticipated impact on the target group is articulated through the project's objective to enhance green skills and competencies within the renewable energy sector. This is envisaged through comprehensive training programs and practical demonstrations.[9]

A detailed needs analysis forms an integral aspect of project planning, considering both current and future demands. This analysis is informed by surveys, demand forecasts, assessments of alternative supply sources, and an exploration of demand elasticity.

Identified beneficiaries span a spectrum, encompassing the entire population in the region, organizations, researchers, teachers, students, and businesses. Direct beneficiaries include entities within the renewable energy sector, while indirect beneficiaries pertain to those entities benefiting from stable markets in renewable energy.[7]

The anticipated social benefits emanating from the project are extensive, ranging from environmental protection and soil preservation to the recovery of renewable plants, reduction in energy imports, accrual of royalties from sold energy, and the prevention of brain drain through the stimulation of researchers and educators.[8]

3. ENSURING LONG-TERM VIABILITY: AN IN-DEPTH EXAMINATION OF FINANCIAL AND OPERATIONAL SUSTAINABILITY, INTEGRATION STRATEGIES, AND EVALUATION METRICS IN A RENEWABLE ENERGY INNOVATION PROJECT

Financial Sustainability

The financial sustainability is confirmed through exceptional bank situations of partners and the commitment of significant financial resources. The partners have substantial assets, including real estate, which can be utilized for obtaining credits or bank guarantees. Short-term financial stability is ensured through exceptional bank situations of partners on short-term contracts, and their equivalent values in euros are specified. Long-term financial sustainability is demonstrated through a detailed financial analysis, showing positive cash flows for at least 6 years, three years after the project's completion.[10] Identified sources of post-project funding include consultancy, project development for incubated firms, domain-specific courses, exhibitions, accessing other projects, and lab expertise.[4]

The project aims to create stable job positions, especially in the expanding field of renewable energies. The newly created infrastructure, programs, and technologies will have economic effects even after project completion. The equipment purchased through the project will be installed in the new laboratories and used not only by current members but also by future members, researchers, and students both during and after project implementation. The project emphasizes the dissemination of results and experiences after completion to individuals and organizations that can best utilize them.[6]

The project's experience will be integrated into the organization and partners through the incorporation of best practices and a dedicated section on the local website. Activities will be connected and integrated into local and regional activities. Best practices will be extended through the development of regional partnerships, accessing European-funded programs, and leveraging the applicant's experience and connections.[5]

The partners have a track record of successfully implementing over 30 national and international projects in the last decade, with stable teams that will persist after project completion. Existing expert teams within the cluster's member entities, especially in areas like photovoltaic cells, hardware, software, and financial accounting, contribute to the successful implementation and sustainability of the project. The project's implementation will strengthen the cluster's legal entity, and support will be provided by key members for post-project activities in research, education, and production.[6]

Financial Analysis

Calculation of financial net present value (FNPV) is presented, comparing investment costs with net income to determine the project's financial viability. RIR(internal rate of return) is calculated, comparing the return on investment with the recommended discount rate. The financial analysis is conducted following the European Union guidelines and includes considerations for financial sustainability, investment costs, operating costs, and funding sources.[10]

Evaluation of Specific Indicators

The achievement of the indicator related to the number of new researchers supported is explained, considering their roles and potential future contributions.[11]

The achievement of the indicator related to the number of researchers working in improved research infrastructures is discussed, considering the correlation with human resources and the creation of new positions. The achievement of the indicator related to private investments combined with public support is explained, taking into account the proposed funding and liquidity of the cluster and its founding members.[12]

4. CONCLUSION

So we have a comprehensive overview of the sustainability, financial aspects, operational aspects, and specific indicators related to the project. The financial analysis, sustainability measures, and the strategic approach to integration and institutional sustainability contribute to a thorough understanding of the project's potential success and long-term impact. The project aims to establish a renewable energy park, focusing on collaboration, research, and knowledge transfer. The risks identified include financial, human, market, marketing, and legal risks, with corresponding mitigation measures. The project promotes equal opportunities, gender equality, non-discrimination, and accessibility for people with disabilities. It aligns with national and regional development strategies, emphasizing economic, transboundary, and regional relevance. The project addresses demographic changes and sustainable development, incorporating measures to reduce pollution and protect biodiversity.

The provided text describes details related to the proposed construction for the cluster's headquarters, including characteristics of the land, plans for expanding the building, administrative and research and development functions, as well as justifications for the technical and economic documents.

The project aims to minimize waste generation, replace traditional machining processes with 3D printing to reduce waste, shift from paper to electronic document circulation, enhance waste recovery and recycling measures, and optimize the use of resources, particularly focusing on renewable energy sources to address climate change.

The methodology section outlines general considerations for project management, including research, education, and production aspects. It also highlights the involvement of various organizations, including the 17 cluster member entities, the Chamber of Commerce and Industry Timis, ROSENC (the Romanian Sustainable Energy Cluster), and other legal entities in the process. The management show as aspects such as quality, human resources, time, risks, finance, conflicts, control, and audit. It emphasizes the use of various management methods throughout the project, including management by objectives, exceptions, budgets, projects, and products.

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MODERN RENEWABLE ENERGY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION ENTITIES

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Abstract: This paper focuses on the development of a green energy industrial park with a commitment to environmental sustainability. The existing industrial park comprises six companies involved in various activities. The main goals include reducing the environmental impact of industries, promoting sustainability, and transitioning to renewable energy sources. The project addresses the challenges of climate change by aligning with the European Climate Law, which increases the EU's emissions reduction target to 55% by 2030 and makes climate neutrality by 2050 a legal obligation. The European Green Deal serves as the roadmap for achieving climate neutrality, incorporating the ambitious "Fit for 55 in 2030" package with 13 interconnected revised laws and six climate and energy proposals.

Key words: energy, energy industrial park, green energy, solar panels, energy resources

1. INTRODUCTION

The EU Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS) aims to reduce carbon dioxide emissions from industries by requiring companies to hold permits for each ton of CO₂ emitted. The scheme, regulating around 40% of the EU's greenhouse gas emissions, is undergoing updates to align with the European Green Deal objectives. The industrial parks play a key role in meeting the EU's energy and environmental goals. Therefore, companies within the industrial park are expected to be major contributors to implementing sustainable energy policies. The development of clean energy sources is crucial for reducing emissions. Currently, over 20% of the EU's energy comes from renewable sources, with a target set to increase it to 45% by 2030. Additionally, there are calls for faster authorizations for renewable energy production, including solar panels and wind turbines. The investment objective of a renewable energy park is to produce sustainable electricity, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and contribute to the community's sustainable development. The investment benefits both direct and indirect beneficiaries, including companies in the industrial park, local communities, researchers, students, and small to medium-sized enterprises.[1] The public benefit involves environmental protection, reduced greenhouse gas emissions, and sustainable community development. The study's main contributors are professionals in engineering, architecture, and academia. The current situation analysis identifies deficiencies such as the lack of renewable energy infrastructure and dependence on traditional energy sources within the industrial park. Legislation on green energy focuses on promoting and regulating renewable energy sources, including solar energy. Common legislative aspects include support schemes, obligations and objectives, network connection regulations, and fiscal incentives. The forecasted increase in demand for renewable energy justifies the investment in renewable energy industrial parks. The investment aims to achieve environmental sustainability, diversify energy sources, create jobs, reduce dependence on energy imports, and stimulate innovation. Specific objectives of the investment include the installation of a wind park, the development of a solar photovoltaic project, a biogas/biodigester project, and improvements in energy efficiency in buildings. The project aligns with global efforts to combat climate change, promote sustainability, and transition to a low-carbon economy.[2]

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2. IDENTIFICATION, PROPOSAL AND PRESENTATION OF AT LEAST TWO TECHNICAL-ECONOMIC SCENARIOS/OPTIONS FOR ACHIEVING THE INVESTMENT OBJECTIV

In Scenario I, the text envisions a situation where an industrial park no longer receives funding or financial assistance. The consequences of this scenario include physical deterioration of the industrial park due to a lack of financial support, leading to disruptions in machinery and equipment. This could result in lower productivity and higher costs for repairs and replacements. Additionally, without additional funding, the industrial park may lose contracts with companies seeking more competitive producers. Lack of investment in research and development can lead to stagnation and decreased competitiveness globally. Moreover, the absence of financial support may lead to job losses and the emigration of skilled labor, potentially turning the industrial park into an economically unviable ghost town.[4]

Scenario II outlines the advantages and disadvantages of installing various renewable energy sources, including photovoltaic panels on buildings and ground, a wind turbine, heat pump systems for a guesthouse and a pool, and equipment for biogas generation. The scenario highlights that limited funding for a specific number of photovoltaic panels may only offer limited reductions in energy costs and greenhouse gas emissions. This limitation could lead to ongoing economic challenges, such as machinery failures and workforce loss. Additionally, there is a risk that the limited funding might not be used efficiently, hindering the integration of photovoltaic panels into a broader renewable energy system. Scenario III proposes the implementation of a SOFTWARE program to integrate all renewable energy production, showing real-time correlations between production and consumption. It suggests creating green spaces with bushes to reduce pollution and provide an environment of green energy. The scenario includes innovative features like retractable panels for shading the parking area and three trees with solar panels, sockets, and benches. Moreover, it recommends installing 20 umbrellas with photovoltaic panels for the pool area. The text emphasizes the importance of synergy between renewable energy parks and adjacent urban areas to optimize energy production and benefit nearby cities.[3]

2.1 DATA CATEGORIZATION AND MEASURABLE PARAMETERS STRUCTURING

To combat climate change, the European Union adopted the European Climate Law which raises the EU's emissions reduction target by 2030 to 55% from 40% and makes achieving climate neutrality by 2050 a legal obligation. The climate law is part of the "European Green Pact",

- Seismic Zoning: Seismic zone with a maximum acceleration of 0.20g.
- Geophysical Characteristics: Soil Type- Predominance of quaternary deposits for foundation.
- Groundwater Level: Depth-Approximately between 3.6 - 3.8 meters relative to the natural ground level.
- Geotechnical Category: Category 2, with moderate geotechnical risk.
- Renewable Energy Sources: Photovoltaic panels, wind turbines, heat pumps, biogas equipment.
- Measurable Advantages of Renewable Energy Source: Reduction in energy costs, Low greenhouse gas emissions, Energy efficiency indicators.
- Additional Costs for Renewable Energy: Hiring specialized personnel., Maintenance costs.
- Artificial Intelligence and IoT Solutions: Software program for real-time monitoring of renewable energies.[5]
- Measurable Aspects of IoT Solutions: Energy production efficiency, Production-consumption correlation, System performance data.
- Proposed Innovations for Energy Efficiency: Green spaces, retractable panels, solar lighting, umbrellas with photovoltaic panels.
- General Measurable Conditions and Data: Seismic Zoning-Located in a seismic zone with a maximum acceleration of 0.20g.
- Geophysical Characteristics: Predominance of quaternary deposits as foundation soil.
- Groundwater Level: Approximately 3.6 - 3.8 meters relative to the natural ground level.
- Geotechnical Category: Category 2, with moderate geotechnical risk.

- Temperatures: Seasonal variations-Temperature range is between -5°C and 30°C.
- Impact of temperatures on equipment and performance of renewable energy systems.[6]

3. SUMMARY OF ESTIMATED INVESTMENT COSTS

a. Estimated Costs for Achieving the Investment Objective:

The first scenario describes the absence of any new investment in renewable energy, with industrial park activities conducted similarly to current practices, relying exclusively on national energy system resources. Scenario II involves placing renewable energy sources, with equipment operational within the next 3 years, generating calculated revenues for most sources, except wind and biogas stations considered experimental. Scenario III involves creating modern spaces with both design and renewable energy equipment.

b. Estimated Operating Costs over the Standardized Investment Life/Amortization:

- SCENARIO I: Acquisition of renewable energy equipment is not possible; all activities are conducted using resources from distributors.
- SCENARIO II: Adds the advantages of the first scenario and places renewable energy sources without an innovative retractable system and without expanding innovative spaces.
- SCENARIO III: Includes both renewable energy sources and the creation of an innovative framework in the renewable energy park.

Presentation of the Analysis Framework:

The three scenarios present different variants, starting from the absence of new investments (scenario 1), continuing with the implementation of renewable energy equipment (scenario 2), and up to creating modern spaces with renewable energy equipment (scenario 3).

Analysis of Vulnerabilities:

Examines the impact of climate change, emphasizing phenomena such as heatwaves, extreme rains, and storms, with a focus on adapting to climate change.

Utilities Situation and Consumption Analysis:

Scenario I assumes consumption from existing sources; the other two scenarios add renewable energy installations without major changes to consumption.

Sustainability of Achieving the Investment Objective:

- Financial Sustainability: Analyzes bank situations, funding sources, and forecasts long-term sustainability.
- Operational Sustainability: Highlights stable jobs, economic effects, and the continued use of equipment after project completion.
- Integrability (Mainstreaming): Aims at integrating experience into organizations and regional partnerships.

Analysis of Goods and Services Demand:

Needs analysis is based on current consumption and forecasts for future demand, including industrial users, energy transformation sector, households/commercial users.

Financial Analysis:

Calculates cumulative cash flow, net present value, internal rate of return, focusing on long-term financial sustainability.

Economic Analysis:

Examines net present value, internal rate of return, and cost-benefit ratio, considering adjustments based on investment specificity and macroeconomic conditions.

Financial Sustainability Scenario by Scenario:

- Scenario I: Financial sustainability may be compromised in the long term due to high costs of conventional energy and dependence on them.
- Scenario II: Has the potential for better financial sustainability in the long term by eliminating or reducing costs of conventional energy.
- Scenario III: Depends on the efficient implementation of technologies and arrangements, with potential for attracting additional revenues and ecological positioning.

All these represent the key details and assessments made in the cost-benefit analysis of the investment in renewable energy for an industrial park.

4. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR OPTIMAL SCENARIO

According to the GUIDE TO - COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS, sensitivity analysis helps identify the "critical" variables of a project that significantly impact its financial and/or economic performance, irrespective of their positive or negative effects. The analysis considers uncertainties, and for this project, it addresses issues related to uncertainty dimensions and anticipated effects, emphasizing the importance of avoiding difficulties imposed by uncertainty.[9]

1. Scenario I: Activities in the existing industrial park buildings, relying on conventional energy sources. Initial financial convenience but with potential environmental drawbacks.

2. Scenario II: Installation of various renewable energy sources, such as photovoltaic panels, wind turbine, and heat pump systems. Higher initial costs, potential long-term savings, and improved environmental impact.

3. Scenario III: Creation of a software program for monitoring and optimizing renewable energy production, coupled with green spaces featuring solar-powered lighting. Incorporates advanced solutions like retractable photovoltaic panels on halls and tree-mounted solar panels.

Comparative Analysis of Scenarios:

- Technical Aspects: Scenarios vary in terms of infrastructure modernization and technological efficiency. Scenario III stands out as an innovative and technologically advanced option, potentially making the industrial park a pioneer in Romania.
- Economic Impacts: Scenario I risks reduced productivity and competitiveness. Scenario II offers moderate improvements but lacks significant economic and ecological benefits. Scenario III, with substantial investments and technological advancements, promises substantial long-term economic benefits.[10]
- Sustainability: While Scenario I and II have limited sustainability impact, Scenario III, with substantial investments in clean technologies, promises improved sustainability and reduced environmental impact.
- Risks: Scenario I poses vulnerability to economic issues. Scenario II might not provide sufficient benefits due to partial investments. Scenario III, with diverse funding sources and significant investments, can mitigate risks through innovation and advanced technologies.

Recommendation: Considering economic, sustainability, and risk factors, Scenario III emerges as the optimal choice. This scenario involves comprehensive funding, substantial investments in clean technologies, and a long-term vision for sustainability. It positions the industrial park as an innovative, competitive, and environmentally conscious entity, contributing positively to the local community and economy.[8]

Implementation Steps for Scenario III:

1. Identify Funding Sources: Analyze public and private funding sources, including European funds, to secure comprehensive financial support.
2. Develop Sustainable Business Plan: Create a sustainable business plan outlining economic, social, and environmental objectives. Clearly define development goals and strategies for long-term profitability and sustainability.
3. Identify Renewable Technologies: Select suitable renewable energy technologies for the geographic area, including photovoltaic panels and other sustainable technologies like waste management systems.
4. Equipment Acquisition and Implementation: Procure necessary equipment for renewable energy implementation. Install and commission the equipment within the industrial park.[9]
5. Monitoring and Evaluation: Implement a monitoring and evaluation system to assess the project's performance in terms of energy efficiency, cost savings, and environmental impact. Regularly evaluate and optimize processes.
6. Community Collaboration: Collaborate with the local community during project implementation to ensure their involvement and benefit. Create job opportunities and contribute to the local economy.

5. THE MAIN TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC INDICATORS RELATED TO AN INVESTMENT PROJECT FOR AN INDUSTRIAL PARK WITH RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES.

The key indicators include production capacity, installation efficiency, investment costs, operating and maintenance costs, investment recovery period, and contribution to greenhouse gas emission reduction. The compliance with specific regulations for the intended function is emphasized, covering various areas such as construction, environment, health and safety, and other legal and contractual requirements. The process involves obtaining necessary permits and approvals, considering environmental protection, waste management, and meeting legal obligations related to health, safety, and property rights.[10]

The financing sources for the public investment are outlined, including European funds, government funding, international financial institutions, investment funds, and private investors. Two financing options are considered: fully self-funded and a combination of 80% non-repayable funds from the European Union and 20% self-funding.

The text also addresses urban planning, agreements, and compliance approvals required for the project. It details the steps involved in obtaining a urbanism certificate for construction authorization, land ownership documentation, administrative acts for environmental protection, utility assurance approvals, topographic studies, and specific agreements depending on the project's nature.

For installing a wind turbine demo or a photovoltaic system, the text provides a list of permits and approvals required, such as urban planning authorization, environmental impact assessment, connection to the power grid, safety and compliance approvals, and other specific permits based on local regulations.

6. INVESTMENT IMPLEMENTATION

The investment implementation will be carried out by the Cluster for Medium and Renewable Energies, WESTTIM. The cluster is committed to realizing all aspects presented in the feasibility study.

The implementation strategy spans three years, with certain equipment becoming operational as early as the second year, including heat pumps and photovoltaic panels on the field. Photovoltaic panels on the hall and wind turbines, along with biogas production equipment, will be operational starting the third year.[7]

The project's financial sustainability is supported by the outstanding financial situations of the cluster, its members, and the companies in the park consuming renewable energy. Short-term funding during implementation is ensured, preventing any risks related to repayment delays. Long-term sustainability is confirmed through the interest of partners in developing new activities and projects even after project completion.

Additional funding sources identified for the post-project period include the use of renewable energy by park companies, exhibitions, fairs in the renewable energy sector, and accessing other funded projects. These contribute to the long-term financial sustainability and continuity of activities within the industrial park.[2]

Ensuring managerial and institutional capacity is recommended for project success. The newly created infrastructure and technologies in the renewable energy sector will continue to have economic effects even after project completion. Integration of project experience can be achieved through the incorporation of best practices and specific location guides into existing local, regional, and European sites.

The sustainability of the institution is guaranteed by the current activity objectives of partners, their material and human resources, and their interest in development activities. The partners, including the Cluster and the University "Ioan Slavici" Foundation, have successfully implemented over 30 national and international projects in the last decade, maintaining stable personnel even after the project's conclusion.[11] Among the investments with the most impact on the society, there are the firms working in the nonconventional energies domain. However exciting this domain is, starting up such a firm is not

an easy task. The innovation can be supported out of public subscriptions or through specific financing programs. [12]

7. CONCLUSION

The use of innovative technologies like Artificial Intelligence and the integration of renewable energy sources can contribute to the economic, social, and ecological sustainability of an industrial park. Scenario III, when implemented with a comprehensive approach, has the potential to create a sustainable, profitable, and innovative industrial park, positively impacting both the local community and the broader economic landscape. Constant evaluation and adaptation are essential for long-term success. A systematic and proactive approach is important to ensure compliance with specific regulations and the complexity of the process highlighting various sources of financing for the implementation of the renewable energy industrial park project. The optimal technical-economic scenario is identified as the third option. This conclusion is supported by the feasibility and numerous benefits of implementing renewable energy equipment, designs, and a retractable panel system. The third scenario allows for the development of necessary spaces for renewable energy park activities, efficiently supporting the energy needs of companies within the park. It is economically sustainable, integrating new technologies and specific programs, ensuring long-term positive impacts on the economy. Overall, the choice of the third scenario is justified and represents the most feasible solution for achieving project objectives sustainably and efficiently.

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ENHANCE STUDENTS' COMPETENCE IN ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION IN FUNCTION OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This paper explores the factors influencing the effective operation of the environmental protection system and the resolution of issues arising from the ongoing ecological crisis. Significantly, ecological education and awareness play a substantial role in addressing these challenges. The study employed diverse research methods, including content analysis, statistical procedures, non-standardized interviews, and surveys/questionnaires as measurement instruments. The research targeted a group of 150 students across five different study programs. This research is characterized as an ongoing process of acquiring environmental knowledge, concepts, and skills, coupled with the concurrent development of ecological awareness, culture, and forms of ecological behaviour. The ultimate aim is to contribute to enhanced environmental preservation and protection in the future. The survey results are utilized to shed light on these issues scientifically and to establish more suitable and promising environmental protection modules (curricula) for the purpose of the existing study programme reaccreditation, aligned with principles of sustainable development, thereby opening up new possibilities and directions for future research.

.Key words: Students' competence, environment protection, sustainable development, curriculum development

1. INTRODUCTION

The gravity of ecological issues and societal efforts toward environmental protection and sustainable development pose a challenge for modern upbringing and education. It also necessitates the promotion of various innovative approaches within the classroom. Considering the escalating intensity and prevalence of environmental threats in our daily lives, it is evident that most European countries are reevaluating and innovating their educational objectives. Alongside socio-economic measures, these nations are concurrently implementing activities to bring about changes in the educational system[1].

What holds particular significance for our research focus is the explicit emphasis on the necessity and significance of integrating environmental protection content across all levels and segments of the educational system. Unfortunately, there is still a lack of sufficient and comprehensive research in this domain within pedagogical and educational literature. The core of the theoretical and methodological aspects of education for environmental protection is encapsulated and conceptually defined within a new theoretical framework that aligns with the concept of "sustainable development"[2]. This framework underscores the understanding that environmental degradation and the depletion of resources have inherent limits, and any further progress must adhere to the principles of "sustainable development" for a "sustainable future"[3].

An increasing number of authors are recognizing the incorporation of environmental protection education as a fundamental principle in the broader framework of the upbringing and education system[4]. This essentially entails integrating environmental protection content into all aspects of extracurricular, school, and extracurricular activities.

This paper employs mathematical statistics, specifically the chi-square test, using survey data to scrutinize the claim that all samples within the population are normally distributed, irrespective of age.

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Through data analysis, we have pinpointed the educational needs of students, provide projections for potential strategies to address existing problems and deficiencies in this domain.

2. EDUCATION ON ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION GOAL IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

2.1. Literature overview

Higher education encompasses both theoretical and practical knowledge of contemporary principles and systems related to labor and environmental protection. This education is particularly tailored to the specific field and profession for which students are being professionally prepared and trained. It involves instructing students on organizing and designing suitable micro-systems for environmental protection within specific areas of labor and production. Additionally, the goal is to shape the opinions, views, and behavioral models of future professionals, enabling them to incorporate versatile, valuable, and effective considerations of ecological ideas, aspects, factors, and laws into their professional activities [4]-[7].

2.2. Research results

Mentioned research aims at shaping the design and program orientation of education on environmental protection, both at the stage of preventive action and continuous preservation, improvement and upgrading of the existing condition of the environment.

The primary objective of this research is centered around the identification, specification, analysis, deliberation, and consideration of all factors, conditions, and circumstances influencing the educational needs of students regarding environmental protection content.

Aligned with these objectives, hypotheses have been formulated, with the overarching hypothesis stating: *Students' competence on environmental protection, within the context of sustainable development, necessitates the incorporation of new content in the curriculum. This integration aims to develop students' knowledge and skills for preventive action in their daily lives and activities.*

For data collection relevant to the research problem, a survey or questionnaire technique was employed as a measuring instrument. The questionnaire was administered to students at all levels of vocational studies, with a total sample size of 150 students. The research assumes, at the outset, that all samples (answers) are normally distributed in the population (the survey), irrespective of the age structure. The assumption of normally distributed samples aligns with the Gauss hypothesis, serving as the null hypothesis in statistical research, specifically a non-parametric test.

The correlation between responses and the difference between groups was extensive part that has been analysed only through two separate defined hypotheses, and those are:

Students are aware that their environment is exposed to substantial threats and harmfulness, with normally distributed responses in the survey, regardless of age;

Students consider necessary introduction of the new contents on environmental protection in the existing curriculum and program, with normally distributed responses in the survey, regardless of age.

At the beginning of the research socio-demographic variables were analysed. The total number of respondents in the sample was 150, and the percentages presented in the tables were calculated in relation to this number.

Most of the respondents belongs to the age limit to 23 years (60%) and therefore most of the sample consists of students from the first and second year of studies (about 71%). As for previously acquired knowledge, the majority of students (about 63%) prior knowledge acquired in the field of technical sciences, while the remaining respondents acquired knowledge in socio-humanistic sciences and natural and mathematic sciences.

Total 58 of respondents (38.67%) is in the first year of studies, followed by 49 students of the second year (32.67%), 33 students of the third year (22.00%) and 10 students of specialist professional studies (6.67%).

In following phases of the research descriptive statistical measures - frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations, respondents' answers to other questions in the survey were used.

Table 1 – Statements of respondents on the representation of the contents on environmental protection in the curriculum of their education

Types of hazards and harms that threaten the environment	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Min	Max
Waste water	2.78	7.41	0	25
The proximity of the landfill	2.67	7.11	0	24
Exhaust gases from cars	0.67	1.78	0	6
Illegally constructed buildings without sanitary control	0.89	2.37	0	8
Inadequate Utilities	1.44	3.85	0	13
Contaminated places	1.67	4.44	0	15
Polluted river headwaters	1.89	5.04	0	17
Polluted air	2.11	5.63	0	19
Destruction of green areas	2.56	6.81	0	23

To the question "*What are the dangers and harmful effects that may lead (or lead) to contamination and threats to the environment in which you live*", the research results show that the largest number of respondents 116 (74.84%) believe that there are existing dangers and harms that can damage the environment in which they live.

The question "*What kind of dangers and harms mostly threaten the environment in which you live*," refers to the following finding: When it comes to the prevalence of different types of risks and harms that can cause environmental pollution (Table 1.), on average as the most common kind of danger stands out the danger of proximity of wastewater and landfills. The destruction of green areas and pollution of river headwaters are listed as rarely, while as far the least frequently states for pollution from traffic noise and exhaust fumes.

To the question "*Do you have enough knowledge and skills for environmental protection*", respondents gave the following answers: 80 of them (53.33%) believed to have a significant knowledge, 70 of them (46.67%) considered to have insignificant knowledge and none of the respondents claimed not to possess general knowledge and skills on environmental protection.

To the question "*Are contents in the field of environmental protection sufficiently represented in the curricula of schools*," answers indicate that 70 (46.67%) of respondents believe that these content are sufficiently represented, while 60 (40.00%) of them believe that they are not sufficiently represented and even 20 of them (13.33%) considered that they are not at all represented in the curriculum of their education.

When asked whether they would like to gain new and expand existing knowledge of environmental protection and knowledge on sustainable development, the results indicate that almost all of them 140 (93.33%) want to acquire new knowledge and 10 of them (6.67%) said they did not want to acquire new knowledge about environmental protection and sustainable development. As the main ways of acquiring knowledge respondents finds lectures in classical teaching, 63 of them (42.00%), and 38 of them (25.33%) opted for education through lecturing through discussion groups, 35 (23.33%) of respondents

opting for acquiring knowledge through media and the remaining 14 (9.34%) opts for acquiring knowledge through self-education and the Internet.

When it comes to areas in which respondents want to gain more knowledge and expand already existing on the protection of working and living environment, more than half of the respondents stated that they need education in the field of water and air pollution and waste management, and the rest of respondents want to expand their knowledge in the field of fire protection, alternative energy sources, protection of plant and animal world and the impact of depleted uranium on human health.

To the question "Do you think you gained enough knowledge and competencies for environmental protection", almost all respondents, 94 of them (62.67%) believe that the necessary knowledge and competence on environment have gained partially and expressed willingness to acquire new or expand existing knowledge, skills and abilities in the field of living and working environment protection.

2.3. Correlation between responses and differences between groups

For the statistical analysis of the correlation between two random variables X and Y (characteristics, in our case, the age structure of respondents), it is necessary to dispose of their values ($x_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) and ($y_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$). The application of mathematical statistics, results in a high value of correlation coefficient, which indicates a very strong correlation relationship ($r > 0.9$). Therefore we come to the conclusion that except the age, a third variable has an impact on respondents, which has been adopted as the various answers given by the respondents to one question, through surveys. Further analysis approach chi-square test, in order to verify the hypotheses. The following tables show the results of comparisons on those variables where there was sufficient variability of respondent responses for comparison to have a sense. Data on substantial association between variables or more substantial differences between the examined groups has been obtained simultaneously.

Table 2 – Correlation between the age structure and identified threats to the environment

Respondents age	Are the threat assessment and harms that threaten the environment:	
	insignificant	significant
Age 18-23	25 (69.44%)	58 (59.64%)
Age 24-28	6 (16.66%)	46 (40.35%)
> 29	5 (13.8%)	10 (8.71%)

A statistically significant correlation was obtained between the respondent's age structure and statements about whether they would like to acquire new or upgrade existing knowledge and skills related to environmental and labour protection.

Table 3. Age structure and their desire to acquire new or expand existing knowledge (skills) related to environmental and labour protection

Respondents age	Do you have the desire for gaining new and expansion of already existing knowledge in the field of environmental protection:	
	Yes	No
Age 18-23	63 (45.00%)	4 (40.00%)
Age 24-28	55 (39.28%)	3 (30.00%)
> 29	22 (15.71%)	3 (30.00%)

Based on samples obtained by the method of mathematical statistics, insignia distribution in the whole population (i.e. the distribution of respondents' answers to the survey) has been evaluated, started from the presumption that the insignia of the entire population are normally distributed.

Particular in this paper, this means that multiple choice of answers to the question about the threats which, according to the respondents threaten the environment, have normal mathematical distribution (the null hypothesis). Chi-square nonparametric test result shows:

	interval (class)	middle interval (x _i)	frequency (m _i)	probability (p _i)	n*p _i	m _i -n*p _i	(m _i -n*p _i) ²	χ ²
1	18-23	20.5	71	0.2746	41.19	29.81	888.6361	21.5740738
2	23-28	25.5	64	0.6319	94.785	-30.785	947.716225	9.998588648
3	more than 28	39	15	0.0935	14.025	0.975	0.950625	0.067780749
Σ		85	150	1	150	0	1837.30295	31.6404432

Figure 1: Testing the hypothesis of normal distribution patterns, i.e. multiple responses to a question about the threats which, according to the respondents harm living and working environment

The value obtained by test statistic is greater than the value read from the table for the threshold of significance $\alpha = 0,05$ ($\chi^2_{1,0,05} = 3,841$), even higher than the value read from the table to the threshold of significance $\alpha = 0,01$ ($\chi^2_{1,0,01} = 6,635$), which means that the presumption of conformity distribution of samples with normal distribution is wrong. Testing reject the hypothesis "Students are aware that their area is exposed to great danger and harmfulness, with normally distributed responses in the survey, regardless of age" with the risk that we will make a mistake in less than 1% of cases.

The paper tested another statement that multiple answers to the question on the wishes of respondents to gain new or expand existing knowledge (skills) related to environmental and labour protection have normal mathematical distribution. Chi-square nonparametric test result shows:

	interval (class)	middle interval (x _i)	frequency (m _i)	probability (p _i)	n*p _i	m _i -n*p _i	(m _i -n*p _i) ²	χ ²
1	18-23	20.5	67	0.187	28.05	38.95	1517.1025	54.08565062
2	23-28	25.5	58	0.4202	63.03	-5.03	25.3009	0.401410439
3	more than 28	44	25	0.3928	58.92	-33.92	1150.5664	19.52760353
Σ		90	150	1	150	0	2692.9698	74.01466459

Figure 2: Testing the hypothesis of normal distribution patterns, i.e. multiple responses to a question on the wishes of respondents to gain new or expand existing knowledge (skills) related to environmental and labour protection

The value obtained by test statistic is greater than the value read from the table for the threshold of significance $\alpha = 0,05$ ($\chi^2_{1,0,05} = 3,841$), even higher than the value read from the table to the threshold of significance $\alpha = 0,01$ ($\chi^2_{1,0,01} = 6,635$), which means that the presumption of conformity distribution of samples with normal distribution is wrong. Testing reject the hypothesis "Students consider it necessary to introduce new content on Environmental Protection to the existing curriculum, with normally distributed responses in the survey, regardless of age" with the risk that we will make a mistake in less than 1% cases. This conclusion opens up space for further testing.

In this study the obtained results is completing a review, leaving the room for further testing the population distribution of the sample, with other alternative hypotheses. Due to a limited volume of the paper, we're leaving this test for some other paper.

3. CONCLUSION

In the conclusive analysis of research problems, grounded in the perspectives and opinions expressed by respondents, we can assert with confidence that incorporating environmental protection into the

curriculum is imperative for fostering sustainable development. The objective is to enhance students' knowledge and skills to enable them to take proactive measures in their daily lives and activities.

Therefore, educational institutions must not only address the urgent call for environmental protection but also recognize the intricate nature and interdependence of all phenomena associated with it. This recognition implies that the educational program of higher institutions should encompass aspects related to natural and technical sciences, technological sciences, and social sciences. Simultaneously, an interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approach to the study of environmental protection is crucial for developing students' abilities in various directions:

- Analyzing the overall environmental situation and changes influenced by both technogenic and antropogenic factors, identifying and considering potential risks and exploring management opportunities for different types of environmental risks;
- Mastering the methodology of creating technologies that preserve nature and resources, implementing measures to prevent and mitigate dangers and harmful effects and restoring ecological balance in divers ecosystems across different regions;
- Understanding the economic aspects of reulation and managing activities for environmental protectionand the rational use of natural resources;
- Examining legal aspects of environmental protection at both national and international levels;
- Mastering methods and measures to address issues related to waste of various origins, noise, radiation and other progressive methods of protecting nature and the environment;
- Acquiring the necessary pedagogical, andragogical and didactic-methodological foundations for the successful implementation of educational and informational activities in the field.

In light of the presented facts and research results, it is evident that there is a compelling need to modernize education, aligning it with the evolving educational requirements for environmental protection within the context of sustainable development and the prevailing needs of our times.

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ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AND ECOLOGICAL BALANCE

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Abstract: Sustainable or responsible development represents a certain code of conduct that should be observed between visitors to protected natural objects and areas/landscapes, in order to avoid degradation and devastation, all for the benefit of current and future descendants and generations. The concept itself is based on the principle of ecological, social, cultural and economic sustainability, which indicates fundamental changes starting with the development of human civilization, primarily in the underdeveloped countries of Europe and the world. The concept of sustainable development indicates significant ethical differences in numerous factors that are involved in various flows, starting from supply and demand as carriers and creators, to visitors who are users of various products, contents and services. The main goal is to reach a consensus about ethical principles as the main actors in the process of making proposals and where the appropriate effects based on the concept of sustainable development can be recognized.

Key words: protection of nature, the concept of sustainable development, economic, social and environmental indicators, environment

1. INTRODUCTION

Spangenberg [1] created a model of sustainable development called the “prism of sustainability”. In addition to the economic, social and social components, he attaches importance to the institutional dimension. The institutional component in the function of realizing the concept of sustainable development implies the role of institutions where it is necessary to harmonize the measures of different sectoral policies, exchange knowledge and experience, influence people's awareness through the provision of different information and mutual connection (harmonization) of different dimensions of development. The procedure itself implies a complex process, where in the future period it should incorporate into a single whole institutions, non-governmental organizations, economic entities and the population that are in some way connected with the economy. According to the authors Carbone and Yunis [2], it is necessary to define three levels:

The analysis of the situation, problems and opportunities is the first step that includes the resources on which economy depends and is based. These are data related to the capacity of economy, market trends, sustainable capacities, degradation and devastation of the environment and the interest of the local (domicile) population in the potential and perspectives of economy [2].

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Determining goals and forming a strategic choice

represents the phase where the state and local self-government, that is, the local community, define and formulate perspectives, visions and guidelines regarding the future development of economy. They must be based on the data obtained from the previous phase (analysis of the situation, overview of the results so far, identification of problems and provision of opportunities, i.e. chances). The goals and objectives may be different on the economy destination/place, but they must primarily have a common interest regarding the protection of nature, the environment and the development potential of ecotourism [2].

The development of policies and action programs represent the final and ultimate phase in the creation and creation of the Sustainable Development Strategy. They relate to the demands and trends of the tourist market, tourist satisfaction, employment, regional, national and international cooperation, support to local governments and communities, protection of natural and immovable cultural heritage. It represents a complex system that requires a large number of experts and professionals in the elaboration, analysis and solving of problems [2].

2. PHASES IN THE CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

According to the authors Stojanović [3] and Jovašević [4], the negative consequences and chaotic development of nature protection imposed the need for the protection of nature economy to be fenced off, that is, to be under control if there was to be a stabilization of progressive growth. This means that they must adhere to the concept of sustainable development and the establishment of "ecological balance". Economic development in recent years and accelerated industrialization/urbanization as well as technical – technological progress have led to a certain level of pollution, destruction or damage to natural living conditions. It imposed a change for many changes that must be included in the system of legal norms as part of the overall social system.

In the document "Our Common Future" which is its official name, the key problem and emphasis is on environmental protection, the extreme poverty of the South and the unsustainable development concept of the North. Numerous international documents adopt, or accept, different standards, classifications and categorizations related to nature protection, which Serbia has also signed. Only harmonized and unified programs, recommendations, guidelines and potentials/perspectives can make a great contribution to the quality and preservation of the environment, as noted by the above-mentioned authors Stojanović [3] and Jovašević [4].

Massive, i.e. progressive growth after 1945, caused negative consequences for the population, space and environment. Economy and industry cannot be viewed in isolation and separately from other activities/actions, because it is incorporated (integrated) into the entire system. According to the author Stojanović [3] in the implementation of strategic documents, laws, regulations, instruments and measures, there was insufficient coordination, that is, cooperation and association. Capacities at the local level are not sufficiently improved and developed.

The first aspect is the interaction (direct and indirect impacts), tourist movements, protected areas and the resident population. Another aspect is the awareness of how tourist movements influence and what consequences they leave on the environment. The third aspect is dependence because sustainable development is based on people needs for the preserved nature and authentic destinations.

Table 1 – The evolution of sustainability over time

PHASE 1	SUSTAINABILITY
<i>Period of time</i>	Pre-industrial
<i>Explanation</i>	People lived sustainably, because technologies were not developed and advanced and they were mostly driven by the desire for survival.
<i>The result</i>	Symbiosis of development with nature.

PHASE 2	CONDITIONAL SUSTAINABILITY
<i>Period of time</i>	Industrial period
<i>Explanation</i>	No limit of human power over natural (driven by economics).
<i>The result</i>	Highlighting economic growth. Sustainability defined beyond the desire to protect.
PHASE 3	UNSUSTAINABILITY
<i>Period of time</i>	Post-industrial
<i>Explanation</i>	Emphasizing economic development without considering the consequences for the environment.
<i>The result</i>	Exhaustion of natural resources and orientation towards economic growth.
PHASE 4	THE RETURN OF SUSTAINABILITY
<i>Period of time</i>	The present and the immediate future
<i>Explanation</i>	An economic and moral obligation for the needs of future generations.
<i>The result</i>	Economic growth and development within ecological limits: complementarity of environmental protection and economic development.

Source: Stojanović [3] adjusted according to Boyd [5]

Bartula [6] points out that a large number of experts have noticed a conflict in the concept of sustainable development. On the one hand, there is a desire to stay within the carrying capacity of natural ecosystems, and on the other hand, there is a desire for growth and development. The question arises as to whether the goals of sustainable development can be achieved in the real world with the constraints imposed by the environment. Perhaps it is better to set the goals of “survivability” rather than “sustainability”, that is, creating the conditions to survive.

The authors Euston and Gibson [7] define the concept of sustainable development as “a moral value in itself”. The fact is that the sustainable development of nature is an imperative for current generations and the responsibility (obligation) of all people to preserve and rationally use natural resources on Earth in a primary form that will enable future generations to use them. They highlight the following ethical and moral values:

- ❖ Care for future generations;
- ❖ Respect for ecological integrity;
- ❖ Responsibility for the preservation of natural system on Earth;
- ❖ Return of justice;
- ❖ Community respect; and
- ❖ Commitment to democracy and civic participation.

Caring for future generations is an incentive and motivation to realize that it is necessary to think not only about one's own and personal interests, but also to give importance to future generations. Sustainability requires respect for nature and its resources, i.e. its connections, relationships and interdependence. Once a degraded and devastated natural environment can hardly be restored to its original (basic) state. That is why it is necessary to act and establish various measures, instruments and laws in order to establish an ecological balance.

Management of sustainable development requires the involvement of all institutions, starting from the national level (state authorities), regional and local self-governments, business entities, various associations, non-governmental organizations and the rest of the population. It is the only way to enable the application of the concept of sustainable development, which is significant for the entire society, because there are often conflicting interests of the local population, tourists, the environment, current and future generations [7].

3. MANAGING THE CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

On the planet Earth, the influence of various representatives/institutions that regulate and manage the concept of sustainable development has been registered. The economic component of the concept, based on the agreement of the European Parliament (European Parliament, 2012), has the most important role in decision-making, apart from the social and environmental components. In order to achieve adequate and best solutions, it is necessary to incorporate all three components into one inseparable whole [8, 9, 10.]

At the Summit “Rio +20”, which was held in 2012, (June Rio De Janeiro), representatives of all institutions at the planetary level had a common goal and interest, and it primarily refers to the applicability of the concept of sustainable development in all European countries and the world. The main topics at the “Rio + 20 Summit were related to the “green economy” [10, 11, 12, 13].

The Summit was preceded by the Fifth Global Review of the United Nations Environment Program (UNEAP) – GEO5 – The Environment for the Future We Want. The warnings highlighted in this Report point to pessimistic forecasts for the survival of humanity and the world is on the path of “unsustainable development”, unless urgent and adequate transition measures towards sustainable development and ecological balance are taken. If current policy and change strategies are strengthened, the achievement of potential sustainable development goals could be realistic by the middle of this century. Ecologically responsible tourism aims to provide a quality tourist experience without causing environmental and social damage. Gaps between what “Should be” and what “roles” are discussed, with implications for the tourism industry and particularly for the training and education sector of that industry [10, 14].

Table 2 – Managing the concept of sustainable development

Management principles	Elements for integration	Challenges
<i>Horizontal integration</i>	Environmental, economic and social policy	In the future, the state will establish its political resources (environmental, profit and social) in a coherent manner.
<i>Vertical integration</i>	Local, regional and national level of policy making	The state government should work to achieve common goals.
<i>Participation (stakeholder integration)</i>	Formerly: decision makers and stakeholders Today: the state, the business and civil society	Stakeholders from the environmental and human population sectors should be included in the system of decisive topics.

<i>Integration of knowledge</i>	Knowledge from different areas of politics	In the future, states will base their determination on the facts provided by society and the achieved scientific work.
<i>Intergenerational equality (integration of goals from the time aspect)</i>	Short and long time frames	Governments should implement long-term political solutions in the framework of their pre-election campaigns.

Source: Đekić and Hafner [15] adjusted according to Steurer [16]

The concept of sustainable development requires the incorporation, that is, the integration of economic, social and environmental goals in the decision-making process and the implementation of the achieved results. According to the author Steurer [16], horizontal and vertical integration of different levels and management aims to achieve common interests. Balancing, i.e. equal consideration of (economic, social and ecological) components in real conditions is practically impossible. For these reasons, it is necessary to decide by distributing the responsibilities of all participants at the local, regional and national level. The integration of all factors and dimensions is the basis for the objective implementation of the “green agenda”.

Procedures and measures in connection with the comprehensive factors of sustainable development, through horizontal and vertical integration, represent a significant feat for all countries (Figure 1). The most important thing in that entire process is the determination of the hierarchy and responsibility for the preparation, implementation and finally the final completion of strategic documents and activities [17].

Figure 1. Integration policy of managing the concept of sustainable development

Source: Đekić and Hafner [15] and Steurer [16]

The mechanisms of integration of different policies depend on each country and over a long period of time they are changed, supplemented and perfected. In order to establish horizontal integration, it is necessary to draw up a Strategy that includes all three factors/components: economic, environmental and social within each sector individually. It is necessary to harmonize the different ministries and state bodies of each country to cooperate with each other and contribute to the common goal and interest. In order to enable adequate support/acceptability, it is necessary to achieve and resolve various conflict situations [17].

One example of horizontal integration is the incorporation of the environmental dimension of "green agenda" into other segments of different political spheres. In the European Union, the Environmental Action Plans (third, fourth and fifth) envisage the incorporation of environmental policy into the policy of development protection of nature, agriculture, industry, energy and transport, according to the "bottom-up" principle [17].

Vertical integration between different levels of policy management structures is necessary for adequate and rational problem solving. The complexity and complexity of global problems (destruction of biodiversity and climate change) are not only a problem of the competent ministry but of the entire vertical chain of different institutions (European Commission, state, national, regional and local governments) [17].

4. CONCLUSION

The most significant challenges to be faced in the future are: ecosystem loss, climate change, health care, water scarcity, food and energy crisis. In this direction, improvements are necessary, i.e. coordination, connection and cooperation between the activities of different sectors at the state level, but also the cooperation of the state and social sectors.

According to the authors Malloy and Fennel [18] the understanding of the nature of ethical codes from a theoretical and methodological perspective is evident in the primary/early stage. For the purpose of better understanding, a conceptual model was used to analyze the ethical content and normative reference point in the context of nature protection. It was found that the existing codes are mostly deontological in nature. The authors caution future writers of ethical codes to consider rule-utilitarianism as the basis for code content. Such a theoretical foundation would be more useful in understanding the intent and educational value of codes, as well as the impact of these codes on tourist behavior.

Јовашевић³ [4] Радукић⁴ [19] Ђекић and Хафнер [15] announced key recommendations for improving the concept of sustainable development at the "Rio + 20" conference:

- ❖ Changes in international documents, resolutions, strategies and programs related to the area of space protection;
- ❖ Implementation of confusions or conflicting thoughts and goals due to the conclusion of bilateral agreements;
- ❖ Creation of innovative and redefinition of old legislation and agreements in management of the concept of sustainable development;

³ "Healthy living environment" enables accessibility where every person has the right to an unpolluted nature/environment and information about their position. In this way, all the necessary conditions were created for quality and efficient realization and protection of the right to information about the environment.

⁴ The system of environmental protection and improvement was regulated by a large number of regulations in the sectoral, divided powers of various state institutions, so that it could not be harmonized and consistently perform its function.

- ❖ Strengthening of the national, regional and local sustainable development management system;
- ❖ Better integration of state and private sectors politics [15].

Responsible development in the future should be incorporated into the economic, social and cultural concept, which is harmonized with the tendencies of nature protection and improvement of the quality of the natural area, which will ensure a quality way of life. Many state institutions, organizations and societies began to take more seriously the importance and function of the concept of sustainable development and to more actively deal with this issue. The result of all this is manifested through various conferences, summits, workshops, symposiums and congresses and through the adoption of various strategies, projects, studies and programs of protected natural resources.

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RENEWABLE ENERGY AND SERBIA CASE

Ljiljana Pecić¹ Marija Mitrović² Doloris Bešić-Vukašinić³

Abstract: *The world lacks a safe, low-carbon, and cheap large-scale energy infrastructure. To ensure everyone has access to clean and safe energy, we need to understand energy consumption and its impacts around the world today and how this has changed over time. Climate changes are our reality and during 2023 whole world have seen the manifestations of climate changes. This paper intends to enlighten the importance of Serbian strong dedication to Green Agenda.*

Key words: *energy consumption, renewable, property damages*

1. INTRODUCTION

Today's world is based on the use of electricity, not only for business, but also for the daily life of modern man. As the world's population grew and industrialization accelerated around the world, energy needs became greater and greater. Uncontrolled development has led to the pollution of rivers, air and the entire environment, as well as the appearance of ozone holes. Finally, the average annual temperature has increased significantly and we are witnessing more and more frequent manifestations of climate change.

Climate change manifestations (floods, heat waves, fires) are accompanied by large material damages. For example, in Serbia, the total material damage caused by extreme events from 2000 to 2022 was estimated at more than 5 billion euros. The biggest damage occurred in 2014, and it is estimated to around 1.5 billion euros, of which 192 million euros was damage caused to roads. For the sake of comparison, the annual budget of the Republic of Serbia for road maintenance is between 300 and 350 million euros, of which around 60 million euros are allocated for urgent maintenance works (which in many cases are due to the consequences of climate change) [1].

People are generally not aware of the energy they consume, nor of its amount. Therefore, the first step towards achieving sustainable goals is measurement. Analytical house "McKinsey" globally estimates a tripling of electricity consumption by the 2050, due to an increase in living standards (air conditioners, a large number of new charging stations for electric cars in private and public buildings, etc.) [2]. Because of all these problems, in the last 30 years countries have started to implement renewable (clean) energy more and more. Renewable energy sources include: hydropower, wind energy, solar energy, energy obtained from biomass (from previously living but almost dead organisms) and geothermal energy.

2. GLOBAL SHARE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY IN TOTAL ENERGY PRODUCTION

Europe is warming twice as fast as the world average, so the countries of our continent are looking for ways to accelerate decarbonization, while meeting energy and food needs. A good sign is that energy production from renewable sources is growing faster than energy production from non-renewable sources.

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According to European Environment Agency (EEA) early estimates, 22.5% of energy consumed in the EU in 2022 generated from renewable sources [3], while in the first quarter of 2023, 39% of the total energy in the EU was generated from renewable sources [4]. That is a big improvement, compared to 2010, when the share of renewable energy was only 19% of global production. EU strives to become climate neutral till the 2050 [4]. The goal is to reduce net emissions by at least 55% by 2030.

Globally, solar and wind are expected to be the major drivers of growth in renewables this decade. In the Net Zero Scenario presented by IEA, global solar and wind share should reach 40% by 2030 [5].

Electricity production from dirty energy sources began to fall in half of the world in 2017, while some countries such as Slovakia and Canada (but also North Macedonia) recorded the maximum share of fossil fuels much earlier, at the beginning of the 2000s [6].

One hundred and seven of the world's 215 economies have reached the peak of fossil fuel use in electricity generation, according to a new analysis by research center Ember. The results are based on data on electricity generation in the period from 2000 to 2022[6].

The problem is very complex - one would expect that when a country is economically strong, even when it has large energy resources, it would choose more expensive sources of renewable energy in order to give its citizens a cleaner environment. However, on the one hand, we have developed countries that sacrifice the quality of the environment for the sake of economic development (for example, the USA), while on the other hand, certain developed countries put the quality of the environment as a priority (for example, Norway and Canada, which have large oil and gas reserves, but most of the energy comes from renewable sources). Also, we have countries such as Ethiopia and Brazil, which do not have large energy reserves, so they are investing in renewable energy. Both countries have great potentials of hydroelectric power (rivers Nile and Amazon). China, where renewable energy is still not predominant, has a 50% increase in the share of renewable energy in the last two years. The reason for this is the large pollution of the environment due to the industrial capacity of the country. Certain countries, e.g. Russia, Arab states, Nigeria, etc. do not invest in renewable energy sources because they have a large amount of fossil energy resources. However, as countries develop, the trend is changing more and more, so that renewable energy occupies a larger and larger part of global production. Figure 1 shows the share of energy produced from renewable sources in total energy production [7].

Figure 1- The share of renewable energy in total energy production by country in 2022 [7]

Energy consumption per capita is a very good indicator of how country is developed or how affordable energy is for the people in that country. The most developed countries include all Scandinavian countries (of which Iceland is the largest consumer in the world), Canada, South Korea, as well as almost all Arab countries, of which Bahrain is the largest consumer. Another factor for consumption is the climate, as well as the culture of the society itself. Countries with a cold climate spend more while countries with a warmer climate, spend less (eg Australia).

An example of how culture affects consumption is Japan, which despite having a high score on the HDI scale, spends little, due to the frugal culture of its people.

Ember's list includes countries that have taken a serious leap in recent years in the energy transition to renewable sources, such as: *Denmark, Finland, Sweden* and the United States of America. Perhaps surprisingly, our country also found itself in this society.

3. DIFFERENTE TYPES OF RENEWABLE ENERGY

The application of any of the renewable energy sources depends primarily on the assessment of availability, but also on the assessment of the ratio of advantages and disadvantages. The annual distribution of energy by source is given in Figure 2. For example, hydropower is very efficient, but unfortunately it can disrupt the environment of the rivers where the hydropower plants are located.

At first glance, solar panels are an ideal solution, but, solar panels themselves reach a high temperature and can harm, even destroy insects (bees) in the environment, change the composition of the soil, etc. The most optimal places for installation are in the deserts, but since it is difficult to maintain the panels that are far from the rest of the infrastructure of the country that installed them, it is not worth it.

Wind energy can damage the ecosystem as well as solar energy (propellers can disturb the flight of birds by their rotation, and a collision with a flock of storks can happen).

Wind and solar reached a record 12% of global electricity in 2022 [1]. The largest share in the total production of electricity from renewable sources belongs to hydropower with 37%, while solar energy is in second place with 31% [2].

Figure 2 – Energy consumption by source in 2022 [7]

Renewable energy sources accounted for more than 50% of electricity in Greece in the first half of 2023. After Greece was hit by a catastrophic fire caused by climate change in the summer of 2023, Greece intensified work on the construction of offshore wind farms, emphasizing the urgency of reducing dependence on fossil fuels. The national goal is to obtain 2 gigawatts of electricity from offshore wind farms by 2030, which is equivalent to a tenth of the capacity of onshore wind farms. This ambitious undertaking could supply with electricity around 1.5 million Greek households. Although environmental groups have expressed concern about potential environmental damage during construction, measures have been taken to protect environmentally sensitive areas and marine activities [8].

By the way, in October 2022, for a short time, for 5 hours, Greece worked exclusively on renewable energy sources, thanks to onshore wind energy, solar energy and hydropower. [8]

Two French scientists, Jacques Pironon i Filip De Donato, searching for fossil fuels under the soil of northeastern France, found an amount of methane underground in the mining basin of Lorraine, using a "world-first" specialized probe, capable of analyzing gases dissolved in the water of rock formations deep underground. The scientists performed the calculations and estimated that between 6 million and 250 million metric tons of hydrogen could be found, which would make this deposit one of the largest when it comes to "white hydrogen". Hydrogen produces only water when burned, which makes it very attractive as a potential source of clean energy for industries such as aviation, shipping and steelmaking. This will significantly rise share of green energy in total energy production in France [9].

4. SERBIA'S RENEWABLE ENERGY CASE

Ember's list includes countries that in recent years have taken a serious leap in the energy transition to renewable sources (Denmark, Finland, Sweden and the United States of America). Perhaps surprisingly, Serbia also found itself in this list, where even to this day two thirds of the electricity comes from coal. The question arises - how is this possible?

Ember calculated that Serbia got the most electricity from dirty energy sources 12 years ago, and that during 2022 fossil fuels generated 13.1% less electricity than the record 2011. This actually illustrates that the peak of fossil fuels, unfortunately, does not mean green power grid transformation.

In the last decade, electricity production in Serbia has declined. In 2011, 38.600 gigawatt-hours of electricity were produced, and ten years later, in 2021, that figure decreased to 38.235. But the key is not only in the amount of gigawatt-hours generated, but also in the plants from which they came. According to the data of the Republic Institute of Statistics, in 2021, hydropower plants produced 2.500 gigawatt-hours of electricity more than ten years earlier, and production in thermal power plants, which still produce about two-thirds of electricity, fell from 28.672 gigawatt-hours to 23.734 gigawatt-hours [6].

Therefore, due to a drop in consumption or a jump in electricity imports, Serbia is among the total of twenty-five world economies that have already achieved the peak of fossil fuel use.

The Green Agenda for the Western Balkans is a regional development strategy. Its goal is to help developing countries harmonize environmental regulations with European standards. The Green Agenda for the Western Balkans is, therefore, a strategic framework for a just transition towards climate neutrality. The Western Balkan countries, and Serbia among them, confirmed their commitment to such a European future by signing the Sofia Declaration in November 2020. In order to put the Green Agenda into practice, an Action Plan for the implementation of the Green Agenda was drawn up in 2021. The plan contains numerous activities that the countries of the Western Balkans should have completed, or at least started. However, most of the work from the Action Plan is still ahead of us, and completed activities are the exception rather than the rule. As one of the contracting parties in the Energy Community, Serbia should also participate in this endeavor by increasing the share of renewable sources in consumption to 40.7% by the end of the decade [10].

The Coalition 27 organization is very important in Serbia when talking about the green agenda. This organization was founded by civil society organizations in 2014 with the aim of monitoring and contributing to the process of harmonizing and implementing the policies and regulations of the Republic of Serbia with the legal acquis of the European Union in the field of environment and climate change (Chapter 27 in the EU accession negotiations). This organization also prepares the Shadow Report. The Shadow Report provides an overview of the achievements of the Republic of Serbia in the mentioned areas and provides recommendations on how to improve existing processes. The report is made available to the public and sent to the relevant national and European institutions [10].

Coalition 27 also produced *Green cards* based on the data obtained in 2022 through the Green Incubator project. As part of the project, which was initiated by the international environmental protection organization The Nature Conservancy (TNC), researchers mapped the best locations for solar power plants in our country. The result of the study is a map with a total of 100 most favorable places in Serbia for the construction of solar power plants with an individual installed capacity of 10 MW (Figure 3). The generated results were checked by experts in the fields of biodiversity, agriculture, tourism, cultural heritage, spatial and urban planning [11],[12].

By implementing projects in the mapped areas, solar energy capacities in our country would increase by 1 GW. With 100 selected locations, enough electricity could be produced to power 200 thousand households, which is 10% of total number of Serbian households. Annual carbon savings would amount to one million tons. The necessary solar panels for this could be installed on 25 square kilometers. It is an area equivalent to half of the municipality of Sremski Karlovci, one of the smallest in Serbia [13].

Figure 3 – One hundred most favorable locations for the development of solar power plants in Serbia [11]

Hope is certainly inspired by the fact that in May 2023, 51% of energy was produced from renewable sources, of which 47% from hydropower [13].

5. CONCLUSION

Every industry uses energy: by 2050, electricity use will triple. That is why the European Parliament directs activities so that by 2030, 42.5% of energy consumption in the EU is realized from renewable sources, and the share of as much as 45% is aimed for.

In contrast to Serbia, which owes its "success" to lower demand for energy, seventy-eight economies, which gradually reduced the use of dirty energy sources, managed to replace fossil fuels with clean energy. On top of that, production has increased in four world economies, but fossil fuels have been left at previous levels, which means that new consumption is met exclusively by clean energy.

Despite the fact that in Serbia the topic of environmental protection seems to be on the political margins, experts have noticed that the awareness of its importance is growing among citizens. The reason is that the public does not get all the information it needs to really participate in decision-making.

In addition to implementation in practice, the completion of important legislative processes that should have already been completed is also missing in Serbia. In the last months of 2023, there was a noticeable increase in the number of households that produce electricity, and at the end of the year, the

Draft Integrated Energy and Climate Plan for the period until 2030 was adopted. The question of financial resources is always raised, but when you take into account that the investments in the specialized exhibition EXPO 2027, during 2024, will be greater than the investments in solving many environmental problems, and in education, obviously the priorities are at stake. In 2023, for the price of one Belgrade apartment, a solar power plant could be built that produces enough energy for 30 to 40 households [14].

And finally, it must be emphasized that although the green agenda is of a regional nature, reforms at the national level and the creation of an Integrated National Plan for Energy and Climate are key to its success. The environmental protection strategy of the Republic of Serbia, which is currently being developed, is structurally followed by the five pillars of the Green Agenda and should be a kind of umbrella strategy for reforms in this sector, at the national level.

At least four of five areas covered by the Green Agenda, relate to Chapter 27: climate, energy and mobility (decarbonization), circular economy, pollution reduction and biodiversity conservation. The fifth area (agricultural and food production) is also indirectly related to Chapter 27.

During 2023, a new law on renewable energy sources was adopted, in the last months of 2023, there was a noticeable increase in the number of households that produce electricity, and at the end of the year, the Draft Integrated Energy and Climate Plan for the period until 2030 was adopted [14].

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ON CONNECTION BETWEEN SERIOUS GAMES AND SAFETY EDUCATION CURRICULA ENHANCEMENT

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Abstract: Gamification in higher education is becoming increasingly important as a tool for addressing issues related to student motivation and enhancing their overall engagement. Gamified elements make the presentation of educational content practical and easier to remember and understand. This, in turn, results in an improved learning experience. The unique characteristics of institutions and study programmes can influence the effectiveness of serious games applications and their potential outcomes. The paper discusses the possibilities of e-learning with serious games that follow the principles of constructivist learning as a didactic approach that can help in the realisation of certain goals of safety education.

Key words: higher education, safety, knowledge transfer, serious games, trends

1. INTRODUCTION

The knowledge revolution, coupled with economic globalisation, has created favourable conditions for the knowledge industry and the widespread integration of modern technologies in education. The use of information and communication technology (ICT) in higher education institutions has become imperative for teaching and e-learning processes within the modern academic community. E-learning is anticipated to offer education at one's fingertips, education on demand, and just-in-time learning, aiming to provide a more effective approach to learning and teaching compared to traditional methods and enhance the overall quality of the learning process. However, some scholars connect these expectations to pedagogical misconceptions, suggesting that a careless and inappropriate adoption of e-learning may result in reduced acceptance, unsatisfactory outcomes, and inefficiencies among students [1].

However, the potential of e-learning lies in its capacity, facilitated by modern information and communication technology (ICT), to bring about pedagogical innovations in higher education. Considering the vastness and proliferation of information, one cannot help but question whether educational institutions are losing their traditional role as mere transmitters of knowledge. Contemporary educators and andragogists emphasise that it is more crucial for professors to cultivate in students the abilities to locate, select, and critically evaluate relevant information - fostering skills in communication, independence, responsibility, and critical thinking. Even with the most advanced software and hardware in educational institutions, addressing the issues of effective learning is paramount. Knowles (1984) highlighted the importance of a collaborative and welcoming learning environment with mutual respect and trust, fostering and encouraging student activity (in [2]). A socio-constructivist understanding of knowledge acquisition is crucial for e-learning, focusing on an approach tailored to the individual [3]. In this context, the concept of an "open learning environment" [4] is noteworthy, rooted in authentic situations, enabling research, and featuring a system centred on the student, placing them at the core of teaching and learning. The design of these learning environments adheres to the principles of self-directed learning, incorporating collaborative, problem-oriented approaches to tackle intricate real-life scenarios. This structure fosters the development of creative solutions, nurturing critical thinking or action competence [5].

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2. BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

While the term "serious games" has been in existence since 1970, as attributed to Abt [6], the application of games for educational purposes has a lengthy history associated with various board games and, more recently, military applications. Various authors attribute the emergence of serious games to the limitations of existing educational methods, which struggle to adapt adequately to the evolving environment [6],[7]. Primarily, this is linked to the weak interactivity of teaching, a lack of active student participation, out-dated content presentation methods, and a disconnection from practical problems encountered in real-world scenarios.

Advancements in information and communication technologies have facilitated their daily integration into various activities, including education. These technologies simplify the visualisation of teaching content and the presentation of specific problem units. Substantial software development in the 1980s allowed ideas previously confined to laboratory conditions or military applications (e.g., The Bradley Trainer, [8]) to enter the market and be accessible to users. The game industry, experiencing significant growth, produced titles like Flight Simulator and The Surgeon (later also Life & Death) that transcended the realm of mere entertainment to varying degrees. The educational value of such content heavily relied on clear user instructions, encouraging users not to give up in case the learning curve proved slow. The early 21st century saw the development of several games by the US Army for simulating military training, with America's Army standing out among them. Anticipated exponential market growth in serious games is expected in the near future [8], driven by the increasing demand for specialized education. Higher education is no exception, having specific needs for serious game applications that can either substitute for or complement traditional content and methods. The specifics of education in the field of safety, which involve assessing the emergence of specific types of risks and the manifestation of adverse effects on individuals, the environment, or society as a whole, make it ideal for the development of various types of serious games.

In [9], the authors defined gamification taxonomy, comprising five fundamental dimensions: ecological, social, personal, fictional, and performance. The ecological dimension includes elements represented as properties that allow the environment to be populated with content, facilitating interaction with the user. This dimension introduces a certain level of randomness, or the probability of specific outcomes occurring, where the user makes choices, performs transactions, or exchanges different types of resources within time restrictions. The social dimension facilitates interaction among students, enabling collaboration, experience exchange, and the cultivation of a reputation in the presence of social pressure. It depicts real-life situations requiring communication and coordination for the execution of complex activities. The personal dimension influences the user by providing motivation through specific content, goals, and problems to solve, and stimuli encountered during activities. This ensures that activities have meaning and connections to real-life situations. The content representing the user, along with fictional elements defining the reasons for engaging in certain activities, is crucial. A narrative can be delivered through either textual or auditory means, contributing to the overarching storyline.

3. SERIOUS GAMES IN SAFETY EDUCATION

In the case of safety education, serious games can be very useful, regardless of whether it is occupational health and safety, fire safety, environmental protection, or disaster management. When considering occupational health and safety, it is particularly important to simulate scenarios from a real work environment in order to imitate the state of the work environment and certain events and then apply safety measures. Thus, students prepare for potential dangers that employees may face when performing work activities at work [10]. In this way, a better familiarisation with safety practices is achieved, and their memorization becomes easier if the training is turned into various forms of interactive games that include safety activities. Contents include, but are not limited to, materials containing gamified and interactive elements (narratives, scenarios, tests), safety trainings realised in the form of simulations in an augmented reality or virtual reality environment with realistic scenarios, obtaining points or digital objects for completing tasks in accordance with safety procedures or based on attending training, identifying potential hazards in a simulated work environment, forwarding micro-lessons on safety in a

gamified form (challenges, quizzes, instant feedback), or a tour of facilities in a real environment with information on dangers (tags) and safety measures that need to be applied [10],[11]. Group work encourages collaboration between students, which brings to the fore the importance of exchanging information about safety in a real work environment.

In the domain of fire protection, situations related to fires are simulated to enable response, evacuation, and the use of equipment. Using the convenience of augmented reality or virtual reality, exercise scenarios can be implemented, equipment used, and decisions made, i.e., the realisation of fire protection scenarios with different roles [12],[13]. Gamified approaches can improve the effectiveness of training and create awareness of the importance of safety. Also, interactive work based on scenarios enables longer memorization of critical information, the acquisition of practical skills, and the practice of decision-making in critical situations when a fire hazard occurs or during a fire.

In the field of environmental protection, gamified approaches help students identify various environmental hazards and apply appropriate safety protocols, as well as learn more about sustainability. Typical examples are simulations of environmental protection scenarios in augmented or virtual reality (disaster response, pollution control), the development of content that highlights eco-friendly activities and encourages sustainable practices (carbon footprint, environmental compliance), training on proper waste management, waste sorting, possibilities of recycling and waste reduction, a virtual tour of areas with environmental problems, or industrial plants with environmental safety measures [14],[15]. Serious games in the field of environmental protection highlight the importance of responsibility and sustainability.

When applying gamification in disaster management education, realistic scenarios are used, which encourages efficient use of available resources in critical situations and decision-making based on limited available information. Resource allocation based on specific disaster scenarios and limitations, evaluation of response plans for disaster scenarios, definition of response based on management strategies, resource allocation and communication, application of appropriate communication strategies, simulating emergency evacuation scenarios, and defining different routes and ways of collaboration can be considered [16],[17].

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

E-learning, grounded in the principles and theories of constructivist learning, presents numerous possibilities to support the development of key competencies in safety education. It is crucial to consider the form of implementation that can both induce and facilitate active student learning, motivation, and competency development, along with identifying fundamental learning methods that can uphold such requirements. In this context, serious games present distinct didactic opportunities, fostering "open learning," facilitating student interaction, and supporting the processes of competency development. The synergy between serious games and the specific objectives of safety education brings several additional potential advantages, adding extra value to education in this domain and, simultaneously, providing pedagogical significance to the technology.

The paper discusses the possibilities of e-learning with serious games that follow the principles of constructivist learning as a didactic approach that can help in the realisation of certain goals of safety education. It is evident that e-learning holds promise for pedagogical innovations, yet it presents certain challenges for both students and teachers. Students need to adapt to the concept of a learning environment and independent learning, as they are often accustomed to more "traditional" forms of learning where they play a passive role. Activating students in this manner necessitates robust support from teachers to facilitate the systematic development of essential skills and foster students' self-confidence. At the same time, the role of the teacher is evolving towards the position of a moderator who significantly influences students' learning outcomes. Consequently, teacher training becomes imperative. We believe that recognising and addressing these challenges can offer substantial benefits to modern universities. In any case, to assist students in confronting the challenges of the twenty-first

century, there is a necessity to transition from existing traditional education models to those aligning with the knowledge economy and the imperative of lifelong learning.

The unique characteristics of institutions and study programmes can influence the effectiveness of serious games applications and their potential outcomes. These factors primarily pertain to the feasibility of implementing various types of competitions or interactive problem-solving approaches. Motivational elements spur increased participation in educational activities, contributing to better information reception. Group and personalised learning, centred on problem-solving and the cultivation of critical thinking, facilitate the development of a workforce with distinct attributes, emphasising teamwork and nurturing various soft skills. The simulation of scenarios from real work environments further enables the integration of theoretical knowledge with practical applications.

Despite these advantages, certain challenges may arise in the application of serious games in higher education. Student responses to specific activities can vary, and the outcomes of practical activities conducted in this manner may not consistently align with the intended goals. Activities need to be tailored to accommodate group dynamics, specific students, and the subject matter, posing a considerable challenge in creating suitable content. Additionally, time constraints, coupled with group-specific dynamics, can impact the successful implementation of such activities during classes.

When introducing serious games, potential problems can arise. First of all, students can focus on earning rewards rather than learning outcomes. Also, the interest and engagement of students can be different, and gamified elements do not have to be a motivating factor for everyone. Simplifying certain teaching content through gamification can lead to a loss of time and a loss of focus on the educational content. If competition is encouraged, it can lead to unwanted relationships in the learning environment. Some content cannot be accessed by certain students if they do not have technical capabilities (for example, a smart phone). Over time, the effect of gamification decreases, so it is necessary to apply it to a reasonable extent and refresh it with new content, taking care that students understand the key concepts.

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IMPLEMENTING PRINCIPLES AND OBJECTIVES OF LOW-CARBON DEVELOPMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: Global climate change observed in the mid-20th century is dominantly caused by greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions due to human activity. The Republic of Serbia is not an exception concerning climate change, and additionally – it's economy is highly dependent on fossil fuels (high carbon dependency). Observed climate change in Serbia between 1961 and 2017., already presents the treat for the infrastructure, agriculture productivity, water availability and public health, and could jeopardize the competitiveness of Serbia's economy in the medium and long-term. This requires huge shift of the Serbian economy towards the low-carbon economy (decarbonized economy) and climate resilient development, which means economy based on energy sources that produce low levels of GHG emissions and have low carbon footprint. The role of higher education in Serbia would be to promote transition to low-carbon (climate neutral) economy and climate resilient society, through activities such as training for new skills and competencies, capacity building and awareness raising.

Key words: low-carbon development, higher education, decarbonization, industry, skills and competencies

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the pre-industrial period (1850-1900) the surface air temperature over land has risen almost twice as much as the average global temperature, and climate change, including increase in the frequency and intensity of extreme weather conditions, have adversely affected food security and land ecosystems and also contributed to desertification and degradation of land surfaces in many regions [1]. As an average temperature in Serbia increase of 0.36 °C per decade between 1961 and 2017, and the average precipitation decrease up to 10% in the same period, the risks that climate change poses to Serbia's sustainable development are evident and already present a threat to the economy and public health [2]. Climatic hazards that cause the most damage and losses in Serbia and whose intensity and frequency are increasing, are heat waves, intense precipitation and droughts, and other climatic hazards (floods, landslides, mudslides, fires), all exacerbated by air, water, and soil pollution [3]. Climate change scenarios for Serbia until 2100 (compared to the reference period 1986-2005) predict an increase of an average temperature between 2.0 °C and 4.3 °C and decrease up to 4.5% of average annual precipitation until 2100 [2]. The obligations of the Republic of Serbia under the Law on ratification of the Paris Agreement and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), require a long-term huge shift of the Serbian economy towards the low-carbon and climate resilient development [2]. This is especially oriented toward Serbian energy sector, industry and agriculture, which have the largest share in GHG emissions (80,6 %, 5,2 % and 8,6 % respectively) [2]. The rate of build-up of carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the atmosphere can be reduced by taking advantage of the fact that atmospheric CO₂ can accumulate as carbon in vegetation and soils in terrestrial ecosystems [4]. Under the UNFCCC, any process, activity or mechanism which removes a greenhouse gas (GHG) from the atmosphere is referred to as a "sink". Human activities impact terrestrial sinks, through land use, land-use change and forestry (LULUCF), consequently, the exchange of CO₂ (carbon cycle) between the terrestrial biosphere and the atmosphere is altered [4].

Low carbon development Strategy of the Republic of Serbia is oriented toward balancing global greenhouse (GHG) emissions and sinks in the second half of the 21st century, as well as toward the EU

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accession process, and the vision is that, by 2050, Serbia will be a low-carbon society with a competitive and resource-efficient economy which provides citizens new, green jobs and a quality life in a climate-resilient society [2].

2. LOW-CARBON DEVELOPMENT: PRINCIPLES AND OBJECTIVES

The concept of low carbon development (which has its roots in the UNFCCC adopted in Rio in 1992.), is now generally expressed using the term low-emission development strategies (LEDS - also known as low-carbon development strategies, or low-carbon growth plans); LEDS are generally used to describe forward-looking national economic development plans or strategies that encompass low-emission and/or climate-resilient economic growth (OECD, IEA 2010) [5]. The ISO 14064-1:2019 standard defines a GHG emission as "greenhouse gas emitted into the atmosphere"; GHG emissions result either directly, e.g. from the manufacture of products, or indirectly, e.g. from the heating of business premises, from a company's business activities. GHG emissions consist mostly of carbon dioxide (CO₂) – cca 80%, methane (CH₄) – 11,5 %, nitrous oxide (N₂O) – 6 %, and the rest of GHG emissions (3 %) is made of hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), perfluorocarbons (PFCs), sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆) and nitrogen trifluoride (NF₃) [6].

2.1. Reducing carbon emissions (decarbonization)

One of the most important aims in reaching sustainability in industry is carbon balanced production. Carbon (CO₂) emissions from industrial processes can be quantified and compared by companies themselves, in the same production scope; carbon balancing is achieved when the CO₂ produced during the entire production and final product delivery have been offset [7]. To make production more sustainable, socially responsible industrial companies should find at the market and purchase carbon balanced raw materials, carbon balanced tools and equipment; also, they can measure their carbon footprint and take steps to reduce and offset it.

Figure 1 – Greenhouse gases (GHG) generation in industrial companies [7]

LEGEND: **Scope 1** - Direct emissions from owned or controlled sources; **Scope 2** - Indirect emissions from the generation of acquired and consumed electricity, steam, heat, or cooling; **Scope 3** - All indirect emissions (not included in Scope 2) that occur in the value chain of the reporting company, including both upstream³ and downstream⁴ emissions

³ refers to all activities related to the organization's suppliers - those parties that source raw material inputs to send to the manufacturer

⁴ refers to activities post-manufacturing, namely distributing the product to the final customer

Carbon – neutral industry, still competitive, low-cost, environmentally friendly, actual and up to the modern world and new arrivals, should understand how important it is for everyone in the production process (from suppliers to dealing with wastes and effluents) to do their part in making sure they conserve the planet for future generations [7]. In general, all industry should be committed to several goals and principles:

- high and constant quality of the whole production run (non under question!),
- attractiveness (design) and usage value of the final product (non under question!),
- high productivity (production speed, serviceability of machines and devices),
- high degree of process automation and usage of digital workflows,
- competitive price of the final product,
- respect for the principles of safety at work and environmental protection and
- increase of emissions to environment (including GHG emissions and solid waste).

One of the most important principles of modern industry on its way to decarbonization is the responsible and rational use of basic and auxiliary raw materials and resources: energy (from renewable resources if possible), water (with recirculation and re-use if possible) and air. This principle is binding for all participants in the production chain: suppliers of raw materials and equipment, manufacturers of production systems (machines and tools), subcontractors and companies dealing with waste treatment [7].

3. EDUCATION FOR LOW-CARBON DEVELOPMENT

Specific objective number 5 of the Strategy [2] is to promote transition to climate neutral economy and climate resilient society, which present horizontal activities and will be implemented, among else, through education, training for new skills, capacity building and awareness raising. A list of different measures is developed, the implementation of which will ensure the fulfilment of specific, and thereby general objectives of the Strategy. To implement low-carbon development in industry and all aspects of living, it is important for it to be presented everywhere - in people's everyday lives, whether in transport, reuse, repair, waste prevention, food and consumers behaviors and decision-making about supporting local businesses, circular designs and sustainability every day [7]. In education in the field of environmental protection the term „low carbon development“ is similar to terms „decarbonization“ and „sustainable development“, whose principles are already implemented in higher education.

Achieving sustainability by applying the principles of low carbon economy in industrial processes demands a multidisciplinary approach and good insight in technical details concerning production process itself, as well as in economics and management. Obtaining carbon neutral processes is based on teamwork among experts in the field, thus it needs competent staff, with the demanded skills, knowledge, and competencies [7]. That is why it is so important for students – future experts in this field to get useful competencies and knowledge about importance of decarbonization and its accomplishment.

3.1. Preparing GHG emissions report

One of a good examples of introducing low-carbon principles and objectives in higher education is including learning outcome such as „preparing Report of GHG emissions and it's verification“. According to the Serbian Climat change Law, operators are obligated to make such a report once a year (for the past year) and to verify it by the authorized institution. According to the Serbian official Rule Book on monitoring and reporting of GHG emissions, reports include data on GHG emissions that must meet the requirements related to completeness of data on GHG emissions, consistency, comparability and transparency of data using the methodology monitoring, accuracy of calculation and measurement of GHG emissions and ensuring the integrity of the methodology and reports on GHG emissions.

Printing industry, as an example of good practice in GHG emissions reduction, mostly consists of small or micro enterprises, in need of a simple model for calculating CO₂ emissions which is easily applicable to their activities, need to adopt an international approach and be easy to use for both large and small companies [9].

3.1.1. Intergraf recommendations

For the printing houses and all graphic industry, international association named Intergraf published recommendations on CO₂ emissions calculation in the printing industry [9], recognizing that calculating the carbon footprint of printing activities and its products is crucial to help clients and consumers understand the environmental impact of their activities. In Intergraf comparison exercise it was made obvious that by including a limited number of parameters in order of magnitude, some 95% of CO₂ emissions could be covered, so as a result, Intergraf is recommending 13 main parameters (presented at Fig. 2) to be included in any calculation of the CO₂ emissions of a printing site or a printed product [9]. The calculation should cover all six greenhouse gases (GHG) defined in the Kyoto protocol, expressed as carbon equivalents (CO₂ e), while direct emissions from combustion (Scope 1) cover exclusively fossil fuel.

Figure 2 – The Intergraf recommended parameters for calculating CO₂ emissions of a printing site or a printed product [9]: all parameters are in Scope 3, except parameters under No. 2 and No. 7 (both in Scope 1 – Direct emissions) and No. 3 (Scope 2 as described at Figure 1)

As shown in Figure 2, there are three limitations to the scope for CO₂ emissions calculation. First, capital assets of a printing plant (such as building material, machinery etc), cannot currently be included in a calculation model, since there is no clear consensus on their impact on CO₂ emissions - it varies across different plants, depending on their individual activities. Secondly, transport of the finished product to the first point of delivery of the primary customer should be included in the calculation, but further transport (to point of sale or end-users) is to be accounted by customers, such as publishers. And thirdly, emissions resulting from “end of life” treatment of paper products, as well as paper waste from a plant, are a highly complex subject requiring detailed analysis, so Intergraf recommend that it cannot currently be included when calculating carbon emissions from printing activities (waste paper can be landfilled (most significant GHG emissions because of releasing methane), incinerated or recycled, with smaller impact on the climate) [9].

3.1.2. GHG emission report

Example for adopted GHG emission report is presented by a company that produces printed and laminated cardboard packaging and blister cardboard for products from various industries (which expect well-designed, quality printed, reliable, on time completed and delivered package); this company is

committed to achieving zero GHG impact on the environment, and regularly measures its impact and transparently reports it to the public [10]. In 2023, this company prepared and presented its first publicly available published report on the GHG inventory, and the activities it implements to reduce its emissions with the goal of achieving zero CO₂ emissions. The described company calculates its own GHG emissions using collected company consumption data and emission factors. The company identifies and documents GHG sources that contribute to direct GHG emissions (Scope 1). The company exempts the direct GHG source "fugitive emissions" from the quantification due to estimated low impact on the Company's GHG inventory and the current impossibility of precise quantification [10]. The company identifies and separately documents the consumed purchased electricity, heat, and steam, as indirect GHG emissions (Scope 2). Purchased electricity is documented through a consumption bill electricity for each month, but it is not specified what is the share of green (renewable) energy in purchased electricity (it's estimated that in Serbia 20 % of produced energy is from renewables). The company does not currently identify or document GHG sources that contribute to others indirect GHG emissions (Scope 3), although is working on the development of the methodology with the intention of the same include in the GHG inventory for 2023.

Table 1 – GHG Inventory for described company [10]

Scope	Source of GHG emission	Tons CO _{2(e)}	The scope of annual production (for 2022): 12.144 t
Scope 1, summary: 281,39 tons CO _{2(e)}	Compressed natural gas (CNG)	253,39	
	Liquefied petroleum gas	5,58	
	Gasoline	0,51	
	Diesel	21,91	
Scope 2, summary: 1.576,23 tons CO _{2(e)}	Electric power	1.576,23	
Scope 3	Not documented, not included		
Scope 1 + Scope 2		1857,62	
	Biomass combustion	14,23	
Total		1871,85	
Specific scope of GHG emission (per ton of produced material): 1871,85 : 12144 = 0,154 tons CO _{2(e)} per ton of produced material			

In next period, described company will try to include the largest part of the supply chain in the GHG emissions reporting to expand their reporting to the Scope 3 range. Previously described Intergraf's recommendations would be helpful toward that aim.

4. CONCLUSION

The Serbia's Low carbon development Strategy determines this country by 2050 as a low-carbon society with a competitive and resource-efficient economy which provides citizens new, green jobs and a quality life in a climate-resilient society. Thus, the role of higher education in the next period must be to promote and educate students for new skills and competencies in the service of decarbonization, and to train and capacitate them for practical and useful skills. A good example of that is introducing new learning outcomes in curricula connected with environmental protection, such as preparing various kinds of reports and following measures in the field of reducing impact on environment. Preparing GHG emissions reports is not an easy task for future experts in the field, since the reports must be based on chosen methodology, and to be comprehensive, exact, complete and comparable. A special challenge in GHG emission report is identifying and documenting the Scope 3, which presents all "hidden", indirect emissions that occur in the value chain of the reporting company, including both upstream and downstream emissions.

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SECTION 4: BIOTECHNOLOGY AND AGRICULTURE

Influence of Abiotic, Ecological, and Climatic Factors on the Development of Wild Pear Seedlings (*Pyrus communis* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Conserving the genetic resources of fruit trees is of great importance, both due to their natural resistance and in the face of climate change, all aimed at producing healthy food and preserving the environment. "In situ" conservation of fruit tree biodiversity involves maintaining and utilizing natural populations within their natural habitat. Wild pear seedlings, *Pyrus communis* L., were observed at two locations: in the Toplica District, the village of Toplička Mala Plana (loc. A), Prokuplje, and the Nišava District, the village of Brest, Municipality of Merošina (loc. B). The results indicated significant differences in the monitored parameters.

Nearly twice as much progress in the development of wild pear seedlings, *Pyrus communis*, proves that Toplica is a good region for pear cultivation.

Keywords: wild pear, seedling, "in situ", climate change, *Pyrus communis*

INTRODUCTION

In Serbia, there is a large number of fruit species living in natural populations. Among them, significant genetic variability has been recognized, caused by adaptation to agroecological environmental conditions [1]. Plant genetic resources are of exceptional importance as a unique source of resistance to diseases, pests, agroecological conditions, and climate change. They are also characterized by great adaptability to environmental conditions. Preserving genetic resources is crucial due to inevitable climate changes, promoting healthy nutrition, developing organic agriculture, and protecting the environment. Natural populations multiply naturally: autochthonously, anemochorously, hydrochorously, and zoochorously, while some spread anthropochorously. As conscious beings, humans should significantly contribute to the preservation and augmentation of these resources. In addition to wild representatives of fruit species, indigenous and domesticated fruit species play a significant role in preserving and enhancing genetic resources [2]. Most of them have been in the same location for centuries with absolute adaptation to the given environment, living in synergy with diseases and pests from the surroundings. They survive solely through their exceptional resistance and immunity [3]. With strong immunity and resistance, the use of agrochemical methods is minimized. Cultivating fruit without the use of pesticides maintains healthy soil and water, ensuring the survival of bees. By using indigenous and domesticated varieties grafted onto seedlings of wild relatives, the need for irrigation is drastically reduced, thanks to their powerful root systems. A significant difference would be noticed, especially in pome fruit, which requires up to 25 treatments per year.

Considering the richness of pear varieties, the Balkan Peninsula can be considered a secondary center of genetic diversity for wild pears [4]. The population of wild pear in the Balkans represents a population of various genotypes. As a result of a long period of adaptation to specific agroecological conditions, wild pear populations are characterized by significant genetic variability. It is widespread on the Balkan Peninsula in plains and mountainous areas up to 1600 m above sea level. It appears in the zones of white hornbeam, pedunculate oak, chestnut, and ash, growing up to the subalpine zone [2].

It represents a valuable and useful wild fruit tree for its nutritional values (production of distillates, honey), needs in fruit growing (serving as a rootstock for grafting noble pear varieties), wood value, and

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as a source of food for forest animals. In addition to all of the above, it contributes to the biological diversity and stability of forest ecosystems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The high-quality wild pear tree, whose seeds were used to raise the seedlings, is located near the Monastery in Ajdanovac on the slopes of Mount Jastrebac, at an altitude of about 428 m. The region is hydrographically rich and characterized by abundant deciduous, mainly beech and oak forests. The tree is over 20 m tall with a broad-crowned, densely branched canopy, of considerable age. The tree's bark is corky and yellowish-brown, cracked in longitudinal parallel grooves. Branches are thorny, and younger shoots are either smooth or finely hairy. The fruits have a bitter-sour taste with a lot of stone cells (brachysclereids) and visible lenticels. When softened (Figure 1), the fruits are edible, exhibiting the presence of sugar and tannins. They ripen from August to October, reaching full maturity. This wild pear is characterized by regular fruiting, moderately large fruits, and a higher number of seeds (6 to 8) per fruit (Figure 2).

The collected fruits (October 2019) were left for a few days to soften a bit, after which the separation and washing of seeds from the pulp were carried out.

The seeds were air-dried for a few days on a paper surface.

Fine river sand, free from organic impurities, was used for stratification (Figure 3):

- a stratification container (wooden vessel) was prepared and placed in a suitable room;
- the fruit seeds and substrate (sand) were thoroughly mixed;
- to ensure uniform substrate moisture, it was filled up to a depth of 20 cm in the stratification container;
- during stratification, the moisture and temperature of the substrate were checked every 2 weeks;
- room ventilation was performed;
- optimal temperatures ranged between 3 and 5°C;
- when over 50% of the seeds sprouted (0.5 cm), the seeds were ready for sowing;
- the stratification period lasted for 100 days (optimal for pears is 74 to 119 days);
- when the pear sprouts reached about 15 cm in height, they were transplanted into a nursery, where the care of the young plants continued;
- in May 2022, the young plants were transplanted, with 14 individuals each (Figure 4), at two different locations with varying abiotic, ecological, and climatic factors;
- climatic conditions were monitored at both locations during the vegetation period;
- at the end of the vegetation period, measurements were taken for all 28 samples.

Measurements included the length and diameter of the stem, as well as the number and length of developed lateral branches.

Figure 1. Wild pear fruits

Figure 2. Wild pear seeds

Figure 3. Container for stratification

Figure 4. Developed two-year-old wild pear seedlings

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Perennial fruit species, such as pome fruits, are more sensitive to climate factors than other plant species. Climatic factors that most influence yield fluctuations include late spring frosts, high temperatures during the growing season (Table 1), drought, stormy winds, and hail. The resistance to these factors is directly related to the base temperatures, i.e., the biological minimum of the fruit species, the vegetative period, and the fruit ripening time.

Table 1. Exposure to risks of high temperatures at the specified locations by periods

Administrative District	Past	Present	Future
	2000-2019	2021-2040	2041-2060
Nišava District	Moderate	Very high	High
Toplica District	Small	High	Medium

The biological minimum for pear is when the average daily temperature reaches 12°C. Therefore, the risk of freezing in the sensitive phase is minimal. The probability of late spring frosts drastically decreases, so damages caused by frost in pear cultivation could potentially occur once every ten years (Table 2).

Table 2. Exposure to risks of late spring frosts by periods

Administrative District	Past	Present	Future
	2000-2019	2021-2040	2041-2060
Nišava District	Small	Moderate	Medium
Toplica District	Small	Small	Low

The length of the growing season refers to the period between the start of vegetation and the ripening of the fruit. Pear is a fruit species with the longest ripening period, lasting for 180 days. In Serbia, it is not possible to cultivate pears on one-third of the territory in terms of the length of the growing season [5], and on more than 50% concerning the overlap of the warm period and the completion of fruit ripening. According to the "median ensemble model" [5] for the period 1986-2005, the percentage of the territory where pear cultivation is not possible will significantly decrease as follows: 1986-2005 - 54.0%; 2021-2040 - 44.4%; 2041-2060 - 22.3%; and in the period from 2081-2100, it will decrease to only 9.2%.

The irrigation needs of pear trees are influenced by the amount of precipitation during the growing season. Research has shown (for the period 2000-2019) that these requirements are significantly lower in the Toplica district, amounting to 391.9 mm, compared to the Nišava district (452.5 mm) [5].

Wild pear seedlings, *Pyrus communis L.*, observed in parallel at these two locations, despite being relatively close (about 25 km) with differences in soil, orographic, and climatic conditions, showed

significant variations in growth and development. Variations in values exist for all monitored parameters: average tree height, stem circumference at the base, average number, and length of lateral branches (Table 3 and 4). These significant differences in growth and development indicate the favorable influence of abiotic, climatic, and ecological factors present in these locations (Table 5).

Table 3. Measurement results for location A

Sample number	The tree		Developed lateral branches	
	Height cm	Diameter mm	Number	Length cm
1	37,50	6,70	7	1-2
2	9,50	6,80	1	1,20
3	28,20	7,30	7	3-5
4	14,50	6,40	5	0,80-1,10
5	31,00	7,50	7	3-5
6	35,00	7,90	4	3-5
7	2,50	3,50	/	/
8	47,50	8,20	14	6-11
9	64,50	9,20	12	8-15
10	27,00	7,30	5	3-7
11	26,00	7,80	4	3-5
12	39,60	7,20	16	5-10
13	36,30	7,10	6	4-7
14	43,90	8,20	14	7-15
Average	31.64	7.22	7.28	4,5

Table 4. Measurement results for location B

Sample number	The tree		Developed lateral branches	
	Height cm	Diameter mm	Number	Length cm
1	10	2,6	/	/
2	13	3,5	10	1,7
3	13	3,2	2	1,5
4	13	4,4	6	3,0
5	15	3,00	2	2,0
6	16	4,2	3	6,0
7	14	4,00	5	2,0
8	18	5,4	6	5,0
9	11	3,4	7	3,0
10	20	4,5	/	/
11	18	5,0	10	3,5
12	17	4,7	5	3,0
13	25	6,5	9	8,0
14	25	4,8	4	2,5
Average	16,29	4,23	5.36	2,95

Location A: area-Toplička Mala Plana
 Toplica district
 Planting depth: 25 cm
 Spacing of planting: 15 cm
 Elevation: 281 m
 Exposure: southern – gentle slope

Location B: area-Brest
 Nišava district
 Planting depth: 25 cm
 Spacing of planting: 15 cm
 Elevation: 251m
 Exposure: southern, flat terrain

Table 5. Average differences in climatic conditions

Parameter	Brest	Toplička Mala Plana
Altitude	251m	281m
Mean daily temperatures annually	13°C	12°C
Mean daily temperatures during vegetation	20°C	18°C
Total sunshine hours annually	2000	2150
Total precipitation annually	600	600
Total precipitation during vegetation	200	300

Pear is one of the most widely distributed fruit species. The first forms of pears were transferred to Europe through Asia Minor and Greece at the beginning of the new era. Although Asia is considered the homeland of pears, most of the domestication work has been done in Europe [6].

Unfortunately, the genetic resources of wild apples and wild pears in Europe are seriously endangered [7]. It is believed that factors leading to this include a smaller number of parent trees and greater distances between them. Natural regeneration is threatened by grazing and crossbreeding with cultivated varieties of apples and pears.

Studies on the population of wild pear have been conducted mainly in areas with high genetic diversity of pear populations. Over the last two decades, comparative research on morphometric characteristics of wild pear and indigenous varieties has been carried out, for example, in Georgia [8] Italy [9], [10], Slovakia [11], Switzerland [12], and Lithuania [13]. More significant studies on the wild pear population in the former Yugoslavia have been conducted in the regions of Belo Polje [14], Sarajevo [15], western Serbia [16], and from indigenous populations [17]. Pear varieties grafted onto wild pear seedlings are much more vigorous than the same varieties grafted onto quince, live longer, enter into fruiting later, and their fruits are of slightly lower quality. However, in poorer soil in hilly regions where pears are grown semi-intensively, this rootstock is more commonly used than vegetative rootstocks [18].

Preserving plant genetic resources must include cultivated species and wild relatives of cultivated plants. Wild relatives can be very useful in breeding programs as a source of genetic variability, with possibilities for gene exchange with cultivated varieties. They often carry genes that can provide desirable qualities, such as disease resistance or tolerance to adverse soil conditions [19].

CONCLUSION

Pear production in Serbia is unjustifiably declining. To achieve better results in pear production, it should be cultivated in regions that suit it, such as Toplica, where climatic, abiotic, and ecological factors provide the fruit with everything it needs to thrive. Fruit signals to us and marks its appropriate territory because nature has its course, and we should follow it to extract the most from it. We cannot stop climate change, but we can adapt fruit production methods to the new conditions.

Almost double the progress in the development of wild pear seedlings (*Pyrus communis*) proves that Toplica is a good region for pear cultivation. It is also an area that should be utilized for preserving the genetic potential of this fruit species, especially given its exceptional adaptability to climate change, diseases, and pests. This is particularly notable considering its strong root system, which, by penetrating deep into the soil, provides the tree with sufficient water during critical periods. The resistance to high lime content in the soil should not be overlooked.

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ANALYSIS OF MEDICINAL PLANTS FROM THE RECULTIVATED LAND OF THE PLJEVLJA MINE LANDFILL

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Abstract: Aim of this work is to carry out biological remediation on the reclaimed land of The Pljevlja Coal Mine, primarily focusing on the process in which soil suitable for the development and cultivation of medicinal plants is applied to the rocky material. Lavender, sage, and balm were planted in the experimental fields. During the two-year study, the mechanical and chemical properties of degraded soil, as well as the chemical properties of the control soil, were monitored. An analysis of the content of microelements and heavy metals in the soil, shale, and humus was conducted, as well as an analysis of the content of microelements and heavy metals in the dry plant mass. The soil undergoing reclamation had an alkaline reaction. Analysis of soil and humus samples did not reveal an increased content of heavy metals. Results of the analysis of medicinal plants from the experimental fields did not show an increased quantity of heavy metals. Bacteriological analysis detected the presence of common saprophytic microflora (fungi from the genus *Mucor*). Reclamation with plant crops is possible on deposited materials from surface mines.

Key words: reclamation, biological remediation, heavy metal

1. INTRODUCTION

The reclamation of surface mines and dumps involves a series of mining, engineering, and agricultural measures aimed at restoring the terrain and ecosystem disrupted by surface exploitation ("Sl. list CG" No. 75/18) [1]. The area covered by reclamation fits into the existing ecosystem or changes its purpose entirely or partially for new needs [2]. The implementation of biological reclamation requires a prior analysis of the existing conditions on-site, phased execution, as well as subsequent monitoring of the process and constant adjustments [3].

Since there are layers of marl in the planned locations, the soil shows more pronounced changes in filtration characteristics, and has medium water permeability characteristics. Experience predicts that the planned type of medicinal plants for planting has modest soil requirements. However, all research shows that it thrives best on well-permeable soils, which are lighter in texture and well supplied with calcium (Ca) [4].

Before initiating any activity, it is necessary to conduct mechanical and chemical analyses, as well as assess the heavy metal content in the soil. High concentrations of heavy metals reduce soil quality, disrupt the biological balance, and damage other ecosystem functions [5]. The study aims to assess the soil quality for the cultivation of specific plant species.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

At the "Cementara" location, land reclamation of 10 ha, 50 a, 59 m² was carried out. Soil samples taken from the surface layer, 0-30 cm, are marked with: 1 (0-30 cm) - medium loam; 2 (0-30 cm) – heavy

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earthworm; 3 (0-30 cm) – medium earthworm; 4 (0-30 cm) – medium earthworm; 5 (0-30 cm) – medium earthworm. Plantations of medicinal plants (50% of the plot) were planted on this location - sage, lavender and myrrh, and medicinal plant plantations are planned to be established on the remaining 50% of the plot in the coming period. Medicinal plants were sampled from this plot. The samples are labeled as follows: Sample I - sage; Sample II - lavender; Sample III - mercy. Samples were collected using a soil auger, as needed for undisturbed sampling for the physical properties of the soil. Before sampling on the map or topographic plan, the location to be investigated was selected and marked. Point sampling was applied. For each measurement profile, two samples were taken. Figure 1 shows the sampling map.

Figure 1 Map of the location of "Cementara"

Soil samples were analyzed using standard analytical methods at the Institute of Mining and Metallurgy in Bor. Mechanical soil analysis was conducted at the Institute of Pomology in Čačak, while the Institute of Fodder Plants in Kruševac performed chemical analysis of plant samples.

3. RESULTS AND DICUSSION

3.1. Mechanical Characteristics of the Soil

For assessing soil quality for the planting of specific plant species and in the context of quality monitoring, understanding the mechanical composition of the soil is crucial (clay content, skeletal structure, coarse and fine sand, silt, and clay). The results of the soil's mechanical parameters, analyzed at the Institute of Mining and Metallurgy in Bor, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Mechanical Fractions of Soil

Sam ples	Mechanical Fractions of Soil (%)					
	coarse sand 2-0,2 mm	fine sand 2-0,02 mm	powder 0,02-0,002 mm	Clay >0,002mm	physical sand >0,02 mm	physical clay <0,02 mm
1	6,78	28,82	31,2	33,2	35,6	64,4
2	7,69	13,21	33,6	45,5	20,9	79,1
3	16,02	22,98	34,5	26,5	39,0	61,0
4	11,64	20,36	31,7	36,3	32,0	68,0
5	11,75	14,11	33,5	40,6	25,9	74,1

The mechanical characteristics of the soil in these plots indicate that it belongs to the category of light loams. These are generally medium-deep and deep soils, with a silty and silty-clayey composition. They have a surface, A-horizon, that is quite structured and loose, extending to a depth of 15-30 cm. Deeper variations of these soils are good agricultural soils.

Many medicinal herbs thrive on very sandy and rocky soils. Thus, this composition suits the planned plant cultures well [4]. Research indicates that it thrives best on well-drained soils, which are of lighter texture and well-supplied with calcium (Ca), which aligns with the investigated location. The need for nutrients in the soil in medicinal plant plantations depends on various factors, primarily the type of substrate, planting density, yield height, and others. For the normal life of plants, biogenic elements are essential: C, O, H, N, P, S, K, and others. Before introducing them, their presence in the soil needs to be determined through analysis. Adding larger quantities than the plants actually need unnecessarily increases production costs and can lead to a decrease in crop quality, the occurrence of toxicity, and deficiencies in other elements [6]. Basic chemical properties of the soil were analyzed through active and substitutional soil acidity (pH in H₂O; pH in 1M KCl), carbonate content, humus, total nitrogen, as well as the content of easily accessible forms of phosphorus and potassium. The results of chemical analyses of samples taken at a depth of 0-30 cm are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Results of chemical analysis of soil from experimental fields and plantations of medicinal herbs

Samples	pH u KCl	CaCO ₃ %	Humus, %	Nitrogen, N %	P ₂ O ₃ (mg/100 g)	K ₂ O (mg/100 g)
1	6,89	3,79	3,15	0,16	2,46	16,3
2	6,93	4,35	3,45	0,17	3,08	14,7
3	6,74	1,96	3,65	0,18	4,27	17,9

Agrochemical analysis results indicate that the soils in the studied area predominantly belong to the group of neutral to slightly alkaline soils, with an average pH value (in KCl) of 7.8. [7]. Such soils, during agricultural use, are stable with a low potential for significant chemical transformation processes. Results show that the examined soil contains 22-24% CaCO₃, classifying it as highly calcareous. This aligns with the literature and makes the soil suitable for the intended plant cultures. Limestone samples exhibit high carbonate content, over 60% Ca, with a neutral pH, indicating compatibility with the chemical characteristics and purpose of the soil. In comparison, Belić et al. (2011) [8]. recorded a wide range of CaCO₃ content (0% to 38.3%) and humus content (1.5% to 5.23%) in the Hetin soil, with a pH ranging from 5.57 to 8.75.

Layer of marl in the soil creates a basic reaction and causes a low content of basic nutrients. Test results indicate that on pure marl without the application of appropriate agrotechnics, it is not possible to expect successful planting of a plantation of medicinal plants. Also, due to the base reaction, disturbances in plant nutrition can be expected, and therefore phosphate fertilizers should be applied.

Planting medicinal herbs directly on the marl would have a negative impact on growth and development. Due to the possibility of drying out and the impossibility of developing the root system. Layers of marl in the absence of government can cause cracking and displacement of the terrain.

Average humus content in the examined samples is 3.45%, classifying these soils as humic. Based on its content in the organic layer, the soil falls into the group of moderately clayey soils with 2.0-5.0% humus. Humic soils with over 4% humus characterize only 10% of the sampled area. The humus content decreases with soil depth.

Adding a layer of humus improves soil quality and plant growth. Humification (introduction of organic material) is performed with well-burnt manure by spreading it in strips in the row space (not over the entire surface) and introducing it into the arable layer (by milling or similar). Introduction of fertilizer in this way is done for the reason that the root system of the planted medicinal plants is insufficiently developed in the first year and that the fertilizer added in, a different way would be available to the weeds and not to the cultivated plants [9]. This measure improves the water-air characteristics of the soil in the upper profile, stimulating root development and, consequently, the growth of the entire plants. In the nutrition program, it is desirable to use foliar fertilizers several times during the vegetation period. Favorable structure and loamy-clay composition of the deeper layers enable good percolation of the soil, but also a greater ability to accumulate moisture, which contributes to the plants' better tolerance to drought. On the other hand, the newly created layer provides the necessary nutritional value.

3.2. Analysis of soil and medicinal plants from experimental fields

Samples of medicinal plants from lavender, sage, and mercy the experimental field were subjected to laboratory analysis for the presence of trace elements, heavy metals and bacteriological analysis. Analyses were done at the Institute for Fodder Plants in Kruševac.

Increased heavy metal content in clays and clayey shales is associated with their ability to adsorb metal ions and the presence of organic matter in sediments, which also acts as an adsorber for heavy metals. Soil contamination with heavy metals disrupts natural geochemical cycles and ecosystem balance [10]. Effects of heavy metals on plant growth and development largely depend on the physicochemical properties of the soil and the form and concentration of heavy metals in the soil [10,11]. The levels of heavy metals in the soil and their forms are influenced by pedogenetic processes. High concentrations of heavy metals reduce soil quality, disrupt the biological balance, and damage all other ecosystem functions [10]. The critical concentrations of metals in plants, where the dry matter decreases by 10%, depend on the plant species, variety or genotype, and the characteristics of the heavy metal. Metal content was determined using atomic absorption spectrophotometry – AAS, Perkin-Elmer 1100.

Table 3 Results of chemical analysis of plant samples

Chemical elements	Concentration [mg/kg]			MDK
	Sage	Lavander	Mercy	
Cu	27,87	16,64	14,43	36,0
Mn	135,56	127,64	143,08	400
Fe	1768,9	1937,6	1876,5	600
Zn	60,56	40,43	51,09	140
Cd	-	-	/	0,8
Cr	15,38	16,64	12,32	100
Ni	4,79	5,54	3,82	35,0
Pb	5,76	3,16	3,09	85,0
Co	-	-	-	9,0

Analyzes of the soil from the plots where lavender, sage and frankincense plantations were already established did not detect the amount of heavy metals exceeding the MDK (except for the iron content). Critical concentrations of metals in plants depend on the plant species, variety or genotype, as well as on soil properties and heavy metal properties. Average critical and toxic concentrations of heavy metals in cultivated plants are shown in Table 3 [12].

Plants can generally adopt large amounts of some elements, if they are present in the soil where the plant is grown, and if their accessibility is high.

The availability of certain elements for the plant depends on numerous factors - soil type, soil composition, soil physical structure, soil acidity (metals are more mobile in acidic media), numerous agroecological conditions under which the plant is grown [13]. On the other hand, most of these elements mutually show synergistic and antagonistic characteristics, so it depends on all the above-mentioned factors which element will be adopted more. And all this implies that the conditions are different in different climates, so in general it is not possible to give a single scale of security, for each plant species and in all territories. On the other hand, the intensity of adoption is not the same in all morphological stages of development, and this is one of the reasons why significant differences in the content of elements in plants can occur.

On the other hand, the intensity of adoption is not the same in all morphological stages of development, and this is one of the reasons why significant differences in the content of elements in plants can occur. In these samples, only the amount of iron can be said to be a high value, but this requires additional research and testing, both at the molecular and genetic level. The assumption is that a high accumulation of iron, and with it some other divalent metals, can occur as a result of stress - if these elements are not available to the plant, the plant activates mechanisms for their accumulation and stores them as a reserve. Of course, this claim also requires serious research to confirm this observation. According to the recommendations of the World Health Organization [14]. Limit values for the content of heavy metals in medicinal plants are given.

3.3. Fitopathological Examination

In the laboratory for phytopathology at the Institute of Pomology in Čačak, examinations were conducted to detect the presence of phytopathogenic fungi using the method of isolation and identification through conventional methods. The investigation involved isolating plant tissue samples on PDA and MA substrates. The examined samples revealed the presence of common saprophytic microflora, specifically fungi from the genus *Mucor*.

Given the organic production context, maintaining a weed-free orchard and using fertilizers and plant protection agents registered in the Lists of registered products for plant nutrition, plant protection, and soil conditioners, which are permitted for use in organic production, is of utmost importance.

4. CONCLUSION

On the degraded soil of surface mines, the cultivation of plant crops through reclamation is feasible. Combined measures of technical and biological reclamation, implemented on large areas, would contribute to stability and improve the presence of essential nutrients, especially nitrogen and phosphorus. Chemical analyses of the soil designated for reclamation revealed that it is alkaline soil with low content of essential nutrients. No increased content of heavy metals was found in the soil samples. Samples of medicinal herbs, lavender, sage and myrrh from the experimental field that were subjected to laboratory analysis did not show an increased content of heavy metals. It can be concluded that the tested soil is favorable for the cultivation of medicinal plants, and that in such conditions it is unlikely that contamination of plant material can occur in the soil. Recultivation with plant cultures is possible on deposited surface mine materials. In order for the process to take place at a faster pace, it is necessary to introduce large amounts of organic and mineral matter in order to improve the presence of basic nutrients, especially nitrogen and phosphorus.

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TESTING THE CAPABILITIES OF CHATGPT 4.0 FOR AGROCHEMICAL SOIL ANALYSIS WITH FERTILIZATION RECOMMENDATIONS

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Abstract: ChatGPT is a new phenomenon that claims to take over a part of human intellectual activities. This article examines the possibilities it offers in the field of agrochemical soil analysis. We used the benefits that Internet technologies allow us to test the possibilities of artificial intelligence in agricultural technology. A JavaScript script was purpose-built that allows us to ask questions for ChatGPT-4. The answers obtained were compared with the official recommendations. The results of the comparison and conclusions are presented in this paper. Comparisons of recommendations for soil fertilization based on the results of agrochemical soil analysis obtained from professional services on the one hand with the results obtained by ChatGPT-4 on the other hand have been carried out and presented in the paper. Reliability of ChatGPT results was achieved only for the recommendations for corn fertilization.

Key words: ChatGPT, Internet technologies, Agrochemical soil analysis, fertilization

1. INTRODUCTION

Agrochemical soil analysis is a basic prerequisite for successful agricultural production in vegetable, arable and fruit growing [1], [2]. Every year, plants take out a certain type and amount of nutrients from the soil, which must be returned to the soil by fertilizing [3], [4]. Chemical analysis of the soil will determine the fertility of the soil, as well as the need for fertilization. By analyzing the soil for fertility control parameters, agricultural producers receive a recommendation on proper fertilization for the next four years.

ChatGPT has already been used in soil research. „The study results indicate that the level of trust of soil science experts in Indonesia to ChatGPT answers has reached above 80%.” [5]. However, the opinion of the vast majority of scientists is that ChatGPT cannot be used independently without the participation of scientists.

Fifteen different algorithms were considered in another study. „This paper includes a discussion on the current state of machine learning in agriculture, highlighting key challenges and opportunities, and presents experimental results that demonstrate the impact of changing labels on the accuracy of data analysis algorithms.” [6]. The results indicated a positive impact of data collection and analysis on harvest growth.

Another paper points out the possibilities and limitations of this chatbot in the field of agriculture. „ChatGPT is a game-changer in the field of agriculture and allied sectors. Its advanced language capabilities can revolutionize precision farming, crop monitoring, food processing, and livestock management. However, it's crucial to keep in mind that this technology also comes with limitations, such as the need for large data sets, potential biases, and computational resources.” [7].

Paper [8] describes one example of using ChatGPT. Here, the possibility that ChatGPT 3.5 provides answers to questions in the field of general culture from the entrance exam was tested. The mentioned paper was the inspiration for the authors to test the capabilities of ChatGPT-4 for agrochemical analysis of soil with recommendations for fertilization.

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2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. ChatGPT-4

ChatGPT is a relatively new phenomenon that does not have a single definition. What is certain is that it is a product of the OpenAI company, and that it has the ability to give more or less reliable answers to questions from different fields.

„ChatGPT is a revolutionary LLM that can maintain human-like conversations and generate human-like text for any natural language query that is nearly indistinguishable. The model can be used to answer questions, write essays, solve problems, explain complex topics, provide virtual tutoring, practice languages, learn programming, teach, and support research.” [9].

„ChatGPT is an advanced language model developed by OpenAI. It is a conversational AI-powered chatbot that can understand and generate human-like text. It is trained on a diverse range of texts and can answer questions, provide explanations, and engage in conversation on a wide range of topics.” [10].

For using ChatGPT-4 a subscription is required to purchase the required number of tokens. We decided to use the API that the company offers. „GPT-4 is available on ChatGPT Plus and as an API for developers to build applications and services.” [11]. For the purposes of this research, a script was written in JavaScript. The script uses a library named openai. An API key was also created, which is not necessary to access the possibilities that the API offers. The program code is available at [12].

By entering text questions into this program code, it is possible to get answers in text form. The questions were asked one by one. After that, the answers were analyzed and compared with the results obtained from the official institution. From this comparison it is possible to determine the capabilities of ChatGPT-4 to give the correct answer or comment.

2.2. Agrochemical soil analysis

Average soil samples consisting of the appropriate number of individual samples (20-25) were taken from plots up to 5 ha. which is taken with a probe. The depth from which to take samples for soil fertility control purposes is 0-30 cm for agricultural and vegetable plant species, and 0-30 cm and 30-60 cm for fruit plant species. Samples were taken with the help of soil sampling hand probes (Figure 1.).

Figure 1. Soil sampling hand probes

Agrochemical soil analysis was done in the accredited laboratory of the Agricultural Expert Service (PSS) in Zrenjanin.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results of testing the agrochemical properties of the soil with the recommendations of fertilization

1. Results of agrochemical analysis of the soil under hazelnut planting with fertilization recommendation for cadastral plot number 2348, cadastral municipality of Žitište, area of 1.7 ha.

The results of testing the agrochemical properties of the soil for the average sample taken at a depth of 0-30 cm are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Results of agrochemical soil analysis for an average sample taken from a depth of 30-60cm

Parameter	Unit	Value	Method
Soil reaction (pH) in 1M KCl		7,70	SRPS ISO 10390:2007
Soil reaction (pH) in water		8,41	SRPS ISO 10390:2007
CaCO ₃ content	%	9,72	SRPS ISO 10693:2005
Easily accessible phosphorus as P ₂ O ₅	mg/100 gr	67,21	MZ 10 05
Easily accessible potassium as K ₂ O	mg/100 gr	36,60	MZ 10 06
Humus content	%	2,93	MZ 10 04
Total nitrogen content(<i>calculation</i>)*	%	0,15	

(Note*: refers to the requested part of the examination that is not in the scope of accreditation)

The results of testing the agrochemical properties of the soil for the average sample taken at a depth of 30-60 cm are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Results of agrochemical soil analysis for an average sample taken from a depth of 30-60cm

Parameter	Unit	Value	Method
Soil reaction (pH) in 1M KCl		7,91	SRPS ISO 10390:2007
Soil reaction (pH) in water		8,56	SRPS ISO 10390:2007
CaCO ₃ content	%	12,52	SRPS ISO 10693:2005
Easily accessible phosphorus as P ₂ O ₅	mg/100 gr	48,98	MZ 10 05
Easily accessible potassium as K ₂ O	mg/100 gr	25,20	MZ 10 06
Humus content	%	1,95	MZ 10 04
Total nitrogen content(<i>calculation</i>)*	%	0,10	

(Note*: refers to the requested part of the examination that is not in the scope of accreditation)

The soil contains excessive amounts of phosphorus and optimal amounts of potassium, so it is not recommended to introduce fertilizers containing phosphorus into the soil in the next four years. The recommendation for the introduction of nutrients based on the results of the agrochemical properties of the soil under the hazelnut plantation is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Fertilization recommendation for hazelnut (13 years old)

Year	Basic fertilization (until December 15)		1. Nitrogen supplementation (in the middle of January)		2. Nitrogen supplementation (in the middle of March)	
	Type of fertilizer	Quantity per hectare	Type of fertilizer	Quantity per hectare	Type of fertilizer	Quantity per hectare
2022	SOP-51%+18% potassium sulfate-200kg/ha		UREA 46%	150 kg/ha	AN 33%	150 kg/ha
2023	SOP-51%+18% potassium sulfate-200kg/ha		UREA 46%	150 kg/ha	AN 33%	150 kg/ha
2024	SOP-51%+18% potassium sulfate-200kg/ha		UREA 46%	150 kg/ha	AN 33%	150 kg/ha
2025	SOP-51%+18% potassium sulfate-200kg/ha		UREA 46%	150 kg/ha	AN 33%	150 kg/ha

ChatGPT-4 fertilization recommendation for hazelnut (13 years old): The amount of fertilizer and nitrogen supplementation required per hectare depends on a number of factors, including the type and age of the crop, climatic conditions, the choice of fertilizer, etc. The following values are generally accepted as guidelines.

Hazelnut crops generally require about 50-100 kg of nitrogen per hectare per year. Since the nitrogen content of the soil is 0.10%, it could be assumed that it is necessary to add additional amounts of nitrogen. The amount of nitrogen fertilizer required depends on the nitrogen content of the fertilizer.

For example, if you use urea containing about 46% nitrogen, it would take about 217 kg of urea per hectare to provide 100 kg of nitrogen ($100 \text{ kg} / 0.46 = 217 \text{ kg}$).

It is important to note that large amounts of nitrogen fertilizer should be applied several times during the season, not all at once.

These values serve as a general orientation - for more accurate recommendations, it is necessary to consult experts in the field of agrochemistry.

- The results of soil analysis with fertilization recommendation for cadastral plot number 256, cadastral municipality Lukino Selo, area 9652m², pre-crop wheat, are shown in Table 4 and Table 5. ChatGPT-4 Fertilization recommendations are shown in Table 6.

Table 4. Soil analysis results

Parameter	Unit	Value
Soil reaction (pH) in 1M KCl		7,56
Soil reaction (pH) in water		8,46
CaCO ₃ content	%	4,35
Easily accessible phosphorus as P ₂ O ₅	mg/100 gr	27,94
Easily accessible potassium as K ₂ O	mg/100 gr	20,77
Humus content	%	2,59
Total nitrogen content(<i>calculation</i>)*	%	0,10

Fertilizer recommendations are based upon the previous crop, the crop to be grown and the yield goals (just for N).

Table 5. Fertilization recommendations

Plant species	Yield kg/ha	Required amount of nutrients by nutritional elements kg/ha		
		N	P2O5	K2O
Corn	10000	147	79	84
Potatoes	50000	350	216	335
Beans	2500	48	14	21
Cabbage	40000	144	37	112

Table 6. ChatGPT-4 Fertilization recommendations

Plant species	Yield kg/ha	Required amount of nutrients by nutritional elements kg/ha		
		N	P2O5	K2O
Corn	10000	120-150	60-80	80-100
Potatoes	50000	200-250	100-150	200-300
Beans	2500	50-70	40-60	40-60
Cabbage	40000	150-200	80-100	80-100

There was matching of the recommendations for fertilization of PSS and ChatGPT-4 only for the the plant type corn. However, for vegetable species (potatoes, beans and cabbage) ChatGPT-4 did not provide adequate answers for fertilization recommendations. As for the fruit species (hazelnut), ChatGPT-4 gave rough recommendations for fertilizing with urea, but did not recognize the terminology: basic fertilization and top dressing.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the capabilities of ChatGPT-4 for agrochemical soil analysis were tested. The basic features of this chatbot were presented. It was accessed via a purpose-built script. The chatbot gave answers to the questions that were compared with the official recommendations.

The results of ChatGPT-4 testing in relation to the agrochemical analysis of the soil showed that it gave an adequate recommendation of soil fertilization for over-fertilized field crop production, but it did not recognize the fertilization of vegetable and fruit crops. The conclusion is that ChatGPT-4 is a useful tool in the field of agrochemistry, but it is insufficiently reliable when recommendations for fertilization are considered, so supervision by an expert is required. It may be concluded that the better results for corn come from the fact that the necessary data for corn are more available on the Internet.

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DETERMINATION OF PROTEINS AND PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PARAMETERS IN WHEAT AND CORN

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Abstract: In this study, crude protein content and physico-chemical parameters of wheat and corn during two consecutive crop years were investigated. The first year was with a higher total amount of precipitation and a regular distribution of precipitation during the summer months, and the second year with a lower total amount of precipitation and with a reduced amount of precipitation during the summer months. The aim of the study was to determine the content of crude proteins and physico-chemical parameters, pH values, and water activity in wheat and corn grains produced in the agroecological conditions of the Toplica District. Average protein contents and pH values of wheat and corn grown in the year with higher total precipitation were lower than in the year with lower total precipitation. In the year with higher total precipitation, higher water activity values were observed in both wheat and corn compared to the year with lower total precipitation.

Key words: wheat, corn, proteins, pH value, water activity

1. INTRODUCTION

Cereals are the most important crops in the world, with total annual grain yields exceeding 2000 million tonnes (mt), compared with less than 250 mt for legume seeds (including pulses, soybean and groundnut). Although a number of cereal species are grown, three (maize (604 mt in 1998), wheat (589 mt in 1998) and rice (563 mt in 1998)) together account for over 70% of the total production. Other cereals include barley, sorghum, millets (which comprise a number of smallseeded tropical species), oats and rye, in order of decreasing total production. Cereal grains contain relatively little protein compared to legume seeds, with an average of about 10–12% dry wt. Nevertheless, they provide over 200 mt of protein for the nutrition of humans and livestock, which is about three times the amount derived from the more protein-rich (20–40%) legume seeds [1].

Regarding total production, wheat ranks second (immediately after corn) as the most significant cereal crop globally [2]. Wheat production accounts for more than a quarter of the world's global cereal production. It is primarily used for human consumption, while some 15% is used for animal feed. The world's largest wheat producers are China, India and the USA. The protein content in wheat grains ranges from 7 to 15% in bread wheat and from 9 to 18% in durum wheat [1], [3], influenced by both genetic and environmental factors. Wheat grains predominantly consist of starch (70-75%), water (12-14%), proteins (8-16%), and other components such as dietary fibers (2-3%), lipids (2%), and ash (1%) [4].

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Corn is among the most significant food and industrially important annual plants worldwide. It has diverse applications, categorized into three main groups: human consumption, animal feed, and industrial use [5]. Corn has one of the richest grains in terms of thermal energy [6]. In Serbia, corn is the most important arable crop in terms of cultivation and production volumes. The chemical composition of corn grains represents a crucial property for both industrial and nutritional purposes [5]. Corn grains predominantly consist of starch (70%), proteins (10%), lipids (5%), dietary fibers (10%), and minerals (1.5%) [4].

The aim of this study was to present the latest research results on the crude protein content in wheat and corn produced in the agroecological conditions of the Toplica District, as well as physico-chemical parameters, pH values, and water activity. This is essential for a better evaluation of the utilized raw materials for human consumption. Wheat and corn were examined over two consecutive growing seasons (harvests in 2020 and 2021).

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

In this study, the wheat variety NS 40S, a selection from the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops in Novi Sad, and the corn hybrid ZP 606, a selection from the Institute "ZemunPolje" in Belgrade, were examined. Wheat and corn samples were collected in the field of the Krstić household (Prokuplje, Serbia). Samples of seeds from the 2020 growing season were investigated, during which there was a measured precipitation of 560 mm with a regular distribution of rainfall during the summer months. In the year 2021, the total precipitation measured was 490 mm, with a reduced amount of rainfall during the summer months.

2.2. Chemicals and Reagents

Chemicals used for protein determination, including potassium sulfate, copper(II) sulfate pentahydrate, concentrated sulfuric acid, sodium hydroxide, sucrose, methyl red, methylene blue, and ethanol, were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH (Steinheim, Germany). Standard solutions of sulfuric acid (0.1 mol/l) and sodium hydroxide (0.1 mol/l) were purchased from MosLab (Belgrade, Serbia). Aqueous solutions were prepared using deionized water (MicroMed high purity water system, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc, Germany).

2.3. Methods

2.3.1. Protein Determination

Crude proteins were determined using the Kjeldahl method [7]. Briefly, wheat and corn samples were weighed on an analytical balance (Chyo JK-180, Tokyo, Japan), ground in a laboratory blender (Waring 7010S, Torrington, Connecticut, US), and transferred to digestion unit cuvettes (Turbotherm, C. Gerhardt GmbH & Co. KG, Königswinter, Germany). Each crucible with a sample received potassium-sulfate, copper-sulfate catalyst, and concentrated sulfuric acid. The sample was heated until charred. After the liquid in the cuvettes became clear, heating continued for an additional 2 hours. Water, sulfuric acid, and a few drops of mixed indicator were added to the cuvettes with decomposed and cooled samples. The cuvettes were individually distilled with 40% sodium hydroxide in a distillation unit (Vapodest VAP 10, C. Gerhardt GmbH & Co. KG, Königswinter, Germany). Sulfuric acid was used to collect the distillate. Excess sulfuric acid was titrated with sodium hydroxide until the indicator color changed from green to purple. A blank test was performed using sucrose.

The nitrogen content was calculated using the formula (1):

$$\%N = \frac{1,4 \cdot (V_0 - V_1) \cdot T}{m} \quad (1)$$

Where:

V_0 - the number of milliliters of sodium hydroxide used for the blank test;

V_1 - the number of milliliters of sodium hydroxide used for determination;

T - molarity of the sodium hydroxide solution used for titration;

m - mass of the sample in grams.

The obtained nitrogen content was multiplied by a factor of 5.7 for wheat and 6.25 corn to calculate the crude protein content.

2.3.2. Physico-Chemical Analysis

pH Measurement - *pH* values were determined by weighing 10 g of the sample on an analytical balance, grinding it in a laboratory blender, and transferring it to extraction bottles. Samples were poured with 100 ml of deionized water. The sample was extracted on a shaker for 15 minutes. The content was filtered, and the *pH* value was directly measured in the clear filtrate using a *pH* meter with a combined glass electrode (CyberScan *pH* 510, Eutech Instruments, Netherlands).

Water Activity Measurement - Water activity (a_w) was measured in ground wheat and corn samples using a water activity meter (Pawkit, Decagon Devices, Inc. Pullman WA, USA).

2.4. Statistical Analysis

All measurements were conducted in triplicate. Measurement values are presented as mean values $\pm$ standard deviations.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The chemical composition of wheat and corn is their most important property, both for those using them for industrial purposes and for their use in human and animal nutrition [8]. Results of determining the content of crude proteins, *pH* values, and water activity in wheat and corn are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1 □ Nitrogen Content (% N), Crude Protein Content (%), *pH* Value (*pH*), and Water Activity (a_w) in Wheat (NS 40S Variety)

Year	% N	% crude proteins	<i>pH</i>	a_w
2020	1.76 $\pm$ 0.03	10.99 $\pm$ 0.16	5.45 $\pm$ 0.06	0.60 $\pm$ 0.02
2021	191 $\pm$ 0.02	11.93 $\pm$ 0.12	5.52 $\pm$ 0.11	0.42 $\pm$ 0.02

According to the results presented in Table 1, the average protein content in wheat grain grown in the year with higher precipitation and a regular distribution of rainfall during the summer months (2020) was 10.99%, 1.08 times lower than in wheat grown in the year with lower total precipitation and reduced rainfall during the summer months (2021). Literature suggests that wheat quality is a function of grain composition, primarily protein composition [9]. While the qualitative composition of wheat grain is genetically determined, the quantitative composition could be significantly modified by growth conditions [10].

Hadži-Tašković Šukalović et al., [9] determined that the increase in protein content in wheat depends on the location and environmental conditions. Although the protein composition of wheat grains depends primarily on the genotype [9], it is significantly influenced by environmental factors and their interactions [3]. As environmental conditions have a significant impact on wheat quality, protein content in wheat significantly increases in conditions of reduced precipitation, mainly due to high nitrogen accumulation rates and low carbohydrate accumulation rates [9], [11]. According to the results of Hadži-Tašković Šukalović et al., [9], colder and wetter conditions result in crops with a lower protein content, which could explain the results of a lower crude protein content in a year with a higher total amount of precipitation. The obtained values of raw protein content are consistent with the results of research by Žilić et al. [12], Janković [4], and Hadži-Tašković Šukalović et al. [9].

The pH value of ground wheat grain in the year with higher precipitation and a regular distribution of rainfall during the summer months (5.45) was lower than in wheat in the year with lower total precipitation and reduced rainfall during the summer months (5.52). The measured pH values for wheat are in line with literature data [4], [13].

Water activity (a_w) is a measure of the amount of "free water" in the sample, i.e., water molecules that are not chemically or physically bound in the sample. Free water can serve as a medium for microbial growth, migration, and contamination. Therefore, water activity is an important parameter for assessing the quality and safety of products [14]. In the year with higher total precipitation, a higher water activity value was determined in ground wheat grain compared to the year with lower total precipitation and reduced rainfall during the summer months.

Table 2 □ Nitrogen Content (% N), Crude Protein Content (%), pH Value (pH), and Water Activity (a_w) in Corn (ZP 606 Hybrid)

Year	% N	% crude proteins	pH	a_w
2020	1.36±0.02	8.49±0.09	5.72±0.06	0.67±0.06
2021	1.46±0.02	9.11±0.10	5.82±0.04	0.56±0.03

According to the results presented in Table 2, the average protein content in corn grain grown in the year with higher precipitation and a regular distribution of rainfall during the summer months (2020) was 8.49%, 1.07 times lower than in corn grown in the year with lower total precipitation and reduced rainfall during the summer months (2021). The obtained values are in accordance with the results of research by Janković, [4], Milašinović et al. [8] i Radosavljević et al. [5]. Higher protein content values in conditions of reduced water could be explained by the analogy with this phenomenon in wheat [11], by a high rate of nitrogen accumulation in these conditions.

The pH value of ground corn grain in the year with higher precipitation and a regular distribution of rainfall during the summer months (5.72) was lower than in corn in the year with lower total precipitation and reduced rainfall during the summer months (5.82). The measured pH values for corn are consistent with literature data [4], [13]. In the year with higher total precipitation, a higher water activity value was determined in ground corn grain compared to the year with lower total precipitation and reduced rainfall during the summer months.

4. CONCLUSION

The average protein content and pH values of wheat and corn grown in the year with higher precipitation were lower than those in the year with lower total precipitation. In the year with higher total precipitation, higher water activity values were observed in both wheat and corn compared to the year with lower total precipitation. The presented results of the research on the content of crude proteins, pH values, and water activities provide data on the quality of wheat and corn in the area of Toplica District.

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SAFE HARVESTS: THE IMPERATIVE ROLE OF PERSONAL PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT IN PESTICIDE APPLICATIONS

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Abstract: Pesticide refers to any substance or combination of substances, whether of natural, chemical, or biological origin, deliberately released into the environment with the purpose of preventing, deterring, controlling, and/or eradicating populations of insects, weeds, rodents, fungi, or other harmful organisms. Although they are applied to protect the quantity and quality of agricultural crops, these chemicals may have side effects on human health and the environment. To minimize these effects, farmers must utilize appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE) throughout all stages of pesticide handling. Unfortunately, empirical and research data indicate a widespread neglect of PPE usage by farmers before, during, and after pesticide application, leading to potential acute and chronic poisoning. The importance of PPE in applying pesticides is underscored in this study. To explore this, a survey was carried out among individuals involved in pesticide application on agricultural farms. The findings indicated that out of 58 surveyed individuals, only 2 consistently used PPE. Consequently, there is a highlighted need for educating the population directly exposed to these chemical substances.

Key words: pesticide, agriculture crops, human health, environment, personal protective equipment (PPE)

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the practice of agriculture began about 10,000 years ago in the Fertile Crescent of Mesopotamia humanity has confronted challenges from pests and diseases that pose a threat to the sustainable food supply. The first recorded use of pesticides dates back approximately 4500 years when the Sumerians utilized sulfur compounds to control insects and mites [1]. In the present day, the World Health Organization (WHO) [2] reports that there are over 1000 pesticides in use globally to safeguard food from damage or destruction by pests. Each pesticide has different properties and toxicological effects. Farmers extensively utilize pesticides to enhance the quality and yield of agricultural production [3], [4]. However, need on environmental protection has led to an increased awareness of the need for alternative approaches to crop protection against diseases and pests. In response to the growing environmental sensitivity, farmers are incorporating different methods to safeguard crops [5]. Cultural and biological techniques for pest control, for instance, have gained prominence. These alternative methods serve the dual purpose of reducing pesticide applications and promoting a more environmentally sustainable approach to agriculture [6]. Despite the strides made in adopting alternative methods, there are instances where the application of pesticides remains unavoidable. Certain pests and diseases necessitate the use of pesticides to prevent significant crop losses, highlighting the complex balance between agricultural productivity and environmental considerations [3], [4]. The use of pesticides in chemical crop protection presents inherent risks to both human health and the environment [7]. Incorrect application or overdosing of pesticides can lead to severe problems. Pesticide residues on crops, water source contamination, and adverse effects on non-target organisms are among the potential challenges associated with their usage [5], [8]. To mitigate the adverse effects of pesticides, it is imperative to apply them using appropriate spraying methods. This involves adhering to recommended dosage guidelines, employing calibrated equipment, and considering environmental factors like weather conditions. The proper application of pesticides is essential to strike a balance between maximizing agricultural productivity and minimizing negative impacts on human health and the environment [6], [7]. Farmers may be exposed to pesticides during the transportation of these chemicals, the preparation of spray solutions, and as well as before, during, or after the actual pesticide application [9]. Farmers

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may experience the impact of pesticides in three distinct ways while using them, namely through oral exposure, dermal exposure, and inhalation exposure. Particularly, when employing techniques like fog spraying (10–30 µm) or aerosol application (30–50 µm), where small droplets are suspended in the air, it is crucial for farmers to utilize a mask [10]. When handling pesticides, the preparation of mixtures should not take place within residential premises or areas where human or livestock food is stored. Utensils intended for household use or for the feeding and watering of livestock should be strictly avoided. Vessels used for weighing and preparation must be diligently cleaned after each use. Residual quantities of treatment solutions are not left overnight but are instead emptied in a designated area away from watering sources, cultivated areas, and grazing zones. Application is conducted during calm and tranquil weather, avoiding the hottest part of the day. Wind can compromise work quality and elevate the risk of particles infiltrating the respiratory system and skin. Spraying should occur in the opposite direction of the wind. Eating, drinking, and smoking are strictly prohibited during work and treatment. Following any task involving pesticides, especially concentrated liquids, workers are mandated to thoroughly wash their hands, face, and body with soap and water [4], [11], [12].

When working with pesticides, it is crucial to use protective clothing and equipment designed to resist the harmful effects associated with exposure. Collective protective measures may include room filters, digesters, and fans. Workers have to wear work clothes made of materials such as cotton, linen, denim, with or without synthetic fibers, in the form of one-piece overalls or two-piece attire (pants and blouse or long-sleeve shirts). Work clothes used in the PPE are easily washable with soap or detergent, but they should be washed separately from family laundry [6], [13]. Protective attire, typically crafted from waterproof cotton or synthetic materials with or without rubber treatment, is worn over work attire. It is crucial to refrain from washing work garments alongside regular laundry. Safeguarding the eyes involves utilizing safety glasses, transparent plastic (plexiglass) eye/face shields, and securely fitting goggles. Helmets, easily detachable and washable, are secured with rubber bands. Hand protection is provided by rubber gloves, which come in various shapes and thicknesses. Lightweight gloves afford tactile sensitivity, medium-weight gloves offer moderate protection, and heavy gloves guard against mechanical injuries. Elbow-length sleeves on gloves shield wrists and prevent the flow of pesticides. Various materials such as natural rubber, nitrile, butyl, neoprene, polyethylene, polyvinyl chloride (PVC), and barrier laminates are employed, each possessing distinct properties. [12]. During activities such as spraying and working with both concentrated and diluted preparations, rubber cape, boots, and aprons made of synthetic or natural rubber are commonly used. It is essential to wash all rubber equipment with water and detergent, avoiding water sources like wells, streams, canals, and rivers. Additional protection for the head includes head guards, hoods, and caps during pesticide application. Nose and mouth guards protect against dust, fumes, and steam. Gas masks, comprising a face mask with a filter for various gases or aerosols, come in three sizes based on face size [6], [11]. Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) plays a crucial role in ensuring the safety and well-being of agricultural workers during pesticide applications [6], [13]. Farmers have to be educated about the importance of PPE in pesticide use [14]. The study conducted by Mohanty et al. (2013) underscores the imperative need for educating agricultural workers on the safe use of pesticides to mitigate health and environmental risks [15]. This paper emphasizing the importance of targeted education programs aimed at equipping agricultural workers with the knowledge and practices necessary for responsible pesticide handling.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

In Serbia, agriculture is an important economic sector. In 2022, the share of crop production in the total value of agricultural production equalled 67.7%, and that of livestock production equalled 32.3%. In 2022, in the total utilized agricultural area arable land and kitchen gardens participated with 74.5%, fruit plantations/orchards with 5.3%, vineyards with 0.6%, permanent grassland with 9.5% and pastures with 9.5%. In the structure of sown arable land areas and kitchen gardens, cereals participated with 66.3%, industrial crops with 20.2%, vegetables with 1.8%, and fodder crops with 8.6%. In the statistics of the Republic of Serbia's Statistical Office [16], data on plant production are collected, including information on the areas sown in autumn and spring, harvested areas, and yields for approximately 60

arable crops, as well as data on the areas and yields of orchards and vineyards. The data pertain to agricultural households, including family farms, entrepreneurial farms, and farms of legal entities.

This study examines 58 agricultural farms situated within the Braničevo District. The Braničevo District is positioned in the northeastern part of Serbia and is one of the country's 30 districts [17], (Figure 1). It spans an area of 6,864 km² [18] and encompasses eight municipalities: Veliko Gradište, Požarevac, Golubac, Malo Crniće, Žabari, Petrovac, Kučevo, and Žagubica. With a population of approximately 250,000 inhabitants, the district's administrative center is located in the town of Požarevac.

Figure 1 - Braničevo District

In 2022, a survey was conducted in the Braničevo District, encompassing 58 agricultural farms. Among these, 16 had an area of less than 2 ha, 30 ranged from 2 to 10 ha, and 12 exceeded 10 ha. Regarding the type of agricultural production, 16 farms were involved in fruit and viticulture production, 13 were cultivating field crops, 7 were focused on vegetable production, and 22 had a mixed production type (including fruit- viticulture, field crops, and vegetable production). Those directly handling pesticides and overseeing agro-technical operations were categorized into three age groups: older than 60 years (14 respondents), between 25 and 60 years (32 respondents), and younger than 25 years (12 respondents). The survey, focusing on pesticide application methods and the usage of protective equipment, involved respondents completing anonymous questionnaires with relevant inquiries. Survey participants were asked to choose from three options for each set of questions. The initial section of the survey focused on PPE, which includes various items such as clothing, boots, gloves, a hat or helmet, glasses, and a protective mask. Participants were provided with options regarding their use of PPE: they could say either fully utilize it, partially use it with a specification of the equipment used, or say that not to use it.

The second question centered around the frequency of PPE usage during pesticide handling. Respondents had the option to indicate whether they consistently used PPE, used it occasionally, or never used it. The following question addressed the regular hygiene practices and maintenance of PPE, including an additional query about how participants handled the equipment after use. Participants were given the option to choose between these answers: immediately washing PPE after each use (separately from household items), periodic washing after multiple uses, or never washing PPE. Continuing forward, the subsequent series of inquiries focused on the handling of used pesticide packaging. Participants had the option to select whether they consistently, occasionally, or never followed the recommended rinsing procedure. Finally, the survey concluded by asking participants whether they had received training or some education in pesticide application and plant protection.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Pesticides play a vital role in agriculture, enhancing crop yields and quality. However, their excessive use raises environmental and health concerns. Exposure, especially for agricultural handlers, poses risks through dermal and inhalation routes. Adverse effects, both acute and chronic, result from inadequate PPE use and unsafe practices. To mitigate risks, adopting proper PPE, adhering to safe practices, and enhancing awareness are crucial. Unsafe behaviors include consuming food during application, improper container disposal, storing pesticides in residential areas, deviating from recommended concentrations, poor hygiene after contact, and ineffective laundering procedures.

The findings from the conducted survey revealed the following: among the 58 survey participants, only 2 individuals utilize completely PPE during pesticide application. Most of the participants (46 individuals) utilize one or more pieces of personal protective equipment every time they engage in pesticide handling, as depicted by the percentage breakdown for each specific item in Figure 2. Additionally, 10 participants declared that they do not use any personal protective equipment whatsoever.

Figure 2 - Percentage use of individual items of personal protective equipment during pesticide application

In terms of regular hygiene practices, the majority of respondents (67%) don't wash their clothing after each use, and a smaller percentage (24%) only wash it when visible signs of use are present. Additionally, 9% of respondents stated that they never wash their equipment. Most respondents (72%) dispose of protective masks and used gloves in regular household waste, while a smaller percentage first places the used personal protective equipment in a plastic bag before disposing of it in the waste bin.

Only 23% of respondents adhere to the recommended procedure of rinsing pesticide containers before disposing of them in the waste. Regarding training or education, the majority of older respondents haven't undergone any form of education. In contrast, respondents aged 25 to 60 sometimes attend winter schools at the Agricultural Advisory and Expert service Požarevac read catalogs freely obtained from agricultural pharmacies in their areas, provided by pharmaceutical companies selling plant protection chemicals. The highest level of education across all survey aspects is observed among students who attended formal education in the field of plant protection.

Agricultural pesticide handlers typically wore basic PPE, including a long-sleeve shirt, long trousers, hat, mask, boots, gloves, and goggles. The most common PPE worn by pesticide handlers consisted of a long-sleeve shirt and trousers, with a smaller number opting for additional items like a mask, hat, goggles, gloves, and boots. Many farmers and laborers expressed a reluctance to invest in PPE, stating that they are accustomed to using pesticides with minimal or no protective gear. The frequent rationale for not using gloves was the discomfort arising from the heat generated while wearing them. The decision to forgo long pants was justified by the prevalent warm weather throughout most of the year, and there was no explicitly stated reason for not wearing a mask. Farmers still lack awareness regarding the importance of safeguarding themselves from the risks associated with pesticide application. The utilization of standard, well-maintained, and complete personal protective equipment by farmers is virtually nonexistent. Statistical analysis of the results revealed a significant correlation between knowledge and attitudes regarding recommended practices, and the actual implementation of personal protective equipment in practice. This is underscored by the fact that 12 farmers pursued agricultural studies with a specialization in plant protection. This underscores that enhanced knowledge and attitudes alone can be sufficient to influence farmers to adopt healthier and safer working practices. Addressing the disparity between knowledge and practical application requires the implementation of a more interactive and participatory training model.

4. CONCLUSION

Despite the wealth of information available, there remains a notable deficiency in farmers' awareness regarding the significance of safeguarding themselves against the hazards linked to pesticide application. This knowledge gap underscores the imperative for targeted educational initiatives and interventions aimed at enhancing farmers' understanding and adherence to proper safety measures during pesticide-related activities. Efforts to bridge this awareness gap are essential for promoting a safer and healthier environment within the agricultural sector. The utilization of PPE is essential to mitigate the negative impacts of pesticides on human health. While PPE cannot entirely eliminate the adverse effects of pesticides, it significantly reduces the risk to human health. The adoption of suitable PPE can contribute to lowering the healthcare costs associated with farmers using pesticides. This research highlights the significant impact of educating pesticide users on the appropriate application of plant protection substances, equipment management, and the utilization of personal protective gear in the context of pesticide application. The findings underscore the pivotal role of education in fostering safe pesticide practices for the well-being of both humans and the environment. Notably, individuals with a background in plant protection studies exhibited the lowest instances of improper personal protective equipment use, emphasizing the relevance and effectiveness of educational interventions in this domain.

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IMPACT OF PELLETIZING MATERIAL ON SUGAR BEET SEED GERMINATION

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Abstract: Seed pelleting is a technological process in the refinement of sugar beet seeds, during which a coating, called the pellet mass, is applied to seeds of smaller size. The process and technology of pellet mass creation, as well as the application of the mass to the seeds, aim to ensure the stability of the pellet, i.e., its strength and easy dissolution under the influence of moisture from the soil. Different compositions of pellet mass (weight ratio of sawdust and perlite) were examined through four treatments: pellet mass with a weight ratio of sawdust and perlite at 60%:40%, 50%:50%, 40%:60%, and a control variant (non-pelleted seed). The results of the study show that the laboratory germination of all pelletized seed variants, regardless of the perlite content in the pellet mass, is significantly higher than that of non-pelleted seed. Pelleted seed with a higher perlite content in the pellet mass (50-60%) showed statistically significant and highly significant differences in both germination energy and total germination.

Key words: pelleted seed, pellet mass, germination energy, seed germination

1. INTRODUCTION

Seed quality, specifically germination as a fundamental indicator of seed viability, depends on several factors, with the most significant influences being agroecological conditions and applied agronomy, as well as seed processing, storage, and more [1]. Germination is a basic indicator of seed viability that determines its utility value. Seeds with excellent germination produce seedlings that achieve the best stand in the field, ensuring consistent crop emergence and, consequently, stable yields of high quality [2],[3].

Pelleting (pelletizing) is carried out to achieve numerous advantages, especially in the processing of seed products: increasing seed dimensions, obtaining a favorable seed shape, increasing absolute and specific seed mass, quality protection against diseases and pests, the possibility of applying growth stimulators, proper sowing, and thus favorable stand and yield [4]. Coated (pelleted) seeds are round, uniform, of larger mass, suitable for precise sowing and proper stand, especially for crops with naturally smaller, lower-quality, and irregularly shaped seeds.

Considering that sugar beet seeds are very coarse and irregular in shape, and their pericarp contains natural germination inhibitors, it is necessary to undergo certain preparations before the pelleting process, i.e., coating. First, polishing is performed to remove excess pericarp, obtaining a more uniform round seed shape. Only optimally polished seeds guarantee a high germination rate, followed by pelleting. The pellet mass applied as a coating on the seed serves as a base for later application of fungicidal and insecticidal active substances in the form of a mixture of water and glue. Pelleted seeds are coated with a specific material mixed with nutrients, growth stimulants, and pesticides, all aimed at achieving more uniform germination and emergence.

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The goal of this research is to determine the ideal ratio of sawdust and perlite in pellet mass preparation and its impact on improving the physiological properties of seeds (germination energy and total germination).

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

In the technology of sugar beet seed pelleting, the application of basic elements of the physical-technological system has been developed, consisting of solid (powdery) and liquid phases. The basic components of the powdery component of the pellet mass are sawdust and expanded perlite. Sawdust (beech) is obtained through a special thermal process at a temperature of 200°C. Sawdust particles have dimensions below 150 microns, with a moisture content of 4-6%. One characteristic of sawdust is its very fine fibrous structure, allowing it to adhere easily and efficiently to the seed's circumference when in contact with the binder. This creates a favorable base for the subsequent application of powdery material until the turning of the pelleting machine forms a pellet of regular shape and satisfactory resistance to crushing.

Expanded perlite is the second component of the powdery component that arises during the thermal treatment of raw perlite at a temperature of 900°C. Raw perlite has a fibrous composition, and during thermal treatment, it expands, and through a cyclone, fractions of small volume weight are separated. Its ability to absorb large amounts of water is highly pronounced. Perlite is chemically inert, non-combustible, non-decaying, odorless, and has a neutral pH value. The primary function of perlite is to facilitate the easy dissolution of the pellet mass in the soil due to its high hygroscopicity.

The binder, or its solution, is the second component in the two-phase system that makes up the pellet mass. In the seed pelleting process, sodium carboxymethylcellulose (NaCMC) is used as the binder, commercially known as Lucel. CMC is obtained by esterifying alkyl cellulose with various esterification agents. The physical-chemical properties of Lucel are: yellowish-white or white powder with extremely hygroscopic properties, good solubility in water, pH value of 7-10 (neutral to alkaline). Lucel solutions are very stable and mix well with other colloids such as starch, dextrin, casein, polyvinyl acetate, and others.

The experiment was conducted in 4 replications, with different compositions of the pellet mass (weight ratio of sawdust and perlite) in 4 treatments: P 1 - control (non-pelleted seed), P 2 - pellet mass with a weight ratio of sawdust and perlite 60%:40% P 3 - pellet mass with a weight ratio of sawdust and perlite 50%:50%, P 4 - pellet mass with a weight ratio of sawdust and perlite 40%:60% Seed germination and germination energy were investigated under laboratory conditions. Germination was tested in plastic boxes measuring 20x12x5cm with folded filter paper with 50 equal folds at a depth of 1cm. Two seeds were placed in each fold, resulting in 100 seeds tested for each combination in 4 replications. Samples were kept in a thermostat at a temperature of 25°C. The first count was performed after 4 days to determine germination energy, and the second count was done after 14 days from the start of the test. The results were analyzed using the analysis of variance method.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For successful sugar beet production, high-quality seeds are crucial to ensure high field germination, good emergence power, and thus achieve optimal plant stand and uniform initial growth. Numerous researchers have focused on studying the germination and emergence of varieties based on their genetic constitution. Under controlled conditions at $t=5/15^{\circ}\text{C}$, larger seed fractions exhibit higher total germination and germination energy [5], [6], [7]. The results obtained from studying the properties of sugar beet seeds have found application in the seed technology of other field crops. Properly processed seed is a crucial prerequisite for a good yield.

Table 1 –Examination of Germination Energy and Seed Germination

Pellet Mass Composition	Germination Energy (%)	Germination (%)
Control (non-pelleted seed)	81.1	85.2
Pellet Mass Sawdust:Perlite 60%:40%	83.2	89.1
Pellet Mass Sawdust:Perlite 50%:50%	86.5	92.5
Pellet Mass Sawdust:Perlite 40%:60%	87.9	93.6
LSD 0.05	2.10	3.08
LSD 0.01	3.43	4.10

Average values of germination energy and laboratory germination depending on the composition of the pellet mass are shown in Table 1. The control (non-pelleted seed) exhibited slightly lower germination energy and total germination (81.1% and 85.2%). The influence of the pellet mass composition on laboratory germination showed statistically significant and highly significant differences compared to non-pelleted variants. The variant with a weight ratio of sawdust and perlite at 40%:60% achieved the highest germination energy and total germination of seeds (87.9% and 93.6%). Good results for the examined seed quality traits were also achieved by the variant with a weight ratio of sawdust and perlite at 50%:50%. The variant with a weight ratio of sawdust and perlite at 60%:40% achieved slightly lower results, indicating a less favorable impact of sawdust on the germination energy and total germination of pelleted seeds.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the investigation into the impact of the composition of the pellet mass on the germination energy and seed germination of sugar beet, it can be concluded that there are statistically significant and highly significant differences in the examined factors. The laboratory germination of all variants of pelleted seeds, regardless of the proportion of perlite in the pellet mass, is significantly higher than that of non-pelleted seeds. Pelleted seeds with a higher proportion of perlite in the pellet mass (50-60%) showed statistically significant and highly significant differences both in terms of germination energy and total germination.

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DETERMINATION OF AFLATOXINS IN MAIZE BY USING SMART APPLICATION – METHOD VALIDATION

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Abstract: Aflatoxins secondary metabolites of toxigenic fungi from the genus *Aspergillus* such as *A. flavus* and *A. Parasiticus* are considered to be most examined mycotoxins. The use of reliable analytical methods to evaluate and monitor such contaminants is of extreme importance. This study aimed to in-house validate a methodology for the determination of aflatoxins in maize, using RIDA®QUICK Aflatoxin RQS test strip and RIDA®SMART APP. One certified reference material and randomly selected sample with low level of contamination were used to validate analytical method. In order to fulfill the requirements defined by the validation process we evaluated: limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), working range and precision. Results received by analyzing samples and evaluating all of the listed performance characteristics proved that this method is in compliance with Eurachem laboratory guides, EU legislation and is 'fit for purpose'.

Key words: Aflatoxins, maize, smart app

1. INTRODUCTION

Aflatoxins are considered to be one of the most toxic and most examined mycotoxins [1,2], and they are classified in the 1st group of toxins by the International Agency for Research on Cancer, IARC [3,4]. Their toxicity is proved in numerous studies, both in vivo and in vitro [5]. They are secondary metabolites produced by toxigenic fungi of genus *Aspergillus* such as *A. flavus* and *A. Parasiticus* and can cause a multiple negative effects on both human and animal health. Aflatoxins are mostly detected in agricultural products from tropical and subtropical climatic conditions like those existing in Latin American, Asian and African countries, southern regions of US and certain parts of Australia [6]. However, as a result of climate change in Balkans aflatoxins became a greater concern for food safety in Serbia [7].

The use of reliable analytical methods to evaluate and monitor such contaminants is of extreme importance. High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) and rapid detection kits based on immunoenzymatic reactions (ELISA) are the most commonly used methodologies for aflatoxins determination. The choice of method depends on economic factors, purpose of analysis, and analysts team, among others [8]. This study aimed to in-house validate a methodology for the determination of aflatoxins in maize, using RIDA®QUICK Aflatoxin RQS test strip and RIDA®SMART APP.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

This research was carried out at the Academy of applied technical sciences Belgrade, in Laboratory Polihem. The following equipment and reagents are used:

- Grinder
- Weighing scale
- Graduated cylinder
- Shaker
- Centrifuge

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- 100 µl pipette
- Latest version of the RIDA®SMART APP software (ZRSAM1000) activated and installed on a compatible smartphone.
- 70 % methanol (e.g. 70 ml methanol (100 %) / 30 ml dist. water)
- Certified reference material TR – A100, batch A-C-294

2.1. Method procedure

All samples are ground and homogenized. Each sample is weighed (10 g) and added 20 ml methanol (70 %). Extraction is performed by shaking (5 min.) with additional step of centrifuge (1 min, 2000 g) until a particle-free solution can be obtained. 100 µl of the particle-free supernatant is dissolved with 200 µl of mobile solvent and mix carefully. 100 µl is applied to the test strip (Fig 1) and incubated at room temperature.

After exactly 3 min of incubation, evaluate the test strip with the RIDA®SMART APP.

Fig. 1: RIDA®QUICK Aflatoxin RQS test strip

3. RESULTS

Limit of detection (LoD) and limit of quantification (LoQ) are determined by calculating standard deviation of the results obtained by analyzing sample of lower concentration. After determination of standard deviation, values for limit of detection (LoD) (Table 1) and limit of quantification (LoQ) (Table 1) are calculated by using a following equations [9]:

$$\text{LoD} = 3 \times s' \tag{1}$$

$$\text{LoQ} = 10 \times s' \tag{2}$$

Where:

LoD – Limit of detection

LoQ – Limit of quantification

s' - standard deviation

Table 1. Determination of LoD and LoQ

Sample	Average value (µg/kg)	Standard deviation (s')	Number of probes (n)	Determined limit of detection (LoD) (µg/kg)	Determined limit of quantification (LoQ) (µg/kg)
Low concentration	1,9	0,7	6	0,8	1,7

Linearity was checked and evaluated by using following concentration levels: 2 µg/ kg, 6 µg/kg, 12 µg/ kg, 24 µg/ kg and 48 µg/ kg. Each concentration level is analyzed in two probes. (Table 2)

Table 2. Determination of linearity

Calibration level (µg/l)	2	6	12	24	48
Probe 1 (µg/l)	1,8	5.2	10.8	21.5	42.8
Probe 2 (µg/l)	2,9	7.8	14.6	27.4	50

Results are statistically processed by Microsoft Excel program, and shown in Table 3. Linearity is illustrated in graph 1.

Table 3. Evaluation of linearity

Scope	2 – 48ppb	
Regression line	$y = 0,9542 x + 0,9533$	
No. of levels	5	
No. of samples	10	
$S_{y/x}$	2,66	
Z_L	0,06	
Slope of the curve	0,9542	
Y-intercept	0,9533	
Trust interval	- 1,9453 do 3,8519	
Is linearity acceptable (Z_L is not significant)?	Yes	
Does trust interval includes 0?	Yes	

Graph 1. Illustration of linearity

Precision in terms of repeatability was checked by analyzing the same sample by one laboratory analyst in different periods of time, under the same conditions in multiple probes. Precision in terms of reproductivity was checked by analyzing the same sample by two laboratory analysts, under the same conditions. Certified reference material is used (TR – A100, batch A-C-294). Sample is analyzed in two probes (double determination) in 6 series (Table 4). Precision (repeatability and reproductivity) was calculated according to following formula [9]:

$$RSD \% (repeatability) = \frac{Std}{average\ value} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$RSD \% (reproductivity) = \frac{Std}{average\ value} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Where:

RSD – relative standard deviation

Std – standard deviation

Table 4. Determination of precision

Precision					
Repeatability			Reproductivity		
Average value	Standard deviation (Std)	% of deviation from average value (RSD %)	Average value	Standard deviation (Std)	% of deviation from average value (RSD %)
6.1	0.66	10.68	6.3	0.82	13.43

Recovery was determined by analyzing certified reference material (TR – A100, batch A-C-294) (Table 5) in 6 series and 2 probes each (double determination). Recovery was calculated according to the following formula [9]:

$$RSD \% (reproductivity) = \frac{Average\ value\ of\ series\ of\ measurments}{CRM\ value} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Where:

RSD – relative standard deviation

CRM – certified reference material

Table 5. Determination of recovery

No of samples	Level of concentration		Recovery (%)
	assigned (ppb)	determined (ppb)	
1	6,6	6,1	79 - 107

4. CONCLUSION

Trust interval of linearity includes 0 and is proved to be acceptable. Precision (repeatability and reproductivity) is ranging from 10.68 % to 13.43, which is in compliance with criteria set for methods for determination of aflatoxins (Commision Regulation (EC) No. 401/2006).

According to Commision Regulation (EC) No. 401/2006 recovery values range from 50 to 120%. Therefore it could be concluded that recovery satisfies the set range. Finally, it could be concluded that this method is suitable for determination of aflatoxins in maize.

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DRONES: GREEN TECHNOLOGY FOR FUTURE MAIZE FARMING

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Abstract: In the quest for sustainable and eco-friendly practices, the integration of green technology in agriculture has emerged as a promising solution to address the challenges posed by climate change, resource depletion, and a growing global population. The intersection of agriculture and technology has given rise to innovative approaches collectively known as "green technology." This transformative shift holds the key to ensuring food security, preserving the environment, and promoting a more resilient and efficient agricultural sector for the future. The adoption of modern technologies in agriculture, including the use of drones or unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), has the potential to revolutionize the way we approach agricultural production. Drones equipped with various sensors, cameras, and data analytics tools enable farmers to monitor and analyze crop health with high precision. This allows for targeted interventions, such as precise application of fertilizers, pesticides, and water, leading to increased efficiency and reduced environmental impact. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have found numerous applications in agriculture, contributing to sustainable and efficient practices the green technology. This paper shows the monitoring of maize conditions using the DJI Mini 3 drone, as a way to implement more sustainable agricultural practices.

Key words: drones, Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), green technology, agriculture, maize

1. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural land covers approximately five billion hectares globally with constitutes about 38 percent of the Earth's total land surface. About one-third of this land is used for cropland, while the remaining two-thirds are meadows and pastures for grazing livestock [1]. The environmental repercussions of agriculture encompass expansion, where croplands and pastures encroach upon new territories, displacing natural ecosystems, and intensification, characterized by the enhanced productivity of existing lands through methods such as irrigation, fertilization, pesticide use, and mechanization [2], [3], [4]. Conventional agricultural practices involve extensive use of fertilizers and pesticides, resulting in soil and water contamination, air pollution, and land erosion [5], land compaction, salinization, and pollution, depletion and pollution of water resources, increasing production costs, the diminishing number of farms, and, consequently, poverty and the decline of the rural population [6], [7] According to FAO, total agricultural use of inorganic fertilizers, expressed as the sum of the three nutrients nitrogen (N), phosphorus (expressed as P_2O_5) and potassium (expressed as K_2O), was 195 million tonnes in 2021, of which 56% was nitrogen. Fertilizer usage witnessed an increase across all regions from 2000 to 2021, with a total rise of 32 million tonnes for the three nutrients. Also, global pesticides use increased between 2000 and 2021 by 62 percent. Additionally, there has been an observed increase in irrigation in 2021 by 22% compared to the year 2000 [8]. At the global level, maize, rice, wheat, barley and sorghum are the five most produced species of cereals. Among these, maize showed the highest production (1.2 billion tonnes in 2021) and fastest growth over the period (+104 percent since 2000) compared to the other major grains. This growth can be attributed to the diverse applications of maize, extending beyond traditional human consumption. Today, maize finds extensive use in the biofuel industry and serves as a key component in animal feed, contributing to its widespread cultivation and robust production as documented by the FAO's Agricultural Production Statistics for the years 2000–2021 [9], [10].

Today, production is inconceivable without the use of new technologies. Drones, also known as Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), have introduced a new approach to conventional agriculture,

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offering various benefits and potential impacts on the environment. These aerial devices contribute to precision agriculture, enabling farmers to monitor crops with unprecedented accuracy. By employing advanced sensors and imaging technologies, drones assist in early detection of crop issues, such as diseases, pests, and nutrient deficiencies. This precision translates into optimized resource use, reducing the need for chemical inputs and water while enhancing overall efficiency. Great potential exists for drones to become a component of green technologies in the near future, with tremendous benefits in achieving sustainable agriculture. In the present era, drones are emerging as a crucial element in precision agriculture, playing a role in promoting sustainable farming. Drones have diverse applications in agriculture, including soil and field analysis, where sensors analyze soil conditions, terrain, moisture, and nutrients for crop planning. They can also be employed for cost-effective crop and tree planting, reducing labor and environmental impact [11], [12].

In this study, the DJI Mini 3 drone was used to observe the maizefield throughout the entire vegetation season, serving for monitoring the condition of plants, indicators of stress, proper nutrient uptake, and the occurrence of weeds. The aim was to determine whether the use of drones in conventional corn production can contribute to controlled and reduced pesticide use.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study was conducted on the agricultural farm of the Trajić family, in the village of Brežane, Požarevac municipality, Braničevo district (S 44° 38' 35", E 21° 04' 21") during 2023 in maize production (2 ha). The humus content, soil pH, CaCO₃, P₂O₅ and K₂O contents were measured in autumn 2022 (Table 1). The barley was the preceding cover crop and the maize hybrid Pioneer P0217 was sown at the end of April 2023 at a density of 75,000 plants per ha. In the fall of the previous year, it was fertilized with Euronatur P26B (300 kg per ha) and in the spring, Urea was applied 15 days before sowing (300 kg per ha). During the maize's vegetative period, mineral fertilizer was used at a rate of 5 l per ha. The standard protection of plants from wireworms has been completed, and on May 13, it was irrigated only once during the month of July. Monitoring of maize crops and tracking plant conditions was conducted multiple times throughout the vegetation period, from sowing to harvest, using the DJI Mini 3 drone (Table 2). The DJI Mini 3 is a compact and exceptionally lightweight camera drone designed for adventure. With its extended battery life, detailed 4K HDR video capabilities, and entertaining features such as True Vertical Shooting for social-media-friendly shots, it's the perfect companion for capturing anything from an epic road trip to research [13]. Additionally, the presence and emergence of weeds in the maize field were monitored using the drone, followed by the application of herbicides as needed.

Table 1. Soil sample analysis during the year 2022.

Soil analysis (november 2022)					
pH (H ₂ O)	pH (KCl)	N content (m/m)	Humus content	P ₂ O ₅ mg/100g	K ₂ O mg/100g
6.81	6.19	0.198	3.14	8.2	21.3

Table 2. Time of monitoring of maize production using a DJI MINI 3 drone

Monitoring of maize	Date
1	May 6, 2023
2	May 13, 2023
3	May 27, 2023
4	May 31, 2023
5	June 5, 2023
6	June 18, 2023
7	July 2, 2023
8	July 17, 2023
9	September 11, 2023

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Plant monitoring was conducted several times throughout the vegetation period, allowing for the tracking of plant condition, weed presence and stress of plant. **The 1st monitoring** of the maize crop with DJI MINI 3 drone was conducted twelve days after sowing (May 6, 2023) to observe the regularity of plant emergence, considering that more plants were sown (75,000 per ha) compared to the previous year (65.000 per ha) (Figure 1). During **the 2nd monitoring**, thanks to the efficient performance of the drone and its ability to fly at a low altitude, a uniform emergence of maize plants across the entire field was observed. Additionally, the appearance of the first weeds was noted: *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Abutilon theophrasti*, *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*, *Helianthus annuus* and *Sorghum halepense*. On some plants of maize, there was evidence of insufficient phosphorus absorption and plant stress due to a cold air mass (Figure 2). **The 3rd monitoring** using a drone was conducted when the maize was in the 6-leaf stage, confirming the effectiveness of herbicide application and the good condition of the maize plants. During **the 4th and 5th monitoring**, the good condition of maize plants, uniform growth, and nearly complete destruction of weed plants across the entire field were observed. After the application of the foliar fertilizer Traiko to simulate the progress of maize plants, **the 6th maize production monitoring** was conducted on June 18, 2023, revealing good plant fitness, exceptional plant condition, and the absence of weeds (Figure 3, 4). In **the 7th monitoring**, it was determined that plant irrigation is necessary as some leaves have dried up due to high temperatures, but the plants exhibited full vigor. With **the 8th monitoring**, the irrigation of plants was observed using water cannons (12 mm per m²). **The 9th crop inspection** monitored the entry of the crops into the ripening phase. The maize yield was 11 tons per ha, while in the previous year without the application of drone monitoring, the yield ranged from 8 to 10 tons per ha with the use of a higher quantity of pesticides.

Figure 1 and 2 - Crop monitoring of maize, presence of weeds and plant stress tracking using DJI Mini 3 drone

Figure 3 and 4 - Monitoring application pesticides and herbicide efficacy using a drone DJI Mini 3

Figure 5 - Monitoring of maize roduction using a drone DJI Mini 3

The use of drones in this study has facilitated the observation of the entire vegetation period of the crop, all phenophase stages of maize, as well as the potential occurrence of plant stress due to high temperatures or insufficient nutrient utilization. It is known that drones streamline crop monitoring throughout the season, providing timely data to prevent yield loss. Additionally, they assist in irrigation scheduling by detecting heat and water stress in crops and assessing crop health early on, enabling timely corrective measures [11]. The use of this new technology has contributed to easier, faster, and more detailed inspection of the entire plot and each row of corn within an area of 2 hectares. It monitored the response of plants to foliar fertilization and determined the optimal timing for irrigation. The literature indicates that this technology eliminates the need for human physical inspection, especially in remote or challenging terrains [12]. Additionally, it is known that drones offer weed identification for timely removal, precision crop spraying based on spatial variability, and efficient management of excess crop residues, preventing environmental pollution. Therefore, by utilizing drones, we have been able to identify weeds multiple times across the entire production area, determine critical timing for their suppression, reduce costs, and apply pesticides in a controlled manner (Figure 5). Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles, we have identified weeds on multiple occasions and determined the critical timing for their application. Inouo (2020) agree with this, considering that sensing through drones enables cost-effective, high-resolution, and adaptable observations of crops and soils [14].

4. CONCLUSION

In traditional global agriculture, maize cultivation primarily adopts monoculture practices or a two year crop rotation, leading not only to soil degradation but also to the persistent presence of diseases, pests, and weeds, uncontrolled pesticide use and environmental pollution. In response to these challenges, emerging "green technologies" emphasize the use of drones for precise and timely pesticide application, as well as early identification of stress-related crop issues due to drought, high or low temperatures, or insufficient nutrient uptake. Monitoring with drones DJI MINI 3 enabled the observation of the entire production area multiple times during the vegetation period, assessing the uniformity of plant emergence, tracking maize response to stress from low and high temperatures, nutrient uptake, the emergence of seedlings, and determining the critical period for suppression. This has contributed to better plot visibility, continuous monitoring of plant conditions, controlled pesticide application, increased yield, and reduced production costs.

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IMPORTANT BIOTECHNOLOGY ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION WITH ADVANTAGES AND RISKS

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Abstract: Using methods like genetic engineering, molecular diagnostics, tissue culture, and molecular markers, agricultural technology refers to the use of live organisms and systems in the development of products for human use. Agricultural biotechnology was practical as people have been trying for a long time identify agriculturally important organisms through breeding and animal husbandry. An example of traditional organic farming. The technology is the development of disease resistant wheat varieties by crossing different types of wheat until the desired disease resistance was present in a result new variety. Agriculture uses biotechnology extensively to disseminate beneficial traits and boost productivity. This is frequently accomplished by selective breeding, a technique that involves changing an organism's genetics. Whether or not biotechnology in agriculture has a negative impact on human health and the environment, it encourages the growth of crops and animals, reduces the use of pesticides, and increases the nutritional content of products.

Keywords: Agriculture, Biotechnology, CRISPR-Cas9

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional biotechnology has been abandoned and replaced by genetic splicing. With genetic splicing, biotechnology in agricultural production is on the agenda. this is often the use of scientific techniques to alter and improve plants, animals and microorganisms to increase their value. Advances in biology were achieved in the 1970s. This gave scientists the flexibility to control DNA, the chemical building blocks that specify the characteristics of living organisms at the molecular level. It also allows for the transfer of DNA between organisms that are more distant than has been possible with traditional breeding technology.

Today, this technology has reached a stage where scientists can target one or more specific genes from almost any organism, including plants, animals, bacteria and viruses, and introduce those genes into another organism. This technology is called biotechnology and therefore the organisms are called genetically modified or transgenic organisms. Transgenic organisms offer a number of benefits beyond humans that have emerged from innovations in traditional agricultural biotechnology. Below are some examples of the benefits of applying the recombinant DNA technology techniques currently available to agricultural biotechnology. When gene splicing reduces dependence on pesticides, we have fewer pesticide residues on food, reduce pesticide leaching into groundwater, and minimize exposure to hazardous products.

However, as mentioned above, there are potential environmental risks associated with this type of technology. Some consumers and environmentalists believe that insufficient efforts have been made to

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understand the dangers of using GM crops, including the potential long-term consequences. Some opponents of biotechnology believe that transgenic crops can cause cross-pollination with related weeds, potentially leading to more difficult "super weeds" to control. One concern is that transferring pollen from glyphosate-resistant crops to related weeds may cause glyphosate resistance. Although the perspective of this, although it is extremely small, it is not unimaginable that resistance to a selected herbicide does not mean that the system is immune to other herbicides, so that the affected weeds can always be checked with other products.

Some environmentalists maintain that when transgenic crops are released into the environment, they might have unforeseen and undesirable effects. Although transgenic crops are rigorously tested before being made commercially available, not every potential impact is foreseen. Bt corn, as an example, produces a awfully specific pesticide intended to kill only pests that go after the corn. In 1999, however, researchers at university found that pollen from Bt corn could kill caterpillars of the harmless monarch. once they fed Monarch caterpillars milkweed dusted with Bt corn pollen within the laboratory, half the larvae died. But follow-up field studies showed that under real-life conditions milkweed butterfly caterpillars are highly unlikely to return into contact with pollen from Bt corn that has drifted onto milkweed leaves—or to eat enough of it to harm them.

2. MULTI-OMICS TECHNOLOGY

In plants, functional genomics has identified several genes that control responses to abiotic and biotic stresses .Some genes have been modified to develop resistance to stresses (biotic and abiotic) in cultivated plants.Many new candidate genes have been discovered from the relative genomics of wild plants for stress tolerance (abiotic and biotic) in cultivated plants .For example, a complete sequence map of the high-density buckwheat genome, sequence data available online from the Hi-C and fosmid DNA libraries .A protein interaction was found.

The results highlighted the different expression of Cshdz genes against salinity, drought, high and low temperatures and the association between Cshdz genes and resistant plants. In *Solanum americanum*, integrated RenSeq and genetic mapping were used to locate the genetic locus that confers resistance to *Phytophthora*.In wheat, MutRenSeq, a new version of RenSeq, has been used to isolate R genes that confer resistance to stem rust.Whole genome analysis with ChIP-seq identified 21 ABA-associated TFs and their extensive regulatory network Furthermore, a new family of TFs functionally involved in saline reactions and ABA has been identified in *Arabidopsis*.

Genotyping by sequencing (GBS) is a recently discovered genomic technology to study the genetic diversity of plants at the whole genome level. An F2 population of *Brassica olearacea* was used to develop a high-density genetic map comprising 879.9 cM genotyped from 4103 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs).

3. TRANSCRIPTOMICS

RNA profiling — realized lately using microarrays, organic miracle, digital profiling, RNA sequencing, and periodical analysis of organic miracle(29) — can identify multiple stress resistance- related seeker genes, inferring applicable gene functions. The available online databases give whole genome-wide transcriptomics data for factory stress responses,(31).

In *Arabidopsis*, transcriptomic analysis under failure and warmth stress linked nearly 770 unchanged reiterations with 53 different specific proteins(32). These findings were verified in sunflower(33). likewise, combined heat and failure upregulated stress cytosolic ascorbate peroxidase1(APX1)(34).

In chickpea, periodical analysis of organic miracle(savant) and coming- generation sequencing(NGS) approaches were used to dissect the overall transcriptome of failure- and swab- stressed shops,(34). also, the subtractive cDNA repression hybridization system was employed in stressed-out chickpea shops(35). A relative microarray approach handed information on functional genes and pathways crosstalk in multiple stress transcriptomic studies in cotton(36). In sludge, RNA sequencing was performed to know the adverse goods of cold, failure, swab stress, and warmth stress(37).

Li et al. proved differentially expressed genes related to signaling pathways, recap, and metabolism(38). RNA gel spot and microarray combined approaches vindicated that DREB2A, a recap factor, controls the expression position of failure and cold wave stress genes(38). periodical analysis of organic miracle(savant) has been used considerably in shops to check gene- related responses against stresses. as an illustration, in rice, from 5921 expressed genes, nearly,122 markers were anatomized. Of,519 markers by global organic miracle,,131 markers were kind of like distinctive reiterations(39). the mixing of RNA- seq and bulked segregant analysis, called BSR- seq, has the installation to support stress resistance in shops. as an illustration, Bra019409 and Bra019410 were possible seeker genes for clubroot resistance in white turnip(,41). RNA- seq- intermediated organic miracle analysis could accelerate factory parentage by garnering knowledge on host- P relations and relating stress- related genes.

4. PROTEOMICS

The qualitative and quantitative study of total proteins expressed in a cell, tissue or organism is known as proteomics. In the context of stress tolerance in plants, complete proteomes are studied; however, numerous studies have examined the cell wall proteome, organellar proteome, proteogenome, nuclear proteome and phosphoproteome .

Recently, various forms of mass spectrometry have been used to profile the proteome in response to abiotic stress. Mass spectrometry for proteomics provides comprehensive information about the proteome when used in plant stress responses and genome-wide studies. Proteome profiles can be compared to identify the function of certain proteins in biotically and abiotically induced stress signaling and differentially expressed stress resistant proteins. In addition, phosphorylation group proteins play an important role in abiotic stress. A study of a proteomic matrix in water-stressed rice identified signaling proteins and reactive oxygen species.

Various studies have used proteomics to highlight heavy metal stress in Brassica juncea, Glycine max, Linum usitatissimum and Arabidopsis thaliana. Heidarvand and Maali-Amiri (2013) extensively studied the proteomic profile of chickpeas exposed to cold stress. The phosphoproteome of wheat leaves has also been studied. Several isoforms of S-adenosylmethionine in soybeans during floods and droughts have been identified. In tomato, nuclear signaling proteins with crosstalk chloroplast proteins have been reported in drought-stressed plants. Another study used tandem MS and two-dimensional gel electrophoresis (2-DE) approaches in wet barley diets to reveal the proteomic profile. In Eriobotrya japonica, RNA-seq with isobaric tags relative absolute quantification (iTRAQ) has been used to understand the mechanism of cold tolerance.

The results showed 1210 differentially expressed genes (DEGs) and 300 differentially expressed proteins (DEPs); out of 3620 genes, only 27 shared both DEPs and DEGs. The Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) analysis predicted that secondary metabolite biosynthesis and metabolic pathways are common. Real-time validation of quantitative reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR) showed that gene expression of phenylalanine ammonia lyase, anthocyanin synthase, and NADP-D-sorbitol-6- phosphate dehydrogenase was consistent with the transcriptome profile. Lou et al. proposed that these three genes play an important role in cold tolerance.

Proteomics is a new technology to identify proteins and signaling pathways involved in plant stress response and plant physiology. Additionally, proteomics improves the understanding of stress-related proteins, which are applied in molecular biology to improve crops.

Thanks to its remarkable success, CRISPR-Cas9 becomes a potential tool to genetically improve desired crop traits, namely disease resistance, nutrient content, adaptation to multiple stresses, architecture and plant yield. In some cases, a specific trait can be potentiated by a negative regulatory gene knockout.

Rice grain weight improved with genetic modification of some QTLs. The yield of maize kernels during drought increased with genome engineering of the ARGOS8 locus. In woody plants, CRISPR-Cas9 produced mutants in the first transgenic generation; this is important because the breeding of woody plants is difficult due to their long lifespan. Another study knocked out the OsGAN1 gene in rice and confirmed that it regulates root length and plant height. Similarly, knockout of the OsABCG26 gene confirmed that this gene regulates pollen exines and anther cuticles, and OsTCD10 played an essential role in cold-stressed rice chloroplasts summarizes the principles of CRISPR-Cas9.

5. CRISPR-CAS9 GENOME ENGINEERING FOR BIOTIC STRESS TOLERANCE

CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing has been successfully applied to several crops, including cotton, corn, rice, and wheat. However, most genome engineering studies target biotic stress such as disease. In wheat, the CRISPR-Cas9 method has been successfully used to eliminate the three homologs of EDR1 to generate plants (Taedr1) with increased tolerance to powdery mildew.

In Arabidopsis, inactivation of the sensitive EDR1 gene increased resistance to powdery mildew. Recessive resistance genes, eIF (eukaryotic translation initiation factor), have been detected in several different hosts, using eIF(iso)4E and eIF4E genes with CRISPR-Cas9 to generate virus-resistant plants in Arabidopsis and cucumber, respectively. CsLOB1 is a susceptible gene for citrus canker (pathogen; Xanthomonascitri); CRISPR-Cas9 has been used to edit this gene to develop resistant grapefruit plants. Moreover, an MLO gene with negative resistance function responsible for powdery mildew susceptibility was successfully mutated by Cas9 knockouts to improve powdery mildew resistance of tomato and wheat.

The use of CRISPR-Cas9 as an antiviral program has split the severe hedgehog virus, reducing viral infection. Rice globular tungro virus (RTSV), linked to the negatively controlled susceptible eIF4G gene, was eliminated using CRISPR-Cas9 to develop resistant rice varieties. Since CRISPR-Cas9, the loss of VWWRKY52 gene function has caused resistance to Botrytis cinerea in grapes (Vitis vinifera). Furthermore, CRISPR-Cas9 has been used to destroy multiple virus genomes, including CLCuK0V, TYLCSV and TYLCV. For cucumber mosaic virus and tobacco mosaic virus, a technology has been developed to modify the RNA virus genomes of sgRNA and FnCas9.

Therefore, molecular immunity against RNA viruses was mediated by sgRNA/FnCas9 expression in Arabidopsis and tobacco. CRISPR-Cas9 successfully targeted OsERF922 against resistance to the resistant fungus in rice. Ethylene-responsive plant factors (ERFs) can control tolerance to various stresses because they are involved in the ethylene (cytokinin) pathway.

Taken together, these reports provide strong evidence that CRISPR-Cas9 can improve resistance to biotic stress in plants. summarizes omics and CRISPR-Cas9 strategies for the production of stress-tolerant cultures.

6. CRISPR-CAS9 GENOME ENGINEERING TO ABIOTIC STRESS TOLERANCE

Abiotic stress tolerance mediated by different genes is a complex trait. Major interactions and interactions exist between components of the metabolic, regulatory and signaling pathways. CRISPR-Cas9-mediated genome editing can be used to alter almost any sequence (based on accessibility to the adant protospacer motif, the PAM site) to reveal its function in the genome.

Molecular breeders have discovered many T genes resistant to abiotic stress and have engineered them in crops. Mutants of the CRISPR-Cas9-generated mitogen-activated protein kinases3 (slmapk3) gene enhanced the defensive response to drought in tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*).CRISPR-Cas9 was used to generate mutants in rice to understand the mechanism of protein kinase2 activated by stress ABA. In *Arabidopsis* under cold stress, CRISPR-Cas9 was used to generate mutants (double and triple mutant cbfs) to determine the role of C-repeat binding factors. In maize, the CRISPR-Cas9 approach was used to increase the expression level of the ARGOS8 gene (negatively regulate the ethylene response) to develop drought tolerance; the promoter of ARGOS8 changed to GOS2.

These mutants had improved grain yield under drought conditions in the field. Furthermore, overexpression of TaCP and SPCP2 increased drought tolerance in *Arabidopsis*Plants overexpressing melatonin biosynthetic genes have been identified as tolerant to abiotic stress.In hybrid rice, targeted editing of the TMS5 gene led to the rapid formation of temperature-sensitive lines.

Plant breeding activities may have reduced T gene alleles after selection for yield-related genes during domestication programs. Breeders have developed stress-tolerant plants with information about gene function. The examples above demonstrate that CRISPR-Cas9 can modify/knock out genes to confer resistance to a variety of abiotic strains, e.g. B. salinity, drought, temperature extremes, heavy metals and nutrient deficiencies.

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NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON AGRICULTURE AND NATURAL RESOURCES

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Abstract: The method the COVID-19 pandemic discontinuous human lives and livelihoods ingrained a check for functioning agriculture production, agroecosystems in developing countries, as a neighborhood of rural and concrete systems and conjointly the worldwide economy. we have a tendency to applied 2 abstract schemes to dissect the proof in peer reviewed literature to date, as a basis for higher understanding and facultative building back higher. reportable positive impacts of the internment anthropause on environmental conditions were seemingly solely short term, whereas progress towards property development goals was additional systematically set back particularly for social aspects like living, employment, and income. The loss of connectedness, driving loss of assets, followed a collapse cascade that enclosed urban to rural migration due to loss of urban jobs, and smuggled exploitation of forests and life. Agricultural activities in gear to international trade were usually discontinuous, whereas additional native markets flourished. Improved understanding of these pathways is needed for activity between the rising adjustive, mitigative, transformative, and reimaginative responses. Dominant potency seeking ways that increase fragility can should be re-evaluated to be higher ready for more pandemics, that current Human : Nature interactions square measure seemingly to trigger.

Keywords: COVID-19; pandemic; agriculture; natural resources; resilience.

Introduction

Agroecosystems as a part of social–ecological systems, function the most bread and butter basis for millions whereas additionally being the autumn back resources at the time of shocks for the bulk. The scheme services generated from agroecosystems type the backbone of the bread and butter of the residents World Health Organization rely on it. Hence, the resilience of a society and therefore the scheme depends on however well the scheme is managed, that sadly isn't in a very sensible state in several developing nations wide suffering from the COVID-19 pandemic. One major determinant of the scheme services generation potential of a given agroecosystem is land use selections. Land use, as a part of resource management, may be represented because the interface of associate 'allocation' selection over four broad classes and a spatial patterning of 'grain' size of the mosaic. For instance, agroforestry as an idea is related to each a 'partial tree cover' class between open-field agriculture and closed cover forest [1], and with a comparatively fine-grained ('integrated', multifunctional) mosaic landscape [2–4]. scheme services will, during this context, be understood as direct edges to humans from (1) natural systems, (2) half-open land use systems, (3) open-field agriculture, and indirect edges (4–6) derived from landscape scale interactions between land cowl sorts [5], see Figure one. Management of such landscapes and social–ecological systems ought to conserve existing natural ecosystems and restore the degraded ones for the advantage of each humans and biological diversity. 'Restoration' during this context has to contemplate each the pattern and overall tree cowl [6]. within the context of zoonoses like the COVID-19 pandemic, each the amount of 'integration' vs. 'segregation' of the landscape mosaic (influencing initial human or stock infection risk), likewise because the overall cowl fractions square measure possible to be vital. As a key step within the methodology, we tend to thought-about variety of

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abstract framings of social–ecological systems subject to riotous changes. As there square measure each gaps and overlaps between alternative routes of framing, we tend to settled on 3 frameworks that enable a multiscaled analysis of proximate and underlying causes, social responses that square measure educated by however not similar with neutral understanding of the ecological/medical aspects and provide sufficiently generic views on system-level responses. For analyzing the depth of the possible impacts and consequences of the present pan- demic and therefore the choices for ne'er waste a crisis [7] in building higher futures, we tend to thought-about 2 frameworks utilized in recent literature. every has its specific strengths and weaknesses, and a mix, instead of single framing perceived to be enticing. because the COVID-19 crisis affects the balance between short, medium, and longer-term goals within the 'safe area for humanity', the temporary dynamics is a difficulty that started from initial denial and con- spiracy theories moving towards acceptance and searches for solutions. It additionally showcases the necessity for a balance between responses on a driver-pressure-system state-impacts responses time. In line with these arguments, we tend to specifically explored: The adaptational (r - K - Ω - α) cycle introduced by the Resilience Alliance [8] accounting for the 'collapse' section (Ω) wherever existing assets likewise as network property square measure lost, preceding a reorganization section (α), a ascension or pioneer section (r), and a gradual approach to carrying capability (K). This framework highlights the processes or phases within which amendment is occurring a given agroecosystem once disruption happen. Interacting Driver-Pressure-System(state) Impacts-Responses (DPSIR) cycles [9], with adaptational, mitigative, transformative, and reimaginative responses, advanced by issue attention cycle that encompasses agenda setting, higher understanding, commit- ment and coalitions for amendment, devolved details of implementation and analysis of effectiveness. DPSIR identifies however a given driver, that causes disruption to the approach agroecosystems operate, creates pressure and thence influences the system as a whol.

Effects of the COVID-19 Pandemic on Social–Ecological

Of the 327 documents reviewed, 43.73% of them clearly expressed COVID-19 had negative impacts on social–ecological systems, while 30.89% bestowed each positive and negative impacts. the most negative aspects rumored area unit on the lines of social aspects of social ecological components like financial gain, livelihood, employment, migration, etc. it's conjointly necessary to notice that positive effects of COVID-19 were rumored by a few quarter of the reviewed papers, for the most part on the reduced human impacts on the atmosphere thanks to travel and movement restrictions. Results from the assessments of the positives and negatives ratios (which were com-puted by assignment +1 for any document reportage positive impacts and one for any docu- ment reportage negative impacts) gave a clearer image of the impact of COVID-19. it's evident that, compared to the opposite attributes analyzed, the massive positive shares rumored area unit principally for atmosphere and life management. COVID-19 has afraid the planet infecting numerous individuals [10] and inflicting total disruptions in however the world is functioning and operational [11;12]. thanks to the illness, countries have closed land borders, ports, and even their airspaces apart from emergencies or provides of medical merchandise and instrumentality. At a time once the world is moving to a additional globalized theme, these measures, adopted to safeguard their population and conjointly to contain the virus unfold, created shocks to the broader economy, livelihoods, and social networks [13]. This resulted in vital social effects that created additional stress to the already prevailing challenges of global climate change, environmental degradation, and different living poignant causes. tho' COVID-19 effects were international, developing countries were the foremost affected thanks to disruptions of economic activities together with production and export trade [14]. Most of those countries accept agroecosystems that area unit sources of agricultural merchandise for export. The property of the agricultural sector and its agriculture industrialisation entirely depends on however the parts of the agroecosystems (i.e., land, water, multifariousness, etc.) area unit properly and sustainably managed. The pandemic exposed the loopholes within the extremely advocated export market by revealing the weak readiness countries have once such international problems poignant larger population arise. Pre-COVID-19, merchandise were exported at once to countries of destination for additional process, consumption, or utilization. Hence, producers

and exporters didn't want an intensive level of preparation in terms of storage places and raw materials provides from the producer communities were additional or less secure as so much as production inputs area unit equipped, and no major climate influence occurred. However, throughout and once COVID-19 (only for a few countries) those operational on perishable agricultural merchandise for international markets (such as tomato, flowers, vegetables, avocado, and different crop products) area unit tally losses because the uptake within the importation countries is discontinuous thanks to the imprisonment. Overall, Infobahn gains from agricul- tural merchandise trade Janus-faced Associate in Nursing uphill challenge that unbroken the world in limbo. The economic impacts trickle right down to the individual households WHO area unit the leading producers of the agricultural merchandise marketed and exported. The pandemic exposed the vulnerability of the internationalized trade infrastructure that was setup for many years during a bid to link the small-scale producers with the exporters and processors and also the global market usually situated within the developed nations. The other aspect of the coin has been a marked improvement of air quality particularly the out of doors one [15], reduced greenhouse emission emissions, Associate in Nursingd an 'anthropause' that provided opportunities for life to reclaim a part of the area condemned by humans [16]. Aspects of watercourse quality were conjointly recorded to be improved [17], however the single-use plastics created further waste issues [18]. The uncontrolled disposal of the facemasks and different COVID-19 kits were, however, expected to extend the amount of pollution.

Collapse section and Early Signs of Reorganization

For the immediate impacts of the pandemic and internment measures, the collapse (Ω) section of the 'panarchy' loops suggests that loss of assets attended the loss of property in cascading cause-effect chains. the main focus within the early section of the pandemic has been regarding dominant the unfold of the virus and saving lives of these affected, however cascading effects might have created the negative impacts larger than predicted. The trickling down result of the virus shortly had devastating impacts on broader natural resources management problems. That, in turn, can presumably shake the full economic base of most developing economies that have confidence natural resources and its product and services. The influences of the pandemic ar either direct (e.g., through job losses, financial gain decline, etc.) or indirect through the implications of the pandemic on economic activities, production systems, and provide chains [19]. aside from this pandemic, there was no recent record of nations closing their air, land, and seaports aside from military or political reasons. The COVID-19 pandemic created countries respond sharply to save lots of lives over livelihoods and targeted on health over wealth. This live, however, came with variety of negative consequences. The sectors that wont to support livelihoods suffered considerably. Economies shrank, jobs were lost, and folks were created to venture into unsustainable and dissatisfying activities e.g., exploiting natural ecosystems that ar the premise of their current and future generations. The response ways adopted varied by the dimensions at that the responses ar checked out. The national and subnational level responses targeted on minimizing movements of individuals in and between countries and conjointly proscribing or whole interference entry of foreign nationals into the country as a full. In Africa, as an example, as of Gregorian calendar month 2020, thirty eighth of the international destinations obligatory a complete or partial closure and forty fifth of the destinations proscribing direct flights [20]. This nearly halting the business and welcome sectors [21] leading to staff in these sectors being ordered off. The result thereforeme[for a few} countries is so severe thanks to the terribly high dependency on international business because the backbone of their economy. as an example, for a few countries, business accounts for over five hundredth of their total exports (Cabo Verde—67%; national capital and Principe—65%; Gambia—53%; Comoros—51%). Others like Seychelles (38%), Mauritius (34%), and Tanzania (29%) conjointly heavily depend upon these sectors [19]. UNWTO [22] conjointly indicated that international traveler arrivals for might 2020 shrank by ninety eight in Black Africa compared to might 2019. At the community level, responses varied by the kinds of community capability and bread and butter sources in the main. as an example, with the closure of manufactories, several casual employees became out of work and had to come to or had to send their immediate families to their rural folks and relatives. The rural-urban migration took

its opposite and urban–rural migration [23] became dominant, even if temporary. In any case upon arrival, such returnees got to cater for his or her families and therefore the tendency to interact within the assortment of untamed foods and looking to feed their families changing into common. Clearing forests for timber and charcoal production (in dryland areas) to get financial gain becomes a right away live at the forest margins, even aggravated by the neglect in low social control as generally mentioned in later elements of this paper. bread and butter within the developing world is powerfully obsessed with system services derived from agroecosystems. The long-run impacts of COVID-19 may most likely be way wider than anticipated tho' it might be troublesome to magisterially quantify at the instant. In distinction to several 'natural disasters' wherever the loss of assets is that the primary trigger of a collapse (Ω) section, the COVID-19 pandemic affected human livelihoods primarily through the 'lockdown' measures taken to manage the unfold of the virus Once the cascade took on its own dynamic, however, shifts occurred on each assets (y-axis) and connection (x-axis).

System Dynamics and also the ensuing Pressure on Agroecosystems

While the collapse section might have perceived to be a free fall, social safety-nets came into play and provided opportunities for early steps of bouncing back. Developing countries, specifically geographic region, intimate with a big rural-to-urban movement within the previous few decades resulting in swelling of the urban and community areas powerfully obsessed with the agricultural agroecosystems. The migration was mostly driven by the opportunities of employment either as casual or different kinds of employment. Hence, virtually the bulk of households have one or a lot of members of the family World Health Organization have enraptured to urban areas for gaining employment of any type. With the emergence of COVID-19, and measures taken to curb the unfold, several employers arranged off and/or reduced workers and laborers, resulting in job losses. The urban counterparts, since they lost their jobs and had no financial gain sources were inquiring for facilitate from relatives and relations in rural areas. Hunting for bushmeat and assortment of untamed foods (e.g., wild fruits, wild vegetables, honey, eggs, etc.) were seen as simple ways in which of complementing the rising food wants thanks to increasing variety of individuals in a very family thanks to the urban returnees. Reports of skyrocketing exploitation of forest and dry land resources was according in several cases [24]. those that had families in rural areas and accustomed add urban areas have to be compelled to currently generate financial gain to sustain their families. The pressure isn't solely from those arranged removed from urban areas however conjointly from the member of native communities serving within the service sector in rural contexts like tourismfactories, and infrastructure constructions.

COVID-19 and Its Potential Impacts on Sectors Directly coupled to Agroecosystems

COVID-19 conjointly affects variety of sectors that directly admit agroecosystems. These impacts, in turn, have an effect on rural households in several ways in which resulting in way reaching impacts. Overall, protected square measureas in developing countries are stressed thanks to the necessity for utilization by native communities. So far, the foremost effective mechanism to safeguard such resources is deploying an outsized variety of rangers and guards World Health Organization man the areas either by victimization technology or manual means that. With COVID-19, there square measure reports of a rising quantity of black access and use, particularly cookery and deforestation. several attributed the increase to the shrinking operational budgets of establishments that accustomed lookout of such resources. The National Geographic, in its latest report [25], unconcealed that cookery is turning into a serious threat to the protected areas thanks to the resource limitation thanks to COVID-19 leading to low returns, which means less rangers manning the parks and conservancies. fundamental principle News [26] conjointly echoed an equivalent issue pertaining to the case in African nation wherever consultants voiced issues over the rising cookery [27] and deforestation. As Bates et al. [28] hypothesized the decreased international. The loosening of restrictions square measure a serious concern for the African continent wherever there's a really high rate of bush meat searching and consumption, particularly at this point once there square measure restricted financial gain sources to shop for food

from the market thanks to individuals not having access to markets in addition as lack of jobs to earn cash. The Telegraph [29] discharged a bulletin, supported the views of consultants, warning a big surge in bush meat searching within the continent that poses a serious threat to wild animals. this could even increase the probabilities of another zoonosis irruption looking on the character of the animals afraid and consumed. Unless swift measures square measure taken, the declining variety of rangers and personnel accustomed defend such areas exposes the wild animals and also the woodlands to severe degradation. this could have a trickling down result decreasing the property of the landscapes and so the livability of the realm.

Disruptions of Interventions and Innovations for Agroecosystems Management

Three main pathways of impact are often known here activity holdup, activity discontinuance, and restricted opportunities for innovation. With countries declaring lock-downs in several elements of the world, movement of knowledgeable personnel World Health Organization may have enraptured from place to position to implement activities was severely affected. As a result, most of the agroecosystem management activities that would not be performed via remote connections are placed on hold for several months. This movement restriction has largely affected the analysis for the event side of natural resources' management interventions. This slows down innovations that would have tackled issues being visaged within the most affected sectors like agriculture, forestry, fishery, water resources management, wildlife, and mining. Most field operations were suspended or were occurring with bottom engagement on the bottom. This has delayed the planned implementation of the many interventions that would have contributed considerably to the productivity improvement, malady management, and/or web site management interventions in these sectors. Zellmer et al. [30] according cases of analysisers and scientists indicating research activities obtaining discontinued thanks to the pan-demic and thence poignant finding solutions to multifariousness challenges. Manenti et al. [31] conjointly according that the internment had helpful effects on multifariousness conservation, especially citing a decline in road killings of untamed animals in Europe. Paital [32] conjointly according increase sightings of animals thanks to the internment. For urban contexts, such positive aspects in regard to life advantages square measure substantially welcome news. However, in contexts wherever life is seen as supply of food for the community, and wherever low social control weakens thanks to inadequate force to require care of the task, the internment may even expose life to larger danger. In agriculture, forestry, and piscary sectors, most interventions area unit time sensitive i.e., season-dependent and if the schedule is lost, one has got to look forward to ensuing year to implement similar tasks. for example, occasional farmers got to begin making ready occasional fields within the month of Gregorian calendar month to March, months once most occasional manufacturing countries went into a imprisonment. an equivalent is true with malady management measures for occasional. For occasional cherries that may be collected ensuing occasional season, the on top of activities that ought to have happened throughout the imprisonment area unit crucial. If those activities don't surface, occasional production is probably going to be affected considerably ensuing season. The impact is essentially thanks to dependency of the activities on labor availableness, that isn't a haul once movement restrictions weren't in situ. However, throughout the imprisonment, no movement was going down as folks were involved regarding their own families and community's health. Due to movement restrictions, field inventories, surveys, knowledge assortment, and alternative relevant field activities [33] were stalled or interrupted fully to avoid risks to the personnel and community among that activities area unit to require place. Manenti et al. [31], victimisation responses from protected space managers, found that there was a challenge to implement activities to manage ecosystems thanks to the imprisonment resulting in flourishing of invasive species that area unit managed through human interventions throughout traditional times once access isn't restricted. At farmers level, the impacts area unit way reaching. for example, thanks to the nonessential travel and movement restrictions and therefore the lack of previous preparation, farmers couldn't access input provides like fertilizers, malady and pesterer management inputs, improved seeds, etc., that area unit crucial for farmers to secure or maintain agricultural productivity to earn financial gain and to satisfy the wants of immediate family.

Shrinking Returns and Revenues from Agroecosystem Dependent Sectors

With the disruptions in world trade and native movements, trade of forest and agricultural product has been affected. With agriculture being the backbone of the economy i.e., up to five hundredth of the GDP in a lot of countries [34] and most countries taking the export-led agricultural development schemes, the disruption crystal rectifier to vital losses in returns. The injury is thus severe for those engaged in spoilable product like vegetables, avocado, and alternative product like milk and milk product. The loss is additionally enlarged by the shortage of state for such AN unforeseen event that nobody expected might happen to disrupt the import: export schemes. One important sector that typically generates substantive revenue for natural resources management (NRM) sector in an exceedingly variety of nations is business enterprise. In several African countries, the world is powerfully addicted to the system i.e., flora, fauna, and therefore the landscape. for example, in {east africa|EastAfrica|geographical area unit|geographicarea|geographicalregion|geographic region} the most important traveller attractions are life and natural ecosystems. With the movement restrictions, folks stopped the cross-country movement of individuals, leading to tourists abandoning the region [35], although quickly. With the imprisonment, revenue from the world has shrunken considerably. it's necessary to notice that the business enterprise sector supports most of the life parks, sanctuaries, and even the personal parks in continent. for instance, UNWTO [35] indicated that as of Apr 2020, nearly 1/2 the world traveller destinations have closed their borders either entirely or part. In Africa, wherever international travellers compose the largest share of the tourist business, the impact on the revenue is incredibly high. for example, nearly two hundredth of the African countries rely on business enterprise with the world accounting for a minimum of two hundredth of their exports. The native economy is additionally for the most part affected owing to declines in international traveller arrivals. International tourists account for a minimum of four-hundredth of tourists in thirteen out of fifty four countries in continent [37] and therefore the impact this can wear the world and people operating within the sector is incredibly sturdy. With the shrank revenue thanks to COVID-19, most of the natural resources (wildlife, landscapes, and alternative natural habitats) that the world relied on received restricted management investments [24] thanks to resource scarceness. Unless there's a replacement support theme these resources could face vital degradation thanks to lack of effective management until the world recovers when COVID-19. it's unfortunate that the countries wherever such resources area unit set are facing monetary constraints forcing them to channel obtainable resources to priority and imperative interventions to manage COVID-19. for instance, Figure three shows a schematic of the interconnected impacts of the pandemic on life conservation. When such sectors suffer economically, the native communities World Health Organization rely on them conjointly suffer considerably. they'll then begin to appear for different bread and butter suggests that like wood harvest home, charcoal production and sale, misbr fishing and looking, and others, that successively exacerbates resource degradation and so threatening the property management of the world at massive.

Shrinking Social Capital for Agroecosystem and Agriculture Production Management

Natural resources management in continent is anchored to the social support systems that square measure engineered among the communities. The labor divisions determined square measure typical of however the social organization is designed to confirm that each unit member features a contribution whereas conjointly neighbors, whether or not relatives or not, lend hands to at least one another to confirm everybody achieves the goal of production, conservation, construction, etc. The role of such social systems is absolutely turning into important with most of the youth preferring to migrate to urban areas and different countries even. as an example, in Ethiopia, communal labor support teams ('Daboo' and 'Daadoo') [38] square measure generally discovered to help neighbors in agriculture, forest management, occasional farming, house construction, etc. The support cluster is common among Oromo communities especially, and such social structures were considerably laid low with the COVID-19 emergence as members got involved concerning their safety. during this regard, the impact of COVID-19 is essentially because of the restriction in social interactions that communities were suggested to

not follow till true of the pandemic is unbroken in restraint. Communities thus don't seem to be even obtaining along for social support despite the dire want for such native mechanisms that facilitate the provision of the scarce labor for agriculture and different natural resources management interventions. Communitylevel designing processes to handle natural resources management challenges are placed on hold. this might result in important degradation of natural resources, significantly areas that got to are managed within the close landscapes. Diversion of Resources removed from Agroecosystems to Pandemic Response During the pandemic amount, countries with restricted money resources square measure taking forceful measures by reallocating resources to tackle COVID-19 [39] and limiting resources that head to different sectors. Sectors enclosed in NRM like agriculture, forestry, fishery, tourism, energy, etc., square measure usually left with least investment from the govt resources and left to any support that would be obtained through bilateral/multilateral/private sector supports. However, Maher et al. [40] disclosed that even non-profit-making organizations square measure experiencing shortfalls in their money standing. In another study from the USA, author and Veuger [41] unconcealed that COVID-19 impacts government revenues as economic activities square measure stalled. an identical business enterprise challenge was rumored for Italia too . Despite being the essential pillar of the economies of the many developing nations, natural resources management efforts square measure usually given low priority in resource allocation and preparation of competent human resources and infrastructure for the case of agriculture for example). wherever there square measure emergency things, past experiences reveal that fund allocation for natural resources management like forests, wildlife, etc., square measure the primary casualties to be cut down. Agriculture cannot survive if the soil it's created on isn't preserved well each on-farm and off-farm. It cannot continue sustainably if water resources within the close areas dry up and water system for animals isn't secured. All this will solely be doable if resources square measure allotted for such interventions. The shifting priorities challenge isn't solely at the national level or government level. it's conjointly being mirrored briefly among international donors and lenders that accustomed support natural resources management it's legitimate that additional resources ought to be allotted to coping with COVID-19-related challenges, however if the shift isn't drained associate degree wise manner, the life support of humanity might be serious danger and it should not be that fast or straightforward to repair the matter. this needs serious thought of property context such the balance between these days and tomorrow will be created a rational decision- creating method. Broader Response choices at Socioecological Scale Though the solution to the question 'how can we build back higher and stronger' might not be that straightforward to answer because the information concerning the impacts of the pandemic is obtaining unconcealed with time, we've tried to place along our insights on however some potential interventions might facilitate the method higher. OECD states that building back higher ought to involve a major investment in making certain future shocks square measure managed properly. At the native level, this wants efforts to avert environmental degradation and deliberate investments in property practices in an exceedingly context-specific manner to confirm the method is comprehensive and progressive to the prevailing efforts. The COVID-19 pandemic exposed the vulnerability of the broader agroecosystems connected sectors and therefore the native resources to challenges that threaten the livelihood of the society that depends thereon each for consumption and financial gain. Addressing these vulnerabili- ties wants measures that descend from the national level to landscape (jurisdictional) and unit levels. It wants a conjunct effort across scales with decentralised roles and responsibilities for actors essential at the assorted levels.The COVID-19 pandemic will probably result in 2 opposite conclusions with reference to fascinating land use: (1) risks of zoonoses that infect humans and/or their placental mammal is also decreased by healthful segregation of something 'wild' and therefore the human spheres of life, however (2) human vulnerability to the internment was lower in 'integrated' landscapes wherever there area unit multiple resource choices and low fragility.we are able to currently relate these contradictory effects to different in progress pressures at the Forest– Agriculture interface. Among the seventeen property Development Goals, each changes towards additional urban and open-field agriculture and changes towards agroforestry and natural forest area unit fascinating ,with a trade-off determined by the terms of the 'Anthropocene equation'. From a robust tradition of high agrobiodiversity at each farm and landscape level, farmers in several components of the tropics have more and more 'outsourced' staple food production and relied on market-based

financial gain, with associate attraction to specialize on the product and market channels that job best for them, as well as 'traditional foods' appreciated in urban areas that were the seemingly begin of COVID-19. However, shocks area unit a part of the system farmers ought to be ready for and trot out. a part of the shocks farmers face originate in 'natural' disasters like volcanic eruptions, earthquakes, and tsunamis, though their aftermath is usually aggravated by changes within the tourism-related industries. Others originate in human behavior, like the money crisis of 2007–2009 or terrorism-related changes in business enterprise preferences. The COVID-19 crisis started with a deadly disease however was changed by associate new internment with restrictions on travel also as long-distance transport inside the country and an entire collapse of business enterprise. below the motto 'nature desires half' a vision ("A world during which folks respect nature's desires, and life on Earth flourishes"), has been developed to show 1/2 the planet into a series of interconnected protected areas expecting that this will conserve regarding eighty fifth of remaining multifariousness. consistent with international knowledge, presently around fifteen.4% of the earth's terrestrial areas and three.4% of its oceans has protected space standing however the 'paper park' while not effective protection has not been separated from these numbers. A planned 'global deal for nature' changed the proposal to half-hour protected areas +20% climate helpful areas. This argument has hereditary the 'land sparing' perspective that deepening agriculture will increase possibilities for nature conservation. However, it should be noticeable that the economic arguments that seem to support the 'half earth' perspective area unit for the most part supported the expected increase in 'tourism' to nature's 0.5, which will increase instead of decrease zoonotic disease risks. Counterarguments have challenged that this 0.5 earth arrange wouldn't meet its conservation objectives however would have widespread negative consequences for human populations within the areas of highest multifariousness worth. an alternate radical action might result in solutions that area unit each more practical and additional evenhanded, targeted directly on the most drivers of multifariousness loss by shifting the worldwide economy from its current foundation in growth whereas at the same time redressing difference. Solutions cannot ignore what happens in 'the different half'. within the in progress discussions for the post-2020 Agenda for the Convention of Biological Diversity, this has been changed to half-hour typical protected areas and two hundredth below autochthonal and customary rule protection. Meanwhile, the worldwide global climate change agenda depends on protective and restoring terrestrial carbon storage and emission reduction within the agricultural sectors which will imply a shift to additional forest and trees, also as finer-grained mosaics. Finally, the counteracting conclusions in animal disease pandemic interference of higher segregation and increase resilience ought to be reconciled with the opposite trends to become a part of a reimagined and transformative land use policy agenda.

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IMPLICATIONS OF HAARP SYSTEM ON CLIMATE CHANGE AND SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE

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ABSTRACT

Global climate changes are caused by the human factor, which is now so large that it exceeds the limits of natural variability. These changes are the result of emissions associated with the use of energy that are manifested as changes in extreme temperatures and precipitation, melting ice in the Arctic and Antarctic and sea level rise. High-frequency Active Auroral Research Program (HAARP) system can directly affect the programming environment and thereby directly negatively influence the climate on a planetary scale. Agriculture and climate change are inextricably linked. Crop yields, biodiversity, water use and soil quality are directly affected by climate change. Indirect climatic impacts include increased competition weeds, spread of pathogens, insects and other changes in the agroecosystem.

Key words: HAARP, climate change, agriculture, agroecosystem, emissions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change, which today speaks indicate negative consequences of the impact of humanity on the climate system factors. Climate change is the most endangered atmosphere because it changes the composition of uncontrolled combustion of fossil fuels. Extra high "greenhouse" led to an increase in global mean air temperature of 0.3-0.6 ° C in relation to the above pre-period. According to the IPCC Directive, the largest part of such a sudden rise in temperature is attributed to human activities. "Climate change" are defined by the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in section 1. As a climate change caused directly or indirectly by human activities which alter the composition of the global atmosphere. As a result of growth in atmospheric temperatures are expected and other changes in the geophysical properties of the planet, such as: changing patterns of rainfall, increase in the frequency of warm episodes of the El Niño, changes in the frequency and intensity of extreme events, sea level rise caused by the withdrawal of the glaciers, melting ice and thermal expansion sea water, in response to higher temperature with a serious endangerment of coastal areas and the islands, the increase in the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere and oceans are increased to cause a change in acidification of sea ecosystem. UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), which is more than a decade, most countries joined one of the first significant steps in the direction of clarifying the situation and setting up possible solutions. The Kyoto Protocol (stronger legally binding document) has been ratified by many countries as a complement to the UNFCCC. With this agreement, countries must achieve the set targets primarily through national measures. Kyoto protocol countries and

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offers additional ways to achieve these goals through market mechanisms that help stimulate “green investment” and help the parties to achieve emission reductions in a cost effective manner. The protocol envisages monitoring of emission of gases of the signatory countries, as well as keeping accurate records of progress. Climate change is not a problem with one solution, but can be seen as four inter-connect problems with human and natural origin: P1-general trend of global temperature is its gradual increase, which is likely to continue in the foreseeable future; P2-changes in atmospheric levels GHG have other effects not temperature, in some cases it is believed that these positive effects, or at least one of them, such as the acidity of the ocean, it is very important negative effects; P3- climate change will cause “roll-over point”, where some believe it will be particularly of the negative feedback or sudden climatic changes to the global warming; P4-will come to a brief episode of global cooling period that arises from large volcanic eruptions, and perhaps from other natural causes, and possible nuclear conflict (*Begich&Manning, 1995*).

2. HAARP SYSTEM

HAARP System (High Frequency Active Auroral Research Program) consists of numerous strings radio transmitter (180 antenna placed on a few hectares) enormous power and adequate instruments to detect. These powerful transmitters broadcast daily and continuously over 3000 KW generator volume using six 3.6 MW, a pulse energy that is emitted can be tens of thousands of times higher. The creator of HAARP is Ph.D. Bernard Eastlund (HAARP was patented in 1980.).In the articles referenced by Eastlund in his patent, was patent of Tesla's (*United States Patent 1,119,732*). This patent led to several others which were related (787,412 and 685,956, among others). Some of these new APTI patents were exactly what was suspected-a wireless power transmission system. Patent number 4,686,605, issued August 11, 1987 to Bernard J, Eastlund and assigned to APTI, is one of three related patents by the same inventor cited (the two other Eastland’s patents are: United States Patent Number 4,712,155; United States Patent Number 5,038,664). These patents revisit and go beyond the technical applications envisioned by Tesla. These patents were originally controlled by ARCO (Power Technologies Incorporated-APTI), which is a subsidiary of one of the largest oil companies in the world (Atlantic Richfield Company). APTI was the contractor that built the HAARP system (Alaska, northeast of Gakon). ARCO sold the branch, and the next phase construction contract to E-System beginning in June 1994. E-Systems was bought out by Raytheon, which works closely with the CIA and covert US intelligence services (*Begich&Manning, 1995*).The first HAARP system in Alaska was put into operation in 1996. and it was very successful. For the force of about 2 billion watts US Senate approves annually about 20 billion dollars for the development of this system. This system has multiple functions and its role is much more than studying the aurora borealis and radio communications to officials insist Research Geophysical Institute in Alaska and their financiers (US Government and Air and Navy forces, and others). The objectives set: 1) communicating with submarines at great ocean depths, with the ELF wave; 2) penetrating in the same way, in the ground itself, in order to search hidden underground tunnel or shelter of military interest; 3) protection of US territory from enemy aircraft and intercontinental ballistic missiles; 4) destroying enemy satellites; 5) identification of types of enemy missiles approaching US soil; 6) an absolute obstruction disabling the communication to a specific area; 7) changing the chemical structure of the upper layers of the atmosphere or climate programming to the desired area of the globe; 8) causing the earthquake and tsunami; 9) control of mental functions and reactions of millions of people in a particular region or globally; 10) the management of human health and biological processes on Earth. Bernard Eastlund’s patent was showned at figure I (figure 1, figure 2, figure 3, figure 4, figure 5):

U.S. Patent Aug. 11, 1987 Sheet 1 of 3 4,686,605

U.S. Patent Aug. 11, 1987 Sheet 2 of 3 4,686,605

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Figure 1. is a simplified schematical view of the earth (not to scale) with a magnetic field (force) line along which the present invention is carried out;

Figure 2. is one embodiment within the present invention in which a selected region of plasma is raised to a higher altitude;

Figure 3. is a simplified, idealized representation of a physical phenomenon involved in the present invention;

Figure 4. is a schematic view of another embodiment within the present invention;

Figure 5. is a schematic view of an apparatus embodiment within this invention.

Source: (United States Patent 4,686,605)

On planet Earth, is now known to exist and act five emitters of various forces and targeted operations directed radio waves of high frequency, and three of them are located on the Scandinavian Peninsula in Tromsø. Later, he turned and emitter in Greenland, which is three times more powerful than the one in Alaska. Broadcasters HAARP on a new technological level, but when they join, disrupt the balance in the Earth's mantle and leads to heating of the ionosphere. May arise artificial plasma formations kilometers wide and a giant fireball. During the experiment, the resulting effects of the formation of artificial plasma interacts with the Earth's magnetosphere, indicating the possibility of creating a system of integrated geophysical weapons. What will happen to the envelope of the Earth if we include the full force of all five broadcasters HAARP physics can not predict (Vukić, 2016).

3. THE IMPACT OF HAARP SYSTEM ON CLIMATE CHANGE

HAARP signal is detected in the upper layers of the atmosphere to a height of between 100-350 km, where it then is absorbed ionosphere which is the cause of gentle heating. Heating may be changing the conductivity of the ionosphere, and to influence its natural properties, which enables the changing of the natural form of the low frequency signals from the ionosphere. The heated part of ionosphere thus becomes a low-frequency giant ELF radiotransmitter, which in the form of vapor of controlled electron beam can be directed to the "target". The US Government has said that the main task of the HAARP system are communications with submarines, repairing the ozone layer, removing pollution caused CO₂ emissions. However, the background of this project is far more complex and dangerous in relation to what is presented to the public. Details regarding the HAARP system designated as a military secret (Top Secret), and the project should be implemented by the end of 2020. Many scientists believe that by using HAARP system can cause devastating earthquakes, activate dormant volcanoes, tsunamis create, cause extreme droughts and floods, etc. Examples are numerous and some of them are: Hurricane Katrina (USA), the earthquake in Haiti (2010.), the earthquake in Japan (2011.), floods in Serbia and the region (2014.). Japan is so close to Pacific Circle of Fire (the boundaries of tectonic plates of the Pacific Ocean), which happens over 80% of all earthquakes in the world, a natural occurrence of earthquakes is quite possible. However, there are indications that the earthquake in Japan caused by using HAARP system. Japan was exposed to a synchronized attack using HAARP system in 9th March 2011. to 11th March 2011. The first was caused by a strong earthquake of 7.2 magnitude on the Richter scale with its epicenter 413 km northeast of Tokyo 9th March 2011. (at 02:45h UTC, 11:45h local time) with hypocentre at a depth of 32 km. This first earthquake did not cause any damage. Then, 11th March 2011. (at 5:46h UTC, 14:46h local time) caused by another earthquake measuring 9 on the Richter scale with its epicenter 373 km northeast of Tokyo at the same depth as the first. Another earthquake caused a tsunami and damaged nuclear reactors in Fukushima I nuclear power plant, causing leakage of radioactive material and spread all of Japan and the Pacific Ocean. In the period of three days (9th, 10th and 11th March 2011) recorded strong activity at induction magnetometer located near the HAARP station in Alaska (Gakon). This instrument records the fine variation of the magnetic field causing the currents in the ionosphere. Before and after the earthquake, they were not such activities. It is believed that HAARP system must operate for several hours or several days before the intention of causing earthquakes and be directed at a specific location. Strange characteristics of both the occurrence of the earthquake is at a shallow depth of hypocentre (ie. a shallow earthquake). This intriguing fact an indication that these artificially induced earthquakes, the weaker earthquake 9th March 2011. is further enhanced by the fact HAARP system at 10th March 2011. What is "prepared the ground" for a major earthquake at 11th March 2011. when were killed or disappeared, tens of thousands of people, the Japanese government has suffered a damage of several hundred billion euros and the consequences for the environment and health conscious people are immeasurable. Given the amount of radioactivity and its expansion this is, after Chernobyl, the world's largest nuclear disaster. The earthquake in Haiti (2010.) had similar characteristics as the Japanese: small depth (13 km) and strong activity recorded at the magnetometer near HAARP station in Alaska. Heavy rains caused by the cyclone in the Balkan Peninsula fell almost without interruption between 13th and 16th May 2014 in Serbia and neighboring countries. Within 24 hours fell more than 100 liters per m² for a total of three days fell more than 200 liters per m². This large volume of rainfall has led to large-scale floods that have not been recorded ever

before in Serbia and the region. An error occurred torrents and river flooding from the river beds. On the territory of Serbia declared a state of emergency in 16 municipalities, and the hardest hit was Obrenovac. As a result of heavy rains and floods have triggered numerous landslides across Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia. Sunk by a large number of residential and commercial buildings, more than 30 000 peoples were evacuated, and the estimated damage is more than 1 billion euros. Starting landslide has led to the collapse of the infrastructure, roads, bridges, housing demolition (most at risk were managed properly, Kosjerić, upper Plana, Požega, Bursa, Kraljevo, Valjevo, Belgrade, etc.) the damage caused by running landslides is enormous. Due to the large amounts of silt trapped in the flooded areas there has been an emergence of massive sanitation problems, the development of mosquitoes, rodents and other pests. Contaminated water has been a source of infectious diseases such as dysentery and leptosproze, infected with the vast area of agricultural land, executed a large number of domestic animals and wildlife. Special teams have removed over 200 tons of dead animals from the affected areas. In Kolubara Basin coal, there was a breakthrough of the dam and Kolubara poured flooding completely the two basins (Large Crljeni and Tamnava-West field) bringing the total production of electricity halved. Given the above facts, the evidence and the damage caused by this catastrophic floods in the history of Serbia and the region we can conclude that their character is not a work of nature but caused artificially. Whether this was a "pilot project" in this region or not time will tell as many scientific studies (*Vukić, 2016*).

4. "ANGELS DON'T PLAY THIS HAARP"

"Angels Do not Play This HAARP" is a document that contains reports of scientists from different fields to talk about the progress in Tesla's technology. This progress is linked to the military plan to manipulate what belongs to the whole world- ionosphere. Some of these assumptions and statements are listed below. Independent researcher, Ph.D. Elizabeth Rauscher, who has behind her an impressive career from high-energy physics papers published in prestigious scientific journals and books give a statement related to HAARP: "You pumping tremendous energy into an extremely delicate molecular configuration that consists of two multi-layer, which is called ionosphere. The ionosphere is prone to catalytic reactions, if it is a small part of the changes happening to a major change in the ionosphere. " Ph.D. Rauscher has made and their personal experience of the ionosphere, calling it a bubble ("a soap- bubble") that surrounds the Earth's atmosphere and the processes occurring on the surface of the balloon. If you create a huge hole in the ionosphere, the ionosphere could burst. Physicist Ph.D. Daniel Winter, of Waynesville (North Carolina) said "high frequency emitted by a HAARP may associate with ELF waves causing disruptions in information that is manifested in the form of vibrations and thus transferred to the wildlife in the biosphere." He called this process geomagnetic "Earth's information bloodstream." Ph.D. Charels Yost of Dynamic Systems, Leicester (North Carolina) said, "If the ionosphere greatly disturbed, the atmosphere will be subsequently disturb". Ph.D. Rosalie Bertell, of Toronto, Canada, a researcher at the International Institute for Public Health said: "The Earth is delicately balanced and seeks to restore balance when it is disturbed" (*Begich&Manning, 1995*).

5. VANDALISM IN THE SKY AND ARROGANCE SCIENCES

The world has a new Agenda called Seven Agenda of Chemtrails and HAARP, which includes the following: 1) Weather and Environmental Modification, which includes: political blackmail and political pressure on various nations at least in NATO (North Atlantic Treaty Organization-responsible for defending its North Atlantic members). Environmental modification would be events like Hurricane Sandy in New Jersey, Hurricane Katrina in New Orleans where the ports and coastal areas are being restructured and remade, Earthquake and tscunami in Japane, Earthquake in Haiti, Floods in Serbia and region; 2) Electromagnetic Operations, which includes: HAARP, Nexrad/Doppler, SBX-Ionization of the upper atmosphere is drawing charged particles into the lower atmosphere. Our atmosphere including our jet stream is sucked up into it. Barium particles are spread for more conductivity. Moreover, Aluminum, barium and strontium are dispersed for increased conductivity. These particles are pulsed for various reasons and steered for various reasons. This is heating up the atmosphere and creating

extreme weather events; 3) Military Operations-which includes: our weather is used as a weapon; 4) Biological Operations, which includes: morcellons although not the only biological experiments going on, is being piggybacked on the polymeric nano fibres is being locked into the chemtrail components as well as nano technology and smart dust (minute micro-processors which can track and monitor us). If you have the frequency of a disease you don't need to broadcast the virus or the bacteria, you simply broadcast the frequency; 5) Planetary Geophysical Operations, which includes: altered plasma, which is what they are deriving from the ionosphere. They are making plasma to keep our atmosphere thickened, it is a medium, something that electrons can be moved around in. Altered plasma means dramatic earth changes via the troposphere and magnetosphere. The magnetosphere is weakened and we are being told it's only because of a certain solar cycle. It is very difficult to tell how much is actual real science that is coming from NASA and NOAA and what is being disseminated as disinformation; 6) Surveillance, which includes: everyone on earth is under surveillance for what the military calls C4; Command, Control, Communications and Computers; 7) Exotic Propulsion Systems, which includes: build an atmosphere in which they can detect exotic propulsion systems. Those exotic propulsion systems can be earth created, in other words, we brought the Nazi's over under Project Paper Clip, we brought over their plans for anti gravity exotic propulsion systems (*Freeland, 2014*).

6. CLIMATE CHANGE AND SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE

In the context of sustainable agriculture and rural development, climate change is becoming an issue, which devotes a major concern in many institutions, especially in the field of agriculture in developing countries. The phenomenon of climate change has a substantial impact on agricultural systems and the scientific community has identified as a major risk factor. Although this sector is responsible for 30% of global warming, including deforestation, biomass burning and land use changes. The phenomenon of climate change has major consequences for agriculture and the scientific community has identified as a high risk. According to FAO reports, the agriculture sector is responsible for about 30% of global warming (including deforestation, biomass burning and changes in land use)(*FAO, 2000*). In Table 1 are shown the most important contribution to agriculture routes, emissions of greenhouse gases (GHG).

Table 1. Contribution to the process in agriculture show major GHG (*Guidi & Best, 2003*)

Type of gas (GHG)	Estimated contribution	The most important way of influence
CO ₂	21-25% of global CO ₂	Fossil fuels used on farms; deforestation; change of tillage
CH ₄	55-60% of global CH ₄	Rice fields; changes in land use; burning biomass; fermentation in the intestines of domestic animal; animal waste
N ₂ O	55-60% of global N ₂ O	Most nitrogen fertilizers; animal waste

The dual role of agriculture, consumer and or energy supplier, increasingly becoming relevant in the context of prevention of global climate change. It can be used as a chance that this sector becomes instead a large consumer, a significant source of clean, renewable energy, particularly through biomass crop residues and cultivation of crops for energy. Carbon emissions reductions can be achieved by replacing the types of fuel (mainly fossil), which are used in agricultural production. Improved agricultural practices or new processing technology can achieve this goal, the efficient use of energy or using renewable energy sources.

7. SPECIFIED RISKS THAT AGRICULTURE WILL FACE IN THE FUTURE

In the future, agriculture will face with these specified risks: 1) Lack of water-the bulk of the impact of climate change on agriculture will come because of the water shortage. Climate change is the most likely result in a reduction of the annual amount of water available to agriculture. It is expected that the summer will be drier and hotter and reduced water resources which could lead to conflicting demands between agriculture and other users. Increased risk of water shortage will have significant consequences for agricultural production because many regions use different types of irrigation for hundreds of years - this is part of their agricultural traditions - but the sector will be forced to undertake an audit of irrigation techniques, which will take into account climate change. Several of the region may have to increase the surface area that is irrigated in order to ensure continuous production and in the future. However, there is no doubt that agriculture must take further steps to improve the efficiency of its use of water resources and the reduction of water losses, while plans for irrigation must be based on careful planning and thorough assessment of their impact; 2) Bad weather-the increased frequency of extreme weather events such as rain -intensive precipitation, heat waves and drought will be felt over the entire planet. Removal of floods, droughts and storms in recent years have demonstrated the vulnerability of the planet in terms of extreme conditions, and their frequency may be increased in the short and medium term (until 2020). In particular, it is expected increase the risk of drought in the southern parts and the possibility of flooding in the central and northern parts of the planet Earth; 3) Increased pest problems-adverse impacts can also be expected from an increase in the spatial distribution and intensity existing pests, diseases and weeds, due to higher temperatures and humidity. Its hard to assess the extent of the effects, but it is expected that they will be highly regionalized. Farmers will be faced with the challenge of solving the problem of increased pest or the emergence of new pests, within the limits imposed by science and regulations; 4) The impact on the size and geographical distribution yield of agricultural crops-anticipated climate change will have an impact on the level and volatility of the yield, livestock management, while the location of agro-climatic zones likely to move toward the north latitudes. These impacts may jeopardize the supply of domestic sources of food in some parts of the planet. They may also lead to increased price volatility and present greater risks mean for the income of farmers. Furthermore, the situation may be exacerbated by the additional effects of climate change, which will undergo a large food producers from countries; 5) However, there are still significant uncertainty in determining the trajectory of climate, as well as the expected consequences for agriculture, particularly the detailed spatial level. Existing variations between forecast generated by different climate models and socio-economic scenarios and their compatibility with different time scales, are an important factor in the impact of the budget; 6) Impact on consumers-the certainty of reducing food production in certain yield volatility, changes in seasonal patterns, can increase farmers costs, as a result of climate change, will have repercussions on consumers. These changes can come in the form have been moved to the location from which we obtain products and / or variations in commodities; 7) The effects of climate change on forests-forest regions will be widely covered by the changes in climatic conditions. There is a high probability that global warming will increase the risk of forest fires and pests. In the long run will affect the composition of forests and their capacity to produce trees, though, should take into account that the frequency of these impacts will be differently distributed geographically. Extreme weather events such as strong winds, storms and prolonged heat waves and droughts will also have a significant impact on forests. In the longer term, climate change may threaten the capacity of our forests to provide economic, social and environmental functions (*Bošković et al, 2016*).

8. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the operating modes HAARP system on climate change at the global level. On the one hand we have the fact of the natural environment with its characteristics are: gravitational field, electromagnetic fields, magnetic fields, microwaves, cosmic radiation, etc., And on the other hand, we have an artificial environment that man builds for two reasons: (1) to improve the conditions and quality of life people; (2) for military use and control of the entire planet and humanity. Unfortunately, as time

goes on science and technology are increasingly turning towards satisfying the needs of military and ruling elite (political, financial, economic). The aim of this study was to point out the negative and very damaging impact of climate change caused by anthropogenic factors on the planet, the whole biodiversity and every individual on this planet, and that the background of projects related to HAARP systems much deeper, more intriguing and dangerous than what it presented to the public.

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INFLUENCE OF THERMAL PROCESSING ON BIOACTIVE COMPONENTS IN FRESH TOMATO (*SOLANUM LYCOPERSICUM*) FRUIT AND JUICE MADE OF IT

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Abstract: The fresh tomato is known as good source of health beneficial bioactive compounds. Because it is difficult to keep it in fresh state and in order to prolong its shelf life it goes thermal processing. This paper was written with the aim to give ratio of total phenol content (TPC) and total flavonoids content (TFC) of fresh tomato from market bought in Niš, Serbia and thermal processed tomato as tomato juice. Results showed that fresh tomato is richer source of polyphenols and flavonoids by 1.4 and 6 fold and they are recommending it in everyday diet.

Key words: tomato, tomato juice, polyphenols, flavonoids, thermalprocessing

1. INTRODUCTION

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) and tomato juice bring multiple benefits to a human health through bioactive components of which they consist such as: flavonoids, polyphenols, carotenoids, potassium, vitamins A, C, D and E [1]. In addition, because tomato and tomato based products are low in fat and calories they present rich source of fibers and proteins [2]. The phenolic compounds are beneficial for health because of their confirmed: anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, antithrombotic, cardioprotective and antiallergenic effects. The phenols are considered as the major antioxidant components [3].

The flavonoids are a class of polyphenols with chemical structure containing three rings (C6-C3-C6). They can be found in fruits and vegetables. The flavonoids are known to be affected by different factors thermal processing and heating temperature and time. The impact of these factors on total phenols content (TPC) and total flavonoids content (TFC) is not a strict rule. The best indicator for showing increased interest on current topic are the number of publications per year that rapidly increased since 2011 and reached 100 [4]. Although dietary flavonoids are sensitive to thermal processing, some researchers found that thermal processing can promote biological activity [5].

The vegetables are of perishable nature and even at lower temperatures it is difficult to store them for a longer period of time. In order to prolong shelf life processing finds its application. Thermal processing is a widely used processing technique in household cooking as well as in food industry [6]. The thermal processing affects undesirable microorganisms responsible for food spoilage, as well as enzymes, and by that increases gastrointestinal digestion of processed food. However, quality of it is usually lower by heating, but it basically depends on the nature of food and therefore can not be generalized [4].

Modern consumers are interested in food composition. The need for healthy food is increasing and therefore it is of importance to inform consumers about chemical composition of food in their everyday diet. As the health beneficial bioactive compounds, total polyphenols and flavonoids contents analysis of tomato and tomato juice is of importance. Therefore, in this paper were analyzed TPC and TFC in tomato fruit from Serbian market in Niš and tomato juice made of it by traditional recipe.

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2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The full ripened tomato fruits bought in September of 2021 at the local market in Niš, Serbia, were washed with deionized water, then sliced and homogenized, while the seed was removed thereby. The tomato juice was prepared by traditional recipe: milled tomato was heated up to boiling point and stirred continuously for 5 minutes. After boiling juice was salted and put into the glass flask.

The TPC was determined by the Folin-Ciocalteu method described by Huang et al. [7]. In short, 0.4 ml of previously prepared and defatted sample was mixed with 0.5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 2 ml of 20% Na_2CO_3 solution in a volumetric flask of 10 ml. The flask filled with deionized water to the line was incubated for 2 h at 20 °C and absorbance was measured at 760 nm, relative to deionized water as a reference solution. Calculation of the TPC in the tested samples was done by the equation of the calibration line and expressed as a milligrams of gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per kilogram of the sample. The equation used is:

$$A = 0.10262c_x + 0.05719 \quad (r^2 = 0.999469) \quad (1)$$

where A is absorbance, c_x is analyte concentration and r^2 is the coefficient of determination.

The TFC was determined by method applied by de Souza et al. [8]. The reaction mixture was prepared by mixing 0.25 ml of the sample, 3 ml of deionized water and 0.3 ml of 5% NaNO_2 . After 5 min, 1.5 ml of AlCl_3 was added to this mixture and then, after next 5 min, 2 ml of 1 $\text{mol}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ NaOH and deionized water was added up to 10 ml. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 510 nm in relation to deionized water as a reference solution by UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Blank solution consisted of all substances without the real sample. A series of working solutions were prepared from the starting solution of (+)-catechin in order to construct a calibration curve. It was linear in the concentrations range from 5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ to 40 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$. On the basis of obtained equation for the calibration line (Eq. 2), the TFC was calculated and expressed as milligrams of catechin equivalents (CE) per kilogram of the sample.

$$A = 0.03612c_x + 0.0091 \quad (r^2 = 0.9993) \quad (2)$$

where A is absorbance, c_x is analyte concentration and r^2 is the coefficient of determination.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ratio between TPC and TFC in fresh tomato and tomato juice made of it are presented as histograms and shown in Figure 1. The TPC is expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents per kilogram fresh weight of the sample, and TFC is expressed as milligrams of catechin equivalents (CE) per kilogram fresh weight of the sample.

Figure 1. The ratio between TPC and TFC in fresh tomato and tomato juice made of it

The results obtained in this study stand in the context of determining the health promoting potential of tomato present in Serbian market and tomato juice made of it. They get on importance as it is known that antioxidant activity is correlated with the content of phenolic compounds [9], of which flavonoids are the most present [1]. As it can be seen from Figure 1. fresh tomatoes are richer source of both polyphenols and flavonoids. More precisely, they are 1.4 fold richer source of TPC and 6 folds of TFC.

The results for such a lower TPC and TFC of tomato juice can be related with thermal processing. The daily intake of flavonoids is related to reduce of the risk of diseases. But, their stability is low and their content is influenced by thermal processing techniques [4]. In this study is shown that both TPC and TFC are getting reduced by thermal processing. This is finding is completely in accordance with the one obtained by Odriozola-Serrano et al. who where determining TFC in tomato juice after pasteurization [10]. However, results obtained in this study for TFC are in rage for the results obtained by Hallmann et al. who determined TFC for organic tomato juice to be 28.1 mg·kg⁻¹[11].

4. CONCLUSION

Tomato and tomato juice are good source of health beneficial bioactive compounds. Thermal processing affects their content in term of decreasing probably because of their degradation on higher temperatures since flavonoids are sensitive. Fresh tomato from Serbian market is better source of health promoting compounds than juice made of it. Results obtained in this study are recommending tomato and tomato juice to be a part of everyday diet.

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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH IN CONDUCTING THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL TEACHING IN THE FIELD OF BIOLOGICAL AND BIOTECHNICAL SCIENCES

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Abstract: *In this paper, a methodical-didactic review of the importance of an integrative approach in the performance of theoretical and practical (field) teaching in the field of biological and biotechnical sciences in higher vocational education will be presented.*

Key words: *theoretical teaching, practical teaching, biological sciences, biotechnical sciences, education.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the course of teaching, as an educational process, a system of knowledge is adopted, which forms the basis of a scientific world view [1]. For the successful realization of the educational goals of the teaching process, in addition to systematic and planned work with pupils or students [1], [2], an integrative approach is extremely important in the performance of theoretical and practical (field) teaching in the field of biological and biotechnical sciences, especially in higher education.

In this paper, a methodical-didactic review of the importance of an integrative approach in the performance of theoretical and practical (field) teaching in the field of biological and biotechnical sciences in higher vocational education will be presented. Special emphasis will be placed on selected teaching units within the teaching of scientific fields, that is, the teaching subjects of botany, pharmacognosy and microbiology (environmental microbiology, food microbiology).

2. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH IN CONDUCTING THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL TEACHING IN THE FIELD OF BIOLOGICAL AND BIOTECHNICAL SCIENCES

Education, one of the basic didactic functions, represents the adoption of the knowledge system as the basis of a scientific view of the world, but also the connection with professional and practical work. In the teaching process, the teacher works in a planned and systematic way with a group of pupils or students with the aim of adopting the teaching contents, in order to maximally develop all their potentials [1], [2]. An integrative approach in conducting theoretical and practical (field) teaching is particularly important in the field of biological and biotechnical sciences in higher vocational education, namely in teaching botany, pharmacognosy and microbiology (environmental microbiology, food microbiology).

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Botany is a biological discipline that studies all aspects of plants life. Given that from the earliest times to the present, plants have been closely related to human, and that they have influenced the historical development of civilization, botanical research has enormous theoretical and practical importance. Plants are an integral part of the scientific picture of the world in which human lives, but they are also directly used in various areas of economic activity. For students of health sciences, in the field of botanical interests, the central place is occupied by medicine, that is, the system of activities that lead to the creation of medicine from different plant parts, that is, plant organs [3], [4]. In this regard, the main goal of teaching botany, as the science of plants, is to present students fundamental knowledge, which is the basis of the use of certain plant species as a source of active ingredients in the pharmaceutical industry. Also, the goal is to enable students to distinguish and recognize, i.e. determination of certain plant taxons (groups), especially those with practical use in pharmacy. This knowledge represents the basis for routine work, but also enables further improvement, as well as the discovery of new herbal products and methods of their isolation. Adequate understanding of herbal drugs enables future pharmacists to participate more actively in bringing the pharmaceutical industry closer to nature and natural active principles. Therefore, the results of botanical research are applied in pharmacy, i.e. its discipline pharmacognosy [4].

Pharmacognosy is a scientific discipline that studies medicinal raw materials originating from nature (drugs), as well as their medicinal ingredients. Today, in pharmacy, the most attention is paid to drugs of biological origin, mainly medicinal plants. Medicinal raw materials of animal and mineral origin are used less. Within the framework of pharmacognosy, students gain knowledge about the chemical structure of the most important groups of pharmacologically active compounds of natural origin, about plants as sources of medicinal and other useful raw materials, the production and cultivation of medicinal plants, the technology of obtaining drugs, their properties, composition, action and application. Also, knowledge and skills of identification and control of natural raw materials, knowledge of phytopreparations, and the possibilities of phytotherapy are acquired [5]. The goal of pharmacognosy is to train students so that the acquired material becomes an integral part of their professional knowledge, which will have practical application in their future work in healthcare, industry and the application of natural medicinal products.

In addition, with the basic knowledge of botany and pharmacognosy, which have exceptional theoretical and practical value, students increase general knowledge and interests, with the possibility of more successful communication with experts from other fields. Thus, this knowledge acquires a cultural value [4]. From the aspect of protecting human health, the study of microbiology at higher health and sanitary schools of vocational studies is extremely important, given that infectious diseases are still one of the leading causes of human mortality. Microbiology is a biological discipline that studies microorganisms, mostly invisible to the naked eye, as well as their effect on other living organisms. Medical microbiology includes general medical microbiology, clinical microbiology, immunology and sanitary microbiology and enables a good knowledge and effective control of microorganisms, as the cause of a large number of infectious diseases. However, the microbiological control of water, food, air, soil and all products of human activity, which come into contact with people, animals and the environment in general, is extremely important for the life of modern man, [6], [7], [8], which is the field of study of environmental microbiology [9]. Safe drinking-water is one of the main challenges of the 21st century. A large number of people on the planet do not have access to safe drinking water, with a significant percentage of the world's population dying from water-borne bacterial infections. According to World Health Organization (WHO) estimates, mortality from diseases caused by unsafe drinking water exceeds 5 million people per year. Diarrhea and other acute diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, caused by microbiologically contaminated drinking water, containing coliforms and potentially deadly pathogens, are a major public health problem, primarily in poor Asian and African countries [10], [11]. In addition to water, numerous infectious diseases caused by microorganisms can also be transmitted through food. That is why the study of food microbiology is extremely important, the goal of which is to acquire the necessary knowledge to assess the microbiological correctness of food, identify microorganisms, the cause of food spoilage, and evaluate the results of food analysis in the microbiological laboratory. Acquired knowledge and skills enable students to analyze food for microbiological correctness, as well as to recognize the most common

microbiological agents that can be transmitted through food or cause food spoilage [7], [12]. Along with the development of knowledge about biological properties, importance and possibilities, and the skills of applying living organisms in various areas of human activity, it is extremely important to actively participate in working with students in developing awareness of the importance of preserving biological resources, as well as the entire biodiversity of the planet. Biodiversity represents the diversity of all living beings and is one of the most significant characteristics of planet Earth. Without biodiversity, there is no cycle of life on the planet, no production of organic matter, no release of oxygen. From the aspect of the development of human society, biodiversity is a source of biological material, necessary for the further technological progress of mankind, and plants have the greatest economic importance. Plants include species on which the food of almost all mankind is based, and a large number of species are used in pharmaceutical medicine [3], [4], [13]. In addition to plants, a very important component of biodiversity, which is crucial for maintaining the continuity of life on Earth, are microorganisms. Also, microorganisms have a very significant application in biotechnology, as a scientific field in which living organisms are used to obtain appropriate products. One of the earliest ways of applying biotechnology methods is the use of living organisms in the fermentation process. The microbiological process of fermentation is used by human in the industrial production of important compounds, alcoholic beverages, dairy and bakery products, etc. With the development of biotechnology in the field of agriculture, forestry and food production, its application in medicine and pharmacy also began. One of the most significant discoveries in the history of biological sciences is the discovery of antibiotics, which became available for the treatment of bacterial infections in humans and animals. With the methods of biotechnology, various biologically active substances are intensively isolated from plants and microorganisms, which are used as medicinal agents in the therapy of a large number of diseases. The field of biotechnology, whose discoveries are most used in pollution prevention and environmental protection, is agriculture. Recent scientific discoveries in this area enable biological methods of regulating plant pests, pathogens and weeds in phytopharmacy, that is, the use of biopesticides instead of chemical pesticides, the use of microbial biofertilization biopreparations instead of mineral fertilizers, which leads to a reduction in environmental pollution [12], [14], [15].

In order to achieve the teaching goals of the mentioned teaching areas and teaching subjects, it is necessary to provide material and technical means for teaching, as well as to apply different teaching methods, and to respect all teaching principles.

The material and technical structure of the teaching process enables the acquisition of knowledge from the mentioned areas by applying certain teaching aids (compulsory textbook literature, handbooks, whiteboards, computers, digital herbariums - used by the teacher, textbook literature, handbooks - used by students). During practical classes, different laboratory equipment, materials and instruments are used, as well as biological materials - collections of organisms (herbal material, herbal drugs, plant extracts, collections of isolated microorganisms, etc.).

Figure 1. *Asarum europaeum*, *Aristolochiaceae* (natural herbarium material, author's collection)

In the course of theoretical teaching and processing of new material, the frontal form of work is applied. In the frontal form of work, the teacher simultaneously works with the entire group of pupils or students, that is, the teacher presents, interprets, explains and demonstrates the teaching material to the entire group at the same time. Students listen or follow the teacher's presentation or other type of work, and follow other students' answers to the questions [1]. Through conversation, presentation and illustration, the topic of the lesson is covered, relying on the students' prior knowledge and the use of teaching aids. Teaching methods according to sources of knowledge and teaching methods according to teaching teaching lessons are applied. Three teaching methods are most often applied according to the sources of knowledge: the conversation method, the oral presentation method and the illustrative-demonstration method [1], [2], [16]. The illustrative-demonstration method is applied by showing schemes and pictures from textbooks, manuals and digital aids (for example digital herbariums) of biological species.

Figure 2. *Achillea millefolium*, Asteraceae, digital herbarium of the Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade [17]

According to the teaching teaching lessons, the following methods are applied: method of generalization and method of abstraction, method of analysis and synthesis, method of comparison and analogy, method of deduction [1], [2], [16].

During teaching, all teaching principles are respected. The principle of scientificity, which implies teaching as a process in which scientific truths are mediated and "discovered", is realized throughout the course of the lesson. Presentation of the topic of the lesson is based on valid, scientifically verified facts [1], [2]. The principle of systematicity and connection is realized especially in the introductory and main part of the lesson, by connecting previously covered teaching topics with the topic of the current lesson. The principle of individualization, which is aimed at adapting teaching and learning to the individual specifics of students, is applied throughout the entire lesson. The principle of permanence of knowledge, which implies learning for life and not for grades [1], [2], as well as the principle of motivation, is achieved by encouraging students to permanently acquire knowledge about the biology of the studied groups of organisms due to their exceptional importance in various areas of human activity (application in food technology, medicine, pharmacy), but also role in nature. In order to fully realize the principle of the permanence of knowledge, an integrative approach to teaching is extremely important. It is desirable to connect theoretical teaching with practical aspects and organize practical and field teaching in the form of student visits to important scientific institutions, protected areas and biotechnology companies.

As part of practical (field) teaching in the field of botany, students visit the Botanical Garden "Jevremovac" (University of Belgrade, Faculty of Biology, Institute of Botany). The Botanical Garden "Jevremovac" is a scientific-research and cultural-educational institution of great importance. It was declared a natural monument and protected as a cultural asset. The open area of the Botanical Garden contains a plant fund of over 1,300 species grouped into geographical and ecological units. It is divided into 14 areas, within which there are units such as the Japanese garden, Systematic plots, rock gardens, pools with water lilies, etc. In the open area, there are elms, specimens of oak (over 140 years old), chestnuts, several types of pines, larch, spruce, yew, cypresses, thuja, specimens of ancient species of sequoia, Ginkgo biloba, as well as specimens of Pančić's spruce, an endemic species of the

Balkans. About 1000 different tropical, subtropical and Mediterranean plant species grow in the greenhouse, grouped geographically and ecologically (a collection of succulent plants, the world of deserts, sand, stone and sun) [18].

Figure 3. Visit of students to the Botanical Garden "Jevremovac" (author's collection)

As part of the field teaching of pharmacognosy, students visit the Institute for the Study of Medicinal Plants "Dr Josif Pančić". The institute carries out scientific research work in the field of pharmacy and agronomy in medicinal plants, and they study the pharmaceutical, agronomic, chemical and biological aspects of medicinal and aromatic plants. Research on the quality and resources of wild plants, chemical analysis of plants and their extracts using modern analytical methods is also carried out. Testing of biological activity is also carried out in order to confirm the effectiveness of plants used in traditional phytotherapy, but also in order to find potential new medicinal herbal raw materials [19].

Figure 4. Visit of students to the Institute for the Study of Medicinal Plants "Dr. Josif Pančić" (author's collection)

Chamomile, mint, lemon balm, flax and others are grown on the plots of the Institute, and a significant number of medicinal plants are provided from spontaneous flora. The products of the Institute, based on about 120 medicinal plant species, contain only raw materials of known origin. The production is organized according to the requirements of the quality standard ISO 9001:2015 and the HACCP system and provides all conditions for the production of safe, efficient and quality products [19]. When visiting the Institute, students can get to know the Institute's wide assortment, which includes the following groups of products: herbal teas (single-component teas, herbal tea blends and filter teas), herbal drops (tinctures and extracts), nutritional supplements, products based on honey and other bee products products, semi-solid pharmaceutical preparations for application on the skin, cosmetic products.

As part of field and practical lessons in the field of microbiology (environmental microbiology and food microbiology), students visit a biotechnology company, which, apart from basic research in the field of microbiology, molecular biology, plant physiology, biochemistry and agrochemistry, also deals with the production of microbial biofertilization preparations and biopesticides. Students visit modernly equipped laboratories for microbiology, PCR, plant physiology, agrochemistry, a greenhouse and open-air plots for growing experimental plants, as well as a factory for the production

of biopreparations. In the microbiology laboratory, students have the opportunity to learn standard microbiological methods of isolation and identification of microorganisms from natural environments, their cultivation, production and extraction of metabolites.

Figure 5. Visit of students to a biotechnology company (author's collection)

The PCR laboratory is equipped for the extraction of genomic DNA using modern methods of molecular biology, amplification of the 16S rRNA gene using PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction), confirmation of the presence of genes by horizontal electrophoresis and detection using a UV-transilluminator. In the laboratory for plant physiology, students learn about equipment for quantitative and qualitative determination of the content of plant hormones using biological tests, and in the laboratory for agrochemistry with modern equipment and soil analysis methods.

3. CONCLUSION

In order to successfully realize the educational goals of the teaching process, in addition to systematic and planned management of pupils or students, an integrative approach in the performance of theoretical and practical (field) teaching is extremely important. This approach is significant in the field of biological and biotechnical sciences, especially in higher education.

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ANALYSIS OF FARMERS' ATTITUDE WHEN WORKING WITH PLANT PROTECTION PRODUCTS IN THE BANAT DISTRICT

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Abstract: Nowadays, plant protection products (PPPs) are inevitable in agricultural production oriented towards meeting the needs of the expanding human population. On the other hand, as one of the most toxic substances synthesized by humans, they represent a potential danger to humans, flora and fauna, and the environment. What aggravates the situation is the fact that the harmful effects of pesticides are detected after a long time due to the cumulative effect. These are substances which decompose slowly, concentrate and show an exceptional acute and chronic toxic effect on all warm-blooded living beings. Therefore, it is inevitable to limit the use of pesticides, and where it is not possible to approach work with maximum respect for safety measures. Due to the inadequate use of these chemicals, everyone is at risk, but those who produce, transport and apply pesticides are at the highest risk. In addition to the prescribed methods of protection, which practically narrow down to the mandatory use of personal protective equipment, it is necessary to conduct education on safe handling of PSP in parallel. However, the implementation of protection measures is difficult and unevenly applied all over the world. The paper deals with the attitudes and opinions of 162 farmers from the territory of Banat regarding the knowledge of the dangers of PPP for people and the environment, as well as the way of using personal protective equipment while working with them. Only some of the most important answers or those with regularities that point to a certain qualitative conclusion are presented and discussed in the paper.

Key words: Plant Protection Products (PPP), Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), polling, closed surveys

1. INTRODUCTION

Chemical compounds of organic, inorganic and natural origin, which are used in agriculture, veterinary medicine, food industry and communal hygiene to control phytopathogenic organisms, harmful insects, rodents, birds, as well as to control weeds and regulate plant growth, are called pesticides [1]. While plant protection products (PPP) are used exclusively on plants in agriculture, forestry, horticulture, parks and gardens, and belong to pesticides, in everyday communication most people do not make a difference between the two terms. The dangers of working with them are reflected in the existence of as many as four ways in which they can enter the human body. These are: through the mouth (oral), inhalation through the lungs (breathing) and most often absorption through the skin or eyes (dermal), which can lead to acute or chronic poisoning of farmers [2].

As PPP are dangerous chemical substances, each of them has a safety data sheet that the user must study in detail before using PPP. Each safety data sheet consists of the following sixteen units - chapters: 1. Identification of the chemical and data on the person who puts the chemical into circulation, 2. Identification of hazards, 3. Composition/data on the ingredients, 4. First aid measures, 5. Extinguishing measures fire, 6. Accident prevention measures, 7. Handling and storage, 8. Exposure control/personal protection, 9. Physical and chemical properties, 10. Reactivity and stability, 11. Toxicological data, 12. Ecotoxicological data, 13. Disposal, 14. Transport data, 15. Regulatory data and 16. Other data [3]. One of the measures to eliminate, prevent and/or reduce risks in today's working conditions is the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), which is mandatory in all jobs where there is a permanent or temporary risk of mechanical, chemical, radiological and other health damage to workers. Personal protective equipment creates a barrier between danger/harm and workers and represents the last defense of workers that must function in the workplace in the absence of complete technical protection or the

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impossibility of replacing technological processes with less harmful ones [4], [5]. The use of PPE does not control the danger/harm at the scene of occurrence, but relies on changes in the behavior of employees.

2. ANALYSIS OF FARMERS' BEHAVIOR IN THE BANAT DISTRICT

2.1. Method of performance

In order to analyze the behavior of farmers when working with PPP, they were surveyed using a closed-type survey, which contained questions to express attitudes, habits and opinions about PPP. The total number of respondents was 162 in the Banat district, and the respondents were mainly producers who cultivate smaller areas or are recreational (hobby) farmers. The created survey, except for socio-demographic data (gender, age and level of education), contained questions related to attitudes about the danger of PPE, ways of getting PPE into the human body, ways of behavior with PPE (studying the label on the packaging, using PPE, dealing with empty packaging, methods of information,...) but also monitoring of Regulations and opinions on educations related to work with PPE. For each question, multiple answers were offered, where in some only one answer had to be circled, while in others the possibility was given to circle several answers. Respondents filled out the paper survey independently.

2.2. Results and discussion

In the course of the analysis of the results of surveys in the Banat district, a special analysis, which covered sub-districts (North Banat, Middle Banat and South Banat), was carried out in order to possibly notice the regional peculiarities of one of the sub-districts. Sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Sociodemographic characteristics of the sample

TOTAL NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS (162)			
District	North Banat district	Middle Banat district	South Banat district
Number of the respondent	66	43	53
The age of the respondent	40-49 - 27,9%	20-29 - 31,8%	50-59 - 35,8%
	50-59 - 23,3%	30-39 - 27,3%	30-39 - 24,5%
	60+ - 23,3%	40-49 - 22,7%	40-49 - 15,1%
Gender	Male - 67,4	Male -71,2	Male - 73,6
	Female - 32,6	Female - 28,8	Female - 26,4
Level of education (the largest number of respondents)	Primary - 18,6%	Primary - 6,1%	Primary - 15,1%
	Secondary - 65,1%	Secondary - 56,1%	Secondary - 52,8%
	Higher - 16,3%	Higher - 37,9%	Higher -32,1%

To the question "Do you think that SZB are harmful to human health", several answers were offered: strongly agree, partly agree, not sure, partly agree and strongly disagree. The obtained results by sub-district are given in Figure 1.

Having analyzed the responses from Figure 1, it is evident that in the North Banat sub-district, the largest number of respondents completely agree that PPP are harmful to human health, as many as 93%. However, in the Central Banat sub-district 1.5% of the residents do not agree that PPP are harmful to human health. This data are surprising, especially since the percentage of respondents with higher education is the highest in the Middle Banat sub-district (37.9%).

Figure 1 The results of respondents on whether PPP are harmful to human health: a) North Banat district, b) Middle Banat district and c) South Banat district

Considering the aforementioned information, we got interesting answers to the question "Can PPP get into the human body and how (multiple answers can be circled)" The answers offered are: through the skin, by inhalation, orally, through the eyes, I don't know and PPP cannot enter the human body. Afterwards, an analysis was conducted on the personal protective equipment they use while working with PPP. The results of the survey are given in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2 Results of answers to the question "Can SZB get into the human body and how (multiple choice answers)"

Answers offered	District			
	North Banat sub-district		Middle Banat sub-district	South Banat sub-district
	Number of respondent	Percentage		
Through the skin	29	67,4%	53 ili 80,3%	44 ili 83%
Inhalation	38	88,4%	55 ili 83,3%	49 ili 92,5%
Orally	15	34,9%	39 ili 59,1%	22 ili 41,5%
Through the eyes	12	27,9%	34 ili 51,5%	33 ili 62,3%
I don't know	0	0%	4 ili 6,1%	1 ili 1,9%
Pesticides cannot enter the human body	0	0%	1 ili 1,5%	0 ili 0%

Table 3 Results of answers to the question "What personal protective equipment do they use when working with PPP"

Answers offered	District		
	North Banat sub-district	Middle Banat sub-district	South Banat sub-district
Protective coveralls	13 ili 30,2%	33 ili 50%	26 ili 49,1%
Chemical resistant gloves	20 ili 46,5%	53 ili 80,3%	35 ili 66%
Googles/face shield	15 ili 34,9%	39 ili 59,1%	27 ili 50,9%
Rubber boots	5 ili 11,6%	34 ili 51,5%	26 ili 49,1%
Face mask/half-face maske	34 ili 79,1%	37 ili 56,1%	31 ili 58,5%
None of the above	2 ili 4,7%	3 ili 4,5%	2 ili 3,8%

The analysis of the results given in Table 2 indicates that all respondents are familiar with the fact that PPP can enter the human body (one respondent is an exception), but they are not familiar with all ways of entering the human body. The largest number of them indicated INHALATION - 83-93%, and when choosing personal protective equipment, they did not indicate that they use a mask/half mask (Table 3). Of particular concern is the fact that a certain number of respondents do not use any personal protective equipment when working with PPP. That percentage is not large, but it is still worrying and indicates the lack of knowledge or irresponsible behavior of individuals. Regardless of the cause, this kind of behavior would certainly be influenced by proper education. It is interesting to note that there is almost a complete matching of the percentage of respondents who know that PPP can enter the human body through the eyes and the percentage of those who use glasses/face shield as personal protective equipment. Although based on the data in Tables 2 and 3, it is clearly seen that the respondents are not familiar with all the ways in which PPP can enter the human body, nor with the correct and complete use of personal protective equipment.

Table 3 also shows that, according to these surveys, the inhabitants of the Northern Banat sub-district use protective equipment in a significantly smaller percentage (with the exception of masks/half-masks), while for Central and Southern Banat the values are invariable. This result can be explained by taking into account the level of education of the respondents. It has already been noted that the lowest percentage of respondents with a university degree is noticeable in the Northern Banat sub-district.

The analysis of the answers received to the question "Do you think that PPP are harmful to the environment" indicates that in all three districts the largest number of respondents completely agree that PPP are harmful to the environment. In addition, it can be observed that this percentage is the highest in the North Banat district and is 88.4%, while the percentage of respondents with a university degree is the lowest. This result indicates that formal education in itself does not provide enough information about PPP and their impact on the environment. Accordingly, it is interesting to analyze the respondents' behavior with packaging for PPP. The results shown in Figure 2 for the question "Do you rinse the packaging from PPP" were obtained, while the results for the question "How do you handle the packaging after using PPP" are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2 The results of respondents on whether they rinse packaging from PPP
 a) North Banat sub-district, b) Middle Banat sub-district and c) South Banat sub-district

Figure 3 Respondents' results on how to dispose of packaging after using PPP: a) North Banat district, b) Middle Banat district and c) South Banat district

According to the literature [5], [6] as long as the pesticide residues in the packaging are in a concentration above 0.1%, the packaging is categorized as hazardous waste that represents a potential risk to human health and the environment. That is why it is necessary to remove PPP residues from the packaging by proper rinsing and then to store and store them safely after use. Rinsing of PPP packaging can be carried out manually (triple rinsing of the packaging) or mechanically (pressure rinsing).

The results of the survey show a great difference in the behavior of respondents by region. For example, Respondents in the northern Banat sub-district treat packaging from PPP as if it were municipal waste in as much as 63%, and what is interesting to note is that they do not burn it, but even in a large percentage nobody knows what they do with it. In the other two regions of Banat, a significantly smaller percentage of respondents mix packaging from PPP with municipal waste, but also burn it independently.

It is particularly important to point out the results that indicate the monitoring of the Legal Regulation and who should do it. That is why the questions "Do you know that starting Dec, 1st 2023. you will be obliged to attend training and apply for a certificate in order to be able to purchase and use PPP" and "Who, in your opinion, should do training on the proper use of PPP". The survey results are given in Table 4.

Table 4 Results of answers to the question

"Do you know that starting Dec, 1st 2023. you will be obliged to attend training and apply for a certificate in order to be able to purchase and use PPP and "Who should do the training"

Answers offered	The Banat District		
	North Banat sub-district	Middle Banat sub-district	South Banat sub-district
Yes	53,5%	16,7%	49,1%
No	46,5%	83,3%	50,9%
Who, in your opinion, should do training on the proper use of PPP			
Advisors from agricultural expert services	61,9%	71,2%	64,2%
Pesticide manufacturers representatives	54,8%	42,4%	41,5%
Pharmacists	21,4%	12,1%	13,2%
Educators and scientists	4%	6,1%	5,7%

The Ministry of Agriculture published the Rulebook on the program, the method of conducting training and the method of checking knowledge for the purpose of issuing a professional user certificate and certificate form ("Official Gazette of RS", No. 104/2023), which refers to the implementation of training for those who use PPP in production. The basic training includes the knowledge about the safe application, handling, storage, transport and disposal of plant protection products and will last ten lessons. Additional training means updating knowledge and it will be carried out five years after receiving the professional user certificate. The lessons are envisaged to last 45 minutes. Knowledge check will be done in the form of a written test. Those who pass will receive certificates. The Ministry in charge will decide on the training mentors.

A large percentage (46-83%) of the received answers indicate that the respondents are not familiar with this legal requirement to acquire professional knowledge mentioned in the survey, which confirms the need to implement a serious approach to work with PPP initiated by the Ministry of Agriculture by adopting the Rulebook. The respondents' view on who should conduct the training are interesting, and perhaps it should be taken into account. The vast majority in all sub-districts are of the opinion that Advisors from agricultural expert services should do the training.

4. CONCLUSION

The paper analyzes the behavior of 162 Banat district farmers when working with pesticides. The data were obtained on the basis of an anonymous survey conducted during May and June 2023. The answers were arranged according to the territory, but the age, gender and educational level of the respondents were also taken into account. It can be concluded that the majority of respondents know that pesticides are harmful to health and that this knowledge does not correlate with educational levels. The assumption is that the harmfulness of pesticides has been highlighted through the media and in every form of communication for several decades, and that this information reaches a wide range of citizens. On the other hand, when it comes to specific mechanisms of protection when working with pesticides and environmental protection, there is still a significant number of uninformed persons who, for example, do not use PPE and do not handle packaging properly. The only solution lies continuous education and then certifying the persons who are fully informed and trained to work with these dangerous chemicals.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF POLYURETHANE HYDROGELS IN PLANT PRODUCTION

Ljiljana Tanasić¹, Jelena Tanasić²

Summary: The increased yield is a result of the application of agrochemicals and advanced technologies. Excessive use of agrochemicals leads to environmental pollution and endangers human health, so more and more attention is focused on the proper and controlled cultivation of crops in agriculture, which implies the controlled application of artificial fertilizers and preparations for plant protection. In this work, three types of polyurethane hydrogels were synthesized and the structure was examined by Fourier transform (FTIR) infrared spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), swelling rate, and plant culture growth with and without hydrogels on plant crop culture were monitored. Fertilizers are water-soluble systems that hydrogels can absorb and later release into the soil along with water. The results of monitoring the crop showed that the application of hydrogels with controlled release of fertilizers has an extremely favorable effect on the plant crop.

Keywords: Polyurethane hydrogels, controlled release, agrochemicals, swelling ratio

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer networks are three-dimensional structures created by establishing chemical (primary) or physical (secondary) connections between segments of linear chains. A special group of polymer networks is represented by hydrogels; they are elastic polymer networks that have the property of swelling in water, but do not dissolve in it [1]. The most important property of hydrogels is swelling, which depends on the nature of the polymer network, degree of crosslinking, polymer-solvent interaction, charge density and environmental conditions. Hydrogels that respond to external stimuli are particularly attractive due to a wide range of applications: tissue engineering, controlled delivery of drugs and proteins, sensors where bacteria are used as indicators, as biomedical patches for faster wound healing, carriers for controlled release of fertilizers in agriculture [2,3].

Polyurethane is most often used to obtain PU hydrogels, which will retain the stable properties of polyurethane, and will also have good swelling characteristics [4,5]. By varying the proportion of components in the polyurethane hydrogel, the structure of the hydrogel changes, and thus the basic property of hydrogels - swelling. It is precisely by changing the proportion of polyol and isocyanate components that the crosslinking density and elasticity of the polymer network is affected, which leads to a change in absorption capacity [6,7].

So far, polyurethane hydrogels have been synthesized, mainly for medical applications, as a substitute for soft tissues, due to their great similarity. Polyurethane hydrogels are ideal systems for agriculture, as they are non-toxic and at the same time do not require much manual work, as once introduced into the system, they simply re-swell and release water, without reducing the swelling capacity [8].

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There are no studies available in the literature for the use of polyurethane hydrogels in agriculture, with a high molecular weight polyol component. Polyurethane hydrogels can be synthesized by incorporating soft segments of polyethylene oxide into a polymer matrix, while a dual-functional isocyanate component and an extension chain are required [9].

This paper gives information about the preparation of three systems of polyurethane hydrogels, with three polyethylene oxide (PEO), with different molecular weights Mw 4000, Mw 6000, and Mw 10000, like polyol components and poly(4,4'-methylene bis (phenyl isocyanate) (PMDI). Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was used as solvent and dibutyltin dilaurate as a catalyst. Hydrogels were synthesized with a molar ratio of 3:1 (PEO: PMDI), due to better water absorption and retention. The synthesized samples were characterized by Infrared spectroscopy and differential scanning calorimetry, the swelling ratio was measured, and testing of water and mineral fertilizer retention and released into the soil with plant cultures.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PART

This paper gives information about the preparation of three systems of polyurethane hydrogels, with three different polyethylene oxide (PEO), - polyols components, and poly(4,4'-methylene bis (phenyl isocyanate) (PMDI), with catalyst dibutyltin dilaurate. Hydrogels were synthesized with a molar ratio of 3:1 (PEO: PMDI), for better water absorption and retention. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was used as solvent.

The synthesized samples were analyzed by the Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopy and differential scanning calorimetry. Too, the swelling ratio was measured, and testing of water with mineral fertilizer retention and released into the soil where are plant cultures. Table 1 shows the Marks of the prepared samples.

Table 1. Marks of the prepared samples

Sample	PEO x10 ⁻³ (mol)	PMDI x10 ⁻³ (mol)	THF x10 ⁻⁵ (mol)
PU-PEO4000	3	1	1
PU-PEO6000	3	1	1
PU-PEO10000	3	1	1

2.1. Methods

Swelling ratio: The swelling ratio of polyurethane hydrogels was examined to a constant mass of swollen hydrogel at a temperature of 25 ° C. Measurements were performed on an analytical balance, with a frequency: the first hour every 15 minutes, the second and third hours every 30 minutes, and then to a constant mass every hour. The swelling ratio is calculated:

$$R(\%) = \frac{m_{sg} - m_{ng}}{m_{ng}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

Where are they: m_{sg} -mass of swollen gel (g); m_{ng} -mass of nonswollen gel (g)

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR): The samples were tested on an ATR-FTIR device Nicolet 6700, in reflective mode. The test was performed in the range of 4000 cm⁻¹-400cm⁻¹.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis: Thermal properties of dried hydrogels were investigated using the differential scanning calorimeter (Q20 TA Instruments). DSC thermograms were recorded under a nitrogen atmosphere, in temperature regime from -90 to 200 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹, because of the conditions under which it would be used.

Testing of water and mineral fertilizer retention and release into the soil: The retention and release of water in the hydrogel during its use on soil with plant culture was investigated. All three types of hydrogels were tested. Systems with hydrogel and with the addition of hydrogel and mineral fertilizer were tested, where the mineral fertilizer is dissolved in water, then the hydrogel swells with the solution of fertilizer, and after drying in a vacuum dryer, the gel is returned to the xerogel state. It is used in the experiment as a xerogel 1% weight of hydrogel was added to the mass of the soil, the hydrogel was crushed to a size of 2 mm and then added to the soil with tomato. After adding hydrogels to the soil, the same amount of water was added to the samples each day, to each sample. The size of the stem was measured every week, for about 90 days, until the fruit appeared in each culture. The appearance of the stem, and leaves, as well as the time of flowering and fruit formation are also visually determined.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Swelling ratio

The change in molecular weight of the spot leads to different degrees of swelling. The addition of a higher molecular weight spot leads to an increase in hydrophilicity resulting in a higher degree of swelling (Figure 1). Synthesized hydrogels reach equilibrium swelling ratio for 5 hours. The highest swelling ratio is reached by PU-PEO10 with the highest molecular weight of PEO, which was expected considering that the properties of hydrogels also stimulate the PEO components, while hydrogels with PEO 4000 are more compact, low swelling ratio.

Figure 1. Swelling ratio of synthesized hydrogels

3.2. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

In the Figure 2, in addition to the peaks common to all three hydrogels, shown in Table 2, spectrum for all samples are the same. In all systems, there was a complete reaction of the components, which tells us the existence of the NCO group at 2320 cm^{-1} .

Figure 2. FTIR results of synthesized

Table 2. Bands of FTIR results

Peaks (cm^{-1})	3600-3000	2950-2850	2320	1723	1603	1543	1500	1425	1345
Groups	OH stretching	C-H stretching	NCO group	NH stretching	C=C stretching	NH bending	C-N-C stretching	CH ₂ bending	CH ₂ bending

3.3. DSC results

The melting temperature (T_m) increases slightly with the change in molecular weight of PEO, as the molecular weight of the PEO increases, the T_m increases. However, all samples have temperature stability at temperatures at which they can be used in agriculture.

Figure 3. DSC results of hydrogels

3.4. Testing of water and mineral fertilizer retention and release into the soil

Table 3 shows the results of the growth of plants (P) under the same conditions with the addition of hydrogel, without a hydrogel in the soil, and with the addition of hydrogel and mineral fertilizer. The table gives comments on the appearance of the plant during growth and fruit formation.

Table 3. Visual detection of plant quality

Visual detection	nothing	MF	PU-PEO4000	PU-PEO6000	PU-PEO10000	MF+PU-PEO4000	MF+PU-PEO6000	MF+PU-PEO10000
Leaves	Small, pale green	Good – dark green	Thin, green	Good, dark green	Small, pale green, bad	Good quality, dark green	Good, good, dark green	Big, pale green, bad
Stem	Thin, pale green	Thin, dark green	Thin, dark green	Thin, dark green	Thin, pale green, bad	Thick, dark green	Thick, dark green	Thick, dark green
Formation of flowers	56 days	45 days	45 days	46 days	48 days	43 days	37 days	45 days
Formation of fruit	92 days	87 days	88 days	88 days	88 days	83 days	72 days	88 days

As an assessment of the application of hydrogels on plant crops, an overall positive effect was observed, which would represent rapid growth, while maintaining the quality of leaves, trees, fruit, and flower appearance on time. This combination of MF (mineral fertilizer) + PU-PEO6000 showed the best results, which was expected, because this hydrogel system has optimal swelling, and thus the release of water and fertilizers. This combination, like other formulations, gave a strong root system, a strong stem, dark green leaves, very large fruits, uniform flowering, and formation of fruit.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Three types of polyurethane hydrogels with polyethylene oxide of different molecular weights were synthesized. It has been observed that the greatest difference between the samples occurs when determining of swelling ratio, because samples with PEO of higher molecular weights, 10000, give hydrogels of high swelling ratio. In terms of thermal properties, they are all stable at the application temperature, while their melting temperature (Tm) increases due to the increase in the molecular weight of PEO. No difference was observed in FTIR results depending on the PEO used. By applying hydrogels on plants, it can be concluded that hydrogel has a favorable effect on plant growth, but not all formulations, because when using PU-PEO10000 there is a decrease in leaf quality and later flowering and fruit formation, PEO with the addition of fertilizers proved to be the best. The addition of fertilizer with hydrogel shows that there is a controlled release of fertilizer, comparing it with a plant without hydrogel, but with fertilizer.

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POSSIBILITY OF USING RESIDUAL SLUDGES FOR THE PRODUCTION OF ENERGY PELLETS

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Abstract: Using residual sludges to produce energy pellets is a promising approach towards sustainable energy production. The process involves preparing the sludge, mixing it with other materials to form a suitable pellet mixture, and then producing and characterizing the pellets. This method not only utilizes waste but also contributes to environmental sustainability by reducing greenhouse gas emissions. However, the feasibility largely depends on the composition of the sludge and the specific requirements of the pellet mill. Further research is needed to optimize the process and maximize the efficiency of energy pellet production from residual sludges.

Key words: residual sludge, pellets, energy, gas emissions, environmental sustainability

1. INTRODUCTION

The idea of using residual sludges to produce energy pellets is gaining attention worldwide due to its potential benefits for both the environment and the economy. In the context of Romania, this concept is particularly relevant given the country's significant waste management challenges and its growing interest in renewable energy sources [1]. This process involves converting organic waste materials, such as agricultural waste, food waste, and other biodegradable waste, into bioenergy pellets. These pellets can then be burned in power plants to produce electricity, heat, or biofuels.

Residual sludges, often byproducts of wastewater treatment processes, contain valuable organic matter that can be converted into bioenergy. Energy pellets, in turn, offer a sustainable and efficient way to store and transport this energy. By recycling sludges into energy pellets, Romanian industries could reduce their reliance on fossil fuels, lower their carbon footprint, and contribute to a circular economy [2].

However, the implementation of this concept in Romania faces several challenges. These include the need for infrastructure and technological support, regulatory considerations, and public acceptance. Despite these obstacles, the potential benefits make it worthwhile to explore and develop this innovative solution for sustainable energy production [3].

2. PRODUCTION OF ENERGY PELLETS

2.1. The process of converting residual sludge into energy pellets

Residual sludge is a type of solid waste produced by wastewater treatment processes. It contains valuable nutrients and organic matter that can be utilized in the production of energy pellets. The process of converting residual sludge into energy pellets involves several steps:

- **Sludge Collection and Storage:** Residual sludge is collected from wastewater treatment facilities after it has been treated to remove pathogens and other contaminants. It is then stored until it is ready to be processed.
- **Sludge Preparation:** Before processing, the sludge is prepared by removing large pieces of debris and screening it to separate the solids from the liquids.

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- **Sludge Digestion:** The prepared sludge is then digested using microorganisms, such as bacteria and fungi, to break down the organic matter in the sludge. This produces a mixture of gases and liquid sludge.
- **Sludge Drying:** The digested sludge is dried to remove water and produce a solid product. This can take several days to weeks, depending on the moisture content of the sludge.
- **Sludge Pelletizing:** The dried sludge is then ground into a fine powder and formed into pellets. The pellets are typically around 8mm in diameter and have a moisture content of less than 10%.
- **Quality Control:** Finally, the quality of the pellets is checked to ensure they meet the standards set by international standards organizations. This includes checking the moisture content, ash content, calorific value, and other properties.

Once the pellets have been produced, they can be transported to a power plant where they are burned to produce heat or steam, which can be used to generate electricity. Alternatively, the pellets can be used as a fuel for boilers or incinerators to produce heat or electricity [4].

This process offers several advantages. It allows for the efficient use of residual sludge, reducing the amount of waste that needs to be disposed of. It also provides a source of renewable energy, contributing to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. However, it also requires careful management to ensure that the process does not result in environmental pollution or health hazards.

It's worth noting that the specific requirements to produce energy pellets can vary depending on the type of sludge being used and the intended use of the pellets. Therefore, it would be beneficial for Romania to conduct further research and pilot projects to determine the best practices for producing energy pellets from residual sludge in their region.

2.1.1. The methodology of empirical experimental research

The calorific value of residual sludge combined with biomass can be determined through a series of experiments involving combustion and measurement of the resulting heat output.

The steps followed for the empirical experimental research are:

- **Combine the Sludge and Biomass:** Start by combining the residual sludge and the biomass in the desired proportions. The exact ratio will depend on the specific characteristics of the sludge and biomass, a good solution is to mix 50:50 [4].
- **Prepare the Sample:** Once the sludge and biomass are combined, prepare a sample for testing. This usually involves drying the sample to reduce moisture content and ensuring it is free of any foreign substances that could affect the combustion process.
- **Combustion Test:** Next, perform a combustion test on the sample. This involves burning the sample in a controlled environment and measuring the amount of heat released. There are various methods to measure heat release, but the method used was a calorimeter. A calorimeter measures the temperature increase of a known volume of water over time, allowing you to calculate the heat released during combustion.
- **Calculate Calorific Value:** With the heat released measured, the calculation of the calorific value of the sample.

A calorimeter was used to determine the lower calorific value with XRY-1B explosive combustion and an Ohaus analytical balance with an accuracy of 0.0002 g. This equipment exists in the Research Center for Thermal Machines and Equipment, Transportation and Pollution Control, from the Department of Mechanical Machinery, Machines and Transport of the Faculty of Mechanics of UPT.

The calorimeter consists of a calorimeter bomb, a calorimeter vessel, a rheostat with switch to regulate the speed of the motor that manipulates the agitator, a sample pelletizing press, and an oxygen cylinder with a pressure reducer. Sample to be analyzed is inserted into the calorimetric bomb, where it is tied with a wire of nickel at its inner terminals [5].

Initially, the calorimeter bomb was calibrated, and the coefficient was obtained calorimetric k (in kJ/degree) of the calorimetric installation.

The preparation of the installation involves the introduction of water into the calorimeter tank up to its level, it exceeds by 1-2 mm the cover of the calorimetric bomb and achieves the thermal balance of the water with the surrounding environment.

Figure 1. XRY-1B calorimeter – operation detail

The preparation of the sample is done in two stages. In a first step, a quantity of 0.6-0.8 g of the material to be analyzed is dried in the oven, at $103 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, until the difference between two successive weighing of the sample is less than two-fold weighing accuracy. After drying, the anhydrous samples are kept in the desiccator until preparation of the pill that is inserted into the calorimeter bomb. The second stage involves making a pill from the sample to be analyzed. For this they have a weight of approx. 10 cm nickeline with the Ohaus balance, then granulate together with the sample and weight again. The mass of the fuel sample is thus obtained.

The free ends of the nickel wire wrap around the two rods of the cover for calorimetric bombs. The lid is then sealed. The cylinder is connected of oxygen and slowly introduce oxygen into the bomb to a pressure of 2.5-3 MPa.

The calorimeter bomb is then placed in the calorimeter vessel, along with 2.02 kg of water, at room temperature. Mount the stirrer so that it does not touch either the calorimeter dish or neither the bomb, then insert the precision thermometer.

To determine the higher calorific value, Q_s , the equation of heat exchange inside the calorimeter is written [5]:

$$m \cdot Q_s = k \cdot (t_f - t_i + \Delta t_r) - (Q_1 + Q_2 + Q_3) \quad (1.1)$$

where m is the fuel mass (in kg), k is the calorimetric factor (in $J/^\circ C$), t_f is the maximum temperature in the main period (in $^\circ C$), t_i is the last temperature in initial period (in $^\circ C$), Δt_r is the temperature correction due to the exchange of heat with the outside environment (in $^\circ C$), and Q_1 is the heat correction due to combustion of the nickel wire (in J), Q_2 and Q_3 are the heat corrections due to the formation of H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 (in J).

Considering the amount of water in the calorimeter vessel as $m_a = 2,02$ kg, the water equivalent of the calorimeter $m_e = 0,425$ kg and mass heat capacity of water $c_a = 4,1855$ kJ/kg K, the calorimetric factor will be [5]:

$$k = (m_a + m_e) \cdot c_a = 10,233 \text{ [kJ/K]} \quad (1.2)$$

The heat correction due to radiation heat exchange is given by the relationship [5]:

$$\Delta t_r = n \cdot v_f - \frac{v_i + v_f}{2} \text{ [}^\circ C\text{]} \quad (1.3)$$

where n is the number of minutes in the main period, v_i is the mean variation of temperature from the initial period, in $^\circ C/\text{min}$, and v_f is the average temperature variation in the final period, in $^\circ C/\text{min}$.

The heat correction due to the burning of the nickel wire is [5]:

$$Q_1 = (m_{si} - m_{sf}) \cdot q_s \text{ [J]} \quad (1.4)$$

where m_{si} is the initial wire mass (in kg), m_{sf} is the final wire mass (in kg), and $q_s = 275 \frac{\text{kJ}}{\text{kg}}$, is the heat of combustion of the nickel wire.

The relationship between the lower calorific power Q_i and the higher calorific power Q_s expressed in MJ/kg is [5]:

$$Q_i = Q_s - \lambda(9H + W) \quad (1.5)$$

where λ is the latent heat of vaporization of water (measured in $\frac{J}{\text{kg}}$), and $9H + W$ represents the amount of water resulting from the oxidation of hydrogen (H) plus the amount of water (W) contained in the fuel.

2.1.2. Determination of calorific value and residual ash for mixtures

For the determination of calorific value and residual ash, a first step is defining an experimental strategy. After the actual realization of the determinations experimentally, the collected data are analyzed and interpreted.

Table 1. Possible mixtures within the experiment

Recipe	A: Factor A	B: Factor B	C: Factor C	D: Factor D
	Sludge	Branches	Beech	Fir
Mixtures of 1 component				
R01	100,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%
R02	0,0%	100,0%	0,0%	0,0%
R03	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	0,0%
R04	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%

Mixtures of 2 components				
R05	50,0%	50,0%	0,0%	0,0%
R06	50,0%	0,0%	50,0%	0,0%
R07	50,0%	0,0%	0,0%	50,0%
Mixtures of 3 components				
R08	33,3%	33,3%	33,3%	0,0%
R09	33,3%	0,0%	33,3%	33,3%
R10	33,3%	33,3%	0,0%	33,3%
Mixtures of 4 components				
R11	25,0%	25,0%	25,0%	25,0%

Factor A. Sludge

Factor B. Branches

Factor C. Beech

Factor D. Fir

Figure 2. The factors of the experiment

Table 2 Experimental results

Recipe	Q- medium value	Standard deviation for Q	Ash-average value	Standard deviation for ash	Q	Ash
	[MJ/kg]	[MJ/kg]	[% masic]	[% masic]	[MJ/kg]	[% masic]
R01	12,386	0,389	4,003	0,128	12,386 ±0,386	4,003 ±0,128
R02	18,375	0,447	2,028	0,028	18,375±0,447	2,028±0,028
R03	18,766	0,837	2,170	0,075	18,766 ±0,837	2,170 ±0,075
R04	18,932	0,807	2,202	0,098	18,932±0,807	2,202±0,098
R05	14,435	0,894	2,323	0,053	14,435±0,894	2,323±0,053
R06	18,209	0,560	2,807	0,040	18,209±0,560	2,807±0,040
R07	18,793	0,987	3,078	0,079	18,793±0,987	3,078±0,079
R08	16,620	0,234	4,009	0,034	16,620±0,234	4,009±0,034
R09	16,358	0,675	2,987	0,057	16,358±0,675	2,987±0,057
R10	16,008	0,980	4,967	0,063	16,008±0,980	4,967±0,063
R11	15,665	0,845	2,947	0,069	15,665±0,845	2,947±0,069

3. CONCLUSION

The possibility of using residual sludges to produce energy pellets presents several potential benefits.

Firstly, it provides a sustainable solution for managing waste. Residual sludge, a byproduct of wastewater treatment processes, can be converted into bioenergy pellets, reducing the amount of waste that needs to be disposed of.

Secondly, it offers a renewable energy source. Energy pellets made from residual sludge can be used as a fuel in power plants, generating electricity or heat. This not only reduces reliance on fossil fuels but also contributes to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions [6]

However, there are also challenges associated with this process. The calorific value and ash content of the residual sludge must be carefully managed to ensure optimal performance of the pellets. Additionally, the process of converting sludge into pellets requires specialized equipment and expertise, which may increase costs.

In conclusion, while there are potential challenges, the use of residual sludges to produce energy pellets holds great promise for waste management and renewable energy generation. Further research and development are needed to optimize the process and make it more economically viable.

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EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF THE SUB-VALUE OF BIODIVERSITY ON ITS TOTAL VALUE

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Abstract: *The paper examines the examining impact of the sub-value of biodiversity on its total value. The research was conducted on a sample of 78 experts in the field of environmental protection. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire. The AMOS model was used for structural equation modelling. The result shows that all sub-values positively impact biodiversity, and the market value has the highest impact on total value.*

Keywords: *biodiversity, value, sub-values, Republic of Serbia*

1. INTRODUCTION

Biodiversity represents the diversity of all life forms on Earth, from the simplest and invisible to the human eye, at the molecular level, all the way to organisms, populations, species, and ecosystems.

Based on this understanding of biodiversity, the biodiversity of a region would represent the set of all genes, species and ecosystems of that region [1]. The diversity of those genes and their combinations in a particular region leads to morphological diversity between individuals and populations within a species between regions, but also taxonomic diversity of species within a community or ecosystem, which results in groups within a particular species being functionally different. The consequence of this diversity in the last instance is the ecosystems' diversity [2,3].

Since it includes the diversity of plants, animals and other forms of life, such as bacteria, viruses, protozoa, etc., the elements of biodiversity can be directly or indirectly used by humans for their well-being. Using natural raw materials and materials in producing food, fuel, fibres and other industrial products is considered a direct benefit of biodiversity to human well-being; for this reason, we can talk about the direct value of biodiversity [4,5]. As biodiversity includes the wild species that are the primary focus of conservation biology, through pollination by insects, water quality regulation, soil erosion control, protection from storms and climate regulation, biodiversity indirectly contributes to human well-being [6]. Thus, through the process of decomposition and production to preserve biology and biodiversity, ensuring the circular movement, the circulation of nutrients and the flow of energy, thus indirectly contributing to the well-being of people. Hence, one can speak of the indirect value of biodiversity.

Therefore, based on the above, it can quickly be concluded that when biodiversity represents an input that directly enters the work processes of people, it generates direct benefits and, therefore, has a direct value, i.e. when it represents an input in the functioning of the ecosystem, which from the perspective of people can be interpreted as ecosystem services (e.g. pollination). Biodiversity has an indirect benefit to humans and has an indirect value. In addition to these two values, other biodiversity values are often discussed in the literature.

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Namely, in the last couple of decades, numerous attempts have been made to systematize all biodiversity values and develop appropriate tools for their assessment [7,8,9]. However, a severe problem arises here. Since the direct benefits of biodiversity have their market value (price), the direct values of biodiversity can be precisely quantified. However, a bigger problem arises when it comes to indirect values. What further complicates the matter is that changes to biodiversity result in changes to economic values as moderated by the processes linking biodiversity as an input to a valuable economic output [2]. Therefore, studying biodiversity's value is a complex issue requiring a multidisciplinary approach.

The author's work is one of the relatively successful attempts to identify all biodiversity values [10]. Alho (2008) identified seven types of biodiversity values: Intrinsic (altruistic or non-humanistic) value - refers to the essence of the existence of nature as it is; Anthropocentric values - refer to economic value, that is, to the dependence of man on Biodiversity; Mitigation and compensation values - refer to mitigating the effects of human actions on the destruction of biodiversity; Aesthetic value - refers to the aesthetic value of biodiversity; Market value refers to the monetary value for biodiversity, but to provide alternatives to avoid loss; Political value - refers to the possibility of applying the concept of sustainable development; Scientific value - refers to the possibility of using biodiversity in scientific research.

Although this systematization of biodiversity values is widely accepted and often cited, more is needed to measure the impact of these partial biodiversity values on the total biodiversity value. In particular, there are no such attempts in the example of biodiversity in the Republic of Serbia. Therefore, this paper aims to examine the influence of individual sub-values of biodiversity on its total value.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Based on the analysis of theoretical concepts of the value of biodiversity, the study starts from the following research model, presented in Figure 1.

Sub-values of the total value of biodiversity

Figure 1- Research model

The model indicates that the total value of biodiversity depends on all its seven sub-values. We aim to determine which sub-value has the most significant impact on the total value. Furthermore, based on the presented model, it is possible to define the following three hypotheses, which enable the primary goal of the work to be realized:

- H1: All sub-values of biodiversity have a positive impact on the total value of biodiversity in the Republic of Serbia;
- H2: In the Republic of Serbia, the most significant importance is attached to the economic value of biodiversity.
- H3: Political value has the slightest influence on the total value of biodiversity in the Republic of Serbia.

The research was conducted on a sample of 78 experts in the field of environmental protection in the Republic of Serbia who have extensive work experience in this field. The data were collected using a structured questionnaire, which was constructed based on the analysis of professional literature. Since it is a new questionnaire, it was tested using principal component analysis [11]. The questionnaire is shown in Table 1. The study was conducted in 2023.

Table 1 - The questionnaire

Variables	Item	Factor loading							
		TV	IV	AV	AeI	MCV	MV	PV	SV
Total value (TV)	Biodiversity in the Republic of Serbia is diverse.	0.743							
	Biodiversity is beneficial for social well-being in the Republic of Serbia.	0.723							
	The Republic of Serbia is characterized by untouched nature.	0.763							
Intrinsic value (IV)	Life forms on Earth should be preserved simply because they exist.		0.717						
	The protection of biological integrity is a moral obligation.		0.702						
	Life forms are the product of a long history of continuous evolution by ecological processes and, therefore, have a right to continue to exist.		0.678						
Anthropocentric values (AI)	Humans depend on biodiversity.			0.718					
	Natural resources are essential in production in the Republic of Serbia.			0.705					
	Indirect benefits from biodiversity in the Republic of Serbia are significant.			0.711					
Aesthetic value (AeI)	I like to go to nature because I feel comfortable.				0.698				
	Natural landscapes are aesthetically pleasing.				0.685				
	After being in nature, I feel good.				0.673				
Mitigation and compensation values (MCV)	Human activities do not threaten biodiversity in the Republic of Serbia.					0.719			
	Measures are being applied to mitigate and compensate for the impact of human activities on biodiversity in the Republic of Serbia					0.642			
	A proactive approach to biodiversity protection is being adopted					0.698			
Market value (VM)	Preventive expenditures for the protection of biodiversity are sufficient.						0.713		
	Mitigating expenditures for the protection of biodiversity are efficient.						0.627		
	Expenditures for finding an alternative to reduce the impact on biodiversity caused by human activity, which results from the pursuit of economic development in the Republic of Serbia, are sufficient.						0.683		
Political value (PV)	The concept of sustainable development is applied in the Republic of Serbia.							0.717	
	Biodiversity is politically and strategically important.							0.703	
	There is a clear gap between pursuing social progress and preserving biodiversity.							0.782	
Scientific value	Biodiversity provides a sound basis for scientific research.								0.802
	Scientific research based on the study of biodiversity has excellent potential.								0.786
	I believe that investing more in research into biodiversity								is necessary 0.672

Respondents graded the items from the questionnaire using a five-point Likert scale with a grade of 1, completely disagree, to a grade of 5, completely agree. Sample adequacy is tested using the KMO test of sample adequacy (test value = 0.819). The findings from the validity test conducted on the questionnaire are presented in Table 1, emphasizing the utilization of oblique Promax rotation. The outcomes of the main components analysis reveal that the questions are organized according to anticipated patterns, thereby ensuring the questionnaire's reliability for future analysis. The data collected for this study were analyzed using the Gretl and the AMOS statistical software for structural equation modelling.

3. THE RESULTS OF THE STUDY

Prior to estimating the parameters of the AMOS model, a thorough analysis of correlations was conducted. A crucial requirement for appropriately implementing factor and structural analysis is that the variables exhibit a strong correlation. The correlation matrix in Table 2 showcases the interrelationships among the variables measured within the model. Additionally, it includes the average variance extracted, which gauges the reliability of sections with multiple items and Cronbach's alpha. Furthermore, the goodness-of-fit indices for the structural equation model, depicted in Figure 2, are also provided.

Table 2 – Correlation matrix, AVE, reliability and goodness of fit indices

	TV	IV	AV	AeI	MCV	MV	PV	SV
TV	1							
IV	0.467	1						
AV	0.49	0.481	1					
AeI	0.512	0.533	0.454	1				
MCV	0.429	0.452	0.462	0.601	1	0.505		
MV	0.444	0.538	0.549	0.554	0.482	1		
PV	0.483	0.663	0.441	0.401	0.332	0.431	1	
SV	0.501	0.496	0.437	0.437	0.348	0.403	0.523	1
AVE	0.691	0.642	0.603	0.611	0.639	0.658	0.672	0.664
Chronbach alfa	0.712	0.729	0.741	0.799	0.771	0.742	0.708	0.708
RMSEA (root mean square error of approximation)				0.042				
RMSR (root mean square residual)				0.055				
NNFI (non-normed fit index)				0.913				
AGFI (adjusted GFI)				0.902				

All correlations are significant at $p < 0.05$.

Source: Author

Table 2 reveals that the variables exhibit correlations. Each construct's Average Variance Extracted (AVE) surpasses the squared correlation coefficient for the corresponding interconstructs. This finding serves as evidence of the model's discriminant validity. Moreover, all Cronbach's alpha values are higher than 0.7, indicating a satisfactory level of reliability for each construct. Additionally, the construct reliability is further supported by all AVEs exceeding 0.50. The fit indices suggest that the proposed

AMOS structural model fits the data well. Detailed results of the confirmatory factor analysis can be found in Table 3.

Table 3 - Results of the confirmatory factor analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Stamd. Error	Critical value	p value
TV $\leftarrow$ IV	0.203	0.013	15.62	0.000
TV $\leftarrow$ AI	0.311	0.076	4.09	0.012
TV $\leftarrow$ AeiL	0.389	0.032	12.16	0.001
TV $\leftarrow$ MCV	0.417	0.086	4.85	0.008
TV $\leftarrow$ MV	0.021	0.009	2.33	0.049
TV $\leftarrow$ PV	0.184	0.053	3.47	0.019
TV $\leftarrow$ SV	0.003	0.001	3.00	0.027

Source: Author

The results in Table 3 show that all sub-values have a statistically significant and positive influence on the total value of biodiversity. This finding enables hypothesis H1 to be accepted as valid. This finding indicates that it is necessary to consider all aspects of biodiversity. The finding that the market value has the highest coefficient of influence testifies to support the initial expectation defined by hypothesis H2. Unfortunately, although this was expected, it is still worrisome because this finding implies that in the Republic of Serbia, biodiversity is most valued as a source of input for exploitation. Without raising awareness about the adverse effects of overexploitation of natural resources, this finding is worrisome because overexploitation leads to the destruction of biodiversity. This is especially true in the context of the findings that the impact of MCV is relatively small, which implies the insufficient allocation of funds for environmental protection. The finding that science value has the most negligible impact on total value implies that hypothesis H3 should be rejected as invalid. This finding indicates that it is necessary to increase society's awareness regarding the scientific value of biodiversity in the Republic of Serbia. On the other side, it shows that, to a certain extent, in the Republic of Serbia, implementing the concept of sustainable development is encouraged because the impact of PV is not the smallest.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper examines the impact of sub/values on the total value of biodiversity. The impact of 7 sub-values of biodiversity, accepted by scientific and professional circles as the values of individual aspects of biodiversity that directly or indirectly impact people's well-being, is examined more precisely. The research refers to the Republic of Serbia, and eminent experts from environmental protection were included.

The results indicate that all sub-values positively influence the total biodiversity value in the Republic of Serbia. They also show that market value has the largest single impact. This implies that the society in the Republic of Serbia values the economic benefits of biodiversity the most, which can lead to excessive exploitation if the society's awareness of the negative effects of excessive exploitation is not

increased. The results of the analysis also show that the scientific contribution is the weakest, which implies that society is still unaware of the quality of biodiversity in the Republic of Serbia. For this reason, further work should be done on society's education.

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Conclusions

The International Multidisciplinary Conference "Challenges of Contemporary Higher Education" (CCHE) 2024 has successfully convened a diverse group of scholars, researchers, educators, social community members, governmental representatives, employers from the economy sector, and students from around the world. The discussions and research presented have underscored the multifaceted challenges and opportunities that contemporary higher education faces.

Interdisciplinary Collaboration: The conference emphasized the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in addressing complex challenges. The range of topics, from Medical Sciences to Language for Specific Purposes, showcased that solutions in one field can often be informed and enriched by insights from another.

Global Participation: The hybrid format of the conference ensured that voices from around the world were heard, reinforcing the idea that higher education challenges are global in nature, and solutions must be sought in a collaborative, international context.

Innovation in Higher Education: Numerous papers presented innovative approaches to pedagogy, technology integration, and institutional collaboration. These innovations are pivotal for higher education institutions to remain relevant and effective in a rapidly changing world.

Stakeholder Engagement: A standout feature of the conference was the active participation and collaboration of various stakeholders. Members of social communities provided grassroots perspectives, governmental bodies offered policy-driven insights, employers from the economy sector highlighted practical needs and expectations, and students, the primary beneficiaries of higher education, voiced their aspirations and concerns. This holistic engagement ensures that the strategies and solutions discussed are comprehensive and grounded in real-world needs.

Future Directions: The conference underscored the importance of continuous dialogue and collaboration among all stakeholders. Institutions are encouraged to foster partnerships, both within and outside their disciplines, and with the broader community, to address the evolving challenges of higher education.

Commitment to Excellence: The quality of research and discussions, overseen by the Scientific Committee, showcased a collective commitment to excellence in higher education research and practice.

The CCHE 2024 has set a benchmark for future discussions on higher education. The insights gained and the collaborations formed during this conference, especially with diverse stakeholders, are expected to have a lasting impact on the higher education sector, driving positive change and innovation for years to come.

Warm regards,

Dr Branko Savić, professor

Бранко Савић

President of the Organizing Committee

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